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Editor's Note

The whirlwind of changes in the contemporary world invites our attention to bring about a synthesis of Advaita philosophy and religious teachings with scientific knowledge. These seemingly distinct terrains of knowledge should go hand in hand to bring about a shift in the current world order, which is characterized by chaos and uncertainty. The mass–energy relation of Albert Einstein proclaims this reality, affirming that all matter is the manifestation of one principle, namely energy alone.

The great sayings of Vedānta, i.e., ‘tat tvam asi’ (that thou art), ‘aham brahmāsmi’ (I am Brahman), etc., proclaim the non-dual reality, underscoring the idea that all this is Brahman and that, in reality, there is no duality in it. Gautama Buddha and Adi Shankaracharya, the great teachers, reiterated the concept of non-duality as the ultimate truth. This reality of Brahman and the Advaita doctrine, which aims at the welfare and liberation of humanity, can be accepted by modern science as well.

Dr. M. Manimohan

IKS in NEP 2020: Sanskrit as the Vehicle for Indian Ethos

Prof. K.K.Harshakumar ¹

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 represents a turning point in India's education scenario, seeking to reclaim the civilizational heritage that had made Bharat a centre of learning. Among its several forward-thinking reforms, perhaps one of the most culturally important is the highlighting of Indian Knowledge Systems (IKS) — an attempt to weave India's ancient wisdom into modern education. In the centre of this renaissance is Sanskrit, not just as a classical language but as the vehicle of Indian ethos — philosophical, scientific, and spiritual.

Indian Knowledge System

Indian Knowledge System (IKS) is a systematic and scientific process of conservation and knowledge transfer of India's rich intellectual, spiritual, and cultural heritage. Based on Vedas, Upaniṣads, Ayurveda, Yoga, Vedanta, and ancient sciences, IKS focuses on NJANA (knowledge), VINJANA (science), and Jeevan Darshan (philosophy of life). Identified in NEP 2020, IKS has a crucial role to play in solving modern-day problems such as health, sustainability, and stress management through holistic practices.

The IKS Division of the Ministry of Education facilitates interdisciplinary research, encourages Sanskrit and ancient wisdom, and inscribes ancient knowledge in contemporary education, through efforts such as specialist courses, IKS centres, faculty development,

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and Vision 2047, NEP 2020 seeks to generate cultural pride, heritage preservation, and an innovation stimulus by harmonizing traditional Indian knowledge with contemporary science and education (Khan and Sharma).

IKS in NEP 2020

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 is an historical landmark in the formal education integration of the Indian Knowledge System (IKS), promoting its scientific integration in all subjects. This integration reaches beyond core subjects to include tribal knowledge and ethnomedicinal practices, an indication of a comprehensive education system. In particular, IKS content is to be integrated into streams like the study of mathematics, engineering, philosophy, yoga, medicine, sports, literature, and languages, and this points to the interdisciplinary character of knowledge transfer

The focus of the policy on specialized courses like tribal ethnomedicine, forest management, and organic farming reflects a conscious attempt at retaining and developing indigenous knowledge in conjunction with contemporary scientific practices. Moreover, NEP suggests the introduction of IKS as an elective subject at the secondary school level to facilitate further investigation by students.

To ensure proper learning, NEP 2020 suggests utilizing contemporary technologies, interactive games, and cultural exchange between states. This strategy aims to render the passing of IKS interesting and accessible in order to enhance experiential learning. Moreover, the policy actively endorses multilingualism due to the linguistic wealth variety within IKS. It encourages teaching in the mother tongue of the children while making Sanskrit—the ancient classical language—a compulsory foundation subject, and thus re-connecting students with India’s linguistic and cultural heritage.

The multilingual education framework is consistent with the provisions of the constitution that are designed to promote national unity and integrity. The policy seeks to facilitate this by allowing students to learn multiple languages, so they can create a rich culture with cohesion. The literature proposes that this will facilitate

smoother integration of India's contributions to the country's history in different fields—for example, placing the history of Indian mathematics in regular mathematics courses, or integrating indigenous knowledge into architecture, philosophy, and Ayurveda courses.

Although NEP 2020 sets ambitious targets for integrating IKS, scholars observe that its implementation will involve incremental, phased action to bring about effectiveness and sustainability in the education sector(Chandel et al.).

Sanskrit: Beyond a Language

Sanskrit, widely acclaimed as one of the world's oldest written languages, going back about 3500 years, has a special place both culturally and linguistically. Its phonemic richness and grammatical intricateness make it a highly developed language system. The historical importance of Sanskrit is closely interwoven with its use as the language of original Hindu sacred texts like the *Vedas*, *Ramayana*, and *Mahabharata*, which makes it a highly privileged language in religious and cultural circles.

Sanskrit's social standing is, however, disputed. While it is revered in the religious sphere, it has also historically been tied to privileged castes in India, symbolizing sociolinguistic tensions over access and authority. This disputed status places Sanskrit in a special position relative to many world languages.

One particularly interesting fact about Sanskrit is the categorization by some scholars and practitioners as a “non-arbitrary” language. The conventional linguistic tradition highlights the arbitrariness of language signs, in which meaning and sound are conventionally related and not inherent. However, Sanskrit counters this position through language ideology that indicates its phonemes were “discovered” via profound states of meditation, linking sounds purposefully with the vibrational nature of their meanings. Unlike onomatopoeia or sound symbolism seen in other languages, this ideology asserts a metaphysical connection between phonetic form and semantic content, contributing to Sanskrit's characterization as a “spiritual language”.

This ideological schema carries over into Hindu spiritual practice, such that Sanskrit mantras and chants are said to hold intrinsic spiritual potency regardless of semantic comprehension. Practitioners assert that the vibrational nature of Sanskrit sounds enables healing, balance of the mind, and raising consciousness. Empirical support is still limited, but these beliefs highlight the strong impact of language ideology on cultural and religious views of Sanskrit.

Phonologically, the alphabet of Sanskrit consists of 48 primary sounds, a system that was at one point asserted by Orientalist Sir John Woodroffe to include all articulable spoken sounds, although this later came under dispute. Nonetheless, Sanskrit has etymological origins common to various Indo-European languages, such as Hindi, Latin, and Greek, illustrating its generative linguistic potential.

One classic instance that demonstrates Sanskrit's distinctive sound-meaning philosophy is the monosyllable "Om" (aum), which is held by many Hindu traditions to represent the whole universe—from creation to annihilation. The way Om is pronounced from the throat to the lips metaphorically reflects universal processes and demonstrates how phonetics and metaphysics meld in Sanskrit's construction(Zoë McCafferty).

Sanskrit as Vehicle for Reviving Indian Ethos

The incorporation of Sanskrit in the Indian education system has been a matter of interest for scholars and educators for many decades, particularly when there is an attempt at reviving Indian culture and philosophical spirit. The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 has brought this discussion to the fore by highlighting the integration of Indian Knowledge Systems (IKS) and encouraging the learning of Sanskrit as a key educational component in various levels of schooling. As per NEP 2020, Sanskrit is to be introduced as an elective course, imparted through interactive means like technology-driven instruction, cultural immersion, and incorporation in subjects like philosophy, mathematics, medicine, and literature(Ministry of Human Resource Development).

Scholars contend that Sanskrit is not just a language, but rather an inventory of India's spiritual, philosophical, and scientific knowledge. It is the language used by original Hindu scriptures such as the Vedas, Upaniṣads, Mahabharata, and Ramayana that contain the ethical and metaphysical laws which constitute the centre of Indian ethos. The pedagogic incorporation of Sanskrit thus fulfils not merely linguistic but also the dissemination of India's civilizational values like Dharma, Satya, and Ahimsa.

Sanskrit is frequently looked at not only as a language, but as a spiritual and vibrational means of communication, with mantras and chanting thought to affect consciousness and mental equilibrium. This makes Sanskrit special in its power to uplift not only learning, but consciousness and moral character.

NEP 2020 is encouraging multilingual education, where Sanskrit can be used alongside local languages, so everyone has access to it, and exclusivity based on caste, traditionally linked with the language, is diminished. It also suggests incorporating Sanskrit into subjects such as mathematics, Ayurveda, philosophy, and architecture, so education is more Indian in focus but remains relevant on the global stage.

Conclusion

Adding Indian Knowledge Systems and Sanskrit to NEP 2020 is more than a scholarly change, it is a cultural revival. It acknowledges that authentic education in India needs to be grounded in its own intellectual and spiritual ground, even as it extends itself to reach international standards. Sanskrit, being the language of Indian ethos, will be instrumental in creating conscious, ethical, and empowered citizens who are not merely job-seekers, but keepers of a timeless heritage. The future of Indian education, therefore, rests in the synchronization of modern innovation with old wisdom — with Sanskrit guiding the path ahead.

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A Study of Trilingual Drśyakāvya viz. Ānandavijaya

Dr. Somdatta Hati¹

In the development of Indian culture Mithilā has a long literary tradition. Writing in Sanskrit, in ancient India, was considered to be a qualification and a sign of greatness but common people did not understand Sanskrit. So the scholars of Mithilā began to use vernacular terms and songs in Sanskrit drama to make the language popular. In those dramas speeches were to be in Sanskrit and Prākṛt and songs in Maithili.

As a result from the medieval period (i.e. 13th to 19th century) Sanskrit dramas had made a new turn and were written in three languages. *Dhūrtasamāgama*, *Goraḥvijaya*, *Nalacarita*, *Ānandavijaya*, *Pārijātaḥaraṇa*, *Gourīsvyamvara*, *Prabhābatīharaṇa*, *Uṣāharaṇa* and such other about twenty variegated dramas came to exit. The dramas incorporating the three languages can be considered to be a totally new type of Sanskrit dramatic composition. Here it should be noted that pure Sanskrit dramas were composed by eminent and trained poets, but the dramas containing three languages came from the pen of less renowned poets having knowledge of Sanskrit. They were certainly the poets of the soil and they prepared the dramatic pieces for the enjoyment of local people. *Ānandavijaya* is one of the popular dramas. It is written by Rāmadās Upadhyay. It describes the story of the love of *Rādhā-Mādhava*.

From the Prologue² of the *Ānandavijaya nāṭikā* we can get some

1 Bejoy Narayan Mahavidyalaya, Hooghly

2 इदं हि कात्यायनगोत्रस्य कुञ्जौलीकुलनन्दनस्य- यस्मिन् गर्जति रोमदण्ड-कपटेनाऽयन्नरत्नाऽङ्क रान्
आतन्वन्ति वपुर्विदुर-खनयो विख्यातसंख्यावताम् । श्रीगोविन्द-घनेन तेन गुरुणा कारुण्य-पुण्याऽम्भसा

information of the life history of the author Rāmadāsa Upādhyāya. Rāmadāsa belonged to the katyāyana Brahmin family and was an inhabitant of kūjaulibāra in Mithilā. He was the younger brother of Govindadāsa, the famous successor of Vidyāpati. In 'The history of Maithilī literature' by Dr. Jaykānta Miśra and in the Gazetteer it is mentioned that Rāmadāsa was born in a village called Makharaunī in kūjauli.

In the prologue of the drama *Ānandavijyaya*, there is a song,³ sung by Nati in *Avahaṭṭa* language and there it is mentioned that Ramadāsa's great grand-father Mahāmahopādhyāya Sacikar Upādhyāya was the *Rājguru* of the Maithila king Maheśa Thākura. All the members of Ramadāsa's family were scholars and literary personalities of significant repute. Rāmadāsa's eldest brother Gangādāsa gained fame as a poet. He composed two anthologies of Sanskrit poem i.e. '*Gaṅgābhakti*' and '*Gaṅgāvilasa*'. His second elder brother Govindadāsa composed a book called '*kṛṣṇalīlā*'. Rāmadāsa's younger brother Haridāsa lived in Sarisavā village. One of his songs was mentioned in '*Rājatarāṅgiṇī*'. It is lucid and melodious poetry. Among the notable successors of Haridāsa, Dr. Chetkar Jhā, Dr. Uṣakar Jhā and Dr. Hetukar Jhā were famous. Rāmadāsa and Govindadāsa had no issue. Tikānāth was the great grandson of Gangādāsa. His daughter was the mother of Mahārāja Laxmiśvara.

In several *bhanitās*⁴ of the drama *Ānandavijyaya*, Rāmadāsa mentioned himself as '*Rāma*', '*Sarasa-Rāma*' and as '*Rasamaya Rāma*'. From this we can conclude that he was endowed with the title '*Sarasa*'. From the description of the marriage of '*Siva-Parvati*' of this *nāṭikā* we realize that he was really a '*Sarasa Kavi*'.

सिक्तस्याऽमरशाखिनो नवरसं रामस्य रम्यं फलम् ॥ - A.V. 1.6

- 3 तक्क-पंकअ अक्करूअ अणूअ सुइअर पण्डिओ । तीय सिक्ख महेम लक्ख-णरेस-आणइ मण्डिओ ॥
 जीअ जूत्ति वखाण सम्भहुपाण-बडिठअ दप्पआ । वीस मेइ समत्थप-पण्डिअ सहओ माणस-छप्पआ ॥
 तीय पुत्त कइत्त-कम्म-सुहा-समुद्द सहकगे । तीरहुत्ति समत्थ भूबइ वेरि पक्ख भअंकरो ॥
 तीअ सुअ पुरिसोत्तमो सो अहीर खानिअ लुट्ठिआ । सग्ग मत्त पआल हिअअं जीअ कित्ति तरगिओ ॥
 दुविअ पुत्त णराअणो णरणाह-लक्खण लक्खिओ । जीअ कम्म विपक्ख-णाअरि णेत्त नीर न सु क्खिओ ॥
 ती सोअर राम भूबइ दाण कण्ण णरेसरा । दुविअ सोअर स्याम पण्डिअ-कम्म धम्मिअ सेहरा ॥ -A.V. 1. 1.
 (Avahatta Song)
- 4 A.V. 1st Act, Song No. 4, 1.6., 1.7., 1.9.

In the registered 'Panji' of Mithilā, Rāmadāsa was mentioned as 'Mahāmahopādhyāya'. At the end of this *nāṭikā* we get hints of his witty and humorous nature.

Rāmadāsa himself copied the manuscript of the book 'Śrād-dha-cintāmaṇi' on palm leaves which are still preserved in Dār-bhāngā University. He had very good handwriting. There it is mentioned, being abided by his elder brother Govindadāsa, he copied this in 1624 A.D. Apart from *Ānandavijaya*, he wrote a religious book called 'Smṛtyāloka'. But this book is incomplete so far.

He mentioned himself⁵ as Rāmadāsa Jhā at the end of this *nāṭikā*. Probably they obtained the title 'Upādhyāya'. To determine the date of Rāmadāsa, we need to consult the history of the Khandawala dynasty.

The rulers of Khandawala were great appreciators of art and culture. They inspired the authors in writing poetry and music.

The first ruler Maheśa Thākura, was a famous scholar of Sanskrit and wrote many devotional songs in praise of Śiva, Gaṅgā and Tārā. He was a lover of poetry and literature. His son Śubhānkara Thākura was a lover of education. The youngest son of Subhankara Thakura was Sundara Thākura, who was also an expert in music and poetry.

Mahārāja Sundara Thākura patronized many scholars and poets. His assembly was full of Maithili writers and poets. The author Ramadasa Upādhyāya flourished during his time. He was the religious *Guru* of Sundara Thākura's mother and was older than Sundara Thākura. In the Gazetteer it is mentioned that Mahārāja Sundara Thākura ruled from 1628-1662 A.D. He died in 1662 A.D.

In the *Ānandavijaya* there are twenty-four songs in Maithili language. In the bhanita of every song Sundara Thākura is praised. He had two wives named kāmavati and Prāṇavati. These names were also mentioned at least eight times in the *bhanitā*.

From this discussion it is clear that Rāmadāsa Upādhyāya lived

5 इति सकल-प्रौढताके प्राप्तकयनिहार म. म. श्रीरामदास झाक बनाओल आनन्दविजय नामक नाटिका समाप्त भेल ॥(A.V, P. 78)

during the period of Mahārāja Sundara Thākura (1628-1662 A.D.).

Ānandavijaya of Rāmadāsa Upadhyāya has four acts. It describes the story of the love of Rādhā-Mādhava. The author has begun his drama with a *nāndī* comprising three *śloka*s, invoking blessing from the Brahma in the avatara of Kṛṣṇa and then Śiva and Kārtikeya. In the prologue, Mādhava, the hero of the drama, is introduced on the stage by *sūtradhāra* which is the characteristic of *prayogātīśaya* variety of *prastāvanā*.

The first act, named '*Sotkaṇṭha-Mādhava*' takes place on the bank of the river Yamuna in Vṛndāvana. Hearing the description of Rādhā, Mādhava is eager to meet her. Throughout this act we see Mādhava in a very inquietude mood and Ānandakanda, one of the most important characters of the drama trying to appease and cheer him up. Here we see that Mādhava is in love with Rādhā and Ānandakanda makes a pass for their meeting under the *keli-kadamva* tree on the bank of Yamunā. This act represents two mellifluous Maithilī songs, describing Mādhava and the loveliness of Rādhā which helps the spontaneity of the flow of the drama and also relieves the monotony of the audience. It also helps the drama to avoid the use of long description or stage-direction. The *bhanitā* of the songs conveys the names of the author and his patron. Act II named '*Sotkaṇṭha-Rādhā*' represents a series of scenes. It contains two episodes of astrologer Guṇanidhāna and of tiger. Both of them contain the seeds of the further development of the plot. Towards the close of the act, when the love relationship between Rādhā and Mādhava is germinating, the presence of Halāyudha changes a variation in the motion of the drama. This act represents melodious Maithilī music along with *avahaṭṭa* music which is really praiseworthy for their lyrical charms. Act III, entitled '*Rādhā-Viraha*' marks the climax by bringing before us two important personalities, *Ardhanārīśvara Śiva* and the sage *Kāpālīka* who evidently aim at making way of union of Rādhā-Kṛṣṇa. Throughout the act we see Rādhā in a lovelorn condition and lamenting for her beloved. In this act the Maithilī songs of separation are pathetic and remind us of Vidyāpati. Act IV, called '*Rādhā-samagama*' represents Kṛṣṇa's intent desire of Radha to be in union and in the end their happy union also. In the end Kṛṣṇa recites

the *bharata-vākya* expressing his desire for happiness for all.

The plot of *Ānandavijaya* is the courtship of Rādhā and Mādhava. The main story of the drama has been extracted from the *Vaiṣṇavapurāṇas* viz. *Harivaṃśa*, *Viṣṇu*, *Bhāgavata* and *Brahma-vaivartapurāṇa* but rest of the story is the brain child of the dramatist. The allegorical love of Rādhā-Kṛṣṇa in the *purāṇa* has been transformed into a helpless love, subject to social constraints. The *paurāṇic* God Kṛṣṇa has turned into mundane lover Mādhava. The supernatural story of Rādhā- Kṛṣṇa becomes realistic in this drama and thus the author has refashioned the *purāṇanic* story and shows his skill in the invention of the plot.

Almost all the characters of the *naṭikā Ānandavijaya* have been taken from the *purāṇa*, their activities are completely mundane. Naturally the drama has become very much credible. Mādhava, a calm and composed man, is full of love for Rādhā. He is an ideal lover. He belongs to the milk-man community. He knows that the society will not approve of their relationship. The princess Rādhā, though the wife of somebody else, is love-sick for Mādhava. She is very innocent and of good faith. She religiously executes the astrologer's advice. Ānandakanda, the jester is eloquent, quarrelsome and humorous. He is the catalyst of love between Rādhā and Mādhava. Without Ānandakanda the drama is pale. The playwright has depicted the other characters with mastery.

The *Ānandavijaya* of Rāmadāsa Upādhyāya has almost followed the guidelines of the *Nāṭyaśāstra* of Bharata. In Sanskrit literature, in point of popularity, the *nāṭikā* stands next to the *nāṭakā*, but the practicing of composing *naṭikā* continued down gradually. In the seventeenth century Rāmadāsa, by his dramatic genius, tried to generate this form and established its lost life-force. Now before discussing whether the *Ānandavijaya* is a *naṭikā* or not, we shall have to see what is *naṭikā*.

According to the rules laid down by Bharata, the *naṭikā* contains the features of the *naṭakā* and *prakaraṇa*.⁶

6 प्रकरणनाटकभेदादुत्पाद्यं वस्तुनायकं नृपतिम्। -N.S., XVIII. 58.

Abhinabagupta in this respect, clearly analyses the comment of his preceptor: ‘*prakaraṇabhedāt prakaraṇa-lakṣaṇam syāt nṛpati-nāyakḥ sthite yatra iti abhiprāye naṭikā – abhūt iti*’ (Nagar, 321). So it is seen that Bharata takes this form as a mixed type and as a separate *rūpaka*, it has not been recognized by Bharata. The *Daśarūpaka* says that the hero of the *nāṭikā* is as of the *nāṭaka* and the plot as of the *Prakaraṇa*.⁷ So it seems that though the *nāṭikā* is described here as a *rūpaka*, it is recognized as a mixed form like the former preceptors. The Rasārṇavasudhākara directly says: ‘*nāṭikā tu anyaḥ bhedo na pṛthaga rūpakam bhavet*’.⁸ On the basis of all these discussions, it may be assumed that all the authorities of Sanskrit dramaturgy takes the *naṭikā* as a mixed type. They take the *naṭikā* as the variation on the original *rūpaka* varieties. So they never feel the necessity to put it in the class of *rūpaka*. Some therefore, have thrown it in the class of *uparūpaka* and someone being silent put it in a separate passage. Now an attempt has to be made to trace the root of the implication that the *nāṭikā* is a mixed form.

The *Nāṭyaśāstra*, *Nāṭakalakṣaṇaratnakośa*, *Daśarūpaka*, *Bhāvaprakāśa*, *Nāṭyadarpaṇa*, *Sāhityadarpaṇa* – all the authorities on Sanskrit dramaturgy admit the view that the plot of the *nāṭikā* would be invented like the plot of a *prakaraṇa* and the hero would be a king like the hero of an *nāṭaka*. All the authorities have mentioned this theory in different expressions.

According to the *Nāṭyaśāstra*, the hero of a *nāṭaka* is to be a person of renowned, exalted and magnanimous nature from royal rear or with divine protection and has many super human powers.⁹ Abhinabagupta explains that the hero may belong to any of these four types: *dhīralalita*, *dhīraprasānta*, *dhīroddhata* and *dhīrodātta* (Nagar, 300). So, when Bharata depicts the nature of a king as the hero of a *nāṭikā*, he appears to belong to any of the four types.

Then about the plot, the *Nāṭyaśāstra* speaks that the *nāṭikā* is to be *utpanna*, whereas Sāgaranandī describes it as ‘*utpādya-vastu*’.

7 तत्र वस्तु प्रकरणात्तदकान्नायको नृपः । -D.R., III. 43.

8 Rasārṇavasudhākara, XVIII. 20-21

9 प्रख्यातवस्तुविषयं प्रख्यातोदात्तनायकं चैव । राजर्षिः वंशचरितं तथैव दिव्याश्रयोपातम् ॥ – N.S., XVIII.

This description is supported by the *Daśarūpaka*. The *Nātyadarpaṇa* describes the plot as 'Kalpārtha'.¹⁰ The *Sāhityadarpaṇa* speaks the plot on 'Kliptavṛtta'.¹¹

This discussion may lead us to believe that as the *nāṭikā* had sprung up from the two full-fledged *rūpakas*, it was non-existent at first and come into being later, but this is impossible. The term *uparūpaka* is a very late name. The earlier designations of *uparūpaka* and *rūpaka* were *nṛtyarūpaka* and the *geyarūpaka*.

After considering the remaining characteristics of the *nāṭikā*, it is seen that the *nāṭikā* is the lesser heroic and erotic *nāṭakā*.

According to the view of the *Nātyaśāstra*, the *nāṭikā* is based on *Kaiśikī-vṛtti*. The *nāṭikā* is related to affairs of the inner apartments of king's palace. It has many female characters. It contains four acts. It is composed with beautiful language, dances, songs, recitations and love. It is noted that the heroine is concerned with erotic enjoyments and treats of royal love. The *nāṭikā* also contains the royal manners, anger, its specification and deceit. The queen, the female messenger and the attendants must be also present in the *nāṭikā*.¹² These features of *nāṭikā* are supported in different expressions by the later authorities of the *Nātyaśāstra*. *Sāhityadarpaṇa* does not produce any special feature (S.D., VI. 269-272).

As an example of the *naṭikā* Śriharṣa's *Ratnavālī* and Rājśekhara's *Viddhaśālavañjikā* are always exemplified. They have given a character to the production of a series of the *naṭikā* which division still continues. It is seen that all the *naṭikās* such as Bilhana's *Karṇasundarī*, Mathurādāsa's *Vṛṣabhānujaya*, Viśvanatha's *Prabhāvatī nāṭikā* etc. are close imitations of the *Ratnavālī*. They cannot break the tradition of the *Ratnavālī*.

10 कल्पार्थचतुरङ्गिका बहुस्त्रीका नृपेशः स्त्री महीपतिः। कल्पार्थ कैशिकीमुख्या पूर्वरूपद्वययोथिता ॥
-Natyadarpana, II. 5.

11 नाटिका लुप्तवृत्ता स्यात् स्त्रीप्राया चतुरङ्गिका । -S.D., VI.269.

12 प्रकरणनाटकभेदादुत्पाद्यं वस्तु नायकं नृपतिम् । अन्तःपुरसङ्गीतककण्ठयामधिकृत्य कर्तव्या ॥
स्त्रीप्राया चतुरङ्गा ललिताभिनयत्मिका सुविहितार्था । बहुनृत्यगीतपाठ्या रतिसम्भोगात्मिका चैव ॥
राक्तोपचारयुक्ता प्रसादनक्रोधदम्भसंयुक्ता । नायकदेवीद्वती सपरिजना नाटिका ज्ञेया ॥ -N.S.,
XVIII.57-59

In the medieval period of Sanskrit literature in Mithila, a cluster of *nāṭikās* such as *Ānandavijaya*, *Kṛṣṇakelimālā*, *Uṣaharṇa*, *Gourīsayamvara* were written. These *nāṭikās* were though abided by the norms of Sanskrit dramaturgy, they cater the audience with different taste. The introduction of Maithilī song in the *nāṭikās* is a pertinent example. Our present work *Ānandavijaya* is worthy of mention among the open to criticism. Its style is rather innovative.

The *Ānandavijaya* is more effectively devised in plot. The main story of *Ānandavijaya* has been taken from *Brahmavaivarta-purāṇa* and *Brahma-purāṇa*, but it was not similar as a whole. The author Rāmadāsa Upādhyāya has organized the plot.

The hero, Mādhava, is full of a gay, gentle, calm and composed, ideal lover, adept in music, lover of amusement and good humour. So he can be easily considered as a *dhīralalita*-hero. The *Ānandavijaya*, containing six female characters, become ‘*striprāyā*’.

Rasa is the third element of *nāṭikā*. According to the Sanskrit dramaturgyists, *śṛṅgāra* is the principal sentiment in the *nāṭikā* which is seen in our present work.

One of the features of the *nāṭikā* is that the hero and heroines are always scared of the eldest wife but ultimately the eldest wife made their union possible, but we do not see such a thing in the *Ānandavijaya* and its absence never affects the quality of this *nāṭikā*. Apart from this, all the features of *nāṭikā* prescribed by Sanskrit dramaturgy are present in the *Ānandavijaya*. Representation of love-scenes, entertainments presented by Ānandakanda, graceful gesture of the female characters, Maithili songs and poetic dialogues prove that *kaiśikī-vṛtti* predominates in the present *nāṭikā*.

The *rasa* is the guiding factor among all the constituents of a dramatic work.¹³ The principal *rasa* admitted by theorists in *nāṭikā* is *śṛṅgāra*. Naturally the main sentiment of the *Ānandavijaya* is *śṛṅgāra*, particularly the *vipralambha-śṛṅgāra* develops into *sambhoga-śṛṅgāra*.

We know that *śṛṅgāra* is the first and most important of the sen-
13. न हि रसादते कश्चिदर्थः प्रवर्तते। -N.S., VI.32

timents.¹⁴ It deals with the rise, growth and development of the love and attachment between man and woman.¹⁵ The *śṛṅgāra* is of two kinds viz. *sambhoga-śṛṅgāra* and *vipralambha-śṛṅgāra*. The author Rāmadāsa Upadhyāya has effectively brought together these two in his *nāṭikā*.

In the first-act of the drama, when Ānandakanda describes the beauty of Rādhā and Mādhava enjoys it fully, the sentiment is *sambhoga-śṛṅgāra*, but while Mādhava, hearing the description, becomes anxious and restless to see Radha and insists Ānandakanda to meet her up, the sentiment is *vipralambha*.

In our text, Rādhā and Mādhava have passed through different stages. In the first- act of the *nāṭikā*, Mādhava eagerly waits to meet Rādhā and laments: ‘*tarhi nirāśho bhava majjibītena*’ (A. V, PAGE-30). In the second-act Rādhā is anxious to meet Mādhava but the social custom regarding marriage hinders their relationship. In the third-act Rādhā is seen in a love-lorn condition. She feels a pang of separation. She cries pathetically for her beloved and becomes unconscious. In the fourth-act Rādhā bereft Mādhava is seen in a wretched condition. He begins to mourn for Rādhā and repeatedly faints bereaving from Rādhā, thus, passing through the stages of *vipralambha-śṛṅgāra*, they are united with the blessing of *Ardhanārīśvara* and also with the help of Kāpālika.

There are occasional infusions of *hāsya*, *bhāyānaka* and *adbhuta rasa*. The quarrel between Ānandakanda and Bācālā in the second act creates laughter, but a sudden attack of a tiger in the same act raises terror. The *advuta-rasa* is evoked with the appearance of *Ardhanārīśvara* in the third act, but *śṛṅgāra* possesses most of the drama.

In the *nāṭikā*, the author has composed fourteen verses in different metres such as *vasantilaka*, *upajāti*, *mālinī* and *śārdūlavikrīḍita*. He has used them with equal skill. The author has produced successfully several *arthālaṃkāras* in this drama such as *upamā*, *utprekṣā*,

14. शृङ्गारहास्यकरुणा रौद्रवीरभयानकाः । वीभत्साद्भूतसंज्ञौ चेत्यष्टौ रसाः स्मृताः ॥ - N.S., VI.15.

शृङ्गारवीरवीभत्सरौद्रेषु मनसः क्रमात् । हास्याद्भूतभयोत्कर्षकरुणानां ते एव हि ॥ -D.R., IV.44

15 सुखप्रायेष्टसम्पन्नः ऋतुमाल्यादिसेवकः । पुरुषः प्रमदायुक्तः शृङ्गारः इति संज्ञितः ॥ D.R. IV. 46

svabhāvokti etc.

The style of *Ānandavijaya* is natural, simple and lucid which makes the drama come alive. Beyond the classical use of Sanskrit and *prākṛt* language, the author has composed two lyrics in *ava-haṭṭa*, describing his own family and the sceneries of Vṛndāvana respectively. He has composed twenty-nine lyrics in Maithili language. In these sweet lyrics, the love of Rādhā and Mādhava has been described. Rādhā's longing for Mādhava¹⁶ and the restless condition of Madhava¹⁷ to secure Rādhā has been picturesquely painted by these finest lyrics. Rāmadāsa has composed these radiant songs. Like *Dhūrtasamāgama* and other dramas of Mithilā, the name of author and patron of the *nāṭikā* are also mentioned in these lyrics. In fact, Rāmadāsa has successfully justified himself as the worthy successor of Vidyāpati. Now, it is very important to discuss how far the title '*Ānandavijaya*' is justified.

There can be various explanations on the implication of the title. In many scenes of the *nāṭikā*, the hero, Mādhava has addressed his vidūṣaka, Anandakanda as Ānanda and Ānanda has obtained triumph (*vijaya*) in many cases. In the first act of the drama, he is triumphant in making Mādhava promise to give thousand '*lāddu*'s in exchange of giving a description of Rādhā. In the second act he has defeated Rādhā's friend Bācālā in an argument. Rādhā also has begged for his forgiveness. Finally, the meeting of Rādhā and Mādhava becomes possible only because of Ānandakanda, thus, the triumphant Ānandakanda becomes the most significant character of the drama. From this point of view, the title is justified.

- 16 माधवविरहे वियोगिनि भेष । देल वृ।भानु दुलहि परवेश ॥
 मानस आकुल विकल शरीर । मुखरुचि मलीन, नयन ढर नीर ॥
 चीर चेत नहि, दीघ निसास । आधि आधीनि आलिञ्जन पास ॥
 विनु पुछलहुँ देअ उत्तर सानि । पुछलहुँ न कहय समुचित वानि ॥
 भनय राम रस बुझ अनुरूप । कमलावति पति सुन्दर भूप ।- A.V. 4, SONG NO.-16
- 17 मलय समीरण परसल मोर । देह दाह उपजावय घोर ॥
 हिमकर बमय गरलसम तेज । दहन गहन सम सरसिज-सेज ॥
 बरिस खार घनसार-कलाप । प्राणहुँ ताहि परम उपताप ॥
 सरस राम भन बुझ अनुरूप । प्राणवतीपति सुन्दर भूप ॥- A.V. 4, SONG NO.-14

On the other hand, Dr. Śaśikānta Jhā has remarked that the word 'Ānanda' actually refers to Mādhava. At the first *nāndī-sloka* of this drama, Śrī-krṣṇa is addressed as '*Parabrahma*': 'आनन्दचिन्मयं वः क्षमयतु दूरितं परब्रह्म' (A.V. Sl. No. 1) '*Parabrahma*' is the word that suggests 'Ānanda' (joy). Again, in the Maithilī-lyric of the first act of this drama, Mādhava is described as 'Ānandamaya' or jovial: 'आनन्दमय माधव परवेश (A.V. 1st act, Song no. 1) ।' Therefore Mādhava succeeds in achieving his goal by winning Rādhā. So Ānanda becomes triumphant or *vijāya*. This explanation is the most acceptable one.

Now, according to Viśvanatha, the title of an *nāṭikā* should be after the name of the heroine: 'नाटिकासट्टकादीनां नायिकाभिर्विशेषणम् (S.D. VI. 143) ।' But in the drama, the title does not abide by this rule of dramaturgy. The meaning of the title expresses the central idea of the drama which is right in case of *nāṭaka* but not right in case of *nāṭikā* : 'नाम कार्यं नाटकस्य गर्भितार्थप्रकाशनम् (S.D. VI. 157) ।' So a question may arise: why does '*Ānandavijaya*' violate the rule?

In reply it can be said that in visual art, the acting matters the most. The title '*Ānandavijaya*', it creates curiosity among the audience and arrests their attention to enjoy every scene with excitement. The suspense created by such a title the playwright achieves his worth as an artist.

Moreover, as we know that most of the rules of dramaturgy are composed after observing and studying the scriptures of Kalidāsa-Vyāsa-Śūdraka and many other legendary writers. Therefore, one cannot follow all the rules inch by inch. Probably this is why Ramcaraṇa Tarkavāgiśa remarked that these grammatical rules are often carried out but not always. (एतद् प्रायिकम्)

Therefore, we can conclude that the title '*Ānandavijaya*' is an apt one and the violation of rules is not that serious. The title has maintained a perfect balance between the characters and the course of the story. It successfully maintains suspense and arrests the attention of the audience, thus, Rāmadāsa shows his uniqueness in this drama. He sometimes has violated the rules of dramaturgy but did not prove himself as a truant and law breaker.

Literature is the reflection of life. A pertinent feature of the life-style of Mithilā was the inclination of the citizens towards music and dance. The people of Mithilā were believers of Hindu Gods and Goddesses. The three major deities that had been inspiring them for ages were Śiva, Śakti and Viṣṇu. The people revered them equally. A *tilaka* is smeared on the forehead of the *sannyāsin* in *Dhūrtasamāgama*. The three horizontal marks of the sacred ash in the *tilaka* suggest that they were devotees of Śiva. The mark of sandal on that suggests their devotion to Viṣṇu and the mark of vermilion suggests their devotion of Śakti.

After the appearance of Vidyāpati, the Maithilī literature started having the influence of Visnu. Their devotion to Śakti can also be traced. That's why, though the plot of the *Pārijātaharana* centres around Rādhā-Kṛṣṇa, it starts with the invocation to Goddess Durgā.

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Cognitive Psychology Reflected on Swami Vivekananda's Thoughts

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Abstract

Cognitive Psychology, Over the past fifty years, cognitive psychology has advanced remarkably, generating a substantial amount of data that focuses on several elements of the mind's intricate cognitive architecture. The development of universal concepts, patterns, as well as models that might be applied to all domains of psychology had not been limited due to its focus on individual processes, that is largely necessary and detailed. In reality, other related fields of research, like clinical psychology, developmental psychology, social psychology, educational psychology, applied psychology, etc., can use the scientific analysis of cognitive psychology since it studies the mind's operations, comprising reasoning, language, attention, memory, and many more, which form the basis of all psychological activities and behaviors. Swami Vivekananda's vision of cognitive psychology goes beyond the traditional boundaries of psychology, offering a holistic approach that integrates the cognitive, emotional, and spiritual dimensions of human experience. His ideas suggest that the mind is not only a tool for intellectual understanding but also a gateway to deeper states of awareness and potential, offering a transformative pathway to personal growth and enlightenment. Nonetheless, there are indications that the moment has come for cognitive psychology to contribute more substantially to the research on individual differences in IQ and other cognitive skills.

Keywords: Behaviorism, Impressions, Indriyas, Behavioral

Introduction

Swami Vivekananda is well known as an inspiring personality

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in the nation as well as the world at large. When the Parliament of Religions was held in Chicago in 1983, the unknown Indian sage unexpectedly rose to fame. His depth of knowledge in Eastern and Western culture coincided with yogic inside and psychological views making him a towering personality with universal Outlook. So this great monk is regarded as one of the advocates of neo-Vedanta philosophy dedicated to the modern weight which is designed for the upliftment of the downtrodden common mass Swami Vivekananda doctrine contains a universal appeal to comparative religion and at the same time his views contained a depth and with of cognitive psychology. Swami Vivekananda, a key figure in the spiritual and philosophical renaissance of India, was deeply concerned with the nature of human consciousness and its potential. His insights into the mind, perception, and self-awareness presage many ideas in modern cognitive psychology, even though his teachings were rooted in ancient spiritual traditions. Vivekananda's vision of cognitive psychology can be understood through his exploration of the nature of the self, the processes of thought, and the concept of mental discipline. Cognitive Psychology, as a branch of psychology, explores how the mind processes information, including perception, memory, decision-making, and problem-solving. Swami Vivekananda, a renowned spiritual leader and philosopher, offered profound insights into the nature of the human mind and consciousness, which align with many of the concepts explored in cognitive psychology.

Elements of cognitive psychology in Swami Vivekananda's thoughts:

A distinctive branch of psychology called cognitive psychology researches mental processes such as perception, memory, learning, and thought processes. Ulaic Neisser, an American psychologist, coined the phrase "cognitive psychology" in 1967 while writing a book on the subject. It is concerned with internal mental states, as opposed to behaviorism, which solely considers observable behavior. Swami Vivekananda's viewpoints which co-incised with cognitive psychology can be seen in the instance on the talk of secret of work. Therefore, it is said that every action we take and every idea we have has an impact on our mental content. Even if these impressions

are not readily obvious, they are strong enough to operate subconsciously beneath the surface. The sum of these mental inputs determines who we are at any one time. Together, all of these impacts determine the character of each guy. A positive impression transforms the character into a good one; a negative one transforms it into a terrible one(Vivekananda).

Here, Swami Vivekananda has shown that my present state is the result of the accumulation of all of my past life's impressions. According to Swami Vivekananda, character is determined by the imprints that are left on the mind. It is believed that if a character prevails a good impression, they become good, and if they make a poor impression, they become bad. A man's head will be filled with negative impressions if he hears and thinks negative things regularly. These impressions will affect his work and ideas without him being fully conscious of it. These negative impressions are constantly at work, and the inevitable outcome must be evil. The man will always be wicked, and he is unable to stop it. The combination of these impressions will give him a tremendous incentive to act inappropriately. His impressions will manipulate him like a machine and make him commit evil. All these facts constitute the root of criminal attitudes found here and there in society and the world at large. This can be corrected by the inducement of positive views on the part of the individuals concerned, thus it can be arrived that no amount of force legislative cruelty or magistracy might change condition of the race. The only way to reverse a negative tendency is through a culture that is moral and spiritual. Here the words of Swami Vivekananda will be relevant in the process of cleansing the mind and creating good visions and thoughts for a sound political setup in a democratic world.

He therefore thinks that a man has an insatiable desire to succeed when he has done a great deal of good work and thought of numerous good things. A man's good character is considered established when something occurs, through this constant reflex of positive thoughts, a good impression spreading all over the mental surface, and an intense tendency to act morally, one feels in control of their senses or Indriyas. India's age-long tradition that prevailed to waking up the kings and princesses early morning by the royal concerts

through rendering good motivations brings home the importance of creating good and positive views on the part of administrators. The beginning words of Sri Venkateswara suprabhata-

Kaushalya Supraja Rama, Poorva Sandhya Pravartate,
Uttistha Narasardula Kartavyam Daivam Ahnikam.

(Oh the good son of kousalya, it is time to wake up in the early morning. Oh the Brave son you have to accomplish the noble tasks)

Thus creating good views and impressions at the waking up of early morning constitutes the best and practical way for the formulation of character. Here Swami Vivekananda's aforesaid psychological views become relevant in the field of education and culture. This illustrates how every mental state causes an associated physical state, and how every bodily action comparably affects the mind. Thus held in the Yogavasista that whatever is done by the mind is the actual work on the part of an individual (Nehru).

Swami Vivekananda and Indian traditions on depth psychology

According to Vivekananda, a nation's psychical ability declines as its population multiplies. There might be more psychological power in a large, sparsely populated country (Rajagopalachari). The study of these sciences is practised by thousands of people and has become an integral part of worship for the entire country. Swami Vivekananda's concept brings to mind the phenomenon of kavus, which are worshipping centres of sacred groves.

The phenomenon that all extraordinary skills are in man's mind is highlighted by the science of Rajayoga. The universal mind contains this mind. A phenomenon of thought transference is present. The mind is universal, so it is believed that my mind, your mind, and all these small minds are fragmentary of the universal mind, like little ocean waves, also because of such continuity, we may share self-thoughts directly with others. For example, an individual is shown thinking something here, & that thought manifests in someone, somewhere else. Distance does not matter; thought travels and reaches another person, that he comprehends (Radhakrishnan).

Further, Vivekananda's thoughts on attention, perception, and the development of cognitive abilities align with contemporary cognitive theories, particularly the role of mental frameworks in shaping reality. He advocated for a balance between intellect and intuition, where the rational mind works in harmony with the deeper, intuitive consciousness. His concept of "mental training" parallels cognitive behavioral approaches, where the restructuring of thoughts can lead to emotional and behavioral changes, enhancing mental well-being.

It is based on this principle Swami Vivekananda has devised a practical philosophy of universal brotherhood with a mission and vision of service. He embraced all religions for his mission of service to the downtrodden people at large. He always cherished a broad mind and broad vision, thus he always exhorts that our mind must be like a deep ocean and vast sky. He emphasized the importance of self-realization, where understanding the true nature of the self leads to mastery over mental faculties. He believed that the mind is shaped by both conscious and unconscious processes and that a disciplined mind, honed through meditation and introspection, can transcend the limitations imposed by habitual thoughts and emotions. He spoke of the mind as a dynamic force, capable of transformation through the power of will and focus, resonating with modern ideas of cognitive reappraisal and neuroplasticity.

Upon reflection, several key elements of Vivekananda's teachings resonate with the principles of cognitive psychology:

1. **Mind as a Tool for Transformation:** Vivekananda emphasized the power of the mind to shape one's reality. He believed that thoughts shape character and, by extension, destiny. Cognitive psychology also focuses on how mental processes (thoughts, beliefs, and perceptions) influence behavior, demonstrating that controlling and transforming one's thought patterns can lead to personal growth and achievement.
2. **Self-awareness and Consciousness:** Vivekananda discussed the importance of self-awareness and higher states of consciousness in understanding one's true nature. Cognitive

psychology examines metacognition—the awareness of one’s thinking processes—and how this self-awareness can enhance learning, decision-making, and emotional regulation.

3. **The Role of Attention and Focus:** Vivekananda highlighted the significance of concentration (Dharana) in achieving success and spiritual growth. Cognitive psychology studies how attention works and how focused attention is crucial for cognitive tasks such as problem-solving, memory, and learning.
4. **Belief Systems and Cognitive Bias:** Vivekananda stressed that belief in one’s potential is a critical factor in overcoming challenges. Cognitive psychology similarly explores how beliefs and cognitive biases can shape perceptions and behavior, often limiting or expanding one’s potential based on the mental frameworks one holds.
5. **Transformation through Mental Training:** Vivekananda believed in the transformative power of disciplined mental practice (yoga, meditation, and self-control). Cognitive psychology acknowledges that mental training, such as mindfulness and cognitive behavioral techniques, can lead to significant changes in thought patterns, emotions, and behavior.

Conclusion

Swami Vivekananda’s teachings on the power of the mind, self-awareness, concentration, and mental transformation are strongly aligned with the principles of cognitive psychology. Both perspectives emphasize the potential of the human mind to shape personal outcomes and achieve higher levels of functioning through awareness, focus, and mental discipline. In essence, Vivekananda’s philosophy and cognitive psychology both advocate for the importance of mastering one’s thoughts to lead a more fulfilling and purposeful life. His insights can be seen as an early exploration of concepts that have since been developed in modern cognitive science.

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Early Sāṃkhya as Depicted in Buddhacarita of Asvaghōṣa

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Abstract

Early sāmkhya depicted as Buddhacarita of Asvaghōṣa” an attempt to examine the ancient sāmkhya philosophy is most important in philosophical studies. Asvaghōṣa was a philosopher and poet. He was a Buddhist monk. Buddhacarita is the first and masterpiece work of Asvaghōṣa. It deals with the biography of Gautama Buddha. The Sanskrit text of Buddhacarita comprises only fourteen cantos. In the twelfth canto of the Buddhacarita, referred to as Arādadarṣana, the sage Arāda provides an explanation of his philosophical views. It is nothing more than a summary of a single school of thinking. Therefore, an early form of Sāmkhya philosophy is offered in Asvaghōṣa’s Buddhacarita. In certain ways, Kapila’s Sāmkhya system is different from an older sarmkhya philosophy.

Life of Asvaghōṣa

Before Kalidasa (5th century), Asvaghōṣa was regarded as India’s greatest poet and the founder of Sanskrit drama. He was also a philosopher. He made the Kavya school of Sanskrit poetry prominent. Asvaghōṣa was born into a Brahmin family, yet there is no denying that he converted to Buddhism through earnest effort and eventually became both a real Buddhist in theory and practice. He was converted to Sarvāstivāda Buddhism and was born in the central Indian city of Saketa. The name of his mother was Suvarnākshi.

आर्या सुवर्णा क्षी पुत्रस्य साकेत स्थमि क्षोराचार्य भदन्ता
अश्वघोषस्य महाकवेर्महावादिनःकृतिरियम् ॥

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Date of Asvaghōṣa's period of living is difficult to be determined. Different scholars give different opinions regarding his date. Prof. Ludens holds that the remaining parts of the manuscript fragments of Sariputra prakarana belongs to the region of Kushan king probably to the reign of Kanishka. Kushan king Kanishka who ruled India in the period of AD 78-150AD. So most of the people agree that Asvaghōṣa lived during the Kanishka period, which means that he lived around 100 AD.

The literary style of Asvaghōṣa proves that he lived several centuries before Kalidasa. We may cite some similarities between the works of Kalidasa and Asvaghōṣa in support of that. Asvaghōṣa's description in respect of the atmosphere of the birth of prince Gautama in Buddhacarita is similar to the description of the birth of Raghu in Raghuvamsa. Similarly the other example in Buddhacarita canto III, Buddha's passage through the royal streets of his kingdom and was witnessed by the beautiful ladies of the harem reminds or siva's entry into oushadi, prastha, a scene from Kalidasa's Kumarasambhavam canto VIII. Besides these there are so many references from which it may be said that Kalidasa was influenced by Asvaghōṣa. Kalidasa flourished probably in the 5th century A.D. Hence Asvaghōṣa and his precursor lived in the 1st century A.D.

Works of Asvaghōṣa

There are a lot of works that are considered to be by Asvaghōṣa, but only three are thought to be genuine. These are Buddhacarita, Saundarananda and Sariputraprakarana. In his writings, he has put forward dry intellectual and moral ideas in a very beautiful way. While many works by Asvaghōṣa have been attributed to him, just three are considered to be genuinely authentic.

1. Buddhacarita (life of the Buddha)
2. Saundarananda (of sundari and nanda)
3. Sariputraprakarana

The first two are Mahakavyas, and the third is Prakarana. Some other ornate works are also attributed to Asvaghōṣa and the works are Sraddhopadasastra, Vajrasuci, and Sutralamkara etc. But this is

a conjecture due to the absence of any solid proof. So Asvaghōṣa authorship of these works is controversial.

Buddhacarita

The first, and by far the best, works of art that Asvaghōṣa produced is the well-known Buddhacarita. But unfortunately, the Sanskrit text of this invaluable work is incomplete. Original Buddhacarita was composed in 28 cantas. The Tibetan and Chinese translation of this epic also mentions the same number of chapters. The original Buddhacarita rediscovered in 1892, had been known from the Tibetan and Chinese translation.

Buddhacarita deals with the biography of Gautama Buddha along with the doctrines of Buddhism in a very attractive style. The work has two parts. The first part describes the life history of Gautama from his birth to his enlightenment. Second part deals with the description of Buddha's return to Kapilavastu, reunion of the father and son, propagation of his doctrines and the reign of Asoka etc. The Sanskrit text is fragmentary. It contains only 14 cantos. The epic Buddhacarita decorated with miraculous elements which depict Buddhist doctrines and worshiping of Buddha. Asvaghōṣa tries to rejoice the heart of the reader with a colorful and meaningful ornate poetry. The poet has introduced a large number of legendary figures and many mythological stories.

The Buddhacarita begins with a beautiful description of Kapilavastu. Because the city was incorporated into the hermitage of Sage Kapila, it was known as Kapilavastu. Asvaghōṣa praises the virtues of the sage Kapila and the Ikṣvaku dynasty's descendent. The epic tells the story of how a group of Ikṣvaku princes visit the calm and peaceful monastery of Kapila and live in the forest before founding a city and establishing a system of popular government. Over time, the kingdom eventually belongs to King Suddhodana.

In the twelfth canto of the Buddhacarita, referred to as Aradadaṛṣana, the sage Arāda provides an explanation of his philosophical views. It is nothing more than a summary of a single school of thinking. Therefore, an early form of Sāṃkhya philosophy is offered in

Asvaghōṣa's Buddhacarita. In certain ways, Kapila's Sāmkhya system is different from an older sarmkhya philosophy.

Early Sāmkhya As Depicted In Buddhacarita Of Asvaghōṣa

Since Sāmkhya philosophy has influenced all of the Astika darśanas, it is well-known among Indian philosophical systems. It offers a logical description of the evolutionary process. Sāmkhya system was developed by Sage Kapila. The philosophy of Sāmkhya is sometimes called Kapila Darśanas. The ancient practises of yoga and sarmkhya are also mentioned in the Mahabharata. Thus, all the systems acknowledge the significance of this sastra.

The word Sarkhya is derived from the Sāmkhya which is again etymologically derived from the root Khya (jijana) preceded by the suffix Sam. Generally Sāmkhya means number. The Sastra where there is the counting of tattvas is called Sāmkhya. This is the common derivation. The word Sāmkhya is used the sense of thinking and counting. Thinking may be with reference to correct knowledge of self. Counting refers to the twenty five principles, three qualities, three sources of valid knowledge and dualism of puruṣa and prakṛiti.

Characteristics of early Sāmkhya

The individual is the subject of study in early Sāmkhya and early Buddhism, as opposed to the cosmos, which is covered in the Mahabharata and the twelfth chapter of Buddhacarita. The primary source of Sāmkhya tradition is acknowledged to be Isvarakṛṣṇa Sāmkhya karika. Yet he is not the originator of this system and number of evidences may be detected regarding the existence of Sāmkhya Karika. In actuality, Indian philosophy was developing for many centuries prior to the composition of any of the surviving, authoritative treatises on the many classical systems. It is stated that during this early stage of orthodox speculation, the early Sāmkhya school teachers' guiding idea predominated over all other theories.

Early Sāmkhya is documented in a methodical and acknowledged manner. Only texts such as the *Vedas*, *Puranic texts*, *Mahabharata*, *Gita*, etc. make reference to early Sāmkhya. Essentially, the theistic

story of Sāmkhya may be found in these writings in various forms. Early Sāmkhya being demonstrates a strong theistic account dominance. If the early Sāmkhya was essentially theistic or atheistic, that is difficult to determine.

Johnson says that he made a good effort in the discussion of general problems related to the texts and question of origin of the early Sāmkhya. He concludes the analysis by summarising that the early Sāmkhya period can be divided into two main categories: theistic Sāmkhya and atheistic Sāmkhya. The development Sāmkhya is carefully observed. It can be discovered that the *Buddhacarita* of Asvaghōṣa, which is included, contains numerous Sāmkhya components. A fairly methodical description of Sāmkhya is found in *Buddhacarita* chapter 12 (slokas 15–44), which is followed by a description of yoga. Although the terms “Sāmkhya” and “yoga” are not mentioned in the text, Asvaghōṣa attributes these teachings to the sage Arada. It is clear that the description is of Sāmkhyayoga. In 12th chapter he described the principles of Sāmkhya philosophy.

Principles Of Sāmkhya Philosophy

Three-fold misery

Sāmkhya claims that people make a great effort to free themselves from the ignorance-based suffering that surrounds them. An overwhelming, three-fold pain gets into a person, prompting them to seek philosophical answers in an effort to end their suffering. In order to free the soul from its captivity, Sāmkhya seeks to impart the knowledge that will permanently eradicate the source of suffering. No ultimate solution could be found using any of the existing methods. The wisdom that will put an end to suffering forever must be obtained. The ability to distinguish between Puruṣa and Prakṛti comes from this understanding. After the twenty-five principles are listed and examined, correct knowledge can be obtained.

Ādhyatmika, or intrinsically caused pain, is the first type of pain. It is separated further into two: Mānasa and Śarira. The imbalance of body fluids leads to the former. Lustre and other negative emotions are the root cause of mānasa. rage, envy, etc.

Adhidaivika, the second type of pain, is caused by paranormal forces like as demons and planetary movements, among others. Adhibhautika, or third-kind pain, is caused by outside factors such as objects or animals. The opening line of the Sāmkhya Sutra states that liberation—the eradication of threefold suffering—is the ultimate goal.

अथ त्रिविधदुःखात्यन्तनिवृत्तिरत्यन्तपुरुषार्थः । (S.S1.1)

The Buddhist belief that there is suffering in the world is comparable to the Sāmkhya concept of threefold pain. Buddhism aims to end suffering by following the eightfold path (अष्टांगमार्गः), whereas Sāmkhya wants to end suffering by gaining knowledge of the twenty-five principles.

According to Sāmkhya, proper knowledge (pramā) or appropriate knowledge is what makes instruments necessary, which is definite and undeniable qualifies as valid knowledge. The validity of knowledge is a subject of debate among several philosophical traditions, thus, each of them accepts a different number of Pramāṇa-s.

Three Pramāṇa-s—Pratyakṣa, Anumana, and Aptavacana—are accepted by Sāmkhya. The three can contain all other forms of information. In Pratyakṣa, Anumiti, or Śabdajñāna, Upamiti is a part. Three types of Anumana exist in Arthāpatti. Pratyakṣa is the only type that Abhava is. In the same way, these three comprise all other Pramāṇa-s. Sāmkhya therefore asserts that there are just three Pramāṇa-s. Via their Pramāṇa-s, all things in this world can be known. Therefore, accepting more pramāṇa-s is not necessary.

Twenty-five Principles

In Aradadarsana Arada says that the twenty-five principles. Sāmkhya believes that Prakṛti is the ultimate cause of the universe and supports the dualism of Puruṣa and Prakṛti, which are the two eternal realities. In addition to Puruṣa and Prakṛti, Prakṛti produces twenty-three other principles. Prakṛti is the first cause of the universe, one that is complex because it is made up of the Gunas. Everything has a cause, except for Prakṛti, which is the root cause from which everything else develops.

Sāmkhyakarika describes the twenty-five principles of Sāmkhya philosophy. In Buddhacarita, Asvaghōṣa divides avyakta into two categories, in contrast to Isvarakṛṣṇa's classification in the Karika. The first is the eight-fold Prakṛti, which includes the five gross elements, Aharnkara, Buddhi, and Vyākta. The group of sixteen vikāra (modifications) is the second. It consists of the five objects of sensation, the mind, and the 10 organs.

Asvaghōṣa mentions the Tanmatras and the objects of the sense as the tattvas,

प्रकृतिश्च विकारश्च जन्ममृत्युजरैव च ।
तत्तावत् सत्वमित्युक्तं स्थिरसत्वपरेहि तत् ॥

The definition of sattva is the primary matters. Its modification, birth, death and old age. All these are said to be Sattva.

तल तुप्रकृति नाम विद्धि प्रकृतिकोविद ।
पन्चभूतान्यहङ्कारं बुद्धिमव्यक्तमेव च ॥

Prakṛti

Prakṛti was the first thing in existence. It is the main reason behind everything. It is the ultimate cause, independent of all other causes. As a result, it is the fundamental evolvent. Prakṛti is synonymized with a number of names, including Tamas, Aja, Avyakta, and Avyākṛta. as the underlying reason that is not the cause. Pradhāna (urea) is what it is. It is the stage in which all effects are manifest. We call it Ayakta. Prakṛti is the material basis of everything and the universe's grid. The term for it is Prakṛti. The entire world is multiplied by it. Since everything eventually melts into it, it is known as pradhāna. It goes under the name Avyakta. Ordinary sense organs are unable to perceive it. Since it is the source of all things, it is Aja. Prakṛti have the dynamic ability to evolve and this universe, but it lacks sentience, Purusha manipulates it to carry out this task rather than it doing so on its own.

Three Gunās constitute Prakṛti and its effects: satva, rajas, and tamas. These are inherently balanced and independent of one another. This equilibrium changes in the presence of Purusha, thus there Gunas unite or separate to form everything else in this cosmos. There

is movement, heaviness, and lightness in the three gunas. They can't be considered Purusha's attributes. The properties of the materials in question. Every object in this world is the outcome of these three guns' permutations and combinations.

The gunās

Three Gunās constitute Prakṛti and its effects: satva, rajas, and tamas. These are inherently balanced and independent of one another. This equilibrium changes in the presence of Purusha, thus there Gunas unite or separate to form everything else in this cosmos. There is movement, heaviness, and lightness in the three gunas. They can't be considered Purusha's attributes. The properties of the materials in question, every object in this world is the outcome of these three guns' permutations and combinations.

Mahat

The first evolutionarily produced being is Mahat, or Buddhi. The Sāṃkhya school of thought disputes the upāṣadic assertion that ākāūa and others are the starting point of development, contending that Mahat is the point at which evolution begins. It is the main item that Prakṛti produces. Because it is stronger and more extensive than the other Prakṛti evolutions, it is excellent in both space and time. which has ascertained as its purpose. Purusha is closest to Buddhi. It works directly for him, giving him the ability to distinguish between Prakṛti and himself and thereby realize his emancipated nature.

The Sāttvika nature of the Buddha, reflects the light of the self in the intellect, like external items in a mirror's clean surface. Upon viewing its reflection in the Buddha's mirror, the self incorrectly associates itself with the mirrored picture and loses sight of its own nature. The source of intelligence and the cause of ahamkāra is Mahat. It is the source of evolution. It joined forces with Ahamkara. It is the source of each soul's unique acts. Mahat is responsible for memory, decision-making, and ascertainment.

Ahaṃkāra

Ahaṃkāra distinguishes oneself from everyone else. It creates a unique personality. It is what gives rise to individual diversity, be-

cause ahamkara is associated with Purusha, he starts to sense “I” and “mine” and starts to think of himself as the agent of actions. The purpose of ahaṃkara, the foundation of all worldly endeavors, is abhimana. There are three different types: Tajasa or Rajasa, which is dominated by Rajas, Tamasa, which is dominated by Tamas, and Sāttvika, which is dominated by Sattva.

Ahamkara is the agent upon which all other items are developed. Its products are divided into five tanmatras and a set of eleven organs. The Sāttvika ahamkara is the source of the eleven organs. The Tamasa ahamkara contains the five Tanmatras. They both start with the Tajasa form.

Tanmatras.

All material realities are built upon tanmatras. They are the imperceptible, delicate essences. They can be deduced from this. The subtle aspects of Sabda, Sparsha, Rūpa, Rasa, and Gandha are known as tanmatras. which are referred to as Avisesas in their actual nature. They are not attached to any one item. Every Tanmitra gives rise to the matching Mahabhitas. As a result, Tanmatras, Sabda, Vayu, Rūpa, Rasa, Tejas, Āpah, and Gandha are the sources of akasa, prthvi, and sparsa, respectively. The viśesas are the Tanmātras.

The foundation of all physical realities are tanmatras. They are the indistinguishable subtle essences that are invisible. By inference, we are aware of them. The subtle aspects of Rūpa, Rasa, Gandha, Sabda, and Sparsha are called tanmatras. which are referred to be avisesas in reality. They are not attached to anything specific. The equivalent Mahabhūtas emerge from every Tanmatra. Thus, Tejas originates from Rūpa, Āpah from Rasa Tanmatras, Vayu from Sparsha, and prthvi from Gandha. Similarly, akasa arises from Sabda. They are viśesas, the Tanmātras.

Sixteen Vikaras.

In *Buddhacarita* Arada says that the sixteen vikaras. They are the parts of twenty five principles. Arada says

विकार इति बुध्यस्व विषयाणि इन्द्रियाणि च ।

पाणिपादं च वाचं च पायुपस्थं तथा मनः ॥

The hands and feet, the voice, the organs of creation and excretion, the objects of sense, and the mind make the secondary matter. The five sense organs (ज्ञानेन्द्रियाणि) and the five motor organs (कर्मेन्द्रियाणि) are the external organs. The sensory organs are the śrotra (श्रोत्र) the tvak (त्वक्), the cakṣus (चक्षुः), the jihva (जिह्वा) and the Ghrana (घ्राण). The motor organs are the vak (वाक्), the pani (पाणि), the pada (पादः), the payu (पायुः), and the upastha (उपस्थः)

The understanding of external objects, such as Sabda, Sparsa, Rupa, Rasa, and Ganda, is the function of the sense organs. Vacana, Dana, Viharana, Utsarga, and Ananda are the functions of the motor organs, in that order. The origin of these organs is the Sāttvika ahankara. Savisesavisayas are the sense organs that are sensitive to particular objects. They make no mention of the skin, ears, or other exterior organs.

Manas

Manas facilitates the Sense organ's operation. It's the eleventh organ. The inner organ, or manas, is considered the major organ. The other Jñanedriyas become active as a result. It is the observational principle that the sense of imagination uses. It has characteristics of both types of organs. It is the Inner organ, which works in combination with the other ten organs. Manas in connection with the many ways that the Gunas are modified. The same individual can act as a lover in front of their beloved, a detached guy in front of someone else, and so on. This is known as the function of many.

Ahamkara, Manas, Buddha, and ten Indriyas are called Karanas. Antakaranas have three in the top place. As understanding is an interior process, they aid in it. In Bahyakaranas, the ten organs are. Through these instruments, Purusha experiences and pleasures herself.

The Mahabhūtas.

The Mahabhūtas of Ākasa, Vāyu, Agni and Bhūmi. They are extracted from the respective Tanmātras. According to the Sāmkhya Sutra, the Tanmatras give rise to the Mahabhūtas.

The quality of Sabda is possessed by Akasa. Its root is śabdatanmatra; Vayu is the combination of śabda and sparsa, and it is derived from Sparsatanmatra. In addition to śabda and Sparsa, Tejas, also known as Agni, has Rūpa as one of its qualities. Rūpatanmatra gives rise to it. Aside from śabda, Sparsa, and Rūpa, Apah possesses the property of Rasa. In addition to Gandha, they also evolve from Rasatanmatra and prthvi, śabda, and rūpa. Gandha Tanmatra evolves as a result of it.

Puruṣa

As a dualistic philosophical theology, Sāmkhya acknowledges Puruṣa and Prakṛti's existence. One of the Principal Sāmkhya philosophies is Puruṣa. In opposition to Prakṛti, it is suggested as a sentient entity. Prakṛti has no sense of awareness. Creation is contingent upon the presence of sentient beings. Puruṣa is the only language spoken in Prakṛti. Puruṣa is eternally separated from Prakṛti, existing outside of it. He is without qualities, without beginning or finish. He is transcendent and quiet. He exists outside of space and time. As pure consciousness, he is the eternal seer, flawless and unchanging. Puruṣa is merely a spectator and not an agent.

Knower

Asvaghoṣa speaks of the division of Kṣetra and Kṣetrajña. At sometimes he is keen to differentiate the Avyakta from the vyakta.

“Something which is conscious and also knows the field is called the knower of the field. Those who investigate or meditate upon the soul is called knower of the field.” “In the opinion of Arāda vyakta is that which is subject to birth, old age, and disease and death. While reverse is known to avyakta.”

अस्य क्षेत्रस्य विज्ञानात् क्षेत्रज्ञ इति संज्ञि च ।

क्षेत्रज्ञ इति यात्मानं कथयन्त्यात्म चिन्नकाः

It is understood that the visible or seen is that which is born, grows old, becomes ill, and passes away. However, the terms “unmanifest” and “unseen” should be separated as having different meanings. No one imparts incorrect information. One must regard the power of the deeds and desire as a “being.” We refer to these three facts as the

causes of the existence cycle.

Eight factors.

Asvaghōṣa enumerates and defines the eight factors of worldly existence.

विप्रत्ययादहङ्कारात् संदेहदमिसंप्लवत्
अविशेषानुपायाभ्यां सङ्गादभ्यवपातत : ॥

They are ahaṃkara(egoism), sanga(attachment), samśaya(doubt), abhisamplava (wrong conjunction), abhyavapāta(Down fall), vipratyaya(Wrong notion), aviśesa(lack of discrimination) and anupāya (wrong means).

Ignorance, Right knowledge & Supreme Absolute

In *Buddhacarita* ignorance can be divided into five. Sage Arada declares ignorance to be a group of five that group consists of delusion, great delusion and two kind of darkness.(तम मोह महामोह तामिस्र अन्धतामिस्र)

इत्यविद्यां हि विद्वान् स पञ्चपर्व समीहते
तलालस्य मोहं महामोहं नामिस्र द्वयमेव च ॥

The eight forms of Tamah are Panjatanmatras, Mahat, Prakṛti, and Aharnkara. Moha has eight layers. Tamisra and Andhatamsira are eighteen fold, while Mahamoha is tenfold. This raises the total to sixty-two, together with the eight other kinds of Tamas. Moha has eleven sections. Mahamoha is the attachment of the eight types of power to the 10 objects of sense.

Liberation

It is also important to pay close attention to the idea of freedom that is promoted in the Sāmkhya accounts of Buddhacarita. The stage of liberation is likewise identified by Asvaghōṣa with Brahman. Consequently, it is discovered that he asserts the absolute Brahman's attribute lessness. It is unchanging, everlasting, unchanging, eternal, and devoid of any distinct signs. This is what the wise man refers to as liberation.. The following verse bears testimony to this view.

एतत् परमं ब्रह्म निर्लिङ्ग ध्रुवमक्षरम्

यन्मोक्ष इति तत्त्वज्ञ कथयन्ति मनीषिणः

“According to Buddhacarita Asvaghōṣa explains the nature of liberation in Sāṃkhya philosophy. Arada explain the method of liberation to Siddhartha. The wise man passes through higher wisdom in order to abolish all body of evils they emerged from a concentrated meditation. The wise man prepares his mind on progress turn away from the material desire from and previously from the passions. The wise man understands a clear idea of space with regard to its solid matter. Firstly, he makes a mental concept about empty spaces but another wise man reaches a higher stage and also contracting his self and looks on much unlimited thing. Another man who was profoundly versed in the supreme self is being himself by himself. He declared himself that he sees nothing -

“When soul is escaped from the body is declared to be liberated just like the munjastak from its sheath or the bird from its cage. This supreme Brahman is constant. The learned men who know these principles are called liberation”.

Conclusion

Asvaghōṣa is considered to be the father of Sanskrit drama. It is credited to him that the word “kavya” was first used. Most people believe that he lived during the reign of the great Kushan ruler Kanishka, which is generally agreed to be between 78 and 150 AD. Without a doubt, Asvaghōṣa is a poet of diverse genius above all else. He was a poet of great distinction, a scholar, a follower of Buddhism, and a man of profound reflection, through his works, he has beautifully conveyed dry philosophical and ethical topics.

Though several works are attributed to Asvaghōṣa, just three are thought to be undoubtedly authentic. These are Sariputrāprakaraṇa, Saundarananda (of Sundarī and Nandananda), and Buddhacarita (the life of the Buddha). Asvaghōṣa’s earliest and best-known creation is Buddhacarita. The *Buddhacarita*’s Sanskrit text is incomplete. Original *Buddhacarita* was composed in 28 cantos.

The *Buddhacarita* opens with a lovely depiction of Kapilavastu. It was founded within the hermitage of Sage Kapila, the city was

known as Kapilavastu. The life and achievements of the sage Kapila and the Iksvaku dynasty descendent are eulogistically described by Asvagoṣa. The epic tells the story of how some Iksvaku princes visit the serene and lovely monastery of Kapila and live in the forest before establishing a city there by popular agreement. Eventually, the kingdom is given to King Suddhodana.

In the *Buddhacarita*'s twelfth canto, known as Aradadarśana, sage Arada is seen to provide an explanation of his philosophy. It is nothing more than a synopsis of one of the Sāmkhya schools. As a result, Asvagoṣa has described early Sāmkhya traits in *Buddhacarita*.

It deals with the biography of Gautama buddha, the founder of Buddha philosophy along with the doctrines of Buddhism in a very attractive style.

In his works literature, religion, philosophy and life are combined together to provide aesthetic delight to the readers in an entertaining way. His aim was also to educate people with the doctrines of Buddha. Asvagoṣa had a deep knowledge of Indian geography. Buddhist literature is full of geographical description. Asvagoṣa has given many geographical descriptions in his writings especially in *Buddhacarita*.

Buddhacarita begins with a wonderful description of Kapilavastu, because the city was incorporated into the hermitage of Sage Kapila, it was known as Kapilavastu. The life and accomplishments of the sage Kapila and the Iksvaku dynasty descendent are eulogistically described by Asvagoṣa. He talks about how certain hermits of Kapila lived in the forest before founding a city and establishing a system of government based on consent. Over time, the kingdom eventually belongs to King Suddhodana.

According to Aradadarśana Arada says that, sattva is the fundamental matter, and its changes include birth, death, and old age. These are all considered to be sattvas. In contrast to Isvarakrishna's karika, Asvagoṣa divides the avyakta into two categories. The first is the eight-fold Prakṛti, which includes the five gross elements, avyakta, buddhi, and ahankara. The ten organs, the intellect, and the

five sense objects make up the vikara (modification) group, which is formed by the second.

Arada discusses the separation of Kṣetra and Kṣetrajña while also emphasizing the need to distinguish between avyakta and vyakta. He lists and defines the eight components of this earthly existence as well. They are lack of discriminating, egoism, attachment, doubt, incorrect conjunction, downfall, and incorrect notion. These eight elements are what give rise to life on Earth. A brief description of an early Sāmkhya philosophy is given in these aspects. Next, Arāda talked about the satkaryavada, pramāṇa-s, and padārthas. Padarthās, pramāṇa-s, the theory of causation, the theory of gunas, the establishment of the multiplicity of the self, the theory of change, and the theory of liberation are among the key components of the Sāmkhya system.

Buddhacarita deals with the early form of Sāmkhya philosophy. Asvagoṣa describes in Buddhacarita only padarthas, theory of guana-s, threefold misery, ignorance liberation etc. The theory of Kṣetrajña in and eight factors of worldly existence can be only seen in Buddhacarita. Sage Arada is the Sāmkhya philosopher who appears in Buddhacarita. The idea of freedom, however, it is impossible for Puruṣa to go free even after one hundred births if it was truly bound, as true bondage is permanent.

So, the comparison of early and later Sāmkhya philosophy shows the similarity of twenty-five principles, Pramāṇa-s and Gunas, liberation etc. The early Sāmkhya philosophy particularly discussed points of Kṣetrajña and eight factors of existence, ignorance. Sage Arada's discourse represents early sarmkhya philosophy. It can be said that Arada's darśana, the 12th chapter of Buddhacarita is a source of information about the early phase of sarmkhya philosophy.

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Mahāśvetā Vṛttānta of Kadambari: A Literary Study

Dr. Kiran A. U.¹

Abstract

This paper explores the *Mahāśvetā Vṛttānta*, a significant narrative section within *Kadambari*, the renowned Sanskrit prose composition by *Bāṇabhaṭṭa*. Known for his vivid imagination and intricate storytelling, *Bāṇa* presents a tale rich in emotional and philosophical depth. The story focuses on the intense and complex relationship between *Mahāśvetā* and *Puṇḍarīka*, highlighting themes such as inner conflict, divine love, and human vulnerability. *Mahāśvetā*'s emotional struggle and *Puṇḍarīka*'s inability to reconcile ascetic ideals with earthly desire are presented with remarkable psychological realism. *Bāṇa*'s literary style varies to suit the tone and subject, skillfully employing the *Pāñcālī*, *Vaidarbhī*, and *Utkalikā* modes to enhance the emotional and descriptive texture of the narrative. Drawing inspiration from the lost *Brhatkathā*, *Bāṇa* transforms the material into a layered and captivating prose masterpiece. His control over language, ability to evoke mood, and use of similes and metaphors demonstrate his unmatched literary artistry. The *Mahāśvetā Vṛttānta* stands out for its lyrical beauty, emotional resonance, and philosophical insight. It exemplifies how prose in Sanskrit, though rare and demanding, can attain a poetic quality that rivals verse. The paper concludes by affirming *Bāṇabhaṭṭa*'s enduring contribution to Sanskrit literature through his stylistic innovation and narrative brilliance.

Keywords: *Mahāśvetā Vṛttānta*, *Bāṇabhaṭṭa*, *Puṇḍarīka*, *Kadambari*, *Pāñcālī*, *Vaidarbhī*, *Brhatkathā*, *Utkā-*

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likā, Sanskrit Literature.

Introduction

Mahāśvetā Vṛttānta forms a vital part of Kadambari, the renowned prose work by Bāṇabhaṭṭa, noted for its intricate and complex plot. Bāṇa's style is marked by dense, layered narration, where each event builds upon the next like ascending steps, culminating in a climax that reveals the story's essence. Sanskrit prose is broadly classified into *kathā* and *ākhyāna*. A *kathā* is fictional and imaginative, written in prose, though it may include verses in *vṛtta* metres such as *āryā*, *vaktra*, or *aparavaktra*.

Often, these works begin with an invocatory verse (*maṅgalācaraṇa*) and a historical overview of the *kāvya* tradition.

Kathāyāṁ sarasaṁ vastu gadyaireva vinirmitam
Kvacidatra bhavedāryā kvacit vaktrāpavaktrake
Adau padyairnamaskāraḥ khalādervṛttakīrtanam.
(Sāhityadarpaṇa, 6.332–333)

Unlike an *ākhyāna*, which is grounded in historical fact, Kadambari exemplifies the *kathā* genre, while *Harṣacarita* stands as a classic *ākhyāna*. Both are seminal works in Sanskrit prose. Bāṇabhaṭṭa, court poet of King Harṣavardhana (ruler of Kānyakubja from 610–650 CE), included autobiographical notes and reflections on poets like Vyāsa, Bhāsa, Kālidāsa, Cora, Bhaṭṭarahaṛicandra, and Pravaṛṣeṇa in the introduction to *Harṣacarita*. Yet, it is Kadambari that secured his lasting fame. Believed to have been completed by his son Bhūṣaṇabhaṭṭa, it tells of Candrāpīḍa of Ujjayinī and Kadambari, alongside the touching tale of Puṇḍarīka and Mahāśvetā, ending in reunion after lifetimes. Bāṇa's major works include: Kadambari, *Harṣacarita*, *Candīśataka*, *Pārvatīpariṇaya*, and *Mukuṭaṭṭāḍika*.

Kadambari from a Literary Perspective

Kadambari occupies a unique place in Sanskrit literature. Its name, also synonymous with '*madirā*' or intoxicating drink, reflects the work's literary richness. Every description enhances this flavour, immersing readers in

its narrative world. It is often said that those who truly immerse themselves in the essence of *Kadambari* lose interest even in food. *Kādambarī rasañjñānam āhāro'pi na riñchate*. Another traditional saying claims that it was none other than the goddess *Sarasvatī* who manifested herself in the form of Bāṇa. *Vāñī bāṇo babhūva*. Bāṇa's prose is filled with vibrancy and a youthful energy. His literary style is grand and majestic, marked by boldness and vitality. This distinctive style is not easily imitated, and perhaps that is why he has been referred to as *Pañcānana*. *Bāṇas tu pañcananaḥ* It is also said that *Kadambari* has, at times, even rendered poets speechless. *Yuktaṃ kādambarīśrutvā kavayo maunam āśritāḥ* (*Kīrtikaumudī*).

The core narrative of *Kadambari* is believed to derive from the *Bṛhatkathā* of *Guṇādhya*, now lost but preserved in later works like *Bṛhatkathāmañjarī*, *Kathāsaritsāgara*, and *Avantisundarikathā*, through Bāṇa's imaginative treatment, it became far more captivating. Sanskrit prose is rare, largely due to the difficulty of composing in the language. There is a popular saying that prose is the *touchstone* of a poet's skill. *Gadyaṃ kavīnāṃ nikaṣaṃ vadanti*. Prose composition demands command over language, grammar, Vedic and *Purāṇic* knowledge, and poetic imagination, all of which Bāṇa possessed. A seasoned traveler with vast experience, he depicted life's richness so vividly that readers remain astonished, justifying the tribute '*Bāṇociṣṭaṃ jagat sarvaṃ*'.

Bāṇabhaṭṭa's Poetic Skill

Bāṇabhaṭṭa, often called '*Turaṅgabāṇa*' for his vivid portrayal of the horse *Indrayūdhā*, blends graceful language, knowledge, and poetic richness in his emotionally powerful prose. His characters embody specific ideals. *Śukanāsa* represents loyalty to the king. *Tārāpīḍa* shows deep trust in his ministers. Female characters like *Vilāsavatī*, *Manoramā*, '*Mahāśvetā*, and *Kadambarī* reflect noble and virtuous Indian womanhood. The description of *Acchodasaras* and the

scene of *Candrāpīḍa* meeting *Mahāśvetā* at *Siddhakṣetra* are especially moving. *Kadambarī* stands out for its originality, multi-life narrative, and use of “story within a story”. After Bāṇa’s death, *Bhūṣaṇabhaṭṭa* completed the story with the intent to finish the narrative, not imitate his father’s style. The *Mahāśvetā Vṛttānta* is the most emotionally powerful part of the work, showcasing Bāṇa’s creativity, compelling narration, and fresh vocabulary. While describing *Mahāśvetā*’s beauty, the poet draws comparisons from every realm, from the skies to *Pātāla*. He uses a wide range of similes and imagery.

“ratimiva madana -deha-nimittam hara-prasādanārtha
māgrhītamhara -ārāghanām Kṣīrodadhi- devatāmiva indu-
mūrti iva. (Kādambarī, Mahāśvetāvṛttānta, p. 3)

The introduction of Puṇḍarīka is also narrated in a delightful manner. A notable feature of the Mahāśvetā Vṛttānta is its psychological depth. When Mahāśvetā first sees Puṇḍarīka, the subtle beginning of love is portrayed with sensitivity, reflecting Bāṇa’s insight into silent, internal emotions. Kāmadeva stirs her heart, leading to emotional conflict between desire and societal expectations like family duty and loyalty. While Mahāśvetā’s love is deeply emotional, Puṇḍarīka’s response is more physical. The story’s second part highlights love and separation, especially in Mahāśvetā’s grief after Puṇḍarīka’s death, expressing universal sorrow. Later, Kapiñjala warns Puṇḍarīka that love without self-control, driven by desire alone, is not acceptable.

Character Portrayal in Mahāśvetā Vṛttānta

Puṇḍarīka, a key secondary hero in *Kadambarī*, is the beloved of *Mahāśvetā* and son of the sage *Śvetaketu*. In a past life, he was *Vaiśampāyana*, son of *Śukanāsa*, minister of *Ujjayinī*. His name reflects his divine origin, as he is born from the gods’ creative will. With noble character and radiant beauty, he captivates even the innocent and pure-hearted *Mahāśvetā*. She herself describes his appearance as

*“Alaṅkāṁiva brahmacaryasya
 Yauvanamiva dharmasya
 Vilāsaṁiva Sarasvatyāḥ
 Svayaṁvara-patimiva sarvavidyānām
 Saṅketa-sthānamiva sarvaśrutīnām
 Atimano-haraṁ ... munikumārakam apaśyat”*

(Kādambarī, Mahāśvetāvṛttānta, pp. 48-49)

Puṇḍarīka, though lean from intense meditation, remains strikingly attractive. Born from *Lakṣmī*, who was stirred by desire for *Śvetaketu*, he is raised under strict discipline. Yet, he cannot suppress his emotions and is deeply drawn to *Mahāśvetā*. Neither his father’s control nor *Kapiñjala*’s warnings can divert him from the path chosen by his heart.

In both beauty and wealth, *Puṇḍarīka* is said to rival *Kāmadeva*. “Tathākāra-tiriktārūpa-raśiḥ makarakeṭuḥ utpāditaḥ”. His aura is even said to challenge the brilliance of the sun. “Ātma-tejasā vijitya savitāram”(Mahāśvetāvṛttānta, p. 48). Like a flame that flickers in the wind, the spiritual calm of the sage is disturbed by the captivating presence of *Mahāśvetā*. Overcome by intense desire, he does not even notice when the *parāśu* (axe) slips from his hand. For a young ascetic, such thoughts and actions, such as offering a garland to an unknown maiden are considered inappropriate. This moment reveals a significant weakness in his character.

*“Sakhe puṇḍarīka naetad anurūpaṁ bhavataḥ
 Kṣudra-jana-kṣunna eṣa mārgaḥ”*(Kādambarī,
 Mahāśvetāvṛttānta, p. 71)

Puṇḍarīka is spiritually trained, he cannot control his passion, leading to his downfall. So intense is his desire that he drops the *aḥṣamālā*, his heart filled only with *Mahāśvetā*. This emotion continues through his rebirths as *Vaiśampāyana* and later a parrot. Yet his love is not shallow, it reflects emotional sincerity, maturity, and deep commitment. This emotional depth is evident when he sends a letter through *Tāralikā*, saying “Me mānasa-janma tvayā dūraṁ nītaḥ”(Kādambarī, Mahāśvetāvṛttānta, p. 120). Through this message, he clearly states his feelings and expresses his intentions with openness and sincerity.

Style of Bāṇabhaṭṭa

According to Rājaśekhara, the literary style of Bāṇabhaṭṭa is categorized as Pāñcālī. “Mādhurya-saukumārya-upapannā Pāñcālī” (Kāvya-lāṅkārasūtravṛtti, 1.1.23). Rājaśekhara explains that Pāñcālī is a style in which words are harmoniously aligned with meaning. “Śabdārthayoḥ samo gumphaḥ pāñcālīr iti iṣyate”. Bāṇa adapts his language to the subject, using elaborate vocabulary for intense themes and soft, direct words for gentle ones. For example, the wild Vindhya forests are described vividly, while Puṇḍarīka and Mahāśvetā are portrayed with delicate refinement. He skillfully varies his style and often employs the Vaidarbhī style, which is characterized by short words, minimal compounds, and a gentle tone in emotionally sensitive scenes. An example can be found when Kapiñjala finds it difficult to advise Puṇḍarīka, and says, “Sakhe puṇḍarīka na etad anurūpaṁ bhavataḥ” (Kādambarī, Mahāśvetāvṛttānta, p. 71). The message is conveyed simply: “This path is not right for you. It leads toward ruin through the influence of trivial distractions. A sage must be filled with patience.” This form of expression, free from heavy compounds, allows for a natural emotional flow and enhances the sincerity of the message. Another use of Vaidarbhī can be seen in the advice given by Śukanāsa about Lakṣmī, where it is said, “Na paricayaṁ rakṣati na abhijanāṁ ikṣate, Na rūpaṁ ālokayate” (Kādambarī, Śukanānopadeśa, p. 320). The character is described with subtle critique: “She is not protecting her dignity. She does not glance at her own navel. She is not concerned with her appearance.” The same stylistic approach appears in the laments of Mahāśvetā and Kapiñjala, where the pain of loss is expressed with emotional clarity and linguistic simplicity.

Bāṇa’s use of the Utkalikā style, marked by grandeur, compound words, and idiomatic expressions, stands out in royal, natural, and divine themes. No other Sanskrit writer matches his mastery of this style. He often compresses complex visuals or emotions into a single phrase, such as gauravarṇa for Mahāśvetā, blending divine and earthly beauty. For female characters like Cāṇḍalakanyā, Queen Vilāsavatī, Patralekhā, Mahāśvetā, and Kadambarī, he effectively uses the softer Vaidarbhī style. His portrayal of the nun Mahāśvetā is

particularly noteworthy.

*“Trayīmiva kaliyuga-dvasta-dharma-śoka-
grhītavān avasām Dehavatīmiva muni-jana-
dhyāna-sampadamDharma-hrdayādiva nirgatam”.*
(Kādambarī, Mahāśvetāvṛttānta, pp. 4–5)

Conclusion

Bāṇabhaṭṭa’s creative power in Sanskrit literature is marked by his extraordinary command over language and a vast, vivid vocabulary. His words seem to respond effortlessly to his creative impulse, always perfectly placed. Each line reveals fresh arrangements, with sound, character, and meaning woven together to create a rhythmic, resonant prose that captivates the reader. Given this mastery, it is no surprise that Dharmadāsa praised him in such terms:

*“Rucira-svara-varṇa-pathā rasa-bhāvavati jagan-
mano-harati Sā kim taruṇī? Nahi nahi, vāṇī bāṇasya
madhura-śīlasya”.* (Ācārya Dharmadāsa)

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Sanskrit Loan Words in Sangam Literature: A Cultural Revisit

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Abstract

This study delves into the intricate dynamics of linguistic borrowing in Sangam Literature, particularly the integration of Sanskrit loan words into Old Tamil, through an analysis of diverse terms, it becomes evident that these borrowings are not direct but occur in the form of Tatbhavam, showcasing a linguistic adaptation process. Predominantly nouns, such as Aariyar and Acokam, are identified as borrowed, while verbs remain absent. This linguistic exchange is explored within the broader context of the Akam and Puram concept, emphasizing the cultural influences and highlighting the absence of significant structural changes in Old Tamil. The study reveals a nuanced interaction, hinting at the adoption of Vedic culture rather than a consciously engineered phenomenon.

Key Words: Sangam Literature, Sanskrit Loan Words, Tatbhavam, Akam and Puram Concept, Linguistic Borrowing, Cultural Synthesis

Introduction

Sangam Literature stands as the earliest literary treasure trove of South India, casting a radiant light on the prehistory of this ancient region. While its primary purpose is to offer a glimpse into the rich tapestry of pure literature, the profound significance of Sangam Literature extends far beyond mere poetic expression. Within its verses, one can discern intricate threads of cultural, historical, and linguistic nuances, enabling a meticulous reconstruction of the ancient legacy that characterizes the southern expanse of India. The term

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“Sangam” itself, with its academy of writers, underscores the collaborative and scholarly nature of this literary endeavour.

Comprising two distinguished literary anthologies, Ettuthokai and Paththuppattu, Sangam literature unfolds like a delicate manuscript, revealing the diverse hues of an ancient civilization. Ettuthokai, a compilation of eight anthologies, and Paththuppattu, featuring ten extensive poems by various poets, together form a comprehensive narrative that spans the multifaceted dimensions of life in ancient Tamizhakam.

The canvas of Sangam Literature is painted by the quills of numerous writers hailing from different corners of the Chera, Chozha, and Pandya kingdoms. Their collective contributions infuse the literature with a regional richness, offering a mosaic of perspectives that enrich our understanding of the socio-cultural milieu of the time.

Thematically, Sangam Literature delves into a myriad of subjects, offering glimpses into the generosity exhibited by diverse chieftains and kings, the intricacies of human affection and love, vivid descriptions of warfare, poetic musings on the beauty and grandeur of nature, and a host of other topics.

The Akam and Puram concept in Sangam literature plays a crucial role in understanding the poetic form and thematic divisions within the literary works of the time. This concept is elucidated in Tholkappiyam, an ancient Tamil treatise that categorizes poetry into two distinct types: Akam and Puram. These categories, while representing polar opposites, also complement each other, offering a comprehensive exploration of diverse themes.

Akam focuses on the individual, delving into the interior aspects of human experiences, emotions, and thoughts. It is associated with the feminine and explores themes of love and romantic experiences, predominantly featuring women and offering a nuanced exploration of the feminine psyche.

On the other hand, Puram shifts the focus from the individual to

the external world, exploring the exterior aspects of life, society, and the broader world. It is associated with the masculine and emphasizes elements of strength, valour, and violence. Puram poetry often centres around male characters engaged in heroic deeds, battles, and leadership roles, reflecting the societal dynamics of the Sangam period.

While Akam and Puram represent polar opposites, they complement each other, providing a comprehensive exploration of diverse themes. Akam delves into the intimate and personal, addressing subjects like love and sexual relations, while Puram engages with external realities such as wars, the role of kings, and personal virtues. Together, these categories form a dual framework that harmoniously presents the intricacies of both individual experiences and the broader external realities, offering a holistic portrayal of the human condition during the Sangam era, through its verses, Sangam Literature becomes not just a literary archive but a living testament to the multifaceted lives and experiences of the people who inhabited ancient South India. In unravelling the poetic intricacies of Sangam Literature, we embark on a journey that transcends time, connecting us intimately with the rich cultural heritage and linguistic diversity that shaped the foundations of this remarkable region.

Review of Literature

There are numerous works related to this topic. Major works are analyzed here. In S. Vaidyanathan's seminal work "Indo-Aryan Loan-Words in Old Tamil" (1971), the author delves into the linguistic intricacies of ancient India, particularly examining the extent of influence from Indo-Aryan languages on Old Tamil. Vaidyanathan identifies 53 Sanskrit words in Sangam literature, a testament to the profound impact of linguistic borrowing. The study's paramount importance lies in its multifaceted objectives, notably establishing a temporal framework to gauge the historical progression of borrowings from Indo-Aryan into Old Tamil. This temporal perspective offers crucial insights into the dynamic evolution of language and cultural interactions.

Vaidyanathan's keen analysis also emphasizes the cultural signif-

icance of borrowed words, shedding light on the nature of cultural contact between speakers of Indo-Aryan and Dravidian languages. Through a meticulous examination of meanings, the study categorizes borrowed words, discerning their predominant relevance to religious or philosophical domains. This nuanced approach enhances our understanding of the cultural dynamics inherent in linguistic borrowing.

In the foreword of this book, S. Agesthalingam points out that the author's methodology is characterized by precision and purpose, systematically documenting potential loan words in Old Tamil, specifically from Sanskrit and Middle Indo-Aryan languages. By considering Middle Indo-Aryan languages, the study acknowledges the intricate linguistic interactions in ancient India. Vaidyanathan intriguingly suggests the possibility of Sanskrit borrowing from early native languages like Munda, proposing a reciprocal linguistic exchange (04).

Beyond its scholarly rigor, "Indo-Aryan Loan-Words in Old Tamil" holds broader implications for historical linguistic and cultural studies. The meticulous cataloguing of loan words and the thoughtful consideration of their cultural connotations make this work an invaluable resource for researchers, linguists, and historians. Vaidyanathan's contribution stands commendable in advancing our understanding of linguistic evolution and cultural interplay in ancient India.

K. Unnikadavu's work, "Tamil Culture in Sangam Literature" (2007), serves as an insightful exploration into the cultural landscape of Tamilnadu during the Sangam period. The author argues, with illustrative examples, that Aryan culture has been ingrained in Tamilnadu since ancient times, influencing the Sangam literary works. While the study primarily focuses on cultural cues, it does not extensively delve into linguistic evidence.

In the preface of this book, I. V. Das states, "A key thesis of Unnikadavu's work challenges traditional Tamil scholarly beliefs, positing that 'The Ancient Tamil culture is only a regional variant of Indian culture.'" This standpoint refutes orthodox notions that Ary-

an and Dravidian cultures are entirely distinct. The book's contents comprise an introduction to literary sections such as Pathupattu, Ettuthokai, and Pathinnkeezhu Kanakattu, exploring the works included therein. The first chapter examines idols and cults, including Mayon, Cheon, Kottavai, and Varuna. The second chapter sheds light on Vedic rituals, while the third chapter delves into the concept of Eka Bharata, astronomy, Tachu Shastra or Vasthu Sasthra (Science of Architecture), and societal aspects such as prostitution and feudalism (09).

Unnikadavu's comprehensive examination of Tamil culture in the Sangam period, though primarily cultural in focus, contributes valuable perspectives to the ongoing discourse on the interplay between Aryan and Dravidian influences in ancient Tamil Nadu. In addition to the studies mentioned earlier, this investigation revisits previous discussions and explores the reasons behind the occurrence of these specific loan words.

Influence of Sanskrit Language

Sanskrit language a connecting bridge between in languages, because that much of Sanskrit influence happened in other Indian languages. In Sangam Literature there are several words are used instead of Tamil words. Some words are listed here.

Aariyar (The kings of Andhra): The term "Aariyar" suggests a connection to the Andhra kings, highlighting historical and political interactions between the Tamil and Andhra regions, mentioned in Akananuru 276-9

Acokam (Saraca indica, the Asoka tree): The use of "Acokam" to refer to the Asoka tree reflects the influence of botanical and cultural exchanges, indicating awareness and integration of flora from different regions. Mentioned in Kaliththokai 57-12.

Ankam (Body): The adoption of "Ankam" for "body" exemplifies the assimilation of anatomical terminology, showcasing the influence of Sanskrit in enriching the Tamil lexicon, mentioned in Akananuru 137-1.

Antharam (Sky): The term “Antharam” for “Sky” demonstrates the incorporation of cosmological concepts, illustrating a cross-cultural exchange in understanding celestial phenomena. Mentioned in Thirumurukattupatai 119.

Iyakkan (Yaksha): The term “Iyakkan” signifies the inclusion of mythological entities like Yaksha, indicating a shared cultural and religious heritage between Sanskrit and Tamil traditions, mentioned in Purananuru 71-14.

Kalam (Pot): The use of “Kalam” for “pot” showcases the integration of everyday vocabulary, suggesting that common household items were influenced by Sanskrit terminology (in Sanskrit Kala-sha). Mentioned in Purananuru 228-1.

Kankai (River Ganges): The reference to “Kankai” for the Ganges highlights the geographical and cultural awareness, illustrating the assimilation of river names from different regions. Mentioned in Perumpanaarupatai 431.

Maakam (Month, Sky): The term “Maakam” reflects the incorporation of temporal concepts, indicating the influence of Sanskrit in describing time and celestial phenomena. Mentioned in Maturaikkaanchi 454, Purananuru 60, 400

Manam (Mind): The use of “Manam” for “mind” showcases the assimilation of psychological terms, indicating a shared understanding of mental processes, mentioned in Purananuru 183-4 and Thirumurukattupatai 90.

Mangala (Auspicious): The term “Mangala” emphasizes the adoption of auspiciousness, reflecting the integration of religious and cultural values into Tamil literature. Mentioned in Purananuru 332

Mani (Gem): The term “Mani” in Purananuru 56 and Porunaraarupatai 21 denotes a gem. This reflects the assimilation of aesthetic and precious elements into Tamil culture, indicating an appreciation for valuable objects and possibly trade connections involving gemstones.

Mukam (Face): “Mukam,” found in Pathittuppaththu -73 and Purananuru 207-4, is used for “face.” The inclusion of this term suggests an enriched vocabulary for describing facial features, indicating a shared aesthetic sense and emphasis on facial expressions in both Sanskrit and Tamil traditions.

Pali (A Ball of Rice): Found in Porunaraarruppatai 183, Pathittuppaththu 179, Purananuru 52, 143, 329, 331, 363, “Pali” refers to a ball of rice. This term demonstrates the integration of culinary vocabulary, possibly reflecting shared culinary practices or regional food exchanges as well as cultural practices.

Pataakai (Flag): Mentioned in Pathittuppaththu 182, “Pataakai” signifies a flag. The adoption of this term points towards the incorporation of military and symbolic elements into Tamil culture, potentially reflecting historical interactions and influences.

Punniyam (Good Deeds): Found in Pathittuppaththu 204, “Punniyam” refers to good deeds. This term reflects the incorporation of moral and ethical concepts into Tamil literature, suggesting a shared understanding of virtuous actions and values.

Puruvam (Eye-brow): Appearing in Porunaraarruppatai 26, “Puruvam” is used for “eyebrow.” This term showcases the assimilation of anatomical terms, indicating a shared vocabulary for describing physical features.

Tantu (Stick): Referenced in Kurunthokai 156-3, “Tantu” denotes a stick. The inclusion of this term suggests the integration of tools and everyday objects into the Tamil lexicon, reflecting practical aspects of daily life.

Ticai (Direction): Found in Pathittuppaththu-2, “Ticai” refers to direction. This term showcases the inclusion of spatial concepts, indicating a shared understanding of navigation and orientation.

Tuumam (Smoke): Mentioned in Purananuru 117-1, “Tuumam” refers to smoke. The use of this term reflects the integration of environmental and elemental concepts, possibly indicating shared experiences related to fire and ritual practices.

Ulaku (World): Found in Purananuru 107-4 and Porunaraar-
ruppatai 176, “Ulaku” denotes the world. This term reflects a shared
cosmological understanding, suggesting a common worldview that
transcends linguistic boundaries.

Vaanika (Merchant): Appearing in Purananuru 134-2 and 208-7,
“Vaanika” refers to a merchant. The inclusion of this term points to-
wards economic and trade interactions, showcasing the integration
of commercial activities into Tamil culture.

Viccai (Learning): Mentioned in Kaliththokai 119-4, “Viccai” de-
notes learning. This term (vidya in Sanskrit) reflects the assimilation
of educational concepts, indicating a shared emphasis on knowledge
acquisition and intellectual pursuits.

The analysis of these words reveals the dynamic exchange of cul-
tural, aesthetic, culinary, military, moral, anatomical, practical, spa-
tial, elemental, cosmological, economic, and educational elements
between Sanskrit and Tamil cultures during ancient times. The
assimilation of these loan words enriches the Old Tamil language,
illustrating the depth of historical interactions and shared experi-
ences between the two linguistic traditions. These examples collec-
tively illustrate the depth and diversity of Sanskrit loan words in Old
Tamil, providing valuable insights into the historical, cultural, and
linguistic interplay between the two ancient civilizations.

Analysis

Upon a detailed analysis of these words, it becomes evident that
they are not direct borrowings from Sanskrit into Old Tamil. In-
stead, they appear in the form of Tatbhavam in Sangam Literature.
Tatbhavam is a linguistic method employed when Sanskrit words
enter Tamil or other languages. In this process, if the recipient lan-
guage lacks certain letters present in Sanskrit, the Sanskrit letters are
adapted and rewritten using the letters of the receiving language.
This linguistic transformation is the mechanism through which each
of these words has integrated into Sangam works from Sanskrit.

Grammatical scrutiny reveals that the majority of these borrowed
words are nouns, exemplified by terms such as Aariyar (referring to

the kings of Andhra), Acokam (indicating *Saraca indica*, the Asoka tree), Maakam (related to Month and sky), Mukam (denoting Face), and Pali (signifying a ball of rice). Interestingly, verbs cannot be identified among these borrowings. The influx of nouns from another language into Tamil is a natural linguistic phenomenon, and such changes occur as a result of language interactions or cultural synthesis.

However, the absence of borrowed verbs in Sangam literature is notable. The introduction of verbs from another language would signify a more profound shift in the organized structure of the language, indicating a subservience to that language. This absence suggests that the structure of Old Tamil remained intact and was not significantly influenced by Sanskrit in terms of verbs.

The nouns mentioned in this context have come into existence primarily when elements rooted in the broader Indian Vedic culture are introduced into poetry. In essence, these terms provide hints of an Aryan culture. Few words enter through adjectives or in other poetic contexts, but the majority originate in situations associated with Sanskrit or Aryan culture. Poets of that era incorporated these words for accurate representation, emphasizing their necessity in conveying the intended meaning within the context of their works. Notably, many of these borrowed words are proper nouns, such as *Iyakkan* (Yakshan), indicating that the influence of Sanskrit words in Sangam works is more of an intrusion necessitated by the adoption of Vedic culture rather than a consciously created phenomenon.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study on linguistic borrowing in Sangam Literature, focusing on the integration of Sanskrit loan words into Old Tamil, reveals several key findings. The borrowed words, predominantly nouns, undergo a linguistic adaptation process known as *Tatbhavam*, indicating a nuanced interaction between Sanskrit and Old Tamil. The absence of significant structural changes in Old Tamil, particularly in the realm of verbs, highlights the cultural influences without compromising the language's core structure.

The influence of Sanskrit on Sangam Literature is evident in the borrowed words used, ranging from terms related to Andhra kings (Aariyar) to elements of nature (Acokam) and mythological entities (Iyakkan). These borrowings reflect a dynamic exchange of cultural, aesthetic, and economic elements, enriching the Old Tamil language. The analysis unveils the depth of historical interactions and shared experiences between Sanskrit and Tamil cultures.

Further analysis of the borrowed words highlights the linguistic method of Tatbhavam, wherein Sanskrit words are adapted into Tamil, primarily manifesting as nouns. The absence of borrowed verbs suggests that Old Tamil's structural integrity remained intact, indicating that the linguistic influence was more a result of the adoption of Vedic culture than a deliberate restructuring of the language.

This study reveals key insights, highlighting the borrowing of certain terms when incorporating mythological contexts into poetry, particularly relying on Sanskrit terminology. This practice becomes evident when integrating Puranic narratives into poetic compositions. Additionally, Sanskrit words are employed in discussions related to astrological information, emphasizing the prevalence of the Vedic astrological tradition in South India. In contrast, when referencing crucial rivers and natural elements in North India, Sanskrit words are adopted. Furthermore, in discussions involving Jyotisha (astronomy), Sanskrit terms find application, suggesting the existence of Vedic astronomy in South India (E.g. Maaka Month). The borrowing of Sanskrit words is also notable in conversations about major rivers in North India and other natural phenomena. In ritualistic contexts, Sanskrit words are employed as well (E.g. Pali (Rice ball)) If these terms are substituted for non-Tamil words, Sangam works reveal the incorporation of popular Sanskrit terms, especially in passages describing warfare. (E.g. Mukham)

In summary, the majority of these borrowed terms are specifically used when discussing Vedic culture. In essence, this study contributes to a comprehensive understanding of the intricate dynamics of linguistic borrowing in Sangam Literature, shedding light on the cultural, historical, and linguistic tapestry of ancient South India.

The assimilation of Sanskrit loan words serves as a testament to the rich interplay of languages and cultures, preserving the essence of the Sangam era within the linguistic fabric of Old Tamil.

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Early Manipravalam literature and Malayalam metres

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Key words- The rhythmic creation - Malayalam metres- Sanskrit metres- Dravidian Culture-Champu literature-achich-aritams-matras- ganas- quantity of time taken for utterance-mode of reciting.

Cholvadivu, the mode of reciting, enhances the audience's understanding and enjoyment of the poem. It lays the foundation for the appreciation of the beauty of the poem. As metre or Vrttam , an important element of literature is a way of measuring a line of poetry based on the rhythm of the words, the study of metre (Vrttasatram) is prepared on the basis of the similarity of the varied modes of singing and by considering aksharasanghya(number of syllables) and mathrasanghya(quantity of time taken for utterance). At the beginning, human beings relied on rich and varied oral literature, the earliest form of literature which is being told from word of mouth rather than written literature, thus it can be said that it is poetry, the rhythmic creation of beauty in words, not prose, came first. Rhythmic sentences look good to the eyes and sound pleasing to the ears which roll off the tongue so that people will remember it.

As poetry is an attribute of nature which has a rhythm of its own, poetry cannot exist without rhythm that creates the tone for the poem. In Malayalam language, Sanskrit and Malayalam metres are quite popular today. A great variety can be seen in the metrical

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composition and in the matra system (time taken for utterance - the music is produced by means of stressing the sound after the lapse of a definite period measured by time moments) of Malayalam metres, thus the study of these metres remains incomplete. On closer examination, it is found that many of the cholvadvu of Sanskrit metres appear to be the same as the native melodies found in folk songs. This makes it all the more important to study Malayalam metres in detail and the history of this metrical composition throws light upon the rich heritage of Dravidian Culture. The presence of Dravidian mode of reciting in Champu³ poetry shows the rich old heritage of Dravidian metres and its popularity too.

Malayalam language has identified its existence with the help of Sanskrit and Tamil. It is the supremacy of Sanskrit during the time of Manipravalam literature that led to the degradation of what was written in Malayalam by calling it as prose. Uddandan⁴, a Sanskrit poet, even despised our Malayalam and the Malayalam poets.

‘bhashakavinivahoyam
doshakaravadwibhathi bhuvanathale
prayena vrithaheena
sooryaloke nirasthagoprasara

Uddanda compares the Malayalam poets to a malefic moon since their poems have no metres. Comparing the Sanskrit poets to the Sun, Uddanda adds that Malayalam poetry is quite weak and afflicted like a malefic moon which will not shine in the sight of the Sun. However, the Malayalam poets of that time could do nothing but just

3 Champu&Champu prose- Though it is considered as the poetic form of Manipravalam literature, it is a combination of prose and poetry. Generally the story is written in verse and the descriptive portion is found in prose. The verse portion is written in Sanskrit while the prose portion is mostly in Malayalam. The early Manipravalam prose is rhythmic. But in later Manipravalam, many prose portions without metre can also be found.

4 . Uddhandan-A South Indian scholar, hailed from Kancheepuram who has made an invaluable contribution to Sanskrit language and literature. He is said to have lived around 15 CE. He is one of the most famous among the renowned ‘Patinettara Kavikal’ (18 1/2 poets or scholars) of the royal court of Saamoothiri. He arrived in Kerala and was received with the traditional hospitality of Saamoothiri. Thus he continued to stay here most of his life. Kokilasandesham and Mallikamaarutham are his best known works.

bow down to Uddanda's arrogance"5. Our own mode of reciting, which we can call it Dravidian metre or Malayalam metre, the Malayalam poets have applied these in the prose of Champus, though it is said to be prose, it is a fragment of rhymed verse. Since these Dravidian metres were considered as unworthy of being lifted to the exalted domain of poetry, these were shrunk into the status of prose. Recognizing the beauty of these Dravidian metres and the language of prose, in later studies it is found that the Malayalam metre is embedded in them. The prototypes of the most of the praised Dravidian metres can be found in early Mani-pravalam literature.

In the first parts of Unniacharitham, the shades of Tarangini, Irattatarangini, Panchachamaram, Induvadana, Kakali and Nathonnatha metres can be noted. Of these, the most important and widely used meter is Tarangini. In the sixth prose the matra system and the rhythmic system are matched perfectly.

Mahithakaleswara sakaleswaranuda
thirumidiyilkkudipoovaanupanatha⁶

Tharangini⁷ consists of eight ganas(feet) of two mathras(the quantity of time taken for utterance) each. Shades of Tarangini can be seen in 2,4,15,16,20,21 and 27 prose of Unniyacharitham. Some prose pieces are in Kakali.

Pinneottangane chentavaremuha
Pinnalottedamummunnalottedemum⁸ (Prose 13)

5. Malayalamsahithyam kalakhattangaliloode-prof. Erumeli Parameswaran pillai, corrent books, 6th edition, 2007, page 119
6. Unniyacharitham-Study by Prof. Mukhathala Gopalakrishnan, the language institute of kerala, Thiruvananthapuram,3rd edition, 2011, page 13
7. Tharangini-Tarangini is the metre par excellence of Oṭṭan Tullal. A stanza consists of any number of couplets. Each line of the couplet contains eight to sixteen syllables forming sixteen mātrās in all. The second and the third matras, the fourth and the fifth and so on (even and odd mātrās) should not be combined into a guru, though the first and the second, the third and the fourth, and so on (odd and even mātrās) may be combined so. Therefore a line has been divided into eight feet of two mātrās each by A. R. Rajaraja Varma. A line will have two equal halves, and yati (caesura) should be observed between these halves; but in practice it is often violated.(A History of Malayalam Meters - N.V. Krishna Varier , First Published in 1977, Dravidian Linguistics Association, Trivandrum, page 213, 214)
8. Unniyacharitham-Study by Prof. Mukhathala Gopalakrishnan, the language institute of kerala, Thiruvananthapuram,3rd edition, 2011, page 38

It is a perfect example of prose where Kakali lakshanam(definition) and cholvadivu (the mode of reciting) coincide with each other. The metre in this passage is Kakali which consists of eight feet of five matras in three syllables. There are many more prose pieces where the shades of Kakali can be found in their cholvadivu. Along with Kakali, the presence of Keka⁹ can also be identified in Unniyachi.

paramapurushanude panchajanyatheyum
parththontikkumapparilasalgashikha¹⁰

It has fourteen syllables in the order-three,two,two; three,two,two. Though the first three feet of the first part and the fifth foot of the second part do not observe the rule of Keka ie. atleast one long syllable (guru) must be there in each foot , it is very much similar to Keka.

Shades of Natonnata¹¹ and Athisthimitha can also be found.The very first verse of Unniyachi can be recited in Natonnata, though the cholvadivu and aksharasanghya resemble Natonnata, these lines do not observe the rule, “guru thane ezhuthellam”(every syllable must be long). Some prose pieces are constructed in Athisthimitha, the metre which is less frequently used in Malayalam though it has a clear rhythmic structure.

varamallikaadhavala varinellilamkazhama

9. Keka is a couplet and must have six feet in each line, the first foot and the fourth having three syllables each and the rest having two syllables each. All the feet must contain at least one long syllable(guru). Yati (cesura) should be observed after the third foot in each line. The first syllables in both lines of a couplet should be of the same length (i. e. both should be either short or long).
10. Unniyachicharitham-Study by Prof. Mukhathala Gopalakrishnan, the language institute of kerala, Thiruvananthapuram,3rd edition, 2011, page 4
11. Nathonnatha This metre is popularly known as Vañchippattu, as most of the boat-songs, including Kuchelavruttam of Ramapurattu Variyar, Vyasotpatti of unknown authorship and Kirātam of Kuñcan Nampiyar are written in this metre. Here also the couplet is the unit. The first line has eight feet, each of two syllables. Each line may be divided into two hemispheres. The first hemistich of the second line is the same as either half of the first line. The second half of the second line has only three feet, the first two of two and the last of one syllable. All the syllables are to be stressed in pronunciation. 10 Each couplet may also be treated as a quatrain, the first three lines of which are of equal length,and the third line a little shorter(A History of Malayalam Meters - N.V. Krishna Varier , First Published in 1977, Dravidian Linguistics Association, Trivandrum, page.125)

marinallavaamalavu tharumallal kettavarkal¹² (Prose 3)

Not only the rhythm but the rule of Athisthimita¹³ is also incorporated in prose 3. The Sanskrit metres such as Induvadana, Panchachamaram and Sankaracharitam have also been employed in many pieces of prose.

Thalirudetharilathathalarvalanthannira
nthalaparakkintethamrojwala¹⁴ (Prose 11)

These lines seem to have the rhythm of Induvadana¹⁵, yet the observance of the rules of Induvadana is not regular here. The prose 5 and prose 28 are composed in the style of Sankaracharitam and Panchachamaram respectively.

As in Unniyachi, the author of Unnichirutevicharitham has extensively employed Tarangini metre. Proses such as 1, 4, 6, 17, 20 follow the exact structure of Tarangini. In Unnichirutevicharitham some prose passages agree with the style of Kakali though they do not observe the principle of metre construction. Prose 11 and 12 have the metre Athistimitha and the metre of prose 23 is Sthmitha.

valarmanthezhum kathali
thaliredukavunila
nilayanchamainja kali
kaliyundu padumali¹⁶ (Prose 11)

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12. Unniyachicharitham-Study by Prof. Mukhathala Gopalakrishnan, the language institute of kerala, Thiruvananthapuram, 3rd edition, 2011, page 6
 13. Atistimita-Stimita-This group is closely related to Kalenduvadana group and seems to have been derived from Miśrakākāṣi. A line consists of four feet. All the feet are quadri- syllabic, the third syllable in the odd feet and the first syllable in the even feet being long. The third foot consists of three syllables only, two long ones and one short. In the odd feet the first two short syllables have been contracted into a long syllable. Harināmakirtanam employs metres of this group. In the third foot in each line only is tri- syllabic. In the third and the fourth lines are trisyllabic. In the third foot of last line alone is trisyllabic. (A History of Malayalam Meters -N.V. Krishna Varier , First Published in 1977, Dravidian Linguistics Association, Trivandrum, page 179)
 14. Unniyachicharitham-Study by Prof. Mukhathala Gopalakrishnan, the language institute of kerala, Thiruvananthapuram, 3rd edition, 2011, page 29
 15. Induvadana - It has Bha ganam, ja ganam, sa ganam na ganam guru guru gana(feet) system
 16. Unnichiruthevi charitham-study by Prof. Sundaram dhanuvachapuram-The language institute of kerala, Thiruvananthapuram, 1st edition, 2005, page 64

Here the rule of Athistimitha is closely allied with the rhythmic pattern. Prose 23 has the principles and the rhythm of the Sthimitha metre. Cholvadivu and the metrical system are completely compatible with Athistimitha and Sthimitha. These lines are not divided according to the principle of aksharasanghya. But this problem has been resolved in Prose 19 and 23.

Sanskrit metres like Panchachamaram, Sragvini, Sankaracharitham, Todakam and Bujangaprayatam are widely used in the prose portions of Unnicchiruthevicharitham just as in Unniyachi. Out of which Panchachamaram is the most extensively used metre.

Idathupaaduchedimaar valathupaadu
Yadithalippunarkku porchilambinodelimpumi¹⁷(Prose 3)

The principle of metre exactly fits in this prose. But in Unnicchiruthi there are some prose pieces which do not observe the rule of Panchachamaram¹⁸ though compatible with its cholvadivu. Other than Panchachamaram, Sragvini¹⁹ is the most widely employed metre.

Thathsuthaseethpuna sathsabhamaanitha
lokaikavasyaoushadham nallasheelaa²⁰ (prose 8)

It can be said that the first line is exactly composed in Sragvini as it follows the principle(lakshanam). Sragvini is perfectly met with in prose 13. In both of these prose pieces no difference can be seen in the rhythm. These can be recited in the rhythm of Kakali. It is very important to note that the standard form of Kakali is 'raḡanam.

- Sankaracaritam²¹, Totakam and Bujangaprayatam have been em-
17. Unnicchiruthi charitham-study by Prof. Sundaram dhanuvachapuram-The language institute of kerala, Thiruvananthapuram,1st edition, 2005, page 31
 18. Panchachamaram - It has JA ganam,RA ganam, JA ganam,RA ganam JA ganam guru gana(feet) system
 19. Sragvini - A line of a Sragvini stanza consists of four Raganas, ie. cretic feet having a short in the middle of two longs.
 20. Unnicchiruthi charitham-study by Prof. Sundaram dhanuvachapuram-The language institute of kerala, Thiruvananthapuram,1st edition, 2005, page 79
 21. Sankaracharitham - SA ganam,NA ganam, JA ganam,NA ganam BHA ganam SA ganam - Feet system A. R. Rajarajavarma defines a stanza of sankaracharitham metre as consisting of four lines, each line having the gaṇas sa, na, ja, na, bha, sa. This metre is not defined in the Vṛttaratnākara, and is not usually met with in Sanskrit.(A History of Malayalam Meters -N.V. Krishna Varier, First

ployed in each of the stanzas of Unniccirutevicaritam.

Dwijasathmasuthodalamala
valayangalil madathodhika
madhurangalil madhurangalil
maruvum kalalapithangalil²² (Prose 9)

This prose exactly follows the rules and cholvadivu of Sankara-caritham except the one related to aksharasanghya.

valarneelamanikkulirmaamalavinnorukaalamali
njupolinjumuthichuvayittukalarnnathulolathisheela²³
(Prose 13)

It is similar to the metrical pattern of Thodakam²⁴ and the Cholvadivu exactly fits in. No other conditions of this metre are met.

Prose 15 roughly agrees with the definition of Bhujanga-prayatam²⁵ and cholvadivu is perfectly matching.

The author of Unniyachicharitham, like the other two Achicharitham writers, preferred the rhythm of Tarangini metre. Most of the prose portions are constructed in Tarangini . About ten prose pieces in perfect Tarangini metre can be found in Unniyachicharitham. Other metres found in Unniyachicharitham resemble Kakali and Sankaracharitham. Unlike other writers of achicharitham, the writer of Unniachicharitham has employed Misrakakali and Deerghatharangini metres.

nakthamangenumappaalozhinjethirave vimalajaladhu
kulicharunasandhyarucha ghusrunameya poocha²⁶ (Prose 2)

The lines quoted above cannot be fully considered as Kakali or

Published in 1977, Dravidian Linguistics Association, Trivandrum, page127)

22. Unnichiruthevi charitham-study by Prof. Sundaram dhanuvachapuram-The language institute of kerala, Thiruvananthapuram,1st edition, 2005, page 57
23. Unnichiruthevi charitham-study by Prof. Sundaram dhanuvachapuram-The language institute of kerala, Thiruvananthapuram,1st edition, 2005, page 70
24. Thodakam - A line of a Thodakam stanza consists of four Saganas, ie. cretic feet having two shorts and one long.
25. Bhujangaprayatam - consists of four YA ganas.i.e.four bacchius feet consisting of one short and two longs.
26. Unniyaadi charitham-study by Prof. Sundaram dhanuvachapuram-The language institute of kerala, Thiruvananthapuram,1st edition, 2007, page 23

Misrakakali²⁷. But the elements of Misrakakali are prominent here. Deerkhatharangini (The longer variety of Tarangini) can be seen in prose 32.

indindiraghana vrundathamobhara chandrakavatha
prabhavacharuka paali²⁸

Not much variety of metres can be seen in Unniyatcharitam. Tarangini passages are more numerous in this work rather than those of any other metre. The other metres found in Unniyachicharitham are Sankaracharitam, Kakali and Deerkhatharangini. Misrakakali, a rarely used metre can also be found in Unniyachicharitham. Tarangini is the most widely used metre in the prose pieces of early Campus. Kakali is the second most important metre seen in early Campus. It is the author of Unnichiruthevicharitam who experimented with metre by using a variety of it in which prose pieces are more in number.

The study of the history of the early period of Malayalam poetry throws light on the antiquity of the concept of Malayalam metre. Since the rhythmic movement of the known Sanskrit metres like Sankaracaritam, Totakam, Sragvini, Induvadana and Panchachamaram, is same as in our ancient literary works, it can be observed that these metres must be fairly old and the cholvadvu (the mode of reciting) is quite Dravidian. As many of the accepted Sanskrit metres seem to have a natural affinity with the Dravidian metres it can be inferred that cholvadvu is representative of a very old tradition.

Sragvini is closely linked with Kakali. The regular form of Kakali is formed when the eight syllables become 'ra' (one short in the middle of two long syllables). From the similarity between Sragvini which is formed out of four 'Raganas' and Kakali in their aksharasanghya (number of syllables) and mathrasanghya (quantity of time taken for utterance) it can be inferred that Kakali must be fairly old.

27. Misrakakali - This metre is a Kakali couplet with feet expanded at random. These expanded feet may contain four or five syllables; in the former case one syllable must be long. 172

28. Unniyaadi charitham-study by Prof. Sundaram dhanuvachapuram-The language institute of kerala, Thiruvananthapuram, 1st edition, 2007, page 186

Induvadana has some similarities with Kurathi ²⁹ Seelu (mode of reciting)
 pachamalai pavizhamalai engalmalai naadu (kurathippattu)³⁰
 pandumuthalinganevelichavumiruttum (Nishkapadathayod)³¹

According to the matra system except the fourth foot of Induvadana all the other ones are formed with four syllables as in Kurathippattu. The rhythm also fits in. Moreover the Sankaracharitham metre of Achicharitham is similar to the Dravidian cholvadivu 'Kanakachilanga'³². On closer examination, it is found that the Sanskrit metres such as Sankaracharitham, Totakam, Induvadana and Panchachamaram are not observing the rules of Sanskrit prosody most of the time. They have deviated from their Sanskrit originals. Thus it can be observed that these metres are not of Sanskrit origin but they are indigenous meters which have close resemblance to the above mentioned Sanskrit metres. If they were standard Sanskrit metres they might not be discarded as Prose. The variety of tones and rhythm used in the prose works must also be noted. With their catchy tone and inherent rhythm, these metres have lifted the work into a performing art rather than considering it as a literary piece.

Poets like Uddhandan considered Sanskrit as the most refined and superior language and they treated the writing in Sanskrit language alone as poetry. At that time the writers of Achicharitham/ Manipravalam writers, without any pretension to this classical grandeur of Sanskrit entered the domain of literature with their plain, simple but expressive poems in Malayalam. It would prove to be revolu-

29. Kurathi- This metre is not defined in Vṛttamañjari. We may divide each line into four feet, the first three of four and the fourth of two syllables, all of which, except sometimes the second syllables in the first three feet, are pronounced as long. (A History of Malayalam Meters-N.V. Krishna Varier, First Published in 1977, Dravidian Linguistics Association, Trivandrum, page 222)

30. kurathippattu - A Folk song of Kerala

31. Nishkapadathayod kumaranasan samboorna krithikal (part 2), kumaranassan. (He was a poet of Malayalam literature, Indian social reformer and a philosopher. 1873-1924), kumaranasan national institute of culture, thonnakkal, 2010, 1st edition, page 125

32. 'Kanakachilanga' This is a rhythm adapted from the folk songs of Pulaya community. This meter got its name because this rhythm was made famous by Changampuzha's (Changampuzha Krishnapillai - a romantic poet in Malayalam literature) poem KavyaNartaki. The poem starts with Kanakachilanga.

tionary because it transformed the domain of literature. Even if our language is suppressed, it will still rise and flourish, as exemplified by these Achicharithams. As G.Sankarakurup observed in Sivathan-davam it is the intrinsic quality of tone and rhythm of the poet that make him the creator of the lyrics. The inimitable forms of creation can only exist in the mind. Malayalam metres became a tool in flourishing the Malayalam language. It is the language's life itself.

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Musings on Silence: A Reading of Anees Salim's *Vanity Bagh*

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Abstract

Silence encompasses all forms of existence and is able to generate, maintain, obliterate, or modify any signifiers connected to it. Authors employ silence to convey subtle expressions of intrinsic emotions that words fail to describe. This paper attempts to analyse the role of silence in the moments of happiness, despair, anger, ambiguity, and negation, in the light of Anees Salim's novel *Vanity Bagh*. Moreover, this study explores the notion of authorial silence apart from the multifaceted impressions of silence in the novel. This paper also discusses the spatial dimension of power dynamics as projected through distinct characters in the aforementioned novel.

Keywords: Silence, Space, Discipline, Power, Resistance

Introduction

Silence is often sensed in verbal communications where both the speaker and the listener get frequent intervals of time, either long or short, to pause, contemplate, and exchange meaningful replies afterwards. Chris P. Miller states in his work "Silence" that it fills the gaps within a text and denotes a paradoxical co-existence of emptiness and abundant signifiers (Miller). The Swiss writer and philosopher Max Picard posits in his seminal work titled *World of Silence* (2006) that "Silence contains everything in itself, and it completely fills out the space in which it appears" (Picard, 2006, p. 17). Writers exploit the scope of silence and use it in their respective fields to achieve

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their desired ends. The critics conceive silence as the wordless imitation or negation of speech. Silence is an integral part of any medium of communication, as it furnishes an organic structure and a closure to the speech. Silence has the potential to create an impact by its presence, absence, and duration. The meaning of silence stands contextual and arbitrary. Renowned author Anees Salim provides a plethora of explicit and implicit instances of silence in his novel *Vanity Bagh*. The novel foregrounds its characters as either being enslaved or enchanted by the enigmatic silence. This paper aims to highlight such instances and explore the power dynamics of silence in narratives and in moments of disciplining, despair, protest, veneration, and grief.

Analysis

Anees Salim's *Vanity Bagh* depicts multiple dimensions of silence, especially the silence pertaining to power and discipline. The narrator references an account of disciplinary silence employed by the jailers over the prisoners. Imran and his friend Zia-ul-Haq are sentenced to imprisonment in connection with the blast in their neighbouring place, where the residents are predominantly Hindus. Both of them hardly meet together within the premise of the prison, as the rules there are as strict as if in Guantanamo (Salim, 2013, p. 71). The constant fear of being watched by the jail wardens restrains them from having a conversation. The gaze of the superintendent in *Vanity Bagh* silently disciplines the prisoners despite employing any violent measures. He stood under the tree, "wordlessly challenging the whistlers for an encore. No one whistled. No one so much as breathed [sic] audibly" (Salim, 2013, p. 72). The working of silence induced by disciplinary power mentioned corresponds to what Cheryl Glenn posits in her *Unspoken: Rhetoric of Silence* (2004) and the French philosopher Michel Foucault in his *Discipline and Punish* (1995, pp. 33–34).

Glenn reflects on the link between silence and the ideas of power, authorship, and agency, whereas Foucault elaborates on the nuances of silence within the realm of disciplinary space. Foucault, in *Discipline and Punish* (1995), marks the transition of obsolete traditional sovereign and episodic exercise of power to the disciplinary power that can be traced in the administrative systems and social institu-

tions like schools, prisons, and mental asylum. The new system of surveillance and evaluation urges people to conform to norms and remain self-disciplined despite any violence or coercive force. There is a contrast between the silence of the superintendent and the eventual quiescence of the prisoners in *Vanity Bagh* in terms of the exercise of power. The silence of the former has an authoritative undertone, whereas the latter resorts to a submissive silence, as they are powerless recipients of the rigorous disciplinary actions.

The surveillance cameras also alert Imran to his actions inside the prison. The inescapable disciplinary gaze of jailors, surveillance equipment, and the watch tower restricts the prisoner from behaviours that are reckoned as deviant or offensive. The power-induced silence thus ensures the disciplined participation of prisoners in the activities and events organised inside the prison. This is evidenced in Imran's words, "I, like many other inmates, was bearing with these workshopmen just because the superintendent was still watching us" (Salim, 2013, p. 37).

Apart from the jail officials, the power hegemony instigates the privileged few to employ their authority to subordinate their fellow beings. Imran's father, Kareem Jabbari, utilises his designation of the chief imam of Masjid-e-Mosavi to curb misconducts of the youth in his community. It is not only the members of his household but also the religious followers belonging there who are subjected to the harsh stare of the Imam. Imran's friends stop laughing in front of the Imam, especially when they are around the mosque (Salim, 2013, p. 20). Imran's mother also silently retreats indoors, renouncing her intention to participate in a local revolt after sensing a strong denial on Imam's face (Salim, 2013, p. 100). It is the veneration for the Imam's job that triggers silence in the first case, whereas it is the privilege of the Imam on the grounds of patriarchal norms that silences Imran's mother. Both instances reflect the involvement of male members in exercising power in society.

Salim projects the irony in women's compliance with the patriarchal rules and how they eventually end up silencing or curbing the freedom of other women as well. In *Vanity Bagh*, Zia's teenage girlfriend Aasia Jamal is under house arrest as she rejected an alliance her parents brought with a stranger who is twice her age. Her moth-

er hinders the chance for an interaction between the couple when Zia visits her family for a negotiation. Aasia's mother glares murderously at her until she disappears behind a curtain (Salim, 2013, p. 139). Her mother represents those women who are instrumental in passing on the hazardous legacy of patriarchal dogma and continue to be the blind carriers of dogmatic norms. They, being oblivious to the invisible chains of perpetual confinement, are collectively responsible for the self-imposed silence and mute compliance of other women whose voices are either muffled or left unheard.

The editors of *John Cage: Composed in America* (1994) provide John Cage's notion of silence as a counterforce to the limits of individual subjectivity or agency. They observe, "The language of silence is one that knows how to listen when the other centres act, so that it can construct itself as a reaction to the others, not only as the self-determined action of its own talking" (Perloff, 1994, p. 184).

Cage, in his work "Silence" (2007), reminisces about listening to his heartbeats in the profound silence of a vacuum chamber on his visit to Harvard University (Miller, 2007). In *Vanity Bagh*, the silence in the courtroom during the trial accentuates the sound of the clock ticking on the wall. The intermittent sound of the clock needles immediately broken by an equal amount of silence metaphorically symbolises the monotonous, empty years of imprisonment Imran should endure (Salim, 2013, p. 1). Imran's heartbeats resembling the ticking of the clock will be the only sound that would accompany him in his solitude. This implies how silence makes individuals aware of the absence of sounds and makes them more attentive, as is substantiated in Imran's account.

The absence of noise makes Imran forced to hear each sound and sight he could possibly capture within the premises of the prison. Imprisonment makes him depressed and nostalgic at the same time, and the sense of alienation makes him long to be outside. The prison cuts him off from all worldly connections he had before (Salim, 2013, p. 2). As part of adapting to a new space where there is no room for talking, Imran actively uses his audiovisual organs. He tries to find peace in solitude by enjoying outdoor jobs that could offer sounds and sights when compared to those of indoor jobs. This shows how individuals listen to voices and get fascinated by the sights that once

seemed trivial.

Of the sounds he could listen to by sitting inside the prison, Imran ranks the sound of the trucks passing by as the best one. Their sound is suggestive of the kinetic and lively world outside in contrast to the sedentary and monotonous life inside the prison. Imran remarks, “The best sight from prison is a silent aeroplane disappearing into an Everest of clouds. It makes you want to get out of prison one day and do well in life” (Salim, 2013, p. 6). However, he dreads the sight of snails as it reminds him of the sluggish years to follow (Salim, 2013, p. 7). Imran’s current state symbolises lonely people’s struggles to stay hopeful in their lives.

Imran restlessly keeps himself engaged to escape the gravity of loneliness in the prison cell. There is a contradiction between loneliness and solitude, as the tranquillity of solitude changes into an uncomfortable emptiness on its forceful imposition on the individual. The seclusion of imprisonment can be transcribed as loneliness, as it lacks the essence of composure and lightness found in solitude. Imran despises indoor jobs since the idea of remaining inside a closed circuit of rigid surveillance seems to suffocate him more than the guilt of his crime. He says, “When you are destined to live in a prison, why would you want to spend your days in another prison inside it?” (Salim, 2013, p. 7). This underlines the spatial relevance in determining the positive and negative undertones of solitude.

Imran finds the bookroom to be the most lifeless work place in the prison. He meditates,

The Book Room is the quietest of all workplaces in the Central Prison. It is many blocks from the nearest sign of human inhabitation. The silence that surrounds it makes you think of a library . . . But the books here have only blank pages, which makes it a library of unwritten books and unforced silence . . . Books are born in near silence. No wonder libraries are such quiet places. (Salim, 2013, pp. 7-8)

The silence inside the bookroom catalyses Imran’s search for alternate ways to escape the boredom of indoor jobs. He conjures up words and places known to him and imagines them appearing in blank pages of the books that he made during imprisonment. “The first place this nearly invisible opening chapter sketched was Vanity

Bagh . . . words, words, and all of them about the life I had lived until they handcuffed me and brought me here . . . A blank book is as good as a jailbreak” (Salim, 2013, pp. 12-60). It is the intricate play of his psyche that revives his life in prison. Imran tries to confront his reality rather than conforming to it. Thus he pushes the constraints of prison using his imagination and memory of *Vanity Bagh*; he had lived for real.

Imran's cognitive cartography involves an articulation of memories of the past against the gnawing silence of the present. The more the quietness inside the bookroom plunges him into despair, the more his memory becomes eloquent, to make him actively engage in the work assigned to him. The blank pages resemble the blank slate of Imran's mind, ready to be engraved with memories and knowledge. They project his own psyche, where he becomes the silent narrator and the reader of his own unwritten memoir. The imaginary voyage is Imran's ploy to escape from the silence in the book room to the spaces about which his memories become vocal as they are the extension of his own self. Unlike Imran, his friend Zia lacks the power of imagination and fails to endure imprisonment. He plots and executes his own jailbreak but gets killed later for challenging the efficiency of the jailors' surveillance. This underlines the sovereign power's agency to subdue its subjects, who either comply or else get silenced altogether.

Salim's portrayal of a mute Yahya throws light into the lives of differently abled people who are often left unheard. Zulfikar mockingly names their group of six friends as “5 1/2 Men,” disqualifying Yahya's representation as a full member (Salim, 2013, p. 31). Yahya's pain is evident from his reaction as he mimes his resignation from the group. Yahya's fingers, “which were his lips, would not part and utter a word for the rest of the evening” (Salim, 2013, p. 31). Yahya's fingers resumed being talkative once he rejoined the group later. This points out how mute people like Yahya find their own ways to communicate their emotions with others even without the agency of speech and how they get silenced out of shame and anger. Yahya is again reduced to silence, realising his unintentional involvement in the blast and casualties (Salim, 2013, p. 216). Overwhelmed by guilt, he attempts to commit suicide and finally loses his life in the hospital

after silently wallowing in pain. Yahya's life portrays different shades of silence—of muteness, of shame, of anger, of guilt, and of pain.

People in Vanity Bagh despised policemen's exercise of sovereign power, but they admire the prowess of a local goon named Abu Hathim and praise his legendary encounters with the police. Imran's father, who employs his agency of power over a limited few, finds himself unvoiced before Hathim, the aging don of Vanity Bagh. Imran recalls, "No one shouts at Abu Hathim sahib. No one even dares hold his gaze for longer than a few seconds" (Salim, 2013, p. 41). The dominance of Imran's father fades away in front of him; his demand to comply with the rituals sounds like a plea before the goon. However, a hostile group attacks Hathim, thereby silencing the voice of the entire Vanity Bagh. An exchange of roles in terms of hierarchy and dominance is evident in these instances, and it highlights the fluidity of power dynamics, where the powerful become powerless and vice versa.

Imran's friend Zulfikar aspires to be the ring leader among his friends and later assumes the vacant position of don following Hathim. Zulfikar's actions are dubious since he remained silent about his deal with Qadir, who seems to be the mastermind behind the bomb blast. The author leaves certain clues or blank spaces for readers to interpret Zulfikar's involvement in the conspiracy. In "The Lacuna as a Cultural Phenomenon," Ledia Kazazi defines lacunas as "gaps found inside the text whose filling would provide the reader with very useful information for the complete embracing of the meaning of the text itself" (Kazazi, 2014, p. 356). In *Vanity Bagh*, there are instances of lacuna that can be translated as authorial silence that is left for the interpretation of the readers. They make the text open-ended, resulting in multiple interpretations. The two prominent junctures where the author remains silent include the mystery behind Zia's death, the identity of the actual culprit behind the bomb explosion, and Zulfikar's complicity in it.

The author's clues imply a chance for an encounter that resulted in Zia's death at the hands of the police. Zia is found dead after the Jailors allowed the imam to visit Imran inside the prison. The police had previously forbidden Imran from paying the last respect to his deceased mother as his father had turned down a deal proposed by

a jailor. The deal was a four-hour parole for Imran only if Imran's father discloses Zia's hideaway (Salim, 2013, p. 232). The puzzle of Zia's death can be resolved if the accounts of Imran and his father are read side by side: Zia's untimely death after Imran's father's visit to the prison and the deal regarding Zia between Imran's father and the jailors. The author is introducing a young college girl towards the end of the novel, where she seeks help from Hathim's spouse to save her husband, who is included in the list of the prime suspects of the bomb blast. It is none other than Zulfikar, whom she identifies as the cousin brother of Qadir (Salim, 2013, p. 220).

A multitude of other variants of silence also find their expression in this novel. Silence induced by sympathy in Imran's brother's attempt, where he exploits his own ailment for the purpose of stopping the petty fights in his home (Salim, 2013, p. 22). Silent pathos can be traced in a death scene at Imran's friend's family. The imam insists on a silence of veneration on the premises of the mosque. Imran's house is filled with silence induced by grief following the death of his mother. Imran, Wasim, and Abu Hathim's grandchild Sinbad also reflect a silence of disavowal, which Imran considers characteristic of people in *Vanity Bagh*. They wordlessly disapprove of anything with a mocking frozen smile in the corner of their mouths (Salim, 2013, p. 42). Imran puts on this smile and refrains from answering the provocative and defaming questions of the workshop man regarding his religious practices. Silence became an effective tool to express his strong disagreement here, as he was unable to respond in other ways since the wardens were watching his actions, waiting to charge at him at the slightest clue of provocation from his part.

Conclusion

The critical reading of *Vanity Bagh* pinpoints multiple dimensions of silence people resort to during the moments of happiness, veneration, sympathy, grief, anger, shame, guilt, fear, and disavowal. Silence is also implemented when a situation demands that one refrain from speaking. One also uses the agency of speech to silence the others. Silence can be comforting to a person at one moment and a discomfoting experience at another time. Studying this novel reinstates the fact that silence is that one thing that is easy to identify yet difficult to explain or decipher. In short, silence is the sublime

expression of all the emotions beyond words.

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Whispers of Nadi Wisdom: Exploring the Ancient Manuscripts

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Abstract

Nadi Vigyan by Maharshi Kanad is a classical Ayurvedic text that explores the ancient diagnostic technique of Nadi Pariksha (pulse diagnosis). This practice provides insights into the physiological and pathological states of the body but is traditionally complex and challenging for contemporary readers. The *Vidyotini Bhasha Tika* commentary by Indradev Tripathi simplifies and contextualizes the text, making it more accessible to modern practitioners, students, and scholars. To analyze the structure, methodology, and core teachings of *Nadi Vigyan* and evaluate the value added by the *Vidyotini Bhasha Tika* in bridging traditional knowledge with modern healthcare practices. A qualitative review of *Nadi Vigyan* and its commentary, focusing on its textual structure, diagnostic methodology, and philosophical underpinnings. The commentary elucidates intricate concepts of Nadi Pariksha, offering clarity and practical relevance. It enables a broader understanding of Ayurveda, aligning traditional diagnostics. The *Vidyotini Bhasha Tika* commentary enhances the accessibility and applicability of *Nadi Vigyan*, fostering its integration into holistic healthcare

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approaches. It underscores the importance of preserving and adapting traditional medical practices for modern contexts.

Introduction

Nadi pariksha or Pulse reading is one of the precedent practices used by Ayurvedic physicians. This practice has been effectuated by physicians to understand the physiological and pathological state of the body. With evolution of different classical Ayurveda diagnostics and interest in holistic health and traditional healing systems continues to grow, the ancient Ayurvedic practice of Nadi Pariksha has gained attention for its profound insights into well-being. Though this is practised only by a selective group of vaidyas in India, but there is a rising movement to explore and integrate these traditional practices into modern healthcare approaches, fostering a greater exchange of knowledge between cultures. The healthcare sector is keen to enhance its understanding of this intricate technique, for which several authoritative books serve as invaluable resources.

Nadi Vigyan by Maharshi Kanad, accompanied by the *Vidyotini Bhasha Tika* (commentary) by Indradev Tripathi, is also such a classical work that explores the ancient science of *Nadi Pariksha*. The original work, with its intricate concepts and foundations in profound philosophical and medical traditions, may pose challenges for contemporary readers in understanding it thoroughly. *Indradev Tripathi's* commentary bridges this gap by offering clarity and practical relevance through a simplified explanation of exquisite concepts. The *Vidyotini Bhasha Tika* makes the text more accessible not only to Ayurvedic practitioners but also to students and scholars hunting through knowledge of traditional Indian medical sciences.

This review will analyse the core teachings of *Nadi Vigyan* as presented in this edition, focusing on its structure, methodology, uniqueness and the value added by commentators.

About the author

Maharishi Kanad was an ancient Indian philosopher and scientist, widely regarded as the father of atomic theory in Indian philosophy. He is best known for founding the *Vaisheshika* school of philosophy, one of the six classical schools (*Darshanas*) of Indian philosophy. His works laid the foundation for the development of

the atomic theory in ancient India, predating similar ideas in the Western world. *Maharishi Kanad* is believed to have lived around the 6th century BCE, although exact dates are not certain. His name “*Kanad*” derives from the *Sanskrit* word “*Kan*” meaning “atom” or “smallest particle,” reflecting his profound contributions to atomic theory.

If there is any other *Kanad* apart from this, their historical periods are not documented.

About the commentator

Dr. *Indradev Tripathi* is a highly respected clinician, known for his expertise in *Ayurveda*. He holds several prestigious degrees, including *Ayurvedacharya*, BIMS, DSC, and AMO, from Uttar Pradesh. His contributions to the field of *Ayurveda* are vast, particularly in the realm of traditional medical texts and their interpretation for modern audiences.

Contents Review

The book contains 116 *Sutra* (*Shloka*). The Sutras begin with *Mangalaacharan* (Prayings) towards Lord *Shiva* and *Vaidyak Prachar* (Gratification of *Vedas*). The Main corpus of the book contains basics of *Nadi Vigyan*. The author has very admirably compiled basic principles of assessment of *Nadi* as per *Dosha*, Curability of Diseases highlighting its implications in diseases such as *Jwar* (Fever), *Atisara* (diarrhoea) and *Grahani*. The book has 2 annexures at the end explaining about the assessment of *Nadi* as per *Unani* and Modern Sciences.

Specific Content Analysis

1.1 Alternative perspective on the descent of *Ayurveda*.

The Book starts with the mention of *Mangalaacharan* and *Vaidyak Prachar* and the author has been peculiar about mentioning that the descent of *Ayurveda* has started with Hindu deity Lord *Shiva* who taught this knowledge to Lord *Brahma*. From the *Brahma*, Lord *Indra* (king of the gods) received this knowledge. Lord *Indra* taught this knowledge to Sage *Kanad*. This suggests the concurrent existence of the science of *Nadi* (pulse examination) alongside the

Ayurvedic principles described in the *Brihattrayi* texts of *Ayurveda*.

1.2 Introduction to Nadi Vigyan: (flow chart-01)

1.2.1 Methods of Examination of Nadi:

Book describes the positioning of the hand, starting from the elbow region, to assess the pulse effectively. The physician uses the three fingers—index, middle, and ring finger—of the right hand below the left thumb of the patient. It emphasises cleaning and positioning the elbow properly to clear the pulse path. Each finger corresponds to the detection of different Doshas—*Vata*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha*—and the conditions of the body. The procedure involves pressing and releasing specific points systematically to evaluate the pulse’s characteristics and gain insights into the patient’s health.

1.2.2 Do’s and Don’ts of Nadi Examination

The text outlines the appropriate timing and guidelines for *Nadi* examination. It emphasises that the ideal time for *Nadi* assessment is in the morning, after the patient has completed natural eliminations and is calm. The physician should perform the examination in a composed state, seated comfortably. While the tradition prioritises morning assessments for accurate readings, pulse examination can also be conducted at other times during acute conditions. However, after midnight, the *Nadi* tends to reflect its natural state, making diagnosis easier. In the afternoon, due to the body’s heat, and in the evening, due to daily fatigue, the pulse may become irregular, potentially affecting accuracy. Therefore, morning is considered the best time for *Nadi* assessment.

1.2.3 Assessment of *Tridosha* through *Nadi*

The characteristics of *Nadi* (pulse) based on the three *Doshas*—*Vata*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha* is explained as *Vata* flows on the outermost side (closer to the index finger), *Pitta* is detected in the middle region (beneath the middle finger), and *Kapha* flows on the innermost side (under the ring finger). This arrangement aids the physician in diagnosing the dominance or imbalance of *Doshas* by observing the specific qualities of the pulse in these positions. (table no.-01)

Aggravated <i>Dosha</i>	Characteristic feature of <i>Nadi</i>	Comparing Locomotion
<i>Vata Dosha</i>	Weak and Irregular	Snake or Leech
<i>Pitta Dosha</i>	Rapid and Sharp	Crow, Pigeon or Frog
<i>Kapha Dosha</i>	Slow and Deep	Swan, Peacock, Dove, Pigeon or Hen
<i>Tridosha</i>	Combined attributes	Quail, Partridge, Francolin Partridge

Table no.01

Aggravated *Dosha* Characteristics with *Nadi* Features and Locomotion Pattern

1.2.4 Prognostic Evaluation through *Nadi*

The author of the book states that when *Nadi* naturally aligns with the body's natural cycles (like *Vata*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha* dominance at different times of the day), it indicates a good prognosis for the patient's recovery. This favourable pulse suggests that the body's natural healing processes are working efficiently, and the disease can be easily overcome without much difficulty.

Characteristic features of *Nadi* depicting *Sannipataj* incurable diseases.

1. Pulse becomes slow, weak, disconcerted, irregular, stops pulsating or disappears for sometime. The pulse may deviate from its normal path.
2. Pulse appears raised, stable, too slow, thick, hard, subtle or demonstrates erratic movements.
3. Pulse feels cold when the body is hot and vice versa with

involvement of different movements of *Nadi*. This is a confirmatory sign of death.

4. The pulse may initially be active, but just before death, it becomes suddenly almost imperceptible.
5. The pulse follows an inverse pattern to the natural physiological sequence, starting with *Pitta*, then transitioning to *Vata*, and finally aligning with *Kapha*. This cycle repeats itself, demonstrating other distinctive traits like fluctuating movement, increased speed, subtlety, and various other variations.

1.2.5 Prognostic features of impending death and declining lifespan

- * The text elaborates on various pulse characteristics considered signs of impending death, emphasizing their prognostic importance in critical illnesses like:
- * When the body becomes emaciated due to a chronic illness and the pulse resemble an earthworm or snake, the person is supposed to die in one month.
- * If a patient's *Nadi* is strong for a while and then rapidly weakens, it indicates that death is likely to occur on the seventh day.
- * If a patient is experiencing a high temperature accompanied by *Tridosha* imbalance but *Nadi* feels cold, it may suggest a critical condition with a potential prognosis of death within three days.
- * If the *Nadi* of a patient resembles the movement of *Bhramar* (Bumblebee), then the death is likely to occur in one day.

1.2.6 Characteristics of Healthy and Unhealthy Pulse

The author explains that a healthy pulse is clear, steady, and moves smoothly at a moderate pace. It should neither be too fast nor too slow, and it should remain within its normal range without any erratic movements. This balanced pulse is considered a sign of good health and vitality.

This text describes the characteristics of a diseased pulse. It mentions that a diseased pulse is filled with blood, feels like a thread, deviates from its normal path, moves too fast or too slow, feels hard

or sticky, and moves in a crooked manner. These abnormal characteristics are caused by imbalances in the three doshas (*Vata*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha*).

1.2.7 Relationship between pulse and Diet

This book explores the intricate relationship between diet and pulse characteristics, emphasising how different foods influence the pulse by affecting the three *doshas* (*Vata*, *Pitta*, and *Kapha*). It highlights that excessive consumption of specific food items can alter the pulse in unique ways. (table no-02) (flow chart-02) (table no-03)

Rasa	Nadi movement
Sweet	Like peacock
Sour	Hot and jumping
Salt	Easy and fast
Pungent	Coletto bird like
Bitter	Earthworm like
Astringent	Hard

Table no.02

Correlation of Nadi Movement with Rasa Characteristics

Flow chart.02- pulse movement after eating food

Diet type	Pulse movement
Liquid diet	Hard pulse
Hard diet	Soft pulse
Sweet, sour food	Cold pulse
Roasted food	Stable, feeble pulse
Pumpkin, radish	Feeble pulse
Green leafy vegetables, banana	Blood filled pulse

Meat	Stable pulse
Milk	Cold, strong pulse
Jaggery, milk, stuffed item	Stable, feeble pulse

Table no.03- Relationship Between Diet Type and Pulse Movement

1.2.8 Variations in pulse rate throughout the day

In this book the author discusses the natural variations in pulse rate throughout the day. (table no-04)

Period	Pulse movement
In morning	Smooth pulse
In afternoon	Hot pulse
In evening	Fast pulse
At night	Slow pulse

Table No. 4- pulse movement according to time

1.2.9 Assessment of diseases on the basis of pulse

In this book the author highlights the relationship between pulse characteristics, fever, and *doshic* imbalances. Also, explores the connection between pulse characteristics and various physiological and pathological conditions. In digestion-related issues, the pulse changes depending on the state of digestion. (table no-05)

Disease/Condition	Pulse
Stiffness of body	Sluggish, Jumping pulse
Hyperthermia	Fast jumping pulse
High grade fever	Hot, fast pulse
Pakvaajeerna (chronic indigestion)	Unconfirmed, slower pulse
Happy person	Stable
Hungry person	Active/agile
Poor digestive fire, Ksheen Dhatu (~wasted tissue)	Slower, swan shape
Heavy stomach	like the front of a serpent
Increase digestive fire	Light and fast

Disease/Condition	Pulse
Stiffness of body	Sluggish, Jumping pulse
Hyperthermia	Fast jumping pulse
High grade fever	Hot, fast pulse
Grahani (Diseases of digestion and metabolism)	In foot- swan like movement of pulse In hand - frog like movement of pulse
Vilambika (~gastrointestinal disorder)	Jumping pulse
Visuchika (~gastrointestinal disorder)	Frog like movement
Anaha (Flatulence), Mutrakrichchha(~urine retention)	Heavy
Prameha (~diabetes)	Glandular form
Visha (~poison)	Jumping
Gulma	curved
Vrana (~wound)	Pittaja like
Bhagandara (~fistula), Nadvrana (~Sinus)	Vataj like

Table no.05- Disease condition and pulse movement

These pulse patterns provide diagnostic insights into various ailments and guide treatment approaches.

2.1 Annexures

Here *Acharya* has also introduced the pulse according to the *Unani* pathy. In *Unani* medicine, the study of the pulse (*Nabz*) is a vital diagnostic tool for assessing health, diagnosing diseases, and understanding a person's temperament (*Mizaj*). The pulse, seen as the rhythmic expansion and contraction of arteries influenced by the heart, reflects the body's intrinsic heat, blood quality, and temperament. *Unani* physicians observe the movement of *Vata* (*Mauji*), *Pitta* (*Gijali*), *Kapha* (*Dudi*) or *Rakta* (*Mumtali*) *doshas* in the pulse and give information about these categories based on the character-

istics of the pulse.

3.1 Annexures

Here *Acharya* has also introduced the pulse according to the western science. In modern medicine, *Nadi* (pulse) examination is an essential diagnostic method used to evaluate cardiovascular and overall systemic health. The pulse represents the rhythmic expansion and contraction of arteries, which occur due to the heart's pumping action.

Status of press

The book "*Nadi Vigyan*" published by Chaukhambha Orientalia, is available in *Hindi* language. It is priced affordably at 25 rupees and was released in its edition year of 2016.

Readability

Nadi Vigyan is presented in a dignified, classical, yet simple language that ensures clarity. Each letter and character is distinctly recognizable, making it easy to read. The content is elaborately explained, facilitating better understanding with minimal reading effort.

Uniqueness of Book

The uniqueness of *Nadi Vigyan* lies in its ability to seamlessly blend classical Ayurvedic principles with practical insights into the ancient art of pulse diagnosis. Unlike many other texts, it focuses exclusively on the science of *Nadi pariksha*, presenting a comprehensive guide that is both scholarly and accessible. The book's dignified yet simple language ensures clarity while maintaining the depth and authenticity of Ayurvedic knowledge. Each concept is explained in an elaborative and structured manner, enabling practitioners and students to grasp the intricate details of pulse analysis and its application in understanding the *doshas*, *prakriti*, and disease conditions. Its meticulous approach, affordability, and focus on preserving traditional wisdom make it a standout resource for those seeking to delve deeply into this specialized area of *Ayurveda*.

Conclusion

The book *Nadi Vigyan* serves as a profound exploration of the ancient science of pulse diagnosis, offering a deep understanding of its principles and practical applications. Written in a dignified and accessible language, it bridges classical Ayurvedic wisdom with a modern interpretative approach, making it comprehensible for both seasoned practitioners and new learners. By emphasizing simplicity and clarity, the text ensures that complex ideas are rendered in a manner conducive to effortless comprehension.

Revisiting the Catuspāthī Education System in Colonial Bhagwanpur

Sanjib Patra¹

Abstract

This research article analyses the practice of Catuspāthī education in Bhagwanpur, its historical importance, pedagogical structure, and contemporary relevance. Originating from the source of the ancient Indian education system, the Catuspāthī emphasizes a holistic approach, where philosophical inquiry, practical skills, and moral development are connected. This study has applied quality methods, including interviews of teachers, students, and community leaders, and analysis of curricular elements. The results of the study show that the Catuspāthī model helps develop critical thinking and cultural awareness, which produces a community consciousness among the students. The article advocates for the revival of the Catuspāthī practice and suggests that by including a modern teaching strategy, its effectiveness can increase. Above all, this study highlighted the importance of reconsideration and adaptation of the Catuspāthī education to empower the future generations, and at the same time honour its rich heritage.

Keywords: Catuspāthī, Bhagwanpur, Sanskrit, Ṭola, Paṇḍita

The Sanskrit language is a glorious and immortal treasure that contains the rich tradition of cherished knowledge in India and the world. Its literature and philosophy are an eternal source of deep traditions and wisdom in ancient India. For over five millennia, the content of Indian culture has been alive through the practice of this beautiful language. Spirituality forms the cornerstone of Indian culture, lifestyle, and, indeed, the broader world culture. When universal consciousness manifests within an individual's thoughts

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and emotions, they evolve into a truly spiritual and cultured person, making their existence in this world meaningful. The essence of the Upaniṣadic hymns, “Sā vidyā yā vimuktaye or Avidyayā mṛtyuṃ tīrtvā vidyayā amṛtam aśnute,” resonates deeply within them, leading to the realization of ‘Saccidānandaṃ Brahma.’ Paṇḍita Jawaharlal Nehru (T. Das 295-304) respectfully acknowledges the significant and lasting impact of Sanskrit on Indian culture and life in his book ‘Discovery of India’ - “If I were asked what is the greatest treasure which India possesses and what is her finest heritage, I would answer unhesitatingly it is the Sanskrit language and literature and all that it contains. This is a magnificent inheritance, and for so long, it has endured and influenced the lives of our people. The basic genius of India will continue. If there is one thing that can embody the greatness of India’s thought and culture in the past, it is Sanskrit..... I would like as many Indians as possible to know Sanskrit, which is the basis of our culture” (Nehru 166). Numerous commissions and committees established by the Government of India to address education reform have suggested incorporating the Sanskrit into the mainstream curriculum. These commissions include the Dr. Sarvepalli Radhakrishnan Commission (1948-49), the Sir Arcot Lakshmanaswami Mudaliar Commission (1952-53), the Bal Gangadhar Kher Commission (1955-56), the Dr. Suniti Kumar Chattopadhyay Commission (1960), and the Dr. Daulat Singh Kothari Commission (1964-1966). Additionally, the West Bengal government convened the Dr. Sambhunath Bandyopadhyay Committee (1960), the Dr. Bhabatosh Dutta Commission (1984), the Dr. Ashok Mitra Commission (1992), and the Dr. Ramaranjan Mukhopadhyay Commission (2004), among others. A consensus among many distinguished scholars and intellectuals has emerged, emphasizing the importance of incorporating Sanskrit into public education, particularly at the school level.

“Bhāratasyāḥ pratiṣṭhā dve —
Saṃskṛtaṃ saṃskṛtiś caiva...”

- Renowned historian Dr. Sardar K. M. Panikkar² Once, it was re-
2. Kavalam Madhava Panikkar (3 June 1895-10 December 1963), popularly known as Sardar K. M. Panikkar, was an Indian statesman and diplomat. He was also a professor, newspaper editor, historian, and novelist—Kavalam Madhava Panikkar - Indian statesman. 6 December 2023.

marked about Sanskrit that... “The unity of India will collapse if it ceases to be related to Sanskrit and breaks away from Sanskrit and the Sanskrit traditions. Sanskrit, being our greatest single national inheritance, the roots of our national behaviour, and the pattern of our ideas being embedded in it, familiarity with it is necessary for anyone who claims to be a true Indian. Sanskrit alone has the pre-eminence which Hindi could never claim over the great regional languages, enabling her to maintain and uphold in every region of India the supreme claim of Indian unity”. Dr. Suniti Kumar Chattopadhyay expresses his sorrow by stating, “Sanskrit has not been allowed to enjoy even the status and facilities it had under the British Raj” (Chattopadhyay 25).

The Sanskrit language, much like the Aryan culture, found its way to East India and Bengal primarily through the influence of Buddhism. The seventh century, marked by the reigns of Harshvardhan in North India (Harsha 18) and Shashank in Gauda, (Sengupta 96-98) is often referred to as the golden age for the proliferation of Buddhism and the Sanskrit language in Bengal (Chakrabarti 11-27). Numerous Buddhist monasteries, such as Mogalmari and Bahiri, were established in Tamluk³ and its surroundings. During this period, the integration of various forms of knowledge, including Buddhist philosophy and Tantra in Sanskrit, significantly enriched the cultural landscape of Medinipur. It is essential to acknowledge that for several centuries during the Middle Ages, both Utkal and Muslim rulers governed significant portions of Midnapore. Consequently, the impact of Orissa’s Hindu cultural heritage—encompassing aspects of education, religious and social practices, and techniques involved in temple and deity construction—was profoundly felt throughout the undivided Medinipur district (Basu 149-150), particularly in the Contai sub-division⁴. In addition to the prominence of Sanskrit

3 Tamluk, known as Tamralipti, was an ancient port and trade center of southeast Asia. It is situated in West Bengal just south of the Rupnarayana River.

4 Before the reign of Utkala king Anaṅgabhīmādevā (1211-1238 CE), the influence of Utkala, as documented in the Madlapanji of Orissa, extended northward to the Kansai River and ultimately reached the Damodar River. The territory under Utkala’s control in Midnapore was divided into six administrative units known as Dandapat, each managed by royal representatives referred to as Deshadhipati. These Dandapat included Jauliti, Tania, Naigaon, Maljhita,

education, Persian studies were also prevalent to meet royal demands. Brahmins engaged in various subjects such as Nyāya, Vyākaraṇa, Darśana, and Smṛti in Catuspāthī, while also participating in Ayurvedic practices, often alongside Vaidya-Kayasthas. For centuries, Deccan Vedic Brahmins, custodians of Aryan culture, have resided and imparted knowledge in regions like United Medinipur, Jhargram, Howrah, Hooghly, and the 24 Parganas.

Various migrations took place during the invasion of Sultan Mohammed Ghazni in 1018 CE. (Ratnawat 91-92). As a result, the Brahmins were forced to flee east to protect the Hindu tradition. A group of Vedic Brahmins entered Bengal through Orissa. On the other hand, some Brahmins come from the west through Mithila, known as 'Western Vedic Brahmins', and those who come to Orissa from the south side are called 'Southern Vedic Brahmins'. The Vedic Brahmins of southern India played an important role in forming a blend culture in South Bengal. They made an exceptional contribution to promoting Sanskrit education through establishing a Ṭola-Catuspāthī,⁵ Or conducting Yājñā-Yajña over the centuries. They are recognized by a variety of titles (surnames), including Nanda, Misra, Rath, Kar, Acharya, Dasa, Sharma, Deva Sharma, Dasha Sharma, Pathak, Pahari, Tripathi, Tiari, Panigrahi, Sanabigrahi, Agasti, Agnihotri, Hota, Praharaja, Panda, Pati, Shatapathi, Bachaspati, Adhikari, Raya, Raychaudhuri, Chakraborty, Bhattacharya, Bhatt, Mahapatra, Karamahapatra, Panchadhyayi, Dwivedi, Trivedi, Chaturvedi, Padiyari, Puri,

Narayanpur, and Bhanjbhum. Some of these divisions were further segmented into various Bishi or Chaur. The Jauliti Dandapat encompassed the Sabong-Maina area, while the Tania Dandapat oversaw the Turka-Dantan region. The Naigaon Dandapat was responsible for the Egra area, the coastal region of Kanthi-Khejuri-Nandigram fell under the Maljhita Dandapat, Narayangarh was included in the Narayanpur Dandapat, and Jangalmahal was part of the Bhanjbhum Dandapat. Furthermore, theories suggest that Patashpur was associated with the Naigaon Dandapat and Bhagwanpur with the Maljhita Dandapat.

- 5 Ṭola, an informal school system of ancient India, where grammar, law, logic, and philosophy were taught. Ṭola's were usually placed in religious and educational places, such as Varanasi, Nadia, and Nasik. The teacher was a Brahmin who used to teach orally and had a group of students around him. These teachers were a vessel of deep respect in the Hindu society, and their livelihood was through gifts received on the occasion of Hindu religious festivals and the donations of the surrounding zamindars.

Bharti, Upadhyaya, Kulvi. In the next few centuries, primarily until the eighteenth century, various zamindars of Medinipur allowed the Brahmin families to live in their region to expand Vedic religion and education. These events help to make Medinipur an essential center of the Sanskrit language and scripture. The contribution of renowned scholars of the district, like Mritunjay Vidyalkar (1762-1819) from Datan and Ishwar Chandra Vidyasagar (1820-1891) from Birsingh, bears testimony to this rich intellectual tradition. At the beginning of the nineteenth century, the comparative analysis of the number of Ṭola-Catuṣpāthī in Medinipur provided valuable insights on the spread of Sanskrit education all over Bengal. In 1931, the Calcutta Sanskrit Association, under the patronage of the Bengal government, prepared a detailed list of the Ṭola-Catuṣpāthī of the five divisions of the whole province. The findings revealed 459 institutions in six districts of the Presidency Division (with 147 located in Kolkata), 708 in six districts of the Burdwan Division (including 366 in Medinipur), 352 in four districts of the Dhaka Division (105 in Faridpur), 353 in three districts of the Chittagong Division (189 in Tripura), and 137 Ṭola's in six districts of the Rajshahi Division (with a maximum of 33 in Rajshahi). Furthermore, a 1963 report from the Bengali Sanskrit Education Council listed 491 professors and details of their respective Ṭola-Catuṣpāthī in the Medinipur district.

The Calcutta Sanskrit Association, also known as the Bengal Sanskrit Association, was established by the British government before India's independence in 1947. Following independence, the Bangiya Sanskrit Siksha Parishad took over the responsibility of promoting Sanskrit through various Catuṣpāthī (Ṭola's) and conducting examinations such as Ādya, Madhya, and Upādhi (or tīrtha). Notably, during the tenure of Mahamahopadhyay Maheshchandra Nyāyaratna (1836-1906) as chancellor of the Calcutta Sanskrit College from 1876 to 1895, the title 'Tīrtha' was officially introduced in 1884 with the approval of the British Government (Bayly 144-145). His efforts also led to the first Sanskrit examination held by the Calcutta Sanskrit College on April 14, 1879, sanctioned by the then-Bengal government. In that inaugural year, the subjects approved for examination included Nyāya, Vyākaraṇa, Darśana, and Smṛti. Out of 62 applicants, 50 candidates participated, with 25 successfully

passing the examination. In addition to the aforementioned government institutions located near the Calcutta Sanskrit College, various Catuṣpāṭhī /Ṭola's across undivided Bengal, including the Contai Sub-division, were supported by esteemed scholars and professors from the Calcutta Sanskrit College during the 19th century and the latter half of the 20th century. Successful students studying under these scholars were awarded various titles, gaining recognition in societal and governmental circles. Furthermore, numerous non-official titles were conferred by various scholarship societies, debating houses, and similar organizations. These titles or Upādhi were –

Subject's / Viṣaya	Sanskrit Titles / Upādhi
<p style="text-align: center;">Sāhitya (Kāvya, Alankāra)</p>	<p>Vidyāratna, Vidyālaṅkāra, Vidyāsāgara, Vidyābinōda, Vidyābāgīśa, Vidyārṇaba, Vidyābāridhi, Vidyābhūṣaṇa, Vidyānidhi, Kabiratna, Kāv्यaratna, Kāv्यabhūṣaṇa, Kabibhūṣaṇa, Kabiśēkhara, Vāṇīkaṅṭha, Sāhityabhūṣaṇa, Sāhityaratna, Sāhityasarasvatī, Sāhityabhāratī, Siddhāntabāgīśa, Kula bhāskara, Kulaśīrōmaṇi, Pañcatīrtha, Kāvyaṭīrtha, Saptatīrtha, Tarkatīrtha, Ṣaṭatīrtha, Daśatīrtha, Kāv्यavyākaraṇatīrtha, Kāv्यavedāntatīrtha, Bhaktiśāstrī, Vyākaraṇatīrtha, Kāvya-kaṅṭha, Vidyāratna</p>
<p style="text-align: center;">Darśana (Tarka or Nyāyaśāstra)</p>	<p>Nyāyaratna, Nyāyabhūṣaṇa, Nyāyālaṅkāra, Nyāyabāgīśa, Tarkaratna, Tarkabhūṣaṇa, Tarkālaṅkāra, Tarkacūrāmaṇi, Tarkapañcānana, Tarkabāgīśa, Nyāyabācaspati, Tarkaśīrōmaṇi, Tarkasiddhānta, Nyāyapañcānana, Tarkabācaspati, Tarkacuñcu, Sāṅkhyavedāntatīrtha, Nyāyavedāntacārya, Tarkavedatīrtha, Tarkatīrtha, Nyāyīrthā</p>

Darśana (Vedānta Darśana)	Vedāntapañcānana, Vedāntabāgīśa, Vedāntabidyārṇaba, Vedāntaratna, Vedāntaśirōmaṇi, Vedāntabhūṣaṇa, Vedāntabiśārada, Vēdaratna
Smṛtiśāstra	Smṛtiratna, Smṛticūrāmaṇi, Smṛtiśirōmaṇi, Smṛtibhūṣaṇa, Smṛti- kaṇṭha, Smṛtibiśārada, Smṛtīrtha
Vēda	Vēdaratna, Vēdakaṇṭha, Vēdajña, Śrutiratna, Śrutikaṇṭha, Purānatīrtha
Jyotiṣa	Jyotiḥśāstrī, Jyotiṣārṇaba, Jyoti- bhūṣaṇa, Jyotirbinōda, Jyotiṣabhāratī, Jyotiṣaratna

There are compelling reasons to believe that Buddhist philosophy and Tantra were practiced in Bhagwanpur before the twelfth century. Bajkul evokes the presence of Vajrayana Buddhists⁶ in the area (Schumann). Likewise, Bacchipur or Sri Bacchipur may have connections to the Buddhist goddess Bachchili. This philosophical backdrop suggests that there was a conducive environment for the study and appreciation of the Sanskrit language in this locale. However, concrete evidence to support this assertion is lacking. It is important to note that the history of Sanskrit usage during the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries heavily relies on available data. The Catuspāthī educational system of that era primarily flourished under the auspices of local landlords, a trend that also applies to Bhagwanpur. Following the decline of the ancient Hijli Das dynasty, two new dynasties emerged in the northern region of the united Midnapore.

6 Tantric Buddhism is linked to groups of wandering yogis known as mahasiddhas from medieval India. John Myrdhin Reynolds notes that these mahasiddhas emerged during this period in North India and employed techniques that significantly differed from those found in Buddhist monasteries, including practices on charnel grounds. The essence of Tantra is the transformation of negative energies into wisdom, leading yogic communities to gather for tantric feasts at sacred sites (pitha) and locations (ksetra). These gatherings involved dancing, singing, consort practices, and the consumption of forbidden substances such as alcohol, urine, and meat. Notably, at least two mahasiddhas mentioned in Buddhist texts are similar to the Shaiva Nath saints, Gorakshanath and Matsyendranath, who practiced Hatha Yoga. Schumann indicates that a Sahaja-siddhi movement emerged in Bengal during the 8th century.

Their establishment occurred after the fall of the Taj Khan dynasty of Kasba-Hijli.⁷ One was the Sujāmuthā dynasty of Kajlagarh, which predated the Taj Khan (Basu). At the same time, the other was part of the Mājnāmuthā dynasty of Contai Kishorenagar Gar and Kishorepur Gar, with origins tracing back to the seventeenth century.⁸

During the 17th and 18th centuries, Catuspāṭhī's flourished in various locations such as Bahiri, Kishoregarh, and Kishorenagar (Contai) in Mājnāmuthā, Gadbbhasudevpur in Jālāmuthā, Pratapadighi in Kajlagarh in Sujāmuthā, as well as Amarshi and Panchetgarh, all under the auspices of zamindars and royal families in the regions of Contai, Egra, Patashpur, and Bhagwanpur in Medinipur. Prabodh Kumar Basu, in his work '*Bhagwanpur Thanar Itibritto*,' discusses the legacy of Vasant Kumar Panda, a prominent Sanskrit scholar from the region. He notes that during the rule of Sujāmuthā Zamindar Mahendra Narayan of Kajlagarh, the Panda family migrated from Odisha to Kotabar. At the king's behest, the Brahmins established Ṭola's to serve as community representatives, a role passed down through generations. The Panda Ṭola was founded in Kotbar during Raja Mahendra Narayan's reign, which is believed to have occurred in the early 18th century. His son, Raja Devendra Narayan, was also a patron of Śāstra and Sanskrit, convening Sanskrit scholars for discussions on scriptures and generously allocating land to esteemed Brahmins, including the renowned Paṇḍita Ramkanai Bachaspati of Bhatpara, whose grandson was the Paṇḍita Mahamaho-

7. Rahmat Khan established a new kingdom and was bestowed with the 'Ikhtiyar Khan' title around 1546 AD. That same year, his sons, Dawood Khan and Taj Khan, took over the leadership. Following this, his brother Sikander expanded their territory by conquering the ancient Hijli kingdom, which included areas such as Amarshi, Pratapadighi, Gumgarh, Naigaon Dandapat, and Sabong, thereby creating a significant Pathan-ruled Hijli kingdom. After the passing of Taj Khan Masnad-I-Ala in 1556, his son, Bahadur Khan, became the ruler of Hijli. However, a few years later, Taj Khan's son-in-law, Zail Khan, conspired with royal officials to seize the throne, ruling Hijli for a decade from 1564 to 1573. Ultimately, Bahadur Khan regained his title as Isha Khan Masnad-I-Ala, ruling from 1574 until 1594.
8. 1611 CE, the entire Midnapore region came under the rule of the Mughal emperor Jahangir. After Hijli's Pathan dynasty, the eastern Midnipur region was divided into two main zamindaris. Krishna Panda leads Jālāmuthā, while Ishwari Pattnāyekār leads Mājnāmuthā.

padhyay Panchanan Tarkaratna. It is worth mentioning that Sanskrit was practiced in the region even before the 18th century. Evidence of this is found in the 'Māroyāla Puskariṇī' near satī śāsmāna and satikuṇḍa in Kotbar. The presence of the Sanskrit texts of that time is significant, especially in the context of the Brahmanical culture of satī. In addition, the circulation of Catuspāthī education is particularly noticeable in the adjoining area of Kishorepur. Among the large Brahmin community in the eastern and northern regions of the average, the family of Dhirendranath Bhattacharya in Tanguria, whose student rallies took place in Ṭola. Kaviraj Ramcharan Chattopadhyay, from the royal lineage, was proficient in elephant-shaking tactics, and he used to travel to various places in the district, such as Narajol and Khaigarh. Pandit Srinivas Sāṅkhyaratna gained special fame among his priests. These details highlight the permanent tradition of Ṭola education in this region. Moving into the 19th and 20th centuries, the teaching of Sanskrit was embraced with great enthusiasm in Catuspāthī, located in Balageria, Mugberia, Maitna, Contai, Egra, Balighai, and Barabaria, where numerous distinguished scholars contributed to the education of Sanskrit. In Bhagwanpur,⁹ notable figures included Paṇḍita Kaliprasad Vedaratna from Ramnagar, his son Paṇḍita Dwarkanath Nanda Smṛtiratna, and his disciple Kulabhāskara Dibakar Misra Vedāntapañcānana, Kulaśiromaṇi Ramesh Chandra Nanda Pañcatīrtha, and Dr. Nirmal Kumar Panigrahi Sāṅkhyavedāntatīrtha. Other prominent scholars were Paṇḍita Prasanna Kumar Kāvyaatīrtha from Ranishahi, Girish Chandra Pati Pañcatīrtha, Nalinikanta Pahari Vyākaraṇasmṛti Purānatīrtha from Abna village, Paṇḍita Gnanadakanth Misra Kāvyaatīrtha of Kalindi, and Paṇḍita Dr. Ramjivan Acharya Kāvya puranatīrtha from Mashfa. Additionally, Paṇḍita Kulaśiromaṇi Ramesh Chandra Nanda Pañcatīrtha, Paṇḍita Yadvendra Roy Ṣaṭatīrtha from Garmadhavpur in Balighai, Shrutkirti Pitambar Kar Daśatīrtha, and Paṇḍita Dr. Dinnath Tripathi Nyāyavedāntācārya, of Contai, contributed significantly to the field. Other notable scholars included Paṇḍita Hemanta Kumar Bhattacharya Kāvya vyākaraṇatīrtha. In the middle

9 Bhagwanpur is located in the East Medinipur district of West Bengal. It lies between the latitudes of about 21°47' N and 21°57' N and the longitudes of 87°42' E to 87°52' E, in a remote area on the south-west border of the state.

of the nineteenth century, a significant network of Sanskrit education was formed, primarily in Mugabaria. An important milestone in this educational development was the establishment of Bholanath Catuspāthī in the year 1860 CE (Bengali year 1267). The institution operated without financial remuneration, and its first principal was Pandit Bholanath Nanda himself. The curriculum included in the Sāhitya, Kāvya, Alaṅkāra, Vyākaraṇa, Darśana, Smṛtiśāstra, Nyāyaśāstra and Purānā. Sanskrit practices in Mugabaria and its surrounding areas are actively conducted through various educational centres, which were called Ṭola's, located in villages such as Mugberia, Vasudevberia, Suadighi, Bhupatinagar, Jukhia, Dumardandi, Ektarpur, Kajlagarh, Tanguria, Barurvedi, Kalurveri, Bhimeswari, Barabaria, Bajarpur, Dhanda, Gopinathpur, Gopalpur, Manikjoḍ, Itabaria, Ubdadal, Vijayanagar, and Kalyanchak. These Ṭola's fostered a deep commitment to the study of Sāhitya, Kāvya, Vyākaraṇa, and Darśana across many areas of the undivided Bhagbanpur. Affluent families or zamindars primarily supported the Ṭola's or Catuspāthī, and education was free. Professors benefited from *Brahmōttōra* or *Brahmadeya* (Agrahāra) land and received esteemed scholarships and farewells during festivals (Talbot). Students were accommodated and fed at no cost. However, after the abolition of the zamindari system in 1952, the Ṭola's, depending on the patronage of the local elites, gradually went on the path of deteriorating or completely stopped. The indifferent attitude of the government makes this situation more complicated.

To give a wide idea about Bholanath Catuspāthī, it is essential to outline the development of Ṭola education in the Bhagwanpur region in the 21st century. With the establishment of the Sanskrit College in Calcutta in 1824 under the leadership of Pandit Vidyasagar, Sanskrit education also expanded in the Midnapore district. Over time, Paṇḍita Maheshchandra *Nyāyīrthā*, the principal of the Sanskrit College, recommended the establishment of the first Sanskrit examination center at the district level for the further development of Chatuspāthī education. With the advancement of the century, in 1892, the Ghatal-Nimtala Sanskrit Society was founded, followed by the formation of the Contai Sanskrit Society in 1909. In 1938, the Contai Sanskrit Society began administering the award exam-

ination in various subjects such as Kavya, Vyākaraṇa, and Vedānta. There were two main test centres in the northern part of the Contai subdivision- one in Amarshi (belonging to Patashpur police station) and the other in Barabaria in Bhagwanpur. Students from different regions of Bengal, even now from the areas of Bangladesh, came to take exams at these centres. The Barabaria center was notably supported by the philanthropic efforts of the Hazra Zamindar family, who generously provided food and lodging for the examinees at no cost. It is reasonable to conclude that several Catuspāthī were established in areas inspired by this examination framework and the encouragement of academic titles. The examination process was consistently maintained for many years, and after independence, Ṭola professors received a modest government honorarium. However, during the Left Front era, the removal of Sanskrit from the school curriculum led to a decline in the study of the four classes, resulting in irregularities in the examination system. Below is a list of the Catuspāthī in Bhagwanpur and their respective Paṇḍita up until the latter part of the 20th century.

No	Name of Catuspāthī	Paṇḍita / Professor's
1	Totanala Catuspāthī	Laxmikanta Chakraborty Tarkavēdatīrtha Haripada Kāvyaīrtha, Srijeeb Kumar Vyākaraṇatīrtha Dhirendranath Kāvyaīrtha
2	Totanala Sitamath Catuspāthī	Krishnath Vyākaraṇatīrtha Smṛtibhūṣaṇa
3	Bibhisānpur Catuspāthī	Aghornath Bhattacharya Kāvyaīrtha Dakshinacharan Bhattacharya Kāvyaīrtha Surendranath Bhattacharya Sāṅkhyavedāntatīrtha
4	Tanguria Catuspāthī	Surendranath Bhattacharya Sāṅkhyavedāntatīrtha Ramsundar Bhattacharya Kāvyaivyākaraṇatīrtha

5	Barurveri Bindhy- abasini Catuspāṭhī	(Mrs.) Vindhyavasini Chakraborty Kāvyaṅyā- karaṇatīrtha
6	Mugberia Catuspāṭhī	(Mrs.) Bhavani Kāvyaṅtīrtha, (Mrs.) Bharti Kāvyaṅtīrtha
7	Gopalchak Ca- tuspāṭhī	(Mrs.) Kaveri Vyākaraṇatīrtha
8	Tethibari Sanskrit Vidyalaya	(Mrs.) Uma Patua Vyā- karaṇatīrtha
9	Basudevberia Bhaga- vati Sanskrit Vidya- laya	Yogesh Chandra Sanabigrahi
10	Basudevberia Mai- treyee Catuspāṭhī	Dinnath Kāvyaṅtīrtha Durgasharan Tripathi Kāvyaṅyākaraṇatīrtha. Ramjivan smṛtīratna. Abninath Kāvyaṅtīrtha. Fanibhushan Mishra Vyā- karaṇatīrtha. Chittaranjan Kāvyaṅtīrtha. Sushant Kumar Pahari Vyā- karaṇatīrtha. Natbar Kāvyaṅtīrtha Niranjan Kāvyaṅtīrtha Byomkesh Sanabigrahi Kāvyaṅyākaraṇatīrth Bhutbhaban Kāvyaṅtīrtha
11	Basudevberia Ṭola	Srinivasa Kāvyaṅtīrtha Ra- jinikanth
12	Khanjadapur Ma- hakali Catuspāṭhī	Laxmikanta Nanda Kāvyaṅyā- karaṇatīrtha
13	Kalurveri Mokkhoda Catuspāṭhī	Ramapati Kāvyaṅyākaraṇatīrtha Mokshadacharan smṛtītīrtha
14	Bhupatinagar Shitala Catuspāṭhī	Parmananda Kāvyaṅyā- karaṇatīrtha

15	Ektarpur Catuṣpāthī	Durgadas Kāvyaṅyākaraṇātīrtha
16	Manikjoḍ Catuṣpāthī	Govind Prasad Kāvyaṅyātīrtha
17	Bajarpur Catuṣpāthī	Bipin Chandra Bhattacharya Kāvyaṅyātīrtha
18	Suadighi Catuṣpāthī	Bhuthanath Kāvyaṅyātīrtha (Head Paṇḍita, Mugberia Gangadhar High School)
19	Kesaidighi Ca- tuṣpāthī	Gayathri Nath Kāvyaṅyakaṇṭha
20	Dumardari Ca- tuṣpāthī	Siddheshwar Kāvyaṅyātīrtha
21	Baruipur Catuṣpāthī	Dinanath Vidyāratna
22	Dhanda Catuṣpāthī	Sasibhushan Smṛtiratna Satyaranjan Kāvyaṅyā- karaṇātīrtha Bhagwaticharan Jyōtirbhūṣaṇa
23	Kajlagarh Catuṣpāthī	Gopal Chandra Vyākaraṇātīrtha Golok Chandra Vidyābhūṣaṇa
24	Gopinathpur Singha- bahini Catuṣpāthī	Tarinicharan Bhattacharya Kāvyaṅyātīrtha Smṛtiratna
25	Jukhiya Catuṣpāthī	Tripuracharan Kāvyaṅyātīrtha
26	Kotbar Catuṣpāthī	Janakinath Kāvyaṅyātīrtha
27	Ektarpur Catuṣpāthī	Keshav Chandra Vedantatīrtha
28	Bhupatinagar Ca- tuṣpāthī	Taranath Kāvyaṅyātīrtha
29	Narayandari Ca- tuṣpāthī	Tarakanath Chakraborty Kāvyaṅyātīrtha
30	Kalaberia Rad- hakrishna Catuṣpāthī	Madhava Chandra Vyā- karaṇātīrtha
31	Bandhagora Baidanath Catuṣpāthī	Paṇḍita Devendranatha Kāvyaṅyākaraṇātīrtha
32	Kulapara Catuṣpāthī	Laxminarayan Kāvyaṅyātīrtha

Here is a list of Sanskrit scholars who, although not directly affiliated with any Ṭola or Catuṣpāthī, gained recognition as distinguished Sanskrit scholars in the Bhagwanpur area during

that period.

No	Name with Sanskrit Title/Upādhi	Birth/ Residential area
1	Paṇḍita Himanshu Shekhar KāvyaVyākaraṇatīrtha	Gopinathpur
2	Paṇḍita Sathyaranjan KāvyaVyākaraṇatīrtha	Gopinathpur
3	Paṇḍita Murarimohan Kabiratna	Tanguria
4	Paṇḍita Ramsundar Bhattacharya KāvyaVyākaraṇatīrtha	Tanguria
5	Paṇḍita Anukal Chandra Vyākaraṇatīrtha	Bibhisanpur
6	Paṇḍita Ukum Kumar KāvyaTīrtha	Bibhisanpur
7	Paṇḍita Kalidas KāvyaVyākaraṇatīrtha	Gopinathpur
8	Paṇḍita Amlananda Misra KāvyaVyākaraṇatīrtha	Gopinathpur
9	Paṇḍita Bireswar KāvyaVyākaraṇatīrtha	Gopinathpur
10	Paṇḍita Durgpada KāvyaVyākaraṇasmṛtīTīrtha	Kalurveri
11	Paṇḍita Tarinecharan KāvyaTīrtha	Barurveri
12	Paṇḍita Khudiram KāvyaVyākaraṇatīrtha	Jukhiya
13	Paṇḍita Byomkesh Vyākaraṇatīrtha	Jukhiya
14	Paṇḍita Vibhutibhushan KāvyaSmṛtīTīrtha	Kishorepur
15	Paṇḍita Srinivas Sāṅkhyaratna	Kishoregarh
16	Paṇḍita Bankimbihari Vyākaraṇatīrtha	Kajlagarh

17	Paṇḍita Varanasi Kāvyaṅyā-karaṇatīrtha	Barabaria
18	Paṇḍita Baghambar Kāvyaṅyā-karaṇatīrtha	Udbadal
19	Paṇḍita Raghunath Kāvyaṅyā-karaṇatīrtha	Itabaria
20	Paṇḍita Sachipada Kāvyaṅyā-karaṇatīrtha	Itabaria
21	Paṇḍita Laxmikanta Pahari Kāvyaṅyā-karaṇatīrtha	Vijayanagar
22	Paṇḍita Srishtidhar Acharya Kāvyaṅyā-karaṇatīrtha	Dumardari
23	Paṇḍita Chakradhar Acharya Kāvyaṅyā-karaṇatīrtha	Dumardari
24	Paṇḍita Mrityunjay Kāvyaṅyā-karaṇatīrtha	Barurveri
25	Paṇḍita Trilochan Kāvyaṅyā-karaṇatīrtha	Shimuliya
26	Paṇḍita Madhusudan Kāvyaṅyā-karaṇatīrtha	Shimuliya
27	Paṇḍita Bhushan Chandra Kāvyaṅyā-karaṇatīrtha	Shimuliya
28	Paṇḍita Birajacharan Kāvyaṅyā-karaṇatīrtha	Bhupatinagar
29	Paṇḍita Saktipada Vyākaraṇatīrtha	Bhupatinagar
30	Paṇḍita Laxmikant Kāvyaṅyā-karaṇatīrtha	Ektarpur
31	Paṇḍita Purnendu Shekhar Kāvyaṅyā-karaṇatīrtha	Ektarpur
32	Paṇḍita Shadanan Chakraborty Vyākaraṇatīrtha	Ilaspur
33	Paṇḍita Adharchandra Kāvyaṅyā-karaṇatīrtha	Bajarpur
34	Paṇḍita Lakshmana Chandra Kāvyaṅyā-karaṇatīrtha	Bajarpur

35	Paṇḍita Sasibhushan Kāvyaṭīrtha	Bajarpur
36	Paṇḍita Hiranmoy Misra Vyākaraṇaṭīrtha	Purvabajari
37	Paṇḍita Gadadhar Mishra Vyākaraṇaṭīrtha	Kotmukha
38	Paṇḍita Banikantha Vyākaraṇaṭīrtha	Kismat Bajkul
39	Paṇḍita Saktipada Kāvyaṭīrtha	Neturiya
40	Paṇḍita Manoranjan Kāvyaṭīrtha	Neturiya
41	Paṇḍita Srikesh Sanabighrahi Kāvyaṭīrtha	Madhakhali
42	Paṇḍita Sasibhushan Grammar Thirtha,	Gopalpur
43	Paṇḍita Prafulla Kumar das Gram- mar Thirtha	Sitadighi
44	Paṇḍita Mrityunjay Kāvyaṭīrtha	Mugberia
45	Paṇḍita Haranarayan Kāvyaṭīrtha	Mugberia
46	Paṇḍita Suresh Chandra Kāvyaṭīrtha	Mugberia
47	Paṇḍita Shaktidas Kāvyaṭīrtha	Mugberia
48	Paṇḍita Sudhir Chandra Kāvyaṭīrtha	Kotabar
49	Paṇḍita Vasudeva Kāvyaṭīrtha	Mugberia
50	Paṇḍita Gopinath Vidyāratna	Mugberia
51	Paṇḍita Manoranjan Kāvyaṭīrtha	Mugberia
52	Paṇḍita Hemanta Kumar Bhattacha- rya Kāvyaṭīrtha	Bibhisampur
53	Paṇḍita Badri Narayan Tripathi Kāvyaṭīrtha	Gopinathpur

54	Paṇḍita Krishna Mohan Chakraborty	Bhimeswari
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In the 19th century, during the Renaissance period, Zamindar Paṇḍita Bholanath Nanda (1819-1879) played a pivotal role in promoting Sanskrit education in Mugberia township. He founded a Catuspāthī in 1860 to facilitate the dissemination of Sanskrit learning within his zamindari area. He appointed a young scholar, Dwarakanath Bhattacharya, from Bibhisampur village, as the principal and educator of this institution. Bholanath ensured that his two sons, Govinda and Digambar, received a Sanskrit education under the supervision of Dwarakanath Bhattacharya. He also set up a hostel to accommodate about 20 to 25 students and managed the hostel himself. After almost two decades of devotional services, he passed 60 in 1879. After his death, the maintenance of the Catuspāthī was operated by the successors, and on the anniversary of Bholanath's death, on June 10, 1945, the Catuspāthī became the status of Bholanath Sanskrit Mahavidyalaya (College). Professor Dwarakanath Nyāyabhūṣaṇa taught in this Catuspāthī from 1860 to 1913, which is a glorious chapter for more than fifty years. His extensive knowledge, poetic talent, moral integrity, and contribution to literature have secured his legacy in the academic community. Among his notable works are the Saṭika Laghu Saṅkṣiptasāravayākaraṇa, Kāraḥsamāsa Vākyaṅvalī, Avyayakośa, Ekākṣarakośa, Gaṇakārikā, Śivatāṇḍavaṭikā, and Durgotsavapaddhati. He also authored two texts, Gurupādukāstavaṭikā and Dīkṣākumudakaumudī, under the guidance of Bhattapalli. Later, 'Maṇibhūṣaṇasambādaḥ' was composed by the Pandits of Catuspāthī based on the correspondence he exchanged with his contemporary, the eminent scholar Ramanath Śiromaṇi. The combinations of śiromaṇi's 'maṇi' and Dwarakanath Nyāyabhūṣaṇa's 'Bhūṣaṇa' formed 'Maṇibhūṣaṇasambādaḥ,' which consists of a total of 166 verses, with 66 attributed to Śiromaṇi and 100 to Nyāyabhūṣaṇa.

During the long educational life of Pandit Dwarkanath Nyāyabhūṣaṇa, numerous individuals from Mugberia and its surrounding areas engaged in the study of various scriptures, and many students

received various Sanskrit titles or Upādhi through his supervision. Notable among these scholars were Govinda Prasad and Digambar Vidyānidhi, the sons of Bholanath Nanda, as well as Gopinath Tripathi Vidyāratna, who served as a vice principal at Catuṣpāṭhī. Bardakanta Nanda Kāvyaṭīrtha, who later held a professorship at Catuṣpāṭhī for many years following Dwarakanath's tenure, was also among the distinguished students. Other prominent scholars included Chaturbhuj Nanda, Ishwarchandra Sharangi, Gayatri Nath Tripathi, Bhuthanath Tripathi (who was the headmaster of Mugberia Gangadhar High School for an extended period), Pramathanath Tripathi Vidyābhūṣaṇa, Mrityunjay Tripathi Kāvyaṭīrtha, Dinanath Tripathi Kāvyaṭīrtha Nyāyaratna, and Ramjivan Tripathi Smṛtiratna from the nearby village of Vasudevberia contributed to this scholarly lineage. Other notable names include Tarakchandra Giri from the southern bayenda, Murari Kabiratna and Srinivas Sāṅkhyaratna from Kishorepur, Dakshinacharan Kāvyaṭīrtha (Dwarkanath's son), Akshay Narayan Kāvyaḥūṣaṇa from Turka village, Jadunath Kāvyaṭīrtha from Mohanpur, Madhusudan Kāvyaṭīrtha from Rasan, Haranarayan Kāvyaṭīrtha from Chatla, Chaturbhuj Kāvyaṭīrtha, and Kartika Chandra Kāvyaṭīrtha from Kalurveri, as well as Priyanath Kāvyaṭīrtha from Sabong, Trailokyanath Kāvyaṭīrtha from Saraswatipur, Jayanarayan Kāvyaṭīrtha, and Sripaticharan Acharya from Kainthor, all of whom are recognized as eminent scholars.

Digambar Nand, the eldest son of Bholanath Nanda, started his primary Sanskrit education from Bholanath Catuṣpāṭhī. Later, he studied higher education in Vedanta, Nyaya, and Smṛiti at Bhatpara Catuṣpāṭhī in the North 24 Parganas, where he was a classmate of Pandit Panchanan Tarkaratna. After completing his education from Bhatpara, he was awarded the title of Vidyānidhi in recognition of his academic excellence. Digambar Nanda, famous for his exceptional poetic talent, authored Kālīkusumābalī, a poem composed of a total of 118 verses. His younger brother, Gangadhar Nand, first published this book on October 1, 1894; the second edition was published by Professor Brahmamoy Nand in 2010. Pandit Digambar Nand organized a Swarnaraupeya Tulyadan ceremony at his residence in Bala-geria. On this occasion, he invited prominent scholars from various quarters of Medinipur, including Kashi, Puri, Nabadwip, Bali, Singh-

bhum, Baleshwar, Kotak, Bhatpara, and Kolkata. These huge assembled scholars created new stimulus and encouragement in studying the Sanskrit language and literature in the Mugabaria region. After the passing of Pandit Dwarkanath, one of his best students, Bardakant Kāvyaṭīrtha, took over the responsibility of teaching the Bhola-nath Catuṣpāṭhī. During this time, the zamindar Gangadhar Nand provided significant assistance for almost 20 years. During this time, about 20 students lived in the hostel of this Catuṣpāṭhī. Among the notable students who excelled under Baradakant's guidance were Kartik Chandra Kāvyaṭīrtha from Erenda, Bhuthanath Kāvyaṭīrtha from Lakshir, Devendra Kāvyaṭīrtha from Brahmsasan, Murari Kāvyaṭīrtha from Maina, Jatadhari Jana Sapatīrtha from Kuchigeria, Raghunath Kāvyaṭīrtha of Itaberia, Jandar Laxmikanta Kāvyaṭīrtha, Madhusudan Kāvyaṭīrtha from Mahishadal, Srinivas Kāvyaṭīrtha from Vasudevberia, Haranarayan Kāvyaṭīrtha from Mugberia, Manmath Kāvyaṭīrtha from Bhupatinagar, Devendranath Kāvyaṭīrtha from Ektarpur, and Khudiram Kāvyaṭīrtha from Ikshupatrika, among others. After the passing of Pandit Bardakanta, Paṇḍita Dinnath Kāvyaṭīrtha Nyā-yaratna served as a professor at Catuṣpāṭhī for eight years. Pandit Jyotirmoy Nanda Vedantatīrtha was the principal, who held that position from 1945 to 1996. The associate professors were Paṇḍita Yadbendranath Roy Nyāyatarkatīrtha (1945-1951), Paṇḍita Prathamath Tripathi Vidyābhūṣaṇa (1945 until his passing), and Pandit Devendranath Tripathi Kāvyaṭīrtha (1945 until his passing). Pandit Jyotirmoy Nanda was famous for his exceptional talents as a poet, orator, and essayist.

His literary contributions are Brahmāvidyāpadāvalī (3 volumes), Mātṛdarśana, Bhajanamaṅgalam, Maṅgalabhāratī, Maṅgalāloka, Upāsanāvijñāna, Virajācaraṇadhyāna, Gaṅgādharma praṇāma, and have been published in various journals. He authored numerous Bengali articles, fertilized with religious and philosophical references from Sanskrit. His notable compositions include Bhāratājananībādanāgītiḥ, Śrīśrībhavatāriṇī stotram, Āgamaṇī, Brahmācāryabādanā, Saccaritrā ṣṭakam, Ācāryabādanam, Gītājananīstotram, Rabīndrāma, Vandevivekānandam, Śrī gurujayantī gītiḥ, ŚrīśrīNigamānandabādanā, Śrīśrī Bhaktivinoda bādanā, Śrīmat Sītārāma

dāsa mahāpuruṣa smaraṇamaṅgalam, and Śrī śrī Svarūpānanda-padyapuṣpāñjalī among others. The town of Mugberia shines brightly with the legacy of his creative brilliance.

In 1952, Bankimchandra Tarkavedanta Bhaktitīrtha began his teaching career at this Bholanath Catuṣpāṭhī. In 1978, a significant new chapter began for this Catuṣpāṭhī. With the help of the Central Sanskrit Authority of the Government of India, the institution was raised to the status of a government college, implementing a teaching framework that included Shastri and Acharya levels. At the time of this approval, Paṇḍita Jyotirmoy Nanda served as the principal of this College. After that, qualified professors and principals across various subjects were appointed by government regulations. Notable appointments were Paṇḍita Nalinikanth Misra KāvyaVyākaraṇasmṛitīrtha as a Principal and others Professors are Paṇḍita Shyamapada Bhattacharya Nabanyāyacāryatarkatīrtha; Paṇḍita Umāpada Chattopadhyay Vedatīrtha Sāhityaśiromaṇi; Paṇḍita Satyapada Bhattacharya, proficient in Vedānta, Sāṅkhya, Yoga, Nyāya, Sāhityacārya, Vedānta NabanyāyākāvyaVyākaraṇatīrtha, and KāvyaVyākaraṇatīrtha; Paṇḍita Sureshchandra Mahapatra, KāvyaSmṛti paurahityatīrtha; and Paṇḍita Chandidas Pati KāvyaVyākaraṇatīrtha. At present, Bholanath Sanskrit Catuṣpāṭhī in Mugabaria and other Sanskrit institutions from nearby villages, such as Basudevberia, Vasudevberia, Dakshin Patharberia, Bajarpur, Madhakhali, Ektarpur, and Kathuriabari, may not be able to retain the impact or popularity as before. Nevertheless, the tradition of Sanskrit education in the Mugabaria region is still alive – numerous families chanting the Sanskrit hymns, worship, and reading of Bhagavad-Gita lessons are regularly observed. Former teachers of Mugberia Gangadhar High School - Durgasharan Tripathi, Srikesh Sanbigrahi, and Mathuranath Tripathi- continue to enhance the spiritual landscape of the area. Prominent scholar Jyotirmoy Nanda's sons - Chinmay, Brahmamoy, and Chaitanyamoy - have fascinated the audience through their Sanskrit verse. Pandit Sudev Acharya has been playing an important role in maintaining spiritual awareness among the community through the celebration of Gita Jayanti and regularly reading the Bhagavad. Individuals such as Durgapada Bhattacharya, Durgadas Tripathi, Sushant Pahari, Triptipada Nan-

da, Kamlesh Sanabigrahi, Birochana Nanda, Yogamaya Nanda, and Shipra Tripathi have contributed to the continuity of Sanskrit practices through rituals and various gatherings. Additionally, Professor Ranjit Kumar Naik hosts a Sanskrit reading session at his residence on the first day of every Āṣāḍha, which sees participation from local Sanskrit scholars. The practice of Sanskrit is deeply intertwined with the cultural fabric of Mugberia, reflecting its traditional essence.

Sanskrit is a crucial component of modernity. This ancient Indian language serves not only as the foundation for sacred texts but also encompasses a wide array of disciplines, including parā and aparā vidyā, philosophy, logic, education, literature, metrics, aesthetics, ethics, economics, law, sociology, political science, military studies, and various branches of science such as mathematics, physics, chemistry, and biology. Its range is also broad in Ayurveda, geography, astronomy, architecture, and environmental science. The influence of Sanskrit flows throughout human life - it makes it a simple, balanced, and elegant progress in the way of knowledge and culture. The historical context of the Sanskrit language made it possible to develop the whole of Indian knowledge and wisdom. Key texts such as the Veda, Vedānta, Vedāṅga, Upaniṣad, Ṣaḍdarśana, Brahmasūtra, Rāmāyaṇa, Mahābhārata, Bhagavad-gītā, Purāṇa, Bhāgavata, Buddhacarita, Abhijñānaśākuntalam, Meghadūta, Kumārasambhava, Raghuvamśa, Naiṣadhacarita, Gītagovinda, Pañcatantra, Hitopadeśa, Smṛtiśāstra, Dṛśyakāvya, Nāṭyaśāstra, along with various Samhitas and Smṛtis, encompass a rich tapestry of drama, lyric poetry, prose poetry, historical narratives, and twelve distinct grammatical frameworks, including Panini's **Aṣṭādhyāyī**. This work also includes theistic and atheistic philosophical discourses, representing an unparalleled reservoir of knowledge documented and disseminated in the Sanskrit language.

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One Ajñāna with Many Ākāras in Ānandajñāna's Tarkasaṅgraha

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Abstract

In the Advaita Vedānta tradition, it is ajñāna which accounts for the experience of a world. The three avasthās (states), which are jāgrat (waking), svapna (dreaming sleep) and suṣupti (dreamless sleep), are taken to be rooted in ajñāna, but is there one ajñāna or many? It is on this question that many Advaita Vedānta philosophers differ. Here I take the case of a 13th century CE ascetic and philosopher Ānandajñāna, who in his text Tarkasaṅgraha accepts one ajñāna which possesses multiple ākāras. For him, the ākāras account for the difference between the jāgrat and svapna. Not only this, the multiplicity of Jīvas also is rooted in these ākāras. Hence, for Ānandajñāna, it is not the ajñāna itself, but the ākāras of ajñāna which produce the multiplicity of the apparent world experienced by the Jīva.

Ānandajñāna's Tarkasaṅgraha²

The 13th century CE ascetic and philosopher Ānandajñāna wrote many commentarial texts on Ādi Śaṅkarācārya's works. It was the time when a lot of dialectical texts were being written to defend one's own philosophy, or to refute that of the opponent. From the Advaita Vedānta's side, there are two well-known texts, namely

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- 2 The Sanskrit text of Ānandajñāna's Tarkasaṅgraha has been taken from the version published by Mr. T. M. Tripathi in the year 1917 under the Gaekwad Oriental Series. This is the only version published so far, which is based on a single manuscript. The only specific division in the text is that of pariccheda. Because there are no other such divisions which could be used in the footnotes, I shall be only mentioning the page numbers of the published text. For example; TS, p. 137 along with the original Sanskrit text.

Śrīharṣa's Khaṇḍanakhaṇḍakhādyā and Citsukha's Tattvapradīpikā, which attempt to refute some significant portions of the Nyāya and Vaiśeṣika philosophies. In these, only some basic categories of the said philosophies are taken up, discussed and refuted. Another such text is Ānandajñāna's Tarkasaṅgraha, in which he attempts to refute the Vaiśeṣika and Nyāya philosophies in detail. A stark difference between Tarkasaṅgraha and the former two texts is that it is only in Tarkasaṅgraha that all the categories and sub-categories of the said philosophies are taken up for refutation. For example, Ānandajñāna does not merely indulge in refuting the main category called dravya, but also takes up all the types of dravya such as pṛthivī and so forth individually. At the end of his text, he attempts to conclude and present his version of Advaita Vedānta. It is at this point that the various problems related to ajñāna are discussed. One major problem is whether ajñāna is one or many. One group of Advaita Vedānta philosophers accepts that as many are the jñānas, so many are the ajñānas (*yāvanti jñānāni tāvanti ajñānāni*). Ānandajñāna, while he accepts some kind of differences within a single ajñāna, he argues against the multiplicity of ajñāna. This paper is concerned with how Ānandajñāna discusses, analyses and criticises the idea of multiplicity of ajñāna and argues for one single ajñāna with multiple ākāras, which resides with Brahman.

Relevance and importance of Ajñāna as a concept in Advaita Vedānta

Every school of Indian philosophy has its own set of problems which it attempts to solve. When it comes to Advaita Vedānta, one of its main problems is how to reasonably explain the real-like experience of a fundamentally illusory world. It cannot be explained by Brahman alone, because it has nothing in its nature to produce anything like the world we experience. As per the philosophers of Advaita Vedānta tradition, it is when one realises their Brahman-nature, that they find an exit route from the bondage of this fundamentally illusory world. Hence, one is compelled to look at ajñāna for solutions. It is on this point, that even Advaita Vedānta philosophers may find each other standing in opposite directions. Basing their ideas mainly on Upaniṣads, they argue variously, where some ac-

cept multiple ajñānas, and others accept one ajñāna which possesses some differences. Another problem which they have to tackle is that even after realising oneself as Brahman, the experience of multiplicity, that is, of this world, does not end. If it is by jñāna that ajñāna is removed in its totality, then someone who has attained jñāna, should not be able to experience the world of multiplicity. The fact that they do experience, is the problem, which both sides of Advaita Vedānta philosophers have to solve. For the one who holds the existence of multiple ajñānas, the solution to this problem is easier, because they could appeal to the destruction of only certain ajñānas, and not of all of them. The one who accepts the existence of only one ajñāna, the solution to the problem requires the acceptance of some or other kind of difference of or within ajñāna. So long as the idea of a single ajñāna does not provide a solution to these issues, one would be compelled to accept the idea of multiple ajñānas.

A case for multiple ajñānas

Vācaspatimiśra in his commentary on Brahmasūtraśāṅkarabhāṣya titled Bhāmatī, puts forward the case of multiple ajñānas or avidyās. The problem which he intends to solve is the existence of saṃsāra after someone has attained the realisation of Brahman, where vidyā would destroy avidyā. If there were only one avidyā, then there would be left no difference between baddha (in bondage) and mukta (liberated) Jīvas. On the Śāṅkarabhāṣya of Brahmasūtra 1.4.3 he says:

Like pradhāna, we do not state (that there is) one avidyā in all Jīvas, due to which we may be taunted, instead (it is) different for each Jīva. Hence, avidyā is destroyed only for the Jīva whose vidyā is born, (and) not of the other Jīva.³

Vācaspati says that his pakṣa cannot be taunted regarding the mukti of all Jīvas followed by the mukti of one, because he believes in the existence of a separate avidyā for each Jīva. It is for this reason that when one Jīva attains mukti, it is only its avidyā which gets destroyed, and not that of other Jīvas. The only problem with this solu-

3 ŚBB 1.4.3 : na vayaṃ pradhānavadavidyāṃ sarvajīveṣvekāmācākṣmahe, yenaivamupālabhyemahi, kiṃtviyaṃ pratijīvaṃ bhidyate | tena yasyaiva jīvasya vidyotpānnā tasyaivavidyāpanīyate na jīvāntarasya |

tion is that Jīva becomes the substratum of avidyā. Jīva itself is Jīva because of avidyā. Instead of providing a solution, Vācaspati states that it is not a problem at all. He says :

(It is) not (that) difference of Jīva is dependent on difference of the avidyā (which is) upādhi, and the difference of avidyā (which is) upādhi is dependent on difference of Jīva, hence due to parasparāśraya (fault) both are unestablished, because of being without beginning, both are established like seed and sprout.⁴

What came first, the bīja (seed) or its aṅkura (sprout)? If the bīja came first, then the bīja would be without a cause. If the aṅkura came first, then it would be without a cause. Generally, without aṅkura, a vṛkṣa (tree) would not be born, which would lead to the new bīja not being born. Similarly, if the bīja would not take birth, the aṅkura would not be born, and consequently the vṛkṣa would not be born. In this manner, whether one chooses either bīja or aṅkura as the first, problem remains. Vācaspati says that this relation between bīja and aṅkura is anādi (without a beginning). Similar would be the case of Jīvabheda (multiplicity of Jīva) and avidyābheda (multiplicity of avidyā). Both being without beginning, the mutual dependence of both is not a problem at all.

A case for single ajñāna

Prakāśātman wrote his commentary Vivaraṇa on Padmapāda's Pañcapādikā, which is further a commentary on Brahmasūtraśāṅkarabhāṣya. It is here that Prakāśātman introduces the concept of one mūlājñāna (basal ajñāna), of which there are avasthābhedas (different states). His opponent puts forward a question :

(It is) your thought that the jñāna of śuktikā, while it removes the appearance of the other form, (it) also removes ajñāna (which is) its material cause. In that case, (when) along with ajñāna, the adhyāsa is being removed due to jñāna of śuktikā, (then) how would ajñāna again appear in Ātman? Hence, (one

4 ŚBB 1.4.3 : na ca - avidyopādhibhedādhiṇo jīvabhedo jīvabhedādhiṇaśca vidyopādhibheda iti parasparāśrayādubhayāsiddhiriti - sāṃpratam; anāditvād bījāṅkuravadubhayāsiddheḥ |

of these options must be) accepted; different ajñāna for each object, or (that) ajñāna is not the material cause of adhyāsa, or (that) removal of adhyāsa (happens) without the removal of material cause.⁵

The problem put forward by Prakāśātman's opponent is simple; if the jñāna of śuktikā (nacre) removes the appearance of rajata (silver) on the śuktikā, then it would also remove the upādāna (material cause) of the false appearance, which is ajñāna. If that is the case, then why, even after the false appearance of rajata in śuktikā is removed, does ajñāna appear as existent? It is not the case that just because the said false appearance was caused by ajñāna, and as it was removed by a certain jñāna, that the complete single ajñāna would be removed, thereby leading to enlightenment. Hence, the opponent gives Prakāśātman some options; to accept that there is a different ajñāna for each viṣaya (object), or to accept that adhyāsa (false appearance) is not caused by ajñāna, or to accept that the adhyāsa is removed even without the removal of ajñāna. To this Prakāśātman responds :

It is stated, that in this case, the adhyāsas of rajata and so forth are merely merged into their cause through the jñāna of śuktikā, like (that of) the earthen pot by the hitting of mace (on it). Or (it could) be imagined (that) the material causes of rajata and so forth, are different avasthās of mūlājñāna, (which) get removed through the jñāna of śuktikā and so forth, along with the adhyāsa.⁶

Prakāśātman provides two solutions for his problem; it could be

5 PPV, p. 58 : śuktikājñānaṃ hi rūpāntarāvabhāsaṃ nivartayat tadupādānaṃ ajñānamapi nivartayati iti te matam / tatra katham śuktikājñānāt sahājñānena adhyāse nivartyamāne punaḥ ātmani ajñānaṃ dṛśyeta / ataḥ prativiṣayamajñānabhedāḥ adhyāsasya ajñānānupādānatvaṃ vā upādānanivṛttimantareṇa adhyāsanivṛttirvā samāśrayaṇīyā iti /

The division of parts in Pañcapādikā is as per varṇakas. The present portion, and the portion in the next footnote are from the prathama varṇaka, which is a long portion. Hence the page numbers have been stated.

6 PPV, p. 58 : ucyate - asmin pakṣe śuktikājñā[naiḥ]nena rajatādyadhyāsānāṃ svakāraṇe pravilayamātraṃ kriyate musalaprahāreṇeva ghaṭasya / athavā - mūlājñāsyaiḥ avasthābhedāḥ rajatādyupādānāni śuktikādijñānaih sahādhyāsenā nivartante iti kalpyatām /

accepted that due to the jñāna of śūktikā, the adhyāsa of rajata merely loses its identity and stays in its cause, just as a earthen pot which is broken into fine pieces, loses its identity as a pot and looks as if it has become clay. The second option is that there is one mūlājñāna, of which a specific avasthā becomes the upādāna (material cause) of the appearance of rajata, which gets removed, along with the adhyāsa, due to the jñāna of śūktikā. Here we see the idea of a single ajñāna as having different avasthās related to different adhyāsas, which is thought to solve the problem mentioned earlier.

Ajñāna in Ānandajñāna's Tarkasaṅgraha

Ajñāna as the basis of Sarvajñatva of Brahman

A discussion on ajñāna appears at the end of Ānandajñāna's Tarkasaṅgraha. Ānandajñāna says that Brahman is the substratum of ajñāna. The problem with this idea is that Brahman is considered Sarvajña (omniscient), and to say that ajñāna resides in Sarvajña, seems contradictory. To solve this, Ānandajñāna attempts to show how ajñāna and Sarvajñatva are not opposed to each other, and that it is on the basis of ajñāna, that Brahman can be called Sarvajña. He argues:

It should not be said that because Brahman is omniscient, it is not possible (that) ajñāna (resides) in Brahman, because it is not contradictory, as ajñāna establishes omniscience. If omniscience of Brahman is meant (to be) through its inherent prajñā, then without ajñāna (there would be) no relation of unattached (Brahman) with all objects; hence ajñāna should be accepted for establishing omniscience.⁷

To say that Brahman is Sarvajña, one would need to first say that something exists which can become the meaning of the word 'sarva' (all), which is based on multiplicity of entities, through 'sarva', many entities are clubbed together, on the basis of some similarity. For example; *sarve manuṣyāḥ* (all humans) and *sarve puruṣāḥ* (all men).

⁷ TS, p. 137 : na ca - brahmaṇyapi na sambhavati ajñānaṃ, tasya sarvajña(tvā) t - iti vācyam, ajñānasya sarvajñatvasādhakatvena tadavirodhitvāt | brahmaṇo yadi svarūpaprajñāyā sarvajñatvaṃ vivakṣitam, tadā tasya asaṅgasya na ajñānaṃ antareṇa aśeṣārthasaṅgatiḥ - iti sarvajñatvasiddhyarthameva ajñānaṃ abhyupagantavyam |

In the former sentence, all humans have been clubbed in the word 'sarva', whereas in the latter sentence all men have been clubbed in the same word. Similarly in the sentence *sarvaṃ jagat*, everything in the world has been clubbed in the word 'sarva'. In this sense, to call Brahman Sarvajña would require one to accept the basis of sarva, which cannot be done without accepting multiplicity. The source of multiplicity is not Brahman. The only source of it, as accepted by the Advaita Vedānta philosophers, is ajñāna. Hence, for Brahman to be Sarvajña, it would be necessary that Brahman has some kind of contact with ajñāna. For this reason, there is no contradiction in saying that ajñāna resides in the Sarvajña Brahman. Ānandajñāna does not stop at this line of argument. He further takes the case of Brahman being inherently Sarvajña, where he argues that because Brahman is inherently asaṅga (without contact or attachment), to establish its relation with all the objects about which it knows (which makes it Sarvajña), one would need to first establish its relation with ajñāna, which is the basis of multiplicity. Further he states:

Even if omniscience is through pramāṇa, the pramāṭṛtva and the relation between pramāṇa and prameya could not be established without a relation with ajñāna, (hence one) should take recourse to possessorness of ajñāna (which resides) in it, or else (there would be) impossibility of omniscience. The Prāgbhūta [Pratyagbhūta?] Brahman alone is to be accepted as the object of ajñāna, because it is established in the apparent object of the experiences (such as) 'I do not know myself, (I do) not know the meaning of your statement'.⁸

It is only when there is multiplicity that the relation between pramāṇa (tool of valid knowledge), prameya (object of valid knowledge) and pramāṭṛ (seeker of valid knowledge) can be established. For this reason, one would need to accept some kind of a relation between ajñāna and Brahman. In the absence of such a relation, it would become impossible to call Brahman as Sarvajña. Ānandajñā-

8 TS, pp. 137-138 : pramāṇataḥ sarvajñatve'pi pramāṭṛtvasya pramāṇaprameyasambandhasya ca ajñānasambadhamantareṇa asiddheḥ tasmin ajñānavattvaṃ avaśyaṃ āsrayitavyaṃ anyathā sarvajñatvayogāt || ajñānaviśayatvamapi tasyaiva prāgbhūtasya [pratyagbhūtasya?] brahmaṇo'bhyupagantavyaṃ, 'mām na jānāmi tvaduktam artham na jānāmi' - iti ca bhāsamāne viśaye tasya anubhavasiddhatvāt ||

na also states that the viṣaya (object) of ajñāna is Brahman itself. How is this the case? He puts forward the direct experience of *māṃ na jānāmi tvaduktam artham na jānāmi* (I do not know myself, I do not understand the meaning of your statement). Through this line of argument, Ānandajñāna intends to prove two things; one, that there is no contradiction between Brahman being Sarvajña and its being the substratum of ajñāna, and second, that Brahman itself is also the object of ajñāna, but this is not where the argument attains a certain level of completion. Ānandajñāna puts forward another objection of his opponent and attempts to solve it :

If (it be said) that if Brahman is the substratum of ajñāna, the separation between vidvat, avidvat, guru, śiṣya and so forth (would be) unestablished, (we respond) no.

Upto the point (that) jñāna (arises), the separation is stable due to its (ajñāna's) force.

Being removed (once) jñāna is (arisen), (such) separation is not needed..

Upto the point (that there is) ajñāna, all (such) separations are possible just like svapna, but (when) ajñāna is removed by jñāna, because there is absence of (any) cause of (such) separation, there is never (such) separation.⁹

The opponent is depicted as saying that if Brahman itself is the substratum of ajñāna, how would there be a vyavasthā (categorisation) of vidvat (wise), avidvat (unwise), guru (preceptor), śiṣya (disciple) and so forth? To this, Ānandajñāna responds that upto the point where jñāna arises, all the existing vyavasthā of the said kind is reasonable, just like upto the point one is asleep, the dream appears to be reasonable and real. Once jñāna arises and removes ajñāna, such vyavasthā ceases to exist.

9 TS, p. 138 : brahmaṇaḥ cet ajñānāśrayatvaṃ, vidvadavidvad guruśiṣyādi vyavasthā('siddhiḥ iti cet, na |

yāvajjñānaṃ vyavasthāyāstadbālādeva susthatā |

sati jñāne'panītatvāna vyavasthā hyapekṣyate ||

yāvadaññānaṃ sarvavyavasthānāṃ svapnavat upapannatvāt, nivṛtte tu jñānāt ajñāne - vyavasthāhetvabhāvāt, na kadācidapi vyavasthāsti ||

Singularity of ātman and ajñāna

Upto this point, Ānandajñāna has attempted to prove that Brahman is the substratum of ajñāna. He has also stated that the vyavasthā of guru, śiṣya, and so forth is valid upto the point that jñāna has not originated. As per Advaita Vedānta, there are three avasthās (states), namely jāgrat (waking), svapna (dream) and suṣupti (dreamless sleep). Jāgrat and svapna can be clubbed together because it is only in these two that one experiences something other than one's own self. In suṣupti, there is a complete absence of such experiences. The experience of any kind of multiplicity, happens in jāgrat and svapna. This becomes the basis for the next stage of argument and exposition. Ānandajñāna begins the new stage :

Also, in svapna-avasthā, another Ātman or Avidyā need not be supplied, due to kalpanā-gaurava.¹⁰

The reason for this stage of argument is twofold; one, that there is no other Ātman in the svapna, and second, that there is no other avidyā. The basis of such an idea, as per Ānandajñāna, is kalpanāgaurava. For him, to believe that in svapna, there exists another Ātman or another avidyā is a lengthier and unnecessary way to explain svapna. He says:

(There is) One Ātman (which is) acknowledged by both of us. Through its ajñāna (which is) indisputably established, everything other than one (Ātman) appears or not? If it appears, then that complete appearance, (which is) like the world of svapna, separate from that (Ātman), manifested through its ajñāna, hence other multiple Ātmans (which are) not superimposed, are not possible. (Division of the form of) jñāna and ajñāna of those (which are) caused by this ajñāna, (and hence) are of the form of ajñāna, are not discerned, because (there is) absence of knowledge of them in that ajñāna. If recourse is not taken to the complete appearance separate from this Ātman, why would it not conflict with its vyavahāra? Because (it is on the basis of) pura, grāma and so forth (which are) separate from oneself, (that) the act of going

10 TS, p. 138: kiñca, svapnāvasthāyāṃ ātmāntaraṃ avidyāntaraṃ vā na kalpyaṃ, kalpanāgauravāt ||

and so forth is seen (through the act of) referring to it.¹¹

Ānandajñāna states for his opponent, that both of them agree on the existence of one Ātman, and that it is because of the ajñāna of that Ātman, that everything other than the one appears. It is to be noted that he calls the ajñāna of the Ātman as avivādasiddha (established without disputation). Further he says that case of jāgrat is just like that of svapnaprapaṅca (world which appears in dream), where it is from one Ātman that everything else appears due to the ajñāna related to it, because of which there is no reason to imagine the existence of multiple Ātmans in the jāgrat as well. The basis of this argument is that in svapna, though many kinds of conscious beings appear and seem to interact, they are not separate ātmans. In a similar manner, as per Ānandajñāna, one could state that in jāgrat, there is no need to think that there are multiple Ātmans, which are to be inferred from the interaction between unconscious bodies. As stated by him earlier, all the so-called real vyavasthās could be taken as valid upto the point that jñāna does not arise, just like svapna, where upto the point one does not wake up, the apparent world of svapna is as good as a real one, causing real emotions and reactions in us. For Ānandajñāna, the idea that ajñāna causes other Ātmans, is not feasible because those ātmans being caused by ajñāna, and consequently being of the form of ajñāna, the distinction between jñāna and ajñāna could not be comprehended. Hence, says Ānandajñāna, that it is necessary to accept that the apparent world made of ajñāna

11 TS, p. 138 : *ekaḥ tāvat ātmā dvayoḥ api āvayoḥ sampratipanno'sti, tasya svājñānādeva avivādasiddhāt ekasmāt atiriktaṃ sarvaṃ pratibhāti | [?] na vā [|] pratibhāti cet, tarhi taddrśyaṃ svapnaprapaṅcavat aśeṣamapi tadatiriktaṃ tadajñānavijṛmbhitaṃ iti na ātmāntarāṇi akalpitāni sambhavanti | na ca etadajñānakalpitānām etadajñānātmakānām jñānājñāne vijñāyate [vijñāyete?], etadajñāne tadanupalambhāt | na cet etasya ātmanaḥ svavyatiriktaṃ sarvadrśyaṃ āśriyate, kathaṃ asya vyavahāro na virudhyate, svavyatiriktapuragrāmādidarśanāpekṣayā taduddeṣe gamanādipravṛttidarśanāt |*

In this excerpt, the pūrṇavirāma sign has been placed after 'ekasmāt atiriktaṃ sarvaṃ pratibhāti', in which case the next sentence begins as 'na vā pratibhāti cet'. If the pūrṇavirāma is placed after 'na vā', it reads; 'ekasmāt atiriktaṃ sarvaṃ pratibhāti na vā | pratibhāti cet, tarhi taddrśyaṃ svapnaprapaṅcavat aśeṣamapi tadatiriktaṃ tadajñānavijṛmbhitaṃ iti na ātmāntarāṇi akalpitāni sambhavanti |' Such a placement of the pūrṇavirāma seems better. The translation of this excerpt is based on this placement of the pūrṇavirāma.

is fundamentally distinct from Ātman. In case such a distinction is not accepted, the vyavahāra (custom), as it happens in the apparent world, could not be explained. In the world, it is only with the things which are different from Ātman, that the actions such as going and so forth, can be performed.

Singular ajñāna with multiple ākāras

From this stage of argument, Ānandajñāna moves forward and gives a glimpse of his view of ajñāna. It is from this point onward, that a long exposition of ajñāna also begins. Ānandajñāna says:

Also, (it is) not (the case that) there is a basis for accepting infinite ajñānas in a single Cidātman, because from its single ajñāna, (which is a) possessor of various śaktis, the appearance of various objects is possible. Also, multiple ajñānas for a single Jīva are not accepted, because (on the basis of the) teaching of one Ātman (through the statement) “Tattvamasī”, (there is) absence of Jīva which is separate from Brahman. (The statement) “as many are jñānas, so many are ajñānas” (does) not have for its object the multiplicity of ajñānas, because its intended meaning is multiplicity of ākāras of a single ajñāna of Ātman.¹²

Ānandajñāna begins this stage of argument and exposition by saying that there is no reason to accept infinite ajñānas in a single cidātman (or ātman), because it is possible that one single ajñāna, which possesses various śaktis, makes appear various kinds of things. The various śaktis of one single ajñāna are connected with the various kinds of appearance in the apparent world. He further considers and rejects the idea that for each Jīva, many ajñānas are accepted, by citing the Upaniṣadic statement of ‘tattvamasī’, which for Ānandajñāna states that there is only one Ātman, implying that there is no Jīva separate from Brahman. So, neither does one Āt-

12 TS, pp. 138-139 : na ca ekasminneva cidātmani anantājñānābhyupagame nibandhanaṃ asti, tadajñānāt ekasmādeva vicitraśaktimato nānāvidhārthapratibhāsasambhavāt | na ca ekasya jīvasya anekāni ajñānāni abhyupagamyante, “tattvamasī” iti aikātmyopadeśāt jīvasyaiva brahmānirasyā (ohmātmyātirekā?)bhāvāt [brahmātiriktasyābhāvāt?] | “yāvanti jñānāni tāvanti ajñā(nā)ni” iti (asya) ca - ātmājñānasya ekasyaiva ākārābhedaḥbhīprāyatvāt - na ajñānābhedaḥvāsiyā(ka)tvam |

man possess infinite ajñānas, nor do Jīvas possess multiple ajñānas. But his opponent, who believes in the existence of multiple ajñānas, could cite a statement, which is, *yāvanti jñānāni tāvanti ajñānāni* (as many are the jñānas, so many are the ajñānas)¹³. Being a statement from a very revered philosopher of the Advaita Vedānta tradition, it could straightaway reject and disprove Ānandajñāna's idea of the singularity of ajñāna. To counter this, Ānandajñāna appeals to the abhiprāya (intended meaning) of the statement. He says that what the statement means is that there are many ākāras in ajñāna, according to their corresponding jñānas. The various śaktis which he has stated earlier in this very portion, are the ākāras. Usually, it is also based on the functions of things that the things are differentiated from one another. If ajñāna in fact possesses many ākāras, and that the multiplicity of ajñāna means the multiplicity of the ākāras of ajñāna, then one could argue that it stands for the multiplicity of ajñāna itself. To counter this, Ānandajñāna provides an example:

(It is) not (that in the case of) multiplicity of ākāras, ajñāna itself (would become) differentiated (merely due to) a separate name, because a single ajñāna corresponding to each kārya (would be) a possessor of that ākāra. (It is) not (the case that) due to multiplicity of ākāra in pitṛ, upādhyāya, śiṣya, bhrātṛ, putra, jāmātṛ, (there arises) multiplicity of svarūpa (in them). Because all of the appearance of multiplicity, which is not fundamental, is possible through the power of one ajñāna, (there is) no basis for multiplicity of ajñāna. It has been said that the difference of guru, śiṣya and so forth is possible in the case of one ajñāna (just) like svapna.¹⁴

The example which Ānandajñāna provides is that of a single person who is known as a father, teacher, disciple, brother, son, son-in-law and so forth, based on the functions he performs toward a

13 Attributed to Vimuktātman's Iṣṭasiddhi, where the statement is found as; kimanantāni śuktyajñānāni / bāḍham ; anantānyeva, yadyanantāni śuktijñānāni /

14 TS, p. 139 : na ca ākārabhede samjñāntareṇa ajñānasyaiva bhinnatvaṃ, tattatkāryapratyogikasya ekasyaiva ajñānasya tattadākārabhedabhāktvāt, na hi pitā upādhyāyaḥ śiṣyo bhrātā putro jāmātā - ityādiṣu ākārabhede'pi svarūpabhedā bhavanti | samastasyaiva apāramārthikasya ekajñānasāmārthyādeva sambhavāt na ajñānabhede hetuḥ asti | guruśiṣyādivyavasthā ca ekajñānapakṣe'pi svapnavat upapannā - ityuktam ||

certain person. For his father he is a son, for his father-in-law a son-in-law, so on and so forth. Ānandajñāna says that simply on the basis of difference of names, which is based on difference of function, the same person does not become many. Similarly is with ajñāna, which on account of the difference of ākāras (based on difference of functions), does not become many. He further says that when the complete non-fundamental appearance of multiplicity can be derived from one single ajñāna, there is no basis to accept multiple ajñānas. The multiplicity of ajñānas is conceptualised on the basis of the different functions it performs and the possibility or impossibility of those functions being performed by one single entity, which is ajñāna in this case. If all those functions can be attributed to different ākāras or śaktis of one ajñāna, to believe that there are multiple ajñānas, would be a case of kalpanāgaurava. Ānandajñāna then reminds the reader of his previous statement that the vyavasthā of guru, śiṣya and so forth, remains valid upto the point that jñāna arises, just as in the case of svapna and the world experienced in svapna.

Two ākāras for two avasthās : At this point the opponent puts forward another question:

Does the ajñāna (which is the) cause of svapna, alone (is the) cause of vyavahāra of jāgrat? Or another (one)? (This has) to be stated. (If the) first option (is correct), in wakefulness the ajñāna (which is the) cause of svapna ends, (then) all vyavahāra of jāgrat also would end, hence (there) would be mukti without Brahmavidyā, and (if) ajñāna does not end, because (there would be) absence of example (to establish) removal of ajñāna through Tattvajñāna, the removal of ajñāna through Brahmajñāna would not be established. (If) the second option (is correct), (there would be) establishing of multiplicity of avidyā. Just as the multiple ajñānas (which are) the differentiators of jāgrat and svapna (have been) accepted, in the same manner there is no fault in accepting, based on the appearance of infinite vyāvahārika Jīvas in the form of liberated, non-liberated and so forth, (for example) Śuka, Vāmadeva, Pāmara and so forth, the infinite ajñānas (which are) the causes of (their appearances), for the reasonability (of

the said appearances).¹⁵

The opponent asks if the ajñāna which produces svapna, also produces jāgrat. If it does, then when svapna ends and a person wakes up, even jāgrat would end, and so without even attaining Brahmajñāna, one would attain mukti. Along with this, the opponent says that if ajñāna does not get removed, the idea that it would, because of tattvajñāna, does not have a dr̥ṣṭānta (example) to support it, in which case the idea that Brahmajñāna causes removal of ajñāna, cannot be established. If it is believed that the ajñāna which causes svapna is different from that which causes jāgrat, then it would establish multiplicity of ajñānas. Further the opponent says that just like one could accept multiple ajñānas for jāgrat and svapna, similarly one could accept infinite ajñānas connected with Jīvas who are of various kinds; mukta (liberated), amukta (non-liberated), and so forth. Ānandajñāna responds to this:

Although the ajñāna (which is the) cause of svapna and jāgarita (is) one alone, (and) there is no difference of svarūpa, even then, because the difference of ākāra in it has been stated, in wakefulness even (though) the ākāra of ajñāna (which is the) cause of svapna ends, the vyavahāra of jāgrat does not end, because the ākāra of ajñāna (which is the) cause of that, has not ended. (It is) not reasonable (to say) that in this way, because (there is) absence of example (to establish) removal of ajñāna through tattvajñāna, (the idea of) removal of ajñāna through brahmajñāna is not established, because without the need for an example, the ascertainment of end of ajñāna through jñāna (happens) through the authority of śāstra (like) “taratī śokamātmavit” (and) so forth. Also (it should) not be said that through the authority of śruti (statements like) “bhūyaścānte viśvamāyānivṛtīḥ”, “indro māyābhiḥ” (and so

15 TS, p. 139: nanu- kiṃ svapnakalpapakameva ajñānaṃ jāgradvyavahārakalpakaṃ, uta anyat iti vaktavyam | ādye, prabodhe svapnakalpakājñānanivṛtttau, jāgradvyavahāro'pi sarvo nivarteta iti brahmavidyāṃ vinaiva muktiḥ syāt; anivṛtttau ca ajñānasya - tattvajñānāt tannivṛtttau dr̥ṣṭāntābhā(vā)t - brahmajñānāt ajñānanivṛtīḥ na sidhyet | dviṭīye tu, avidyābhedasiddhiḥ | yathā hi jāgratsvapnavibhedakaṃ nānā ajñānaṃ abhyupagataṃ, tathaiiva muktāmuktādirūpeṇa vyāvahārikānantajīvanāṃ śukavāmadevapāmaraprabhṛtīnāṃ pratibhānāt tadupapattaye taddhetubhūtānantājñānābhyupagame'pi na kiñcit dūṣaṇam

forth), let multiple ajñānas and their sequential destruction be accepted, because on the basis of the aforementioned śruti (statements), even (though there is) acceptance of difference of ākāras of ajñāna and the sequence of their destruction, by (its) svarūpa (there is) absence of mūlājñāna, (which is a) possessor of multiple ākāras, (and) because its destruction (is) based on tattvajñāna, has been stated.¹⁶

Ānandajñāna reiterates his point that in his concept of ajñāna, there is ākārabheda (multiplicity of ākāras) and not svarūpabheda (multiplicity of svarūpa). Therefore, when the ākāra which causes svapna, ends, there still exists the ākāra which causes jāgrat. Regarding the idea that there is no dṛṣṭānta to suggest that ajñāna would be removed by tattvajñāna, Ānandajñāna says that it is through the statements of the Upaniṣads like ‘tarati śokamātmavit’ (the one who knows ātman, overcomes grief), that the removal of ajñāna through tattvajñāna is established, without the need of a dṛṣṭānta. The reason of this statement by Ānandajñāna is that Upaniṣad is śabdapramāṇa, in which case it does not need dṛṣṭāntas to establish its statements. Further, says Ānandajñāna, that even though one may accept multiple ajñānas and a sequence of destruction of ajñāna, on the basis of Upaniṣadic statements like ‘bhūyaścānte viśvamāyanivṛtīḥ’, ‘indro māyābhiḥ’ and so forth, the mūlājñāna, which possesses multiple ākāras, does not exist by its own self (svarūpa), and hence its destruction by tattvajñāna has been stated earlier. In conclusion of this portion, Ānandajñāna says that because the difference in relation to

16 TS, p. 139 : yadyapi svapnajāgaritayoḥ ekameva kalpakam ajñānam - na tatra svarūpabhedo'sti, tathā'pi tasmin ākārabhedasya udīritatvāt prabodhe svapnakalpakājñānakāre nivṛtte'pi jāgradvyavahāro na nivartate, taddhetvajñānakārasya anivṛttatvāt | na ca - evaṃ tattvajñānāt ajñāna(ni) vṛttau dṛṣṭāntā(bhā)vāt brahma(jñānāda)jñānanivṛtīḥ na sidhyet - iti yuktam, dṛṣṭāntapekṣam antareṇa “tarati śokamātmavit” ityādi śāstrapramāṇyādeva jñānāt ajñānanivṛttyadhyavasāyat | na ca - tarhi “bhūyaścānte viśvamāyanivṛtīḥ” “indro māyābhiḥ” ityādiśrutipramāṇyāt anekāni ajñānāni tannivṛttayaśca krameṇa iti svikriyatam - iti vācyam, darśitaśrutyaṣṭambhāt ajñānakārabhedaḥ svanivṛttikramaśca ityaṅgikāre'pi - mūlājñānasya anekākāravataḥ svarūpe(ṇa) abhāvāt, tattvajñānāyattāyāśca tannivṛtteḥ uktatvāt | na ca svapnajāgradbhedakam anekam ajñānam abhiṣṭam, tatprakārabhede'pi tatsvarūpabhedaḥbhāvasya uktatvāt | ato na taddṛṣṭāntena muktāmuktādirūpeṇa anantajīvapratibhānopapattaye taddhetubhūtanantājñānābhhyupagamopapattiḥ |

ajñāna is that of ākāra and not svarūpa, it is not reasonable to imagine infinite ajñānas for infinite Jīvas. Ānandajñāna has used the term mūlājñāna in this portion of his argument. Mūlājñāna here refers to the basal ajñāna, which possesses various ākāras. He has also stated that it does not exist per se, that is, it does not exist on its own. Hence, if it is thought to be an independently existing entity, ajñāna does not exist. It is its dependency on Ātman or Brahman that makes it destructible. Ānandajñāna continues his argument :

Also, by the words Śuka, Vāmadeva, Pāmara and so forth, (is) the specific upādhi, or (is) that which is connected with the specific upādhi, or (is) the complete pure Caitanya being stated? In the first and second (options), because that which is connected with upādhi is superimposed, is included in ajñāna and its effects, jñāna and ajñāna are not possible. In the third (option), due to the absence of appearance in it, one ajñāna (which) resides with essential Caitanya, is the cause of all appearances. (This is the way) our desired (thesis) is established.¹⁷

Ānandajñāna further explores the options regarding the nature of Jīvas, who are divided on the basis of jñāna and ajñāna. The typical examples of such varied Jīvas are Śuka, Vāmadeva, Pāmara, and so forth. Are they upādhi? Or are connected with upādhi? Or are they Brahman? He rejects the first and second options because the upādhis and even those connected with upādhis are included in ajñāna and its effects, due to which they cannot be divided on the basis of jñāna and ajñāna. He accepts the third option saying that it establishes his concept, that is, a single ajñāna which resides in Caitanya which is the essence (niṣkṛṣṭacaitanya), is the cause of the appearance of multiplicity. Here again, Ānandajñāna rejects the idea that each Jīva has separate or infinite ajñānas. As per the opponent, Jīvas are of many kinds, that is, mainly those with jñāna, and those without ajñāna. Ānandajñāna explores the idea that Jīvas are sep-

17 TS, p. 140 : kiñca śukavāmadevapāmaraśabdaiḥ tattadupādhimātram vā tattadupādhyupahitam vā niṣkalam vā pariśuddham caitanyam parigīyate? tatra prathame dviṭīye ca, upādhisahitasya ca kalpitatvena ajñānatatkāryāntarbhāvāt na jñānājñāne yujyete | ṭṛtīye tu, tasminneva pratibhānābhāvāt niṣkṛṣṭacaitanyaniviṣṭam ekameva ajñānam akhilabhedapratibhānanidānam iti asmadabhiṣṭasiddhiḥ ||

arate from Brahman. In the options he presents for his opponent, the options related to upādhi have no room for such a difference of types in Jīvas, because the division of jñāna and ajñāna is impossible, the reason being that the upādhis are themselves the effects of ajñāna. The last option is that the Jīvas are Brahman, in which case, says Ānandajñāna, that his concept is established, which is, one single ajñāna resides in Brahman, and is the cause of the experience of multiplicity.

Avidyāleśa and Jīvanmukti

Ānandajñāna takes up a small yet significant idea from the opponent, that is, the one who attains jñāna of Brahman, still experiences dvaita (duality). If that is the case, how would it be proved that attaining jñāna destroys ajñāna? As has been stated, ajñāna is one, so if ajñāna is destroyed, it should be destroyed as a whole, unless it also has parts. At this point, Ānandajñāna refers to the term avidyāleśa (a bit of avidyā). He says :

Because it has been accepted that (for the) wise also (there is) appearance of dvaita, due to a bit of avidyā.¹⁸

Leśa means a minute portion or part. Ānandajñāna says that even in the case of someone who has realised Brahman, a minute part of avidya or ajñāna could remain existent, due to which they could still experience the appearance of dvaita. This small portion of Ānandajñāna's argument suggests that in his conception, ajñāna could be seen as something which has parts, or acts as if it has parts. Earlier he has stated multiple ākāras of ajñāna, which differ from each other in function. Here, leśa also seems to point to some ākāra, or something like an ākāra which is potent enough to produce the experience of dvaita. Why this leśa could remain existent even after attaining jñāna, is another question which deserves a detailed reading and analysis, which is beyond the purview of this paper.

Ajñāna's relation to Jīva

Ānandajñāna has earlier stated that the substratum of ajñāna is Brahman and not Jīva. A Jīva which is separate and independent of

18 TS, p. 140 : viduṣo'pyavidyāleśavaśāt dvaitapratibhānābhyupagamāt ||

Brahman is not accepted in Advaita Vedānta. Upto this point, even after a lot of refutation, discussion and analysis, we do not find any answer as to how does ajñāna relate to Jīva. So, Ānandajñāna begins a small exposition on this issue. He says:

So, in this way one ajñāna (which) has Cidātman as its substratum, (and) has it as its object, alone (is the) accomplisher of all vyavahāra, appears (to be) biased toward Jīva. (It is) seen (that) the mirror, (which is) related to only the face, (is) biased toward the reflection. Also, it has been said that in truth, Jīva is not separate from Cidātman, because of the teaching of unity. And it is said, that by the (authority of) śruti “brahma vā idamagra āsit”, the complete Cidātma-tattva through its ajñāna, having experienced the world (which is) undesirable, experiences peace by the destruction of that (ajñāna) through its jñāna. Through the śruti (statements) like “tadyo yo devānāṃ pratyabudhyata”, by the reiteration of multiplicity established through error, this alone is demonstrated that by the destruction of ajñāna through tattvajñāna, puruṣārtha is achieved, (and through the same statements) multiplicity of Jīva or avidyā is not stated, because (in that case there would be) a contradiction with the pramāṇa of (the existence of) one Ātman.¹⁹

Ānandajñāna again states that Cidātman (that which is of the form of jñāna) is the substratum of one ajñāna, and is also the viṣaya (object) of the same ajñāna. He adds that just like a mirror which is actually related to a face, is much more connected with the reflection of the face, in a similar manner, ajñāna is much more related to, or appears as being related to Jīva, which may be imagined as a reflection of Brahman in ajñāna. He repeats that Jīva is not something other than Brahman, for him, Upaniṣadic statements like ‘brahma

19 TS, p. 140 : tadevaṃ - cidātmāśrayaṃ tadviṣayaṃ ca ajñānaṃ ekameva aśeṣavyavahāranirvāhakaṃ jīvapakṣapāti pratibhāti | dṛṣṭaṃ hi loke mukhamā(tra)sambandhino'pi darpaṇasya pratibimbapakṣapātitvam | na jīvaḥ cidātmano vastutaḥ atiricyate, tādātmyopadeśāt - iyuktam | kiñca, “brahma vā idamagra āsit” ityā(di)śrutyā paripūraṇacidātmatattvameva svājñānāt ānarthātmakaṃ (anarthātmakaṃ?) saṃsāraṃ anubhūya svājñānāt tannivṛtṭyā svāsthyam anubhavati - iti ucyate | “tadyo yo devānāṃ pratyabudhyata” ityādyayā śrutyā ca bhrāntisiddhabhedānūvādena tattvajñānāt ajñānanivṛtṭyā puruṣārthasiddhiḥ - ityetāvanmātraṃ pradarśyate, na tu jīvabhedo avidyābhedo vā nigadyate, aikātmyapramāṇavirodhaprasaṅgāt |

vā idamagra āsīt' (this Brahman alone was in the beginning) tell that pure Ātman, which is Brahman, comes in contact with its own ajñāna, experiences the saṃsāra, and then through the jñāna of its own self, feels at peace. Regarding the Upaniṣadic phrases like 'tadyo yo devānāṃ pratyabudhyata' and so forth, which seem to establish multiplicity of Jīvas and ajñānas, Ānandajñāna says that through the anuvāda (reiteration) of illusory multiplicity, they only state the destruction of ajñāna through jñāna and do not establish the multiplicity of Jīvas and ajñānas. In this portion of his argument, one gets a hint about how Ānandajñāna thought about the relation between Jīvas and ajñāna. He has earlier stated that, by its own self, ajñāna does not exist. Its existence is dependent on Brahman. It is only when Brahman becomes the viṣaya of ajñāna, that it appears to itself as Jīva, through the jñāna of itself as 'I am Brahman', it destroys ajñāna. This destruction of ajñāna may take time, for reasons discussed elsewhere in the relevant portions of texts of Advaita Vedānta. Even the smallest part of ajñāna has been thought to be potent enough to cause the experience of dvaita in a person who has realised themselves as Brahman.

Anirvācyatva of ajñāna

At this point, Ānandajñāna wraps up and concludes the whole discussion and says:

Hence, (there is) one Brahman (which is) caitanya itself, appears (to be) bound due to avidyā (which is) without beginning, without definition and without limits. That (Brahman) itself appears as if liberated, due to the direct knowledge of tattva (through) statements (of Upaniṣads). It should be acknowledged that in reality, (there is) no bondage or liberation in it, instead (there is only) the complete fundamental, inward, existence-knowledge-bliss itself (which is) Brahman, (and) is of the form of highest puruṣārtha.²⁰

20 TS, pp. 140-141 : tasmāt ekameva brahma caitanyaikatānaṃ anādyanirvācyānavacchinnāvidyāsambandhāt baddhamiva pratibhāsate | tadeva ca vākyiyatattvasākṣātkārāt ekākino muktamiva bhavati | vastutastu na tatra bandho muktiḥ vā asti, kintu paripūrṇaṃ paraṃ brahma pratyagbhūtaṃ saccidānandaikatānaṃ apākṛtāśeṣānarthaṃ paramapuruṣārtharūpaṃ - iti āstheyam |

He adds a few more points about ajñāna or avidyā. He calls it anādi, anirvācyā and anavacchinna. Ajñāna has no beginning, but has an end, through jñāna. It is anirvācyā or indefinable as existent, nonexistent and existent-nonexistent. Ānandajñāna has defined anirvācyatva as:

(This) nirvacana (of anirvācyatva) is ascertained; while not being the substratum of sattva, while not being the substratum of asattva, not being the substratum of sadasattva is anirvācyatva.²¹

Ānandajñāna defines anirvācyā as that which is not the substratum of sadasattva, while not being the substratum of sattva and asattva. It means that something which cannot be defined as sat (existent), asat (nonexistent) and also sadasat (existent-nonexistent), is anirvācyā and so is ajñāna. He further says that ajñāna is anavacchinna. Avacchinna means limited, and so its antonym anavacchinna means that which is not limited. It could mean that ajñāna is not limited by the descriptions of sat, asat and sadasat, which is why it is anirvācyā. But such a meaning would be repetitive, because Ānandajñāna has already called it anirvācyā. So it could mean this; although ajñāna is the basis of limits of deśa, kāla and so forth, ajñāna itself is not limited by deśa (space), kāla (time) and so forth. It is because of this reason that it is said to have the potential to produce the appearance of a world so complex and layered. Limits like deśa, kāla and so forth are themselves effects of ajñāna. This is also congruent with the Ānandajñāna's statement where he says that ajñāna possesses varied śaktis. Along with this, the idea that a very small portion of ajñāna could produce the experience of multiplicity, further gives a glimpse of what kind those śaktis or ākāras could be.

Discussion

Advaita Vedānta accepts the existence of ajñāna or avidyā, which is the cause of the appearance of multiplicity. As has been stated by Ānandajñāna, it does not exist on its own, that is, independently. Had it been independently existent, any attempt to get rid of it would

21 TS, p. 136 : sattvānadhikaraṇatve sati asattvānadhikaraṇatve sati sadasattvānadhikaraṇam [sadasattvānadhikaraṇatvaṃ?] anirvācyatvaṃ - iti nirvacanaṃ paryavasyati |

have been in vain. To say that ajñāna has a dependent existence, one needs to answer the entity on which its existence depends. When it comes to such an entity, one has only two options; Brahman and Jīva. This is where Ānandajñāna's detailed exposition on ajñāna in relation with Brahman and Jīva begins. He accepts Brahman as the substratum of ajñāna. He goes on to show how Brahman's being Sarvajña is not in contradiction to its being a substratum of ajñāna. When one says that Brahman is Sarvajña, one has to derive the existence of all that which is included in 'sarva', a word which is based on multiplicity. For an Advaita Vedānta philosopher, multiplicity can only be derived from ajñāna. In this way, Brahman becomes Sarvajña because of ajñāna. In case, one takes Brahman's Sarvajñatva as being its nature, even then the expression of its Sarvajñatva would need Brahman's being in contact with objects, and objects are an effect of ajñāna. To take Jīvas as the substrata of ajñāna has its own set of problems. Firstly, Advaita Vedānta does not take Jīvas to be existing independently from Brahman, and secondly, Jīva itself is a product of ajñāna insofar as its separateness from Brahman is concerned. The Jīvatva of a Jīvas being dependent on ajñāna, Jīvas cannot become the substrata of ajñāna.

Further, the question of multiplicity of ajñāna is raised. Ānandajñāna states that it is not the ajñāna which is multiple, but the ākāras, prakāras or śaktis of ajñāna that are multiple. These ākāras are the cause of various kinds of experience. A certain ākāra is capable of producing only one kind of experience. For example, the experience of svapna is caused by the ajñānākāra related specifically to svapna. Once a person wakes up, another ajñānākāra enters the picture and causes the jāgrat experience. Similarly, the appearance of each distinct thing which is a part of one's experience, can be attributed to a specific kind of ajñānākāra instead of a completely different ajñāna. Each ākāra of the ajñāna is to be inferred from each distinct experience. It seems that Ānandajñāna has used the terms śakti, ākāra, prakāra and leśa to refer to the same thing. It also seems that in his scheme of things, ajñāna imitates something which is made of parts. Towards the end of his exposition, he calls ajñāna as anavacchinna, which seems to exclude ajñāna of things which are limited in space and time. So ajñāna, which behaves like something which has parts,

is fundamentally something which is devoid of parts, and has an existence dependent on Brahman. Ajñāna is hence anirvācyā, because it is not sat, asat and not even sadasat. Ānandajñāna states that the basal ajñāna or mūlajñāna is nonexistent by its svarūpa, that is, it does not exist independently or it does not exist per se. Although it is called anirvācyā, yet this opinion about it hints toward its having an illusory existence. This is because at the level of custom, anything which does not exist by itself, is taken to be illusory, like the snake which appears on the rope. Something which is illusory can be removed by direct knowledge about the thing on which the illusion seems to exist. In a similar manner, direct knowledge of Brahman is said to remove ajñāna once and for all.

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Study of The Passages of Śivadharma Texts Cited in Śaivakalpadurma and Śivāmṛtsārasamuccaya

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Abstract

Śivadharma texts, otherwise known as Śivadharma corpus, are ancient literature for lay Saivites. Of those Śivadharma texts, Śivadharma and Śivadharmottara are the most important and authoritative texts which have a wider presence. Manuscripts of these two texts are found in almost every part of India, and passages from those texts are also found to be cited in different texts in various contexts. Odisha's Saiva literature is not an exception in this matter. Śivadharma and Śivadharmottara seem to have influenced the Saivite literature of Odisha to a greater extent. In this background, this paper aims to discuss at length the passages of Śivadharma and Śivadharmottara cited specifically in Śaivakalpadruma and Śivāmṛtsārasamuccaya, two important Saiva literature proper of Odisha.

Keywords: Śivadharma, Śaivakalpadruma, Śivāmṛtsārasamuccaya, Saivism, Odisha

Introduction

Lord Śiva is one of the three prime deities of Hindus. Those who are ardent devotees of lord Śiva are called Śaivas, and the distinctive doctrines, behaviours, and characteristics of Śaivas are called Saivism. Śaivas are one of the ancient and popular sects of the Hindu religion spread throughout India and in some parts of Southeast Asian countries, and they could be broadly divided into two categories namely orthodox and unorthodox. Pāśupatas, Kāpālikas,

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Kālāmukhas, etc. are orthodox Śaivas, and others who in general keep devotion towards lord Śiva and observe daily worship and vows are called unorthodox or lay Śaivas. Orthodox Śiva devotees are specifically initiated into sectarian doctrines and practices of Śaivas, and they have their typical scriptures to follow. Unlike orthodox, lay Śaivas follow the path of devotional practices prescribed in different Puranas and *paurāṇic* texts. Among those *paurāṇic* Śaiva literature for lay Saivites, Śivadharmā texts are ancient and authoritative. Śivadharmā texts are eight in number, viz. Śivadharmāsāstra (SDS), Śivadharmottara (SDU), Śivadharmasamgraha, Vṛṣasārasamgraha, etc., and are otherwise called Śivadharmā corpus. Of these eight Śivadharmā texts, Śivadharmā and Śivadharmottara are the most important and have a wider presence. Manuscripts of those two are found in almost every part of India, and passages from those texts are also found to be cited in different texts in various contexts.

Śaivakalpadruma (SKD) and Śivāmṛtsārasamuccaya (SASS) are two Śaivite *nibandha* texts belonging to the lay Saivite tradition of 17th-century Odisha, authored by Lakshmidhara Mishra of Ekāmra (old Bhubaneswar) and Śrīśadeva of Gauḍa region, respectively. SKD and SASS are complete with eight and forty chapters, respectively. These texts cite passages from the abovementioned SDS and SDU texts to explain different subject matters about the worship of lord Śiva. Preliminary observations on the cited passages attributed to SDS and SDU in both SKD and SASS were published in my article “*Traces of Śivadharmā and Śivadharmottara in the Śaiva Texts in Odisha*”.² This article could be referred to for more facts, i.e. regarding authors, probable date, contents, etc., on these two texts. Also, an Odia edition of SKD, jointly edited by myself and Dr. Mamata Mahapatra, was recently published, and the verse numbers of SKD mentioned in this work are as per that edition, and, the draft digital edition of SASS has been consulted to prepare this article. It is worth mentioning in this context that, the preparation of critical editions of both SKD and SASS in the Devanagari script have been undertaken by me as two separate independent projects and those editions are in progress and will soon be published in coming years. In this background, this paper aims to compile the passages

of Śivadharma texts cited in SKD and SASS to present a comparative study with the presently available parallel passages of Śivadharma texts. It is worth mentioning that here the term ‘Śivadharma texts’ denotes SDS and SDU only, and two printed editions of those two texts have been consulted for this work. Those two editions are 1. Text titled *Paśupatimatam Śivadharma-mahāśāstram Paśupatināthadarśanam*, Edited by Yogi Naraharinath, published from Nepal in the year Nepal Saṃvat 2055 (CE 1998) which contains all the texts of the Śivadharma corpus (Nep.). 2. Two separate texts titled *Śrīmad-śivadarmapurāṇam* and *Śrīmad-śivadharmottarapurāṇam*, Edited with own sufficient notes & translation by Dr. Srikrishna ‘Jugnu’ and Prof. Bhanvar Sharma, Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series Office, Varanasi, 2014 & 2016 (Chow.). Besides, a paper transcript of SDS numbered T32 preserved in the manuscript repository of the French Institute of Pondicherry (T32 IFP) is occasionally consulted for this work. Passages attributed to SDS and SDU in SKD and SASS along with the variant reading found in the printed editions of SDS and SDU are recorded as endnote in this article.

Passages of Śivadharma texts cited in Śaivakalpadruma

Śivadharmaśāstra cited in Śaivakalpadruma

- Chapter – I: Passages attributed to SDS have been cited thrice in this chapter³ of SKD. All together six verses, viz. verse no. 28, 29, 37, 80, 81, 82, are cited, and all those are found almost parallel with verses available in the 7th and 3rd chapters of the printed editions of the SDS. First, 28th and 29th verses

3 तथा च शिवधर्मे – दक्षिणाङ्गाद्भवेद्ब्रह्मा (दक्षिणाङ्गे भवेद्ब्रह्मा-ने.सं; दक्षिणाङ्गे भवो ब्रह्मा-चौ.सं.) ह्रिर्वामाङ्गसम्भवः । हृदयान्निर्गतो रुद्रो (हृदयान्नीलरुद्रश्च-चौ.सं.) ब्रह्मविष्णुप्रबोधकः ॥28 ॥ जगत्सृष्टिकरो ब्रह्मा विष्णुर्लोकविमोहकः । अनुग्रहकरो नित्यं नीलो रुद्रः (लीनोरुद्रः-ने.सं; नीलरुद्रः-चौ.सं.) शिवात्मकः ॥29 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 7.45-46, pp.46-47; Chow. -7.49cd-51ab)/ शिवधर्मे -अर्धमात्रापरो (अर्धमात्रात्परो-ने.सं) देवः (रुद्रः-ने.सं; चौ.सं.) शिवः परमकारणम् । तस्मादेतत्समुत्पन्नं जगतः कारणत्वम् ॥37 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 7.49, p.47; Chow.-7.53cd-54ab)/ तथा च शिवधर्मे - ब्रह्मा च पूजयेत्लिङ्गं नित्यं शैलमयं पुरा (ब्रह्मा पूजयते नित्यं लिङ्गं शैलमयं शुभम्-ने.सं; चौ.सं.) । तस्य सम्पूजनात्तेन प्राप्तं ब्रह्मत्वमुत्तमम् ॥80 ॥(Parallel with Nep.-3.23cd-24ab, p.6; Chow.-3.30) इन्द्रनीलमयं लिङ्गं विष्णुर्चयते (विष्णुः पूजयते-चौ.सं.) सदा । विष्णुत्वं प्राप्तवांस्तेन अच्युतैकसनातनम् (अर्चितेन सनातनम्-ने.सं; सोऽद्भुतैकं सनातनम्-चौ.सं.) ॥81 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.-3.28cd-29ab, p.6; Chow.-3.31) शक्रोऽपि देवराजेन्द्रो लिङ्गं मणिमयं स्मृतम् (शुभम्- ने.सं; चौ.सं.) । भक्त्या पूजयते नित्यं तेन शक्रत्वमाप्नुयात् (तेनेन्द्रत्वमाप स-ने.सं; तेन शक्रत्वमाप्तवान्-चौ.सं.) ॥82 ॥(Parallel with Nep.-3.24cd-25ab, p.6; Chow.-3.32)

have been cited in the context of explaining the faith that both Brahmā and Viṣṇu are parts of Lord Śiva; second, 37th verse has been cited in the context of narrating Lord Śiva as the cause of this universe; third, 80th to 82nd verses have been cited to describe that Brahmā, Viṣṇu, and Indra have obtained their power and position by worshipping Lord Śiva in the form of *linga* made of different substances viz. *śaila*, *indnīla*, and *maṇi*, respectively. In the process of comparison between passages from different editions of SDS and citations attributed to SDS in the first chapter of the SKD, it is observed that the sequence and vocabulary of verses 80th to 82nd of SKD are alike with the SDS of Chow. than Nep.

2. Chapter – II: In this chapter of SKD, passages attributed to SDS have been cited twice⁴, of which the first is a complete verse quoted in the context of defining Dakṣiṇāmūrti *linga* (*dakṣiṇāmūrtiliṅgalakṣaṇa*) and another a half verse in the context of *mālānīrnaya* (*rudrākṣamāhātmya*). No parallel of the first verse is yet found in the printed editions of the SDS, and the half verse is parallel with a half verse in the 12th chapter of the printed editions of SDS. In the context of the non-availability of parallel verse on *dakṣiṇāmūrtiliṅgalakṣaṇa*, it is worthy to mention herewith that SDS's 7th chapter in verse no. 68 mentions the term 'śivadakṣiṇāmūrtau'⁵ and the verse no. 11 of the 9th chapter mentions the term 'dakṣiṇāmūrtau'⁶. This shows that the concept of Dakṣiṇāmūrti was known to the author of the SDS, and therefore it seems that the verse in question may be available in other MSS of SDS. Also explaining the abovementioned passage of SDS it has been mentioned in the SKD that the term 'dakṣiṇasya' means the southern side of a west-faced *liṅga* (*paścimābhīmukhaliṅgasya dakṣiṇapārśve*) and the term 'yatomūrti' has been explained as - "akāro vāsudevasyāditi vacanāt| asya vāsudevasya yatomūrtir ityanvayah|".

4 दक्षिणामूर्तिशब्दस्य व्याख्यामाह शिवधर्म - वामदेवाननं यत्र तत्र गौरीजनार्दनौ । दक्षिणेऽस्य यतोमूर्तिर्दक्षिणामूर्तिरिति ॥49 ॥ (No parallel yet found)/ तथा च शिवधर्मे रुद्राक्षमालामाहात्म्ये – जपश्च (जपाच्च-चौ.सं.) रुद्रमन्त्राणां कोटी कोटी गुणोत्तरम्| (कोटिकोटिगुणोत्तरम्-ने.सं; चौ.सं.) इति वचनात् सावश्यं कार्या । (Parallel with Nep. 12.570ab, p.174; Chow. 12.106cd)

5 शिवदक्षिणामूर्तौ तु तत्पुण्यमयुताऽधिकम् । 7.68ab, Chow.

6 स्थाप्य दक्षिणामूर्तौ तु बिल्वपत्रैस्तदर्चयेत् । 9.11ab, Chow.

3. Chapter – III: This chapter of SKD cites passages attributed to SDS fourteen times, viz. verses 2-4, 15, 17-21, 25, 27-30, 50-52, 63, 139, 145-146, 153, 165-170, 187-188, 191, and 234 – 236⁷ of SKD. These verses are quoted in different con-

- 7 शिवधर्मे शिववाक्यम् -मद्भक्तजनवात्सल्यं पूजायां चानुमोदनम् (पूजायाश्चानुमोदनम्-ने.सं.; पूजायमनुमोदनम्-चौ.सं.)। स्वयमभ्यर्चनं कृत्वा (स्वयं मेऽभ्यर्चनं कुर्यात्-ने.सं.; स्वयमभ्यर्चनं भक्त्या-चौ.सं.) ममायं चाङ्गचेष्टितम् ॥2 ॥ मत्कथाश्रवणे भक्तिः स्वरनेत्वाङ्गविक्रिया। ममानुस्मरणं नित्यं (ममानुसंस्मरन्नित्यं-ने.सं.) यश्च मां नोपजीवति (मां नोपजीवति-ने.सं.; मां चोपजीवति-चौ.सं.) ॥3 ॥ भक्तिरष्टविधा ह्येषा यस्मिन् म्लेच्छेऽपि वर्तते। स विप्रेन्द्रो मुनिः श्रीमान् स यतिः स च पण्डितः ॥4 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 1.27-29, p.2; Chow. 1.27-29)/ तथा च शिवधर्मे – यः शिवब्रह्मचारी स्यात्स शिवार्चाऽग्निदत्परः। भवेज्जितेन्द्रियः शान्तो नैष्ठिको भूतिकोऽथवा (भौतिकोऽपि वा-चौ.सं.) ॥15 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 11.378, p.145; Chow. 11.117) / तथा च शिवधर्मे – शिवार्चाग्निपरो (शिवार्चनपरो-चौ.सं.) नित्यं तद्भक्तोऽतिथिपूजकः (तद्भक्तानाश्च) भोजनं-ने.सं.; तद्भक्तातिथिपूजकः -चौ.सं.)। सर्वमैथुनवर्जं च (पर्वमैथुनवर्जः स्यात्-ने.सं.; पर्वमैथुनवर्जो स्याद्-चौ.सं.) श्रीमान् (धीमान्-चौ.सं.) शिवगृहश्रमी ॥17 ॥ देवाय्यतिथिभैक्षार्थं पचेन्नैवात्मकारणम् (नैवार्यकारणात्-चौ.सं.)। आत्मार्थं यः पचेन्मोहान्नरकार्यं स जीवति ॥18 ॥ देवार्थं पचनं येषां सन्तानार्थं च (सन्तानार्थन्तु-ने.सं.) मैथुनम्। स्वर्गार्थं जीवितं तेषां नरकार्यं विपर्यये (नरकार्यविपर्यये-ने.सं.) ॥19 ॥ वित्ततृतीयभागेन प्रकुर्वीत शिवार्चनम्। कुर्वीत वा तदर्थेन यतोऽनित्यं हि जीवितम् ॥20 ॥ न्यायेनोपार्जयेद् वित्तमन्यायं परिवर्जयेत्। अन्यायोपार्जितैर्वित्तैर् (अन्यायेनार्जितैर्वित्तैर्-चौ.सं.) नरकार्यं हि जीवितम् (स जीवति-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) ॥21 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 11.373-377, p.144; Chow. 11.11-13, 15-16) / शिवधर्मे -सर्वसङ्गविनिर्मुक्तः (सर्वरोगविनिर्मुक्तः-चौ.सं.) कन्दमूलफलाशनः। शिववैखानसो ज्ञेयः शिवार्चाऽग्निपरो (शिवार्चनपरो-चौ.सं.) भवेत् ॥25 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 11.379, p.145; Chow. 11.18) / शिवधर्मे - निवृत्तः सर्वसङ्गभ्यः (सर्वरोगभ्यः-चौ.सं.) शिवध्यानरतः सदा। ज्ञेयः शिवः यतिः श्रीमान् भस्मलिप्तो (ज्ञेयः शिवव्रतीन्द्रोऽयं भस्मनिष्ठो- ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) जितेन्द्रियः ॥27 ॥ जटी मुण्डी शिखी (जटामुण्डीशिखी-चौ.सं.) वाऽपि भिक्षाशी विगतस्पृहः। मौनी भूतानुकम्पी च (भूतानुकम्प्य-चौ.सं.) यतिः शान्तमतिश्चरत् (शान्तमनाश्चरत्-चौ.सं.) ॥28 ॥ चरेन्माधुकरं भिक्षाम् (माधुकरीञ्चरद् भैक्षम्-ने.सं.; माधुकरं चरेद् वृत्ति-चौ.सं.) एकाग्रं परिवर्जयेत्। उपवासात्परं भैक्ष्यमेकाग्रं गृहीणां मत्तम् (गृहीणां मत्तम्-ने.सं.; गृहीणाऽऽहृतम्-चौ.सं.) ॥29 ॥ सर्वसङ्गविनिर्मुक्तः (यः सर्वसङ्गविनिर्मुक्तः-चौ.सं.) शुद्रः (शुद्रः-ने.सं.; शिवः-चौ.सं.) शिवपरायणः। सोऽपीह वपनं कृत्वा योगीन्द्रानुचरो भवेत् ॥30 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 11.380, 404-406, pp.145, 148-149; Chow. 11.19, 48cd-51ab) / शिवधर्मे -ब्रह्मचारिसहस्रेभ्यो वेदाध्यायी (गृहस्था हि-चौ.सं.) विशिष्यते। वेदाध्यायिसहस्रेभ्यो (गृहसंस्थ सहस्रेभ्यो-चौ.सं.) अग्निहोत्री (ह्यग्निहोत्र-ने.सं.; ह्यग्निहोत्री-चौ.सं.) विशिष्यते ॥50 ॥ अग्निहोत्रिसहस्रेभ्यो यज्ञयाजी (सत्रयाजी-चौ.सं.) विशिष्यते। यज्ञयाजिसहस्रेभ्यः सत्रयाजी विशिष्यते (नोपलभ्यते-चौ.सं.) ॥51 ॥ शतयाजिसहस्रेभ्यः (सत्रयाजिसहस्रेभ्यः-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) सर्वविद्यान्तपाराः (सर्वविद्यार्थपराः-चौ.सं.)। सर्वविद्याविल्कोटिभ्यः (सर्वविद्याविद्वकोटिभ्यः-ने.सं.; सर्वविद्यार्थविल्कोट्या-चौ.सं.) शिवभक्तो विशिष्यते ॥52 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 7.70-72, p.48; Chow. 7.77-79ab) / तथा शिवधर्मे - शिवध्यानपराः शान्ताः शिवधर्मपरायणाः (शिवध्यानपरः शान्तः शिवधर्मपरायणः-चौ.सं.)। सर्व (सर्व-चौ.सं.) एवाश्रमा ज्ञेयाः शिवभक्ताः शिवाश्रमाः (शिवधर्मा शिवाश्रमाः-चौ.सं.) ॥63 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 11.409, p.149; Chow. 11.54) / शिवधर्मे - ग्रामे वा यदि वारण्ये जले वापि स्थलेऽपि (स्थण्डिलेऽपि-चौ.सं.) वा। यत्नैव (यत्न वा-चौ.सं.) दृश्यते लिङ्गं सर्वतीर्थानि तत्र वै ॥139 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.- missing, but found in T32 of IFP; Chow. 1.14cd-14ab) / शिवधर्मे – आरामावसथं (दानाद्यावसथ-चौ.सं.) कूपं तडागं (उद्यानं-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) देवतागृहम् (देवतालयम्-चौ.सं.)। शिवक्षेत्रेषु (तीर्थेष्वेतानि-ने.सं.; स्थानेष्वेतेषु-चौ.सं.) यः कुर्यात् सोऽनन्तफलमाप्नुयात् (सोऽक्षयं लभते फलम्-ने.सं.; सोऽक्षयं फलमाप्नुयात्-चौ.सं.) ॥145 ॥ गृहं श्राद्धस्य यत्पुण्यमरण्ये तच्छताधिकम् (तच्छवाधिकम्-ने.सं.)। शिवाश्रमेषु विज्ञेयं तत्पुण्यमयुताधिकम् (तन्नदीष्वयुतं पुण्यम् अनन्तं स्याच्छिवालयं-चौ.सं.) ॥146 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.12.533, 544cd-545ab, pp.168, 170; Chow.12.68cd-69ab, 81cd-82ab) / शिवधर्मे -शिवक्षेत्रसमीपस्थं (शिवलिङ्गसमीपस्थं-चौ.सं.) यत्तोयं पुरतः स्थितम्। शिवगङ्गैति विज्ञेयं तत्र सात्वा शिवं व्रजेत् ॥153 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.205cd-206ab, p.26; Chow.5.215cd-216ab) / शिवधर्मे -भस्मस्नानं जलस्नानादसङ्ख्येयगुणात्चितम् (...)

texts, viz. importance of *śivabhakti* (devotion towards Lord Siva) and eightfold feature of *śivabhakti*; special qualities and conducts of the devotees of Śiva (*śivabhakta*) belonging to four different stages (*caturāśramas*); the superiority of *śivabhaktas*; holiness of the site of liṅga worship and virtue of digging pond or well that is called śivagaṅgā near that site; the virtue of performing sraddha in the abode of Śiva; superiority of *bhaṣmasnāna* (smearing holy ash in the body) and virtue bearing *rudrākṣa* beads; superiority of performing sandhya with *śivapañcākṣaramantra* (five-syllabled hymns of Śiva) in a Śiva temple, etc. All these quoted verses are found to be existent in the available printed editions of the SDS, and, it is observed that verses attributed to SDS and cited in the SKD are more similar to the Nep. edition of SDS than the Chow. edition, because in the process of comparison 61 variant readings were recorded from Chow. edition and only 34 variants from Nep. edition. Besides, it is worth mentioning that this chapter, through explanations of citations attributed to different texts, mentions SDS as an authoritative text having two parts with twelve chapters each, all together there are twenty-four chapters, and advises that

गुणाधिकम्-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.)। तस्माद् वारुणमुत्सृज्य स्नानमाग्रेयमाचरेत् ॥165॥ सर्वयज्ञेषु (सर्वतीर्थेषु-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) यत्पुण्यं सर्वतीर्थेषु (सर्वयज्ञेषु-चौ.सं.) यत्फलम्। तत्फलं लभते नित्यं (सर्व-चौ.सं.) भस्मस्नानान्न संशयः ॥166॥ महापातकसंयुक्तो (महापातकसंयुक्तो वा-चौ.सं.) युक्तो वा सर्वपातकैः। (भस्मस्नानं निषेवेत (निषेवीत-ने.सं.) मुच्यते सर्वपातकैः।-ने.सं., चौ.सं. -this line missing in SKD) भस्मस्नानात्परं स्नानं पवित्रं नैव विद्यते ॥167॥ उक्तमेवं मुनिर्देवैः (उक्तं देवमुनिर्देवैः-ने.सं.; इत्युक्त्वा मुनिदेवेभ्यः-चौ.सं.) स्नातो देवो सदाशिवः (स्नातो देवः स्वयं शिवः-ने.सं.; स्नातोऽनेन शिवः स्वयम्-चौ.सं.)। ततः प्रभृति ब्रह्माद्या मुनयश्च शिवार्थिनः ॥168॥ सर्वपर्वसु यत्नेन भस्मस्नानं प्रचक्रिरे। तस्मादेवं (तस्मादेव-ने.सं.; तस्मादेव-चौ.सं.) शिवस्नानमाग्रेयं यः समाचरेत् ॥169॥ अनेनैव शरीरेण स रुद्रो नात्र संशयः ॥170॥ (Parallel with Nep.11.388-390ab, 391-393, pp.146-147 ; Chow. 11.30cd-32, 33cd-36ab)/ शिवधर्मं - सितेन भस्मना कुर्यात्त्रिसन्ध्यं यस्त्रिपुण्ड्रकम् (त्रिसन्ध्यं सस्त्रिपुण्ड्रकम्-चौ.सं.) सर्वपापविनिर्मुक्तः शिवलोके महीयते ॥187॥ रुद्राग्रेयत्परं वीर्यं (बीज-ने.सं.) तद्भस्म (भस्मस्म-ने.सं.) परिकीर्तितम्। ध्वंसनं सर्वदुष्टानां (सर्वदुःखानां-चौ.सं.) सर्वपापविशोधनम् ॥188॥ (Parallel with Nep. 11.384-385, pp.145-146); Chow. 11.26cd-28ab) / शिवधर्मं - हस्ते मूर्ध्नुपवीते (मूर्ध्नुपवीते-ने.सं.) वा रुद्राक्षं धारयेत्तु यः (धारयेद्वृत्ती-ने.सं.; धारयेत्तु यः-चौ.सं.)। अगम्यं (अगम्यः-ने.सं.; अगम्य-चौ.सं.) सर्वभूतानां (सर्वसत्त्वानां-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) रुद्रलोकं स गच्छति ॥191॥ (Parallel with Nep.11.382, p.145; Chow. 11.24cd-25ab)/ शिवधर्मं - तस्मात्पञ्चाक्षरेणैव (तस्मादनेन मन्त्रेण-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) प्रकुर्वीत शिवार्चनम्। सन्ध्यायां (सन्ध्यानां-चौ.सं.) च जपेदेनं सर्वपापविशुद्धये ॥234॥ गृहाच्छतगुणं पुण्यं सन्ध्यायां च जलाशये (शिवालये-चौ.सं.)। शिवस्य दक्षिणामूर्तौ (शिवदक्षिणामूर्तौ च-ने.सं.) शिवदक्षिणामूर्तौ तु-चौ.सं.) तत्पुण्यमयुताधिकम् ॥235॥ तस्माच्छिवालये सन्ध्याम् (जप्यम्-चौ.सं.) आचरेच्छान्तमानसः। शिवमन्त्रेण सततं सर्वकामप्रसिद्धये ॥236॥ (Parallel with Nep.7.62-64, pp.47-48; Chow.7.66cd-69ab)

every Śiva devotee must have knowledge of that and should follow the preaching⁸. It also mentions that SDS is a text belonging to the Pāśupata sect of Saivism and is different from the 'restricted Pāśupata' as mentioned in the later part of the Padma Purana which is a text belonging to the Kāpālika sect of Saivism⁹.

4. Chapter – IV: This chapter of SKD cites passages attributed to SDS five times.¹⁰ Those are verses no. 8, 68-70, 94-96,

- 8 बहुनात्र किमुक्तेन स्वधर्मपरिपालनम् । ईश्वराराधनपरान् सन्नियोगात्प्रमुच्यते ॥60 ॥ स्वधर्म - शिवधर्मशास्त्रं पूर्वोत्तरचतुर्विंशत्यध्यायसहितं पालयन्ति ये तान् । अनेन शिवधर्मशास्त्रालोकनं शैवानां परमधर्म उक्तस्तदवश्यं कार्यम् ॥ तथा च जैमिनीभारते - ये तु भक्ता महेशाने तद्धर्मपरिचिन्तकाः । न तेषां पुनरावृत्तिः सत्यं सत्यं वदाम्यहम् ॥62 ॥ तद्धर्म - पूर्वोत्तरशिवधर्मशास्त्रं शैवानां तच्चिन्तनम् आवश्यकम् एवोक्तम्/ तथा शिवधर्म - शिवध्यानपराः शान्ताः शिवधर्मपरायणाः । सर्व एवाश्रमा ज्ञेयाः शिवभक्ताः शिवाश्रयाः ॥63 ॥ शिवधर्म - शिवधर्मशास्त्रे पूर्वोत्तरचतुर्विंशत्यध्याये परायणाः निरताः । अनेनापि शिवधर्मशास्त्रालोकनं तदुक्तकृत्यं च शैवानाम् आवश्यकमुक्तम् ॥ तथा एकाम्रपुराणे -शिवधर्मं च येश्चिन्ना वैशेषिकविनिर्णयाः । सिद्धयन्ति सिद्धयो व्यग्रा आगमोक्ता पृथग्विधा ॥64 ॥ सम्भवन्ति न लीयन्ते ईश्वराणामिति स्मृताः ॥65 ॥ ये शिवधर्मशास्त्रे पूर्वोत्तरसहिते अभिज्ञाः पण्डितास्तेषामेव आगमोक्ताः सिद्धयो व्यग्राः सिद्धयन्ति । ते भवे न सम्भवन्ति ईश्वराणामंशतो लीयन्ते साजुज्यं प्राप्नुवन्ति इत्यर्थः । शिवधर्मशास्त्राभ्यां सफलम् पुतद्वर्षितम् । अतस्तन्मार्गैरेव शिवाश्रयः कर्तव्यः ॥ तथा च भविष्ये -विष्णुधर्माणि शास्त्राणि शिवधर्माणि भारत । तेषु ये प्रतिपन्नस्तु ते भक्ता परमे शिवे ॥66 ॥शिवधर्मशास्त्रे यस्यालोकनश्रमः स शिवस्य परमभक्त इत्यर्थः ।
- 9 पाशुपतमित्युक्ते शिवधर्मशास्त्रं न तु पद्मपुराणोत्तरखण्डनिषेधितं पाशुपतमिति कापालिकशास्त्रम् । याज्ञवल्क्येन पाशुपतमिति शिवधर्मोत्तरशास्त्रमेव वेदेः समानमाद्रियते । अतः शैवानां शिवधर्मशास्त्रमार्गोक्तधर्म एवाश्रयणीय इत्यर्थः ।
- 10 शिवधर्म -लिङ्गे देवो महादेवः सर्वदैव (साक्षादेव-ने.सं.; साक्षादेव-चौ.सं.) व्यवस्थितः । अनुग्रहाय लोकानां तस्माल्लिङ्गं प्रपूजयेत् ॥8 ॥(Parallel with Nep.3.44cd-45ab, p.7; Chow.3.49)/ अतः सर्वत्र लिङ्गं समर्चयेदित्याह । तत्रापि स्वयमभ्यर्चने विशेषफलम् । शिवधर्म -लिङ्गद्वयं समाख्यातं चरं वाचरमेव (सचराचरमेव-ने.सं.; चरं चाचरमेव-चौ.सं.) च । चरं प्रतीतमाख्यातम् (प्राणैति विख्यातम्-ने.सं.; व्यक्तिते विख्याते-चौ.सं.) अचरं पार्थिवादिकम् (पार्थिवादिषु-ने.सं.) ॥68 ॥ प्रतीतं - संशयहीनम् । स्वयम्भुरित्यर्थः । चरे सदा वसत्येव प्रीतियुक्तो (प्रतिच्छन्नो-चौ.सं.) महेश्वरः । अचरे मन्त्रसंस्काराद् (अचरो यत्तु संस्कारो-ने.सं.) वसत्येव सदाशिवः (द्वयं नित्यं सदाशिवम्-ने.सं.) ॥69 ॥ चर्यते - ज्ञायते शिवः प्रत्यक्षतयाऽनेनेति, चरम् - स्थावरलिङ्गम् । चर गतौ इति धातुः । जङ्गमस्यापमानेन (...स्यावमानेन-चौ.सं.) स्थावरो (स्थारं-चौ.सं.) निष्फलं भवेत् । तस्माल्लिङ्गद्वयं प्राज्ञो नावमन्येत जातुचित् (सर्वदा-चौ.सं.) ॥70 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 3.56-58, p.8; Chow.3.62-63,65; prose lines between verses are explanation by Lakshmidhara Mishra, the author of SKD. It is worthy to mention that in Chow. edition of SDS and in the paper transcript of SDS bearing no. T32 of IFP an extra verse is there between verses 69 and 70, that reads-स्थारं जङ्गमं चैव द्विविधं लिङ्गमिष्यते । स्थावरं स्थापितं लिङ्गं जङ्गमं दीक्षितं विदुः ॥; but this verse is missing in Nep. edition of SKD, also not mentioned in SKD)/ शिवधर्म- दृष्ट्वा (पश्यन्-चौ.सं.) परिहरन् जन्तून् (परिहरेज्जन्तून्-ने.सं.; परहरञ्जन्त्-न्तु!)-चौ.सं.) मार्ज्याया मृदुसूक्ष्मया (मार्ज्यायात्यतिसूक्ष्मया-चौ.सं.) । शनैः सम्मार्जनं कुर्वन् (कुर्यात्-चौ.सं.) चान्द्रायणफलं लभेत् ॥94 ॥ अथोपलेपनम् - नाहार प्रतिजीर्णया (वशजीर्णया-चौ.सं.) बन्ध्यायाः क्षीणवत्सका (क्षीणवत्सयोः-ने.सं.; क्षीणवत्सया-चौ.सं.) । रोगार्तायाः (रोगार्ता-चौ.सं.) प्रसूतायाः (नवसूता या-चौ.सं.) गोष्ठगोमयमाहरेत् (गोश्च गोमयमाहरेत्-ने.सं.; भोग्यो गोमयमाहरेत्-चौ.सं.) ॥95 ॥ खसंस्थं (स्वसंस्थ-चौ.सं.) गोमयं ग्राह्यं स्थाने वा पतितं शुभे । उपर्यधस्तत् (उपर्यधस्तात्-ने.सं.; उपर्यधश्च-चौ.सं.) संत्यज्य प्रत्ययं जन्तुवर्जितम् ॥96 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.4.32-34, p.12 ; Chow.4.31-33)/ प्रत्ययं - सद्योजातम् । शिवधर्म - वस्तूपलेन तोयेन यः कुर्यादुपलेपनम् । पश्यन् परिहरन् जन्तून् (परिञ्जन्त्-चौ.सं.) चान्द्रायणफलं लभेत् ॥97 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 4.35,

97, and 99 of SKD quoted in the context of emphasizing the worship of Lord Siva in the form of a *linga*, types of *lingas* namely *cara* and *acara*, rite of *sammārjana*, *upalepana*, and making of *śivamaṇḍala*, etc. Parallels of all verses cited in SKD and attributed to SDS are found in the existing printed versions of SDS, and those citations are more similar to Nep. edition of SDS than the Chow. edition. In the process of comparison, 19 numbers of variant readings are recorded from Chow. edition and 12 from Nep. edition.

Also, in the explanation of verse no. 54 of SKD that is attributed to certain smṛiti, this chapter defines the word 'pustaka' (book) as the text Śivadharmāśāstra having two parts namely SDS and SDU.¹¹

5. Chapter – V: The highest number of citations attributed to SDS are traced in this chapter of SKD. This chapter cites passages independently attributed to SDS forty-five times. Those are verse no. 55-57, 181, 230, 232, 234-235, 238, 242-244, 252-255, 261-266, 268-270, 274, 280, 285-286ab, 295, 298, 304, 310-311ab, 313, 323, 326, 331-332, 337, 346-351, 367, 387-390, 396, 401, 408, 441, 444-446, 452, 471-473, 475-476, 479-481, 483, 489, 509, 515-516, 534, 540-541, 546, 549-554, and 560¹² of SKD. All these verses are cited

p.12; Chow. 4.34)/ अथोपलेपने परिप्राप्तं मण्डलमाह शिवधर्मं -शिवमण्डलकं कृत्वा (वृत्तं-ने.सं.) हस्तमालं शिवाग्रतः । अवकीर्याक्षतैः (यः कुर्यादक्षतैः-चौ.सं.) पुष्पैः पत्रैर्वाप्यथकोमलैः (पत्रैर्वाप्यथकोमलैः-ने.सं.; पत्रैर्वाप्यथ केवलैः-चौ.सं.) ॥99 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.193cd-194ab, p.25; Chow. 5. 203))

- 11 अथवा स्मृतिः -निजमूर्तौ गुरौ मूर्तौ पुस्तके सलिलेऽनले । चितादौ स्थण्डिले वापि बाणश्चात्यन्तमुत्तमम् ॥54 ॥ निजमूर्तौ – स्वात्मनि । गुरौ – देवस्वरूपिणं गुरुं वा । मूर्तौ – शिवप्रतिमायाम् । पुस्तके - पूर्वोत्तरश्चतुर्विंशत्यध्याये शिवधर्मशास्त्रे ।.....
- 12 शिवधर्मं -नमस्तारादिसंयुक्तं (नमस्कारादिसंयुक्तं-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) शिवायेति निरन्तरम् (शिव इत्यक्षरद्वयम्-ने.सं.; शिवायेत्यर्चये त्वयम्-चौ.सं.) जिह्वग्रे वर्तते यस्य सफलं तस्य जीवितम् ॥55 ॥ कृतो नमः शिवायेति (कृत्वन्नमः शिवायेति-ने.सं.; उक्त्वो नमः शिवायेति-चौ.सं.) मुच्यते सर्वपातकैः (सर्वबन्धनात्-चौ.सं.) । यस्मात्तस्मान्महामन्त्रम् (यस्मात्तस्मात्सदा मन्त्रम्-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) ओंकाराद्यमतः स्मरेत् (ओंकाराद्यमनुस्मरेत्-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) ॥56 ॥ सवीजं (सद्वीजं-चौ.सं.) सर्वविद्यानामार्थं ब्रह्मपरायणम् (ब्रह्म परात्परम्-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) । सर्वार्थसाधकं मन्त्रं शिवसूक्तं (शिवसूक्तं-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) षडक्षरम् ॥57 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.1.41, 7.53&60 p.3&47; Chow.1.37, 57cd-58ab, 64cd-65ab)/ शिवधर्मं -यः कृत्वा पार्थिवं लिङ्गम् अर्चयेत् सर्वदेव हि (अर्चयेत् सुरेश्वरम्-ने.सं.; अर्चयित्वा सवेदिकम्-चौ.सं.) । इहैव धनवान् श्रीमान् सोऽन्ते रुद्रोऽभिजायते (रुद्रश्च जायते-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) ॥181 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.3.65, p.8; Chow.3.72)/ तत्रादौ स्नानमाह । शिवधर्मं - अयुतं यो गवां दद्याद् दोग्ध्रीणं (दोग्ध्रीणां-चौ.सं.) वेदपारगे । वस्त्रहेमादियुक्तानां (वस्त्रहेमयुक्तानां-चौ.सं.) क्षीरस्नानेन (घृतस्नानेन-चौ.सं.) तत्फलम् ॥230 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.19, p.15; Chow.5.18)/ दधिस्नानमाह । शिवधर्मं -दध्ना च (तु-ने.सं.) स्नापयेत्लिङ्गं सकृद्भक्त्या तु (च-ने.सं.) यो नरः । सर्वपापविनिर्मुक्तो विष्णुलोके महीयते (स्नाप्य दध्ना सकृत्लिङ्गं विष्णुलोके महीयते-चौ.सं.) ॥232 ॥

(Parallel with Nep.5.21, p.15; Chow.5.20ab)/ घृतस्नानमाह । शिवधर्म - कल्पकोटिसहस्रेण यत्पापं समुपाजितम् । घृतस्नानेन तत्सर्वं दहत्यग्निरिवेन्धनम् ॥234 ॥ नैरन्त्येण यो मांसं घृतस्नानं समाचरेत् । एकविंशत्कुलोपेतो (एकविंशः कुलोपेतः-ने.सं.; एकविंशत्कुलोपेतः-चौ.सं.) याति वै शङ्करारण्यम् (क्रीडते द्विवि रूद्रवत्-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) ॥235 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.17,42, pp.15,16; Chow. missing, 5.40)/ मधुस्नानमाह । शिवधर्म - मधुना स्नापयेत्लिङ्गं सकृद्भक्त्यापि यो नरः । सर्वपापविनिर्मुक्तो वह्निलोके महीयते (मधुना स्नापयित्वा तु वह्निलोके स गच्छति।-चौ.सं.) ॥238 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.22, p.15; Chow.5.20cd)/ एवं पञ्चामृतफलं पृथक् पृथक् फलेन दर्शितम् । शिवधर्म - कपिलापञ्चगव्येन कुशवारियुतेन (कुशवारिप्लूतेन-ने.सं.) च । स्नापयेन्मन्त्रपूतेन ब्रह्मस्नानं (तत्स्मृतम्-ने.सं.; चौ. सं.) ॥242 ॥ एकाहमपि यो लिङ्गे ब्रह्मस्नानं समाचरेत् । विधूय सर्वपापानि (स विधूयाशु पापानि-चौ.सं.) शिवलोके (रूद्रलोके-चौ.सं.) महीयते ॥243 ॥ इति पञ्चगव्यस्नानम् । वस्तुविशेषे फलविशेषमुक्तम् । अथ तैलस्नानमाह । शिवधर्म - स्नापयेत्तिलतेलेन हस्तयन्त्रोद्भवेन (हस्तयन्त्रोद्भवेन-ने.सं.) च । श्वेतपीतकपुष्पैर्वा (श्वेतपीतकपिष्टैर्वा-चौ.सं.) वायुलोके महीयते ॥244 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.11-12, 23, p.15, 16; Chow. 5.10-11, 21)/ अथोद्घृतनमाह । शिवधर्म - घृताभ्यङ्गे घृतस्नानेन यस्तु लिङ्गं (यत्नालिङ्गं-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) विरूक्षयेत् । यवगोधूमजैश्चूर्णैः (ये न गोधूमजैश्चूर्णैः-ने.सं.) कषायैर्नान्ययोर्जितैः-चौ. सं.) ॥252 ॥ सुखोष्णान्भसा वापि स्नापयेत्तदनन्तरम् । घर्षयेद्विल्वपत्रैश्च तत्पीठं (तेव पीठं-चौ.सं.) च विशोधयेत् ॥253 ॥ दशधेनुसहस्राणि (दशकोटिसहस्राणि-चौ.सं.) यद्वत्वा लभते फलम् । तत्फलं लभते सर्वं (मर्त्यो-चौ.सं.) लिङ्गस्योद्घर्तने कृते ॥254 ॥ अथ केवलजलस्नानमाह । शिवधर्म - वस्त्रपूतेन तोयेन यो नरः (लिङ्गं-ने.सं. चौ.सं.) स्नापयेत्सकृत् (स्नापयेन्नरः-ने.सं. चौ.सं.) । सर्वकामसु तृप्तात्मा (सर्वकाम सुतृप्तात्मा-चौ. सं.) वारुणं लोकमाप्नुयात् ॥255 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.43cd-46ab,27 p.17,16; Chow.5.42-44,25)/ अथ जलद्रव्यविशेषे फलविशेषमाह । शिवधर्म - सर्वाधिभिः (कुशोदकेन-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) यो लिङ्गं सकृदास्नापयेन्नरः (सकृत्स्नापयते नरः-ने.सं.; भक्त्या स्नापयते सकृत्-चौ.सं.) । काञ्चनेन विमानेन ब्रह्मलोके महीयते ॥261 ॥ यस्तु चन्दनतोयेन (गन्धचन्दनतोयेन-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) स्नापयेत्सुकृदीश्वरम् । गान्धर्वलोकमाप्नोति गन्धर्वैश्चापि (गन्धर्वैश्च स-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) पूज्यते ॥262 ॥ कर्पूरागरुतोयेन यो लिङ्गं स्नापयेन्नरः (स्नापयेत्सकृतम्-चौ.सं.) । सर्वपापविशुद्धात्मा (सर्वपापविनिर्मुक्तः-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) शिवलोके महीयते ॥263 ॥ फलोदकेन यो लिङ्गं सकृदास्नापयेन्नरः (सकृत्स्नापयते नरः-ने.सं.; भक्त्या संस्नापयेन्नरः-चौ.सं.) । उत्सृज्य पापकलिलं (पालकलिलं-चौ.सं.) पितृलोके महीयते ॥264 ॥ पुष्पोदकेन सावित्रं (सावित्र्यं-चौ.सं.) कौर्वरं हेमवारिणा । रत्नोदकेन चाप्येन्द्रं (माहेन्द्रं-चौ.सं.) लोकं प्राप्य स मोदते ॥265 ॥ तत्रपुष्पोदकेषु पूष्यनिर्णयः - पाटलोत्पलपद्मानि (पाटलोत्पलखण्डानि-ने.सं.) करवीराणि सर्वदा । स्नानकाले प्रयोज्यानि (स्नानकालेषु योज्यानि-ने.सं.; स्नानतोयेषु योज्यानि-चौ.सं.) स्थिराणि सुरभीणि च ॥266 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.28-29,33,25,30-31, pp.15-16; Chow.5.26-27,31,23,28-29)/ शिवधर्म - कुशोदकेन यो लिङ्गं सकृदास्नापयेन्नरः (सकृत्स्नापयते नरः-ने.सं.; भक्त्या स्नापयते सकृत्-चौ.सं.) । काञ्चनेन विमानेन रूद्रलोके (ब्रह्मलोके-ने.सं. चौ.सं.) महीयते ॥268 ॥ मन्त्राष्टशतजपेन विमलेनाभसा शिवम् । स्नापयित्वा सकृद्भक्त्या शिवलोकमवाप्नुयात् (शिवलोके महीयते-चौ.सं.) ॥269 ॥ पितृनुद्दिश्य (पितृनुद्दिश्य-चौ.सं.) यो लिङ्गं स्नापयेच्छीतवारिणा । तृप्ताः स्वर्गं गमिष्यन्ति (प्रयास्यन्ति-चौ.सं.) पितरो नरकादपि ॥270 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.28,34,36, p.16; Chow. 5.26,32-33)/ भस्मस्नानमाह । शिवधर्म -सितेन भस्मना स्नाय सकृत्लिङ्गं प्रमोदते । चन्द्रांशुनिर्मलः श्रीमान् (शुद्धः-ने.सं.) शिववत्सोममण्डले (शिववत्सोममण्डलम्-ने. सं.) ॥274 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.26, p.15; Chow. 5.24)/ एवं चन्दनादिप्रलेपनफलं दर्शयित्वा तदङ्गतया तालवृन्तवीजनपुण्यमाह । शिवधर्म -संवीज्य तालवृन्तेन लिङ्गमेव (लिङ्गमेभिः-ने.सं. लिङ्गं गन्धैः-चौ. सं.) प्रलेपितम् । दशवर्षसहस्राणि (वर्षकोटिसहस्राणि-चौ.सं.) वायुलोके महीयते ॥280 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.67, p.18; Chow.5.63)/ वनसम्भवं शिवाचने प्रशस्तमुत्तमम् । तदभावे स्वाजितपुष्पं वदन्ति शैवागमविदः । तद्यथा-शिवधर्म -पुष्पैररण्यसम्भूतैः (पुष्पैररण्यसम्भूतैः-ने.सं. चौ.सं.) पत्रैर्वा गिरिसम्भूतैः । अपर्युषितनिश्चिद्रैः प्रोक्षितैर्जन्तुवर्जितैः ॥285 ॥ आत्मारामोद्भवैर्वापि पुष्पैः सम्पूजयेच्छिवम् ॥286 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.72-73ab, p.18; Chow.5.69-70ab)/ शिवधर्म -धुत्तूरकैश्च यो लिङ्गं सकृत्पूजयते नरः । स गोलक्षफलं प्राप्य शिवलोके महीयते (स गोलक्षप्रदानस्य शिवं प्राप्य फलं लभेत्।-चौ. सं.) ॥295 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.98, p.20; Chow.5.96cd-97ab)/ शिवधर्म - नागघण्टकपुत्राणाः धुत्तूरकसमाः (धुत्तूरकसमाः-चौ.सं.) स्मृताः । श्वेतमन्दारकुसुमं श्वेतपत्रं च तत्समम् (सितपद्मेन तत्समम्-ने.सं.; सितपद्मसम् भवेत्-चौ.सं.) ॥298 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.86ab,85cd, p.19; Chow. 5.82cd,82ab)/ शिवधर्म -शमीपुष्पं कदम्बं च (वृहत्याञ्च-ने.सं.; बृहत्याञ्च-चौ.सं.) कुमुदं

(कुसुम-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) तुल्यमुच्यते (तुल्यमेव च-चौ.सं.)। करवीरसमा ज्ञेया जातीविजयपटलाः ॥304 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.84cd-85ab, p.19; Chow. 5.81)/ शिवधर्म - जातीपुष्पाद्विशेषण (पुष्पाजातिविशेषण-ने.सं. चौ.सं.) भवेत्पुण्यमशेषतः (भवेत्पुण्यं विशेषतः-ने.सं.; भवेत्पुण्यं ततोऽधिकम्-चौ.सं.)। तपःशीलगुणोपेते पाले वेदस्य पारगे (वेदपारगे-चौ.सं.) ॥310 ॥ दशदत्त्वा सुवर्णानि यत्फलं तदवाप्नुयात् ॥311 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.73cd-74; Chow. 5.70cd-71)/ शिवधर्म - धुतूरकसहस्रेभ्यो बृहती पुष्पमुत्तमम् (बृहत्पुष्पं विशिष्यते-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.)। बृहतीनां सहस्रेभ्यो (बृहत्पुष्पसहस्रेभ्यो-ने.सं.; missing-चौ.सं.) द्रोणपुष्पं विशिष्यते ॥313 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.78, p.19; Chow. 5.76cd & second half missing)/ एवं मासाचिंतफलानि दर्शितानि। शिवधर्म - यः सुगन्धैर्मुक्तपुष्पैः (सुगन्धैर्मुक्तपुष्पैः-चौ.सं.) सम्यक् लिङ्गं प्रपूजयेत्। सर्वपापविनिर्मुक्तः शिवलोके महीयते ॥323 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.95, p.20; Chow. 5.94cd & second half missing)/ शिवधर्म - मालाभिर्वा सुगन्धिभिर्यो लिङ्गं पूजयेन्नरः। सवैदिकं विशेषण (सवैदिकविशेषण-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) सोऽनन्तफलमश्नुते (मालाभिर्वा सु घटितैः अनन्तं फलमाप्नुयात्-चौ.सं.) ॥326 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.96, p.20; Chow. 5.95ab & second half missing)/ शिवधर्म - अनेकाकारसंयुक्तं यशिशेव कौसुमं गृहम्। कुर्वीत पर्वकालेषु (सर्वकालेषु-ने.सं.; missing-चौ.सं.) विचित्रकुसुमोज्वलम् ॥331 ॥ (verse 331 is missing in चौ.सं.) स पुष्पकविमानेन दिव्यस्त्रीपरिवारितः (स पुष्पकविमानानां सहस्रेः परिवारितः। दिव्यस्त्रीसुखसम्भोगक्रीडारतिसमान्वितः-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.)। अक्षयं लभते लोकम् (मोदते कालम्-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) अतिरस्कृतशासनः ॥332 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.109, 110ab, 111ab, pp.20-21; Chow. 5.112cd-113ab)/ शिवधर्म - बिल्वपत्नैरखण्डैश्च सकल्लिङ्गं प्रपूजयेत्। सर्वपापविनिर्मुक्तः शिवलोके महीयते ॥337 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.97, p.20; Chow. 5.95cd-96ab)/ शिवधर्म - वस्त्रानीतं करानीतं चालितं चार्कपत्रके। एरण्डपत्रेणानीतं धीतपुष्पन्तु वर्जयेत् ॥346 ॥ मुकुलैः पतितैर्मलैर्जीर्णैर्वा जन्तुवर्जितैः। आप्लुतैर्ङ्गलैश्च पर्युषितैश्च नार्चयेत् ॥347 ॥ लिपत्वाप्यनकुसुमैर्नार्चयेत् कुदचन। भृगतं वर्जयेत्पुष्पं शेफालिवकुलैर्विना ॥348 ॥ शेफालि गङ्गशुलि। उन्मत्तमर्कपुष्पं विष्णोर्वर्ज्यं सदा बुधैः। कलिकाभिः सदा त्याज्या विना चम्पकपद्मकैः ॥349 ॥ केतकीं चातिमुक्तं च (केतकञ्जातिमुक्ताञ्च-ने.सं. केतकी माधवी चैव-चौ.सं.) कुन्दयूथीमदन्तिकाः (कुन्दयूथीमदन्तिक-ने.सं.)। शिरीषसर्ज (सज्ज-चौ.सं.) बन्धूककुसुमानि विवर्जयेत् ॥350 ॥ अत्र कुन्दो वराहदाढ इति प्रसिद्धः। शिरीषः खिरिञ्ज। सर्जः शालः। अक्षवीपलकुसुमं करञ्जेन्द्रसमुद्भवम्। विभीतकानि पुष्पाणि यत्नतः परिवर्जयेत् ॥351 ॥ (No parallel of verses 346-349 & 351 except verse no 350 that is parallel with Nep. 5.86cd-87ab, p.19; Chow. 5.83)/ शिवधर्म - केशकीटोपविद्वानि (कीटकेशोपविताणि-ने.सं.; कीटकेशोपविद्वानि-चौ.सं.) निशापर्युषितानि (शीर्णपर्युषितानि-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) च। स्वयं पतितपुष्पाणि त्यजेदुपहतानि च ॥367 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.90, p.19; Chow. 5.88cd-89ab)/ शिवधर्म - कृष्णागुरुं सकर्पूरं (कृष्णागुरुश्च कर्पूरं-ने.सं.) धूपं दद्यान्महेश्वरे (दद्यान्महेश्वरी-ने.सं.)। नैरन्तर्येण मासार्थं तस्य पुण्यफलं शृणु ॥387 ॥ कल्पकोटिसहस्राणि कल्पकोटिशतानि च। भुङ्क्ते (भुक्त्वा-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) शिवपुरं भोगान् तस्यान्ते स (तस्यान्ते तु-ने.सं.; तस्याप्यन्ते-चौ.सं.) महीपतिः ॥388 ॥ गुग्गुलोः (गुग्गुलं-चौ.सं.) शतसाहस्रं (दशसाहस्रं-चौ.सं.) सधूपं द्विगुणं भवेत्। प्रियश्च गुग्गुलोर्धूप (गुग्गुलनिर्वत्यं-चौ.सं.) आज्यैर्युक्तो (आज्ययुक्तो-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) विशेषतः ॥389 ॥ तत्रापि विशेषः - द्वे सहस्रे (missing-ने.सं.) फलानां तु महिषाक्षस्य (महिषाक्षस्यद्वि-ने.सं.) गुग्गुलोः। दग्ध्वार्धेनाज्यमिश्रस्य (दग्धत्वेनाज्यमिश्रस्य-ने.सं.; दग्ध्वाज्येन तु सम्मिश्रं-चौ.सं.) शिवतुल्यः प्रजापते ॥390 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.120-121, 126-127, p.21; Chow. 5.122cd-124ab, 128cd-130ab)/ शिवधर्म - नमरुं (अगरुं-चौ.सं.) घृतसंयुक्तं दग्ध्वा बिल्वमथापि वा (अनन्ताश्च फलानि च-चौ.सं.)। अग्निष्टोमस्य यज्ञस्य (यागस्य-ने.सं.) फलं प्राप्नोति (फलमाप्नोति-चौ.सं.) मानवः ॥396 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.128, p.22; Chow. 5.130cd-131ab)/ अथ दीपमाह। शिवधर्म - घृतप्रदीपदानेन शिवाय शतयोजने (शतयोजनम्-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.)। लङ्घयित्वा तमो (ततो-चौ.सं.) गच्छेद्विमानैः (याति विमानैः-चौ.सं.) सूर्यसन्निभैः (सूर्यसन्निभैः-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) ॥401 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.147, p.23; Chow. 5.151cd-152ab)/ शिवधर्म - द्वीपवृक्षं सुसमुद्भं (समुद्भ्य-चौ.सं.) लोहमुच्चं (शोभयुच्चं-ने.सं.) शिवालये। दत्त्वा कल्पायुतं साग्रं शिवलोके महीयते (missing-चौ.सं.) ॥408 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.152, p.23; Chow. 5.156cd-157ab) / शिवधर्म - मातुलुङ्गफलादीनि सुपक्वानि (पक्वानि च-चौ.सं.) निवेदयेत्। शिवाय तत्फलं तुल्यं (तस्य-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) भक्ष्याणां यन्निवेदयाम् (विनिवेदयेत्-ने.सं.; यन्निवेदने-चौ.सं.) ॥441 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.146, p.23; Chow. 5.148cd-149ab)/ शिवधर्म - मुकुलैर्नार्चयेद् देवम् अपक्वं न निवेदयेत्

(अर्चिते सति कुडमले-चौ.सं.) । फलं प्रकथितं विद्धं (कथितमिच्छन्ति-ने.सं.) यन्नात्यक्मपि त्यजेत् ॥444 ॥ कथितं गतरस्मम् । विद्धं कीटादिभिर्दुषितम् । यन्नात्यक्ं धूमादिभिः पक्वम् । ताम्रपात्रं विधायदौ मून्मयं वा नवं शुभम् । देवस्याग्नेयदिग्भागे नैवेद्यं तु निवेदयेत् ॥445 ॥ मार्जितापानकादीनां (भर्जितायान्नकादीनां-ने.सं.; मज्जिका पानकानां तु-चौ.सं.) दत्त्वा (भक्ष्याद्ध-ने.सं.; भक्ष्यार्थ-चौ.सं.) तत्फलमिष्यते (फलमिष्यते-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) । तदर्थं सलिलस्यापि वासितस्य निवेदने ॥446 ॥ (No parallel of the verse 445 found in the printed editions of SDS; and other verses, i.e. verse no 444 & 446 are parallel with Nep.5.91,145 p.19,23; Chow.5.89cd,91ab,147cd-148ab)/ शिवधर्मं - धारयेच्छिवनिर्माल्यं भक्त्या लोभात्र (लेह्यं च-चौ.सं.) भक्षयेत् । भक्षणन्नरकं (भक्षणान्नरकान्-चौ.सं.) गच्छेत् तद्विलङ्घ्य अधोगतिम् (त्वधोगतिम्-ने.सं.; च मूढधीः-चौ.सं.) ॥452 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.12.494, p.163; Chow.12.13cd-14ab)/ शिवधर्मं -दारवेणार्घ्यपालेण (दारवेण्वर्घ्यपालेण-चौ.सं.) दत्त्वार्घ्यं यत्फलं लभेत् (यद्दत्त्वा लभते फलम्-चौ.सं.) । तस्माद्दशगुणं (तस्माच्छतगुणं-चौ.सं.) पुण्यं मृत्यालेण प्रकीर्तितम् ॥471 ॥ ताम्रपात्रार्घ्यदानेन (ताम्रपात्रेऽर्घ्यदानेन-चौ.सं.) पुण्यं शतगुणोत्तरम् । पलाशपद्मपलाशाभ्यां (पलाशताम्रपात्राभ्यां-ने.सं.; पलाशपद्मपात्राणां-चौ.सं.) ताम्रपालसमं (ताम्रपात्रे समं-चौ.सं.) भवेत् ॥472 ॥ रौप्यपालेण (रूप्यपालेण-ने.सं.) विज्ञेयमर्घ्यं लक्षगुणोत्तरम् (शतगुणोत्तरम्-ने.सं.) । सुवर्णपालविन्यस्तम् अर्घ्यं कोटिगुणोत्तरम् ॥473 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.52-54, p.17; Chow.5.49-51)/ शिवधर्मं -योऽर्घ्यमष्टाङ्गसंयुक्तं (योऽष्टाङ्गमर्घं सम्पूर्णं-ने.सं.; अर्घ्यमष्टाङ्गमूर्प्यं-चौ.सं.) शिवमूर्ध्नि निवेदयेत् । दशवर्षसहस्राणि शिवलोके (रुद्रलोके-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) महीयते ॥475 ॥ आपः क्षीरं कुशाग्राणि दधिसर्पिः (दध्याज्यं च-चौ.सं.) सतपडुलम् । तिलाः सिद्धार्थकाश्चैव (तिलसिद्धार्थकैश्चैव-चौ.सं.) अष्टाङ्गोऽर्घ्यः (अर्घ्योऽष्टाङ्गः-चौ.सं.) प्रकीर्तितः ॥476 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.50-51, p.17; Chow.5.47-48)/ तथा च शिवधर्मं - शिवाहृत्या (शिवभक्त्या-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) जगत्सर्वं (जगत्कृत्स्नं-ने.सं.) दृष्टिद्वारेण धारयते (वृष्टिसारेण सार्यते-चौ.सं.) । यत्सन्धार्यं जगत्पुण्यमग्निकायेण तद्भवेत् ॥477 ॥ यः कुर्यादिष्टकागारं रुद्राग्नेरतिशोभनम् । तत्र कृत्वाग्निकार्यं च (सकृत्तत्राग्निकार्येण-चौ.सं.) शिवलोके महीयते (रुद्रसायुज्यमाप्नुयात्-चौ.सं.) ॥480 ॥ शिवाग्निकार्यं यः कुर्याद् (कृत्वा-चौ.सं.) आयुषश्चापि चात्मनः (कुर्यात्सायुषमात्मन-चौ.सं.) । मुच्यते दशभिः (दशभिर्मुच्यते-चौ.सं.) पापैः सितेन शिवभस्मना (शिवभावना-चौ.सं.) ॥481 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.180cd-182ab, p.25; Chow.5.189cd-190ab,191-192; in चौ.सं. after verse no. 479 there is an extra line that reads - जगत्तु धारणं कुर्याद् अग्निकार्ये विशेषतः ॥190cd ॥ that is neither found in Nep. edition of SDS nor in SKD)/ तथा च शिवधर्मं -रौद्रं सन्ध्याबलिं (रौद्रसन्ध्याबलिं-ने.सं.; रौद्रं सन्ध्याबलिं-चौ.सं.) कृत्वा (दत्त्वा-ने.सं.) नित्यं शर्वाश्रमे(पर्वसु वा-चौ.सं.) निशि । कल्पायुतं सहस्राणं (कल्पायुतसहस्राणि-ने.सं.; कल्पायुतशतं साणं-चौ.सं.) शिवलोके महीयते ॥483 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.186cd-187ab, p.25; Chow.5.196)/ तथा शिवधर्मं -पुष्पधूपजलोपेतं (अर्घ्यं पुष्पजलोपेतं-चौ.सं.) ताम्रपात्रे प्रकल्पयेत् । रुद्रमातृगणादीनां दिक्पतीनां (दिव्यतीनां-ने.सं.; देवतानां-चौ.सं.) च सर्वतः ॥489 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.184cd-185ab, p.25; Chow.5.194)/ शिवधर्मं -यः कुर्यात्सकृदप्येवं दशदिक्षु बलिक्रियाम् । दशवर्षसहस्राणि शिवलोके (रुद्रलोके-चौ.सं.) महीयते ॥509 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.185cd-186ab, p.25; Chow.5.195)/ अथ शिवपूजाफलमाह । शिवधर्मं -न शिवार्चनतुल्योऽस्ति (शिवार्चनतो ह्यस्ति-चौ.सं.) धर्मोऽन्यो (धर्मोऽन्य-ने.सं.) भूवनत्रये । इति विज्ञाय यत्नेन पूजनीयः सदाशिवः ॥515 ॥ यावन्नाभ्येति (यावन्नायाति-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) मरणं यावन्नाक्रमते जरा । यावन्नेन्द्रियवैकल्यं तावत्पूज्य शङ्करम् ॥516 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.211cd-212ab, 2010cd-211ab, pp.26-17; Chow.5.220cd-221ab, 219cd-220ab)/ कालपूजायां विशेषमाह । शिवधर्मं -प्रातरुत्थाय यः (प्रातरुत्थाय-ने.सं.) शम्भुं (लिङ्गं-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) भक्त्या सम्पूजयेत्सकृत् (पूजयते सदा-ने.सं.; पूजयते सकृत्-चौ.सं.) । कपिलानां शतं दत्त्वा यत्फलं (यत्पुण्यं-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) तदवाप्नुयात् ॥534 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.7.29, p.46; Chow.7.28)/ अथ विषुवसङ्क्रान्तौ शिवधर्मं -नैरन्तर्येण षण्मासं (षण्मासान्-ने.सं.) विधिना पूजयेच्छिवम् (विधिना पूज्य शङ्करम्-चौ.सं.) । पुण्यं तदेव सकलं लभते विषुवार्चनात् (विषुवार्चने-ने.सं.) ॥540 ॥ एतदेव (एवमेव-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) तु विज्ञेयं (विधिज्ञेयं-ने.सं.; फलं ज्ञेयं-चौ.सं.) ग्रहणे चोत्तरायणे (ग्रहणायनयोरपि-चौ.सं.) । सङ्क्रान्तिषु दिनच्छिद्रे (संक्रान्तिदिनच्छिद्रेषु-ने.सं.; संक्रान्तौ च दिनच्छिद्रे-चौ.सं.) षडशीतिमुखेषु (षडशीतिमुखे-चौ.सं.) च ॥541 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.7.15-16, p.45; Chow.7.14-15)/ शिवधर्मं -मासैश्चतुर्भिर्त्यस्य विधिना पूज्य शङ्करम् । तत्कार्तिक्यां भवेत्पुण्यं (लभेत्पुण्यं-चौ.सं.) पौर्णमास्यां विशेषतः (शिवार्चने-ने.सं.; शिवार्चनात्-चौ.सं.) ॥546 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.7.17, p.45;

in the context of narrating different subject matters related to the worship of *śivaliṅga*, viz. importance and virtue of reciting six-lettered hymn – ‘*om namaḥ śivāya*’; virtue of bathing a *śivaliṅga* with different substances like milk, gee, curd, honey, oil, water, etc.; smearing of different substances (*lepana*) on *śivaliṅga* and its virtue; rite of fanning (*vījana*) and its virtue; prescription of various flowers to be used in the worship and virtues of offering those; virtue of offering different substances as *dhūpa*; virtue of offering different kinds of *dīpa*; prescription of offering different fruits and eatables as *naivedya* and different pots to be used for the same, and virtues of doing so; restriction on consumption of *śiva-nirmālya*; *śivāgnikārya* and its virtue; virtues of worshipping *śivaliṅga* on different specific times and special days, etc. Almost all of the abovementioned verses are found to be existent in the presently available printed editions of SDS, except verses 346 to 349, 351, and 445 which are cited in the context of narrating a list of flowers not to be used in the worship of *śivaliṅga* and in the context of offering *naivedya*.

Also, passages attributed to SDS conjoined with other Puranas are cited eight times, i.e. once with Skanda Purana¹³ and seven times with Bhavisya Purana¹⁴, in this chapter. Like

Chow.7.16)/ शिवधर्मे-लिङ्गमूर्तेर्महेशस्य शिवस्य परमेष्ठिनः । स्नानकाले प्रकुर्वीत जयशब्दादिमङ्गलम् ॥549 ॥ स्नानकाले पुष्पाभिषेके । त्रिशूलवज्रशङ्खाब्ज (त्रिशूलवज्रशङ्खाव-ने.सं.)श्रीवत्सस्वस्तिकादिभिः । हेमरौप्यादिपालेषु कल्पितैर्गोमयादिभिः ॥550 ॥ नानावर्णकसंयुक्तैः(नानावर्णकसंयुक्तै-ने.सं.; नानावर्णश्च कुसुमै-चौ.सं.)रक्षतैस्तिलतण्डुलैः । भक्तैश्च दधिसंयुक्तैः(सिद्धार्थदधिसम्मिश्रैः-चौ.सं.)यथाशोभं प्रपूरितैः (यथाशोभं च पूरितैः-चौ.सं.) ॥551 ॥ द्रव्यैर्यष्टिप्रदीपाद्यैर्(द्रव्यैः पिष्टप्रदीपाद्यैर्-ने.सं.; missing-चौ.सं.) श्रुताऽश्रुत्यादिपल्लवैः । औषधीभिश्च मेध्याभिः सर्वबीजैर्यवाङ्कुरैः-चौ.सं.) ॥552 ॥ शङ्खभेर्यादिभिर्घोषैर् (शङ्खभेर्यादिनिर्घोषैर्-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) महागोयस्वरैर्युतैः (महाङ्गैर्गोयसंयुतैः-चौ.सं.) । कुर्यान्नोराजनं लिङ्गे शिवमुद्दिश्य मङ्गलैः ॥553 ॥ पर्वण्यभ्यर्च्य(यावत्पर्वणि-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) विधिना (विधिवत्-चौ.सं.) कुर्यान्नोराजनं शिवे । तावद्युगसहस्राणि रुद्रलोके महीयते ॥554 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.2-5, 7-8, p.14; Chow.7.1-4, 6-7)/ तथा शिवधर्मे -पीतं शुक्लं सुशीतं (निवृच्छुक्लं सुपीतं-ने.सं.; निवृच्छत्सुपीतं-चौ.सं.) वा पट्टसूत्रादिनिर्मितम् (पद्मसूत्रादिनिर्मितम्-ने.सं.) । गन्धोपवीतं (दत्वोपवीतं-चौ.सं.) रुद्राय दत्त्वा वेदान्तगो भवेत् (भवेद्वेदान्तगोचरः-चौ.सं.) ॥560 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.135, p.22; Chow.5.137cd-138ab)

- 13 अथदुग्धादीनां महास्नानसंख्यामाह । शिवधर्म-स्कन्दपुराणयोः -स्नानं शतपलं ज्ञेयम् (स्नानं पलशतं ज्ञेयम्-ने.सं.; जलस्नानं पलशतं-चौ.सं.) अभ्यङ्गे (अभ्यङ्ग-ने.सं.; अभ्यङ्गः-चौ.सं.) पञ्चविंशतिः । पलानां द्वे सहस्रे तु (द्वि सहस्राणां-ने.सं.) महास्नानं प्रकीर्तितम् (तु भक्तितः-चौ.सं.) ॥248 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.42cd-43ab, pp.16-17; Chow.5.41)
- 14 इक्षुरसस्नानमाह । शिवधर्म-भविष्यपुराणयोः -स्नानमिक्षुरसेनापि यो लिङ्गे (लिङ्ग-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) सकृदाचरेत् । लभेद्वैद्याधरं (लभेद्वैद्याधरं-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) लोकं सर्वकामसमन्वितम् ॥240 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.24, p.15; Chow.5.22)/ अथ स्नानभेदमाह । शिवधर्म-भविष्यपुराणयोः - लिङ्गं शीताम्बुना साप्य धारोष्णपयसा

the above passages, these passages also are cited in the context of narrating different rites associated with the worship of *śivaliṅga*, viz. numbers of *mahāsnāna* to be performed; bathing of *śivaliṅga* with different substances and virtues of doing that; smearing of different substances (*lepana*) and its virtue; virtues of offering different flowers to Lord Śiva; offering of *naivedya*, etc. In the process of comparison, it was observed that 168 numbers of variant readings were recorded from Chow. edition of SDS and 119 from the Nep. edition. This shows that verses cited in SKD and attributed to SDS are more similar to Nep. edition of SDS than Chow. edition.

6. Chapter – VI: This chapter of SKD cites passages, verses 2-6, 16-19, 22-26, 36-37, 47, 49, 51, 106, 181, 185-201, and 213-214ab, attributed to SDS eleven times.¹⁵ Almost all verses,

ततः । स्राप्य पश्चाद् घृतेनेशं (घृतेस्नानं-ने.सं.; घृतेनापि-चौ.सं.) त्रयमेवं विशिष्यते (तत एव विशिष्यते-ने.सं.; कृतमेकं विशिष्यते-चौ.सं.) ॥271 ॥ एतत् (एवं-ने.सं.) स्नानत्रयं दत्त्वा (कृत्वा-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) पूजयित्वा तु (च-चौ.सं.) भक्तितः । अश्वमेधसहस्रस्य फलं प्राप्नोति (फलमाप्नोति-ने.सं.) मानवः ॥272 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.37-38, p.16; Chow.5.34-35)/ पञ्चोपचारैरर्चनमाह । तद्यथा शिवधर्म-भविष्यपुराणयोः-लिङ्गस्य लेपनं कुर्याद् दिव्यैः गन्धैः (दिव्यगन्धैः-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) सुगन्धिभिः । वर्षकोटिशतं दिव्यं शिवलोकै (रुद्रलोकै-ने.सं.) महीयते ॥277 ॥ गन्धानुलेपनात्पुण्यं द्विगुणं (द्विगुणः-ने.सं.) चन्दनस्य तु । चन्दनादगुरोर्ज्ञेयं चन्दनादागरुज्ञेयं-ने.सं.) पुण्यमष्टगुणाधिकम् ॥278 ॥ कृष्णागुरोर्विशेषेण (कृष्णागुरोर्विशेषेण-चौ.सं.) द्विगुणं फलमीष्यते (फलमिष्यते-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) । तस्माच्छतगुणं पुण्यं कुङ्कुमस्य विधीयते (विशेषतः-ने.सं.) ॥279 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.63-65, p.18; Chow.5.59-61)/ अथ पुष्पफलमाह । शिवधर्मभविष्यपुराणयोः-अर्कपुष्पं तथैकं च (अर्कस्य पुष्पमेकं च-ने.सं.; अर्कस्य पुष्पे चैकस्मिन्-चौ.सं.) यः शिवाय (शिवाय-चौ.सं.) निवेदयेत् (विनिवेदिते-चौ.सं.) । दश दत्त्वा सुवर्णानि यत्फलं तदवाप्नुयात् ॥292 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.75, p.18; Chow.5.72)/ शिवधर्मभविष्ययोः-सर्वेषां पुष्पजातीनां (सर्वेषामेव पुष्पाणां-ने.सं.) प्रवरं नीलमुत्पलम् । शमीपुष्पसहस्रेभ्यः श्रीदं नीलोत्पलं शुभम् (श्रीमन्नीलोत्पलं परम्-ने.सं.) ॥302 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.81ab, 80cd, p.19; Chow.-missing)/ तत्रापि विशेषः शिवधर्म-भविष्ययोः-नीलोत्पलसहस्रेण-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) यो मालां सम्प्रयच्छति । शिवाय विधिवद्भक्त्या तस्य पुण्यफलं शृणु ॥328 ॥ कल्पकोटिसहस्राणि कल्पकोटिशतानि च । वसेच्छिवपुरे श्रीमान् (नित्यं-ने.सं.) शिवतुल्यपराक्रमः ॥329 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.81cd-83ab, p.19; Chow. 5.78-79)/ शिवधर्म-भविष्ययोः-गुडखण्डकृतानां (गुडखण्डकृ(चु)तानां-चौ.सं.) च भक्षणाणि (भक्ष्याणां-ने.सं.; भक्ष्याणां च-चौ.सं.) निवेदनम् । घृतेन पाचितानां तु (यद्-ने.सं.) दत्त्वा (पुण्यं-चौ.सं.) दशगुणं (शतगुणं-चौ.सं.) फलम् (भवेत्-चौ.सं.) ॥434 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 5.144, p.22; Chow. 5.146cd-147ab)

- 15 तत्रादौ चतुर्दशीपूजनमाह । तत्राप्यादौ व्रतमाह । शिवधर्मे-चतुर्दश्यामथाष्टम्यां (चतुर्दश्यां तथाष्टम्यां-चौ.सं.) पक्षयोरुभयोरपि (पक्षयोः शुक्लकृष्णयोः-चौ.सं.) । योऽब्दमेकं न (अब्दमेकत्र-ने.सं.) भुञ्जीत शिवार्चनरतः शुचिः ॥2 ॥ यत्पुण्यमक्षयं प्रोक्तं सततं सत्रयाजिनाम् । सत्यवादिषु यत्पुण्यं यत्पुण्यं तीर्थगामिनाम् ॥3 ॥ अग्निहोत्रेषु यत्पुण्यं यत्पुण्यं यज्ञयाजिनाम् । तत्पुण्यं सकलं तस्य (प्राप्य-चौ.सं.) शिवलोकं स गच्छति ॥4 ॥ तत्रापि - कृष्णपक्षे त्रयोदश्यामुपोष्य परमेश्वरम् (परमेश्वरे-चौ.सं.) । प्रातर्मध्याह्नयोः पूजां (प्रातर्मध्याह्नयः पूजां-ने.सं.; प्रातर्मध्याह्नपूजां च-चौ.सं.) चतुर्दश्यां समाचरेत् (समारभेत्-चौ.सं.) ॥5 ॥ पञ्चगव्यं स पित्वादौ (सकृत्पीत्वा-चौ.सं.) हविर्भुञ्जीत वायतः । दशानां सोऽश्वमेधानां (अश्वमेधानां-चौ.सं.) फलं प्राप्नोति मानवः ॥6 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.10.141-143;7.8-9,pp.109&44; Chow.10.1-

3;7.7-8)/ शिवधर्मे - कृष्णाष्टम्यां तु नक्तेन (नक्ताशी-चौ.सं.) यावत्कृष्णचतुर्दशी। इह भोगमवाप्नोति परत्र च परां (शिवां-ने.सं. चौ.सं.) गतिम्॥116॥ तथा - योऽब्दमेकं प्रकृवीत (न भुञ्जीत-चौ.सं.) नक्तं पर्वसु पर्वसु। ब्रह्मचारी जीतक्रोधः शिवस्यार्चनतत्परः (शिवार्चाजपतत्परः-चौ.सं.)॥117॥ पर्वसु अष्टमीषु। पर्वसु चतुर्दशीषु। संवत्सरान्ते विप्रेन्द्रान् शिवभक्तान् समाहितः (सदक्षिणम्-चौ.सं.)। भोजयित्वा ततो ब्रूयात् प्रीयतां भगवान् शिवः॥118॥ एवं विधिसमायुक्तः शिवलोकं स गच्छति (शिवलोकं महीयते-चौ.सं.)। न च मानुष्यकं लोकमध्वं प्राप्नुयान्नरः (न च स मानुष्यकं देहं पुनः सम्प्राप्नुयान्नरः-चौ.सं.)॥119॥ (Parallel with Nep.10.149-152, p.110; Chow.10.9-11,17; there are some extra verses after verse 11 in the Chow. edition)/ शिवधर्मे - देवैस्तु भुक्तं (देवैर्यु(भु)क्तं तु-चौ.सं.) पूर्वाह्ने मध्याह्ने ऋषिभिस्तथा। अपराह्णे च पितृभिः सन्ध्यायां गुह्यकादिभिः॥122॥ वामाचारां (कामाचारे-चौ.सं.) महादेवो नक्तेनोद्धरते नरान् (नरम्-चौ.सं.)।23। वामाचारां वक्राचारः। तथा - उपवासाद्वरं (उपवासात्परं-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) भैक्ष्यं भैक्षाद्वरम्(भैक्षात्परं-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) अयाचितम्। अयाचिताद्वरं (अयाचितात्परं-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) नक्तं तस्मान्नक्तेन वर्तयेत्॥124॥ हविष्यभोजनं स्नानं सत्यमाहारलाघवम्। अग्रिकार्यमधःशय्यां नक्तभोजी समाचरेत्॥125॥ तलापि पालविशेषात्कलविशेषमाह - यः पृथ्वीं भाजनं (यः पृथ्वीं भोजनं-ने.सं.); पृथिवीं भाजनं-चौ.सं.) कृत्वा भुङ्क्ते (भुक्तः-चौ.सं.) पर्वसु यत्नतः। अहोरात्रेण चैकं त्रिरात्रफलमश्नुते॥126॥ (Parallel with Nep. 10.154,155cd,153,156,144 p.111,109; Chow.10.19,20cd,18,21,4)/ अथ तलार्चनमाह। शिवधर्मे - ब्रह्मचारी शुचिर्भूत्वा तिसन्ध्यं (तिसन्ध्यां-ने.सं.) पूजयेच्छिवम् (योऽर्चयेच्छिवम्-चौ.सं.)। कुलसप्तकुलमुद्धृत्य (तिसप्तकुलमुद्धृत्य-चौ.सं.) शिवलोके महीयते॥36॥ दानोपवासनिर्घमैः पूजाजागरभोजनैः। महास्नानादिविधिना शिवं पर्वसु पूजयेत्॥37॥ (Parallel with Nep.7.11-12, pp.44-45; Chow.7.10-11)/ शिवधर्मे - चम्पकैर्विल्वपत्रैश्च पूजयेद्यः सदाशिवम्। कृष्णपक्षे चतुर्दश्यां स याति पदमव्ययम्॥47॥ (No parallel in Nep. and Chow.)/ शिवधर्मे - शिवे कृष्णचतुर्दश्यां (शिवकृष्णचतुर्दश्यां-चौ.सं.) यः साज्यं (यामार्द्धं-ने.सं.) गुग्गुलं दहेत्। अपराधसहस्रैकम् (अपराधसहस्रं तद्-चौ.सं.) इहामूलकृतं क्षमेत्॥49॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.123, p.21; Chow.5.125cd-126ab)/ शिवधर्मे - शालितण्डुलप्रस्थेन (शालिनां तण्डुलं प्रस्थं-चौ.सं.) कुर्यादन्नं (शूपदिना-ने.सं.) सुसंस्कृतम्। शिवाय तं चरुं (तच्चरु-ने.सं.) दद्याच्चतुर्दश्यां विशेषतः॥51॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.141, p.22; Chow.5.143.cd-144ab)/ शिवधर्मे - जागरं (जागराद्-ने.सं.) नृत्यगीताद्यैः सकृत्कृत्वा तु शङ्करे (पर्वणि-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.)। मन्वन्तरशतं सायं शिवलोके वसेत्सुधीः (महीयते-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.)॥106॥ (Parallel with Nep.8.20, p.88; Chow.8.20)/ अथ कृष्णाष्टमीव्रतविशेषमाह। शिवधर्मे - कृष्णाष्टम्यां घृतस्नानं कृत्वा लिङ्गे सकृन्नरः। कुलैकविंशमुद्धृत्य शिवलोके महीयते॥181॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.18, p.15; Chow.5.17)/ वर्षपूर्णमाह शिवधर्मे - कृष्णाष्टम्यां प्रयत्नेन नक्तं कुर्यात् (नक्तं कृत्वा-ने.सं.; कृत्वा नक्तं-चौ.सं.) प्रयत्नतः। मार्गशीर्षे शुभे मासे शङ्करं देवमर्चयेत्॥185॥ पीत्वा शक्त्या तु गोमुलमनाहारो निशि स्वपेत्। अतिरात्रस्य यज्ञस्य फलमष्टगुणं लभेत्॥186॥ एवं पौषेऽपि (पुष्येऽपि-चौ.सं.) सम्पूज्य शम्भुनामानमीश्वरम्। कृष्णाष्टम्यां घृतं प्राश्य वाजपेयाष्टकं (वाजपेयफलं-चौ.सं.) लभेत्॥187॥ माघे महेश्वरं नाम कृष्णाष्टम्यां प्रपूजयेत्। निशि पीत्वा च गोक्षीरं गोमेधाष्टकमाप्नुयात् (गोमेधस्य फलं लभेत्-चौ.सं.)॥188॥ फाल्गुने च (फाल्गुन्यां तु-चौ.सं.) महादेवं सम्पूज्य प्राशयेत्तिलान्। वर्षलक्ष महाभोगैः शिवलोके महीयते (राजसूयस्य यज्ञस्य फलमष्टगुणं लभेत्-चौ.सं.)॥189॥ चैत्रे च स्थाणुनामानं कृष्णाष्टम्यां प्रपूजयेत्। यवांश्च भर्जितान् (यवासुसञ्जितान्-चौ.सं.) प्राश्य सोऽश्वमेधफलं लभेत्॥190॥ वैशाखे च शिवं पूज्य (वैशाखे शिवमिष्ट्या च-ने.सं.; वैशाखे शिवनामानम् इष्ट्या-चौ.सं.) पिबेद्ब्राह्मी (ब्राह्मी-चौ.सं.) कुशोदकम्। पुरुषमेधयज्ञस्य (पीत्वा पुरुषमेधस्य-चौ.सं.) फलमष्टगुणं लभेत्॥191॥ ज्येष्ठे पशुपतिं पूज्य गवां शृङ्गोदकं पिबेत्। गवां कोटिप्रदानस्य यत्पुण्यं तदवाप्नुयात्॥192॥ आषाढे चोग्रनामानमिष्ट्या प्राश्य च गोमयम्। सौतामण्यस्य (सौतामण्येस्तु-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) यज्ञस्य फलमष्टगुणं लभेत्॥193॥ श्रावणे शर्वनामानम् इष्ट्या पिण्याकभक्षणम् (इष्ट्या पिण्याकभक्षणात्-ने.सं.; पिण्याकं निशि भक्षयेत्-चौ.सं.)। वर्षकोटिशतं सायं रुद्रलोकं महीयते॥194॥ मासे भाद्रपदेऽष्टम्यां व्यम्बकं नाम पूजयेत् (देवम् अर्चयेत्-चौ.सं.)। प्राशनाद् (प्राशनं-चौ.सं.) बिल्वपत्राणाम् अनन्तफलमाप्नुयात्॥195॥ ईश्वरं चाश्विने मासि (पूज्य-ने.सं.) पीत्वा वै तण्डुलोदकम्। पौण्डरीकस्य यज्ञस्य फलमष्टगुणं लभेत्॥196॥ (मासे चाश्वयुजेष्टम्याम् ईश्वरं नाम पूजयेत्। तण्डुलोदकमालिह्य पौण्डरीकाष्टकं लभेत्-चौ.सं.) कार्तिके रुद्रनामानं सम्पूज्य प्राशयेद्दधि। अग्निष्टोमस्य यज्ञस्य फलमष्टगुणं लभेत्॥197॥ वर्षान्ते भोजयेद्दिप्रान् शिवभक्तिपरायणान्। पायसं मधुसंयुक्तं (घृतसंयुक्तं-चौ.सं.) घृतेनोपरि संप्लुतम् (मधुना च परिप्लुतम्-चौ.सं.)॥198॥ शक्त्या हिरण्यं वासांसि भक्त्या तंभ्यो निवेदयेत्। निवेदयत (निवेदयती-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) रुद्राय गां च कृष्णां पयस्विनीम्॥199॥ वर्षमेकं चरेदेवं नैरन्तर्येण यो नरः। कृष्णाष्टमीव्रतं भक्त्या

except verse no. 47, are found existent in the printed editions of the SDS. These verses are cited in the context of describing virtues of observing religious vows (*vratas*) showing devotion towards Lord Śiva on different auspicious days, viz. *aṣṭamī*, *ekādaśī*, *trayodaśī*, *caturdaśī*, etc., of the bright and dark half (*śuklapakṣa* and *kṛṣṇapakṣa*) of a month for once or year-long at day or night, and specially elaborating at a length the observance of the religious vow on the 8th day of the dark half of a month (*kṛṣṇāṣṭamīvrata*). The last verses, numbered 213 to 214ab of SKD which mention special days (*tithis*) pleasant to Brahmā, Viṣṇu, and Śiva, are syntax-wise found to be somewhat parallel with Nep. edition of SDS; though contextually parallel with verses of both Nep. and Chow. editions. Also, it is worth mentioning that verses, in the abovementioned context, verses in both the printed editions of SDS are also not parallel. Verse no. 47, no parallel of which is found in both the Nep. and Chow. editions of SDS, describes the virtue of worshipping Śiva with *campā* flower and *bilva* leaves on the 14th day of the dark half of a month (*kṛṣṇacaturdaśī*). Like earlier, herein also verses attributed to SDS and cited in SKD are more parallel with Nep. edition of SDS than Chow. edition, because in the process of comparison 49 numbers of variant readings are from Chow. edition whereas only 20 numbers of variant readings from Nep. edition.

7. Chapter – VII: This chapter of SKD cites passages attributed to SDS eleven times. Those verses are verse no. 29-30ab, 41-42, 45, 60, 62, 81ab, 179, 207, 211-213, 219ab, and 69-274 of SKD¹⁶ quoted in different contexts, viz. narration of the vir-

तस्य पुण्यं फलं शृणु ॥200 ॥ सर्वपापविनिर्मुक्तः सर्वैश्वर्यसमन्वितः । वसेच्छिवपुरे नित्यं नेहायाति कदचन (न भूयो भुवि जायते-चौ.सं.;T32; missing-Nep.) ॥201 ॥ इति कृष्णाष्टमीव्रतविधानम् । (Parallel with Nep.10.157-171,pp.111-112, and verses 200 to 201 are not found in Nep., but those verses are found in the paper transcript of SDS bearing no. T32 of IFP; Chow.22-38)/ तथा शिवधर्मे - दशमी शोभना चैव ब्रह्मणः प्रीतिवर्धनी । तिथिरेकादशी पुण्या शङ्करस्य प्रियङ्करी ॥213 ॥ द्वादशी चैव शान्तात्मा विष्णोः सन्तोषवर्धनी ॥214 ॥ (दशमी शोभना चैव तिथि एकादशी तथा । द्वादशी चैव शान्तात्मा तथा तिथि त्रयोदशी ॥-ने.सं. दशमी यमसंयुक्ता इन्द्रेणैकादशी मता । द्वादशी विष्णुसंयुक्ता मदनेन त्रयोदशी ॥-चौ.सं.) (Parallel with Nep.6.37[137], p.36; Chow.6.135; In fact, verses found parallel in the printed editions are not exactly the same as cited in the SKD, rather somewhat identical in their context.)

16 तथा च शिवधर्मे -कृत्वा प्रदक्षिणं (प्रदक्षिणा-ने.सं.) भक्त्या लिङ्गस्य च यथाविधि (शिवस्यैव यथाविधि-ने.

tues of performing with devotion the act of salutation (*namaskāra*), circumambulation (*pradakṣiṇa*), dancing (*nṛtya*), singing (*gīta*), playing musical instruments (*vādāna*), etc. in the abode of Siva; prescription of restrictions on performing certain works on specific auspicious days; restriction and bad effects on consumption of certain foods by the devotees of Siva; virtues of performing the repeated utterance of

सं.; शवस्याऽऽयतनं नरः-चौ.सं.)। सर्वयज्ञोपवासेषु सर्वदानेषु (सर्वयज्ञेषु-ने.सं.) यत्फलम् (this line missing in चौ.सं.)॥29॥ अश्वमेधसहस्रस्य यत्फलं तदपाप्नुयात् (सुखेन लभते फलम्-ने.सं.; लभते फलमुत्तमम्-चौ.सं.)॥30॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.157-158ab, p.23; Chow.164cd-165ab)/ अनेन दण्डप्रणामस्य नमस्काराङ्ग एवोक्तः। तथा च शिवधर्मे -याः सङ्ख्यास्तस्य रेणुनां स्पृशन्ति पाणिपादयोः। तावद्दर्शसहस्राणि रुद्रलोके महीयते॥41॥ प्रणम्य दण्डवद्भूमौ नमस्कारेण योऽर्चयेत्। स यां गतिमाप्नोति न तां सर्वैर्महामखैः (यज्ञशतैरपि-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.)॥42॥ (No parallel of verse no 41 was found and no. 42 is parallel with Nep.5.159cd-160ab, p.23; Chow.5.166cd-167ab)/ अत्र नमस्कारमाह। शिवधर्मे - ओं नमः शिवाय शान्ताय कारणत्रयहेतवे। निवेदयामि चात्मानं त्वं गतिः परमेश्वर॥45॥ (Parallel with Nep.3.83,p.9; Chow.-missing)/ शिवधर्मे - तदेव पुण्यं गीतस्य नृत्यस्य च विशेषतः। तदेव जयशब्दस्य तदेव तालकध्वनेः (हस्तातालध्वनौ तथा-चौ.सं.)॥60॥ (Parallel with Nep.8.43cd-44ab,p.91 ;Chow.8.45cd-46ab)/ शिवधर्मे - भूमिदानेन (भूमिदानस्य-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) यत्पुण्यं कन्यादानेन (कन्यादानस्य-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) यत्फलम्। मुखवाद्येन तत्सर्वं (तत्पुण्यं-ने.सं.; यत्पुण्यं-चौ.सं.) लभते नाल संशयः (उभयं लभते नरः-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.)॥62॥ (Parallel with Nep.8.42cd-43ab; Chow. 8.44cd-45ab)/ शिवधर्मे - लिङ्गस्य दर्शनं पुण्यं दर्शनात्स्पर्शनं वरम् (शुभम्-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.)॥81॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.40ab, p.16; Chow.5.37ab)/ शिवधर्मे -चन्दनागरुकर्पूरैः सुक्ष्मपिष्टैः (प्लक्षपिष्टैः-ने.सं.; कृष्णपिष्टैः-चौ.सं.) सकृद्भूमैः। लिङ्गं पर्याप्तमालोक्य (पर्याप्तमालोक्य-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) कल्पकोटिं वसेद्विचि (कल्पकोटिशतं दिवि-ने.सं.); कल्पकोटिं वसेद्विचि-चौ.सं.)॥179॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.66, p.18; Chow.5.62)/ तत्रापि निषेधः शिवधर्मे -अष्टम्यादिषु सर्वेषु पक्षयोरुभयोरपि। श्मश्रुकर्माङ्गनाभ्यङ्गप्रस्थानानि (श्मश्रुकर्माङ्गनाभ्यङ्गप्रस्थानानि-ने.सं.; श्मश्रुकर्माङ्गनाभ्यङ्गं प्रस्थानं च-चौ.सं.) विवर्जयेत्॥207॥ (Parallel with Nep.12.500, p.163; Chow.12.19cd-20ab)/ भोजने निषेधानाह। शिवधर्मे - मृगाश्चोष्ट्रपयोमत्स्यमांसलशुनगुञ्ज नम् (यूकाश्चोष्ट्रपयोमत्स्यमांसं लशुनकृ(गृ)ञ्जनम्-चौ.सं.)। करञ्जाद्यानि बीजानि (कवकाद्यानि वीर्यञ्च-ने.सं.; कवकद्रव्यं च सूवीर्यं-चौ.सं.) कृत्स्तिं च विवर्जयेत्॥211॥ सर्वदानोद्यतपसामश्वमेधाद्युत्सय च। फलं प्राप्नोति यत्नेन (प्राप्नोत्ययत्नेन-ने.सं.) मत्स्यमांसविवर्जयेत् (मत्स्यमांसविवर्जनात्-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.)॥212॥ सर्वदोषाश्रयं मद्यम् इतिदूराद् (इति पुराद्-चौ.सं.) विवर्जयेत्। क्व मद्यं क्व शिवे भक्तिः क्वाशौचः (क्व शौचं-ने.सं.; क्व मांसं-चौ.सं.) क्व शिवार्चनम्॥213॥ (Parallel with Nep.12.488-490, pp.161-162; Chow.12.6cd-7ab, 8-9)/ तथा शिवधर्मे -आत्मार्यं यः पचेन्मोहान् नरकार्यं स जीवति॥219॥ (Parallel with Nep.11.374cd, p.144; Chow.11.12cd) / शिवधर्मे -कीर्तयिष्यन्ति ये (येऽर्चयन्ति सदा -ने.सं.; अर्चयन्ति सदा -चौ.सं.) रुद्रं न ते प्रकृतिमानुषाः। रुद्रलोकात्परिश्रष्टा विज्ञेयास्ते गणेश्वराः (ते रुद्रा नाल संशयः-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.)॥269॥ एतदेव परं मन्त्रं शिव इत्यक्षरद्वयम्। विस्तारादपि विस्तारं तैलबिन्दुमिवाग्भसि॥270॥ सकृदुच्चारितं येन शिव इत्यक्षरद्वयम्। वद्भुःपरिकरस्तेन मोक्षाय गमनं प्रति॥271॥ एककालं द्विकालं वा त्रिकालं नित्यमेव वा (यत्र वा दृश्यते लिङ्गं सर्वतीर्थानि तत्र वै-चौ.सं.)। ये स्मरन्ति विरूपाक्षं विज्ञेयास्ते गणेश्वराः (गणेश्वरः-चौ.सं.)॥272॥ भवभक्तिपरा (शिवभक्तिपरा-ने.सं.) ये तु भवप्रणतचेतसः (भवप्रणतमानसः-ने.सं.)। भवसंस्मरणोद्युक्ता (भवसंस्मरणे युक्त-ने.सं.) न ते दुःखस्य भागिनः (ते न दुःखस्य भाजनम्-चौ.सं.)॥273॥ नाममालप्रयत्नस्तु (नाममालप्रयत्नोऽपि-चौ.सं.) क्षणधर्मपि (क्षणाधर्ममपि-चौ.सं.) यः शिवे। स मुनिः स महासाधुः स योगी शिवतां (स शिवं-चौ.सं.) ब्रजेत् (this verse missing in Nep., but available in T32 and चौ.सं.)॥274॥ (Parallel with Nep.1.16,14,20,p.2; Chow.1.17,15,21; 12.80cd-81ab; No parallel of verses 270 and 271 are found in the printed editions of SDS)

just the name of Śiva (*nāmakirtana*), etc. Almost all of these verses are found available in the printed editions of the SDS, except verse no. 41, 270 and 271 which record virtues of *daṇḍapraṇāma* and the merits of the utterance of the term Śiva even once in life. Verses cited in SKD and attributed to SDS are more parallel with the Nep. edition of SDS than the Chow. edition. In the process of comparison, 28 numbers of variant readings were recorded from Chow. edition of SDS and 23 from Nep. edition.

8. Chapter – VIII: This chapter of SKD cites passages independently attributed to SDS fifteen times. Those verses are verse no. 2-4, 35, 39, 44-48, 50-54, 58-60ab, 66, 73-75, 80-82, 85-86, 89-96, 99-102, 103-104, 112-115, and 135¹⁷ of

- 17 आदौ शिवालये शिवधर्मः - मृदा चेष्टकं शैलं वा (मृप्रेष्टकं शैलं वा-ने.सं.; मृदाश्लिष्टकशैलं वा-चौ.सं.) यश्च कुर्याच्छिवालये (यः कुर्याद्दि शिवालये-चौ.सं.) । तिसप्तकुलसंयुक्तो (तिसप्तकुलमुद्रुत्य-चौ.सं.) रुद्रलोके (शिवलोके-चौ.सं.) महीयते ॥2 ॥ मृगयात्कोटिगुणितं पुण्यं स्याद्धारुभिः कृते । कोटि कोटि गुणं पुण्यं दारवादिष्टकामये (दारवादिष्ट कामये-ने.सं.; मृत्काष्ठादिष्टकामये-चौ.सं.) ॥3 ॥ ऐष्टकादे (इष्टकाद्-चौ.सं.) द्विगुणं पुण्यं शैले यत् (शैलजे-ने.सं.; शैलके-चौ.सं.) स्याच्छिवालये (स्याच्छिवालये-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) । मृच्छैलयोः समं ज्ञेयं पुण्यमाब्धदरिद्रयोः ॥4 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.4.23-25, p.12; Chow.4.)/ शिवधर्मं - खण्डस्फुटितसंस्कारं (खण्डस्फुटित संस्कारं-ने.सं.; खण्डं स्फुटितं संस्कारं-चौ.सं.) यः कुर्यात्तु (कुर्वीत-चौ.सं.) शिवालये । आरामवासथाद्येषु (आरामावथे वापि-चौ.सं.) लभते मौक्तिकं (मौक्तिकं-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) फलम् ॥35 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.4.51, p.13; Chow.4.51)/ तथाऽप्यूलिङ्गपूजाफलमाह । शिवधर्मं - क्वचिद्गच्छन् (क्वचिद्गच्छे-ने.सं.) यदा पश्येच्छिवलिङ्गमपूजितम् (शिवलिङ्गं पूजितम्-चौ.सं.) । तदा (सदा-चौ.सं.) सम्पूज्य गच्छेद्युः (तत्पूज्य यः गच्छेत्-ने.सं.; सम्पूज्य यो गच्छेत्-चौ.सं.) स याति परमां गतिम् (स रुद्रो नात्र संशयः-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) ॥39 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.12.484, p.161; Chow.12.2)/ अथ शिवालये सुधालेपनफलमाह । शिवधर्मं - सुधाप्रलिप्तं (सुधाविलिप्तं-चौ.सं.) यः कुर्यात् सर्वयज्ञैः शिवालये । तावत्पूयं लभेत्सोऽपि (भवेत्सोऽपि-चौ.सं.) यावदायतने कृते ॥44 ॥ प्रत्यब्दं (प्रत्यन्तं-ने.सं.) यः प्रकुर्वीत शम्भोरायतनं बुधः । धवलं क्षीरसुधया (धवलं सूतं सुधया-चौ.सं.) यथाशोभं च (यथाशोभिश्च-ने.सं.) वर्णकैः ॥45 ॥ यावन्त्यब्दानि (यावत्यहानि-ने.सं.) कुरुते धवलं तु (तत्-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) शिवालये । तावद्ब्रह्मसहस्राणि (तावद्युगसहस्राणि-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) शिवलोके (रुद्रलोके-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) महीयते ॥46 ॥ अथ चित्रलेखनफलमाह । तत्रैव- कारयेच्चित्रशास्त्रज्ञैः यत्राच्चित्रं शिवालये । रुद्रावतारक्रीडाद्यैः प्रयोगैरागमोदितैः ॥47 ॥ यावन्ति (यावत्स-ने.सं.) रुद्ररूपाणि सुरूपाण्यवलेखयेत् (स्वरूपाणि तु लेपयेत्-ने.सं.; स्वरूपाण्यपि लेखयेत्-चौ.सं.) । तावद्ब्रह्मं (तावद्युग-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) सहस्राणि रुद्रलोके महीयते ॥48 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.4.46-50, p.13; Chow.4.48,49cd,50,49ab, 46-47)/ अथ गर्भगृहे लिङ्गोपरि मण्डपदानफलमाह । शिवधर्मं - शिवस्योपरि यो दद्यात्सर्वरत्नोपशोभितम् । मण्डपं (मण्डनं-चौ.सं.) मौक्तिकं श्रीमान् तस्य पूयं फलं शृणु ॥50 ॥ कोटिकोटि विमानैस्तु (विमानैश्च-चौ.सं.) सर्वकामसमन्वितः । आभूतसंप्लवं यावद् आस्ते शिवपुरे सुखी (तावच्छिवपुरे वसेत्-चौ.सं.) ॥51 ॥ तत्रैव वितानवन्धनफलमाह - वितानं (विमानं-ने.सं.) सितपद्मान् मध्ये कमलभूषितम् (पद्मविभूषितम्-ने.सं.) । विचित्रमेकवर्णं वा नववस्तोपशोभितम् (नानावर्णोपशोभितम्-चौ.सं.) ॥52 ॥ किङ्किणीरवकोपेतं कन्दुकैरुपशोभितम् (चन्द्रकैश्चोपशोभितं-ने.सं.; कन्दुकैश्चोपशोभितम्-चौ.सं.) । लम्बितैर्मुक्ताहारैश्च (लम्बकैः सुलदात्मैश्च-ने.सं.; लम्बकैर्मुक्तादात्मैश्च-चौ.सं.) घण्टाचामरशोभितम् (घण्टारुतविभूषितम्-ने.सं.; घण्टाचामरभूषितम्-चौ.सं.) ॥53 ॥ शिवस्योपरि यो दद्यात्पुरतो वापि कल्पयेत् । रुद्रवत्सर्वलोकेषु युगकोटिं स मोदते ॥54 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.176cd-178ab, [174A]cd-176ab; Chow.5.185cd-187ab, 182cd-185ab)/ अथ शिवालये नाना दानफलमाह । तदादौ पात्रप्रशंसा । शिवधर्मं - सर्वेषामेव पात्राणामतिपात्रं महेश्वरः (महेश्वरम्-ने.सं.) । पतनात् लायते यस्मादतीवनरकार्णवात् (.नरकार्णवे-चौ.सं.) ॥58 ॥ यदिष्टं च विशिष्टं च (यदिष्टं विशिष्टं च-चौ.सं.)

न्यायेन समुपार्जितम् । तच्छिवाय निवेद्यं स्याद्भक्त्यानन्तफलार्थिभिः ॥59 ॥ तस्य पात्रस्य माहात्म्याद् दानं भवति (दानमण्वपि-चौ.सं.) चाक्षयम् ॥60 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.4.14;5.198cd-199ab;4.15ab, pp.11,26; Chow.4.12; 5.208;4.13ab)/ शिवधर्मे -पलकोटिसुवर्णस्य (पलं कोटिं सुवर्णस्य-चौ.सं.) यो दद्याद्देवपारगे । शिवाय रौप्यपालेण तस्य पुण्यं ततोऽधिकम् ॥66 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.58, p.17; Chow.5.54)/ शिवधर्मे - भक्त्या निवेद्यं रुद्राय तालवृन्तं मनोहरम् (सुशोभनम्-ने.सं.; सुशोभितम्-चौ.सं.) । दशवर्षसहस्राणि रुद्रलोके (लभते-ने.सं.) महीयते (परमं पदम्-ने.सं.) ॥73 ॥ शिवस्य पुरतो दत्त्वा (दद्याद्-ने.सं.) दर्पणं च सुनिर्मलम् (चापिनिर्मलम्-ने.सं.; चारु निर्मलम्-चौ.सं.) । कल्यायुतसहस्राणि शिवलोके महीयते ॥74 ॥ सुविनीतां स्त्रीयं दार्श्रीं भृत्यं वा यो (भृत्यं वापि-ने.सं.; हृद्यां वा-चौ.सं.) निवेदयेत् (विनिवेदयेत्-चौ.सं.) । नरमेधस्य यज्ञस्य (पुरुषमेधयज्ञस्य-ने.सं.) फलमष्टगुणं लभेत् ॥75 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.68,155ab,156cd;8.97, p.18,23,102; Chow.5.64,162cd,164ab; 8.103)/ शिवधर्मे -महान्महास्वनं दत्त्वा (महान्महास्वनं दद्यात्-ने.सं.; महास्वनं तु यो दद्यात्-चौ.सं.) शङ्खयुग्मं शिवालये (शिवाय तु-चौ.सं.) । युगकोटिसहस्राणं (युगकोटि महाभोगैः-ने.सं.; युगकोटि शतं दिव्यं-चौ.सं.) शिवलोके (रुद्रलोके-चौ.सं.) महीयते ॥80 ॥ भेरी-मृदङ्ग-मुरज (मुरव-चौ.सं.)-तिमिला(तिमिलं-ने.सं.; तिमिलो-चौ.सं.)-पटहादिकम् । वंशकांस्यादिवाद्यं तु यः (वंशकांश्यादि वादितं-ने.सं.; वंशकांस्यादिवादितं यः-चौ.सं.) शिवाय निवेदयेत् (विनिवेदयेत्-ने.सं.) ॥81 ॥ स विमानैर्महाभोगैर्वंशवीणाकृतस्वनैः । युगायुतशतं दिव्यं शिवलोके महीयते ॥82 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.173cd-[174A]ab,170cd-172ab, p.24; Chow.5.181cd-182ab,178cd-180ab)/ अथ गोभूमिपात्रदानफलमाह । शिवधर्मे - दद्यादुभयमुखीं गां च (दद्यादुभयमुखीं गां-ने.सं.; यो दद्यादुभयमुखीं-चौ.सं.) शिवायातीवशोभनम् (शोभनान्-ने.सं.) । सप्तद्वीपां क्षितिं दत्त्वा यत्फलं तदवाप्नुयात् ॥85 ॥ सानादिकार्यमुद्दिश्य (शिवाग्निकार्यमुद्दिश्य-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) सुरुपां च पयस्वीनिम् (सुपयस्वीनीम्-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) । शिवाय (कुलीनां-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) कपिलां दत्त्वा फलं (दत्तं-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) भवति गौशतम् (चाक्षयम्-ने.सं.; गोशतम्-चौ.सं.) ॥86 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.10.362,8.47cd-48ab, p.142,92; Chow.10.228cd-229ab, 49cd-50ab)/ शिवधर्मे -शिवाय यः (यः शिवाय-चौ.सं.) फलोपेतां (जलोपेतां-चौ.सं.) सर्वसस्यप्ररोहिणीम् । महौ महीपतिर्दद्यात् तस्य पुण्यफलं शृणु ॥89 ॥ यावद्गुण्डा भवेद्दूमिर् मयमाना (मीयमाना-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) समन्ततः । तावत्स कल्पसंख्यानं (तावत्कल्पसहस्राणि-चौ.सं.) रुद्रलोके महीयते ॥90 ॥ एवं सर्वत्र विज्ञेयं फलं दण्डप्रमाणतः । ग्रामं पत्तनकं क्षेत्रं विषयान् (ग्राम-क्षेत्र-पुर-क्षेत्र-विषयान्-ने.सं.; ग्राम-खेट-पुर-क्षेत्र-विषयादि-चौ.सं.) विनिवेदयेत् (विनिवेदने-चौ.सं.) ॥91 ॥ सर्वसस्यफलोपेतां (सर्वसस्यफलोपेतं-चौ.सं.) सर्वाबाधाविवर्जितां (सर्वबाधाविवर्जितम्-चौ.सं.) । ग्रामान् (ग्रामं-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) शिवाय यो दद्यात् तस्य पुण्यफलं शृणु ॥92 ॥ सर्वतीर्थेषु यत्पुण्यं सर्वयज्ञेषु यत्फलम् । सर्वदानेषु यत्पुण्यं ग्रामदानेन तत्फलम् (तल्लभेत्-चौ.सं.) ॥93 ॥ सूर्यकोटिप्रतीकाशैः देविकोटिसंयुक्तैः (दिव्यस्त्रीकोटिसंयुतैः-ने.सं.; दिव्यस्त्रीभिरलङ्कृतैः-चौ.सं.) । संयुक्तः (संयुक्तं-चौ.सं.) कोटिशोऽनेकैः सर्वकामसमन्वितैः ॥94 ॥ विमानैर्ग्रामदानेन तिसप्तकुलसंयुतः । यथेष्टमैश्वर्यं लोके मोदते (क्रीडते-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) कालमक्षयम् ॥95 ॥ पुण्यं नगरदानस्य ग्रामदानाच्छताधिकम् । देशदानेन चानन्त्यं (चानन्तं-ने.सं.) न शक्यं तत्रकाशितुम् (तत्रकीर्तितुम्-ने.सं.; परिकीर्तितम्-चौ.सं.) ॥96 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.8.102-109, pp.103-104; Chow.8.108-115)/ शिवधर्मे -रौप्यपात्रदानेन यत्फलं (यत्पुण्यं-ने.सं.) वेदपारगे । तस्माच्छतगुणं पुण्यं शिवं मृत्यालदानतः (शिवे मृत्यालदानतः-ने.सं.; शिवमृत्यालदानतः-चौ.सं.) ॥99 ॥ हेमपालाणि यद्दत्त्वा पुण्यं स्याद्देवपारगे । ताम्रपात्रदानेन तस्माच्छतगुणं भवेत् (शिवे-चौ.सं.) ॥100 ॥ पलकोटिं (पलं कोटिं-चौ.सं.) सुवर्णस्य यो दद्याद्देवपारगे । शिवाय रौप्यपालेण तस्य पुण्यं ततोऽधिकम् ॥101 ॥ हेमपालाणि यो (हेमपालं तु यो-चौ.सं.) भक्त्या शिवाय विनिवेदयेत् । अशक्यं तत्फलं वक्तुं (न शक्यं तत्फलं वक्तुं-ने.सं.; न तस्य शक्यते वक्तुं-चौ.सं.) पुण्यानन्त्यादशेषतः (पुण्यानन्त्यं विशेषतः-चौ.सं.) ॥102 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.56-59, p.17; Chow.5.52-55)/ अथात्रैव वृषोत्सर्गफलमाह । शिवधर्मे - वृषभं (वृषञ्च-ने.सं.) परिपूर्णाङ्गमुदारं च शशिप्रभम् । गोपतिं (गोपितं-ने.सं.) नीलवर्णं च (धूर्वहञ्चापि-ने.सं.; धूर्वहं वाऽपि-चौ.सं.) यथेष्टं (यथेष्टञ्च-ने.सं.; शिवाय-चौ.सं.) विनिवेदयेत् (निवेदयेत्-ने.सं.) ॥103 ॥ यावन्ति देहरोमाणि (तस्य रोमाणि-चौ.सं.) तत्पशोश्च कुलैः सह (तत्रसूतिकुलेषु च-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) । तावद्युगसहस्राणि रुद्रलोके महीयते ॥104 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.8.45cd-47ab, p.92; Chow.8.47cd-49ab)/ शिवधर्मे -दश गावः सवृषभो (वृषश्चैको-चौ.सं.) वृषभैकादशस्मृता (वृषभैकादशी स्मृता-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) । शिवाय विनिवेद्यैव (विनिवेद्यैव-चौ.सं.) विशुद्धैरान्तरात्मना (अवधारय तत्फलम्-चौ.सं.) ॥112 ॥ रुद्रैकादशतुल्योऽसौ (रुद्रैकादशतुल्यात्मा-ने.सं.; रुद्रैकादशतुल्याब्जो-चौ.सं.) बहुभोगादिभिर्गुणैः (बलभोगादिभिर्गुणैः-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) । शिवादिसर्वलोकेषु यथेष्टं मोदते वशी (सुखी-चौ.

SKD. These verses are cited in the context of narrating different subject matters, viz. virtues of constructing an abode for Lord Śiva using different materials; the virtue of worshipping an abandoned *śivaliṅga*; the virtue of painting the abode of Śiva; the virtue of offering *maṇḍapa* and canopy (*vitāna*); the virtue of donating different objects for Lord Śiva. And, passages attributed to SDS conjointly with the names of other Puranas, viz. Sknda and Bhaviṣya Puranas, are cited twice, verses 56-57 and 67-68 of SKD, in this chapter.¹⁸ These are also cited in the context of narrating the virtues of donating different objects for Lord Śiva.

All the above-cited verses are found available in the printed editions of SDS, except verse no. 135 which records a piece of advice not to disrespect Śiva, śaiva scriptures (*śivaśāstra*) and experts in śaiva scriptures (*śivaśādhaka-guru*). In the process of comparison, 97 numbers of variant readings are recorded from Chow. edition of SDS and 73 from Nep. edition. This shows that verses attributed to SDS and cited in SKD are more parallel with the Nep. edition of SDS than the Chow. edition.

Sivadharmottara in cited in Śaivakalpadruma

- Chapter – I: This chapter of SKD cites once a verse attributed to SDU in the context of narrating the superiority of Lord

सं.) ॥113 ॥ कल्पकोटिसहस्राणि कल्पकोटिशतातानि (कल्पकोट्ययुतानि-ने.सं.) च। भुक्त्वा स(तु-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) विपुलान् भोगान् विशेषकुलजैः (अशेषकुलजैः-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) सह ॥114 ॥ तदन्ते ज्ञानमासाद्य प्रसादात्परमेष्ठिनः। विमुच्य मोहकलिलं स्वात्मन्येवावतिष्ठते (स्वात्यन्त्रवावतिष्ठति-चौ.सं.) ॥115 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.10.353-356, p.141; Chow.10.219cd-223ab)/ शिवधर्मं -न शिवं शिवशास्त्रं च शिवात्मसाधकं गुरुम्। निन्दां न लङ्घयेत्तेषां छायामपि कथञ्चन ॥135 ॥ (No Parallel found in Nep. and Chow.)

18 शिवधर्मभविष्ययोः -श्वेतं महाध्वजं दत्त्वा (दद्यात्-चौ.सं.) कृत्वा वा पञ्चरञ्जितम् (वासश्च रङ्गिकम्-ने.सं.; वै पञ्चरङ्गिकम्-चौ.सं.)। किङ्किणीरवसम्पन्नं (किङ्किणीरुतसम्पन्न-ने.सं.; किङ्किणीरवकोपेत-चौ.सं.) मयूरछन्न-शोभितम् (मयूरछन्नभूषितम्-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) ॥56 ॥ स तेनैव (एतेनैव-ने.सं.; स सितेन-चौ.सं.) विमानेन सर्वदेवोपरि (सर्वेषां चोपरि-चौ.सं.) स्थितः। मन्वन्तरसहस्रैकं (संवत्सरसहस्रैक-ने.सं.; मन्वन्तरसहस्रं तु-चौ.सं.) मोदते दिवि रुद्रवत् ॥57 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.161cd-163ab, pp.23-24; Chow.5.168cd-170ab)/ वस्त्रदानफलमाह। स्कन्दे शिवधर्मं च-वासांसि सुपवित्राणि (सुविचित्राणि-ने.सं. चौ.सं.) सारवन्ति (सुरभीणि-ने.सं.) मृदूनि च। धूपितानि शिवे (शिव-चौ.सं.) दद्याद् अकेशानि (अक्लेश्यानि-ने.सं. विकेशानि-चौ.सं.) नवानि च ॥67 ॥ यावत् तद्रस्वतन्तूनां परिमाणं विधीयते (समन्ततः-चौ.सं.)। तावद् युगसहस्राणि (वर्षसहस्राणि-ने.सं.) रुद्रलोके (शिवलोके-ने.सं.) महीयते ॥68 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.136-137, p.22; Chow.5.138cd-140ab)

Siva.¹⁹ And, no parallel has yet been traced in the printed editions of SDU.

- Chapter – II: Passages attributed to SDU, verses 28 and 91-93, have been cited twice in this chapter of SKD²⁰ in the context of narrating the fact that the hymn ‘*namaḥ śivāya*’ is called ‘six-syllabled hymn’ (*ṣaḍakṣara-mantra*) in both Vedas and Āgamas, but is known as ‘five-syllabled hymn’ (*pañcākṣara-mantra*) in general; narrating the characteristics of three different varieties of *japas*, viz. *vācika*, *upāṃśu*, and *mānasa*. And, these verses are found available in the printed editions of SDU. These cited verses of SKD are found more parallel with the Nep. edition of SDU than the Chow. edition, because 8 numbers of variant readings are recorded from Chow. edition and only 4 from the Nep. edition.
- Chapter – III: In this chapter of SKD, verses attributed to SDU have been cited nine times. Those are verse no. 57-58, 70, 74-76ab, 84, 86-87ab, 92, 95-101ab, 104-107, 156-158, and 175-180ab²¹ cited in the context of narrating the great-

- 19 तथा च शिवधर्मोत्तरखण्डे - एवं त्रयोऽपि रागाद्यैर्दोषैर् देवाः समन्विताः । एभ्यः परशिवः शान्तः परिपूर्णः समुक्तिदः ॥39 ॥ एभ्यः - ब्रह्मविष्णुरुद्रेभ्यः । (No parallel yet found in Nep. and Chow.)
- 20 वेदे शिवागमे चैव उभयत्र (चायमुभयत्र-ने.सं.; चैवमुभयत्र-चौ.सं.) षडक्षरः । मन्त्रः स्थितः सतां (सदां-चौ.सं.) मुक्त्यै (वक्त्रे-चौ.सं.) लोके पञ्चाक्षरः स्मृतः ॥28 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.1.36, p.187; Chow. 1.35) इति शिवधर्मोत्तरवचनात् रुद्राध्याये - ‘नमः शिवाय च शिवतराय च’ इति वचनाद् वा वैदिकोऽयमवगम्यते । षडक्षरत्वेन ब्राह्मणक्षत्रियवैश्यमुच्चारणाय वैदिकः । पञ्चाक्षरस्य स्त्रीशूद्रयोः कौलिकत्वपेक्षया सिद्धादीन्न शोधयेत् ॥ एषां लक्षणं च शिवधर्मोत्तरे - यदुच्चनीचस्वरितैः शब्दैः स्पष्टपदाक्षरैः । मन्त्रमुच्चारयेद् वाचा जपयज्ञः सवाचिकः ॥91 ॥ शनैरुच्चारयेन् मन्त्रमीषदोषी प्रचालयेत् । किञ्चिच्छब्दात्स्वयं (किञ्चिच्छब्दं स्वयं-चौ.सं.) विद्यादुपांशुस्तज्जपः (विद्यादुपांशुरुज्जपः-ने.सं.; विद्यादुपांशुः सजपः-चौ.सं.) स्मृतः ॥92 ॥ धिया पदाक्षरश्रेण्या (यदक्षरश्रेण्यां-ने.सं.; यदक्षरश्रेण्या-चौ.सं.) वर्णाद्वर्णं पदात्पदम् । शब्दार्थचिन्तनाद्यद्यत् (शब्दार्थचिन्तनाभ्यस्तं-ने.सं.; शब्दार्थचिन्तनाभ्यन्तः-चौ.सं.) तदुक्तं (स उक्तं-चौ.सं.) मानसं जपम् (मानसः स्मृतः-चौ.सं.) ॥93 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 10.99-13001, p.274; Chow.10.161-162, p.218)
- 21 शिवधर्मोत्तरखण्डे - गङ्गास्नानसमं पुण्यं दर्शनं शिवयोगिनाम् । सर्वतीर्थाभिषेकञ्च (सर्वतीर्थाभिषेकाच्च-चौ.सं.) तत्सम्भाषणमुत्तमम् ॥57 ॥ शिवयोगिशरीरे तु नित्यं सन्निहितः शिवः । योगीन्द्रं पूजयेत्समात् स साक्षात्पूजितः (साक्षात्सम्पूजयेः-चौ.सं.) शिवः ॥58 ॥ तथा शिवधर्मोत्तरे - स्वर्गापवर्गफलदं नरकार्णवतारकम् (नरकार्णवतारणम्-चौ.सं.) । शिवधर्मोत्तरं नाम शास्त्रमीश्वरभाषितम् ॥70 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.4.420,430; 1.16, pp.214, 184; Chow.4.37cd-38ab,47cd-48ab; 1.15cd-16ab)/ अथ प्रातःकृत्यमाह शिवधर्मोत्तरे - उत्थाय पश्चिमे यामे सुगृहीतकमण्डलुः । धीतपादुकम् आक्रम्य (आक्रामन्-चौ.सं.) मूलं कुर्याद् यथाविधि (यथाक्रमम्-ने.सं.; यथाक्रमः-चौ.सं.) ॥74 ॥ दीक्षाविनीतश्चित्तज्ञ (दीक्षाविनीतचित्तज्ञ-ने.सं.; दक्षो विनीतचित्तज्ञो-चौ.सं.) स्तोयदानविधानवित् (भस्मोदकविधानवित्-चौ.सं.) । सहायः शौचकार्येषु (स्वभावशौचकार्येषु-चौ.सं.) तद्भावात्कमण्डलुः (तदभावात्कमण्डलुः-ने.सं.; तदभावे कमण्डलुः-चौ.सं.) ॥75 ॥ शिरः प्रातृत्य तत्कुर्यादन्तर्याय तृणैर्महत् (तृणैर्महीम्-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) ॥76 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.11.39-40,41cd, p.277; Chow.11.2-3,4cd)/ शिवधर्मोत्तरे - दिवा सन्ध्यासु कर्णस्थब्रह्मसूती (कर्णस्थब्रह्मसूत-चौ.सं.) ह्युदङ्मुखः । कुर्यान्मूत्रपुरीषे तु रात्रौ चेद्दक्षिणामुखः ॥84 ॥ (Parallel

ness of *śivayogī* and SDU and specific procedure to perform daily morning routine works, viz. excretion, bathing, cleans-

with Nep.11.42, p.277; Chow.11.5)/ शिवधर्मोत्तरे - न विष्णुमूत्रदीक्षेत (विष्णुमूत्रस्त्रिपत्तल-ने.सं.) छायायामात्मनो (तच्छायायामात्मनो-चौ.सं.) न च। नानिलानलदेवानां गोब्राह्मणजलं प्रति॥86॥ जन्तुश्राद्धवत्(श्राद्धल-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.)भस्मास्थिवृक्षछायां(कृष्णच्छायां-ने.सं.; कृषि छायां-चौ.सं.) विवर्जयेत् (विनिर्जयेत्-चौ.सं.)॥87॥ (Parallel with Nep.11.43cd-44, p.277; Chow.11.6cd-7)/ शिवधर्मोत्तरे - पादावसेचनं (पादावसेवनं-ने.सं.; पादावलेपनं-चौ.सं.) मूत्रं पुरीषं घृणिवनं (मूत्रं पुरीषघृणिवनं-ने.सं.; मूलपुरीषं विघृणिवनं-चौ.सं.) च यत्। दूरादावसथात् सर्वं (कुर्यात्-चौ.सं.) यच्चान्यद्विकृतं भवेत्॥92॥ (Parallel with Nep.11.45, p.277; Chow.11.8)/ शिवधर्मोत्तरे - मार्जनं वामहस्तेन (वामहस्तेन-ने.सं.; वामहस्तेपि-चौ.सं.) वीरणादैरयाज्ञिकैः (वारिणादैरयाज्ञिकैः-चौ.सं.)। (अयाज्ञिकैः वृक्षोद्भवैरित्यर्थः।) गृहीतशिश्रुश्रोत्राद्य समायुक्तकमण्डलुः॥95॥ शौचं कुर्यान्मृदाभ्योभिर् (मृदाभ्योभिर्-ने.सं.) गन्धलेपापनुत्तये (गन्धलेप विमुक्तये-चौ.सं.)। तिस्रो लिङ्गे मृदो योज्यास्त्वैकैकान्तरमृत्तिकाः (योज्यास्त्वैका कान्तरमृत्तिका-चौ.सं.)॥96॥ आमलीफलमालं तु (च-ने.सं.) पञ्च वामकरे तथा (पञ्च वामकरे यथा-ने.सं.; शौचार्यमग्राह्य उत्तमम्-चौ.सं.)। मृदस्तिस्त्रय (मृदस्तिस्त्रय-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) पादाभ्यां (करभ्यां तु-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) मूलोत्सर्गं भवेत् शुचिः॥97॥ पञ्चापाने (पञ्चापादे-चौ.सं.) मृदो योज्यास तत्रिरन्तरमृत्तिकाः (तिस्रश्चान्तरमृत्तिका-चौ.सं.)। दश वामकरे देयाः (योज्याः-चौ.सं.) पाण्योस्सप्त तथोभयोः (तथोभयोः-चौ.सं.)॥98॥ जङ्घाशौचे मृदस्तिस्त्रय (जङ्घाशौचमृदस्तिस्त्रय-ने.सं.) एकैकान्तरमृत्तिकाः। (जङ्घा इत्युक्ते जङ्घादारभ्य पादपर्यन्तम्।) अक्षिणी नासिका कर्णां तिस्रः संशोध्य हस्तयोः॥99॥ कर्दमामेध्यमूलाद्यैर द्रव्यैः सप्तपञ्चधा (मृदङ्ग सप्तपञ्चधा-ने.सं.; दिग्भंगस्तवन्तं पञ्चवार-चौ.सं.)। क्षालिते वारिणा पूर्वं (मृद्भिः-चौ.सं.) स तिस्रोत्तरमृत्तिकाः (तिस्रोत्तरमृत्तिकाः-ने.सं.; तिस्रश्चान्तरमृत्तिका-चौ.सं.)॥100॥ आमणिबन्धनात्पाणिं (आमणिबन्धनाद्य करौ-चौ.सं.) मृत्तोयेन विशोधयेत्॥101॥ (Parallel with Nep.11.43ab,46-49ab,50-52ab, pp.277-278; Chow.11.6cd, 9-12ab, 13, 14cd-15)/ शिवधर्मोत्तरे - उपस्पृशनकाले तु तिसृभिः क्षालयेत्करौ। अन्तः कृत्वा भुजौ (बहिः-चौ.सं.) सम्यग् बहिर्जानुं (बहिर्जानु-ने.सं.; बहिर्जानु-चौ.सं.) विधाय (निधाय-चौ.सं.) च॥104॥ उद्धृताभिरुफेनाभिः (उद्धृताभिरुफेनाभिः-ने.सं.; उद्धृताभिरनुष्णाभिः-चौ.सं.) पूताभिर्वीक्ष्य (पूताभिर्वस्त्र-ने.सं.; पूताभिर्वान-चौ.सं.) चक्षुषा। हृदमाभिरशस्ताभिस् (हृदयाभिरशब्दाभिस्-ने.सं.) हृदमाभिरसेनाभिस्-चौ.सं.) लिखतुर्वा (लिखतुर्वा-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) समाचरेत्॥105॥ परिमृज्य (परिमृज्येद्-चौ.सं.) द्विराचम्य (द्विराचम्यं च-चौ.सं.) द्वादशशङ्खानि वा लभेत् (चालभेत्-ने.सं.; संस्पृशेत्-चौ.सं.)॥106॥ द्वादशशङ्खानि - इन्द्रियस्पर्शादीनि। वा शब्दोऽल व्यवस्थावाची। तत्रापि विशेषः। आचमेद् ब्रह्मतीर्थेन ब्रह्मसूत्री उदङ्मुखः (ह्युदङ्मुखः-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.)। तदन्तरान्तरे पाणिमाल्याप्लाव्य चाम्भसा॥107॥ (Parallel with Nep. 11.49cd,52cd-54ab,55, pp.277-278; Chow.11.12cd,16-17,18cd,20ab)/ शिवगङ्गायां वारुणमन्त्रैः स्नात्वा शैवस्नानं कुर्यात्। तद्यथा शिवधर्मोत्तरे - सोपवीतः (सोपनीयः-ने.सं.) समाचम्य पानीयमभिमन्त्रयेत्। एकविंशतिवारंश्च (एकविंशतिवारं तु-चौ.सं.) शैवमन्त्रेण (शिवमन्त्रेण-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) भावितः (भक्तिः-चौ.सं.)॥156॥ (शैवमन्त्रेण पञ्चाक्षरेण।) ध्यायमानः शिवे शान्तं शनैः स्नानं समाचरेत्। आचम्य चात्मनः कुर्यादभिषेकं ततः पुनः॥157॥ कुम्भेन पर्णपुटैः करद्रव्यपुटेन वा। जपन्नेकादशान्मानं (शिवेनैकादशान्मानं-चौ.सं.) स्नापयेत्तेन वा पुनः (स्थापयेद्येन वा पुनः-ने.सं.; स्वयमन्येन वा पुनः-चौ.सं.)॥158॥ (Parallel with Nep.11.93-94, p.280; Chow.11.58-60)/ अत्र वस्त्रविशुद्धिमाह। शिवधर्मोत्तरे - वस्त्रशौचं प्रवक्षामि तच्छुद्धौ (तच्छुद्धौ-चौ.सं.) शुद्ध्यते यतः। वस्त्रशौचविहीनात्मा शुचिरप्यशुचिर्भवेत्॥175॥ देवकार्योपयोगानां (देवकार्या प्रयोगानां-ने.सं.; देवकार्योपयुक्तानां-चौ.सं.) प्रत्यहं शौचमिष्यते। वाससामितरेषां च शौचं कुर्याद्यथाविधिः (शौचं कुर्यान्मलागमे-ने.सं.; कार्यं शौचं मलागमे-चौ.सं.)॥176॥ खगैर्वाऽदूषिते (खगैर्वा दूषिते-चौ.सं.) वृक्षे निर्मले वा शिलातले। दुर्वाजाले (दुर्वाजाले-चौ.सं.) शुचौ वापि क्षालितेन तृणेन च (क्षालितेषु तृणेषु वा-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.)॥177॥ विष्णुमूत्रशुक्रदिग्धानां (विष्णुमूत्रशुक्रदिग्धानां-ने.सं.; विष्णुमूत्रशुक्रादिन् धूलि-चौ.सं.) मृत्तोयेन विशोधनम्। कार्यमादौ ततः क्षारैर वस्त्राणां च मनीषिणा (क्षारैर्गोमूलाद्यैश्च शोधनं-ने.सं.; क्षारैः गोमूलाद्यैर्विशोधयेत्-चौ.सं.)॥178॥ सुचेलरज्जुनेलाणां (चैलवद्रज्जुनेलाणां-ने.सं.; चैलावद्रज्जुनेलाणां-चौ.सं.) पक्षचामरचर्मणां (पक्षचामरचर्मणि-ने.सं.; वत्याशुद्ध पालाणां-चौ.सं.)। वल्कलानां च सर्वेषां प्रोक्षणं तु विधीयते (शुद्धिः कार्या विज्ञानता-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.)॥179॥ गोपालैर्वर्षणं (गोपालैर्वर्षणं-ने.सं.) चैषां विशेषः परिकीर्तितः (विशेषः परिकीर्तितः-ने.सं.; विशेष अश्वादिक वर्तत-चौ.सं.)॥180॥ (Parallel with Nep.11.56-57, 59-60,63,64cd, p.278; Chow.11.20cd-22ab,23cd-25ab,27cd-28ab,29ab)

ing of clothes, etc., of a *śivayogī*/Saivite mendicant. Parallels of all these cited verses are available in the printed editions of SDU. Besides, there are other general references to SDU as the later part of SDS and mention that according to Yājñavalkya SDU is a Pāśupata text that is not inferior to Vedas²². Sixty-one numbers of variant readings are recorded from the Chow. edition of SDU and only thirty-seven from Nep. edition. Thus, it is concluded that the abovementioned cited verses of SKD are more parallel with Nep. edition of SDU than the Chow. edition.

- Chapter – IV: There is no direct mention of passages attributed to SDU in this chapter of SKD; however, a verse in this chapter which is attributed to SDS is found in the available printed edition of the SDU.²³ The same verse is cited earlier in the second chapter of SKD and is attributed to SDU.
- Chapter – V: Passages attributed to SDU, verses no. 2-5, 7, 9-15, 20-21, 23-35, 38-39, 58-59, 130-148ab, 425-426, 562-563, and 571-581, have been cited eleven times in this chapter of SKD.²⁴ These verses are cited in the context of

22 याज्ञवल्क्येन पाशुपतमिति शिवधर्मोत्तरशास्त्रमेव वेदैः समानमाद्रियते ।

23 शिवधर्मं [actually found in शिवधर्मोत्तरे] -वेदे शिवागमे चैव उभयत्र (चायमुभयत्र-ने.सं.; चैवमुभयत्र-चौ.सं.) षडक्षरः । मन्त्रः स्थितः सतां मुक्त्यै (सदां वक्त्रे-चौ.सं.) लोके पञ्चाक्षरः स्मृतः ॥378 ॥ (Parallel with Nep. 1.36, p.187; Chow. 1.35)

24 तलादावासननिर्णयः । शिवधर्मोत्तरे - आसनं(आसन्न-चौ.सं.) तूलसम्पूर्णं सितवस्त्रावगुण्डितम् । कृष्णाजीनोत्तरीयं (व्याघ्रकृष्णजिनं-चौ.सं.) च (वाथ-चौ.सं.) विन्यसेन्मृदुचर्मणि (विन्यसे मृदुचर्मण-चौ.सं.) ॥2 ॥ चर्मणि - व्याघ्रचर्मणि । पद्मक(पद्मक-चौ.सं.)स्वस्तिकादिनाम् अभ्यस्तेनासनेन तु (अभ्यसेदासने दृढे-चौ.सं.) । सन्निध्यास्य (तथाचार्य-चौ.सं.) नमस्कृत्य (नमस्कृत्वा-चौ.सं.) शिवं देवीं गणाधिपम् ॥3 ॥ ऋजुग्रीवः शिरोवक्षो नाभिश्लिष्टोष्ठ(नातिश्लिष्टोष्ठ-ने.सं.; नातिष्ठेच्छ्लिष्ट-चौ.सं.)लोचनः । किञ्चिदुन्नमितशिरा दन्तैर्दन्तान् न च स्पृशेत् (दन्तैर्दन्तान् संस्पृशेत्-चौ.सं.) ॥4 ॥ दन्ताग्रसन्निधौ जिह्वां सचलां सन्निवेशयेत् (सन्निवेश्य च-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) ॥5 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.10.1199-1202ab, p.168; Chow.10.61cd-64)/ शिवधर्मोत्तरे - तपांसि यानि तप्यन्ते (पठ्यन्ते-ने.सं.; कीर्यन्ते-चौ.सं.) यज्ञदानव्रतानि च । सर्वतीर्थभिषेकश्च प्राणायामश्च तत्समः ॥7 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.10.81, p.273; Chow.10.145)/ शिवधर्मोत्तरे - प्राणो वायुः शरीरस्थस्तस्यायामो (स्तदायामो-चौ.सं.) निरोधनम् । रेचकः पूरकः (पूरकश्चैव-चौ.सं.) कुम्भस्त्रिविधः परिकीर्तितः (कुम्भस्त्रिविधः सम्प्रकीर्तितः-ने.सं.; कुम्भकश्च लिधोच्यते-चौ.सं.) ॥9 ॥ नासिकापुटमङ्गल्या पीड्यैकमपरेण च (तु-चौ.सं.) । औदर्यं (जठरं-चौ.सं.) रेचयेद्वायुं रेचकाद्रेचकः (रेचनाद्रेचक-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) स्मृतः ॥10 ॥ बाह्वेन वायुना देहं हतितव्यूरयेद्दशम् । तथा पूर्णः (पूर्णश्च-चौ.सं.) स तिष्ठेत् (सातिष्ठत्-चौ.सं.) पूरणात्पूरकः स्मृतः ॥11 ॥ न मुञ्चति न गृह्णाति वायुमन्तर्बहिः स्थितम् । आपूर्णः (सम्पूर्ण-चौ.सं.) कुम्भचत्तिष्ठेदचतः स तु कुम्भकः ॥12 ॥ कन्यसः (कनिष्ठस्य-चौ.सं.) सकृदुद्धातः (सकृदुद्धातः-ने.सं.; सकृदुद्धूतः-चौ.सं.) स च द्वादशमालकः (द्वादशमालकम्-चौ.सं.) । मध्यमश्च द्विरुद्धातः(द्विरुद्धात-ने.सं.; द्विरुद्धूत-चौ.सं.) श्वतुर्विंशतिमालकः ॥13 ॥ उत्तमश्च त्रिरुद्धातः(त्रिरुद्धात-ने.सं.; त्रिरुद्धूतः-चौ.सं.) षट्त्रिंशत् तत्त्वमालकः(कालमालकः-चौ.सं.) । स चागर्भः(अगर्भश्च-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) सगर्भश्च प्राणायामो द्विधा स्थितः(स्मृतः-चौ.सं.) ॥14 ॥ जपध्यानं विनाऽगर्भः(जपं ध्यानं विनागर्भः-चौ.सं.) सगर्भस्तसमन्वितः(सगर्भस्

तत्समन्वयातु-चौ.सं.)॥15॥ (Parallel with Nep.10.50-55ab,71, p.271-272; Chow.10.112-117ab,135)/ शिवधर्मोत्तरे - ध्यानयज्ञपरः (ध्यानयज्ञः पर-ने.सं.; ध्यानं यज्ञः पर-चौ.सं.) शुद्धः सर्वदोषविवर्जितः। तेनेष्टा मुक्तिमाप्नोति (तेनेष्टा मुक्तिमाप्नोति-ने.सं.; इष्टा मुक्तिमाप्नोति-चौ.सं.) बाह्यशुद्धैश्च नाध्वरैः (बाह्यैः स्थूलैश्च साध्वकैः-चौ.सं.)॥20॥ हिंसादिदोषमुक्त्वात्तद्विशुद्धो (हिंसादिदोषमुक्त्वात्तद्विशुद्ध-चौ.सं.) चित्तसाधनः (चित्तसाधनम्-चौ.सं.) ध्यानयज्ञः (ध्यानयोगः-ने.सं.; ध्यानयज्ञः-चौ.सं.) परस्तस्मादुपवर्गाफलप्रदः॥21॥ (Parallel with Nep.10.1209-10, p.268; Chow.10.71cd-73ab)/ तद्यथा शिवधर्मोत्तरे - चिन्त्येद्दुदये पूर्व क्रमाद्वापि गुणलयम्। तमः प्रच्छाद्य रजसा रजः सत्वेन छादितम् (छादयेत्-चौ.सं.)॥23॥ ध्यायेत्तमण्डलं पूर्वं कृष्णं रक्तं सितं क्रमात्। सत्योपरि गुणातीतं पुरुषं पञ्चविंशकम्॥24॥ हेयमेतदशुद्धं च (धेयमेतदशुद्धं च-चौ.सं.) मुक्त्वा शुद्धं (त्यक्त्वा शुद्धं-ने.सं.; त्यक्त्वाशुद्धं-चौ.सं.) विचिन्तयेत्। ऐश्वर्यं (ऐश्वरं-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) पङ्कजं दिव्यं पुरुषोपरि संस्थितम्॥25॥ द्वादशाङ्गलविस्तीर्णं शुद्धं विकशितं सितम्। नालमष्टाङ्गलं तस्य नाभिकन्दसमुद्भवम्॥26॥ पद्मपलाहकं ज्ञेयमणिमादिगुणाष्टकम्। तत्कणिका च वैराग्यं नालं ज्ञानं शिवात्मकम्॥27॥ शिवधर्मं च (शिवधर्मश्च-ने.सं.) तत्कन्दमिति पद्मं विचिन्तयेत्। तद्भ्रमज्ञानवैराग्यशिवैश्वर्यमयं (तद्भ्रमज्ञानवैराग्यं शिवधर्ममयं-चौ.सं.) परम्॥28॥ ज्ञात्वा पद्मासनं शार्वं (पद्मासनेन धार्यं-चौ.सं.) सर्वदुःखान्तमाप्नुयात्। तत्पद्मकणिकामध्ये शुद्धे दीपशिखाकृतिः (शुद्धदीपशिखाकृति-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.)॥29॥ अङ्गुष्ठमात्रमचलं ध्यायेदौंकारमीश्वरम्। ध्यायेद्वा (ध्यात्वा वा-चौ.सं.) सततं शान्तं वक्ष्यमाणैकरूपकम् (वक्ष्यमाणैकरूपकम्-ने.सं.; वक्ष्यमाणैकरूपिणम्-चौ.सं.)॥30॥ प्रधानपुरुषातीतं सितपद्मस्थमीश्वरम्॥31॥ वक्ष्यमाणरूपमाह - शुद्धस्फटिकसंकाशं जटामुकुटभूषितम् (जटामुकुटमण्डितम्-चौ.सं.) प्रसन्नवदनं शान्तं सर्वावयवशोभनम् (भस्मना चोपशोभितम्-चौ.सं.)॥32॥ सितपङ्कजमध्यस्थं समाधिस्थं तिलोचनम्। पद्मासनमथमचलमीषत्संवृतलोचनम्॥33॥ सबीजपूरककरं (सद्भुजपूरककरं-ने.सं.) वरदाभयपाणिकम् (वरदाभयपाणिकम्-चौ.सं.) द्वीपिचर्मपरिधानम् (द्वीपिचर्मोम्बरधरम्-चौ.सं.) अक्षमालाधरं हरम्॥34॥ प्रभाकिरणपर्यन्तं भाषयन्तं दिगाननम् (प्रभाकिरणपर्यन्तं नैर्भाषयन्तं दिगाननम्-ने.सं.; प्रभाकिरणवर्षन्तमाभासितं दिगाननम्-चौ.सं.) संसारार्णवपर्यन्तं (संसारपर्यन्तं-ने.सं.) पुरुषानीकतारणम् (पुरुषानीकतारणम्-ने.सं.; पुरुषातीतकारणम्-चौ.सं.)॥35॥ (Parallel with Nep.10.1212-1219,1221,1240-1243, pp.268-270; Chow.10.75-82ab,83cd-84ab,102-105)/ शिवधर्मोत्तरे - श्रीकण्ठनाथं वरदं चतुर्वेदपरं (चतुर्वेदं परं-ने.सं.) हरम्। ध्यायमानस्य सततमैश्वर्यं सम्प्रवर्तते॥38॥ वरदोक्तत्वादभयोऽपि वाच्यः। चतुर्वेदो मृगस्तदुक्तत्वात् परशुरपि वाच्यः। एवं मुहूर्तमर्थं वा ध्यायेद्यः (ध्यायेत्-चौ.सं.) श्रद्धया शिवम्। सोऽपि गतिमाप्नोति न तां सर्वमैहामखैः॥39॥ (Parallel with Nep.10.1228,1296, pp.269,274; Chow.10.88,158)/ शिवधर्मोत्तरे - ईशानाद्यानि सूक्ष्माणि ब्रह्माण्येकाक्षराणि (ब्रह्माण्येकाक्षराणि-चौ.सं.) तु। मन्त्रे नमः (मन्त्रोन्नमः-ने.सं.) शिवायेति संस्थितानि यथाक्रमम्॥58॥ मन्त्रे षडक्षरे सूक्ष्मे (सूक्ष्मः-चौ.सं.) पञ्चब्रह्मतनुः शिवः। वाच्यवाचकभावेन स्थितः साक्षात्स्वभावतः॥59॥ Parallel with Nep.1.28-29, p.185; Chow.1.27-28)/ अथ प्रयोगानुसारेण प्रायश्चित्तान्याह। शिवधर्मोत्तरे -सन्ध्यालयपरिभ्रष्टः (सन्ध्या यत् परिभ्रष्टः-चौ.सं.) शिवैकादशिकालयम् (शिवैकादशकं लयम्-चौ.सं.)। जपत्वा सिद्धिमाप्नोति (शुद्धिमाप्नोति-ने.सं.; विशुद्धिमाप्नोति-चौ.सं.) शानहीनश्च तज्जपेत्॥130॥ शिवस्य शिवपञ्चाक्षरस्य। एकादशिकालयं लयस्त्रिंशद्धारम्। पर्वण्यपूज्यं (पूर्वण्यपूज्यं-चौ.सं.) देवेशं गुरुमग्निं च भक्तितः। अदत्त्वा च बलिं तल शिवस्याष्टशतं (शिवाष्टस्य शतं-चौ.सं.) जपेत्॥131॥ पर्वणि चतुर्दश्याम्। अष्टशतम् अष्टोत्तरशतम्। पलं पुष्यं फलं मूलमन्नपानाद्यमौषधम्। अनिवेद्यं न भूञ्जीत यदाहाराय कल्पितम्॥132॥ अनिवेद्यं प्रभुज्ञानः प्रायश्चित्ती भवेन्नरः (प्रायश्चित्तं समाचरेत्-चौ.सं.)। शिवाष्टशतजप्तेन पूजया च (पूजयाच्य-चौ.सं.) विशुद्धयति॥133॥ अनस्थिप्राणि(प्राण-ने.सं.)संघातं हत्वैकादशकं (हत्वैकादशिकां-ने.सं.) जपेत्। हत्वा (हत्वा-ने.सं.) च पक्षिणः सर्वाः (सर्वान्-ने.सं.) त्रिरैकादशकं (त्रिरैकादशिकां-ने.सं.) पुनः॥134॥ पक्षिमारेणे - एकादशोत्तरशतम्। सर्पमार्जारानकूलं (सर्पमार्जारानकूलान्-चौ.सं.) श्वानमृष्टं खरं हयम्। गजाद्यांश्च (अजाद्याश्च-चौ.सं.) मृगान् सर्वान् हत्वा चाष्टशतं (वाष्टशतं-ने.सं.) जपेत्॥135॥ अलं अष्टशतम्-अष्टोत्तरशतानि। जपेदष्टसहस्रं च (जपे च तत्सहस्रं तु-चौ.सं.) सच्छूद्रस्य (स शूद्रस्य-ने.सं.) प्रमारणे। सद्भुतः शिवभक्तश्च नाद्यान्मृतकसूतके (नान्यं मृतकसूतके-चौ.सं.)॥136॥ संस्करेषु च सर्वेषु गृहेषु किमुतान्यतः। सूतके न तु (सूतकेन्यत्र-चौ.सं.) भोक्तव्यं नैत्यकं (नित्यं-चौ.सं.) च (किञ्चिद्-चौ.सं.) विवर्जयेत्॥137॥ भुक्त्वा प्रमादतः स्नेहाच्छिवस्याष्टशतं जपेत्। श्वविड्वराहचाण्डालैः (श्वानवाराहचण्डालैः-चौ.सं.) दुर्जनैः कपिकुकुटैः॥138॥ उलूकगृध्रकाकायैः (चक्रवाकगृध्रकाकायैः-चौ.सं.) स्पृष्टमन्त्रे न भक्षयेत्। शिवैकादशजप्तेन गव्येन हविषा ततः (बुधः-ने.सं.; पुनः-चौ.सं.)॥139॥ पीतेन शुद्धते (शुध्य-ने.सं.) क्षिप्रमभोज्याहारदूषितः। तीर्थयात्राविशुद्धात्मा (विशुद्धात्मा

narrating seating materials (*āsanas*), rite of breath control (*prāṇāyama*), and meditation (*dhyāna*) associated with the procedure of performing muttering (*japavidhi*); prescription of different expiations (*prāyaścittas*) for committing various mistakes pertaining to the worship of *śivaliṅga*; different food-offerings (*naivedyas*) to be offered during the worship of *śivaliṅga*; worship of a *śivaliṅga* with six different products acquired from a cow, viz. *gomaya*, *goracanā*, *gomūtra*, *gokṣīra*, *godadhi*, and *gogrta* (*ṣaḍaṅgaśivārcanavidhi*). Parallels of all these cited verses are available in the printed editions of the SDU, and, in this context, it is to be

च-चौ.सं.) सद्वृत्तः शिवभावितः ॥140 ॥ पुलैरपि न भुञ्जीत सार्धं क्रूरैरधार्मिकैः । महापातकशुद्धयर्थं सहस्राणि जपेदृष्ट ॥141 ॥ प्राणायामैस्त्रिसन्ध्यासु (प्राणायामैस्त्रिसन्ध्यं च-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) शिवमग्निं च पूजयेत् । रेतोमूत्रपुरीषाणि प्राश्य पीत्वा च वारुणीम् ॥142 ॥ वारुणीम् - मदिराम् । भुक्त्वा चान्नमभोज्यानां (चान्नम् अभोज्यानां-ने.सं.; चान्नं न भोज्यान्नं-चौ.सं.) गत्वा चाप्यन्त्यजां स्त्रियम् (चाप्यन्तिमस्त्रियम्-चौ.सं.) । जप्त्वा शिवायुतं सम्यक् पूर्वोक्तविधिना बुधः (पुनः-चौ.सं.) ॥143 ॥ पञ्चगव्यं सकृत्पीत्वा सर्वपापैः प्रमुच्यते । गोमूत्रं गोमयं क्षीरं दधि सर्पिरनुक्रमात् ॥144 ॥ जपेत् त्रिः पञ्चब्रह्मण (जपं च पञ्चभिर्वर्णैः-चौ.सं.) ओंकारेण कुशोदकम् । पलाशपद्मिनीपत्रे (पलाशपद्मपत्रे वा-चौ.सं.) ताम्रपत्रेऽथवा (ताम्रे वाप्यथवा-चौ.सं.) स्थितम् (स्थितः-चौ.सं.) ॥145 ॥ कृत्वैकस्थं शिवेनैव जपेदृष्टशतं (जपमष्टशतं-चौ.सं.) पुनः । अहोरात्रोषितः स्नातः शिवस्य पुरतः स्थितः ॥146 ॥ ओंकाराद्येन (ओंकाराद्येन-चौ.सं.) मन्त्रेण प्राङ्मुखस्तच्छनैः पिवेत् (जपेत्-चौ.सं.) । मन्त्रेण - पञ्चाक्षरेण । पीतमालो (पीतमाले-चौ.सं.) भवेत्पूतः सम्पूर्णः शशिनिर्मलः ॥147 ॥ ब्रह्महत्यादिभिः (ब्रह्महत्यादिभैः-ने.सं.) पापैः सर्वैरवाशु (सर्वैरपि-चौ.सं.) मुच्यते (विमुच्यते-चौ.सं.) ॥148 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.11.1398cd-1404ab,1406-1418ab, pp.280-282; Chow.11.63cd-69ab,71-83ab)/ शिवधर्मोत्तरे - पायसं दधिभक्तं च घृतं मध्वा (घृतमध्वा-ने.सं.; घृतं दध्ना-चौ.सं.) परिप्लुतम् । निवेदयीत शर्वायापूपांश्च (निवेदयीत शर्वाय भक्तांश्च-ने.सं.; निवेदयेच्छिवायैतन्-चौ.सं.) घृतपाचितान् (घृतपाचितम्-चौ.सं.) ॥425 ॥ क्षीरयुक्तेन नैवेद्यं (क्षीरभक्तेन नैवेद्यं-ने.सं.; क्षीरधु नैवेद्यैः भुङ्क्ते-चौ.सं.) दशकोटिगुणाधिकम् (दशगुणाधिकं फलम्-चौ.सं.) । शर्करादधिसंयुक्तं (दधिशर्करया युक्तं-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) तत्पुण्यं स्याद्दशाधिकम् ॥426 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.1.88.4.412cd,414cd, p.191,213; Chow.1.87cd-88ab,4.28cd-29ab)/ तद्यथा शिवधर्मोत्तरे - गोमयं गोरचना (गोरचन-चौ.सं.) मूत्रं क्षीरं दधि घृतं गवाम् । षडङ्गानि पवित्राणि सर्वसिद्धिकराणि च ॥562 ॥ गोमयादुत्थितः श्रीमान् बिल्ववृक्षः शिवप्रियः । तलास्ति (तलास्ते-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) पद्महस्ता श्रीः श्रीवृक्षस्तेन स स्मृतः ॥563 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.1.80-81,p.191; Chow.1.79cd-81ab)/ शिवधर्मोत्तरे - बीजान्युत्पलपद्मानां पुनर्जातानि गोमयात् । गोरोचना च माङ्गल्या पवित्रा सर्वसाधिका(सर्वसिद्धिदा-चौ.सं.) ॥571 ॥ गोमूलाद्गुगुलुर्जातः सुगन्धिः (सुगन्धः-चौ.सं.) प्रियदर्शनः । आप्रेयः (आहारः-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) सर्वदेवानां शिवस्य च विशेषतः ॥572 ॥ यद्भीजं जगतः किञ्चित् तद् ज्ञेयं क्षीरसम्भवम् । दध्नः सर्वाणि जातानि माङ्गल्यान्यर्थसिद्धये ॥573 ॥ घृतादमृतमुत्पन्नम् (घृतादमृतमुद्भूतम्-चौ.सं.) अमराणामतिप्रियम् । तस्माद्भूतेन पयसा दध्ना च स्नापयेच्छिवम् ॥574 ॥ तदन्ते चोष्णतोयं कषायैश्च विरक्षयेत् । स्नाय शीताम्बुना पश्चाल्लिङ्गं रोचनया लिपेत् (रोचनमालभेत्-ने.सं.) ॥575 ॥ पूजयेद्विल्वपत्रैश्च पद्मनीलोत्पलैरपि (पद्मनीलोत्पलैरपि-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) । अर्चयित्वा दहेद्भक्त्या (दहेत्पश्चाद्-चौ.सं.) घृतयुक्तं तु (च-चौ.सं.) गुगुलुम् ॥576 ॥ पायसं दधिभक्तं च घृतमध्वा (घृतं दध्ना-चौ.सं.) परिप्लुतम् । निवेदयेत् (निवेदयीत-ने.सं.; निवेदयेत्-चौ.सं.) शर्वायापूपांश्च (शर्वाय भक्तांश्च-ने.सं.; शिवायैतन् भक्ष्यं च-चौ.सं.) घृतपाचितान् (घृतपाचितम्-चौ.सं.) ॥578 ॥ कृत्वा प्रदक्षिणं (प्रदक्षिणां-ने.सं.) चान्ते प्रणिपत्य क्षमापयेत् । अनेन विधिना देवः षडङ्गेन प्रसीदति ॥579 ॥ इहलोकं परं चैव सर्वान् कामान् (सर्वकामान्-चौ.सं.) प्रपच्छति । षडङ्गविधिना तस्मान्प्रपतिः पूजयेच्छिवम् ॥580 ॥ शिवभक्तः समुत्तारं कुलानामेकविंशतिम् । स्वर्गं स्थाप्य स्वयं गच्छदैश्वर्यं पदमव्ययम् (परमं पदम्-चौ.सं.) ॥581 ॥ इति षडङ्गविध्यचर्चनम् । (Parallel with Nep.1.82-91,p.191; Chow.1.81cd-91ab)

mentioned herein that these cited verses are more parallel to the verses of Nep. edition of SDU than the Chow. edition, because in the process of comparison 108 variant readings are recorded from Chow. edition of SDU and only 47 from Nep. edition.

- Chapter – VI: Passages attributed to SDU were not cited in this chapter of SKD.
- Chapter – VII: Passages from SDU have been cited twice, verse no. 177 and 275, in this chapter of SKD.²⁵ These two are cited in the context of preaching the greatness of the worship of Lord Siva. and parallels of these are available in the printed editions of SDU. All recorded variant readings are from Chow. edition of SDU, thus, like earlier, these verses are more parallel to the verses of the Nep. edition of SDU than the Chow. edition.
- Chapter – VIII: Only verse no. 138 of this chapter of SKD is attributed to SDU.²⁶ It is cited in the context of preaching the significance of following the teachings of Śivadharmasāstra for a Saivite, and its parallel verse is found in the printed editions of SDU. In the process of comparison, two variant readings are recorded from Nep. edition of SDU and 3 from Chow. edition. Thus, it is concluded that this verse is more parallel to Nep. edition of SDU than the Chow. edition.

Passages of Śivadharmasāstra and Śivadharmottara cited in Śivāmṛtsārasamuccaya

Regarding the citation of passages attributed to Śivadharmasāstra, i.e. SDS and SDU in the SASS of Śrīśadeva, it is worth mentioning that an elaborate discussion on this matter has been published earlier in my article “*Traces of Śivadharmasāstra and Śivadharmottara in the Śaiva Texts in Odisha*”. Though SASS has all together forty chapters, the

- 25 शिवधर्मोत्तरे - सम्पूज्यमानं विधिना यः पश्येच्छुद्धया शिवम् । सोऽपि यागफलं कृत्स्नं प्राप्नुयान्नात्र संशयः (तत्समं फलमाप्नोति शिवस्य वचनं तथा ।-चौ.सं.) ॥177 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.1.97,p.192; Chow.1.98)/ शिवधर्मोत्तरे – शिवदासत्वम् अपन्ना (आपन्नाः-चौ.सं.) नरनारीनपुंसकाः । तेऽपि तन्नामसंयोगाद्यान्ति रुद्रपदं हि तत् (रुद्रपुरं महत्-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) ॥275 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.2.266,p.203; Chow.2.166cd-167ab)
- 26 शिवधर्मोत्तरे-यावदक्षरसङ्ख्यानं(सङ्ख्यानां-चौ.सं.) शिवशास्त्रेषु पुस्तकम् (शिवज्ञानस्य पुस्तके-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) । तावद्दर्शसहस्राणि(तावत्कालसहस्राणि-चौ.सं.) शिवलोके महीयते (दाता शिवपुरे वसेत्-ने.सं.; तथा शिवपुरे वसेत्-चौ.सं.) ॥138 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.2.178,p.197; Chow.2.77cd-78ab)

purview of the discussion on the aforementioned topic in the above article was within the first thirty-five chapters of the SASS, and, the remaining five chapters, i.e. 36th to 40th chapters, were out of the purview of that article. This was because, the digital transcript of those chapters was then not prepared from the only complete palm-leaf MS of SASS preserved in Odisha State Museum, though a digital copy of that MS was then recently collected from the said repository. Now, as an edition of the SASS by me is under process with financial assistance from ICPR, New Delhi, and almost in its completion stage, therefore herein, without repetition of published matters, I would focus only on passages cited within the 36th to 40th chapters of SASS and attributed to SDS and SDU. There are only seven and a half numbers of verses in the 36th chapter of the SASS and none of those are attributed to SDS and SDU. The last verse, i.e. verse no. 9²⁷, of the 37th chapter, is attributed to SDS and no parallel of this verse is yet found in the printed editions of the SDS. It is worth mentioning that the same verse is cited in the 8th chapter of SKD and attributed to SDS. In the 38th and 39th chapters, no verses have been attributed to SDS and SDU. The 40th chapter cites passages attributed to SDS eight times²⁸. All those cited verses are available in printed editions of SDS

- 27 शिवधर्मे – न शिवं शिवशास्त्रं च शिवात्मसाधकं गुरुम् । निन्दां न तं दयेतेषां छायामपि कथञ्चन ॥9 ॥ (No parallel found in Nep. & Chow.)
- 28 शिवधर्मे – सर्वयज्ञोपवासेषु सर्वतीर्थेषु यत्फलम् । शिवजाप्योपहारेण (स्तुतिजप्योपहारेण-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) सर्वं (शिवे-चौ.सं.) तत्फलमाप्नुयात् ॥2 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.5.160cd-161ab, p.23; Chow.5.167cd-168ab)/ शिवधर्मे – शिवभक्तिः (शिवे भक्तिः-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) क्षमा सत्यं समस्तेन्द्रियसंक्षमः (अशेषेन्द्रियसंयमः-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) । सर्वभूतेषु (शिवभक्तेषु-ने.सं.) मैत्री च शिवधर्मस्य लक्षणम् ॥13 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.12.536,p.168; Chow.12.70cd-71ab)/ शिवधर्मे – निर्गतः (निवृत्तः-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) सर्वसङ्गैर्भ्यः (सर्वरोगैर्भ्यः-चौ.सं.) शिवध्यानरतस्सदा । ज्ञेयः शिवयती श्रीमान् (शिवयतीन्द्रोऽयं-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) अभ्यनिष्ठो जितेन्द्रियः ॥19 ॥ चरेन्मधुकरभिक्षाम् (माधुकरीञ्चरेद्भिक्षाम्-ने.सं.; माधुकरीं चरेद्भिक्षाम्-चौ.सं.) एकान्नं परिवर्जयेत् । उपवासात्परं भिक्षामेकान्नं गृहिणामलम् (गृहिणाऽऽहृतम्-चौ.सं.) ॥20 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.11.380,405,pp.145,149; Chow.11.19,49cd-50ab)/ शिवधर्मे – यः सर्वसङ्गनिर्मुक्तः (सर्वसङ्गविनिर्मुक्तः-ने.सं.) शुद्धः(शुद्धः-ने.सं.; शिवः-चौ.सं.) शिवपरायणः । सोऽपि (योऽपीर-ने.सं.; सोऽपीह-चौ.सं.) तद्वचनं श्रुत्वा (वपनं कृत्वा-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) योगीन्द्रो चतुरो(योगीन्द्रानुचरो-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) भवेत् ॥25 ॥ तुल्यमेव फलं प्रोक्तं शिवेनाढ्यदरिद्रयोः (शिवे चाढ्यदरिद्रयोः-चौ.सं.) । तयोरप्यधिकं तस्य (पुण्यं-ने.सं.) यः शिवे भावनाधिकः ॥26 ॥ विभवे सति यो मोहात् कुर्याद्विधिविस्तरम् । न(नैव-चौ.सं.) तत्फलमावाप्नोति (तत्फलमाप्नोति-चौ.सं.) प्रलोभाक्रान्तमानसः ॥27 ॥ (Parallel with Nep.11.406,5.60-61,pp.149,17-18; Chow.11.50cd-51ab,5.56-57)/ शिवधर्मे – यावन्ति (यावत्स-ने.सं.) पशुरुद्राणि (रुद्ररूपाणि-ने.सं.-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) सुरूपाण्यवलेखयेत् (सुरूपाणि तु लेपयेत्-ने.सं.; सुरूपाण्यपि लेखयेत्-चौ.सं.) । तावद्युगसहस्राणि शिवलोके (रुद्रलोके-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) महीयते ॥29 ॥ शिवमाल्योपनयनं (शिवमाल्यापनयनं-चौ.सं.) पूजान्ते (पूजान्ते-ने.सं.) यत्प्रमार्जनम् (प्रमार्जनम्-ने.सं.; भूप्रमार्जनम्-चौ.सं.) । एकैकमेव तुल्यं स्यात् चान्द्रायणफलं लभेत् (चान्द्रायणफलं तु-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) ॥30 ॥ चिरं पर्युषितं (चिरपर्युषितं-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) माल्यं शिवस्यापनयेत्(शिवस्यापनयेत्-ने.सं.; शिवस्थानयेत्-चौ.सं.) यः । गोसहस्रफलं तस्य लभतीति(भवतीह-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) न संशयः ॥31 ॥ (Parallel

and of these, two verses, i.e. verse no. 29 and 32, are also found cited in the 8th chapter of SKD and attributed to SDS.

Conclusion

From the above deliberation, it may be easily concluded that the Saivite tradition of Odisha was very much influenced by SDS and SDU, and, the versions of SDS and SDU available or influenced by Odisha's Śaiva tradition bear much closeness with Nepal's versions of SDS and SDU than the Chowkhamba editions of SDS and SDU which are prepared, according to the editor's declaration, based on the manuscript preserved in Adyar Library, Chennai, Tamil Nadu.²⁹

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- with Nep.4.50,9.140,5.192cd-193ab, pp.13,108,25; Chow.4.47,9.21cd-22ab,5.202)/ अथ पूज्यलिङ्गपूजाफलमाह। शिवधर्मे – क्वचिद्द्रच्छन् (क्वचिद्द्रच्छेद्-ने.सं.) यदा पश्येच्छिवलिङ्गमपूजितम् (शिवलिङ्गप्रपूजितम्-चौ.सं.)। तदा सम्पूज्य गच्छेद्यः(तदा तत्पूज्य यो गच्छेत्-ने.सं.; सदा सम्पूज्य यो गच्छेत्-चौ.सं.) स याति परमां गतिम् (स रुद्रो नाह संशयः-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.)॥32॥ यः शिवं पूजयेन्नित्यं मनुजोऽपि (अन्त्यजोऽथ-चौ.सं.) जितेन्द्रियः। भावाभाव(भवभाव-चौ.सं.)समायुक्तः स याति(स गच्छेत्-ने.सं.; सोऽपि गच्छेत्-चौ.सं.) परमां (परां-चौ.सं.) गतिम्॥33॥ (Parallel with Nep.12.484,7.69,pp.161,48 ; Chow.12.2,7.75cd-76ab)/ शिवधर्मे – निर्मलैः शुद्धसलिलैर् (क्षान्तिसलिलैः-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) लोकमाह्लादकारकैः (समाप्यायनशीतलैः-ने.सं.; लोकमाह्लाद्य शीतलैः-चौ.सं.)। इह सौख्यमवाप्नोति परल च परां (शिवां-ने.सं.; चौ.सं.) गतिम्॥38॥ (Parallel with Nep.11.451cd-452ab,p.156; Chow.11.96) / शिवधर्मे – य इदं (इमं यः-ने.सं.) पठते नित्यं शृणुयाद्वा समाहितः (शृणुयाद्वापि भक्तितः-ने.सं.)। स मुक्तः सर्वपापेभ्यो (सर्वपापैस्तु-ने.सं.) शिवलोके महीयते॥65॥ धनमायुर्यशोविद्यां प्रभावमतुलं (धनमायुर्यशोविद्याप्रभावेऽतुलो-चौ.सं.) लभेत् (भवेत्-चौ.सं.)। शुभेनोपचयं याति नित्यं पूर्णमनोरथः॥66॥ (Parallel with Nep.1.42,45,p.3 ; Chow.1.39,42)
- 29 'अञ्चार पुस्तकालय से प्राप्त मातृका के आधार पर इसका पाठ हेमाद्रि के चतुर्वर्गचिन्तामणि के व्रतखण्ड, लिंगादि पुराणों के पाठमलों से अनुसम्मत कर सम्पादित किया है।' -SDS, Chow., p. ix; 'प्रस्तुत पाठ को अञ्चार लाइब्रेरी, मद्रास में विद्यमान पाठ के आधार पर सम्पादित किया गया है.....' – SDU, Chow., p. xvii.

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Kokilasāndeśa: A Messenger Poem with Historical Insights

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Abstract

Kokilasāndeśa, the Sanskrit messenger poem of **Uddaṇḍa Śāstri**, is a significant and invaluable source of information on the geographical and socio-cultural progress of North Kerala during the medieval period. It offers valuable insights into administrative systems, rulers, local traditions, major festivals, temples, rivers, and eminent scholars in the region. The poem also provides a comprehensive view of the importance of the Sanskrit language and its growth in ancient times. *Kokilasāndeśa* witnesses that many Sanskrit scholars held influential roles at the courts of various kings in the medieval period. The comprehensive nature of this poem, which aims to bridge the gap between literature and historiography, enlightens us about the interdisciplinary value of *Kokilasāndeśa*, providing a thorough understanding of Kerala's history and culture.

Key Words: Lādapuram , Kamba, Karigiri, Kṣīrasindhu, Kottayam, Sambadgrāma, Kolathunāḍu, Kukkudakrodadeśa , Vetathunāḍu, Sambharakrodam, Azhavānchery, Kalady, Porkalam, Vrishapurasingi, Sangamagrāma, Thiruvañcikuḷam, Cennamaṅgalaṁ

Introduction

Kokilasāndeśa is a comprehensive guide to the socio-cultural history of North Kerala. It presents a detailed note on the various places, temples, and major festivals that were integral to the medieval period of this region. **Uddaṇḍa Śāstri** was born in Lādapuram, in Tamil Nadu (near **Kāñcipuram**). He was a court poet of Māna-

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vikrama, a prominent member of the Zamorin Dynasty of Kozhikode (Kunhunni Raja, 1980: 76). He wrote this poem, inspired by Kālidāsa, the first poet to write the messenger poem in Sanskrit. The beauty of the *Kokilasāndeśa* is unparalleled, comprising 162 verses divided into two parts: the *Pūrva* and the *Uthara*. The poem's primary objective is to provide its readers with geographical and historical awareness. The narration, essentially a heartfelt message conveyed to his girlfriend in Jayanthamaṅgalam, Kochi, via *Kokilā*, adds a layer of beauty and creates a fantastic experience for the readers. The journey of the cuckoo, which begins in the coastal region of the Kambam river in Tamil Nadu, is a beautiful and enlightening testament to the power of nature and the unwavering resilience of life. The poet vividly describes the lifestyle and friendly conditions of the people of North Kerala and suggests several safe places, ensuring a smooth and issue-free journey. The assessment of Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī's significant contribution to historical insights during the medieval period of North Kerala is the main objective of the present paper.

The journey begins

The poet's masterful depictions of Kerala's regions, intricately intertwined with the marking of important places and temples in Tamil Nadu, evoke a profound sense of awe and admiration for the natural landscape. Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī's portrayal of the fragrant breeze from the flourishing garden on the banks of the river Kamba, accompanied by the melodious chirping of birds, is a testament to his artistic prowess. The Viṣṇu temple nestled in the foothills of Karigiri and the pigeon, which resembles smoke holes, resonate with the thematic essence of the cuckoo, drawing the audience into the poet's world. They invite the audience to marvel at the natural beauty of these regions and feel inspired by the poet's deep admiration for the environment.

Significant Places and Rivers in Tamil Nadu

Kāñcipuram, a city steeped in ancient Indian history, is renowned for its unique cultural experiences. The Tundira region near Kāñci, with the shrine of Kāmākṣī there, as mentioned in *Kokasāndeśa*, offers a distinct experience. The poet underscores the idea that the

best poetry is born from Tuṇḍīradarśana. This concept alludes to the divine inspiration or vision that poets receive, enriching the cultural significance of the region. This divine inspiration, often associated with the sighting of a particular bird or natural phenomenon, is believed to enhance the writer's poetic prowess. Kāñcipuram, with its breathtaking natural beauty, appears very different from above. The Kṣīrasindhu (Pālāzhi) and the arecanut trees that grow on its banks are the blessings of the region. The poet mentions that many sacrifices took place on the banks of the Kṣīrasindhu. A large number of scholars who had proven their proficiency in Vedic chant and were well-versed in the sciences resided in the Agrahāra-s, which were traditional Brāhmin settlements known for their role in preserving Vedic knowledge. Even parrots chanting Vedic hymns while sitting on a tree branch were a regular sight in the region, amidst its awe-inspiring natural beauty.

Describing the *Kṣīrasindhu*, the poet compares the beauty of the *Kokilā* to that of the *Kāḷindī*, hinting at a potential ecological threat. The *Kṣīrasindhu*, a river that flows two miles south of **Kāñci**, is a significant part of India's cultural and historical heritage. The river *Vegavathi* (*Vegavatiyar*) is a branch of *Pālāzhi*, also known as *Kambayār* and *Kambānadi* (Kodungallur Kunjikuttan Thampuran, 2014: 104). The *Kṣīrasindhu* river, with its rich cultural and historical significance, originates in Nandi Durgam in Mysore and flows through Mysore, North Arcot and Chinkalpet before entering the Bay of Bengal (Kodungallur Kunjikuttan Thampuran, 2014: 112). It is a river that has been a part of Kerala's history and culture for centuries, often associated with religious and cultural practices. However, the river is now facing ecological concerns, a fact underscored by the evidence of ancient sacrifices on its south bank (**Uddaṇḍa Śāstri**, 2012, Vs:25)

Embarking on a journey to the Chola region, Cuckoo is in for a spiritual awakening. The poet's suggestion to visit the Vilva temple, where Lord Śiva is revered, after the wind from the river Nīva blows, is a profound experience. The majestic Cauvery river, a sight to behold, can be seen from a distance, framed by lush green trees and groves as one traverses the area. The poet's vivid portrayal of

Śrīraṅgapuram, a paradise that gleams like an emerald in the midst of the river Kāveri, is a testament to the spiritual beauty of this land.

Kokilā's next destination is Hosalam, home to the renowned Lakshmi Nārāyaṇapuram temple. This spiritually significant place, adorned with small towns and gardens, is situated on the banks of the Cauvery. The journey to Kerala, across the forested Sahya mountain range, is a pilgrimage in itself. Kanyākumāri, the southernmost tip of the Sahyādri mountain range, offers a spiritual view that spans the states of Gujarat, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, and Kerala. The distance is about 1600 km. The *Kokilasāndeśa* described that Paraśurāma lived in the foothills of these natural hills after killing all the *Kṣatriya*-s. Verse 39th of the *Pūrva* part of this text also attests that Paraśurāma donated the entire land to the Brāhmins, establishing a longstanding tradition in the region.

The poet offers *Kokilam* practical advice on how to combat the threat of forest fires. The poet's words can be considered a villager's folklore, as they state that the heat and cold of the wind will help identify the presence of fire. The poet indirectly emphasises the importance of forest protection, and the practical advice given to *Kokilam* reflects the region's geographical challenges and the poet's profound concern for the journey's safety. This approach ensures *Kokilā* is well-prepared and protected, instilling a sense of care and responsibility in the audience and making them feel adequately prepared due to the poet's practical advice.

Prominent places in Kerala

The significance of the *Kokilasāndeśa* cannot be overstated, as it meticulously details the region's geographical peculiarities and administrative systems of the 15th century AD, providing a wealth of enriching information. It provides valid and reliable information on scholars from the area who contributed to different fields during the medieval period, which is advantageous for further research. Kottayam, Sambadgrāma, Kolathunāḍu, Kukkudakrodadeśa (Kozhikode), Vettathunāḍu, Sambharakrodam, Āzhavānchery, Kalady, Porkkalam, Vrishapurasangī (Thrissure), Sangamagrāma, Thiruvañcikuḷam, and **Cennamaṅgalam** are notable cities from the me-

dieval period of North Kerala, as mentioned by Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī in *Kokilasandeśa*.

Kottayam

In the 15th century, Kottayam was a renowned city in northern Kerala, boasting a unique charm to behold. High-rise mansions and enchanting gardens were the hallmark of this ancient city. Adding to its charm, it never fails to captivate and attract all. Verse 44th of the first part of the *Kokilasandeśa* extols the beauty and allure of Kottayam, a place that truly captivated the senses and engaged the interest of all.

Kokilasandeśa, a significant literary work, mentions Harischandra, a prominent king in Kottayam. The kings' profound respect for *Mīmāṃsā* philosophy and scholars is a testament to the intellectual richness of Kottayam's history. The 47th verse of the *Pūrvabhāga* of *Kokilasandeśa* mentions a spirited, eloquent, and learnt princess named Swathi. *Kokilasandeśa* mentioned that the *Kṣatriya*-s, whose lineage traces back to the Tripunithura dynasty, ruled Kottayam. The poem reveals that the Kottayam dynasty had adopted princes from the Trippunithura dynasty in ancient times. Before its adoption, the dynasty was known as the *Bhṛgugotṛa*, and later, they were regarded as the *Bhṛgu Viśvāmītra* tribe. The present location of the Kottayam dynasty is in the North Malabar region, encompassing the Kannur and Wayanad districts (Kodungallur Kunjikuttan Thampuran, 2014: 120).

Sambadgrāma

Sampadgrāma, a picturesque area nestled in the western region of Kottayam, holds a unique geographical significance. *Kokilasandeśa* describes Sambadgrāma as a place where flowers stir due to the wind coming from the hair of Śiva's head (*Gaṅgā*). This region, also known as the village of wealth due to its rich land (Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī, 2012, Vs:50), is situated in the Taliparamba taluk of the Kannur district. The tall buildings, polished with lime, further enhance the village's charm. The poet recommends that *Kokilā* be lured into the beautiful Śiva temple, Vellimala (Mount Kailāsa), a symbolic place (Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī, 2012, Vs:51). This suggests that the large houses were a sym-

bol of the economic progress of North Kerala in the medieval period. Sampadgrāma, located in Chirakkal Taluk between Kannur and Kavvā in North Kerala, is now known as Thaliparamba. (Kodungallur Kuññikkuṭṭan Tampuṛān, 2014:127) Historians confirm that the name Thaliparamba was derived from the word *Thalikaṇṇaramba* in Malayālam. A temple in Thaliparamba, known as Lakshmiapuram, holds a significant place in history. The legend of Lord Rāma offering prayers at the shrine (*maṇḍapa*) is a testament to its rich cultural heritage in ancient tradition. This historical significance connects us to a rich past, where the temple was a place of worship and reverence. According to the law, a Brāhmin does not worship at the same place where a *Kṣatriya* worships; hence, they refrain from worshipping at this temple. The temple also upholds the tradition of not allowing kings and royal princes to enter the *maṇḍapa* at Taliparamba. Similarly, women are restricted from entering the temple during the daytime, except on the days of *Śivarātri* and *Viṣu*. The tradition of opening the passageway of Śrī Pārvatī only when the Zamorin king arrives is a unique custom that is still practised today. (Kodungallur Kuññikkuṭṭan Tampuṛān, 2014:123)

Kolathunāḍu

Kolathunāḍu, the administrative centre of the Kola kings in the northern part of Kerala, was a region of lush greenery and abundant cardamom cultivation. The area, known as Sabaram in the *Kokilasāṇdeśa*, was a picturesque landscape that even inspired poets like the great scholar Śankara. Ezhimala, the headquarters of Kolathunāḍu, was strategically located in the Malabar region, with its coastal beauty and hilly terrain. Today, Ezhimala, in the Kannur district, remains a significant location, now home to the Naval Academy, which adds a modern touch to its historical charm.

The Kola region, a vast expanse that extended from the Perumba river to Puthupattanam, also encompassed parts of the state of Karnataka. The kings who embraced the history of Kerala in the Kolathiri series ruled the Kola kingdom, a region of immense historical significance. Historians have documented that Cheramān Perumāḍi divided Kerala into four parts: Kolathunāḍu, Eranāḍu, Perumbadappu, and Venād. These parts were further divided into the princely

states of Kolathiri, Kozhikode, Kochi, and Travancore, respectively. Kolathunāḍu, a region in northern Malabar, was under the rule of King Chirakkal, a significant leader in the region's history. It is also noted that they co-existed with Hyder Ali. Kadathanāḍu and Kottayam were each part of Kolanāḍu (Kodungallur Kunjikuttan Thampuran, 2014: 127).

Kozhikode

When the renowned poet **Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī** mentions Kozhikode, the first image that comes to mind is of the large mansions situated on elevated ground. In the *Kokilasāndeśa*, the poet refers to this region as *Kukkutakrodadeśa*. In this city, famous for its beauty, many houses, beautifully whitewashed with lime, stood as a symbol of prosperity. During the medieval period, red stone was used in the construction of buildings, a unique architectural practice in this region. The poet advises *Kokilā* not to mistakenly try to carve the building in Kozhikode as if it were a tender leaf. This advice not only speaks to the unique architectural style of Kozhikode but also to the cultural symbolism of the buildings. The awe-inspiring strength and beauty of the medieval buildings in Kozhikode are a testament to the rich local culture.

Water resources and water transportation played a significant role in the economic development of each region. To assess Kozhikode's strength in relation to the complex, we can count the number of goods carriers present there. **Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī** mentions that a large number of boats were waiting on the seashore to unload their goods. King Mānavendra of the Zamorin dynasty (1467–1475) maintained diplomatic relations among neighbouring rulers and built a powerful kingdom (K. V Krishna Ayyar, 1999: 81)

He accepted tribute from the conquered kingdoms. **Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī**, a court poet of Mānavendra, spent a long time living a joyful life in Kozhikode, discovering the coolness and freshness that the blossoming trees and the sprawling beach offer to those who love Kozhikode. His perspective on Kozhikode, as a place of beauty and tranquillity, adds a personal and emotional dimension to the region's cultural aspects, evoking a sense of admiration and wonder.

Vettathunāḍu

Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī has used the word *Deprān Prakasān* in *Kokilasāṇḍeśa* to indicate the Vettathunāḍu dynasty (Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī, 2012, Vs: 70). In addition, he explains that the kings here, who valued Vedic studies, provided numerous incentives in the fields of art and culture, thereby enriching the cultural fabric of South India. The kings in the dynasty had regarded that the *kalidoṣa* could be reduced through the study of the *Veda*-s. This belief resonates with the deep-rooted cultural traditions of the region. *Kokilasāṇḍeśa* attests that *Śvetāraṇyam* (Tṛprāññoṭu temple) was a famous temple in the medieval period. Devotees hold the belief that the temple will completely wipe out the sins of those who visit from afar. Kings from the Nair community have ruled this region, including Tirur and Ponnāni, in the medieval period. The kings of Vettathunāḍu maintained an alliance with the powerful Zamorin of Kozhikode.

Sambharakrodam

In the regions of Malappuram and Ponnāni, a robust administrative system once thrived on the banks of the **Bhāratapuzha**. The poet's advice to the cuckoo, to provide a beautiful breeze when it sees the king of Sambarakrodam, adds an intriguing layer to the historical significance of this system, inviting us to delve deeper into the region's past. The temple of Chamravattom Ayyappa, a significant cultural landmark in the regions of Malappuram and Ponnāni, is a testament to the strong faith and devotion of its followers. The temple, often submerged in water during the monsoon season, is believed to be protected by the fierce deity of Lord Ayyappa. Despite the torrential rain, no object from the temple is washed away, reinforcing the believers' unwavering faith in the deity's power.

Āzhvanchery

Verse 77th of the *Kokilasāṇḍeśa* describes Āzhvanchery as being ruled by a dynasty known as the *Netranārayana*-s. They ruled over the *Oriparambil Mana* (Guruvayur) and *Āzhvanchery Mana* (Āthavaāḍu). Their headquarters were located in Āthavanāḍu in the Malappuram district. The name Athavanāḍu was derived from *Āzhvanchery Thambrakkal Vazhumnāḍu*. The king was well-versed in

mathematics, astronomy, and other sciences. Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī attests that this region, renowned for its unparalleled sweetness and abundance of mangos, was a testament to the sweetness of its character, akin to the sweetness of honey.

Kalady

The *Kokilasāndeśa* describes a place known as *Pādapadma* (Kalady) in Tānūr, Malappuram district. (Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī, 2012, Vs: 78) The poet says that this is the place where Lord Śiva, in a display of unparalleled tenderness, carefully placed the stone outside when the pain became unbearable during the wedding. The *Kokilā* message makes it clear that this place, located in the Mukkola temple, is as delicate as Pārvatī's skin and as beautiful as the lotus flower. Its sternness in destroying *Mahiṣāsura* makes it a must visit.

Porṅkaḷam

Porṅkaḷam, also known as *Raṅakhaḷabhuvī* in the *Kokilasāndeśa*, was a place of scholarly conversations. The poet advises Cockoo to visit Porṅkaḷam before entering the Mukkoḷa temple. He suggests a visit to the house of Payyūrāndya Brāhmaṇa (*Maharṣi*), a place rich in both scholarship and wealth. Payyūr Bhattathiri, the esteemed scholar of the poetic court of the Zamorin king Mānavikrama, was known as the Maharṣi. His house, located in Pūṅkuṅṅam, near Guruvayur, which was part of the Kochi district, was a hub of art, culture, and scholarly activities. *Kokilasāndeśa* describes that even the parrots in his house were known to engage in intellectual arguments. Many Brahmins who excelled in the fields of art and culture were part of their lineage. In the venue of scholars of Zamorin Mānavikrama, nine people from that floor were participants simultaneously (N. P Unni, 1997: 30). The poet suggests that if the description of the scriptures from the *Maharṣi*'s house, the recitation of the *Purāṇa*-s, the hospitality, the respect, or the scholarly conversation brings happiness to the mind, then you should listen to the audience full of his faithful scholars. This statement indicates that the great scholar Payyūr Bhattathiri (*Maharṣi*) has realised the propriety of his conduct.

Thrissur

Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī mentions the word *Vriṣapurasangī* to refer to Thrissur. The poet describes the beautiful breeze blowing in *Vriṣapurasangī*, which removes the foam from the face of the divine bull. It is similar to jasmine in colour, spreading a fragrance as it touches the hair of Pārvatī, who is sleeping with her head on Śiva's lap. The poet provides a vivid and awe-inspiring description of the famous Vadakkunnatha temple in Thrissur.

Saṅgamagrāma

The temple of Bharata in Irinjalakuda, popularly known as Saṅgamagrāma, is beautifully depicted in the *Kokilasandeśa* by Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī. The poet notes that the dark colour of the shrine is similar to the glow of the green trees, which spreads to the surrounding areas. Uddaṇḍa advises that those who come to the temple do not recognise the cuckoo, which has the same ornament as the green creepers. Historians explain that this temple was a famous Jain temple in ancient times. However, the *Kokasandeśa* refers to the existence of this Viṣṇu temple in the Saṅgamagrāma as early as the 15th century, underscoring its enduring cultural significance.

Thiruvanchikulam

Thiruvanchikulam is considered the ancient capital of Kerala (N. P Unni, 1997: 23). Also known as Mahodayapuram and Cheramān Kovilakam, this place was a thriving town during the time of *Uddaṇḍa Śāstri* (Kodungallur Kunjikuttan Thampuran, 2014: 142). The Śiva temple in Thiruvanchikulam was famous in ancient times (Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī, 2012:88)

Cennamaṅgalaṁ

The poet uses *Jayanthamaṅgalaṁ* to refer to **Cennamaṅgalaṁ** in the *Kokilasandeśa*. The poet states that this pristine region, with its fame and beauty as hallmarks, will conquer the heavens. The famous Vishnu temple and Devi temple are located nearby in this region.

Major Temples in North Kerala

Holy places were of enormous prominence in the ancient period, as evidenced by the numerous temples mentioned in the *Kokilasāndeśa*. The unique architecture, idol features, shrine style, construction methods, and materials used in North Kerala during the medieval period have led to a depth of scholarly studies, enriching our understanding of these ancient structures in a way that is both profound and significant. Tirunelli, Kottiyoor, Peruvanam, and Śrī Kuramba are some of the temples in North Kerala that were particularly popular during this time and continue to hold historical prominence, underscoring their enduring legacy and the depth of knowledge and research in this field.

Thirunelly

In Kerala, the historic Thirunelly is the first place suggested for visiting in *Kokila*. Here was a great temple, serving as a spiritual site from the early period of Kerala. The main deity of this ancient temple is Lord Viṣṇu. The place is situated 32 km from Mananthavady in Wayanad. Thirunelly, a place of immense historical significance in South India, has a history dating back to the time of the Chera king, Bhāskara Varman I (962–1019 AD). Many devotees have been visiting this place since ancient times, connecting it to a rich past. *Pāpanāśini* is very popular and is situated near the temple. The temple in Thirunelli is also known as the *Sahāmalaka* (Rajan Gurukul, 1992: 2). This name accentuates the historical significance of Kerala's temples. It also invokes a sense of reverence and respect for the cultural heritage in the readers.

Kottiyoor

Kottiyoor temple, a historical and cultural landmark in Kerala dating back to the ancient period, is situated on the banks of the Vāvali river. The temple's location near the famous *Trijata Kunnu*, a significant cultural site, enriches the region's cultural heritage. The poet also mentions a renowned temple named *Cherumannam* in the Kannur district, where *Pūrakkāḷi* is the foremost celebration. These two temples, located in proximity, stand as a testament to North Kerala's rich Hindu religious heritage. The goddesses in these tem-

ples instil a deep sense of cultural pride and appreciation, fostering strong connections and respect among the believers. The poet's advice to visit the temple only after bathing in clear water underscores the importance of maintaining internal and external purity, a value deeply ingrained in the cultural fabric of Kerala, as well as the reverence associated with this act. (**Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī**, 2012, Vs:25)

Peruvanam

The Peruvanam temple, located in Thrissur, was one of the famous worshipping centres in the medieval period, which *Kokilasāṇḍeśa* refers to as *Mūrtidvandvam vahati*. The significance of its location in Thrissur, a region known for its rich cultural and historical heritage, cannot be overstated. There are two main shrines dedicated to Lord Śiva. They are known as *Erattayappan* (on the north side) and *Mādathilappan* (on the south side). The duality of Śiva is seen there. The idol displays a large *Śivaliṅga* next to a smaller one. The shrine of the temple is located at a very high place. The temple's unique architecture, adorned with numerous sculptures and mythological paintings, is considered the first in Kerala in terms of area. This Śiva temple is believed to have been built in the 9th century AD at *Thaikulangara* in the Triprayār region of north Kerala. It is one of the two most significant temples dedicated to Lord Śiva. The legend that Śiva cut off Brahma's head and dressed himself is popular in this region. The eye on the forehead, the serpent on the neck, the nectar falling from the body of the moon, and other similar elements are depicted in the sculptures. The poet recalls that scholars in this region would correct the mistakes made during the Vedic period.

Ūrakam Ammatiruvadi.

It is a Bhagavatī temple, historically referenced in *Kokilasāṇḍeśa* as *Kanaka Bhavana* (**Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī**, 2012, Vs :85), and is a significant site near the Peruvanam temple. The temple's gold idol of **Pārvatī**, along with its vibrant atmosphere, as suggested by the *Kokilā* message, made it a popular daily destination for many devotees in the past.

Śrī Kurumba

After visiting the **Saṅgamagrāma**, the poet reminds *Kokilā* to ap-

proach the vast forest surrounding the *Kālī* temple. The poet mentions the *Śrī Kurumba* temple, a place of great importance. The poet notes that visits from the gods were a common occurrence in this temple. The 87th verse of the first part in *Kokilasāndeśa* narrates that once, when *Kāla* arrived to worship *Bhadrakālī*, a prominent deity here, he stopped his vehicle near the buffalo and attempted to sacrifice it, mistakenly believing it to be a sacrificial animal. It also adds that the ghosts, who were friends of the goddess, intervened and convinced *Kāla* of the truth, releasing the vehicle. Although this is purely hypothetical, it can be verified whether animal sacrifices were performed in temples.

Major Rivers

Rivers have a significant role in the cultural development of a region. *Vāvali*, *Bhārathapuzha*, *Periyār*, *Valli* and *Kauṇī* are mainly mentioned in *Kokilasāndeśa*, which still symbolises the cultural heritage of north Kerala.

Vāvali

After visiting Tirunelli, the poet suggests a visit to North Kottayam, where the *Vāvali* river is mentioned. The *Vāvali* river, with its rich historical significance, originates from the northern region of *Brahmagiri* and is known as the *Vāngmazhī* river in *Kokilasāndeśa*. This river, often associated with ritual practices among the Hindu community, is a significant aspect of Kerala's cultural history. Its mention in the poet's work serves as a testament to the region's social status and richness, offering readers a unique and fascinating insight into the religious practices of Kerala during the 15th century.

Bhārathapuzhā

Uddaṇḍa describes the *Nilā* river as playing a significant role in the cultural prosperity of Kerala in the ancient period. Devotees revered the Triprangot Śiva temple, located on the adjacent side of *Nilā*. *Kokilasāndeśa* has clearly described the past condition of *Bhārathapuzhā*. There were plenty of lotus flowers in the river. The poet has described it excitingly, with many flamingos coming to the dunes and jumping into the water. The poet has compared this river,

significantly depleted during the time of *Kokilasāṇḍeśa*, to his own lover (*Kāmini*), who was very thin. The poem affirms that the grief of separation equally affects *Kāmini* and *Bhāratapuzhā*. The poet depicts Nilā as a face strewn with wrinkles on all four sides. The present condition of Nilā is no different, as the river, known as the *Ponnāni* river, a symbol of antiquity is reduced to mere dunes in the summer, primarily due to human activities such as sand mining and dam construction.

Periyār

The *Periyār*, a significant water body in central Kerala, is known by different names, each reflecting its cultural significance. It is the birthplace of **Śrī Śaṅkara**, the renowned scholar of Advaita philosophy, which adds a sense of reverence to the river. The region of Aluva, located on its banks, is famous for the *Śivarātrī* festival. The poet in the *Kokilasāṇḍeśa* uses the word *Curnī* to denote the *Periyār*, stating that *Jayanthamaṅgalaṁ* can be reached by travelling on the north side of this natural *Curnī*. This rich region, now known as *Cennamaṅgalaṁ*, is a testament to the river's historical and cultural importance. The *Periyār*, also known as the *Āluvappuzhā*, flows north of **Cennamaṅgalaṁ** and ultimately meets the Arabian Sea through the historic *Kodungallur* (Kodungallur Kunjikuttan Thampuram, 2014: 108).

Festival

During the medieval period, Kerala had its own history, and various festivals were celebrated in the nooks and crannies of North Kerala. Many of the festivals were celebrated in conjunction with temple festivals. *Māmāṅkam*, a festival of great historical significance, was very popular during the medieval period and was considered a well-organised programme. It is a renowned festival in Malabar. The origins of the **Māmāṅkam** festival date back to the 14th century, in the Thirunavāya temple, situated on the banks of the Nilā river during the reign of Kulasekhara Varma. The Kings, scholars, traders, and local people participated in this festival. The settlement of the birth mothers' financial transactions was a significant part of this festival. The event, a grand spectacle that spanned 28 days, contin-

ued until the 18th century (K. V Krishna Ayyar, 1999: 90.312)

Verse 72 of the *Kokilasāndeśa* beautifully captures the essence of the festival, describing how it was a time when beautiful women would accompany their husbands to participate in the festivities during the month of *Māgha*.

Kerala Brāhmaṇa-s

The poem, which acknowledges the presence of *Pāradeśī Brāhmaṇa-s* in Kerala, underscores the unique scholarship that sets them apart. The Zamorin King Mānavikrama's tribute to these scholars is a significant recognition of their historical importance and the respect they commanded. *Kokilasāndeśa* highlights the Brāhmins' global eminence, a position they achieved through their intellectual prowess. Those who reached the middle of the rivers, such as *Vallī* and *Kauṇī*, were the best among the Brāhmin-s, their scholarly achievements setting them apart. **Uddaṇḍa** explains that those who felt the purity of *Nilā*'s wind were the best Brāhmins, their intellectual purity matching the purity of the wind. The Brāhmins in this region were known for their excellent education, conduct, and zeal, which demand our respect and appreciation for their cultural contributions. With this reference to the Brāhmaṇa-s, **Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī** provides an overview of the region's artistic education.

Conclusion

Kokilasāndeśa is a captivating work that unveils the history of North Kerala. It stands as a unique example of how Sanskrit *kāvya* transcends its poetic boundaries to function as a cultural and historical document. The poem's detailed narration of Kerala's northern landscapes, dynasties, and festivals offers a unique and invaluable perspective for historical research. The poet's imaginative thinking, which he used to express newsworthy facts as symbols of antiquity, is truly inspiring. His use of the *kokilā* to describe his way through its eyes testifies to the depth of his creative prowess. Such views of the *kokilā* undoubtedly reflect the poet's inner eye. By embedding historical details within the framework of a messenger poem, **Uddaṇḍa Śāstrī** has left behind a literary monument that preserves Kerala's political and cultural ethos of his time. Therefore, the study

of *Kokilasandēśa* not only enriches the understanding of the regional history of North Kerala but also underscores the significant role of Sanskrit literary texts as reliable and informative supplementary sources for cultural and historical reconstruction.

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The Eloquence of Silence: A Buddhist Philosophical Perspective

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Abstract

Silence occupies a profound and multidimensional role in Buddhist philosophy, serving not merely as the absence of speech but as an essential mode of insight, wisdom, and liberation. Across Buddhist traditions—Theravāda, Mahāyāna, and Zen—silence functions as a philosophical metaphor, an ethical discipline, and a meditative practice that transcends conceptual thought. This article explores the doctrinal and practical dimensions of silence within Buddhist thought, tracing its manifestation in canonical texts and later interpretations. By examining silence through the frameworks of mindfulness, emptiness (*śūnyatā*), and non-duality, this paper argues that silence embodies a dynamic epistemology—one that points toward direct realisation beyond linguistic constructs. The study concludes that Buddhist silence, rather than negating communication, refines it into an expression of Ultimate Truth (*paramārtha-satya*).

Keywords: Silence, Buddhism, Emptiness, Mindfulness, Theravāda, Mahāyāna, Zen, Non-duality

1. Introduction

In the Buddhist tradition, silence holds a paradoxical yet central position. It is simultaneously a method of communication and a denial of conceptual discourse. Unlike Western philosophical traditions, where silence is often treated as an absence or negation of meaning, Buddhism regards silence as the fertile ground of insight

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and liberation. The Buddha's own moments of silence—particularly when confronted with metaphysical questions about the nature of the self, the world, or the afterlife—reveal an epistemic strategy aimed at transcending dualistic thinking (Rahula, 64).

This article examines silence as both a philosophical stance and a spiritual discipline in Buddhism. It situates silence within three interconnected contexts: (1) **Doctrinal silence**—as found in the Pāli Canon and early teachings; (2) **Metaphysical silence**—as elaborated in Mahāyāna philosophy; and (3) **Experiential silence**—as manifested in Zen and meditative practice.

The central argument proposed here is that silence functions as a mode of non-conceptual knowing that bridges the gap between conventional truth (*saṃvṛti-satya*) and ultimate truth (*paramārtha-satya*).

2. Silence in Early Buddhist Canon (Theravāda Perspective)

In early Buddhism, silence is not merely abstention from speech but an ethical and contemplative discipline known as right speech (*sammā vācā*), a component of the Noble Eightfold Path. Right speech is not simply abstention from lying, divisiveness, harsh speech, and idle chatter; it is an ethical and contemplative discipline central to the Noble Eightfold Path, binding both monastics and lay followers to a practice of truthfulness, kindness, and meaningful communication (Bodhi, 167). The Buddha discouraged idle chatter (*samphappalāpa*) and emphasised speech that is truthful, timely, and beneficial (Maurice, 467). Yet, the Buddha's own silence—most notably his refusal to answer the “unanswerable questions” (*avyākāta*) concerning the eternity of the world, the existence of the self, or the afterlife—reveals an epistemological commitment to pragmatic knowledge rather than speculative metaphysics (Collins, 96-99).

In the Cūḷa-Māluṅkya Sutta (Majjhima Nikāya 63), the Buddha likens such metaphysical inquiry to a man struck by a poisoned arrow who refuses treatment until he knows who shot it. This analogy underscores that silence is not ignorance but skilful means

(*upāya-kauśalya*), designed to redirect attention from conceptual proliferation (*papañca*) to direct realisation through meditation and insight.

Theravāda commentaries, such as Buddhaghosa's *Visuddhimagga*, further elevate silence as a moral virtue (*ariyā tuṅhībhāva*)—the silence of the noble one who speaks only when speech conduces to enlightenment (Buddhaghosa, 100-110).

3. Silence in Mahāyāna Thought: The Emptiness of Speech

The Mahāyāna movement expanded the metaphysical implications of silence through the doctrine of emptiness (*śūnyatā*). In this framework, language and conceptualisation are seen as provisional designations (*prajñapti*) that cannot capture ultimate reality (Conze, 29)⁶. Nāgārjuna's *Mūlamadhyamakakārikā* deconstructs linguistic categories, demonstrating that all statements about existence or non-existence are equally empty of inherent essence (Garfield, 1-20).

For Nāgārjuna, true understanding arises only when the mind transcends the limitations of conceptual dichotomies—a state that silence most aptly represents. This philosophical silence does not signify the absence of meaning but the cessation of false reification. As the *Vimalakīrti Nirdeśa Sūtra* illustrates, when the bodhisattvas debate the meaning of non-duality, Vimalakīrti remains silent, and the assembly recognises his silence as the highest teaching (Watson, 126).

Thus, in Mahāyāna philosophy, silence operates as the language of non-duality—a communicative act that transcends both affirmation and negation. It becomes the most refined expression of *prajñā*, or transcendental wisdom, revealing that truth cannot be spoken but must be realised.

4. Zen and the Wordless Transmission of Truth

Zen Buddhism inherits this Mahāyāna understanding but emphasises it through direct experience and spontaneity. The famous dictum attributed to Bodhidharma, “A special transmission outside

the scriptures, not relying on words or letters,” encapsulates Zen’s radical valorisation of silence (Suzuki, 41).

Zen masters often employ paradoxical dialogues and non-verbal gestures to provoke insight. The story of the Buddha holding up a flower and Mahākāśyapa’s silent smile (*Flower Sermon*) illustrates the wordless transmission of the Dharma. Silence here represents immediate, non-conceptual awareness (*satori*), a mode of knowing before linguistic formulation.

Thich Nhat Hanh interprets silence as “the voice of understanding,” emphasising that mindfulness allows one to listen to silence as the sound of the present moment (Hanh). In this way, silence in Zen is not retreat but realisation—a dynamic awareness in which speech and silence merge into the same continuum of truth.

5. Ethical and Soteriological Dimensions of Silence

Silence is not only epistemological but deeply ethical. The Buddha’s teachings associate verbal restraint with compassion and mindfulness. To speak truthfully and with purpose is an act of moral responsibility; to remain silent when speech would cause harm is an act of wisdom (Harvey, 163–165, 300–301).

Moreover, the silence of meditation (*jhāna*) reveals an inner purification process, through mindful silence, the practitioner encounters the stillness of the mind, which allows insight (*vipassanā*) to arise. Silence thus functions as both method and fruit of enlightenment—the expression of mental serenity (*upekkhā*).

In Mahāyāna ethics, the bodhisattva’s silence represents compassion that transcends speech, as verbal instruction often cannot convey the ineffable nature of awakening. Silence becomes the language of liberation—communicating beyond the limitations of ordinary discourse.

6. Comparative Discussion: Silence, Language, and Realisation

Buddhist silence stands in contrast to Western notions of linguistic philosophy, where silence often implies the boundary of lan-

guage. Wittgenstein says, “Whereof one cannot speak, thereof one must be silent” (Wittgenstein)². In Buddhism, however, silence is not the boundary but the ground of all speech—a fertile field from which meaningful communication arises (Loy, 108).

While Western philosophy frequently situates silence within epistemological scepticism, Buddhism frames it within transformative realisation. The function of silence is not to negate reality but to reveal its non-conceptual nature, thus, silence and speech are not opposites but interdependent expressions of the same ultimate truth.

7. Conclusion

Silence in Buddhism is a philosophical, ethical, and spiritual principle that transcends mere absence of sound. The Buddha’s prudent silence in the *avyākata* questions to Vimalakīrti’s eloquent wordlessness and Zen’s flower sermon, silence has functioned as both method and realisation. It embodies the Buddhist view that the ultimate truth cannot be confined to words yet can be communicated through the depth of non-verbal awareness.

In recognising the eloquence of silence, Buddhist philosophy challenges the assumption that meaning is bound to language. Instead, it reveals silence as the highest form of expression—one that points directly to the nature of reality beyond dualistic thought.

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From Tradition to Conservation- Exploring Vṛkṣāyurveda in the Modern Era

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Abstract

Plants and trees play a vital role in sustaining life in Indian culture. The importance of trees and plants in today's living has led philosophers of India to take utmost care in conserving and preserving them. In the Vedas and related texts, not only were the merits of planting trees discussed, but also the concept of worshipping trees and plants was developed. The unique and priceless wealth of the Vedas and their teachings have always been keen in including every discipline of learning, though in informal ways. An organic farming system is indistinguishably linked with soil, water, microbes, animals, plants and the atmosphere. This farming system of India relies on biodiversity and cultivation activities taken up to the present conditions. They support us in keeping the balance and equilibrium in the environment. The traditional wisdom of Vrikshayurveda reveals the hidden techniques that help to make people aware and explore the benefits of plants and their cultivation. The knowledge and skills acquired through the study of Vṛkṣāyurveda will greatly help in the preservation of biodiversity, soil health, irrigation and deliverance from the adversities of climate change. Vṛkṣāyurveda dwells in detail on cultivation methods, agriculture and gardening, the importance of cultivation and also about harvesting methods and garden maintenance.

Introduction

India has a lot of forest resources, and Indians have, from ancient times, given immense importance to plant protection

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and taking care of biological resources. They were very knowledgeable about the conservation, medicinal and agricultural potential of plants, and the importance of soil and atmosphere. Their activities were all about taking care of the plants and trees without harming them. They stressed universal peace and harmony, which includes the harmony of nature. They were conscious of all the changes happening in the environment and of building ecologically balanced surroundings. The Santimantras of the Vedas open a way to make explicit their thoughts on the value of skillfulness as well as the interrelatedness of all natural powers. This prayer gives importance to living harmoniously and peacefully- शान्तिरन्तरिक्षं शान्तिं पृथिवी शान्तिरापः शान्तिरोषधयः शान्तिः। वनस्पतयः शान्तिर्विश्वदेवाः शान्तिर्ब्रह्म शान्तिः सर्वं शान्तिःशान्तिरेव शान्तिः सा मा (Yajurveda 36.1)

People, right from Vedic times, had become an integral part of the ecosystem, and the benignant nature had evoked a sense of faith in them, thus, the principal doctrine reflected in the Vedas is that all creatures of God should live in concordance. *R̥gveda* and *Atharvaveda* contain a lot of references regarding plants, trees and the environment. Different taxonomic categories of plants are found in India. Most of them have medicinal values, and many of them have been used as food. The Vedas mentioned the number of trees and their relevance. The *Pṛthvisūkta* of *Atharvaveda* is the oldest and the most evocative environmental invocation. In it, the Vedic Acaryas solemnly declare the imperishable relationship and commitment of humankind to Mother Earth. Oshadhi Sukta of the *R̥gveda* says that ‘hundreds are your birthplaces and thousands are your shoots’.

Vṛkṣāyurvedic literature founded its principles from various texts like *Agnipurāna*, *Bṛhatsamhita*, and *Śārngadharapadhati*. The word Vṛkṣayurveda was initially mentioned in Kautilya’s *Arthasāstra*, but detailed explanations are given in *Bṛhatsamhita* as well as *Agnipurana*. Texts like *Viśvavallabha*, *Kṛṣi-parāśara*, *Kaśyapīyakraṣisūkti*, *Kṛṣisangraha*, *Mānasollasa*, *Sivatatvaratnakara* and *Lokopakaraka* also comprise the data

regarding the skill of agriculture. *Brihatsamhita* of Varahamihira includes a section entitled Vṛkṣāyurveda and related topics such as water resources, fruitfulness of land, seed preservation and preparation and related topics. The other text describing Vṛkṣāyurveda is Śārṅgadhara's *Śārngadharapaddhati*.⁴ This text gives details about the various kinds of land or soil, and the improvement of water. The Scripture Vṛkṣāyurveda, written by Surapala, explains countless techniques and discusses various topics connected with plants and plant life. Preservation and treatment of seeds, fertilisation and selection of soil or bhoominiroopana, how to prepare pits for planting and methods of watering. The chapters of Vṛkṣāyurveda deal with agro-horticulture, home gardening, the cultivation of plants, nourishment of fertilisers, management and conservation of water, and handling of various diseases of the plants.

Significance of Vṛkṣāyurveda in the Modern Era

Environmental issues relating to sustainable development have emerged in today's world, and this is a topic of major concern. Human beings face endless illnesses because of the use of chemical fertilisers and pesticides. These fertilisers affect the health of human beings, causing devastating effects on nature, like pollution of air, soil, and groundwater. These chemicals destroy microorganisms in the soil. Therefore, it is very important to validate effectively. In contemporary society, the grave effects of fast food and chemically contented foods have adversely affected the health of human beings. This has resulted in the common man turning their interests towards organic methods of farming. This is a positive sign, and they now understand the importance of the sustainability of natural resources and the conservation of nature. They now look forward to receiving, following and propagating the organic farming techniques like Vrikshayurvedic methods imparted by great preceptors who lived in ancient India.

According to Vṛkṣāyurveda, trees are the source of pleasure in this world, इहलोक and the other worlds, परलोक. It states that a man who plants a beautiful garden full of fruit and flower trees goes to heaven. A tree planted on the side of a road, which gives

shade to a tired traveller, is spoken of as better than a son who is devoid of wealth and virtues (Vṛkṣāyurveda 4) ⁵. Vṛkṣāyurveda contains various ancient practices like the organic production of plants and trees, agricultural practices for their well-being and appropriate treatment for diseases pertaining to medicinal plants are mentioned.

Nowadays, the ecological balance is deteriorating, and the environment in which we live is getting contaminated through human activities. Ancient knowledge systems of India provide insight into the implications and applications of our culture, and they play a key role in stopping or restraining global warming and such other effects. Vṛkṣāyurveda firmly states that trees save the world from various kinds of troubles, difficulties and disasters; therefore, they are recognised as our protectors. Vriksayurvedic practices attempt to bring the agricultural knowledge of ancient times that prevailed in India, involving the practices and preservation of our trees, soil, water, etc, to the limelight. The present condition in the field of agriculture is very decisive. At this juncture, we have to reflect on the great, unique wealth of the Vedas and their teachings that are keen to include every discipline of learning, though through their informal methods. These practices of Vṛkṣāyurveda encourage people to upgrade their skills and apply them for the benefit of society through academic advancement.

The wide range of production of organic products will help and enrich Ayurveda personnel, as the treatment is based largely on herbal drugs, and the supply of efficacious raw materials will improve the condition of the suffering patients, thus, this text will prove beneficial not only to the farmers or researchers of the discipline of Ayurveda but also to ordinary people from any category. This thorough study ensures the production of medicinal plants has proven efficacy, and the traditional wisdom of Vrikshayurveda helps to aware people to explore the benefits of plants and their cultivation.

According to Vṛkṣāyurveda, the diseases of plants should be treated appropriately, after taking the causative factors into account and proper examination of the abnormal conditions of plants. Surapala

talks about the causes which may destroy the trees, such as drought, flood, chemical, biological and pathological conditions, including natural hazards (Vṛkṣāyurveda 182).⁷ It can undoubtedly be held that the practices of growing plants, along with their preservation and yielding depicted in the ancient literary works of Indian culture and heritage, can be followed for a desirable environmental life. They are essential to the system of modern agriculture and farming.

मांस किं एव शितांभोभिः कुणपांभो विमिश्रितैः ।

भवन्ति फल पुष्पाढ्याः सर्वाभूरुह जातयः ॥ (Vṛkṣāyurveda 114)

Traditional practices and Ecological wisdom

Vṛkṣāyurvēda gives a keen insight into the farmers for the development of skills necessary in this venture. It is already clear that our ancestors, in their available environment, utilised all organic materials and manures like kunapajala and Pancagavya for the nourishment of plants and protecting them against insects and diseases. Treatment of seeds and plants with the organic manure kunapajala from Vṛkṣāyurveda, written by Surapala, is efficacious for preserving and conserving seeds. *Vṛkṣāyurveda* states that the output of the organic manure kunapajala is that all types of trees bear profuse flowers and fruits by providing a better yield of flowers and fruits. The slurry of cow dung is very efficient in increasing the percentage of sprouting and the proportion of the speedy growth of plants. Another organic manure, Panchagavyam, is advisable than urea as a nourishment component for seed plants. The knowledge and skills acquired through the study of Vṛkṣāyurveda will help in the preservation of biodiversity and in resisting climate change. Organic fertilisers play a life-sustaining role in maintaining physical, chemical and biological conditions in soil. These fertilisers provide both macro and micro nutrients for crop production. This helps to understand the limitations, merits and demerits of both contemporary and past agricultural practices. The study of Vṛkṣāyurveda ensures the production of medicinal plants and agricultural products without harming the environment. It proves its efficacy and also gives insights into the finest structure of the agricultural and gardening system.

Environmental degradation refers to the large-scale destruction of natural resources available to us. It interferes with human sensibility and human connection with nature. The main reason for the destruction of the Earth's balance is due to widespread human interference. In order to eliminate this type of environmental damage, it is very important to protect the relationship between man and nature. So, we must give priority in following and practising environmentally safe ancient techniques. In *Carakasamhita*, Acarya Caraka states- 'The purusarthas or the eternal values of life, Dharma, Arha and Kama are achieved only by a person who has Arogya or health. The diseases destroy the whole life of a man.

धर्मार्थकाममोक्षाणां आरोग्यमुत्तमम् ।

रोगास्तस्यापहर्तारः श्रेयसो जीवितस्य च ॥ (चरक सूत्रस्थान 1.15)

Tridosa Principle

Ayurveda is a science of life, and it is one of the traditional Indian medicinal systems. The fundamental principle of Ayurveda is the Tridatu theory. This theory is based on the perfect balance of three doshas, i.e., कफ (kapha), वात (vata), and पित्त (pitta). These three doshas signify the health and wellness of a person, and they indicate if any imbalance exists. Since the three humours are capable of getting vitiated due to their respective causes and modifying or disturbing the physiological function to initiate the process of the assault of the diseases, they became known as Tridosa. Same as in Ayurveda, the *Vṛkṣāyurveda* also applies this tridosa theory to the trees and plants, and it contains a systematic exposition of its theory. Therefore, diagnosis and treatment of trees are conducted according to these doshas.

नराणामिव वृक्षाणां वातपित्तकफाद् गदाः ।

संभवन्ति निरूप्यातः कुर्यात्तद्दोषनाशनम् ॥

Apart from these, there are several special processes or wonders that are discussed. They are bearing flowers and fruits around the year, bearing flowers and fruits out of season, producing fragrance, changing the colours, changing the flowers, changing the fruits, changing the fragrance, arresting fragrance, transforming trees into creepers, dwarfing the trees, longevity of ripeness, quick production

of fruits, increasing the size of fruits and so on, and then this text discusses how to create a pleasure garden, natural indications of groundwater for the construction of wells, etc. Anyway, this ancient text on plant science is an asset to Indian agriculture, and it leads to preparing healthy and nutrient products without annoying the human body.

Findings And Suggestions

Agriculture and the preservation of plants are unavoidable subjects for mankind, and these are to be received as a necessary part of our mundane life. These are the fundamental requisites for the development of any nation. People belonging to any category should know this subject and take care of the plants and soil available to us. As is already experienced, nature-related issues and global warming have really affected the environment, and this is due to the enhanced emission of greenhouse gases. Anyway, the teachings of ancient Indian seers are very much relevant. It is the prime duty of everyone to enhance our cultural heritage, imparted to all human beings, and thereby build up a fresh and healthy environment.

In brief, *Vṛkṣāyurveda* provides a receptivity into the Agrarian history of ancient India in its most benignant and nature-friendly position. In this condition, it can be held with high esteem that the contribution of *Vṛkṣāyurveda*, the ancient wisdom of India, to the world of agriculture and plant development is tremendous. Undoubtedly, this text stands as the epitome of the power of intelligence developed in human beings, and this is a great resource which helps the growth of the economy of the state and society, enriches life and makes it more worth living. The learning of our cultural history, traditional perceptiveness and the eternal Vedic knowledge is very helpful in combating as well as eradicating our complex environment and global warming for a smooth life. As a result of this, it is indispensable to study our historical knowledge. It paves the way to overcome all the challenges faced by the contemporary agricultural world. The proper interpretation through learning and implementation of the methods prevailed in *Vṛkṣāyurveda* is competent to make the nature conducive to intercropping. *Vṛkṣāyurveda* insists on the usage of organic fertilisers and plays a vital function in creating awareness

in man to create environmentally safe surroundings. This is the appropriate time to re-establish the wealth of Vṛkṣayurveda into application, as there is uncontrolled use of pesticides and fertilisers. A wise amalgamation of Vṛkṣāyurvedic practices and current practices is inevitable for the welfare of society and our environment.

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Relevance of Upaniṣads in the Modern Education System

Tutan Barman¹

Abstract

The real meaning of education is to fulfill oneself through acquiring knowledge. Education is the measure of social control, personality formation, social and economic progress of any state and society. We all know how important education in our life is. Without education, humans are like animals. Education has separated humans from animals – येषां न विद्या न तपो न दानं, ज्ञानं न शीलं न गुणो न धर्मः । ते मर्त्यलोके भुविभारभूता, मनुष्यरूपेण मृगाश्चरन्ति ॥ (cāṅkyaṇīti 10.7) The Upaniṣads are the world's oldest religious scriptures, the last and most important part of the Vedas. The Upaniṣads are a part of Vedic literature that provides the basis for Vedic education, which focuses on the development of human character and literacy. The Upaniṣads teach critical thinking, self-inquiry, and contemplation, and are said to provide a universal philosophy of education. And through the knowledge gained in these Upaniṣads, the all-round development of human character is achieved. The knowledge gained from Upaniṣads teaches human life to take a significant role in the progress of civilization by making it useful to society. Therefore, in the present context, it is absolutely necessary to be involved in the current education system of Upaniṣads.

Keywords: Education, Knowledge, Upaniṣads, Vedic education, society.

Introduction

Today we are living in the era of rapidly changing scientific and technological society, education is not associated with knowledge, but with employment prospects or economic aspects. The main pur-

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pose of education is to achieve the overall development of the student, to enrich the student with knowledge and provide employment opportunities. At the same time, the purpose of education is to develop human qualities in the student, to develop the moral, spiritual, mental and character qualities of the student, but in today's modern education system, education is not able to fulfill all its objectives. I personally think that with the industrialization of the present time, moral education has lost its roots. In the rush of material life, we have ignored the ideals of truth. Advanced science and technology which we can use to increase our knowledge and skills but we are often using it only for entertainment purposes. As a result, irresponsibility is often seen among the students. Not only that, lack of discipline is also easily observed among the students today.

The Upaniṣads are ancient texts that emphasize the importance of morality and ethics and provide guidance for living a righteous life. The Upaniṣads present a concise view of morality and ethics. Moral education makes a person civilized and cultured, teaches him to differentiate between good and evil. In the era of the Upaniṣads, the Guru was completely devoted to his duty and performed his duties without any greed. At that time, teaching was considered a sacred duty. During this time, the disciple, away from his home, would learn qualities like discipline, sense of discipline, firmness of character, honesty, ethics, etc. along with knowledge. The knowledge gained from the Upaniṣads helped the student to become a civilized and cultured person fit for the society. Therefore, the relevance of the Upaniṣads and the knowledge gained from them in the modern education system cannot be ignored even today. So in my full research proposal, I will shed light on this topic.

Objectives

- * Identify the importance of Upaniṣads in modern education system.
- * Studying the principles of the Upaniṣads in the modern education system.
- * To provide suggestions and decisions for making the modern education system student-friendly and socially useful.

Methodology

This is a theoretical work based on historical research that explores the knowledge derived from the Upaniṣads and the educational system of that time in detail and tries to know the importance of the Upaniṣads in the current education system. The main objective of this study is to know the impact of the Upaniṣads in the modern education system and to integrate the Upaniṣads in modern education.

Results and Discussions

The word Upaniṣad means gaining knowledge by sitting with a teacher. Upaniṣad Vidyā destroys ignorance, dispels suffering and leads to union with Brahman. The concept of freedom from the cycle of birth and rebirth, known as moksha, is a central theme in Hinduism. The Upaniṣads, which are indeed the philosophical part of the Vedas, delve deeply into this concept, exploring the nature of reality, the self (Atman), and the ultimate reality (Brahman). They propose that through self-realization and the understanding of the oneness of Atman and Brahman, one can achieve liberation from this cycle. The Upaniṣads are considered the last part of the Vedas, often known as Vedānta. The *Vedas* contain mantras which were explained by the Brahmins, the wise men. Each school teaching the Vedas specialized in the Upaniṣads and then simultaneously published more than 1,000 Upaniṣads. However, today, most Vedic inscriptions are missing; No one knows what happened to this education. The modern world knows only about 108 Upaniṣads, of which only 10 or 11 are major Upaniṣads – ईश केन कथा प्रश्न मुंड मांडूक्य तैत्तिर ऐतरेयं च छान्दोग्यं बृहदारण्यकं दशम ।

The Upaniṣads are indeed considered the primary source of Indian philosophical thought. They form the foundation for many later schools of Indian philosophy, including Vedānta, Samkhya, and Yoga. They are regarded as a “storehouse of supreme knowledge” because they delve into fundamental questions about existence, consciousness, and reality. Upaniṣads provide the knowledge which leads man from falsehood to truth, from darkness to light, and from death to immortality.” - असतो मा सद्गमय । तमसो मा ज्योतिर्गमय । मृत्योर्मा अमृतं

गमय ॥ - Brihadaranyaka Upaniṣad (1.3.28)

The Upaniṣads are a collection of profound and enlightening wisdom from ancient Indian wisdom, guiding seekers through a rich weave of spirituality and philosophy. The Upaniṣads, rooted in the Vedic tradition, are a treasure trove of eternal wisdom, providing profound insights into the nature of life, awareness, and the pursuit of knowledge. Profound truths in these religious books transcend time and culture, providing significant insights into educational philosophy. The Upaniṣads provide a unique educational perspective through their meditative and philosophical outlook, urging teachers and students to dig into the depths of human knowledge and self-realization. In the search for knowledge, the Upaniṣads urge seekers to go beyond conventional wisdom and investigate the timeless truths hidden beneath the fabric of creation. The Upaniṣads reveal the mysteries of existence, awareness, and the interconnectedness of all beings through profound conversations between respected sages and curious students. They highlight the value of self-inquiry, critical thinking and reflection as important tools in the educational journey, leading to greater awareness of oneself and one's surroundings.

Around 500 BCE, various schools of thought arose in India during the Upaniṣad period, each with its own interpretation and philosophical system. These include Vedanta, Sankhya, Yoga and Jainism. These schools of thought led to new developments and interpretations of the original Vedic teachings, resulting in a diversity of Indian knowledge and philosophy.

The Upaniṣads are a collection of ancient Hindu philosophical texts that teach many concepts, including:

Soul

The Upaniṣads teach that the soul is eternal and by uniting with Brahman it can be liberated from the cycle of death and rebirth.

- * A verse from the Upaniṣads that describes the Atman (soul) is from the Katha Upaniṣad: “न जायते म्रियते वा विपश्चित् नायं कुतश्चिन्न बभूव कश्चित् । अजो नित्यः शाश्वतोऽयं पुराणो न हन्यते हन्यमाने शरीरे ॥» – Katha Upaniṣad (1.2.18)

This verse emphasizes the eternal, immutable nature of the soul, which is not subject to birth, death or decay of any kind.

- * स वा अयमात्मा ब्रह्म विज्ञानमयो मनोमयः प्राणमयश्चक्षुर्मयः श्रोत्रमयः पृथिवीमय आपोमय वायुमय आकाशमयस्तेजोमयस्तेजोमयः काममयोऽकाममयः क्रोधमयोऽक्रोधमयो धर्ममयोऽधर्ममयः सर्वमयस्तद्यदेतदिदंमयोऽदोमय इति यथाकारी यथाचारी तथा भवति साधुकारी साधुर्भवति पापकारी पापो भवति पुण्यः पुण्येन कर्मणा भवति पापः पापेन । - **Brihadaranyaka Upaniṣad (4.4.5)**

This passage equates the soul with the Absolute Truth Brahman. It also focuses on the concept of karma, explaining that our actions shape our experiences and future.

- * नायमात्मा बलहीनेन लभ्यो न च प्रमादात्तपसो वाप्यलिङ्गात् । एतैरुपायैर्यतते यस्तु विद्वान् तस्यैष आत्मा विशते ब्रह्मधाम ॥ - **Mundaka Upaniṣad (3.1.4)**

This shloka emphasizes the importance of strength (both physical and mental), hard work and proper spiritual practice in attaining the soul. It says that self-realization requires dedicated effort and discipline.

These are just a few examples of the many verses discussing the soul in the Upaniṣads.

Brahman

The Upaniṣads teach that Brahma, the supreme power of the universe, is linked to humanity. The word “Brahma” represents the ultimate reality or God. Here are some prime examples with explanations:

- * सर्वं खल्विदं ब्रह्म तज्जलानिति शान्त उपासीत । अथ खलु क्रतुमयः पुरुषो यथाक्रतुरस्मिल्लोके पुरुषो भवति तथेतः प्रेत्य भवति स क्रतुं कुर्वीत ॥ - **Chandogya Upaniṣad (3.14.1)**

This famous stanza declares that everything in existence is Brahman. It claims that Brahman is the origin, maintenance, and destination of the universe. It also highlights the importance of meditation and the willpower of an individual in shaping one’s destiny.

- * ब्रह्मैवेदममृतं पुरस्ताद् ब्रह्म पश्चाद् ब्रह्म दक्षिणतश्चोत्तरेण । अथश्चोर्ध्वं च प्रसृतं ब्रह्मैवेदं विश्वमिदं वरिष्ठम् ॥ - **Mundaka Upaniṣad (2.2.10)**

This verse emphasizes on the omnipresence of Brahman. It states that Brahma exists in all directions and dimensions, and pervades the entire universe.

Enlightenment

The Upaniṣads teach that one can become enlightened by realizing one's divine nature and rising above the material and physical realms.

- * भिद्यते हृदयग्रन्थिश्छिद्यन्ते सर्वसंशयाः । क्षीयन्ते चास्य कर्माणि तस्मिन् दृष्टे परावरे
॥ - **Mundaka Upaniṣad (3.2.9)**

This verse describes the effects of attaining knowledge. The concept of the “knot of the heart” is a key idea in the Upaniṣads and later Vedānta philosophy. It represents the entanglement of our true self (Atman) with ignorance (Avidya) and attachments (Raga-Dvesha). When the true nature of reality is realized, this knot is broken, all doubts disappear, and the effects of past karma are reduced to zero.

- * यदा सर्वे प्रमुच्यन्ते कामा येऽस्य हृदि श्रिताः । अथ मर्त्योऽमृतो भवत्यल ब्रह्म समश्नुते
॥ - **Katha Upaniṣad (2.3.14)**

This verse emphasizes the role of desire in binding us. Enlightenment is described as a state where all desires are eliminated, leading to immortality (not literal physical immortality, but liberation from the cycle of birth and death) and Brahman.

Meditation

The Upaniṣads teach the importance of meditation as a means of understanding the self and the omnipresence of Brahman.

- * तम् दुर्दर्शं गूढमनुप्रविष्टं गुहाहितं गह्वरेष्ठं पुराणम् । अध्यात्मयोगाधिगमेन देवं मत्वा
धीरो हर्षशोकौ जहाति ॥ - **Katha Upaniṣad (1.2.12)**

This verse describes the soul as hidden and difficult to understand by ordinary means. It clearly mentions “Adhyatmayoga”, which can be translated as “meditation on the self” or “inner yoga”, as the path to realizing the Self and going beyond duality (happiness and sorrow).

Good deeds

The Upaniṣads stress the importance of good deeds.

- * कुर्वन्नेवेह कर्माणि जिजीविषेच्छतं समाः । एवं त्वयि नान्यथेतोऽस्ति न कर्म लिप्यते नरे
॥ - Isha Upaniṣad, Verse 2

This verse emphasizes the importance of performing karma, but with a non-attached sentiment. It suggests that karma performed without attachment to any fruit does not bind a person. This concept is put forward in the *Bhagavad Gita* as “Niṣkāma Karma” (action without desire for fruit).

The sacred syllable Om

The *Chāndogya Upaniṣad* teaches about the sacred syllable Om, which is believed to be the sound representation of Brahman.

- * ओमित्येतदक्षरमिदं सर्वं तस्योपव्याख्यानम् । भूतं भवद्भविष्यदिति सर्वमोङ्कार एव । यच्चान्यत् लिंकालातीतं तदप्योङ्कार एव ॥ - **Mandukya Upaniṣad (Verse1)**

This verse describes Om as representing all existing objects including time. It is said that whatever was, is and will be is contained in Om. Furthermore, it depicts Om as something beyond time, indicating its connection to the timeless Brahman.

- * ओमिति ब्रह्म । ओमितीदं सर्वम् । ओमित्येतदनुकृतिर्ह स्म वा अप्यु श्रावयेत्या श्रावयन्ति । ओमिति सामानि गायन्ति । ओमिति शस्त्राणि शंसन्ति । ओमित्यध्वर्युः प्रतिगरं प्रतिगृणाति । ओमित्य ब्रह्मा प्रसूति । ओमित्यग्निहोत्रमनुजानाति । ओमिति ब्राह्मणः प्रवक्ष्यन्नाह ब्रह्मोपाप्रवानीति ब्रह्मैवोपाप्नोति ॥ - **Taittiriya Upaniṣad (1.8.1)**

-This excerpt highlights the extensive use of Om in Vedic rituals and practices. This shows that Om is not just a sound, but a sacred utterance that pervades all aspects of Vedic life, connecting actions to divinity.

Harmony and peace

The Upaniṣads stress the need to strive for harmony and peace.

- * यस्तु सर्वाणि भूतानि आत्मन्येवानुपश्यति । सर्वभूतेषु चात्मानं ततो न विजुगुप्सते
॥ - Isha Upaniṣad, Verse 6

This verse talks about the goodwill that arises from seeing the soul in all beings, which leads to a lack of hatred and a feeling of unity.

There are many features of the Vedic education system which can be accepted in the modern education system, and the Upaniṣads are the best and last part of the Vedas. Higher education is that education which not only gives us information but makes our life compatible with all existence (Rabindranath Tagore). The Vedic period was an important period in the progress of Indian civilization and culture. Education is the key to progress of any civilization. The teachings of the Upaniṣad era were the source of all knowledge that showed the true path in various areas of life. Therefore we can use various aspects of Upaniṣad teachings to bring about some changes in our modern society.

The relation of the Upaniṣads to the school is as follows: The Upaniṣads are a source of knowledge and wisdom that can be relevant to modern education in several ways, including:

Aim of Education

In the era of the Upaniṣads, the main goal of education was the all-round development of the student. Special emphasis was laid on physical, intellectual and spiritual development of students. The Guru helped in shaping the character of the disciple. In this way, the human qualities of the student were developed through education. Upaniṣads encourage questioning of traditional beliefs and seeking knowledge beyond externalities. They teach that true happiness comes from finding satisfaction within oneself, not from accumulating wealth or fame. The main aim of the modern education system is to develop the students in all aspects, but in today's schools, this is limited to books only. The present-day education is mainly oriented towards economic prosperity.

Teaching methods

In ancient times there were no black boards, pens and papers. Dialogue in the form of question and answer between student and teacher played an important role in teaching. Sri Shankaracharya has said in his commentary on Kenopanishad that,

“शिष्याचार्यप्रश्नप्रशिवचनरूपेण कथनं तु सूक्ष्मवस्तुविषयत्वात् सुखप्रविषयत्वात् प्रतिपत्तिकारणं भवति” ।

Various types of teaching methods also have been used in the Upaniṣads, which include esoteric, formulaic, etymological, mythological, analogical, dialectical, synthetic, monologue, ad-hoc and regressive methods. For example, the Prashno Upaniṣad is structured as a question-and-answer dialogue between a disciple and Guru Pip-palada. In the Katha Upaniṣad, philosophical theories such as Brahma Vidyā and Agni Vidyā are introduced through the conversation between Yama and Nachiketa. Even today these methods are very important in our classroom teaching.

Teacher-student relationship

In the era of Upaniṣads, the relationship between teachers and students was like that of father and son. The teachers were the most powerful men in terms of knowledge and spiritual development. Teachers always tried to develop the qualities of their students so that they could excel themselves. He never gave them any trouble and always tried for their overall development and the students tried to please the teachers, obeying the teachers as much as possible. But the bitterness of that relationship is easily visible in the present day. In other words, that sweet relationship has gotten a lot more stirred up today.

The Upaniṣads emphasize the importance of the teacher-student relationship and the need for teachers to be properly enlightened so that they can build a healthy and educated society.

The National Education Policy (NEP) 2020 is restructuring India's education system to incorporate more elements of the Vedic education system. This includes an emphasis on interdisciplinary learning, critical thinking, and a strong foundation in the arts, sciences, and humanities.

- * यस्य देवे परा भक्तिर्यथा देवे तथा गुरौ । तस्यैते कथिता ह्यर्थाः प्रकाशन्ते महात्मनः
॥ - Shvetashvatara Upaniṣad (6.23)

This verse highlights the importance of devotion to both God

and Guru in attaining spiritual enlightenment.

- * ॐ सह नावतु । सह नौ भुनक्तु । सह वीर्यं करवावहै । तेजस्वि नावधीतमस्तु मा विद्विषावहै ॥ ॐ शान्तिः शान्तिः शान्तिः ॥ - Taittiriya Upaniṣad

The meaning of this mantra is that both the Guru and the disciple should have a feeling of goodwill and cooperation towards each other. Both of them should strive together to acquire knowledge and there should not be any kind of hatred or opposition between them. This mantra emphasizes on establishing a sacred and cooperative environment of education.

Curriculum

The Upaniṣads are a collection of more than 200 Sanskrit texts written between 800 and 500 BC. The Upaniṣads emphasize contemplation and contemplation, and focus on key concepts such as dharma, karma, samsara and moksha. The Upaniṣads also explain the relationship between Brahman and Atman.

Topics

The Upaniṣads relate to the philosophical aspect of Hinduism and are central to various philosophical traditions of India. This includes morality, nature of Brahma (God), soul, Ideal human conduct, Truths about life and death, Ahimsa (non-violence), Satya (truthfulness), and Damah (temperance) etc. The Upaniṣads are called “Vedanta” or the last chapter of the Vedas and they explain the meaning of the Vedas or the purpose for which the Vedas were written.

Holistic education

The Upaniṣads emphasize on a holistic approach towards education which includes the development of mind, body and soul. Upaniṣads encourage the students to develop their intellectual, emotional and spiritual dimensions. Upaniṣads also encourage students to develop harmonious relationships with their environment and realize that education goes beyond the classroom.

Values-Based Education

The Upaniṣads emphasize the importance of ethical behavior and moral values. In response, many educational institutions have

incorporated values-based education, which instills qualities such as compassion, honesty, and empathy.

* सत्यमेव जयते नानृतम् - **Mundaka Upaniṣad (3.1.6)**

This famous phrase stresses the power and importance of truth.

* सत्यंवद । धर्मचर । स्वाध्यायान्माप्रमदः । - **Taittiriya Upaniṣad (1.11.1)**

* मातृदेवो भव । पितृदेवो भव । आचार्यदेवो भव । अतिथिदेवो भव । - Taittiriya Upaniṣad (Shiksha Valli, 11th Anuvaka)

This verse emphasizes on the importance of honesty and devotion in all areas of life.

Critical thinking

The Upaniṣads encourage students to use critical reflection and self-inquiry to understand the mysteries of existence and the interconnectedness of all beings.

Literacy

The Upaniṣads stress the importance of literacy and the ability to understand, remember and analyze what is learned.

Intelligence and life skills

The Upaniṣads contain a wealth of knowledge on science, ethics, history and philosophy and can help students develop essential life skills and knowledge.

* तस्मै स होवाच— द्वे विद्ये वेदितव्ये इति ह स्म यद् ब्रह्मविदो वदन्ति परा चैवापरा च
॥ तत्रापरा ऋग्वेदो यजुर्वेदः सामवेदोऽथर्ववेदः शिक्षा कल्पो व्याकरणं निरुक्तं छन्दो
ज्योतिषमिति । अथ परा यया तदक्षरमधिगम्यते ॥ - Mundaka Upaniṣad
(1.1.4-5)

These verses differentiate between Paravidya (higher knowledge) and Aparavidya (lower knowledge). Aparavidya includes knowledge of Vedas, grammar, phonetics, astronomy, etc., whereas Paravidya is the knowledge of the immortal Brahman.

Critical life lessons:

The Upaniṣads teach moral concepts and life lessons that can help students develop virtue and compassion.

- * ईशा वास्यमिदं सर्वं यत्किञ्च जगत्यां जगत् । तेन त्यक्तेन भुञ्जीथा मा गृधः
कस्यस्विद्धनम् ॥ - Isha Upaniṣad (Verse 1)

This teaches us to be content with what we have and not be driven by greed or material possessions. It encourages a balanced and mindful approach to material life.

Mindfulness

The Upaniṣads teach that incorporating meditation and mindfulness practices into daily life can make people more aware of their thoughts, emotions and actions. It can help people better control their responses to stress and develop greater emotional balance. Here are the key concepts and related terms, as well as their application to everyday mindfulness:

आत्मानं रथिनं विद्धि शरीरं रथमेव तु । बुद्धिं तु सारथिं विद्धि मनः प्रग्रहमेव
च ॥ इन्द्रियाणि हयानाहुर्विषयांस्तेषु गोचरान् । आत्मेन्द्रियमनोयुक्तं
भोक्तेत्याहुर्मनीषिणः ॥ - Katha Upaniṣad (1.3.3-4)

This is a famous example of the chariot, which is used to explain the relationship between the soul, body, mind, and intellect.

Social psychology

The teachings of the Upaniṣads can be applied to social psychology, suggesting that our relationships and interactions with others can have a profound effect on our mental health and well-being.

Conclusion

The Upaniṣads have deeply influenced the world of learning with their timeless wisdom and spiritual insights. These ancient texts emphasize the importance of self-knowledge, calling upon individuals to realize their true nature and inner potential. They highlight the essential role of the teacher or guru in guiding the students towards knowledge and self-realization. Traditional education systems such as Gurukul were inspired by these teachings, fostering a close teacher-student relationship for holistic learning. The relationship between teacher and disciple in the Upaniṣads has influenced mentoring programmes and guidance counseling in modern education. Furthermore, the Upaniṣads advocate a holistic approach to educa-

tion that includes intellectual development as well as spiritual, moral and emotional development. Ethical values are given utmost importance, as education seeks to develop character; compassion and social responsibility in individuals. The Upaniṣads encourage direct experience and contemplation, encouraging experiential learning, self-reflection and critical thinking in the modern education system. The influence of the Upaniṣads on education is profound and transformative. Their timeless teachings have shaped educational philosophy worldwide, leading individuals on a journey of self-discovery, ethics and spiritual growth. Education inspired by the Upaniṣads goes beyond the acquisition of knowledge and becomes a path to self-realization and understanding of the interconnectedness of all existence, that means, besides learning from the Upaniṣads, the students also learned to be socialist people. I am trying to highlight the features of the Upaniṣads in this research work.

So we can say, the Upaniṣads are a collection of ancient philosophical texts that have had a profound and lasting impact on education in ancient times and in current times. These sacred texts provide various insights into the nature of reality, the self, and the ultimate truth, providing valuable principles that are important and can be applied in education. From the emphasis on experiential learning in the *Chandogya Upaniṣad* to the emphasis on self-inquiry in the Prashna Upaniṣad, each Upaniṣad offers unique teachings that can enrich modern education.

This research will help in strengthening the relationship between teachers and students, broadening the thinking of students, inculcating moral values in students, strengthening the educational system, revising the curriculum, adding knowledge from Upaniṣads and Vedic teachings to that curriculum. Therefore, an analysis of the significant concepts of the Upaniṣads in relation to current teachings is discussed in this study. In this study, I have tried to say that without Upaniṣad knowledge the real education of students cannot be complete. In the current education system, today the rival of Vedic education and the Upaniṣads cannot be ignored. Finally, for this reason, I would like to conclude my topic that we are living in modern times but we should be proud of the civilization

and culture inherited from our forefathers. Students should realize the importance of Upaniṣads in making them beautiful, healthy and smooth. Only then students will be able to realize themselves by being educated in the philosophy of Upaniṣad and will be able to contribute to society.

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Social and Cultural Dissent between the Tenkalai and Vatakalai Sects of Viśiṣṭādvaita

Vijitha Vijayan A¹

Vaiṣṇavism is one of the major branches of Hinduism, which is believed to have originated primarily in South India. It is enriched by a variety of customs, rituals, beliefs, philosophy, and a vast collection of distinctive scriptures. Vaiṣṇavism is a living religion with a very significant following and has a continuous tradition in India. It is widely regarded as the cradle of the bhakti movement in India, serving as the foundation for its philosophical evolution and devotional practices. Vaiṣṇavism, due to its social and cultural position, is regarded as an important factor of Indian culture for the development of the bhakti cult. Among Vaiṣṇavas there are many sects and schools. The Viśiṣṭādvaita of Rāmānuja, the Dvaita of Madhva, Śuddhādvaita of Vallabha, Dvaitādvaita of Nimbārka, and Acintyabhedābheda of Śrī Caitanya are all known Vaiṣṇava sects. The sampradāya followed by Rāmānuja is known as the Śrī Sampradāya, that of Madhva is well known as the Brahma Sampradāya, the sampradāya followed by Vishnusvami is known as Rudra Sampradaya, which Vallabhacharya developed further, and that of Nimbārkācārya is the Kumāra Sampradāya.²

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2 Baladeva Vidyabhushana, the author of Prameyaratnavali, quotes this verse as it is from the Padmapurana, and this text not found in printed editions of Padmapurana. सम्प्रदायविहीना ये मन्त्रास्ते विफला मताः । अतः कलौ भविष्यन्ति चत्वारः सम्प्रदायिनः ॥

स्रीब्रह्मरुद्रसनका वैष्णवाः क्षितिपावनाः । चत्वारस्ते कलौ भाव्या हृत्कले पुरुषोत्तमादिति ॥

रामानुजं श्रीः स्वीचक्रे मध्वाचार्यं चतुर्मुखः । श्रीविष्णुस्वामिनं रुद्रो निम्बादित्यं चतुःसनः ॥ Prameyaratnavali (4-6)

Viṣṇu and His avatāras are prominent in Vaiṣṇavism. This powerful tradition, strengthened by the lineage of the Āḷvārs followed by the lineage of ācāryas, has endured for centuries. The Āḷvārs, along with Nāthamuni, and the ācāryas such as Rāmānuja, strengthened, expanded, and popularised the Vaiṣṇava system. In the Vaiṣṇava tradition, the Bhagavad Gītā, the Vedas, and the Āgama pramāṇas such as the Pāñcarātra and Vaikhānasa, along with the Nālāyira Divya Prabandham, are regarded as the fundamental scriptural authorities. Each of these texts contributes uniquely to the philosophical, theological, and ritual dimensions of Śrī Vaiṣṇavism. The Nālāyira Divya Prabandham, also known as the *Tamil Veda*, consists of 4000 divine verses in Tamil composed by the twelve Āḷvārs and was collected and preserved by Nāthamuni.

In the ninth century, Rāmānuja Ācārya profoundly harmonised the devotional hymns of the Āḷvārs with the Vedic tradition, thus creating a distinct synthesis of bhakti and Vedānta and formulating the Viśiṣṭādvaita (qualified non-dualism) system of philosophy (Carman). For this reason, Rāmānuja's philosophical approach is known as Ubhaya Vedānta signifying the equal authority given to both the Tamil *Divya Prabandhas* and the Vedic revelation. Rāmānuja's devotion to social and religious traditions broke through caste barriers and social stigma and attracted a wide range of followers. Later, during the time of Vedānta Deśika, a powerful philosopher who played a major role in expanding the tradition, Viśiṣṭādvaita evolved into two distinct divisions known as Tenkalai and Vaṭakalai (Dutta, 22). Among these two, the Vaṭakalai tradition regards Vedānta Deśika as its principal preceptor, while the Tenkalai school reveres Piḷḷai Lokācārya as its foremost teacher. The Vaṭakalai sect is traditionally associated with northern culture, while the Tenkalai sect is linked with southern tradition. The distinctions between them do not concern fundamental tenets but rather specific interpretative aspects of Śrī Vaiṣṇava philosophy. The linguistic difference between Sanskrit and Tamil was one of the main reasons for the emergence of these two branches of Viśiṣṭādvaita philosophy. These sects produced extensive philosophical and religious literature deeply embedded with social, cultural, and theological significance.

Rāmānuja gave equal importance to Sanskrit and Tamil, but later there arose disputes among his successors regarding whether the Nālāyira Divya Prabandham should be given the same authority as the Upaniṣads and the Bhagavad Gītā written in Sanskrit. This led to major controversy. The Tamil language is so closely intertwined with Dravidian culture that it cannot be separated from it.

The Tenkalai sect gave importance to Dravidian culture and placed emphasis on temples, their administration, and rituals, with its centre at Śrīraṅgam. Vaṭakalai followers, on the other hand, adopted a literary and philosophical approach to criticise and refute systems such as Advaita, Buddhism, and Jainism and to establish their own philosophical positions. Vaṭakalai flourished mainly around Kāñcīpuram, which was a prominent centre of Sanskrit learning. These differences are primarily doctrinal and are commonly enumerated as the Aṣṭādaśa Bhedas, the eighteen recognised points of divergence between the two sects (Ramanuja Acāri). Their differences are not fundamental but relate to ritual, social practices, and soteriological interpretation within Vaiṣṇavism.

The division between the Tenkalai and Vaṭakalai traditions represents a significant instance of social and cultural dissent within a shared theological framework. Although both sects remain firmly grounded in Rāmānuja's Viśiṣṭādvaita philosophy, their divergent interpretations of language, authority, ritual practice, and salvation produced distinct religious cultures. These differences were not merely abstract theological debates but manifested concretely in social organization, temple practices, ritual hierarchies, and modes of devotional participation.

Vaṭakalai soteriology emphasises ethical discipline and scriptural authority, limiting salvation to those capable of ritual observance and spiritual qualification. It can be understood that the main difference between these two sects is the approach to the path to salvation and the vision of the relationship between god and bhakta. There are specifically required spiritual qualifications for the salvation for devotees who want to do eternal service to Narayana. It demands preconditions, restrictions and is only accessible to limited groups (Dave, 81).

Tenkalai, by contrast, stresses divine compassion and inclusivity through prapatti-mārga, wherein liberation depends solely on God's grace rather than moral or ritual eligibility. The Tenkalai school follows Mārjāra-nyāya (the cat analogy), in which the devotee makes no effort and is saved entirely by divine grace. Not moral factors are the eligibility for salvation because God acts freely. He, only moved by compassion, chooses to liberate the devotee. According to this analogy, the kitten makes no effort of its own; it merely cries and waits for its mother, who then lifts and carries it away by the scruff of the neck. This illustrates the belief that liberation depends entirely upon divine grace, with no decisive role assigned to individual effort. Saranagati is open to all to practice. Vaṭakalai adheres to Markaṭa-nyāya (the monkey analogy), where the devotee must actively cling to God (Chari, 398-399). The school of vadakalai devotees hangs to god, who saves him through his grace, like a monkey protects its baby. Here, the baby monkey is actually holding on to its mother without separating from her. That is also what the devotees of the vadakalai sect believe. Although Ramanuja's devotion was intended to enable everyone to reach the presence of God without distinction, the Brahmanical intrusion can be seen to have deviated from that fundamental vision.

While remaining within the philosophical framework of the viśiṣṭādvaita philosophy, these two schools can be clearly identified in society by their differing ritual orientations, with some emphasizing complexity and others simplicity in religious practice.

In Tenkalai practice, temple obeisance and participation are open to all without discrimination based on caste, age, or gender. Vaṭakalai observance follows stricter hierarchical norms governing praṇāma and ritual propriety. A younger person may prostrate only before an elder. Obeisance to women is generally not permitted, except in specific cases namely, one's mother, elder sisters, and the wife of one's ācārya. Furthermore, prostration is one-sided: only the disciple offers obeisance. but inter-marriage is also allowed in these two sects.

By promoting devotional religious faith, challenging rigid hierarchies and exclusivist practices, and contributing to the democratization of the social structure, the Bhakti movement was able to deeply document the socio-cultural life of the people, with a distinct dualistic perspective.

Another one of the most visible and continuing features that differentiates the two traditions is the distinct style of tilak worn on the forehead. It facilitates the recognition of these deities and their forms and enables the identification of adherents belonging to specific traditions. Symbolic identity is expressed through the tirumaṇ (ūrdhva-puṇḍra). Vaṭakalai followers wear a *U*-shaped mark with haridrā (mañjal), while Tenkalai adherents wear a *Y*-shaped mark with kuṅkumam. Differences also exist regarding the theological role of Śrī (Lakṣmī) and the nature of salvation.

The Thenkalai emphasis on Tamil, temple-centered devotion, and unconditional divine grace reflects a socially inclusive orientation rooted in Dravidian cultural consciousness. By privileging *prapatti* as universally accessible and minimizing the role of ritual eligibility, the Thenkalai tradition articulated a vision of liberation that challenged inherited social stratifications. In contrast, the Vadakalai tradition's reliance on Sanskrit learning, scriptural discipline, and ethical qualification reinforced a more regulated religious order, emphasizing hierarchy, propriety, and doctrinal precision. These contrasting orientations generated internal dissent within Śrī Vaiṣṇavism while simultaneously enriching its intellectual and devotional diversity.

Thus, the social and cultural dissent between the Thenkalai and Vadakalai schools should not be understood as a rupture from Viśiṣṭādvaita but as an internal pluralization of the tradition. This dissent reflects broader patterns in Indian religious history, where philosophical systems evolve through dialogue with linguistic, cultural, and social realities. In this sense, Śrī Vaiṣṇavism exemplifies how a unified theological vision can accommodate divergent social imaginaries, allowing both continuity and contestation to coexist within a living religious tradition.

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The Global Journey of Yogic Meditation

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Abstract

This research paper explores the journey of Yogic Meditation from its ancient roots in India to its global adaptations and modern interpretations. It examines the philosophical foundations established in Vedic and Upaniṣadic traditions, the codification of practices by Patanjali, and the integration of meditation within texts like the Bhagavad Gita. The paper highlights the transmission of these practices along trade routes, particularly through Buddhist and Hindu missionaries, and their influence on cultures in China, Japan, and the West. Key figures such as Swami Vivekananda and Paramahansa Yogananda played pivotal roles in popularizing yoga in Western contexts. The study addresses contemporary challenges, including commodification and cultural appropriation, while emphasizing the importance of preserving authenticity. As the global market for yoga and meditation continues to expand, this paper advocates for a balanced approach that honours traditional practices while adapting to modern needs, ensuring that Yogic Meditation remains relevant and meaningful for future generations.

Keywords: Yogic Meditation, Cultural Transmission, Commodification, Authenticity, Modern Adaptations

1. Introduction

Definition of Yogic Meditation

Yogic Meditation is a holistic practice that integrates mind, body, and spirit, aiming to achieve a state of mental clarity and emotional stability. It involves various techniques designed to train attention and awareness, allowing practitioners to detach from habitu-

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al thought patterns and cultivate a profound sense of inner peace (Matko, Sedlmeier, 2019). This practice is not only rooted in spiritual traditions but has also gained recognition for its psychological benefits, including stress reduction and enhanced well-being (Mayo Clinic).

Brief Historical Roots in India

The origins of Yogic Meditation can be traced back to ancient Indian civilization, with early references found in the Vedic texts and Upaniṣads. These texts describe meditation as dhyana, a contemplative practice integral to the spiritual landscape of Hinduism, Buddhism, and Jainism. The Vedic period established foundational concepts that would later be elaborated upon in classical texts like the Bhagavad Gita and Patanjali's Yoga Sutras, which detail systematic approaches to meditation and self-realization (Bryant, 2009).

Purpose and Scope of the Paper

This paper aims to trace the journey and evolution of Yogic Meditation as it transcended geographical boundaries, influencing various cultures worldwide. By examining its historical transmission through trade routes and missionary activities, as well as its adaptation in modern contexts, this study will highlight the significance of preserving its traditional essence while acknowledging contemporary interpretations (Flood, 1996).

2. Origins and Philosophical Foundations

Yogic Meditation in Vedic and Upaniṣadic Traditions

The roots of Yogic Meditation are deeply embedded in the Vedic and Upaniṣadic texts, which laid the groundwork for early meditative practices. The Vedas introduced rituals and meditative techniques aimed at achieving spiritual knowledge and self-realization (Dinabandhu Mahavidyalaya). The Upaniṣads, written between 800 and 200 BCE, further expanded on these concepts, emphasizing dhyana (meditation) as a means to unite the individual soul (Atma) with the universal soul (Brahm) (Flood). Texts such as the Yogatattva Upaniṣad provide detailed descriptions of yoga techniques, including meditation practices that lead to extraordinary states of consciousness and self-realization (Eliade, 2009).

Role of Patanjali's Yoga Sutras

Patanjali's Yoga Sutras, composed around the 2nd century BCE,

codified the philosophy of yoga and meditation into a systematic framework. This seminal text outlines the eight limbs of yoga with dhyana (meditation) being a crucial component in the pursuit of self-realization and liberation (kaivalya) (Bryant). Patanjali emphasizes that through disciplined practice (abhyasa) and detachment (vairagya), practitioners can attain deep states of meditation that lead to profound insights into the nature of reality. His work has been instrumental in shaping both ancient and contemporary understandings of meditation within various spiritual traditions.

Meditation in Bhagavad Gita and Other Classical Texts

The Bhagavad Gita, part of the Indian epic Mahabharata, integrates meditation within broader spiritual contexts, presenting it as a vital practice for achieving self-knowledge and fulfilling one's dharma (duty) (Dinabandhu Mahavidyalaya). The Gita introduces various paths of yoga, including Karma Yoga (the yoga of selfless action), Bhakti Yoga (the yoga of devotion), and Jnana Yoga (the yoga of knowledge), all emphasizing meditation as a means to connect with the divine and understand one's true nature (Flood, 1996). Other classical texts also explore meditation's role in achieving enlightenment, illustrating its significance across diverse philosophical traditions in ancient India.

3. Transmission of Yogic Meditation Beyond India

Ancient Transmission

The transmission of Yogic Meditation beyond India can be traced through ancient routes such as the Silk Road, which facilitated not only trade but also the exchange of spiritual ideas and practices. Buddhist and Hindu missionaries played a crucial role in this dissemination, introducing yogic principles and meditation techniques to various cultures across Asia (India First Life). The movement of monks and traders along these routes allowed for the blending of Indian spiritual practices with local traditions, fostering a rich tapestry of meditation practices adapted to different cultural contexts (Flood, 1996).

Influence on China, Japan, and Southeast Asia

The influence of Yogic Meditation is particularly evident in the development of Buddhism, Zen, and Taoist practices in China and

Japan. As Buddhism spread from India to these regions, it carried with it meditative techniques that were integrated into local spiritual practices. For instance, Zen Buddhism emphasizes zazen (sitting meditation), which shares similarities with yogic meditation techniques focused on mindfulness and inner stillness. In Southeast Asia, the adaptation of yogic principles can be seen in Theravada Buddhism, where meditation is central to achieving enlightenment (Glo).

Spread to the Middle East and European Encounters

The transmission of Yogic Meditation also reached the Middle East and Europe through interactions with Greek philosophers and Sufi traditions. Greek thinkers such as Pythagoras and Plato were influenced by Eastern philosophies, including concepts akin to yogic meditation (Mayo Clinic). Sufism, the mystical branch of Islam, incorporates meditative practices that parallel yogic techniques, emphasizing inner purification and connection with the divine (Yogoda Satsanga Society). These cross-cultural exchanges enriched both Eastern and Western spiritual traditions, illustrating the universal appeal of meditation as a means to attain higher states of consciousness.

4. Yogic Meditation in the West

19th–20th Century Influence

The introduction of Yogic Meditation to the West is often credited to Swami Vivekananda, who first visited the United States in 1883. His participation in the 1893 Chicago World's Fair marked a significant moment in popularizing yoga, as he presented it as a "science of the mind" and translated key yogic texts into English. Vivekananda's teachings resonated with Western intellectuals, including the New England Transcendentalists, who were already exploring Eastern philosophies (Mandalayoga Ashram). Following him, figures such as Paramahansa Yogananda and Maharishi Mahesh Yogi further popularized yoga and meditation in the West during the 20th century. Yogananda's book, *Autobiography of a Yogi*, introduced millions to the spiritual aspects of yoga, while Maharishi's *Transcendental Meditation* gained widespread acceptance for its practical benefits (The Whole U).

Role of Modern Spiritual Movements

The rise of modern spiritual movements has significantly influenced how traditional yogic practices are adapted for contemporary audiences. Movements such as Transcendental Meditation, founded by Maharishi Mahesh Yogi, emphasize simple techniques that can be easily integrated into daily life, making meditation accessible to a broader audience (Mayo Clinic). Similarly, Vipassana meditation, rooted in Buddhist traditions, has gained popularity through ten-day silent retreats that focus on mindfulness and self-awareness (Positive Psychology). Mindfulness practices have also emerged from these traditions, emphasizing present-moment awareness and stress reduction, which have been embraced by various sectors including healthcare and education.

Scientific Research and Acceptance

The scientific community has increasingly validated the benefits of yogic practices through research in neuroscience and psychology. Studies have shown that regular meditation can lead to changes in brain structure and function, enhancing emotional regulation and cognitive flexibility (Glo). Furthermore, yoga and meditation have been incorporated into wellness programs across various industries, highlighting their effectiveness in reducing stress and improving overall health (Mayo Clinic). The integration of these practices into mainstream healthcare reflects a growing acceptance of their benefits beyond spiritual or philosophical contexts.

5. Global Adaptations and Modern Trends

Commercialization and Western Reinterpretation

The commercialization of yoga in the West has led to significant reinterpretations of its original practices and philosophies. As yoga gained popularity in the 1960s and 1970s, particularly among the counterculture movement, it began to be marketed as a lifestyle choice rather than a spiritual discipline (Ecthyer, 2018). This transformation resulted in yoga being presented primarily as a physical exercise, often stripped of its deeper philosophical roots (White). The commodification is evident in the proliferation of designer yoga apparel, celebrity endorsements, and luxury retreats that cater to affluent consumers (Antony, 2018). Critics argue that this com-

modification dilutes the essence of yoga, reducing it to a mere fitness trend while overlooking its spiritual and cultural significance.

Integration into Medical and Therapeutic Practices

Despite concerns about commercialization, there has been a notable integration of yogic principles into medical and therapeutic practices. Healthcare systems are increasingly recognizing the benefits of yoga and meditation for mental health, pain management, and overall wellness. Research has shown that practices such as mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR) can effectively alleviate symptoms of anxiety and depression (Glo). Hospitals and clinics are incorporating yoga into treatment plans, reflecting a holistic approach to health that acknowledges the interconnectedness of mind, body, and spirit (The Catalyst News).

Contemporary Global Spiritual Movements and Retreats

Current trends in spiritual tourism highlight the global appeal of yogic practices. Many individuals seek out retreats in India and other countries to immerse themselves in authentic yogic experiences. These retreats often combine traditional teachings with modern wellness practices, attracting participants from diverse backgrounds (Stop Hindu Dvesha). However, this trend also raises questions about authenticity and cultural appropriation as Western interpretations of yoga continue to proliferate (American Kahani). The challenge remains to honour the original teachings while adapting them for contemporary audiences without losing their essence.

6. Challenges and Controversies

Authenticity vs. Commodification

The commodification of yoga poses significant challenges to preserving its authenticity. As yoga has transitioned from a spiritual practice rooted in ancient Indian traditions to a multi-billion-dollar global industry, tensions have emerged regarding the balance between maintaining traditional practices and adapting them for commercial gains (Antony, 2018). This shift often leads to a dilution of yoga's original intent, with many practitioners focusing more on physical fitness and aesthetic appeal rather than the meditative and philosophical aspects that define its essence (Shvasa, 2024). The

commercialization is evident in the proliferation of luxury yoga studios and branded merchandise, which can overshadow the spiritual journey that yoga traditionally represents (Oxford Student).

Misinterpretations and Cultural Appropriation

Cultural appropriation remains a contentious issue within the discourse surrounding yoga. Many critics argue that non-Indigenous practitioners often strip yoga of its historical and cultural context, reducing it to mere exercise (Baitmangalkarde). This “sterilization” process can lead to the erasure of significant cultural narratives associated with yoga, while the exoticization and commercialization of Indian culture can further perpetuate stereotypes (Oxford Student). Moreover, the predominance of affluent demographics in yoga classes raises concerns about inclusivity and representation, as these practices may become inaccessible to those who do not fit the marketed image of a typical yogi (Weber, 2022)

Balancing Traditional Practices with Modern Adaptations

Navigating the balance between honouring traditional roots and embracing modern adaptations is essential for practitioners today. Many modern yogis advocate for an approach that respects the historical and spiritual dimensions of yoga while also making it relevant to contemporary audiences (Shvasa, 2024). This can be achieved through educational initiatives that emphasize the philosophical underpinnings of yoga alongside its physical practices. Furthermore, fostering an environment of cultural appreciation rather than appropriation can help bridge gaps between different communities and ensure that the practice remains inclusive and respectful of its origins (Weber, 2022)

7. Conclusion

Summary of Findings

The exploration of Yogic Meditation reveals its rich historical roots in India, its philosophical foundations, and the significant transmission of these practices across cultures. From ancient Vedic traditions to contemporary adaptations in the West, Yogic Meditation has evolved while maintaining its core principles. The modification and commercialization of yoga present challenges, yet

they also reflect a growing global interest in holistic health practices. As the yoga and meditation market continues to expand, with projections indicating substantial growth over the next decade, it is crucial to address the tensions between preserving authenticity and adapting to modern needs.

Future Prospects of Yogic Meditation Worldwide

The future of Yogic Meditation appears promising, with the global market for yoga and meditation projected to grow significantly. According to recent estimates, the yoga and meditation market is expected to reach approximately USD 24.6 billion by 2034, reflecting a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 13.5% from 2024 to 2034. As awareness of mental health issues increases, more individuals are likely to turn to these practices for stress management and overall well-being. Innovations such as virtual reality yoga retreats and personalized experiences through artificial intelligence are set to enhance accessibility and engagement, making these practices more appealing to diverse audiences.

The Importance of Preserving Authenticity While Adapting to Modern Needs

While the adaptation of Yogic Meditation for contemporary lifestyles is essential for its survival, it is equally important to preserve its authenticity. Practitioners and educators must strive to maintain the philosophical and cultural roots of yoga while embracing innovative approaches that resonate with modern audiences. This balance can be achieved through educational initiatives that highlight traditional teachings alongside contemporary practices. By fostering an environment that respects the origins of yoga while promoting inclusivity and accessibility, the practice can continue to thrive in a way that honours its rich heritage. The ongoing dialogue surrounding Yogic Meditation's evolution underscores the need for a thoughtful approach that balances tradition with innovation. As we move forward, it is vital for practitioners, educators, and enthusiasts alike to engage in this conversation, ensuring that Yogic Meditation remains a meaningful practice for generations to come.

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Trees as Sacred Spaces: A Reading of Select Writings of Ruskin Bond

Geethu Felix¹

Abstract

Worshipping trees is a common practice in all religions, especially in Hinduism. Plants were considered sacred because of their social, economic, and health concerns by ancient humans. Tree worship is an earliest form of nature worship. They are believed to be inhabited by good or evil spirits. These trees were worshipped to please these gods. Tree worship is one way of protecting nature. The present paper analyzes trees as sacred spaces in the writings of Ruskin Bond. Spiritual Ecology is also used as a tool to analyze the paper.

Keywords: Ecology, Tree, Sacred, Spiritual Ecology, Ruskin Bond.

The concept of spiritual ecology addresses the emotional, mystical, and spiritual connections humans have with other entities on the planet. According to Zsolnai and Flagnan, spiritual ecology encourages “a non-violent revolution in human relationships with nature” (123). Llewellyn Vaughan-Lee sees spiritual ecology as “the exploration of the spiritual dimension of our present environmental crisis.” (Qtd. in Zsolnai and Flanagan 59-66) Leslie Sponsel defines spiritual ecology as “the diverse, complex, and dynamic arena of intellectual and practical activities at the interface between religions and spiritualities on the one hand, and on the other, ecologies, environments, and environmentalism.” (Sponsel 33)

Spiritual ecology integrates three key elements: intellectual (scientific and academic), activism (environmental), and emotional

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(personal spirituality in connection with nature). It is rooted in the spiritual, moral, and inherent value of the natural world, promoting respect, affection, and reverence for nature. This approach emphasizes caring stewardship and a compassionate, harmonious coexistence with all living things.

Spiritual ecology combines ecological awareness with spiritual values, advocating for a holistic understanding of nature. Sacredness of nature, interconnectedness, cultural narratives, and myths are the basic concepts of spiritual ecology.

Trees are extraordinary expressions of the spirit of nature. Trees and their products benefit and enrich human culture in different ways. According to Steven C. Rockefeller and John Elder, they are “particularly apt symbols of the interdependence of spirit and nature” (Sponsel 59).

In Vedic literature, trees are considered sacred. In the *Bhagavad Gita*, Lord Krishna considers trees as great blessed souls who live for the wellbeing of others. They provide food and shelter to mankind. Besides providing food and shelter, trees are believed to be inhabited by spirits.

Nathaniel Altman gives his opinion on how a tree became holy. He comments that “a tree becomes sacred by recognizing the power it expresses.” (Sponsel 60) This power may manifest as food, shelter, fuel, materials used to build boats, or the medicine it provides. A tree varies according to geography, species, and the specific needs of human culture. Sacred trees nurture and heal the emotional and spiritual levels of our being. They are symbols of life, prosperity, creativity, stability, energy, and strength.

Ruskin Bond is an Anglo-Indian writer who loved and respected nature and talked about the importance of trees in his life. Amita Agarwal talks about Bond’s concept of nature in her book *The Fictional World of Ruskin Bond*. “Bond shares many ideas about nature. His attitude is not that of a naturalist. At times he is very close to paganism. It is part of the Indian psyche. He is a nature admirer and passionately promotes nature’s causes through fiction. He reinforces his point by quoting from myths and legends popular among the

common people. He sees a grandmother passing down old beliefs to her grandchildren. She says, "There is a blessing in a tree-shaded house." (79)

Bond's knowledge of Indian mythology and history gleaned from interactions with common people and rich Indian literature. It is best exemplified in his story "Sacred Trees." And he describes the various trees worshipped in India and the myths associated with them. Tree worship is an ancient practice in India. By worshipping trees, one protects the environment.

In "Sacred Trees," Bond describes the various trees and mythological stories behind each tree, as well as demonstrating the medicinal values of each tree. Ruskin Bond in "*Sacred Trees*" illustrates the spiritual and cultural significance of trees in the Indian landscapes. His reflections resonate deeply with the principles of spiritual ecology as he explores how trees serve as sites of reverence and connection for both individuals and communities.

One of the important manifestations of spiritual ecology is the recognition of the sacred places in nature. Sacred places are specific locations or areas that possess one or more qualities. In this sense, sacredness can be attributed to natural phenomena like mountains, forests, trees, groves, plants. The religious and cultural designation of an area as sacred promotes biodiversity conservation.

Bond discusses three trees as sacred: Banayan, Peepal, and Pakar, which in Hinduism are known as Harshankari, the seat of Hari. In Jnana Vriksha, he associates sacred trees like peepal trees with Puranas. He says that sages meditate under the Peepal tree. Buddha attained enlightenment under a Peepal tree. This tree is called Bodhi, or 'tree of wisdom'. For Hindus, the Peepal tree is especially sacred. The Peepal tree and its various parts are known as the embodiment of Gods. Its roots represent Brahma, its bark Vishnu, and its branches Shiva. According to the Vishnu Purana, the seed contains the Peepal tree, and the entire universe is contained in Brahma.

The Mahua tree is considered sacred by many tribes. In a wedding ceremony, the Mahua tree plays an important role on the eve of the wedding day. The Badgi community has a tradition where the groom

performs a mock marriage with a Mahua tree before his actual wedding. This ritual, which includes symbolic acts such as hugging the tree and tying threads to it, demonstrates the cultural importance of nature and spiritual beliefs.

Bond incorporates local myths that attribute spiritual qualities to trees. These myths serve to deepen the readers' appreciation for trees as places of worship and reflection. Bond discusses the legend associated with the Peepal tree in relation to women. He says that when the new moon falls on Monday in rural areas, women worship Peepal. They pour water on the trunk of the tree and put a copper coin and sweets on its roots. There is a belief that it is dangerous to lie or cheat under the Peepal tree. So, one cannot deceive others under the shade of a Peepal tree.

The Pallas tree also has a special place in folklore. The tree has a tendency to drop its leaves when flowering. Flowers are also used to spread colours during Holi celebrations. In Indian mythology, the Palas tree holds great significance. Legends associated with this tree say that the sun god shot an arrow into the earth, and it took root and became the Pallas tree (Bond 147).

Trees growing near the grave of a Muslim saint are given special importance. Bond gives a picture of this event. A Champa tree was there near the tomb of the famous saint Musa Sohag. The branches of the tree are decorated with glass bangles. The story behind this ritual is that childless people come here and offer bangles to the saint. When the saint blesses them, the bangles are taken back and worn on the hands.

Folklore surrounding the Babul tree highlights its cultural and spiritual relevance. Legends describe it as a remedy for fevers and headaches through symbolic acts involving cotton threads and tree embraces. Additionally, consistent watering of the tree is believed to grant influence over its spiritual entities, showcasing a deep connection between natural elements and human belief systems.

The mango tree is seen as a source of blessings and wish fulfillment in Indian tradition. The practice of closing one's eyes and making a wish before the tree reflects the cultural connections with

nature. However, this belief comes with the idea that wishes must be renewed annually to sustain their effect.

Kalp-Vriksha is celebrated as a divine tree, often associated with spiritual legends. One such story describes it as the tree under which Sankaracharya meditated in the Himalayas.

Neem trees, too, have a strong connection to Indian mythology. They were linked to deities believed to shield humans from illnesses. Certain communities worshipped the tree as sacred to Sitala, the goddess of smallpox, and used its branches to treat children suffering from the disease.

Bond's reverence for trees serves as an implicit call to action. His writings encourage readers to appreciate and protect these sacred trees, aligning with the aspects of spiritual ecology that advocate for responsible stewardship of the earth. Bond writes that anyone who plants a peepal tree will receive the blessings of generations to come. Bond emphasizes the importance of tree planting as a way to create a legacy for future generations. He highlights the value of not just peepal trees but a wide variety of species that offer practical benefits like shade and shelter, alongside aesthetic and ecological contributions. Through the lens of myth Bond conveys important life lessons learned from trees. This aligns with the spiritual ecology view that nature offers guidance and insight into ethical living.

The King and Tree Goddess! (The Road to the Bazaar) is a story that discusses the ethical viewpoint of the trees and how they protect both living and nonliving things, and the destructive attitude of humans towards trees. The story is of a king who one day decides to build a palace; he decided to build something different. "The entire palace was to be supported by one column only and that the column was to be made from the tallest tree in the kingdom" (Ruskin Bond's *The Road to the Bazaar* 42). The king ordered his men to cut the tallest tree deodar in his kingdom. The tree goddess who resides in that tree appears in the dream of the king and requests him to change his mind. She pleads before him saying, "*But consider oh King! For hundreds of years, I have been worshiped by the people of all the villages in your kingdom and nothing but good has gone out from me to them. The bird's nest in me. I sent a most lovely shade upon the grass.*"

Men rest against my trunk and wild creatures rub themselves against me. The earth blesses me and sends up new plants and herbs under my protective arms. I bind the earth with my strong roots. Children play at my feet, and women returning from the fields seeks refuge in my coolness” (The Road to the Bazar 45). But the king stands firm about cutting the trees, then the tree goddess replied to king that if he wants to cut down the trees, she requested to the king to cut down the tree into three different parts, the goddess gives the reasons for this, she says “ Dozens of young deodar trees have sprung from me and have grown up around me; should you tell me with one mighty stroke, My weight would certainly crush all my children to death. But if I suffer the stroke three times, and fall in three pieces, some of the young ones may escape” (The Road to the Bazar 46). The king changed his mind and built the palace with stones instead of wood. The story depicts tree as embodiment of life, wisdom and continuity. It stands as a witness to his history and experience.

Sacred groves provide a clear example of the connection between spiritual ecology, sacred places, and biodiversity conservation. These groves represent a form of spiritual ecology and can also contribute to the protection of biodiversity. Sacred groves often consist of forested areas or clusters of trees that communities protect because of their spiritual or religious importance. In addition to their spiritual value, sacred groves may also offer a range of economic, nutritional, medical, social, cultural, and ecological benefits.

Trees play an important role in Ruskin Bond’s life, and his description of trees shows how trees function as sacred spaces in light of the spiritual environment. Bond calls the trees guardians of his consciousness. He lives and works under the principled stewardship of trees. He also admits indigenous people’s care and reverence to certain trees as a means to preserving and conserving biodiversity.

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Traditional Enlightenment: Didacticism in the Texts on Shiva from Indian Mythology

Lisha¹ and Pradeep Singh²

Abstract

Mythologies are part of the philosophical traditions, which carry an abundant source of immense knowledge. Some timeless tutors from mythologies are, Dronacharya from Indian mythology, Sōjōbō from Japanese, Scáthach from Irish, Merlin from British, and so on. Indian philosophical tradition epitomises the accumulation of a massive body reflecting the philosophical activity of around 2,500 years. It prevails as an essence within most of its contemporary people who are connected to it through their ethnicity. Indian mythology has a significant impact on Indian culture, literature, art, and religious traditions. It influences the shared imagination and perspective of millions of individuals, offering a diverse range of narratives and symbols that shed light on the human experience and the enigmas of the universe. Shiva is a figure from Indian mythology, a widely worshipped god in Indian subcontinents, and known by the name Adiguru, the first guru. The texts on Shiva contain didactic lessons and themes. Re-interpretations, retellings, and translations of ancient texts on Shiva fulfil the timeless objectives applicable to contemporary circumstances. Even the devotional songs and stories indi-

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cate hidden lessons that can help understand life's circumstances. The article interprets the selected texts on Shiva to enlighten the masses and develop a fresh and healthy perspective towards life.

Keywords: Didactic; Indian Mythology; Reinterpretations; Shiva; Translations.

Introduction

Different areas and religions have diverse perceptions regarding the meaning of 'enlightenment'. In Europe, enlightenment is the period of the 18th century when people began to pay attention towards science and reason rather than religion. According to Cambridge Dictionary, enlightenment is "the highest spiritual state that can be achieved" in Hinduism and Buddhism. It also means "the state of understanding something" (*Enlightenment*). Enlightenment in Hinduism is a divine and transcendent experience described as a transformative moment of awakening and a steady process of liberating oneself from the bondage of the mind ("What Is Enlightenment?"). There are distinct ways to attain enlightenment, which can be achieved at any stage in life. For some, meditation and mindfulness are the medium of enlightenment. Others regard education as one such source. The process of meditation itself widens knowledge in numerous aspects. The practice of meditation entails the cultivation of mental discipline through the redirection of thoughts. It is frequently employed to heighten present-moment awareness, alleviate tension, encourage relaxation, and foster personal and spiritual development. There are various forms of meditation, but most methods entail locating a calm environment, assuming a comfortable position, and focusing attention on a specific point of focus, for instance, the breath, mantra, a visualisation, or bodily sensations. While practicing Isha Yoga meditation, Sadhguru suggests chanting the line– "I am not the body; I am not even the mind", hence completely distancing the material as well as the internal self, concentrating on the energy beyond the world. People often consider enlightenment a "greater awareness of the world or a higher consciousness" (Israel and Blinka). One might not achieve it merely by reading what others have written. Nevertheless, the acquisition of knowledge from any given source can enhance one's comprehen-

sion of oneself and one's thinking, perhaps leading to the attainment of enlightenment. Knowledge acquisition is a complex and diverse process that encompasses the use of several methods, for instance, books, educational videos and podcasts, courses and tutorials, social media and forums, documentaries and films, traditional media such as newspapers, magazines, television programmes, and radio broadcasts, libraries and archives, as well as personal experiences and experiments. Traditions serve as a valuable means of imparting quality knowledge within a nation. Traditions function as reservoirs of knowledge, culture, and identity, enhancing individuals and society with a wide range of viewpoints and insights from previous generations. Nevertheless, it is crucial to adopt a discerning and receptive viewpoint while engaging with traditions, acknowledging their merits and constraints in addressing contemporary obstacles. Traditional knowledge provides a vast amount of valuable information, methods, and viewpoints that can enhance sustainable development, environmental preservation, healthcare, social unity, and cultural strength. Incorporating it into processes for making decisions is crucial for constructing resilient, inclusive, and peaceful societies.

Traditional knowledge can be helpful in solving contemporary obstructions of life if superstition is kept aside and a proper interpretation is made. Superstition is a belief or behaviour that is usually based on fear or ignorance, rather than scientific understanding or rational thinking. Superstitions sometimes entail ascribing supernatural origins to events, objects, or behaviours, and they exhibit significant variation across different cultures and groups. Traditional knowledge provides significant insights, behaviours, and perspectives that can enhance and enrich contemporary approaches to sustainable growth, health, administration, resilience, and multiculturalism. It is crucial to acknowledge and honour old knowledge systems in order to promote cooperation, inclusiveness, and cultural admiration in our ever more interconnected global society. A study claims that two ethnic groups found that traditional knowledge concerning local plant resources helped communities deal with significant problems like famine (Pardo-de-Santayana and J. Macia). The way it helps in dealing with major ecological issues, traditional

knowledge can be equally helpful in handling other life problems as well. Children in primary classes are taught subjects such as moral science, which includes folk tales and stories from mythology. Tradition is inculcated in children from a very young age, not only in schools but at home through festivals and celebrations. Media is also essential for spreading education. It is difficult for an ordinary human mind to understand the philosophy of the world directly, and hence, it is conveyed through stories contained in folklore and myths. Several characters from Indian mythology are portrayed in cartoons such as Ganesha, Bhim, Hanuman, and so on. These characters positively impact children as they suggest helping people in need, fighting against the wrongs, maintaining a friendly attitude, and yielding emotions such as forgiveness, empathy, etc. In contemporary times, characters from mythology are rising to great heights in influencing people of all age groups. Tradition never loses its value. It lives in fragments, in stories, myths, and culture. Whenever there has been a change in ideologies, the culture has always looked back to traditions. Mythological characters go through numerous circumstances and the way they deal with the problems brings out the moral of the story. The prominence of characters from Indian mythology has increased over time among the masses through translations and reinterpretations.

Shiva, an Indian mythological character, is one of the most worshipped gods in the Indian subcontinent. He is eminent among the youth as well. Every year, people from different parts of the world visit famous Shiva temples. Modern reinterpretation and retellings of traditional texts are blurring the gaps between science and religion. One such instance can be seen in Amish Tripathi's *Shiva Trilogy* as well, where the writer mixes mythology with science and substantiates what otherwise have been perceived as superstition. Contemporary people are moving towards tradition to find solutions to tribulations in their lives. Not only ancient books but songs and *kathas*³ used while worshipping are also noteworthy in evolving a person's mindset. Folk songs are essential in influencing identity formation, promoting cultural perpetuation, and enhancing the

3 Originated from Sanskrit word *katha*, is an "Indian style of religious storytelling, performances of which are a ritual event" ("Katha (Storytelling Format)")

shared human experience. They stand as evidence of the ingenuity, perseverance, and variety of cultures across the globe. Ancient books are highly precious artefacts that enhance our comprehension of history, stimulate originality and advancement, and enhance the abundance and variety of human culture. They maintain their relevance and importance in modern society, functioning as reservoirs of wisdom, motivation, and cultural legacy. The article focuses on *Shiva Amritwani*, *Somvar Vrat Katha* and three translated works on Shiva— *Speaking of Shiva*, *Ishwar Geeta: Lord Shiva's Songs*, and *Shiva: Stories and Teachings from Shiva Mahapurana*.

Shiva Amritwani

Amritwani is a Hindi word meaning 'good sayings'/ 'beautiful promises'. Shiva is regarded as the worshiper of his worshipers. It is also said that Shiva's devotees relate themselves with him by following his dressing style and often try to inculcate the qualities of his nature. Teachings of the Upaniṣads help to reach a higher state of being by liberating the self from any bondage by losing our identities and becoming one with God. *Tat Tvam Asi* translated as 'That thou art' demonstrates that God and our self is indistinguishable. *Ayam Atma Brahma* meaning 'This Self is Brahman' indicates to the consciousness within. Atman and Brahma are said to be the same. Atman is mindfulness that activates the body and enables it to act and perceive. *Aham Brahma Asmi* translated as 'I am Brahman', where Brahma means reality. This teaching is about the declaration of one's enlightenment. It means that the one being enlightened "declares *his Self to be God*" (Terrell). In this regard, one can listen to the "Shiva Amritwani" and relate to the character of Shiva, try to attain an essence of his being, and imbibe the qualities of his humble nature. Shiva Amritwani is a devotional song in Hindi, praising Shiva. It is divided into five parts known as 'Bhaag'. The album was released in 1999 and sung by Anuradha Paudwal (संपूर्ण शिव अमृतवाणी *Shiv Amritwani Complete* | Anuradha Paudwal | *Shiv Amritwani*).

The song deals with the teachings of Shiva by describing his qualities. It is said that to please a god, one must serve some indulgences, which depends on the person and the god they worship. Shiva's character is drawn in such a way that, as a god, he does not care

about the bhog⁴; instead, he is only concerned about the devotion a person shows. Here, material things are unheeded, and true-pure emotions are cherished. “सत्संगति में बैठ कर/करलो पश्चाताप” which means to sit in a good company and repent for whatever wrong one has done in life. Repentance is a sincere resolution to amend one’s way of life. Justified brutal treatment becomes vital in repentance: “it acts as a penance through which the offender can make a forceful, public apology to his victim and the wider community for the wrong he has committed.” (Tasioulas 310). Therefore, sitting in good company and repenting for the wrongs done can not only uplift the social and moral status of the person but also provide mental peace, which is much needed for stable psychic growth. “प्रीत से ही तो प्रीत है बढ़ती” means love begets love, i.e. love is an emotion which increases through love (J. Nicholson). One must stay humble towards people who love them. Developing humility is crucial for nurturing constructive relationships, individual development, and emotional welfare. It allows you to embrace life with a receptive mindset, an empathetic nature, and a readiness to acquire knowledge and develop from each encounter. People often don’t pay much heed to the feelings of those who genuinely love them as they are often taken for granted, which in turn hurts people who care. Contemporary youth are facing trouble balancing their love life and work life. In the hustles of life, people often forget to value relationships. Balance is crucial for comprehensive wellness, individual satisfaction, and the ability to bounce back in the midst of life’s difficulties. By cultivating all facets of life and placing importance on what is truly significant, you can achieve a more balanced, purposeful, and fulfilling life.

Shiva, according to this song, says to wake up from inside, show love, and give up pride– “शिव कहते हैं मन से जागो, / प्रेम करो अभिमान त्यागो”. One should forego the ego, which is one of the root causes of self-destruction and the disputes behind relationships. Being patient, engaging in self-reflection, and making consistent efforts are all necessary components of the process of letting go of one’s ego. Keeping aside the ego, one should shower love and blessings to maintain a positive aura and spread around oneself, as the ego tends to destroy human relationships. Further, it is said that Shiva is like

4 The things used in worship, especially food– sweets, or fruits.

water for a thirsty person. Ravan, Parshuram, and Vishnu are all said to be the worshippers of Shiva. They are entirely different from each other. The innocence of Shiva's character reflects forgiveness as he blesses and gives boons even to the wrongdoers who later repented in their lives, symbolising that one must forgive if people genuinely repent. "सत्य क्रम की देते शिक्षा" meaning he teaches to follow a path of integrity (साह).

"दुनिया का मोह त्याग के/ शिव में रहिए लीन" means 'give up the worldly desires and stay absorbed in Shiva'. As Shiva is known by the name Adiyogi as well as Adiguru, it might indicate that one should focus on gaining knowledge that sharpens the mind and turn towards yoga and meditation, to keep oneself physically fit. "पूजे हम सब तभी हैं शंकर", which means Shiva exists only when we worship him. However, the song here is not being studied from a religious perspective; instead, the universal connotation derived from the worship of Shiva is being explored here. It lucidly states in the second part that Shiva is present only when we believe in him. Shiva here can denote any energy or form of energy worshipped by people all over the world. Their existence is dependent on the human belief system. "शिव सा दयालू और ना दूजा" meaning that there is no one as kind-hearted as Shiva. He teaches the act of forgiving. "भाष्मासुर को वर दे डाला, / शिव है कैसा भोला-भाला", he blesses all those who truly worship him; he is neither partial nor does he judge people. "निर्बल के बल रूप है शंभु/ प्यासे को जल रूप है शंभु" Shiva's strength-giving trait is revealed here. Like Shiva, we should also try to support the weak around us and act like water to a thirsty person. "शिव मस्तक की रेखा बदले" *mastak rekha*, meaning 'forehead lines' are the instruments used by astrologists and palmists to predict the aspects of one's life. This line suggests that Shiva can change the forehead lines, which indicates that no matter what fortune you are born with, you can change it by your devotion or good actions in this birth. Believe in your present; nothing is impossible, and you can alter the direction of your life. Embracing the present moment is important for fostering a profound bond with oneself, others, and the surrounding environment. It has the potential to result in more tranquilly, joy, and satisfaction in one's life. Taking responsibility for one's life is empowering, liberating, and crucial for individual development and well-being. It empowers you to live genuinely, make significant

contributions, and build a life that mirrors your authentic identity and potential. “नेकी का रस बाँटते हरपल” points at Shiva’s message of righteousness. In traditional thinking, there is confusion regarding righteousness and holiness. The word righteousness is translated as “in right-standing” and is a “power to reign over your life, your garden, your body and your household.” (Robinson).

There are several stories about Shiva in this song. One such is that of Ravana, where he lifts the mountain Kailash, which is the abode of Shiva and Parvati. The story behind the mentioned lines is– that Ravana mocked Shiva and Nandi, and when cursed by Nandi, he lifted the mountain Kailash in vain with his twenty powerful arms. When Shiva pressed the mountain with his toe, Ravana began to cry in pain. He sang the praises of Shiva for a thousand years to gain his forgiveness, and at last, he was not only forgiven but also rewarded for his devotion. This story communicates that no matter how powerful or extraordinary a person is, vanity can crush you, the way Ravana got crushed under the mountain. In Indian mythology, as interpreted by the contemporary world, Ravana symbolises a true human being, possessing, imbibing, and justifying all human emotions. Even though you commit some mistakes due to overpowering emotions, repenting can be the best solution. Later, Ravana not only gained Shiva’s forgiveness but was granted various boons in his lifetime due to his constant devotion.

Therefore, this interpretation of the song on Shiva helps enrich the ideology and build a distinct perspective on life. Shiva Amritwani acts as a tool in understanding life and its aspects. It helps in understanding oneself by relating with Shiva, analysing human behaviour in different situations, and bringing a positive change in life. The text enlightens the mind, filling it with hope to become a better human.

Somvar Vrat Katha

It talks about the story of a moneylender who could not have a child in his destiny due to the karma of his previous birth. Still, he used to worship Shiva wholeheartedly. Due to his devotion to his Lord, Lady Parvati requested Shiva, her consort, to grant him a son. Shiva did so but stated that the child would be short-lived and sur-

vive only until 12 years. Shiva came in his dream telling him that the couple will soon be blessed with a boy, but he will have a short life. Soon the house filled with the waves of happiness welcoming a beautiful child. But the moneylender was neither so happy nor sad, as parents always wish for a long and healthy life for their children, he knew this happiness will be, just like the child, short-lived. When the child turned 11, the moneylender sent him to Kashi, for his education, with his maternal uncle, who was asked to perform yajna and feed the Brahmins on their way and during their stay. When the child came to the predicted age, he died in the ashram where they were performing a yajna. His maternal uncle controlled his emotional state and continued the worship and thought of lamenting the death of his nephew only when the yajna was over because crying during the process of a yajna was considered to be inauspicious. Seeing the untimely death of the child and the sufferings of his uncle, Lady Parvati once again bidden Shiva to grant him life. He did so, and the child was revived and blessed with a long life. Meanwhile, parents of the child, who were conscious about the upcoming danger on the life of their son, had taken a resolution that if their son did not return home safely, they would jump from the terrace and commit suicide. He married a princess on his way home, and all the members returned home happily. One picks up several lessons from this story—for instance, the enthusiasm of never giving up. (सोमवार व्रत कथा 2021 - सोमवार व्रत की कहानी - सोमवार व्रत की कथा - Somvar Vrat Katha 2021).

Even though the moneylender knew his son would survive only for 12 years, he continued his worship, not paying much heed to the future. Controlling one's emotions in times of crisis is another lesson one learns from the katha. The child's maternal uncle controlled his urge to cry over his nephew's demise. He knew that if he did so, the entire process of worship would be futile. There are instances in our lives where our emotions overpower us and become the reason for our failures. Controlling one's emotions is a great power one can possess. The story also highlights the power of truth—when the moneylender's son, accompanied by his maternal uncle, was on his way to Kashi, he came across a king who wanted to marry his disabled son to the princess. He asked the moneylender's son to re-

place the prince in order to hide the fact that his son could not see from one eye. He did so but conveyed the whole truth while leaving the palace by writing it on the princess's clothes. When the princess came to know, she refused to go with the prince and lawfully returned to the moneylender's son as his wife. So, the twelve-year-old was rewarded for his truthfulness. Lie has a habit of sneaking out. It will show up at some point in life. The prince and his father had to suffer humiliation because of their attempt to betray the king and his daughter. The story also instructs that money cannot be all-sufficient to buy all the happiness in one's life. Though the moneylender was wealthy, he wasn't happy because money could not beget him a son. Only his good deeds, optimism, and consistent devotion helped him change his destiny and turn his dreadful future into a hopeful one.

Translations of Ancient Shiva Texts

Speaking of Siva

Speaking of Siva is a book of vacanas⁵, translated into English by A.K Ramanujan. In this work Shiva is believed to be a spiritual teacher. It contains the poems of four medieval Vīraśaiva saints from the 10-11 century. These saints are— Devara Dāsimayya, Basavanna, Allama Prabhu, and Mahādēviyakka. Basvanna, a political activist and social reformer of the 12th century, in his vacana 820, says, “things standing shall fall, / but the moving ever shall stay” (lines 11-12). It can be interpreted as we are not just humans; we're human beings. 'Being' is not a permanent thing; it keeps on changing, and it implies the process of becoming. Change is a necessary part of life. We tend to destroy ourselves as human beings when we remain static. There will be no difference between living and non-living when we too become as rigid as a rock. The goal should be to develop a mindset of moving forward in life. Talking about an innocent sacrificial lamb, Basvanna ends the poem by asking, “did the killers survive, /O lord of the meeting rivers?” (lines 7-8). A person must repent for the sins he/she commits as the cycle of Karma goes on and the same will eventually happen to the killers as they too, like the lambs, cannot survive forever because of the inevitability of death. Before harming a feeble, one must be aware about the consequences. We should not

5 In Hinduism, Yajna is a Vedic tradition, a ritual done in front of the fire along with chanting of mantras.

be the reason for harming others, as we too might meet the same fate because what goes around, comes around. (Ramanujan).

When Basvanna states in his vacana 97 that “Lies in the body, / lust in the heart:/ no, the master of the house is not at home,/ our Lord of the Meeting Rivers.” (lines 5-8). The saint here, being a social reformer, is talking about corruption. It could imply that when we’re corrupt, the lord⁶ does not stay near us. When we adapt to the crooked ways in life, we won’t be able to attract positive energy around us. So, an honest path must be followed to attract happiness. Any work done without the willingness of heart will not provide good results. It doesn’t matter how hard or how long the person works if the heart lingers somewhere else, as Basvanna in Vacana 99 says, “Does it matter how long/ I’ve spent in worship/ when the heart is fickle?” (lines 4-6). Here, the poet talks about worshiping, but concentration/ focus is generally a necessary tool for staying dedicated. The story of Nachiketa, a five-year-old character from the Upaniṣads, also highlights the importance of intensity in work; without intensity, there is no transformation. Dasimayya, one of the earliest of the vacana poets, in his Vacana 42, also focuses on the analogous theme where he tells how a man filled grain in a tattered sack without being aware about its ragged condition and walking all night, he emptied his sack at the end. The only fear he had was of the tollgates. (Ramanujan, 1973, p. 81). The vacana suggests that one should be attentive and concentrate on the work being done. Only by fixing the present one can mend the future. If one absent-mindedly ignores the loopholes in life, he/she might lose everything. The man was concerned about future problems, ignoring the present mess, and hence, he could not even reach the future hurdles. The knowledge gained here is– to live in the present and don’t unnecessarily worry about things that don’t exist in the present. In his 80th vacanna, Dasimayya states, “The earth is your gift, / the growing grain your gift,/ the blowing wind your gift.”(lines 1-3). Everything around us, living or non-living, is a gift and should be valued. Everyone has the fundamental human right to live on this planet, for instance, the right to food. In pursuing wealth and success in life, people tend to forget what they must value as gifts from a higher being. In her Vacanas, Mahadeviakka, a younger

6 Saying; religious lyric in Kannada free verse

contemporary of Basvanna, keeps a positive attitude towards the ills of life as she states in her 65th Vacanna, “If the skies tear down/ I shall think them pouring for my bath”. Optimism is a healthy mindset that helps in overcoming the hindrances of life without much fuss.

Ishwar Geeta: Lord Shiva’S Songs

This book translated by Andrew J. Nicholson contains 8th century songs. It is a long philosophical poem that conveys the teachings of Pashupatas⁷. In this work Shiva is the Pashupati⁸ who guides a group of sages about the highest truth and the means to realise it through the practice of yoga. Chapter 2 mentions that according to wise men “in the highest truth/ there is only nonduality” (J. Nicholson). Nonduality, here, might symbolize the interconnection of everything around us. When one gets enlightened with the highest truth and perceives all things and beings as interconnected, the tendency to harm or destruct anyone or anything will be reduced. According to this book, Shiva resides in all beings as he says in chapter 6, “I am the eternal self of all beings” (p. 87). One can relate to Shiva when he states, “I am the destroyer. /I am the creator and maintainer.” (p. 68). We all are responsible for most of the events in our lives. We can create it the way we desire. It’s in our hands to maintain it and we can likely destroy it as well if we choose the wrong path in life. Shiva also states that “I am the householder” (p. 100). Men generally tend to associate themselves with the outer world, distancing themselves from the home as it is associated with women. Here the character Shiva, as a pro-feminist. Being pro-feminist entails actively advocating for gender equality and confronting the social, political, and economic systems that sustain gender-based disparities and injustices. Creating a more just and equitable world for all genders necessitates continuous dedication and implementation. Shiva, as a pro-feminist, provides an insight into how a person who possesses the qualities of both the genders is valued the way people worship Shiva. His *Ardhanareeshvara*⁹ form is itself an example of his ways of accepting and cherishing the dualistic human nature present as feminine and masculine forces.

7 The interpretation is not talking about any specific god of a particular religion. ‘Lord’ might mean any form or energy that a person worships or relies upon.

8 Group of Shiva worshippers

9 The master of beasts

Talking about balance in Chapter 7, purity is said to be knowledge, and inertia is considered ignorance. When we don't act in any situation, we tend to ignore our duty to act. Change is a part of life, and one must accept it. Agitation is the mixture of knowledge and ignorance. The imbalance of *gunas*¹⁰ results in the error in intellect. This excerpt talks about maintaining a balance in life as the otherwise condition might create disturbance in life. Chapter 11 talks solely about yoga. There are five restraints of yoga mentioned, which purify the minds of human beings. They are non-harming, non-stealing, non-acquisition, truthfulness, and celibacy (p. 127). "There is no *dharma* higher than non-harming" (p. 128). It is said to be the greatest happiness. When people stop the actions intended to harm others, physically or emotionally, the world will become a better place to live in. One must understand the depth of hurting someone and act with a sense of empathy. Internal purity is the purification of the mind (p. 130). We must think wisely and keep our thoughts clear.

Shiva: Stories And Teachings From Shiva Mahapurana

Shiva and Vishnu are the two characters from Indian mythology, and the major gods in Hinduism. It is stated in *Bhagavat Purana* that, "Lord Visnu possesses all opulences, while Lord Siva lives in poverty. Yet the devotees of Visnu are generally poverty-stricken, while Siva's attain abundant wealth." ("Canto 10: The Summum Bonum"). The physical portrayal of Shiva is against the set standards of society as his images/idols are often seen in tattered clothes with ashes from the cremation ground smeared all over the body. Though his ways seem inauspicious, his name itself means auspiciousness. "Shiva is the symbol of purity despite dabbling in impurity." (Vanamali). This line suggests that no matter how bad the environment or circumstance is, one must be conscious about the surroundings and remain as vibrant as the character of Shiva. Balance in life is an essential factor of survival. According to an incident from *The Sivapurana*, if Shiva became entirely detached from the world, the cosmic balance would extinguish. (Shastri). So, the text suggests that "a certain amount of tension is always necessary to maintain the work

10 Ardhnareeswara is a manifestation of Shiva where he is half-male and half-female. The female represents his consort Parvati/Sati. 'Ardh' means half, 'nare' means woman, and 'eswara' means god, representing Shiva.

of creation” (Vanamali, 2013, p. 40). Though it discusses cosmic creation, it also applies to an individual’s life. Constantly, human beings are subjected to suffering for a variety of reasons. The disturbance might be physical or psychological. Everyone goes through a certain level of problems in life. However, one must understand that there are difficulties in balancing the happiness of one’s life. What pleasure can the day provide if there is no night? Karl Marx said, “Accumulation of wealth at one pole is at the same time accumulation of misery, the agony of toil, slavery, ignorance, brutality, mental degradation, at the opposite pole.” (Marx, 2007, p. 709). It is evident in every situation of life. Positive or negative, are such aspects that must equally be accepted and cherished as a natural part of life. The character of Shiva from Indian mythology represents gender parity– “With Parvati as his consort, Shiva will become Ardhanareswara” represented as “two halves of a whole” (Vanamali, 2013, pp. 74-99). The devotion of this character towards his devotees provides a sense of selflessness when he says, “I am willing to give up my own interests in order to serve yours.” (p. 87). With dignity he mentions himself as a slave of his devotees.

Conclusion

Attaining knowledge is a core aspect of humanity. A person can be enlightened at any point in life by anything or anyone. Everything contains meaning within, though the process of attaining that meaning might differ from person to person. Even the absurd plays known for their nihilistic aspect and absence of purpose in life eventually provide a sense and understanding of the process of life from a unique perspective. Numerous texts around the globe carry infinite symbols depending on how they are interpreted. Indian traditional knowledge believes in the intimate relationship of philosophy and life. The Indian philosophical tradition is the oldest and the most extended continuous development of assumptions about the nature of reality and man’s place therein. Indian thinkers of all ages have been profoundly concerned with the ultimate reality and truth, which is as timeless as the Santana Dharma, translated as ‘eternal religion’. The study of the inner self of a man, according to traditional Indian knowledge, is ultimately a study of the universal nature of man. The paper attempted to highlight the message Indian mythology and its

characters can provide and the way they can be helpful in building up a healthy perspective towards life.

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Vedānta and the Global Dissemination of Sri Ramakrishna's Spiritual Wisdom through Max Müller.

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Abstract

This paper examines the global dissemination of Vedānta philosophy through the life and teachings of Sri Ramakrishna and the scholarly mediation of Max Müller in the late 19th century. It highlights Müller's deep engagement with Hindu philosophy and his efforts to introduce Ramakrishna's teachings to Western audiences through his two seminal works: the essay *A Real Mahatma* (1896) and the book *Ramakrishna: His Life and Sayings* (1898). These publications, alongside Swami Vivekananda's letters and lectures in America and Europe, played a pivotal role in bridging Eastern spiritual wisdom with Western scholarly inquiry. The study analyzes Ramakrishna's sayings, emphasizing the universality of spiritual devotion, the dissolution of social and caste distinctions through self-knowledge, and the ethical and practical application of Vedānta in daily life. His respect for all religions, including Muslim and Christian practices, reflects an integrative approach that resonates with modern intercultural dialogue. By situating Ramakrishna's teachings within their historical context and examining Müller's two major works, the paper demonstrates how 19th-century essays, books, and correspondence facilitated the global transmission of Vedānta. The research underscores Vedānta's relevance for moral consciousness, spiritual development, and cross-cultural understanding, illustrating its enduring applicability in contemporary philosophical and religious discourse.

Keywords: Vedānta, Sri Ramakrishna, Max Müller, *A Real Mahatma* (1896), *Ramakrishna: His Life and Sayings* (1898), Swami Vivekananda, 19th-century correspondence, Eastern philosophy, Western reception, devotional practice

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Introduction

Vedānta, one of the six classical schools of Indian philosophy, emphasizes the realization of the self's unity with Brahman, the ultimate reality. Its principles have guided spiritual seekers in India and inspired philosophical discourse worldwide. Among the pivotal figures in the global dissemination of Vedānta are Sri Ramakrishna, a 19th-century mystic and saint, and Max Müller, a renowned Western scholar of religion.

In the late 19th century, Müller engaged deeply with Hindu philosophy and recognized the universal significance of Ramakrishna's teachings. His essay *A Real Mahatma* (1896) and his book *Ramakrishna: His Life and Sayings* (1898) introduced these insights to Western audiences, highlighting the devotional, ethical, and practical dimensions of Vedānta. These works played a crucial role in popularizing Ramakrishna's life and teachings, presenting his spiritual message in a form accessible to scholars and the general public alike.

Complementing Müller's publications, Swami Vivekananda's letters, lectures, and travels across America and Europe further disseminated Ramakrishna's message, establishing Vedānta Societies and promoting intercultural understanding. This paper explores the convergence of Eastern spiritual wisdom and Western scholarship, examining how 19th-century writings, books, essays, and correspondence enabled the global transmission of Vedānta philosophy. By analyzing Ramakrishna's sayings and Müller's two seminal works, the study demonstrates the enduring relevance of Vedānta in fostering spiritual unity, ethical consciousness, and cross-cultural dialogue.

Max Müller's Devotion to India and Vedānta

Max Müller's profound admiration for India and her cultural-philosophical heritage has been widely acknowledged in both Eastern and Western scholarly circles. Though rooted in Western intellectual training, he was irresistibly drawn toward the study of Hindu philosophical systems—especially Vedānta, which he regarded as one of the most refined expressions of metaphysical thought. While examining the evolution of the six orthodox systems of Indian philosophy (Śaḍdarśanas), Müller also emphasized the need to un-

derstand the universal spiritual principles uniting diverse religious traditions. His lifelong engagement with the Vedas, particularly his translation of the R̥gveda Saṁhitā along with its commentarial literature, earned him exceptional reverence among Indian scholars and lay readers alike.

Harmonizing Eastern and Western Religious Traditions

A distinct feature of Müller's scholarship was his unwavering belief in the essential unity underlying the world's religions. He perceived India not merely as a geographical space but as a sacred intellectual treasury capable of illuminating universal truths. Through comparative studies, he attempted to bridge the philosophical distance between Eastern mystical traditions and Western theological thought. His writings repeatedly argued that the foundations of religious consciousness—whether articulated in the Vedas, the Upaniṣads, or Christian scriptures—are rooted in the same divine ground of existence. This pursuit of harmony became a hallmark of his work and influenced generations of scholars after him.

Müller and the Rise of the Science of Religion in the West

Max Müller is recognized as one of the earliest architects of the 'Science of Religion' (Religions Wissenschaft) in Europe. His method combined philology, comparative philosophy, and historical analysis to establish a structured academic discipline for the study of world religions. In 1898, he published *Ramakrishna: His Life and Sayings*, a landmark work that brought the spiritual genius of Ramakrishna to Western readership. Even earlier, in 1896, he wrote the celebrated essay *A Real Mahatma*, which offered the first accessible portrait of Ramakrishna to English-speaking audiences. Müller's contributions played a foundational role in shaping modern Indological studies.

A Real Mahatma and the Composition of Ramakrishna: His Life and Sayings

The publication of *A Real Mahatma* in 1896 in a prominent English journal marked a significant cultural exchange between India and the West. It introduced Ramakrishna as an authentic mystic saint whose life embodied the deepest spirit of Vedānta. Two years later, Müller expanded his research into the more comprehensive volume

Ramakrishna: His Life and Sayings, released twelve years after the Master's passing. Drawing upon available biographies, testimonies, and thirty-one selected sayings, Müller portrayed Ramakrishna as a spiritual phenomenon unparalleled in the modern era. His text was not merely descriptive; it acted as a bridge connecting Eastern spiritual experience with Western intellectual curiosity.

Swami Vivekananda's Global Vedānta Movement

During the same period, Swami Vivekananda was actively disseminating Vedānta across America and England. He often clarified that the Vedānta he taught was not an abstract philosophy but a direct expression of his Master Ramakrishna's realization. Swamiji's intention was never personal glorification but the transmission of Ramakrishna's universal message. As a result, he established several Vedānta Societies, delivered groundbreaking lectures, and dismantled Western misconceptions about Hindu philosophy. Vivekananda's presence in the West created a receptive audience for Müller's later writings on Ramakrishna, enabling a deeper cultural and philosophical dialogue.

Correcting Western Misconceptions about India and Hinduism

The 19th century West was rife with misunderstandings about India—its religious practices, social systems, and philosophical heritage. India was often misrepresented through colonial narratives and superficial observations. Swami Vivekananda, through his electrifying Chicago addresses and extensive travels, challenged these inaccuracies with unmatched clarity and authority. His teachings revealed the ethical and metaphysical depth of Hindu thought, compelling Western audiences to re-evaluate their preconceived notions. In parallel, Müller's writings helped dispel intellectual prejudice and provided scholarly validation for Indian spiritual wisdom. Their combined efforts significantly transformed Western perceptions of India.

Ramakrishna as a Mystic Saint and the Vedāntic Essence of His Sayings

Ramakrishna Paramahansa emerges in Müller's writings as a saint of extraordinary simplicity yet profound spiritual insight.

Deeply absorbed in meditation and inner realization, Ramakrishna's life embodied the experiential essence of Vedānta rather than its mere theoretical exposition. Each of his sayings—rooted in direct experience—radiated the fragrance of Vedāntic truth while paradoxically resonating with Western intellectual frameworks. Müller observed that Ramakrishna's teachings showed a remarkable capacity to converse simultaneously with Indian metaphysics and European rational thought, creating a unique synthesis within a Vedāntic consciousness. This universality explained his growing appeal across continents.

Ramakrishna's Sayings and the Vedāntic Consciousness

The sayings of Śrī Ramakrishna are permeated with an unmistakably Vedāntic consciousness. Philosopher Max Müller observed that, unlike the terrifying popular forms of Kālī worship prevalent in India, Ramakrishna's interpretation of the Divine Mother contained no trace of harshness or hostility. For him, the Mother was nothing but the embodiment of pure tenderness. His relationship with Kālī was that of a child with its loving mother—an experience of blissful spiritual intimacy symbolizing the divine maternity that represents the power and influence of womanhood.

Śāradā Devī and the Ideal of Spiritual Purity

Śāradā Devī, the Holy Mother and Ramakrishna's wife, was never associated with him in any physical or conjugal manner. Ramakrishna often said, "Women possess a power of fascination that can separate one from the divine love of God." In order to free himself from the influence of kāmīnī (lust), he would pray and cry out in heart-rending anguish—sometimes on the banks of the Ganges and sometimes in his room. He would call upon the Mother in a loud, plaintive voice, seeking liberation. This devotional intensity deeply moved many people, drawing large crowds who wept with him and prayed for spiritual welfare and perfection.

The Universal Vision of Woman as Divine Mother

To him, every woman was an embodiment, a symbol, an incarnation of the Divine Mother—whether young or old. Mother Kālī herself, as he affirmed, taught him to behold every woman as the

manifestation of Jagadambā. He prayed to Her thus:

“Mother, I do not desire honour from men. I do not seek physical pleasure. May my soul fly to You—the eternal confluence of the Gaṅgā and Yamunā. Mother, I have neither devotion nor yoga. I am poor and friendless. I seek no praise from anyone. May my mind dwell forever at Your lotus feet.”

Ramakrishna’s Harmonization of World Religions

Ramakrishna did not confine himself to the rituals, deities, or doctrines of Hinduism alone. He practised Islam with the same sincerity with which he practised Christianity. He ate, prayed, and lived according to the disciplines of these religions. He quoted from the Qur’ān, and on hearing the name of Lord Jesus he would bow his head reverently and participate in Christian worship. He stated that the devotional practices of every religion were, to him, a living and inspiring personal mantra. He was a true traveller on the path of universal religious harmony. Through his celebrated dictum “Yato mat, tato path” (“As many faiths, so many paths”), he accepted and integrated the truths of all religions. He examined the good in each, and with deep respect honored their devotion to God, their pursuit of truth, and their love for humanity.

Significance of Max Müller’s Essay in the Nineteenth Century

By the end of the nineteenth century, the importance of Max Müller’s essay was immense. In the history of the Ramakrishna Movement, the publication of this essay created a significant stir in numerous journals and newspapers. The book *The Life and Letters of the Right Honourable Max Müller* observes:

“Max Müller collected his sayings and materials for his life, feeling that attention ought to be drawn in this country to the utterances of men like Ramakrishna, who gather large multitudes round them, and who exercise a powerful influence, not only on philosophers but on large masses of the people.” (p. 59)

Max Müller’s Presentation of Ramakrishna’s Sayings and Their Universal Appeal

Max Müller highlighted the sayings of Śrī Śrī Ramakrishna in a manner that could stir the deepest emotions of an ordinary reader. Ramakrishna’s expressions often carried a simplicity that concealed

profound spiritual insight. For instance, upon hearing descriptions of God in the Divine Mother-form, he would be overwhelmed with wonder. His spontaneous questions such as, “Why does a devotee become so intoxicated when he calls upon the Mother?” revealed his intimate understanding of the devotee’s heart. He would explain, “A child is most free and fearless only with the mother; the mother is the closest, the dearest, the most forgiving—no one else in the world offers such nearness.”

Similarly, his teachings—“What is the strength of a spiritual aspirant? It is the childlike cry of the seeker”—expressed the essential psychology of devotion. His famous declarations such as, “He who has faith has everything; he who lacks faith has nothing,” or “God is in everyone, but not everyone is in God, and that is why there is so much suffering”—affirmed the Vedāntic understanding of the divine presence within the human soul.

From such sayings it becomes evident that, unlike any other civilization, India has uniquely perceived the presence of divinity in the depths of the human heart and nature—especially in the form of the Universal Mother. Ramakrishna’s devotional fervor, rooted in complete self-surrender to God, flowed naturally and spontaneously through his words. These inspired millions because of their profound simplicity, emotional immediacy, and universal relevance. His reflections on life and death articulated the hopes and inner faith of countless individuals, offering a vision of spiritual optimism for the future. Ramakrishna’s teachings reveal that every human being partakes in the divine consciousness, and that this awareness can lay the foundation for a grand inner temple in the hearts of future generations. Such is the basis of his worship as a great and universal spiritual personality.

Deeply moved by Ramakrishna’s sayings, Max Müller felt that Ramakrishna was truly an exponent of Vedānta—despite not being a scholar of Sanskrit or English. Müller remarked:

“To my mind these sayings—the good, the bad, and the indifferent—are interesting because they represent an important phase of thought and attempt to give prominence to the devotional and practical side of the Vedānta, and because they show the compatibility of the Vedānta with

other religions. They will make it clear that the Vedanta also possesses a morality of its own (61).”

Conclusion

On May 24, 1896, Swami Vivekananda had a personal meeting with Max Müller. During this encounter, Swamiji observed Max Müller’s profound affection for India and the Indian people. He further explored and noted Müller’s deep reverence for Sri Ramakrishna. Müller had written:

“Who would have thought that the life and teachings of a poor Brahmin youth from a Bengal village would, within a few years, reach such distant lands? Our ancestors could never have imagined this, even in their dreams.”

In the *Ninety Century* journal, Professor Müller authored an essay on Ramakrishna, stating that anyone who sincerely loves Ramakrishna—regardless of gender, community, or caste—experiences a pilgrimage-like knowledge by coming into his presence.

Ramakrishna himself worshipped the divine as manifest in forms like Vishnu, Shiva, and other deities, yet he saw the singular Ultimate within all these varied manifestations. His devotion to the Divine Mother was a pure reflection of a human child’s love for its mother—unwavering, complete, and tender. Even while being close to the Brahmanic ideal, his supreme aspiration was to merge entirely with the Absolute.

Through simple examples drawn from everyday life, Ramakrishna guided individuals from the darkness of ignorance to the light of knowledge. His teachings cleanse the dust of human life, allow one to breathe purely and freely, and illuminate the soul with Vedantic wisdom. In every verse of his sayings, the radiance of Vedāntic light shines forth, promoting the welfare of humanity and the world.

Professor Max Müller, with profound admiration, highlighted the Vedantic essence in Sri Ramakrishna, revealing the inner illumination of the heart and the realization of the Supreme Self. With Swami Vivekananda’s guidance, Müller endeavored to present even a glimpse of the wisdom of this great Tantric sage. The invaluable insights of these three human-divine figures continue to serve as a living message for the welfare of humanity, remaining highly rele-

vant and ever-flowing. The Vedantic knowledge imparted to every human heart kindles the lamp of consciousness—a light of joy, the mantra for living in bliss, eternal and enriching

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Customary Law and Criminal Justice in Medieval Kerala

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Abstract

This paper investigates the customary law and criminal justice of medieval Kerala focusing on the discussion of temple records and Dharmaśāstra traditions. Law and order were governed by Maryādā (local law) in medieval Kerala, which was influenced by *Dharmaśāstra* customs and temple-centered society. Unlike modern legal systems, criminal justice was reactive, situational, and connected to local customs rather than organised courts. Temple records, though limited, provide understandings into the procedures, punishments, and roles of caste and community in administering justice. The paper also explores the Vyavahāramālā, a *Dharmaśāstra* text from Kerala, which outlined legal processes rooted in caste hierarchy and Brahmanical privilege. The study highlights how the political and social structures of the period were deeply connected with religion, with rulers often acting as protectors of customary laws. By analyzing these records, the paper contributes to understand the legal and social history of medieval Kerala.

Keywords: Dharmaśāstra, Maryadā, Vyavahāramālā, Custom, Law, Brahmin,

Medieval Kerala

Crime exists in all organized societies but can vary in type and frequency depending on the environment and population. Ensuring the protection of life and security is a primary responsibility of the government. Therefore, establishing law and order has historically been a concern of all citizens since the formation of organized societies or states. According to Manu, the ideal state and society aim to

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achieve *Mokṣa* through the pursuit of *Dharma* (duty), *Artha* (prosperity), and *Kāma* (pleasures). To sustain this social order, certain forces need to be applied, as reflected in the ancient customs and practices of the land. Thus, punishments are used to maintain order, since finding a completely innocent person is rare. The fear of punishment helps ensure that society remains orderly and able to enjoy its benefits.²

In medieval Kerala, legal procedures and criminal law were part of what was known as *Maryādā*, the local law. Unlike land law, however, there are fewer records detailing criminal law practices. Crime, punishment, police procedures, and legal processes were often mentioned incidentally in temple records, which primarily focused on documenting temple finances³. Therefore, understanding of criminal law in medieval Kerala is limited.

The following comparison does not explore into the differing views on criminal law within *Dharmaśāstra* itself. These debates are not relevant for comparing *Dharmaśāstra* and Kerala temple records. However, it is important to note that not all *Dharmaśāstra* s have a unified stance on criminal law. Despite the scarcity of evidence regarding criminal law in medieval Kerala, temple records provide some insight that can improve our understanding of this aspect of Kerala's history. Previous descriptions of Kerala's criminal law before colonial times have been brief and dismissive. For example, the basic overview given in K.V. Krishna Ayyar's *Zamorins of Calicut* states that justice was administered by upholding local customs and safeguarding each caste's and community's *Dharma* and *Maryāda*. Local bodies known as *Panchayats* handled disputes. It was a simple criminal justice system. Caste tribunals handled crimes pertaining to religion and morals. To guarantee fair trails and uphold the ver-

2 सर्वो दण्डजितो लोको दुर्लभो हि शुचिर्नरः ।

दण्डस्य हि भयात्सर्वं जगद्भोगाय कल्पते ॥ (Manusmṛti, VII.22)

3 The *Talaśśery Rekhakaḷ* (1796-1800) provide detailed information on criminal cases and their resolution. However, since these records come from a later, partially colonized period, they are less reliable for understanding medieval Kerala's legal traditions. The basic legal patterns are similar, but caution is needed when applying these later records to earlier history. Here, the *Talaśśery Rekhakaḷ* are used mainly to supplement evidence from temple records before the mid-18th century.

dicts, the king appointed an official named *Koyma* (1938, 280-282).

Criminal law in medieval Kerala was mainly reactive. The procedures, punishments, and policing for dealing with crimes were seldom initiated by the area's political leaders, except when the crime directly affected them or their interests. This does not imply that all aspects of criminal law were improvised by those prosecuting the crime. Instead, it indicates that those in charge of apprehending, trying, judging, and punishing criminals had significant control over the process and could take into account factors beyond just legal rules when deciding a case. The reactive nature of criminal law in medieval Kerala reflects principles found in *Dharmaśāstra* texts. According to Manu, it was up to individuals to start both civil and criminal proceedings: "Neither the king nor any official shall independently initiate a lawsuit; nor shall they suppress an action brought by someone else."⁴ Priyanath Sen noted that *Dharmaśāstra* literature advised that neither kings nor their officers should start or encourage litigation on their own, but should only act on complaints from the aggrieved party (1984, 336).

Courts in late medieval Kerala were not established institutions but rather events. Although some foreign travelers described the Zamorin of Calicut holding court for criminal cases, these accounts reveal that even the most powerful political leader in Malabar did not have a regular court system. This is further evidenced by Col. John Munro, who, upon becoming Resident and Divan of Travancore in 1809, prioritized creating a hierarchical court system in British Kerala, highlighting the previous lack of institutionalized courts and procedures (Shungoony Menon, 1878, 270-280). In the absence of formal courts, temple communities in rural Kerala handled local crimes with the involvement of rulers, officials, and Nairs.

Despite the lack of organization in Kerala's criminal code during the medieval period, temple records show some rules. The Brahmin temple at Trkkandiyūr, which is run by the Vanjeri Brahmin family, is a noteworthy example. The assassination of a Brahmin council member at the temple is described in this document. The Vanjeri

4 नोत्पादयेत्स्वयं कार्यं राजा नाप्यस्य पुरुषः ।

न च प्रापितं अन्येन ग्रसेदर्थं कथं चन ।। (Manusmṛti, VIII. 43)

record⁵ states that on the 15th day of the month of Makara in Kollam year 783 (1607 C.E.), Ūrakattu Uṇṇāman, an official of the Zamorin, killed Karipuram, a Nampūtiri Brahmin, while he was bathing at the temple tank. Uṇṇāman ran away south, prompting a pursuit by the locals. He was captured and taken to Tṛkkandiyūr, where he was struck in the head. The head of the Vanjeri family informed the Zamorin and received permission to execute the *Sanketa Maryāda* (local law). On the 19th, a council including Vanjeri, other notable families, and Nāyars deliberated on the case. They were responsible for enforcing the law, referred to as *Daṇḍa*, or the ruler's rod, in *Dharmaśāstra*. Due to illness, the Kovil Nambi⁶ provided a writ to carry out the law (Narayanan M.G.S., 1987, 29).

Karunāṭṭu Nair, Kommāḷi, and the Nairs of Pantirālam took Uṇṇāman to Poṭṭalākal⁷, where he was executed by Kommāḷi. Uṇṇāman's belongings were given to the Vanjeri, who then passed them to Uṇṇāman's relatives. His mother received his earring and silk cloth. Uṇṇāman's relative turned over the weapon on the ninth day of *Mīna* (A month of Kollam year) and was given a written receipt. The legitimacy of the execution was validated by a royal writ issued by the Zamorin. Using the local legislation (*Sanketa Maryāda*), the local council decided to execute Uṇṇāman with the Zamorin's consent. Localized law, which refers to the general law of a place and may be a component of a larger regional legal system, must be distinguished from local law, which is specific to a given area. It is essential to comprehend this distinction, particularly when discussing custom and customary law.

The procedures of criminal law in this case were hardly formalized procedures at all. The resolution followed the specific details of the case. The victim, Karipuram, was a senior member of a promi-

5 The Vanjeri Record consists of palm leaf manuscripts kept in the Vanjeri Illam (Nampūtiri House) located in Tṛkkandiyūr Village, Tirūr Taluk, Malappuram District, Kerala. These manuscripts have been gathered, organized in chronological order, and copied and edited by M. G. S. Narayanan.

6 In the context of temple duties, the Kovil Nambi, appointed by the regional ruler, was responsible for administering punishments.

7 For details on the special punishment site known as the Poṭṭalākal, see Narayanan M.G.S., 1987, Vanjeri Grandhavari, Introduction, xxvi.

ment Brahmin family and part of the yogam council. His high status required a severe punishment to satisfy those responsible for administering justice. The murderer, Uṅṅāman, was an official appointed by the powerful Zamorin of Calicut, so the Zamorin's permission was needed before any serious action could be taken against him.

These instances illustrate the crime and legal procedures of temple-centered rules. The range of punishments recorded in Kerala's temple records is surprisingly limited. One might expect a society with a reactive and situational criminal procedure to have developed numerous independent methods of punishment for various offenses. However, the temple records of medieval Kerala describe only four types of punishment: corporal (including mutilation and death), fines, banishment, and public censure. There is no evidence of other punishments like imprisonment, forced labor, or torture. Punishments were typically combinations of these main types and often included religious expiations. Among the *Dharmaśāstra* texts, *Vyavahāramālā* holds a significant position in this area. *Vyavahāramālā*, a Keralite *Dharmaśāstra* text, focuses on legal procedures and served as an unofficial constitution of Kerala for a time.

Legal Procedures in *Vyavahāramālā*

The opening verses of the *Vyavahāramālā*, which outline the initiation of legal procedures, state the following: - The king must sit in the Dharmāsana posture, wearing an uthariya as a sacred thread and meditating before the gods, to begin the trial.⁸ The king administers justice by closely observing the smṛtis and the people's needs, similar to how a hunter tracks a wounded animal by following its footprints and blood. This is the proper way to follow Raja dharma.⁹ For *Vyavahāraḥ* (legal proceedings), there should be ten members: the king, the chairman, courtiers, *Dharmaśāstra* experts, an accountant, *Rāyasakkāras*, *Harikkarās*, gold, fire, and water. These ten elements, appointed for *Vyavahāraḥ*, are referred to as *Puruṣāṅga*.

Puruṣāṅgas are represented as follows: the king as the head, the chairman as the face, the courtiers and *Dharmaśāstra* experts as the hands, the accountant and *Rāyasakkāra* as the thighs, gold, fire,

8 धर्मासनमधिष्ठाय संवीतांगासमाहितः । प्रणम्य लोकपालेभ्यः कार्यदर्शनमारभेत् ॥ (*Vyavahāramālā*, 8)

9 यथा नयत्यसृक्पातैर्मृगस्य मृगयुः पदम् । नयेत्तथानुमानेन धर्मस्य नृपतिः पदम् ॥ (*Vyavahāramālā*, 9)

and water as the eyes, and *Harikkāra* as the legs. Witnesses must have directly seen and heard the events in question. Women, infants, and the elderly were exempt from disputes. Judicial proceedings consist of four parts: the plaintiff's declaration, the defendant's written response, the trial of the case by the court, and the judicial decision or judgment. The four parts of judicial proceedings are *Pūrvapakṣa* (plaintiff's declaration), *Uttara* (defendant's response), *Kriyapāda* (trial), and *Nirṇayaḥ* (judgment).

A statement outlining the year, month, fortnight, time, and location of the contested transaction should be provided by the client. The plaintiff's name and address, the names of the ruling kings, the claimed item, the names of ancestors, the injury or loss, the name of the person who received the property, the donor's name, the caste or tribe, physical description, age, the measurements of the items to be recovered, the disputed material and amount, and the plaintiff's caste or tribe should all be mentioned. Ten information should be included in the statement for conflicts involving immovable property: the nation, location, circumstance, caste, name, residence, measurement, field name, names of ancestors, and names of kings.¹⁰

Key subjects addressed in the *Vyavahāramālā* include: The origin, definition, and classification of *Vyavahāra*, the Dharma of the chief justice, the construction of courts, rules about non-suit, the king's authority over punishments, court procedures, methods for resolving disputes between plaintiffs and defendants, trials and disputes based on evidence, the role and evidence of witnesses, victory documents (judgment), ordeals for determining truth, payment and recovery of debts, the definition of interest, pledges and mortgages, suretyship, paying and collecting debts, sale without ownership, partnership law, resumption of gifts, employment law (breach of contract of service), non-payment of wages, disputes between masters and servants, customs according to caste and tribes, non-delivery after sale, buying and selling of goods, boundary disputes, defamation and classification of crimes, assault, theft, crimes of violence, adultery and rape, property partition, gambling and betting, miscellaneous matters.

¹⁰ (Kātyāyanasmṛti, 124-128), Also see Yajñavalkyasmṛti, II.6-8.

Similar to *Manusmṛti* and *Śāṅkarasmṛti*, *Vyavahāramālā* is a text that justified the feudal land system in Kerala, serving as its legal framework. The rulers of the country did not create laws. Instead, they governed according to the rules set by the Brahmins. *Vyavahāramālā* states that if the king lacks time to investigate, a Brahmin should be appointed to handle the legal matters¹¹. If a Brahmin is not available, the responsibility can be given to a *Kṣatriya* or a *Vaiśya*, but never to a *Śūdra*.¹² Additionally, *Vyavahāramālā* warns that if a king appoints *Śūdras* or other lower caste groups to such ruling positions, excluding Brahmins, it will lead to the downfall of his kingdom¹³. The Prakirna Prakarana section of *Vyavahāramālā* emphasizes that the king's primary duty is to uphold the Cāturvarṇya system, which categorizes society into four main varnas: Brahmins, *Kṣatriyas*, *Vaiśyas*, and *Śūdras*. According to *Vyavahāramālā*, the king must protect and enforce the caste dharma of Brahmins and *Kṣatriyas*, ensuring their roles and privileges are maintained. The text does not recognize other groups as significant citizens within its legal and social framework. Essentially, *Vyavahāramālā* outlines a governance system that heavily prioritizes and preserves the status and duties of the Brahmins and *Kṣatriyas*, thereby marginalizing other castes and groups in the kingdom.

Politics played a role in criminal law in two main ways. First, rulers maintained their influence and connections with temple communities by appointing security to guard temple lands. Second, the Brahmin-influenced worldview, which shaped religion, politics, economics, and culture, also impacted legal decisions. This worldview guided the powerful upper castes who controlled the rural temples and their agricultural lands. In conclusion, the societal norms and governance of late medieval Kerala were deeply influenced by the customs and practices established by the *Nampūtiri* Brahmins in the *Dharmaśāstra* texts and the temple records.

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- 12 यत्नं पित्रो न विद्वान् स्यात् क्षत्रियं तत्र योजयेत् । वैश्यं वा धर्मशास्त्रज्ञं शूद्रं यत्नेन वर्जयेत् ॥ (*Vyavahāramālā*, 18)
- 13 द्विजान् विहाय यः पश्येत् कार्याणि वृषलैः सह । तस्य प्रक्षुभ्यते राष्ट्रं बलं कोशं च नश्यति ॥ (*Vyavahāramālā*, 19)

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अद्वैते प्रतिपादितः अख्यातिवादनिरासः

डॉ. सन्तोष सि. आर्¹

प्रबन्धसंग्रहः

अतस्मिन् तत्प्रतिभासः भवति अविद्यायाः सामान्यलक्षणम् । अनित्याशुचिदुःखानात्मसु नित्यशुचिसुखात्मख्यातिः अविद्येति पातञ्जलयोगदर्शने निरूपिता । तेन अनित्ये, अशुचौ, दुःखात्मके तथा जडात्मके च प्रपञ्चे नित्यत्वस्य, शुचित्वस्य, सुखत्वस्य, आत्मत्वस्य च विज्ञप्तिर्भवति अविद्या । इयं अस्मिता राग द्वेष अभिनिवेशसहितस्य संसारपरिणामस्य मूलभूतेति दार्शनिकैः परिकल्प्यते । बौद्धादिषु प्राचीनदर्शनेषु अविद्यायाः निरूपणमस्ति । प्रायेण अर्वाचीने शाङ्करदर्शने च अविद्यायाः प्रतिपादनं प्रभूतं दृश्यते । सत्त्वेन असत्त्वेन सदसत्त्वेन च स्वरूपनिर्णयार्थं अशक्या अनिर्वचनीयरूपा भवति अविद्या इति शङ्कराभिप्रायः । त्रयोदशशतकीयेन अद्वैतचिन्तकेन चित्सुखेन तावत् स्वग्रन्थे तत्त्वप्रदीपिकायां अनादित्वे सति भावरूपं विज्ञाननिरस्यं अज्ञानं इति लक्षितम् । तत्र भ्रमोपादानत्वमित्यज्ञानस्य लक्षणमपि अद्वैतवेदान्तस्य अभिमतमिति प्रतिपादितम् । किन्तु अख्यातिवादिनः प्राभाकरमीमांसकाः भ्रमात्मकमिति ज्ञानमेव नास्तीति प्रतिपादयन्ति । भ्रमस्याभावे तदुपादानत्वस्यापि असम्भवात् भ्रमोपादानत्वलक्षणं अज्ञानं न सिद्ध्यति । प्राभाकरमीमांसायां समेपि प्रत्ययाः यथार्थाः इति सिद्धान्तितः । विगीताः प्रत्ययाः यथार्थाः प्रत्ययत्वात् सम्प्रतिपन्नवत् इत्यनुमानेन तत्र प्रत्ययमात्रस्य याथातथ्यं राद्धान्तितम् । इह प्रबन्धे अद्वैतिभिः विहितः प्राभाकरसिद्धान्तस्यास्य निरासः संग्रथितः ।

मुख्यशब्दाः - भ्रमः, भ्रमोपादानत्वम्, अख्यातिः

आमुखम्

उत्तरकाले बाधितं ज्ञानं भ्रमः इत्युच्यते । रज्जौ सर्पभ्रमः तथा शुक्तौ रजतभ्रमश्च प्रातिभासिकभ्रमः इति लोके प्रसिद्धः । तदभाववति तत्प्रकारकः अयथार्थानुभवः एव भ्रमपदस्यार्थः । भ्रमः, ख्यातिः, अध्यासः, भ्रान्तिः इत्येते पर्यायशब्दाः । पारमार्थिकज्ञानेन अध्यारोपभूतः प्रपञ्चानुभवश्च बाधत इति सोपि भ्रम इति मिथ्या इति अवास्तव इति अद्वैते सन्दर्शितः । संशयविपर्ययतर्कभेदेन त्रिविधः भ्रमात्मकः अयथार्थानुभवः

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शाङ्करवेदान्ते अध्यासः इति व्यवहियते । तदुक्तं ब्रह्मसूत्रस्य शारीरकभाष्योपोद्धाते यथा स्मृतिरूपः परत्र पूर्वदृष्टावभासः । तं केचित् अन्यत्र अन्यधर्माध्यास इति वदन्ति इति । विभ्रमोयं दार्शनिकग्रन्थेषु ख्यातिपदेन प्रोच्यते । विज्ञानवादिबौद्धानां सौत्त्वान्तिकबौद्धानां च आत्मख्यातिः, माध्यमिकशून्यवादिनां असत्ख्यातिः, प्राभाकरमीमांसकानां अख्यातिः, नैयायिकानां अन्यथाख्यातिः, शाङ्करवेदान्तिनां अनिर्वचनीयख्यातिः, रामानुजमतानुगतानां यथार्थख्यातिः, विज्ञानभिक्षुणः सदसदख्यातिः, प्रत्यभिज्ञादार्शनिकानां अपूर्णख्यातिरूपा अख्यातिः, माध्वमतानुयायिनां अभिनवान्यथाख्यातिः, वंशीधरस्वामिनः सत्ख्यातिः इत्येवं प्रतिदर्शनं विभिन्नख्यातयः अथवा भ्रमप्रकाराः सन्ति । सर्वं ज्ञानं यथार्थं इति मन्वानः भवन्ति गुरुप्राभाकारमीमांसकाः । शुकतौ रजतमिति स्थले प्रत्यक्षात्मकं स्मरणात्मकं ज्ञानद्वयं वर्तत इति ते भ्रम नास्तीति विचिन्तयन्ति ।

अयथार्थव्यवहारः

प्राभाकरमते अयथार्थज्ञाननिषेधेपि असंसर्गस्याग्रहनिबन्धनः अयथार्थव्यवहारः - इदं रजतमित्यादि - अभ्युपगतः । तत्र संसर्गाभावस्य अग्रहणात् प्रसञ्जितं संसर्गव्यवहारमात्रं नेदं रजतमिति बाधकबोधेन बाधते । प्राभाकरमतमनुसृत्य इदं रजतमित्यत्र ग्रहणस्मरणात्मकं सामान्यविशेषगोचरं अविज्ञातविवेकं ज्ञानद्वयमस्ति । इदमिति प्रत्यक्षः दोषदूषितनेत्रजन्यतया शौक्तिकविशेषाविषयः तत्सामान्यांशमात्रं अवलम्बते । प्रत्यक्षोयं स्वं स्वविषयञ्च इतरज्ञानान्न विविच्य विज्ञायते । असन्निकृष्टस्य ग्रहणायोगात् रजतप्रतीतिः न प्रत्यक्षः, नाप्यनुमितिः, किन्तु असन्निकृष्टार्थविषया स्मृतिरेव । सा सदृशदर्शनोद्बुद्धसंस्कारा ज्ञायते । स्मृतेरस्याः दुष्टमनोयोगित्वात् स्मरणांशाविषयतया, नेयं स्वं स्वविषयञ्च विवेकेन विजानाति । किन्तु स्मृतिरियं स्वं, स्वविषयं च यत्किञ्चित्प्रत्यक्षेण योजयति ।

शौक्तिकसामान्यविशेषविषययोः प्रत्यक्षस्मरणयोः स्वरूपतः विषयतश्च विरुद्धयोः संसृष्टप्रवृत्तिः परमार्थतः अनुपपन्ना । यस्मादिदमिति ज्ञानं इदमि सामान्यमात्रे, रजतज्ञानं रजताकारविशेषमात्रे च प्रवर्तयतः । अन्योन्यसंसर्गस्याकाङ्क्षयान्वितयोः ग्रहणस्मरणयोः स्वरूपतः विषयतश्च अगृहीतासंसर्गयोः सामान्यविशेषाश्रययोः अव्यवहितोत्पत्ती रजतार्थिपुरुषस्य पुरोवर्तिवस्तुनि भ्रमः (संसृष्टप्रवृत्तिरूपः अयथार्थव्यवहारः) संभवति । व्यवहारस्य मिथ्यात्वेपि द्वेषि ज्ञाने परमार्थे । तस्मात्ते अयथार्थव्यवहारप्रवर्तके इति तयोः नैरन्तर्योत्पत्त्या भ्रमात्मकव्यवहारः सिद्धयतीति प्राभाकरमतम् । मतेस्मिन् समस्तज्ञानानां स्वरूपतः सत्यत्वस्वीकारात् भ्रमज्ञानं नाम किञ्चिन्नास्ति ।

अख्यातिवादस्य दोषः

समस्तज्ञानानां याथार्थ्यसाधकानुमाने प्राभाकरैः विगीतप्रत्ययस्य (भ्रमस्य) स्वीकारात् तेषां स्वसिद्धान्तहानिः अपरिहार्या । अन्यथा प्रत्ययत्वहेतोः आश्रयासिद्धिः स्यात् । उभयदोषवारणाय अयथार्थव्यवहारहेतुः ज्ञानं पक्षश्चेत् न्यायाभिमतेश्वरज्ञाने सर्वव्यवहारहेतुत्वात्, अयथार्थव्यवहारं प्रत्यपि हेतुतया अनुमाने सिद्धसाधनत्वं स्यात् । किञ्चेदं रजतमित्यत्र रजतरूपायथार्थव्यवहारहेतौ इदमंशे अद्वैतिभिः यथार्थत्वाङ्गीकारात्

तदाधारेणापि सिद्धसाधनमिदं अनुमानम् ।

ज्ञानत्वं यथार्थमात्रवृत्ती ज्ञानमात्रवृत्तित्वात् प्रमात्ववद् इति प्राभाकरानुमितौ सिद्धसाधनतादोषः वर्तते । प्राभाकरमते अयथार्थज्ञानाभावेऽपि ज्ञानत्वानधिकरणायथार्थव्यवहारः सम्मतः । साध्यगतमात्रशब्देन अयथार्थवृत्तित्वविवक्षायां, ज्ञानत्वे आयथार्थव्यवहारनिरूपितवृत्तित्वाभावात् सिद्धसाधनत्वमेवायाति । मात्रशब्देन अयथार्थवृत्तित्वानधिकरणत्वं ज्ञानत्वे विवक्षितञ्चेत् दुष्टेन्द्रियाप्रसूतमात्रवृत्तित्वं उपाधिः स्यात् । उपाधौ न च साधनव्यापकता दुष्टसामग्रीप्रसूतग्रहणस्मरणयोरपि ज्ञानत्वस्य वृत्तेः इति प्रत्यगस्वरूपः ।

प्राभाकरोक्तानुमानयोः साध्यगतयथार्थशब्देन सत्त्वं वा असद्भिन्नार्थत्वं वा विवक्षितमिति विवेचनीयम् । प्राभाकरमतानुरोधेन सर्वे प्रत्ययाः सदर्थश्चेत् रज्जुनिष्ठसर्पबोधस्यापि सत्त्वात्, नायं सर्पः इति नहि बाधते । असद्भिन्नार्थत्वे तु सिद्धसाधनत्वं दोषः । यस्मादद्वैते मिथ्यात्वेन असद्भिन्नार्थत्वं अभ्युपगतम् । तत्र मिथ्यार्थः सदसद्द्विलक्षणमस्ति ।

किञ्चायथार्थज्ञानमस्तीति ज्ञानस्य विषयभूतः कश्चनायथार्थप्रत्ययः भवितव्यः । तत्र यथार्थत्वलक्षणसाध्याभावेऽपि प्रत्ययत्वहेतुसद्भावात् अनैकान्तिकत्वमस्ति । असंसर्गाग्रहनिबन्धनसंसृष्टव्यवहारोऽपि व्यवहर्तव्यसंसृष्टपदार्थानां संसर्गज्ञानमन्तरा अनुपपन्नः । व्यवहारो हि व्यवहर्तव्योपलम्बनिबन्धनः । असंसर्गस्य अग्रहणात् (ज्ञानाभावात्) व्यवहारस्तर्हि शब्दप्रामाण्यमेव भज्यते । प्रत्यगस्वरूपेणोक्तम् गामानयेति हि उत्तमवृद्धेनोक्ते मध्यमवृद्धस्य प्रवृत्तिं दृष्ट्वा बालः इत्थं आकलयति । नूनमनेन पदकदम्बकेनैतावदर्थविषयं ज्ञानं संसृष्टप्रवृत्तिहेतुभूतं उत्पादितमिति, पश्चाद् आवापोद्गाराभ्यां पदार्थविशेषेषु पदविशेषसामर्थ्यं गृह्णातीति व्युत्पत्तिरपि पाटी । तदत्रापि संसृष्टव्यवहारस्य संसर्गाग्रहादेवोपपत्तौ संसृष्टपदार्थविषयप्राथमिकज्ञानानुदयात् तन्मार्गसंगतिग्रहायोगात् गतं शब्दप्रामाण्येनेत्यर्थः ।

रजताकारबोधस्थालम्बनं शुक्तिश्चेत् अनुभवविरोधः आपद्यते । तदा अन्याकारबोधस्य अन्यविषयत्वं स्यादिति प्राभाकराक्षेपः अद्वैतिनं प्रत्यस्ति । किन्तु इदमाकारज्ञानमस्ति रजतज्ञानस्य विषयः, न शुक्तिरिति चित्सुखः । ततः इदं रजतमिति सामानाधिकरण्येन प्रतीतिः । केषाञ्चन ज्ञानानां विफलप्रवृत्तिजनकत्वेऽपि ज्ञानान्तरेषु अविश्वासः यद्वन्नास्ति प्राभाकराणां, तथैव ज्ञानस्य कदाचित् विषयव्यभिचारेऽपि समस्तज्ञानेषु न ह्यद्वैतिनामविश्वासः ।

संस्कारमात्रजन्यमिति रजतज्ञानस्य स्मृतिरूपत्वं प्राभाकरैः समर्थितम् । किन्तु मिथ्यार्थस्य स्फुरणकारणं दोषदूषितसामग्रीति चित्सुखः । असन्निहिते इन्द्रियासम्बद्धे च विषये प्रत्यक्षविषयत्वं कथमिति सन्देहः स्यात् । किन्तु रजतसंस्कारसहितं दुष्टमिन्द्रियं रजतं विषयीकरोतीत्यद्वैतपक्षः । ततः रजतप्रतीतेः प्राभाकराभ्युपपगतस्मृतिमात्रता अयुक्ता । नह्ययथार्थज्ञानमस्ति प्राभाकरमते । तत्र नेदं रजतमिति बाधकज्ञानात् असंसर्गाग्रहप्रसञ्जितसंसर्गव्यवहारमात्रं बाधते नायथार्थज्ञानम् । संसर्गव्यवहारकारणं न संसर्गज्ञानं, किन्तु असंसर्गाग्रह इति प्राभाकरः । मायावादिपक्षे संसर्गज्ञानमेव संसर्गव्यवहारं निर्वहति, नासंसर्गाग्रहमात्रम् । अतः असंसर्गाग्रहनिर्वाह्यव्यवहारबाधेन बाधकज्ञाने बाधकता न

व्यवहारनिवृत्तिमात्रेण इति चित्सुखः ।

भ्रमज्ञाने प्रमाणम्

ज्ञाने भ्रमत्वं प्राभाकराणां असम्मतमपि अद्वैतिनां सम्मतमेव । तत एव भ्रमोपादानं अज्ञानमिति वेदान्तिनां अविद्यापरिभाषा । एतच्चक्षुः एतच्चक्षुर्जन्ययथार्थज्ञानातिरिक्तज्ञानजनकं चक्षुष्णात् इन्द्रियत्वाद्वा चक्षुरान्तरवदिन्द्रियान्तरवच्च इत्यनुमानादपि चाक्षुषः भ्रमः सिद्धयतीति, ततः भ्रमसिद्धिरिति चित्सुखः । इन्द्रियाणि प्रमावत् भ्रमामपि जनयन्तीति चित्सुखस्याभिप्रायः । चक्षुरिन्द्रियं यद्यपि रसाद्यतिरिक्तं ज्ञानं नोत्पादयति तथापि चाक्षुषप्रमया सह यत्किञ्चित् ज्ञानमात्रं जनयति । यत्किञ्चित् अन्ततो गत्वा प्रमेतरानुपपत्त्या भ्रममात्रमिति अनुमानतः विज्ञायते ।

भ्रमसाधकानुमानस्य सत्प्रतिपक्षः

चक्षुः चक्षुर्जन्ययथार्थज्ञानजनकत्वे सति अतिरिक्तज्ञानाजनकं इन्द्रियत्वात् घ्राणवदिति भ्रमसाधकानुमानस्य सत्प्रतिपक्षः प्राभाकराणां अस्ति । तेषां सिद्धान्ते न चक्षुः तद्विषयातिरिक्तं ज्ञानान्तरं जनयति, येनायथार्थज्ञानजनकत्वं चक्षुषि स्यात् । चित्सुखस्तावत् प्राभाकराणां सत्प्रतिपक्षे नेत्रजन्ययथार्थज्ञानस्य अजनकत्वं नामोपाधिं सम्पश्यति । घ्राणादीं चाक्षुषप्रमायाः जनकत्वविशिष्टातिरिक्तज्ञानस्याजनकत्वं साध्यं चक्षुषप्रमाअजनकत्वमुपाधिश्च वर्तते इति उपाधावस्ति साध्यव्यापकत्वम् । पक्षेस्मिन् इन्द्रियत्वसत्त्वेपि चक्षुषप्रमाअजनकत्वमुपाधिर्नास्तीति उपाधेः साधनाव्यापकत्वमपि युक्तम् । घ्राणादिषु यद्वत् उपाधिसाध्ययोः अन्वयव्याप्तिः तथा मनसि व्यतिरेकव्याप्तिः (उपाध्यसिद्ध्या साध्यासिद्धिः) विद्यते । न तस्मिन् चाक्षुषप्रमाअजनकत्वं अतिरिक्तज्ञान अजनकत्वं च वादिनां सम्मतम् ।

विवादपदानि (इदं रजतमित्यादि) स्वस्मारितपदार्थान्वयप्रतिपादकानि आकाङ्क्षासन्निधिमत्पदकदम्बकत्वात् गामानय इत्यादिपदकदम्बवत् इत्यनुमानं शब्दविभ्रमे प्रमाणमिति चित्सुखः । तत्र योग्यतावत्त्वं (अर्थाबाधत्वं) इत्युपाधिं प्रदर्शयन्ति प्राभाकराः । तथाहि गामानय इत्यत्र साध्यवति योग्यतावत्त्वात् साध्यव्यापकत्वं, पक्षे हेतुसत्त्वेपि इदमः रजतस्य चाभेदस्य बाधात् साधनाव्यापकत्वं च उपाधौ घटते । किन्तु चित्सुखः योग्यतावत्त्वोपाधौ साध्यस्य समव्याप्यभावात् (यस्मिन्नुपाधौ साध्यस्य व्यापकत्वं व्याप्यत्वं चोभे वर्तते सः समव्याप्तिकः) दोषं प्रदर्शयति । अयमेति पुत्रः राज्ञः पुरुषः अपसार्यताम् इत्यत्र योग्यतावत्त्वेपि अनेनास्मिन्वाक्ये काचनार्थप्रतीतिः- आकाङ्क्षाभावात् स्वस्मारितपदार्थान्वयबोधकत्वं नाम साध्यं नास्तीति न साध्यस्य व्यापकत्वम् । अतः उपाधौ साध्यस्य व्यापकत्वे सति व्याप्यत्वरूपसमव्याप्यभावात् नोपाधित्वमिति चित्सुखः ।

दोषवारणाय प्राभाकरैः आकाङ्क्षासन्निधिमत्वविशिष्टयोग्यतावत्त्वमिति उपाधिं परिष्कृत्य समव्याप्तिः साधिता तथापि उपाधिगतयोग्यतावत्त्वस्य विशेष्यस्य वैयर्थ्यं तिष्ठत्येव । उभयवाद्यभिमतधिकरणे यत्र आकाङ्क्षासन्निधिमत्त्वेपि योग्यताभावमात्रेण न पदार्थान्वयप्रतीतिः, तत्र साध्यव्याप्तिसिद्धये उपाधौ योग्यतावत्त्वाख्यविशेष्यांशः उपादेयः ।

किन्तु अयोग्यवत् (अयोग्यार्थविषयकं) आकाङ्क्षादिविशिष्टं च सर्वं पदं पक्षे अन्तर्भवति । सन्दिग्धसाध्यवानस्ति पक्षः । नच पक्षे साध्याभावः (पदार्थान्वयप्रतिपादकत्वाभावः) निर्णीतः । पक्षभिन्नं साध्याभावस्य अधिकरणं च नास्ति । अतः आकाङ्क्षादिविशिष्टयोग्यता वत्त्वस्य पक्षमालव्यावर्तकतया पक्षेतरत्वमिति उपाधौ उपाधित्वं अनुपपन्नम् ।

योग्यतावत्त्वे साध्यस्य विषमव्याप्तिः (यस्मिन्नुपाधौ साध्यस्य व्यापकत्वमात्रं, सः विषमव्याप्तिकः) प्राभाकरेण प्रदर्शिता । यस्मात् स्वस्मारितान्वयप्रतिपादकत्ववदधिकरणे योग्यतावत्त्वमस्ति । साधनाव्यापकत्वं च पूर्वं प्रदर्शितम् । इत्थं विषमव्याप्त्या योग्यतावत्त्वे उपाधित्वं उपपद्यते इति प्राभाकरः । नेतस्मादपि उपाधेः व्यतिरेकव्याप्तिः साध्ये सिद्ध्यतीति चित्सुखः । यदयोग्यार्थकं पदं तन्न अन्वितार्थजनकं भवतीति व्यतिरेकव्याप्युपसंहाराय दृष्टान्तः नास्ति । यतो हि व्यतिरेकव्याप्यधिकरणं सर्वं पक्षकोटौ अन्तर्भवति ।

विवादपदानि (इदं रजतमित्यादि) स्वस्मारितार्थान्वयप्रमितिजनकानि आकाङ्क्षासन्निधिमत्पदत्वात् , गामानयेतिपदवत् इति आभाससमानयोगक्षेमत्वं अपि पूर्वोक्तानुमाने नास्ति, येन आभासदोषः अद्वैतिनामनुमाने स्यात् । आभासानुमानं नेदं रजतमित्यादि बाधकज्ञानेन बाधते । बाधितरजतविषयतया इदं रजतमिति ज्ञानं अप्रमास्ति । ततः अप्रमाजनकं विवादपदं बाधितमस्ति । वेदान्तिभिः स्वस्मारितार्थबोधकत्वेन साध्येन प्रतीतिमालजनकत्वं विवक्षितम् । शशविषाणादिपदवत् इदं रजतमिति पदेपि (योग्यत्वा भाववदाकाङ्क्षासन्निधिवति) प्रतीतिजनकत्वं सम्मतम् । अत्यन्तासत्यपि ज्ञानं अर्थे शब्दः करोति हीति कुमारिलभट्टस्य अभिप्रायः । शशविषाणं खपुष्पं इत्याद्यसत्यर्थे अत्यन्तायोग्ये अपि आकाङ्क्षासन्निधिमाञ्छब्दो ज्ञानं करोतीति भट्टवार्तिकार्थः ।

योग्यतारहितस्य आकाङ्क्षासन्निधिमत्तश्च पदस्य प्रतीतिजनकत्वं न प्राभाकरैरभ्युपगत्तम् । तदानीं इतरैः ज्ञातेपि वस्तुनि प्राभाकराणां ज्ञानाभावात् कथाप्रवृत्तिः अनुपपन्ना । ततस्तु अज्ञानं नाम निग्रहस्थानं आपद्यते । तदा विप्रतिपत्तिनिरासोपि अनुपपन्नः स्यात् ।

सहायकग्रन्थाः

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जगद्गुरुमानन्दाचार्यः

अनिमेषरायः¹

प्रबन्धसारः

भारतीयाध्यात्मिकनभोमण्डले दर्शनमिति पदं मध्याह्नमार्तण्डस्येव सुप्राचीनकालादेव सर्वदा प्रकाशमानं परिदृश्यते। प्रमाणाधारेण दृश्यमानानाम् अनुभूयमानानां ज्ञायमानानां वा वस्तूनां विषये स्वस्वमतमेव दर्शनम् इत्युच्यते। अत्र विशिष्टाद्वैतदर्शनविषये विशेषतया आलोचितं वर्तते, यस्य मुख्याचार्यत्वेन श्री रामानुजाचार्यः वर्णितो विद्यते। आचार्यस्य देशः कालः कृतयश्च प्रतिपादितः। श्रीरामानन्दस्वामिनः मतानुसारं भगवान् श्रीरामः पूर्णपरब्रह्म-परमेश्वरः अखण्डाद्वयाद्वितीयः परमात्मा अनाद्यनन्तः नित्यः विभुः सच्चिदानन्दश्च वर्तते। जीवात्मा तु अस्यैव परब्रह्मणः श्रीरामस्य अंशभूतः इति उच्यते। अतः जीवोऽपि सच्चिदानन्दरूपः त्रिगुणातीतः नित्यशुद्धबुद्धमुक्तस्वभाववान् भवति। एष एव जीवः अज्ञाने नष्टे सति यदा श्रीरामचरणाश्रये स्वं सम्पूर्णरूपेण समर्पयति तदा श्रीभगवत्कृपाबलेन तस्य आत्मोपलब्धिः सञ्जायते। तदात्मोपलब्ध्या च मोक्षरूपपरमपुरुषार्थसिद्धिः भवति। श्रीरामानन्दाचार्यानुसारं, - संसाररूपमहासागरं सन्तर्तुं भक्तिरेव उत्तमसेतुः भवति। ज्ञानकर्ममार्गौ तु भक्तिमार्गसहायकौ भवतः। दर्शनेऽस्मिन् भक्तिस्वरूपम् उक्तं, - “ब्रह्मणः सर्वस्वामिनः रामस्य अनवच्छिन्ना स्मृतिः भक्तिरिति” (श्रीरामानन्दसिद्धान्तसारः ३४)। किञ्च भक्तिरेव निःसन्दिग्धतया सुनिश्चिता मोक्षप्रदायिनी इति उच्यते “भक्तिश्चाथ प्रपत्तिश्च ज्ञानावस्थे हि मुक्तिदे” इत्यादिसिद्धान्तसारश्लोकात् (श्रीरामानन्दसिद्धान्तसारः १०८)।

मुख्यपदानि- जीवनपरिचयः, शिष्यपरम्परा, कृतयः, आनन्दभाष्यम्, श्रीसम्प्रदायः/ रामानन्दसम्प्रदायः, विशिष्टाद्वैतदर्शनम्, भक्तिः।

उपोद्घातः

भारतवर्षस्य पूण्यभूम्याम् अस्यां कालचक्रेण अद्वैतद्वैतविशिष्टाद्वैतादीनि नैकानि दर्शनानि आविर्भूतानि निरूपितानि च तत्तद्दर्शनाचार्यैः। एवं भारतीयास्तिकदर्शनेषु विशेषतया वेदान्तदर्शनेषु अन्तर्भूतं सुप्रसिद्धमेकं दर्शनं भवति विशिष्टाद्वैतदर्शनं यत् न केवलं कल्पनया लिखितम् अपि तु आचार्याणाम् अध्यात्मसाधकानाञ्च अनुभवप्रतिष्ठितं

1 शोधच्छात्रः, संस्कृतदर्शनविभागः, श्रीशंकराचार्यसंस्कृतविश्वविद्यालयः

सत् वर्तते। विशिष्टञ्च विशिष्टञ्च विशिष्टे, विशिष्टयोः अद्वैतम् विशिष्टाद्वैतम् इति ब्रह्मसूत्रानन्दभाष्योक्तवचनात् (१.१.२)(सिंहासनासीन जी २५)। विशिष्टाद्वैतवेदान्तस्य अस्य प्रमुखेषु आचार्येषु जगद्गुरुरामानन्दस्वामिनः विशिष्टवर्य्याः आसन्। “रामानन्दो रामरूपो राममन्त्रार्थवित्कविः। राममन्त्रप्रदो रम्यो राममन्त्ररतः प्रभूः॥”(रसिकराम. “श्रीमद्रामानन्दाचार्यः”) इत्यादिअगस्त्यसंहितावचनं श्रीरामानन्दाचार्यणां श्रेष्ठत्वं भजते। इमे आचार्याः रामावतसम्प्रदायस्य रामानन्दीसम्प्रदायस्य वा प्रवर्तकाः आसन्। दर्शनस्य श्रुतिस्मृतिन्यायप्रमाणमूलत्वात् आचार्यैः दशोपनिषत् ब्रह्मसूत्रं श्रीमद्भगवद्गीतां च अधिकृत्य भाष्यरूपेण स्वमतं प्रतिष्ठापितं यत्, आनन्दभाष्यम् इति नाम्ना पण्डितजनैः आद्रितं वर्तते। प्रस्थानत्रयं विहाय श्रीरामानन्दाचार्यविरचिताः नैके भगवद्विषयवीजभूताः ग्रन्थाः समुपलभ्यते यत्र विशिष्टाद्वैतवेदान्तसिद्धान्तस्य स्पष्टतया अवतरणं दरिदृश्यते।

जीवनपरिचयः

ब्रह्मसूत्रानन्दभाष्यस्य तत्त्वप्रकाशिकाख्यभूमिकायां श्रीरघुवरदासस्वामिना रामानन्दाचार्यस्य जन्मवृत्तान्तविषये वैश्वानरागस्त्यादिसंहिताश्लोकः उद्धृतः दृश्यते (श्रीरघुवराचार्य ६)। “माघे च कृष्णसप्तम्यां चित्तानक्षत्रसंयुते। कुम्भलग्ने सिद्धियोगे सुसप्तदण्डगे रवौ” ॥ इति वैश्वानरसंहितायाः उपर्युक्तप्रसिद्धवचनात् इदम् स्पष्टतया अवगम्यते यत्, श्रीरामानन्दाचार्यस्य रामावताररूपेण उत्तरभारतस्थिते प्रयागप्रदेशे माघकृष्णसप्तमीतिथौ चित्तानक्षत्रे कुम्भलग्ने कान्यकुब्जब्राह्मणवंशे जन्म अभवत्। कालस्तु षड्षष्ट्यधिकद्वादशशतकमारभ्य षड्पञ्चाशदुत्तरतयोदशशतकान्तमति (वदरीनारायण श्रीवास्तव ६९) अर्थात् ईशवीयत्रयोदशशताब्दीति निर्दिश्यते। शुक्लयजुर्वेदान्तर्गतस्य वसिष्ठगोत्रजस्य अस्याचार्यस्य पिता पुण्यसदनशर्मा माता श्रीमती सुशीला देवी च आसीत्। यद्यपि कैश्चित् पण्डितैः आचार्यस्य जन्मस्थानं काशी इति मन्यते। तथापि अगस्त्यसंहितानुसारं रामानन्दानुयायिभिः प्रयागप्रदेश एव जन्मस्थानरूपेण सुनिश्चीयते। केषाञ्चित् मतानुसारम् आचार्यस्य पूर्वपरिचयः रामदत्तो रामभारती इत्यादिनाम्ना ज्ञायते। परन्तु वैष्णवकबीरः, रामानन्दायनः, द्वादशभागवतम् इत्यादिरामानन्दसम्प्रदायान्तर्गतग्रन्थेषु आचार्यस्य पूर्वपरिचयः रामानन्देति नाम्ना एव प्राप्यते। श्रीरामानन्दाचार्यस्य गुरुः श्रीराघवानन्दः इत्युच्यते, यः श्रीसम्प्रदायस्य एकविंशतितमाचार्यरूपेण प्रसिद्धोऽभूत्। काशीप्रदेशस्थिते श्रीसम्प्रदायस्य श्रीमठे अयमाचार्यैः वेदान्तस्य विशिष्टाध्ययनं समाप्य स्वगुरोः समक्षे तत्त्वज्ञानं साक्षात् कृतमासीत्। आचार्यरामचन्द्रशुक्लैः स्वकीये “हिन्दी साहित्य का इतिहास” इति ग्रन्थे उल्लिखितं यत्, श्रीरामानन्दाचार्यः शाङ्करज्योतिर्मठे ब्रह्मचारीरूपेण निवसन् वेदान्ताध्ययनं कृतवान्। किञ्च शास्त्रार्थद्वारा मुस्लिम-जैन-बौद्ध-योग-अद्वैतादिसम्प्रदायानां सिद्धान्तं निराकृत्य बहुवारं तान् परास्तम् अकरोत्। द्वात्रिंशदधिकपञ्चदशमविक्रंसंवत्सरे श्रीरामानन्दाचार्यः इमं पाञ्चभौतिकशरीरं परित्यज्य अमृतत्वम् अप्राप्नोत्। एवं रामानन्दाचार्यः षट्सप्तत्यधिकैकशतवर्षं दीर्घायुम् अलभत (श्रीरागिनीसिंह ७)।

गुरुशिष्यपरम्परा

डःमनोजतिवारीमहोदयेन स्वस्य शोधप्रवन्धे श्रीरामानन्दाचार्याणां गुरुपरम्पराविषये आलोचनावसरे स्वामीरामेश्वरानन्दाचार्याणां मतं प्रतिपादितम्। तल्लोच्यते, स्वामीरामेश्वरानन्दाचार्येण श्रीरामानन्दसम्प्रदायाचार्यदर्शननामके स्वग्रन्थे श्रीरामानन्दाचार्यस्य गुरुपरम्परा वर्णिता। तत्र क्रमेण गुरुपरम्परा एवमुच्यते,- १) श्रीरामः २)श्रीसीता ३)श्रीहनुमान् ४)श्रीब्रह्मा ५)श्रीवशिष्ठः ६)श्रीपराशरः ७)श्रीव्यासः ८)शुकदेवः ९)श्रीपुरुषोत्तमः १०)श्रीगङ्गाधरः ११)सदानन्दः १२)रामेश्वरानन्दः १३)श्रीद्वारानन्दः १४)श्रीदेवानन्दः १५)श्रीश्यामानन्दः १६)श्रीश्रुतानन्दः १७)श्रीचिदानन्दः १८)श्रीपूर्णानन्दः १९)श्रीश्रियानन्दः २०)श्रीहर्यानन्दः २१)श्रीराघवानन्दः २२)जगद्गुरुरामानन्दः इति। श्रीनाभादासविरचितभक्तमालग्रन्थानुसारं रामानन्दुचार्यस्य द्वादश शिष्याः आसन्(श्रीगोविन्दशर्मा २६२)। ते च, १)श्रीअनन्तानन्दाचार्य २)श्रीसुरसुरानन्दजी ३)श्रीसुखानन्दजी ४)श्रीनरहरियानन्दजी ५)श्रीयोगानन्दजी ६)श्रीपीपाजी ७) श्रीकबीरदासजी ८)श्रीभावानन्दजी ९)श्रीसेनजी १०)श्रीधन्वाजी ११)श्रीगालवानन्दजी १२) श्रीरमादास इति(मनोजतिवारी ३०)।

श्रीसम्प्रदायः/रामानन्दसम्प्रदायः

श्री इत्यत्र अर्थद्वयं विद्यते। तत्र श्री इत्यस्य माता सीता इत्यर्थो गृह्यते रामानन्दसम्प्रदाये। किञ्च लक्ष्मी इत्यर्थो गृह्यते रामानुजसम्प्रदाये। अनयोः उभयोरपि वादः विशिष्टाद्वैतवाद इत्युच्यते। रामानन्दीयश्रीसम्प्रदायस्य धेयः ज्ञेयश्च वर्तते मर्यादापुरुषोत्तमः श्रीरामः, माता जानकी, एवम् अनयोः दिव्यचरित्रं महर्षिबाल्मीकिना उपनिबद्धं श्रीमद्-रामायणम् किञ्च तुलसीदासविरचितं श्रीमद्रामचरितमानसम् इति। अस्मिन् सम्प्रदाये सायुज्यरूपा मुक्तिः स्वीकृता। अर्थात् श्रीसीतारामयोः परमधामे दासरूपेण नित्यनिवासः मुक्तिपदवाच्यः इत्युच्यते। एवञ्च मुक्त्यर्थं मोक्षसिद्धयर्थं वा भक्तिः सर्वोत्तमसाधनत्वेन सर्वथा सुनिश्चीयते।

आचार्यप्रणीतकृतयः

श्रीरामानन्दाचार्यैः प्रस्थानत्रयम् अधिकृत्य स्वमतं भाष्यरूपेण उपस्थापितं, यत् आनन्दभाष्यम् इति उच्यते। तत्र ईशकेनकठप्रश्नमुडकमाण्डूक्यतैत्तिरीयैतरेय-छान्दोग्यबृहदारण्यकश्वेताश्वतराणाम् परेषां दुर्व्याख्यानेन मालिन्यमुपगतानां विशुद्धार्थप्रकाशनपरम् एकादशोपनिषदाम् आनन्दभाष्यं श्रुतिप्रस्थानं, श्रुतिसूत्रानुसारिसुगमव्याख्यानसमन्वितं परभक्तिप्रकाशनपरं गीतानन्दभाष्यम् स्मृतिप्रस्थानं, ब्रह्मसूत्रानन्दभाष्यं न्यायप्रस्थानञ्च श्रीवैष्णवानां परमनिःश्रेयसनिधानं निखिलवेदान्तार्थप्रकाशनपरम् इत्युच्यते। आनन्दभाष्यम् इति नाम्नः बीजं किमिति चेत्, आनन्दभाष्ये तत्त्वप्रकाशिकाख्यायां भूमिकायां ग्रन्थकारैः उक्तं,- “ब्रह्मणः आनन्दगुणसारत्वादनन्दपदेनव्यपदेशो दृश्यते “तद्गुणसारत्वात्तुतद्ग्रन्थपदेशः प्राज्ञवत्” (ब्रह्मसूत्रम् २/३/३०) इत्यादि पारमर्षानुशासनात्” इति (श्रीरघुवराचार्य १३)। एतान् विहाय श्रीरामानन्दाचार्यविरचितं भगवदुपासना

हस्यकालक्षेपाद्यभिधायकः श्रीवैष्णवैरनुष्ठेयार्थस्योपदेशकः श्रीवैष्णवमताब्जभास्कर इति। ग्रन्थोऽयं रामानन्दाचार्यस्य धार्मिकसिद्धान्तानां प्रामाणिकः आकरः वर्तते यस्य मुख्यमुद्देश्यमासीत् श्रीवैष्णवसम्प्रदायस्य उपसनारहस्यस्य च उन्मोचनम्। किञ्च परमपुरुषश्रीरामस्य अर्चनादिप्रकारस्य बोधिका श्रीरामार्चनपद्धति इति ग्रन्थः यस्मिन् षोडशोपचारोपसनादिपद्धतिः आचार्येण निहिता दृश्यते। ग्रन्थद्वयमपि संस्कृतभाषायां समुपलभ्यते यत्र विशिष्टाद्वैतवेदान्तसिद्धान्तस्य स्पष्टतया प्रतिफलनं दरिदृश्यते।

विशिष्टाद्वैतदर्शनम्

“विशिष्टञ्च विशिष्टञ्च विशिष्टे, विशिष्टयोः अद्वैतं विशिष्टाद्वैतम्” इति ब्रह्मसूत्रान् दभाष्योक्तवचनात्। अर्थात् सूक्ष्मचिदचिद्विशिष्टं कारणं ब्रह्म, स्थूलचिदचिद्विशिष्टं कार्यब्रह्म इत्यनयोः अद्वैतम् अभेदः इति। अस्मिन् दर्शने सगुणब्रह्मण एव सर्वदा स्वीकारः न तु निर्विशेषब्रह्मणः। उच्यते यत्, उपनिषत्सु निर्गुणत्वेन ब्रह्मणः वर्णनं प्राकृतगुणानाम् अभावात्। श्रीरामानन्दाचार्यस्य मतानुसारं भगवान् पूर्णपरब्रह्म-परमेश्वरः परमात्मा अनाद्यनन्तः नित्यः विभुः सच्चिदानन्दश्च अखण्डाद्ब्रह्माद्वितीयः श्रीरामो वर्तते। उक्तञ्च ब्रह्मसूत्रानन्दभाष्ये,- “ब्रह्मशब्दश्च महापुरुषादिपदवेदनीयनिरस्त-निखिलदोषमनवधिकातिशया असंख्येयकल्याणगुणगणं भगवन्तं श्रीराममेवाह सामान्यवाचकानां पदानां विशेषे पर्यवसानात्” इति(श्रीरघुवराचार्य१.१.१/४)। बृहदारण्यकोपनिषदि “आत्मैवेदमग्र आसीत् पुरुषविधः” (श्रीरामपदार्थदास ४७) इत्यादि मन्त्रभाष्ये आत्मशब्देन साकेताधिपतेः श्रीरामस्यैव द्योतकत्वम् उच्यते। अत्र आत्मशब्दः जीवे प्रयुज्यमानोऽपि परमेश्वरस्यैव वाचकः भवति बहुषु स्थलेषु पुरुषशब्दस्य परमेश्वरे प्रयोगदर्शनात्। तदुक्तं तत्रैव भाष्ये,- “यद्यप्यन्यत्रात्मशब्दस्य जीवपरकत्वं दृष्टं तथापि आत्मैवेदमग्रेत्यादिवाक्यं कारणवाक्यतया साकेताधिपतिद्योतकत्वमेव” इति(श्रीरामपदार्थदास ४८)। तथा च “श्रीरामाख्यं परब्रह्म सदाभ्यायान्तदीपितम्। स्वभक्तैर्ध्वंयमाप्यञ्च वन्दे दिव्यगुणाकरम्।”(ब्रह्मसूत्रानन्दभाष्यमङ्गलश्लोकः) इति आचार्यकृतानन्दभाष्योक्तमङ्गलाचरणादेव दर्शनस्यास्य ब्रह्मतत्त्वम् अनायासेन अवगन्तुं शक्यमस्माभिः। एवञ्च सर्वेश्वरश्रीरामेण सह पराशक्तेः भगवत्याः सर्वेश्वरीश्रीसीतामातुरपि ग्रहणमत्र परिदृश्यते। एवं सीतारामयोः युगलरूपस्य वन्दना विधीयते। किञ्च कल्याणगुणधामः दिव्यदेहो राघवः चिदचिद्देहवैशिष्ट्याद् विशिष्टं ब्रह्म इत्युच्यते “स सूक्ष्म चिदचिद्देहवैशिष्टः परमात्मा” इत्यादि-ऐतरेयोपनिषदानन्दभाष्योक्तवचनात् (श्रीरामपदार्थदास.ऐतरेय१८६)। अपि च निराकारोपि साकारः निर्गुणोपि सगुणः सच्चिदानन्दरूपः सर्वदोषविवर्जितः सर्वाराध्यश्च श्रीरामः कारणं ब्रह्मेति कथ्यते “स एव प्रलये रामः कारणं ब्रह्म कथ्यते। स जगद्रूपतां प्राप्तः कार्यब्रह्मेति उच्यते” इत्यादिवचनात्(श्रीरामानन्दसिद्धान्तसारः ७)। एवं सर्वेश्वरमहेश्वरजगदीश्वरपरमपुरुषपरमात्मापरब्रह्मसर्वान्तर्त्तामीसर्वनियामकसर्वाधिष्ठातासर्वप्रेरकः कर्मसंयोजकः सिद्धिदायकः सकलफलदायकः पुरुषपदवाच्यः श्रीरामः समस्तभूतान्तरात्मा इत्याचक्षते। अयं सर्वसर्जकश्रीसाकेताधिपतिः

सर्वशक्तिसम्पन्नः श्रीरामः सर्वानेव बाह्यार्थान् समुत्पादयति इत्यतः श्रीरामाख्यं परब्रह्म चराचरस्य अस्य जगतः कारणम् इत्युच्यते “ रामं विना न किञ्चिद्वि वर्तते स चराचरम् ” इत्याचार्योक्तेः (श्रीरामपदार्थदास ३/२८) । एवं प्रकारेण भगवन्तं श्रीरामं ज्ञात्वा तदात्मोपलब्ध्या च मोक्षरूपपरमपुरुषार्थसिद्धिः भवति । उक्तञ्च, - “ राममभ्यर्च्य दृष्ट्वा च नत्वा स्तुत्वाऽथवा जनः । भवाम्बुधिं स्वयं तीर्त्वा स्वकुलं तारयत्यपि ” इति रामानन्दसिद्धान्तसारग्रन्थे (श्रीरामानन्दसिद्धान्तसारः १३५) । किन्तु मोक्षसिद्धौ सत्यां जीवात्मनः परमात्मनि न विलयः अपि तु तस्य मुक्तात्मनः सत्यलोकगोलोकवैकुण्ठधामादिलोकप्राप्तिर्भवतीति ।

ज्ञानकर्मभक्तियोगेषु त्रिषु मार्गेषु विशिष्टाद्वैतवेदान्ते तावत् मोक्षसिद्धयर्थं भगवद्भ्रामप्राप्त्यर्थं भक्तिः सर्वोत्तमसाधनत्वेन सर्वथा सुनिश्चीयते । तदुक्तं श्रीरामानन्दाचार्येण ब्रह्मसूत्रानन्दभाष्ये “ ध्यानापोषणवेदनादिशब्दवाच्यया परमपुरुषैकचिन्तनलक्षणया अनन्यभक्त्या प्रसन्नेन परमपुरुषेण अर्चिरादिना ब्रह्मालोकं नीतस्य मुक्तस्यानावृत्तिरेव “ इति (श्रीरघुवराचार्य ४३०) । श्रीरामानन्दाचार्यमतानुसारं भक्तिस्वरूपम् एवम् उच्यते, - “ ब्रह्मणः सर्वस्वामिनः रामस्य अनवच्छिन्ना स्मृतिः भक्तिरिति “ (श्रीरामानन्दसिद्धान्तसारः ३३) अर्थात् भगवत्साक्षात्काररूपा ध्रुवा स्मृतिरेव भक्तिशब्देन अभिधीयते । सा च भक्तिः परमप्रेयो भगवदितरवैतृष्यपूर्वकपरमपुरुषानुरागरूपो ज्ञानविशेष एव इति । एवं भक्तिरेव निःसन्दिग्धतया सुनिश्चिता मोक्षप्रदायिनी इति उच्यते “ भक्तिश्चाथ प्रपत्तिश्च ज्ञानावस्थे हि मुक्तिदे “ इत्यादिसिद्धान्तसारश्लोकात् (श्रीरामानन्दसिद्धान्तसारः १०४) ।

उपसंहारः

भारतीयवैष्णवपरम्परायां प्रस्थानत्रय्याम् प्रतिष्ठितस्य विशिष्टाद्वैतवेदान्तस्य सम्पोषकसंवर्द्धकरूपेण श्रीरामानन्दाचार्याणां कीदृशं महत्त्वपूर्णं योगदानम् आसीत् इति स्पष्टमेव अवगन्तुं शक्यते अस्माभिः । उपर्युक्तपर्यालोचनद्वारा इदं वक्तुं शक्यं यत्, - दर्शनेऽस्मिन् भक्तेः दार्शनिकतत्त्वानां च मध्ये एकं सामञ्जस्यं प्रतिफलति, यत् विशिष्टाद्वैतवेदान्तसिद्धान्तानां लोककल्याणकारीव्यवहारिकं जीवनदर्शनं प्रस्तोतयति । किञ्च रामोपासना रामभक्तेश्च सुव्यवस्थितं श्रुतिस्मृतिन्यायसहकृतं तत्त्वं अस्मिन्नेव दर्शने समुपलभ्यते यत् भक्तिमार्गानुसारिणां आध्यात्मिकचिन्तनक्षेत्रं सर्वथा संवर्द्धयति संरक्षयति च ।

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चरकसंहितान्तर्गतं पदार्थविज्ञानम्

डा. एस्. त्यागराजन्¹

पत्रसारः

लोकानां श्रेयसः साधनतया हितावहेषु विविधेषु ज्ञानविज्ञानप्रभेदेषु सर्वोपजीव्यं यद्विज्ञानरत्नं तदेव आयुर्विज्ञानम् इत्युच्यते। एतदीयं विज्ञानं न केवलं स्वस्य एकद्वयव्यक्तिमात्रस्य वा उपकृतये, अपि तु कुटुम्बस्य समाजस्य समस्तलोकस्यापि उपकृतये समुन्नतये च भवति इत्यवश्यं विज्ञेयं शरीरिभिः, उपदेष्टव्यञ्च विज्ञातृभिः। तस्माद्विशेषतः अर्थवान् अस्य अवबोधः उपदेशश्च। आयुर्वेदोपदेशेषु विधेयः परमादरः इत्युक्तरीत्या आयुर्वेदस्य उपदेशेषु परमादरः विधेयः। आयुर्बोधकेषु निखिलेषु ग्रन्थेषु लोके त्रयो ग्रन्थाः मुख्यतमाः मन्यन्ते। तदुच्यते -

चरकः सुश्रुतश्चैव वाग्भटञ्च तथाऽपरः।

मुख्याश्च संहिता वाच्यास्ति एव युगे युगे ॥ (हारीतसंहिता, परिशिष्टाध्यायः - ६,७)
अलोच्यमानेषु चरकसंहितासुश्रुतसंहितावाग्भटीयेषु प्राचीनतमा वर्तते चरकसंहिता यस्यां न केवलं वैद्यकीयविषयाः चर्चिताः अपि च तत्त्वज्ञानसंबद्धविचाराः, पदार्थविज्ञानसंबद्धविचाराश्च चर्चिताः वर्तन्ते याश्च चार्चाः सूक्ष्मेक्षिकदृष्ट्यालोचनेनैव प्राप्तुं शक्याः। तद्रीत्या चरकसंहितायां पदार्थविज्ञानमपि चरकाचार्येण प्रतिपादितं दृश्यते। तत्र सूत्रनिदानादिरूपेषु अष्टविधस्थानेषु सूत्रस्थाने प्रथमाध्याये पदार्थज्ञानमिदं सुष्ठु विचारितं वर्तते। अत्र हि द्रव्यगुणकर्मसामान्यविशेषसमवायादिपदार्थानां लक्षणं सप्रमाणं निरूपितं वर्तते चरकाचार्येण। तानि लक्षणानि, इतरशास्त्रेषु प्रतिपादितैः पदार्थलक्षणैः सह एषां तुलना इत्येवमादयो विषयाः पत्रेऽस्मिन् विचारिताः ॥

उपोद्घातः

लोकानां श्रेयसः साधनतया हितावहेषु विविधेषु ज्ञानविज्ञानप्रभेदेषु सर्वोपजीव्यं यद्विज्ञानरत्नं तदेव आयुर्विज्ञानम् इत्युच्यते। एतदीयं विज्ञानं न केवलं स्वस्य एकद्वयव्यक्तिमात्रस्य वा उपकृतये, अपि तु कुटुम्बस्य समाजस्य समस्तलोकस्यापि उपकृतये समुन्नतये च भवति इति अवश्यं विज्ञेयं शरीरिभिः, उपदेष्टव्यञ्च विज्ञातृभिः। तस्माद्विशेषतः

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अर्थवान् अस्यावबोधः उपदेशश्च । आयुर्वेदोपदेशेषु विधेयः परमादरः इत्युक्तरीत्या आयुर्वेदस्य उपदेशेषु परमादरः विधेयः । कुत इति चेदेतदेव धर्मार्थकाममौक्षरूपस्य पुरुषार्थचतुष्टयस्य आधारभूतस्य मनुष्यस्य आरोग्यतायाः प्राप्तये तथा आयुषः रक्षायै विषयान् उपदशति ।

कायवाग्बुद्धिविषया ये मलाः समुपस्थिताः ।

चिकित्सालक्षणाध्यात्मशास्त्रैस्तेषां विशुद्धयः ॥ (वाक्यपदीयम् १.१७४)

इत्युक्तन्युसारं संस्कृतजगति विद्वद्भिः वाचः शुद्धये व्याकरणाध्ययनं भूरिशः क्रियते । एवमेव कायशुद्धयर्थं चिकित्साशास्त्रम्, बुद्धिशुद्धयर्थं च अध्यात्मशास्त्रमित्येवं कायवाग्बुद्धिविशुद्धिविषये बहुशोऽध्ययनं सङ्गतमेव । अतः सर्वैरपि स्वास्थ्यसंरक्षणाय आयुर्वेदस्य लेशांशो वा पठनीयः एव इति चिन्त्यते । आयुर्बोधकेषु निखिलेषु ग्रन्थेषु लोके लयो ग्रन्थाः मुख्यतमाः मन्यन्ते । तदुच्यते -

चरकः सुश्रुतश्चैव वाग्भटञ्च तथाऽपरः ।

मुख्याश्च संहिता वाच्यास्तिष्ठ एव युगे युगे ॥ (हारीतसंहिता, परिशिष्टाध्यायः - ६,७)

अत्रोच्यमानेषु चरकसंहितासुश्रुतसंहितावाग्भटीयेषु प्राचीनतमा वर्तते चरकसंहिता यस्यां न केवलं वैद्यकीयविषयाः चर्चिताः अपि च तत्त्वज्ञानसंबद्धविचाराः, पदार्थविज्ञानसंबद्धविचाराश्च चर्चिताः वर्तन्ते याश्च चार्चाः सूक्ष्मेक्षिकदृष्ट्या आलोच्यते कृते एव ज्ञातुं शक्याः । तद्रीत्या चरकसंहितायां पदार्थविज्ञानमपि चरकाचार्येण प्रतिपादितं दृश्यते । तत्र सूत्रनिदानादिषु अष्टविधस्थानेषु सूत्रस्थाने प्रथमाध्याये पदार्थज्ञानमिदं सुष्ठु विचारितं वर्तते । अत्र हि द्रव्यगुणकर्मसामान्यविशेषसमवायादीनां षण्णां भावपदार्थानां लक्षणं सप्रमाणं निरूपितं वर्तते चरकाचार्येण ।

षट् पदार्थाः

पदस्य अर्थः पदार्थः इति व्युत्पत्त्या सर्वसम्मतम् अभिधेयत्वं पदार्थसामान्यलक्षणम् । पदार्थचर्चेयं दार्शनिकैः बहुधा विहिता वर्तते स्वग्रन्थेषु । तत्र न्यायवैशेषिकशास्त्रे पदार्थविज्ञानप्रतिपादने मुख्ये वर्तते । तत्र वैशेषिकदर्शने प्रसिद्धतया षडेव पदार्थाः अङ्गीकृताः । न्यायमते तु सप्तपदार्थाः । द्रव्य-गुण-कर्म-सामान्य-विशेष-समवायाः षट् पदार्थाः इति वैशेषिकमतम् । एभिः सह अभावस्यापि पदार्थत्वेन सप्त पदार्थाः अङ्गीकृताः नैयायिकैः । एवंरीत्या महर्षिणा चरकेनापि स्वीये आयुर्विषयप्रतिपादिके चरकसंहिताख्ये ग्रन्थे पदार्थविषये प्रतिपादितं वर्तते ।

ऋषयश्च भरद्वाजाज्जगृहस्तं प्रजाहितम् । दीर्घमायुश्चिकीर्षन्तो वेदं वर्धनमायुषः ॥

महर्षयस्ते दृष्टशुर्वथावज्ज्ञानचक्षुषा । सामान्यं च विशेषं च गुणान् द्रव्याणि कर्म च ॥

समवायं च तज्ज्ञात्वा तन्नोक्तं विधिमास्थिताः । लेभिरं परमं शर्म जीवितं चाप्यनित्वरम् ॥

(चरकसंहिता (च.सं), सूत्रस्थानम्, १.२७-२९)

इत्यादिना पदार्थविचारमारभते चरकाचार्यः । अस्यार्थः — महर्षयः आयुर्वेदाध्ययनेन ज्ञानचक्षुषा दृष्टुः । किं दृष्टशुरिति चेत् - विश्वरूपान् सामान्यादिषट्पदार्थान् दृष्टुः ।

ज्ञानचक्षुषा सामान्यादीन् दृष्ट्वा किं चक्रुः इति चेदुच्यते – सामान्यादिकं ज्ञात्वा आयुर्वेदोक्तं विधम् आश्रिताः बभूवुः । तेन च महर्षयः अनित्वरमगत्वरं, शर्म नाम सुखं लेभिरे इति । एतेन ज्ञायते यदाचार्येण षडेव पदार्थाः अङ्गीकृताः इति । तेषां पदार्थानां लक्षणं ग्रन्थोक्तक्रमेण विचार्यते -

1. सामान्यम्

आदावेव सूत्रस्थाने प्रथमे दीर्घञ्जीवितीये अध्याये आयुर्वेदप्रयोजनस्य धातुसाम्यरक्षणस्य, विषमधातूनां धातुसाम्यकरणस्य च कारणं सामान्यविशेषादिषट्कं क्रमेण उपदेष्टुं प्रथमतः तदाधारभूतयोः सामान्यविशेषयोः कार्यमुपदिशन् पदार्थविषये चर्चामकरोत् । यथा –

सर्वदा सर्वभावानां सामान्यं वृद्धिकारणम् ।

हासहेतुर्विशेषश्च प्रवृत्तिरुभयस्य तु ॥ (च.सं, सूत्रस्थानम् १.४४)

इति सर्वेषां पदार्थानां निरूपणात् प्राक् तदवतारिकां यच्छन् पदार्थनिरूपणमारभते । सर्वदा सर्वस्मिन् काले, सर्वभावानां सत्तामनुभवतां द्रव्यगुणकर्मणां, वृद्धिराधिक्यं, तस्य कारणं सामान्यम् । हासः अपचयः, तस्य हेतुः विशेषः विशिष्यते व्यावर्तते इति विशेषः । उभयस्य सामान्यस्य विशेषस्य च, प्रवृत्तिः प्रवर्तनं नाम एवंभूता प्रवृत्तिः धातुसामान्यविशेषयोः वृद्धिहासे कारणम् इत्यर्थः । निष्कृष्टतया वक्तव्यं चेद् यो भावः यस्य समानः तयोः उभयोः प्रवृत्तिः सामान्यं वृद्धिकारणम् । यो भावः यस्माद् विशिष्टः तयोरुभयोः प्रवृत्तिः विशेषः हासहेतुः । यथा – पञ्चसु ब्राह्मणेषु अपरः कश्चिद् ब्राह्मणः यदि आगच्छति तर्हि षड्ब्राह्मणाः इति तेषां वृद्धौ तद्ब्राह्मणत्वं सामान्यं वृद्धौ हेतुः भवति । एवमेव यदि तत्रैव कश्चित् क्षत्रियः आगच्छति तर्हि षट्सु च पुरुषेषु सत्सु पञ्चैव ब्राह्मणाः एकः क्षत्रियः इति तत्क्षत्रियत्वं विशेषः ब्राह्मणानां हासहेतुः ।

इमाम् अवतारिकां यच्छन्

सामान्यमेकत्वकरं विशेषस्तु पृथक्त्वकृत् ।

तुल्यार्थता हि सामान्यं विशेषस्तु विपर्ययः ॥ (च.सं. सूत्रस्थानम्, १.४५)

इत्यनया कारिकया सामान्यविशेषयोः स्वरूपं निरूपयति ।

सामान्यमेकत्वकरम् इत्यनेन सामान्यस्य लक्षणं कथयति आचार्यः । एकत्वबुद्धिकरं सामान्यम् इत्यर्थः । अनेकासु भिन्नदेशकालासु गवादिव्यक्तिषु अयं गौः, अयं गौः इत्यादिप्रकारा एकाकारा या बुद्धिः तत् सामान्यम् । अत्र पूर्वोक्तं सर्वदा सर्वभावानां वृद्धिकारणम् इति वाक्यं योज्यम् । तर्हि अधुना सर्वभावानां सर्वदा मेलनेन एकीभावं करोति यत्तदेव सामान्यमित्युच्यते । तदेव च तेषां वृद्धिकारणम् इत्यर्थः पर्यवस्यति । यथा – दुग्धजलयोः एकापरविशिष्टद्रवत्वापन्नत्वेन एकमेव वस्तु जलरूपं सत् द्विधा भवतीति तत्र द्रवत्वादिकं सामान्यम् । किञ्चोच्यते – तुल्यार्थता हि सामान्यम् इति । तुल्यार्थता नाम एकसामान्यरूपार्थानुयोगिता । अनेकेषां समानानां भावः सामान्यम् । तेन अनेकेषां स्ववृत्तिवस्तुभावः उच्यते । येन समानं यत्, तस्य तेन सह तुल्यार्थत्वं सामान्यम् इति

निष्कृष्टार्थः । यथा – पुरुषाणां पुरुषघटकं वस्तु सत्त्वात्मशरीरं तुल्यमिति तदेव सामान्यम् । अत्र सामान्यं त्रिधा विभज्यते कैश्चित् । यदुक्तं सत्त्वात्मशरीरं तुल्यं सामान्यमिति तच्च द्रव्यभूतं सामान्यम् इति एको भेदः । तत्रैव पुरुषेषु यः कृष्णवर्णादिगुणः तत्र गुणभूतं सामान्यम् इति द्वितीयो भेदः । यच्च गमनादिकर्म तत् कर्मभूतं सामान्यम् इति तृतीयः इति केषाञ्चिदभिप्रायः ।

2. विशेषः

पूर्वोक्तकारिकायामेव द्वितीयपादेन चतुर्थपादेन च विशेषस्य लक्षणं प्रत्यपादयदाचार्यः विशेषस्तु पृथक्त्वकृदिति । अस्य व्यावृत्तबुद्धिकृदित्यर्थः । पृथक्त्वं स्यादसंयोगो वैलक्षण्यमनेकता इत्युक्तं वर्तते । तथा च अयोगेन भावानामनेकत्वं करोति इत्यर्थः । यथा पारदजलयोः द्रवत्वविशेषः पृथक्त्वमेव करोति । कथमिति चेत् – उभयोः सत्यपि द्रवत्वे सामान्ये, विशेषः अस्त्येव तत्स्थयोः द्रवत्वगुणत्वयोः । अत्र पूर्वोक्तोदाहरणं पुनः स्मर्तव्यम् । पञ्चब्राह्मणेषु यदि एकोऽपरः ब्राह्मणः आगच्छति तर्हि तेन सह मेलनं करोति ब्राह्मणत्वरूपं सामान्यम् । तत्रैव यदि कश्चन क्षत्रियः आगच्छति तर्हि अपरेण तेन क्षत्रियेण सह ब्राह्मणत्वस्य पृथक्त्वं करोत्ययं विशेषः क्षत्रियत्वधर्मः । अत एवोक्तम् – विशेषस्तु विपर्ययः इति । अस्यार्थस्तु अतुल्यार्थता इति । यः यत्र वर्तते अर्थः सः तस्य भावः । तर्हि गोषु गोत्वं वर्तते इति तत्र गोत्वं भावः । एवमेव गजेषु गजत्वं वर्तते इति तत्र गजत्वं भावः । अधुना अतुल्यार्थता इति कथनेन तयोः गोत्वगजत्वरूपार्थयोः पृथग्बुद्धिः युक्तैव इति विशेषस्य विपर्ययत्वम् ।

3. समवायः

तृतीयः पदार्थः समवायः । अस्य लक्षणमेवं ब्रवीत्याचार्यः -

समवायोऽपृथग्भावो भूम्यादीनां गुणैर्मतः ।

स नित्यो यत्र हि द्रव्यं न तत्रानियतो गुणः ॥ (च.सं. सूत्रस्थानम्, १.५०) इति ।

अस्यायमर्थः – अपृथग्भावो नामायुतसिद्धिः । निष्कृष्टस्तु सहैव अवस्थानमिति । तदेवोक्तं नैयायिकैः – नित्यसम्बन्धः समवायः, अयुतसिद्धवृत्तिरिति । अयुतानां पृथक् पृथक् स्थितानां, सिद्धानां कारणानां, किञ्चिद् आधार्यं भविष्यद् इत्येवम्भूतानां कार्यत्वमापन्नानां तेषां कार्ये खलु इदम् इत्येवं प्रत्ययहेतुः यः संबन्धः सः कार्यकारणयोः सम्बन्धः समवायः इत्यर्थः । अपि च लक्षणं विस्तारयत्याचार्यः – भूम्यादीनां गुणैः मतः इति । अस्यायमर्थः – भूमिः भूयसाम् आधेयानां प्रत्यक्षसिद्धा आधारा । अतः आधारत्वोदाहरणार्थमुक्ता । तथा च भूमिप्रकाराधारभूतानां गुणैः अप्रधानैः, गुणसंज्ञकर्मसंज्ञान्यतरैः, अपृथग्भावः आधाराधेयभावः, संबन्धः समवायः इति । सः समवायः नित्यः अविनाशी इत्यर्थः ।

यत्र हि द्रव्यं नियतमित्यादिना समवायस्य नित्यत्वं साधयति आचार्यः । यत्र द्रव्यं नित्यं, तत्र नित्ये द्रव्ये, अनियतः विनाशी, गुणः कश्चित् न स्यादित्यर्थः । अत्रावधेयांशः - नैयायिकैः नित्यानित्यभेदेन समवायः द्विधा व्याख्यातः । परमाचार्यः न तत्रानियतो इत्यनेन विनाशी न कश्चित् स्यादिति कथनपुस्सरं समवायस्य एकत्वं साधयति । आश्रयद्रव्यनाशे समवायस्य

विनाशः न स्यादित्यभिप्रायः ।

4. द्रव्यम्

चतुर्थः पदार्थः द्रव्यम् । अस्य लक्षणमेवं कथयति आचार्यः –

यत्नाश्रिताः कर्मगुणाः कारणं समवायि यत् ।

तद् द्रव्यं समवायी तु निश्चेष्टः कारणं गुणः ॥ (च.सं, सूत्रस्थानम्, १.५१) इति

अत्र तद् द्रव्यमित्येतावता द्रव्यस्य लक्षणं प्रतिपादयति । यत्र यस्मिन्, आश्रिताः समवेताः, कर्मगुणाः कर्म च गुणाश्च कर्मगुणाः, यत् यच्च, समवायिकारणं, तद् द्रव्यमिति कथ्यते इत्यर्थः । अत्र गङ्गाधराचार्यः स्पष्टतया लक्षणं विवृणोति – कार्यमारभमाणे यत्र कारणे कर्मगुणाः आश्रिताः भवन्ति, कार्ये जायमाने जायमानतत्कर्मगुणाश्रयः सन् यत्कारणं समवायि तत्कार्ये समवायि भवति, तत्कारणं द्रव्यमुच्यते इति । तत्र षडेव पदार्थाः इति पूर्वमुक्तम् । सामान्यविशेषयोः लक्षणं तु प्रतिपादितम् । अवशिष्टेषु पदार्थेषु द्रव्यगुणकर्मणां समवायिकारणं यद्भवति तदेव द्रव्यमिति कथ्यते इति निष्कृष्टार्थः । यतः समवायः कश्चन संबन्धः । गुणकर्मणी तु न समवेतं कार्यं जनयतः । तस्मात् समवायगुणकर्माणि समवायिकारणानि न भवितुमर्हन्ति । तथा च यदुक्तं द्रव्यगुणकर्मणां समवायिकारणं यत्, तद् द्रव्यमिति कथ्यते इति । तच्च द्रव्यस्य गुणादिपञ्चपदार्थव्यावृत्तिमात्रलक्षणकथनम् ।

एवमुक्त्वा –

खादीन्यात्मा मनः कालो दिशश्च द्रव्यसंग्रहः ।

सेन्द्रियं चेतनं द्रव्यं निरिन्द्रियमचेतनम् ॥ (च.सं, सूत्रस्थानम्, १.४८)

इत्यादिना द्रव्याणि कानि इति निर्दिशति । कानि च तानि इति चेत् – खादीनि – महाभूतानि खं वायुरग्निरापः क्षितिस्तथा (च.सं, शारीरस्थानम्, १.२७) इत्यादिनिर्देशात् पृथिव्यपतेजोवाय्वाकाशरूपाणि भूतानि, आत्मा, मनः, कालः, दिशश्च द्रव्याणि भवन्ति इत्यर्थः ।

5. गुणः

पञ्चमो पदार्थः गुणः । पूर्वोक्तकारिकायामेव अन्तिमपादेन गुणस्य लक्षणं प्रतिपादयति आचार्यः । किं तदिति पृष्टे – **समवायी तु निश्चेष्टः कारणं गुणः** इति । यश्च समवायाधेयः, चेष्टायाः निर्गतः, कारणं च भवति तस्य गुण इति नाम इत्यर्थः । समवायाधेयः इत्यनेन आकाशादिभ्यः व्यापकद्रव्येभ्यः निष्क्रियेभ्यः गुणस्य व्यावृत्तिरुक्ता । निर्गतः चेष्टायाः इति निश्चेष्ट इत्यनेन चेष्टाशून्यत्वं चेष्टाव्यतिरिक्तत्वञ्च उच्यते येन चेष्टारूपात् कर्मणः अस्य व्यावृत्तिरुक्ता । कारणमित्यनेन च सामान्यविशेषसमवायादिभ्यः अकारणेभ्यः गुणस्य व्यावृत्तिरुक्ता । तथा च गुणस्य निष्कृष्टलक्षणमेवं वक्तुं शक्यम् – यस्य कार्यस्य आरम्भे यः भावः क्रियाहीनः एव सन् अन्यक्रियया परिणमन् कार्यत्वम् आपद्यते सः तस्य कार्यस्य गुणो नाम कारणम् उच्यते इति ।

के च ते गुणा इति चेत् –

सार्था गुर्वादयो बुद्धिः प्रयत्नान्ताः परादयः ।

गुणाः प्रोक्ताः... (च.सं, सूत्रस्थानम्, १.४९)

इत्यादिना गुणान् निर्दिशति । अर्था इत्यनेन 'अर्थाः शब्दादयो ज्ञेयाः गोचराः विषया गुणाः' (च.सं, शारीरस्थानम्, १.३१) इत्यादिनिर्देशात् शब्दस्पर्शरूपरसगन्धाः ज्ञेयाः, गुर्वादयः गुरुलघुशीतोष्णादयः, बुद्धिः ज्ञानम्, प्रयत्नान्ताः इच्छा, द्वेषः, सुखं दुःखं, प्रयत्नश्च इच्छादिप्रयत्नान्ताः, परादयः परापरत्वे युक्तिश्चेत्यादिनिर्देशात् परापरयुक्तिसंख्यासंयोगविभागपृथक्त्वपरिमाणसंस्काराभ्यासाः, इत्येते गुणाः प्रोक्ताः इति गुणान् निर्दिशति । पुनश्च विस्तृतरूपेण शारीरस्थाने प्रथमे अध्याये इमान् विवृणोति ।

6. कर्म

अन्तिमः पदार्थश्च कर्म । अस्य लक्षणमेवमुक्तम् –

संयोगे च विभागे च कारणं द्रव्यमाश्रितम् ।

कर्तव्यस्य क्रिया कर्म कर्म नान्यदपेक्षते ॥ (च.सं, सूत्रस्थानम्, १.५२)

द्रव्यमाश्रितं सत् यत् कारणं संयोगे वियोगे च अन्यत्कर्म नापेक्षते तत् कर्म इति कथ्यते इत्यर्थः । अस्य अयमर्थः – उत्पन्नं कर्म स्वाश्रयस्य द्रव्यस्य पूर्वदेशविभागे उत्तरदेशसंयोगे च कर्तव्ये नान्यत् कारणं पश्चात्कालभाव्यम् अपेक्षते इति । सरलतया वक्तव्यं चेत् – संयोगविभागेषु अनपेक्षकारणं कर्म इति । निष्कृष्टार्थस्तु – कार्यम् आरम्भमाणानां द्रव्याणां संयोगे पुनः विभागे च यत् कारणम्, अन्यत् कर्म स्वभिन्नं कर्मान्तरं नापेक्षते तद् द्रव्यमाश्रितं कर्म, कर्तव्यस्य तस्य कार्यस्य कर्म इत्युच्यते इति ।

किञ्च –

प्रयत्नादि कर्म चेष्टितमुच्यते ॥ (च.सं, सूत्रस्थानम्, १.४९)

अस्य अर्थकथनवेलायां कर्मस्वरूपं निर्दिशति । यद्यपि प्राणिव्यापार एव चेष्टितमित्युच्यते तथाऽपि प्रकृतस्थले चेष्टितपदेन सामान्येन क्रिया विवक्षिता ।

उपसंहारः

एवं न केवलं वैद्यकीयविषयान् अपि तु तत्त्वज्ञानसंबद्धान् विषयान्, शास्त्रान्तरे निहितान् विषयांश्च तत्र तत्र सूक्ष्मरूपेण कदाचिच्च विस्तृतरूपेण प्रत्यपादयदाचार्यः । अत्राऽपि कथं लक्षणनिरूपणं कृतमाचार्यैः इति यद्यवलोकयामस्तर्हि आचार्यस्य विशिष्टां शैलीं ज्ञातुं शक्नुमः । पदार्थनिरूपणशास्त्रेषु द्रव्यगुणकर्म इत्येवं क्रमः । परमत्र आचार्यः सामान्यविशेषसमवायद्रव्यगुणकर्म इति क्रमान्तरम् अनुसरति । तत्र कारणं किं स्यादिति व्याख्यातृणां वचनैः ज्ञातुं शक्नुमः । एतत्सर्वं निरूप्य अन्ते कर्मलक्षणानन्तरम् इत्युक्तं कारणम् (च.सं, सूत्रस्थानम्, १.५३) इति वदति चरकाचार्यः । अस्य व्याख्यावेलायां चक्रपाणिदत्तः – एतावदेव सामान्यादिषट्कं सर्वस्यैव कार्यजातस्य कारणम्, नान्यत् कारणमस्ति इति लिखति । सामान्याद्विशेषं प्रति इति क्रममनुसृत्य सर्वदा ज्ञातस्य सामान्यस्य लक्षणम् आदौ प्रतिपाद्य ततश्च तस्य संबन्धेन विशेषं व्यावर्तयति इति विशेषलक्षणं प्रतिपाद्य, कथं व्यावर्तयति इति प्रश्नमवलम्ब्य संबन्धेन इति वक्तुं समवायलक्षणं

प्रतिपाद्य, एतौ सामान्यविशेषौ वृद्धिहासे कारणे भवतः इति चोक्त्वा, केषां वृद्धिहासे इत्यवतारिकाम् अवलम्ब्य, सत्तामनुभवतां द्रव्यगुणकर्मणां वृद्धिहासे कारणं भवतः इति ततः द्रव्यगुणकर्मणां लक्षणं प्रत्यपादयदाचार्यः। तथा च विशिष्टया रीत्या येन क्रमेण सुलभतया च अवगन्तुं शक्नुमः पदार्थान् तं क्रममनुसृत्य तान् लक्षयति।

यद्यपि आयुर्वेदसंबन्धग्रन्थत्वात् तदनुसारं पदार्थाः व्याख्याताः तथाऽपि एकैकस्मिन्नपि पदार्थलक्षणे सूक्ष्मदृष्ट्या विचारं कुर्मो यदि, तर्हि सर्वसम्मतं पदार्थलक्षणमपि ज्ञातुं शक्नुमः। यथा – सामान्यलक्षणे। नित्यमेकमनेकानुगतं सामान्यम् इति इतरशास्त्रे सामान्यस्य लक्षणं प्रतिपादितं दृश्यते। तदेव अत्र एकत्वकरम्, तुल्यार्थता इत्याभ्यां पदाभ्यां निरूपितं ज्ञायते। तथैव च विशेषलक्षणे – नित्यद्रव्यवृत्तयो विशेषाः इति। तदेव चात्र विशेषः पृथक्त्वकृत् इति व्यावृत्तिकृदिति व्याख्यातम्। एवमेव एकैकस्मिन्नपि लक्षणे विशिष्टांशं विधाय निरूपणं कृतं वर्तते आचार्येण। अतश्च आयुर्वेदग्रन्थ एवायमिति मतिं विना अत्र प्रतपादितान् विषयान् केवलायुर्वेददृष्टिं विहाय शास्त्रदृष्ट्या दर्शनदृष्ट्या च अध्येतुं प्रयतामहे यदि तर्हि अवश्यं नवांशान् ज्ञातुं शक्नुमः ॥

उपयुक्तग्रन्थसूची

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दीपिकादिव्याख्यासहितः, बालमनोरमा प्रेस्, चेन्नै।

तारानाथतर्कवाचस्पतिः (१९८१). वाचस्पत्यम्, काव्यप्रकाशमुद्रणालयः, कल्कत्ता।

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राजाराधाकान्तदेवः (१९६७). शब्दकल्पद्रुमः, चौखम्बा संस्कृतसीरीज् आफिस्, वाराणसी।

श्रीनरेन्द्रनाथ सेनगुप्तः श्रीबलाञ्चन्द्रसेनगुप्तश्च (सं) (१८४९). चरकसंहिता,
महर्षिणा पुनर्वसुनोपदिष्टा, अग्निवेशेन प्रणीता, चरकदृढबलाभ्यां प्रतिसंस्कृता,
जल्पकल्पतरुव्याख्योपेता, धन्वन्तरि मुद्रणालयः, कल्कत्ता।

‘काव्यालंकारः’ इति ग्रन्थस्य मङ्गलाचरणश्लोकस्य तात्पर्यविश्लेषणम्

डा. अञ्जु दास्¹

शोधसारः

भारतीयदर्शनं द्विविधम् आस्तिक-नास्तिकभेदात्। तत्र आस्तिकाः ग्रन्थादौ मङ्गलाचरणं कुर्वन्ति निर्विघ्नग्रन्थपरिसमाप्तये शिष्यशिक्षायै च। ननु मङ्गलाचरणस्य कर्तव्यत्वे किं प्रमाणमस्तीति चेदुच्यते प्रमाणमस्ति, तत्र शिष्टाचारानुमितश्रुतिरेव प्रमाणम्- ‘समाप्तिकामो मङ्गलाचरेत्’। अतो मङ्गलाचरणं विशेषतात्पर्यमण्डितं कर्म। शास्त्रविद्विः मङ्गलाचरणस्य त्रिविधत्वमङ्गीकृतम्- नमस्कारात्मकं, वस्तुनिर्देशात्मकम् आशीर्वादात्मकञ्चेति। केषाञ्चन नये अपरमेकं मङ्गलाचरणं हि उपासनात्मकम्। यद्वा भवतु भामहाचार्येण ‘काव्यालंकारः’ इति ग्रन्थे नमस्कारात्मकं वस्तुनिर्देशात्मकञ्च मङ्गलाचरणं विहितम्। श्लोकस्य पूर्वार्धे नमस्कारः विहितः, उत्तरार्धे च ‘काव्यालंकार इत्येष’ इत्यनेन वस्तुनिर्देशः कृतः। श्लोके यानि पदानि सन्ति तेषां पदानां तात्पर्यं मया स्वयुक्त्या विश्लेषितम्। तत्र नूतनं तथ्यमुन्मोचितम्।

कूटशब्दाः:- आस्तिकः, नास्तिकः, काव्यम्, प्रणम्य, सार्वः, सर्वज्ञः।

आस्तिक-नास्तिकभेदेन भारतीयदर्शनं द्विधा विभक्तम्। तत्र ये खलु वेदस्य प्रामाण्यं स्वीकुर्वन्ति ते आस्तिकाः, ये च वेदनिन्दकास्ते तु नास्तिकाः। आस्तिकसम्प्रदायेन ग्रन्थरचनायाः प्रारम्भे मध्ये अन्ते च मङ्गलाचरणं क्रियते- ‘मङ्गलादीनि हि शास्त्राणि प्रथन्ते वीरपुरुषाणि च भवन्ति’ (शास्त्री १९७९,i) इति। वस्तुतः ग्रन्थस्य निर्विघ्नपरिसमाप्तये शिष्यशिक्षायै च शिष्टाचारानुमितश्रुतिबोधितकर्तव्यताकम् इष्टदेवस्य नमस्कारपूर्वकं मङ्गलाचरणं क्रियते। अत्र नास्तिका वदन्ति मङ्गलाचरणेन ग्रन्थसमाप्तिर्न भवेत्, यतः आस्तिकसम्प्रदायस्य कादम्बर्यादिग्रन्थेषु मङ्गलाचरणश्लोके कृतेऽपि परिसमाप्तिर्न दृश्यते, परन्तु नास्तिकसम्प्रदायकृतग्रन्थेषु मङ्गलाभावेऽपि परिसमाप्तिर्नादित्यत्र अन्वयव्यतिरेकव्यभिचारदोषो भवेत्। दोषस्यास्य निवारणाय वक्तुं शक्यते यत्र ग्रन्थे मङ्गले सत्यपि समाप्तिर्न दृश्यते तत्र विघ्नो बलवत्तरस्तथा विघ्नप्राचुर्यमस्तीति बोध्यम्। अर्थात् विघ्नसमसंख्यकमङ्गलस्य विघ्ननाशकत्वेऽधिकसंख्यकमङ्गलान् न्यूनसंख्यकविघ्नस्य नाशो

न स्यात्, तथा च कादम्बर्यादिग्रन्थेषु बलवत्तरमङ्गलाभावान्न विघ्ननाशो भवेदिति । अतः असति विघ्ननाशे स्वजन्यविघ्नध्वंसवत्तासम्बन्धेन तत्र तादृशमङ्गलाभावान्न समाप्तिरिति नान्वयव्यभिचारः । ततश्च यत्र ग्रन्थे मङ्गलं नास्ति परन्तु ग्रन्थसमाप्तिर्दृश्यते तत्रापि जन्मान्तरीयं कल्प्यते, अतः न व्यतिरेकव्यभिचारः । तदुक्तं न्यायसिद्धान्तमुक्तावल्याम्- “नास्तिकादीनां ग्रन्थेषु जन्मान्तरीयमङ्गलजन्यदुरितध्वंसः स्वतःसिद्धविघ्नान्ताभावो वाऽस्ति न व्यभिचार इत्याहुः” (शास्त्री, २०१६, ३५-३६) ।

ननु जन्मान्तरीयमङ्गलस्य तदानीमेव नष्टत्वात् एतज्जन्मीयसमाप्त्यव्यवहितपूर्वमसतस्तस्य कथं कारणत्वं, कथं वा व्यतिरेकव्यभिचारपरिहार इत्याशंक्य वक्तुं शक्यते स्वजन्यविघ्नध्वंसवत्त्वसम्बन्धेन मङ्गलस्य कारणत्वात् मङ्गलाभावेऽपि तज्जन्यविघ्नध्वंसद्वारसत्त्वात् कारणत्वमुपपद्यते, यथा यागस्य नाशेऽपि तज्जन्यापूर्वरूपद्वारस्य स्वर्गाव्यवहितपूर्वं सत्त्वात् यागस्य स्वर्गकारणत्वं तद्वदिति ।

ननु मङ्गलाचरणस्य कर्तव्यत्वे किं प्रमाणमस्तीति चेदुच्यते प्रमाणमस्ति, तत्र शिष्टाचारानुमितश्रुतिरेव प्रमाणम्- ‘समाप्तिकामो मङ्गलमाचरेत्’ इति । परन्तु श्रुतिरियं न प्रमाणम् तादृशश्रुतेः पठ्यमानवेदे कुत्राप्यदर्शनात् । तदा उच्यते यद्यपि श्रुतिर्न प्रत्यक्षा तथापि आचारेण लिङ्गेन तादृशी श्रुतिरनुमीयते । तथा च आचारानुमिता श्रुतिः मङ्गलकर्तव्यत्वे प्रमाणमिति आस्तिकानामाशयः । तत्र अनुमानप्रकारश्च- ‘मङ्गलं वेदबोधितकर्तव्यताकम् अलौकिकाविगीतशिष्टाचारविषयत्वात्, दर्शादिवत्’ इति । अत्र केचन वदन्ति वेदबोधितकर्तव्यताकत्वं हि साध्यं, न तु वेदः । यत् अनुमानसाध्यं – अनुमितिविधेयं तदेवानुमितमिति । तथा च वेदबोधितकर्तव्यताकत्वं शिष्टाचारानुमितं न तु वेद इति कथं श्रुतेः शिष्टाचारानुमितत्वमुपपद्यते? तत्रैवं वक्तुं शक्यते- ‘मङ्गलं वेदबोधितकर्तव्यताकम्’ इति प्रतिज्ञायाः मङ्गलं स्वबोधितकर्तव्यताकत्वसम्बन्धेन वेदविशिष्टम् । तथा च तादृशानुमितौ वेद एव विधेय इति वेदस्यानुमितत्वम् अनायासेन उपपद्यत इति । अथ अलौकिकाविगीतशिष्टाचारविषयत्वहेतुपदस्य तात्पर्यं हि- शिष्टानामाचारः शिष्टाचारः, तस्य विषयः शिष्टाचारविषयः । अविगीतश्चासौ शिष्टाचारविषयश्च अविगीतशिष्टाचारविषयः, अलौकिकश्चासौ अविगीतशिष्टाचारविषयश्च अलौकिकाविगीतशिष्टाचारविषयः, तस्य भावस्तत्त्वम् । अलौकिकत्वे सति अविगीतत्वे सति शिष्टाचारविषयत्वं हेतुरिति । लौकिकत्वं नाम विध्यतिरिक्तप्रमाणगम्यत्वम्, तद्विघ्नत्वमलौकिकत्वम् । हेतौ अलौकिकत्वानुपादाने रागप्राप्ते भोजनादौ वेदबोधितकर्तव्यताकत्वरूपसाध्याभाववति अविगीतशिष्टाचारविषयत्वरूपहेतुसत्त्वाद् व्यभिचारः स्यात् । तद्वारणाय अलौकिकत्वमुपात्तम् । अविगीतत्वं नाम धर्मशास्त्रानिषिद्धत्वम् । तदनुपादाने वेदबोधितकर्तव्यताकत्वरूपसाध्याभाववति रात्रिश्राद्धादौ अलौकिकशिष्टाचारविषयत्वरूपहेतु-सत्त्वात् व्यभिचारो भवेदिति वारणाय अविगीतत्वं प्रयुक्तम् । अतः रात्रिश्राद्धादेः ‘रात्रौ श्राद्धं न कुर्वीत’ इति धर्मशास्त्रनिषिद्धत्वान्न तत्र व्यभिचारः ।

वस्तुतः वयं जानीमः वेदोक्तं यत्तत्त्वं तद्विषयकज्ञानजन्या या वेदविहितकर्मविषयककृतिः तदाश्रयः शिष्ट इति। परन्तु वेदविहितकर्मकर्ता शिष्ट इत्येतावन्मात्रोक्तौ वेदविहिताहिंसादिकर्मकर्तुः बौद्धस्यापि शिष्टत्वापत्तिरिति शंकायामुच्यते बौद्धस्य यत् अहिंसादितत्त्वज्ञानं न तद्वेदजन्यमिति। वस्तुतः इदं वेदोक्तमिति ज्ञानपूर्वकं यः वेदविहितम् कर्म करोति स शिष्टः। बौद्धस्तु वेदविहितमहिंसादिकं कर्म कुर्वन्नपि इदं वेदोक्तमिति बुद्ध्या न करोति, तेन वेदप्रामाण्यानभ्युपगमादिति न तस्य शिष्टत्वापत्तिरिति।

अतः मङ्गलाचरणं विशेषतात्पर्यमण्डितं कर्म। शास्त्रविद्विः मङ्गलाचरणस्य त्रिविधत्वमङ्गीकृतम्- नमस्कारात्मकं, वस्तुनिर्देशात्मकम् आशीर्वादात्मकञ्चेति। केषाञ्चन नये अपरमेकं मङ्गलाचरणं हि उपासनात्मकम्। यद्वा भवतु इदानीं भामहाचार्यकृतस्य 'काव्यालंकारः' इति ग्रन्थस्य मङ्गलाचरणस्य तात्पर्यविश्लेषणावसरः-

“प्रणम्य सार्वं सर्वज्ञं मनोवाक्कायकर्मभिः।

काव्यालंकार इत्येष यथाबुद्धि विधास्यते ॥” इति। (काव्यालंकारः, २०१३, १/१)

अर्थात् मनसा वाचा कायेन च सार्वं सर्वज्ञं परमात्मनं प्रणम्य काव्यालंकारनामकग्रन्थः भामहेन यथाबुद्धि विरच्यते। अत एव दृश्यते भामहाचार्येण नमस्कारात्मकं वस्तुनिर्देशात्मकञ्च मङ्गलाचरणं कृतम्। श्लोकस्य पूर्वार्धे नमस्कारः विहितः, उत्तरार्धे च 'काव्यालंकार इत्येष' इत्यनेन वस्तुनिर्देशः कृतः।

प्रणम्य

'प्रणम्य' इति पदे प्र-शब्देन भक्तिश्रद्धातिशयलक्षणः प्रकर्षः प्रकाशयते। तादृशमेव मङ्गलं विघ्नकूटस्य शान्तिं सन्तनोति। ननु अत्र नम्-धातुः कथं सकर्मकत्वेन व्यवहृतः प्रह्वीभावप्रवृत्ते रस्याकर्मकत्वात् 'नमन्ति शाखा नवमञ्जरीभिः' इत्यादिप्रयोगदर्शनाच्च? इह उपसर्गयोगात् सकर्मकः न स्यात्। प्र-शब्दस्य प्रकर्षमालार्थत्वेन कर्मसम्बन्धोपपादकत्वायोगात्। अपि च 'नमामि देवम्' इत्यादिस्थले उपसर्गस्यापि अभावात् सकर्मकः। अस्य न चायमन्तर्निहितः अर्थः अनौचित्यप्रसङ्गादिति। तदेतत् पाणिनिभणितिपरायणपरिणतान्तःकरणानाम् अस्माकं चेतसि चोद्यं न चातुरीमाचरति। यथा जयतिरकर्मकः प्रकर्षेण विराजते, पराजये तु सकर्मकः; तथा नमिधातुः यदा प्रह्वीभावार्थमालविवक्षया प्रयुज्यते तदानीमेषः अकर्मकः। यदा च नमस्कारार्थविवक्षया प्रयुज्यते तदा सकर्मक इति। यदि एवं समाधानं भवेत्तर्हि 'देवं प्रणतः' इत्यत्र कर्तरि क्तप्रत्ययो न सिध्येत्। कारणं हि वयं जानीमः 'सकर्मकाकर्मकाद्वातोः क्तो भवेत् कर्मभावयोः' इत्यनेन सकर्मकाद्वातोः कर्मणि क्तप्रत्ययविधानात्। अपि 'गत् यर्थाकर्मकश्लिषशीङ्स्थासवसजनरुहजीर्यतिभ्यश्च' (७/४/१२) इति सूत्रे नम्-धातोः परिगणनाभावादित्यपि न चोदनीयम्। वस्तुतः अनेन सूत्रेणैव कर्तरि क्तप्रत्ययो भवेत्। गत्यर्थादिसूत्रे 'च'कारः विद्यते, अस्मात् चकारादनुक्तसमुच्चयार्थात् कर्तरि क्तप्रत्ययो भवतीति सूत्रस्यार्थः।

सार्वः

मङ्गलाचरणश्लोके भामहाचार्येण कश्चिदपि विग्रहविशिष्टपुरुषो न पूजितः, वस्तुतस्तेन

परमात्मनं प्रणम्य ग्रन्थो विरच्यते । तत्र परमात्मनः द्वौ विशेषणौ प्रयुक्तौ- सार्वः सर्वज्ञश्चेति । सार्वशब्दस्यार्थो हि सर्वहितकारिता । स्वेन आचार्येण सार्वशब्दस्य व्युत्पत्तिर्विहिता षष्ठपरेच्छेदे-

“हितप्रकरणे पञ्च सर्वशब्दात्प्रयुञ्जते ।

ततश्छमिष्ट्या च यथा सार्वः सर्वीय इत्यपि ॥” इति । (काव्यालंकारः, २०१८, ६/५३)

अर्थात् हितप्रकरणे सर्वशब्दादुत्तरं णप्रत्ययेन सार्वशब्दस्य निष्पत्तिर्भवति । पुनश्च इष्टवार्तिकेन विभाषया छ-प्रत्ययेन सर्वीयशब्दः निष्पद्यते । वस्तुतः पाणिनेः अष्टाध्याय्यां ‘तस्मै हितम्’(५/१/५) इति सूत्रतः हितप्रकरणस्यारम्भः जातः । ‘तस्मै हितम्’ इत्यर्थे नैके तद्धितप्रत्यया भवन्ति । तेषु प्रत्ययद्वयं हि ण-प्रत्ययः ङञ्-प्रत्ययश्च । सर्वशब्दादुत्तरं णप्रत्ययविधानसूत्रं हि- ‘सर्वपुरुषाभ्यां णङ्जौ’(५/१/१०) इति । सर्वीयशब्दस्य प्रयोगः सूत्रेण न भवेत्, तत्र वार्तिकेन सर्वीयशब्दो निष्पन्नः स्यात् । वार्तिकं खलु- ‘सर्वाणो वेति वक्तव्यम्’ इति । अत्रेदमवधेयं यत् सार्वशब्दः भामहाचार्यस्य अतीव प्रियः आसीत्, तथाहि तेन मङ्गलाचरणे शब्दोऽयं प्रयुक्तः इति मन्यते ।

सर्वज्ञः

इदानीं सर्वज्ञशब्दस्य विश्लेषणावसर आगतः । सूतमनेन विश्वमिति सर्वम्, मेघदूते सर्वशब्दस्यार्थो कृतः- ‘रिक्तः सर्वो भवति हि लघुः पूर्णता गौरवाय’ इति । सर्वशब्दः यदा पुल्लिङ्गेन प्रयुज्यते तदा अर्थो भवेत् विष्णुः शंकरो वा इति अभिधानम् । ज्ञः नाम जानाति, सर्वस्य ज्ञः इति सर्वज्ञः । वस्तुतः सर्वज्ञशब्दस्य त्रिविधोऽर्थः भवति- १) सर्वं जानाति इति सर्वज्ञः, २) शङ्करः- कृशानुरेता सर्वज्ञो धूर्जटिर्नीललोहितः(अमरकोषः-१/३५), ३) बुद्धः- सर्वज्ञः सुगतो बुद्धो धर्मराजस्तथागतः (अमरकोषः-१/१३) इति ।

आचार्यभामहस्य ‘सर्वज्ञ’शब्दव्यवहारेण केषाञ्चन विदूषां नये भामहः बौद्ध आसीत् । यतः सर्वज्ञः भगवतः बुद्धस्यापरं नाम इत्येका युक्तिः । अपरा युक्तिर्हि भामहस्य पितुर्नाम रक्रिलगोमिन् इति । रक्रिलः नाम राहुल-सोमिल-पोतलादिबौद्धाभिधानेन सह ध्वनिसाम्यं भवति । गोमिन्-शब्देन तेषां युक्तिः वलवत्तरा स्यात्, यतः गोमिन् नाम एकः शिष्य आसीद् भगवतः बुद्धस्य । अतः रक्रिलः गोमिन् चेति शब्दद्वयं मिलित्वा भामहस्य पिता रक्रिलगोमिन् बौद्धः सिध्यति । एवं निर्बलयुक्तिद्वारा भामहस्य बौद्धत्वम् सिद्धमिति ।

युक्तिद्वयस्यास्य खण्डनमिदानीं क्रियते मया- प्रथमतः, ‘सर्वज्ञ’शब्दः केवलं बुद्धस्य पर्यायवाचकः नहि । अपि तु वयं पश्यामः शंकरवाचकः भवितुमर्हति ‘सर्वज्ञ’शब्दः । अतः केवलं बुद्धार्थे सर्वज्ञशब्दस्य प्रयोगः न समीचिनः ।

द्वितीयतः, केवलं ध्वनिसाम्येन किमपि नाम सम्प्रदायविशेषस्य भवितुमर्हतीति यथार्थप्रतीतिर्न भवेत् । तथा च ‘रक्रिल’ इति न हि बौद्धनाम । पुनश्च ‘गोमिन्’ इत्यस्य साहचर्येण अतिरिक्तोऽर्थः धर्तुं न शक्यते । वस्तुतः ‘गोमिन्’ इति ‘गोस्वामिन्’ इत्यस्य

अर्थोऽपि भवितुमर्हति । गोस्वामिन् खलु ब्राह्मणस्य पदवीति वयं जानीमः । अपि च चान्द्रव्याकरणे 'गोमिन्'शब्दस्यार्थो हि पूज्य इति- "गोमिने पूज्ये" (४/२/११४) । अत एव भामहस्य पिता रक्रिलगोमिन् कदापि बौद्धः नासीत् ।

तृतीयतः, भामहाचार्येण स्वकीये काव्यालंकारग्रन्थे बौद्धदर्शनस्य अपोहवादः खण्डितः । तत्र तेन कतिपया युक्तयः प्रदर्शिताः-

“यदि गौरित्ययं शब्दः कृतार्थोऽन्यनिराकृतौ ।

जनको गवि गोबुद्धेर्मृग्यतामपरो ध्वनिः ॥

अर्थज्ञानफला शब्दा न चैकस्य फलद्वयम् ।

अपवादविधिज्ञाने फले चैकस्य वः कथम् ॥

पुरा गौरिति विज्ञानं गोशब्दश्रवणाद्भवेत् ।

येनागोप्रतिषेधाय प्रवृत्तो गौरिति ध्वनिः ॥

वर्णभेदादिदं भिन्नं वर्णां स्वांशविकल्पिताः ।

के शब्दाः किञ्च तद्वाच्यमित्यहो वर्त्म दुस्तरम् ॥” इति ।

(काव्यालंकारः, २०१८, ६/१७-२०)

अपोहवादिनः दृष्टौ शब्दस्यार्थो हि अतद्वावृत्तिः, न तु वस्तु । अतद्वावृत्तौ शब्दस्य प्रवृत्तेः परं वस्तुनः निषेधात्मकबोधो जायते, न विध्यात्मकः । अस्याः असङ्गतेः निराकरणाय आचार्येण रत्नकीर्तिना शब्दस्य विध्यात्मकः निषेधात्मकश्च उभयथा प्रवृत्तिः स्वीकृता- “नास्माभिरपोहशब्देन विधिरेव केवलोऽभिप्रेतः । नाप्यन्यथावृत्तिमात्रं किन्त्वन्यापोहविशिष्टो विधिः शब्दानामर्थः” इति । अर्थात् एकेन शब्देन निषेधः विधिश्चेति प्रयोजनद्वयं सिध्यति । यथा 'गो'शब्देन गोभिन्न-वस्तुनः व्यावृत्तिः(निषेधः) भवति तथा गो-वस्तुनः प्रतीतिरपि(विधिः) भवेत् ।

परन्तु भामहाचार्येण मतमिदं खण्डितम् । तत्रय एकेन शब्देन द्विविधा प्रतीतिर्न सम्भवेत् । यतः शब्दप्रयोगस्य कतिपयः स्वीकृतनियमः अस्ति, येन विधिः निषेधश्चेति उभयस्यावकाशो न स्यात् । यदि तस्य नियमस्य किमपि लङ्घनं क्रियते तर्हि तस्य स्वच्छन्दतामात्रं भवति । खण्डनमेनं दृष्ट्वा आचार्येण शान्तरक्षितेन तदीये तत्त्वसंग्रहग्रन्थे गदितम्-

“अन्यापोहापरिज्ञानादेवमेते कुदृष्टयः ।

स्वयं तुष्टा दुरात्मनो नाशयन्ति परानपि ॥” इति (शास्त्री, २००६, ३१६,)

चतुर्थतः, भामहेन वैदिकविधेः यज्ञानुष्ठानस्य च प्रशंसा कृता । परन्तु बौद्धैः यज्ञविधेर्निन्दनं कृतम् । भामहमते आगमविरोधः एकः दोषः-

“आगमो धर्मशास्त्राणि लोकसीमा च तत्कृता ।

तद्विरोधि तदाचारव्यतिक्रमणतो यथा ॥” इति ।

(काव्यालंकारः, २०१८, ४/४८)

अर्थात् धर्मशास्त्रविहितलोकमर्यादा आगमत्वेन परिगणिता। अस्य लङ्घनकर्ता हि आगमविरोधीति।

अत एव एताभिर्युक्तिभिः वक्तुं शक्यते भामहाचार्यः बौद्धः नासीत्, स तु वैदिकमतानुसारी आसीत्।

काव्यालंकारः

कवयतीति कविः, तस्य कर्म काव्यम्। मम्मटाचार्यमते काव्यशब्दस्यार्थो हि ‘लोकोत्तरवर्णनानिपुणकविकर्म काव्यम्’ इति। भामहेनापि ‘प्रज्ञा नवनवोन्मेषशालिनी प्रतिभा मता। तदनुप्राणनाज्जीवेद् वर्णनानिपुणः कविः। तस्य कर्मस्मृतं काव्यम्’ इति। पुनश्च रूढोऽर्थो हि चारुताशालि शब्दार्थयुगलं काव्यम्, तस्यालंकारः काव्यालंकार इति। वस्तुतः प्राचीनकाले काव्यस्वरूप-दोष-गुण-अलंकारादिविवेचनपरकसम्बन्धितशास्त्रं हि अलंकारशास्त्रमिति कथ्यते। समयेऽस्मिन् शास्त्रे अलंकारस्य प्राधान्यं दृश्यते, तथाहि राजशेखरेण अलंकारशास्त्रस्य नामान्तरं कृतं ‘साहित्यविद्या’ इति। अलंकारशब्दस्य द्विविधा व्युत्पत्तिः स्यात्- अलंक्रियतेऽनेनेति अलंकारः इति करणव्युत्पत्त्या यमकादयः अलंकारा बुध्यन्ते। अलंकृतिरलंकारः इति भावव्युत्पत्त्या च गुणानां(ओजःप्रसादादीनां) काव्यग्रहणहेतुत्वमिति। उदाहरणेनैकेन विषयः परिष्क्रियते-

“युवतेरिव रूपमङ्गं काव्यं स्वदते शुद्धगुणं तदप्यतीव।

विहितप्रणयं निरन्तराभिः सदलंकारविकल्पकल्पनाभिः॥” (बन्धोपाध्याय, ५९)

अत्र दृश्यते यथा गुणमात्राविशिष्टमपि काव्यं युवते रूपमिव स्वदते रोचते रसिकेभ्यः, कटकादयः अलंकाराः तस्या युवतेः शुद्धगुणविशिष्टतनुं बर्धयन्ति; तथैव यमकादिभिः अलंकारैः काव्यमुपादेयं भवेत् केवलम्। एवं विविच्य ग्रन्थकृता भामहेन काव्यालंकारशब्दः प्रयुक्तः।

यथाबुद्धि विधास्यते

‘यथाबुद्धि विधास्यते’ इति वाक्येन प्रतीतिर्जायते आचार्यभामहात्प्राक् अलंकारशास्त्रस्य कश्चिद् स्वतन्त्रग्रन्थोऽनुपलब्ध आसीत्। केवलं भरतमुनेः नाट्यशास्त्रं विराजितम्। इमं ग्रन्थमाधारीकृत्य भामह एव अलंकारशास्त्रस्य प्रथमः आचार्य इति स्वीक्रियते। ततः नैके अलंकारग्रन्थाः विरचिता इति शिवम्।

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द्वैतदर्शनस्य गौडसारस्वतब्राह्मणसमाजोपरि प्रभावः ।

डा.शुशान्त. एस्¹

भारतीयदर्शनेषु न केवलं तात्विकविचारः किन्तु सामाजिकविचारः अपि द्रष्टुं शक्यते । दर्शनस्य विचारमण्डलं सामान्यरूपेण प्रमेयशास्त्रं प्रमाणशास्त्रम् आचारशास्त्रञ्चेति त्रिविधं भवति । तत्र दार्शनिकतत्वानां सिद्धान्तानां च विचारः प्रमेयशास्त्रे अन्तर्भवति । प्रमेयसमर्थकप्रक्रियाविचारः भवति प्रमाणशास्त्रे । दार्शनिकलक्ष्यप्राप्त्यर्थं ये आचाराः अवश्यं कर्तव्याः तेषां विचारः आचारशास्त्रे अन्तर्भवति । तत्र प्रायेण सामान्यजनसम्बद्धं भवति आचारशास्त्रम् । अस्मिन् प्रबन्धे गौडसारस्वतब्राह्मणसमाजोपरि द्वैतदर्शनस्य प्रभावः कथमिति विचार्यते ।

श्रीमन्मध्वाचार्यस्य द्वैतवेदान्तदर्शनम्

श्रीमन्मध्वाचार्यः (क्रिस्तोरनन्तरं 1199-1278) पूर्णप्रज्ञः अथवा आनन्दतीर्थः इति नाम्ना अपि प्रसिद्धः । सः द्वैतदर्शनस्य संस्थापकः इति मन्यते । तस्य जन्म कर्णाटकस्य दक्षिणकानरामण्डलस्य उडुपीनगरस्य समीपे पाजकग्रामे तुलुब्राह्मणकुटुम्बे अभवत् । तस्य दर्शनस्य सारांशं निम्नलिखितरूपेण वक्तुं शक्यते । भगवान् विष्णुः अथवा नारायणः स्वतन्त्रः यथार्थः अस्ति तथा च अन्ये सर्वे वस्तूनि तस्मिन् आश्रितानि भवन्ति । सः सर्वैः शुभगुणैः योग्यः । द्वैतः विश्वस्य वास्तविकतां तथा जीवानामस्तित्वं तथा बहुत्वं च स्वीकरोति । एतासु वास्तविकतासु भेदम् अपि अङ्गीकरोति । ईश्वरः विश्वस्य कर्ता नियन्त्रकः च भवति । तस्य अनुग्रहः एव मुक्तेः एकमात्रः मार्गः अस्ति । भक्तिरेव तत्र उपायः । द्वैतवेदान्तप्रचरणार्थं आचार्येण नैके ग्रन्थाः विरचिताः । देशस्य विभिन्नेषु भागेषु भ्रमणं कृत्वा स्वस्य दर्शनस्य प्रचारम् अकरोत् । उडुपीनगरे अष्टमठस्थापनम् कृतम्, यत् तेन कृतप्रयत्नेषु अन्यतमम् भवति, यतः एते मठाः भारते अस्य दर्शनस्य व्यापकरूपेण प्रचारहेतवः अभवन् । बहवः शैवमतानुयायिनः वैष्णवमतं स्वीकृत्य वैष्णवमतानुयायिनः अभवन् । पालिमार्, आदामार्, कृष्णपुर, पुट्टीगे, सिरूर, सोडे, कानूर, पेजावर् च अष्टमठाः भवन्ति । तस्य शिष्याः देशस्य विभिन्नेषु भागेषु स्थापितैः विविधैः मठैः अस्याः व्यवस्थायाः शिक्षणं प्रसारणं च अकुर्वन् । तेषु जयतीर्थः (क्रि. अ. 14 शतकीयः), व्यासतीर्थः (क्रि. अ. 16 शतकीयः) च सर्वाधिकं

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उल्लेखनीयौ । तयोः प्रयत्नैः च एषा व्यवस्था दक्षिणभारतस्य जनानां महतीं मान्यतां प्राप्नोत् । एवं अन्ये बहवः जनाः ये अन्येषु दर्शनशास्त्रेषु अथवा अन्येषु व्यवस्थासु अपि विश्वसन्ति, ते अपि द्वैतं स्वदर्शनरूपेण, वैष्णवमतं च स्वव्यवस्थारूपेण अङ्गीकृतवन्तः ।

गौडसारस्वतब्राह्मणसमाजः

भारते ब्राह्मणाः भौगोलिकमूलस्य आधारेण मुख्यतया द्विधा विभक्ताः आसन् । विन्ध्यस्य उत्तरदिशि निवसन्तः ब्राह्मणसमूहाः गौडब्राह्मणाः इति निर्दिश्यन्ते स्म, विन्ध्यस्य दक्षिणदिशि निवसन्तः ब्राह्मणाः द्राविडब्राह्मणाः इति निर्दिश्यन्ते स्म । प्रत्येकं समूहः स्वनिवासस्य क्षेत्रानुसारं पञ्चसु खण्डेषु विभक्तः आसीत् । पञ्च गौडब्राह्मणसमूहाः सारस्वताः, कन्याकुब्जाः, गौडाः, उत्कलाः, मैथिलाः च आसन् । पञ्च द्राविडब्राह्मणसमूहाः आन्धीयाः, महाराष्ट्रीयः, तमिलब्राह्मणाः, कर्नाटकीयाः, केरलब्राह्मणाः च आसन् ।

गौडसारस्वतब्राह्मणसमाज इति भारतस्य एकः ब्राह्मणसमाजः भवति । गौडसारस्वताः प्रायेण कोङ्कणीभाषां मातृभाषारूपेण वदन्ति । उच्चपञ्जाब्ददेशस्य अथवा काश्मीरस्य अधुना विलुप्तायाः सरस्वतीनद्याः तटमासीत् गौडसारस्वतानां मूलस्थानम् । ते सरस्वतीनदीतटवासेन सास्वताः इति लब्धनामधेयाः । सारस्वतमुनेः अनुयायिनः सारस्वताः इति प्रथिताः इत्यपि अस्ति प्रसिद्धिः । सारस्वताः स्मार्तपरम्परानुशीलाः शिवः विष्णुः देवी सूर्यः गणेशः च इति पञ्चदेवतोपासकाः च । सर्वेषां सारस्वतानां पारम्परिकः धर्मः शैवधर्मः आसीत् । अन्तिमेषु कतिपयेषु शताब्देषु केचन सारस्वताः श्रीमन्मध्वाचार्यस्य वैष्णवं द्वैतदर्शनं स्वीकृतवन्तः । सम्पूर्णं इतिहासे, ते विविधेषु स्थानेषु प्रवासं कृतवन्तः, अधिकतया भारतस्य पश्चिमतटे दृश्यन्ते च (“Gaud Saraswat Brahmin”) ।

हिमालये भूरूपान्तरणस्य कारणात् सरस्वतीनदी शुष्का जाता । तदा सारस्वताः हरितचारणभूमिं प्रति प्रवासं कर्तुं निर्बन्धिताः अभवन् । केचन उत्तरस्यां दिशि काश्मीरं प्रति अगच्छन्, अन्ये तु पूर्वस्यां दिशि अगच्छन् । केचन कोङ्कणगोवाप्रदेशं प्रति गतवन्तः । उत्तरदिशि स्थितेभ्यः अन्येभ्यः सारस्वतसमूहात् तान् पृथक् कर्तुं एते गौडसारस्वताः अथवा दक्षिणात्यसारस्वताः इति मान्यतां प्राप्तवन्तः । गौडसारस्वताः अन्यैः हैन्दवैः सह गोवाराज्ये अनेकानि मन्दिराणि निर्मितवन्तः । 14 शताब्द्यां वैदेशिकाक्रमणेन तेषां शान्तियुतमस्तित्वं बाधितम् । परन्तु, यदा गोवाराज्यं हिन्दुविजयनगरराज्यस्य आधिपत्ये आगतम् तदा शान्तिः पुनः प्राप्ता । अयं कालः प्रायः 150 वर्षाणि यावत् अन्ववर्तत, यावत् प्रथमः ऐरोप्यनिवासिनः पोर्चुगल् जनाः भारतस्य पश्चिमतटे न आगताः । पोर्चुगीस् जनाः, धार्मिकराजनैतिकप्रयोजनार्थं 1510 तमे वर्षे गोवाप्रदेशं गृहीतवन्तः । पोर्चुगीस् शासनकाले, बलात् क्रैस्तवीयमतं प्रति धर्मान्तरणस्य, अत्यन्तं उत्पीडनस्य च कारणात्, सारस्वताः कानरा (कर्नाटकम्) केरल-महाराष्ट्र-प्रदेशान् प्रति पलायिताः । पोर्चुगल् जनाः सारस्वतानां मन्दिराणि ध्वंसं कृतवन्तः, तथापि केचन साहसिकजनाः स्वदेवतानां संरक्षणं कृत्वा, पश्चात् क्रमेण देवालयनिर्माणं कृतवन्तः । लेखकः बि एन् के शर्मा वदति

यत् गौडसारस्वताः 1540-60 वर्षे गोवाप्रदेशात् प्रवासं कृत्वा उत्तरकानरा दक्षिणकानरा मलबार् कोच्चिन् ट्रावन्कोर् इत्यादिषु तटीयमण्डलेषु, बेलगम्-मण्डलस्य केषुचित् भागेषु च अधिकतया निवसन्ति स्म इति (Sharma 577) ।

द्वैतदर्शनस्य गौडसारस्वतब्राह्मणसमाजोपरि प्रभावः

गौडसारस्वतब्राह्मणसमाजस्य इतिहासे जीवने आचारविचारेषु संस्कृत्योपरि जीवनमूल्येषु च द्वैतदर्शनस्य महान् प्रभावः अस्ति । वैष्णवमतपरिवर्तनम् मठसम्प्रदायः गोकर्णमठस्थापनम् काशीमठस्थापनम् जीवनविचाराचारधार्मिकसांस्कृतिकप्रभावः च इति मुख्यतया पञ्चबिन्दुरूपेण विचारः कृतः ।

1. शैवमतात् वैष्णवमतं प्रति परिवर्तनम्

उत्तरदेशतः दक्षिणं प्रति गौडसारस्वतब्राह्मणसमाजस्य प्रवासकाले ते द्वैतवेदान्तदर्शनम् अङ्गीकृतवन्तः । गोवाराज्ये गौडसारस्वताः मूलतः शैवमतविश्वासिनः आसन् । द्वैतदर्शनस्य संस्थापकः मध्वाचार्यः उत्तरभारतात् प्रत्यागमनयात्रायां गोवानगरं गतवान् । तस्य द्वैततत्त्वज्ञानेन आकर्षिताः बहवः गौडसारस्वताः वैष्णवमतं स्वीकृतवन्तः । उत्तरादिमठाधिपेन पद्मनाभतीर्थेन परिवर्तनस्य औपचारिकताः सम्पन्नाः कृताः । स्वस्य चातुर्मास्ये सः सासष्टि बर्देश् नगरयोः बहुसङ्ख्यकान् गौडसारस्वतान् परिवर्तितवान् । माध्वविजयः मध्वस्य गोवाभ्रमणम् दर्शयति । लेखकः बि एन् के शर्मणा गौडसारस्वतब्राह्मणसमाजस्य परिवर्तने उत्तरादिमठस्य भूमिकामधिकृत्य प्रतिपादितमस्ति ² ।

2. मठसम्प्रदायः

मठः समाजस्य आध्यात्मिकं दार्शनिकं च आश्रयः अस्ति । तत्र मठस्य मुख्यदेवः, तथा तस्य अनुयायिनः, मठस्य एकः अधिपतिः च भवन्ति । अधुना गौडसारस्वतसमाजस्य चत्वारः मठाः सन्ति । ते कव्लेमठः, चित्तपूरमठः, गोकर्णमठः, काशीमठः च इति । एतेषु चतुर्णां कालेमठः गौडसारस्वतसमाजस्य प्रथमः मठः भवति । पूर्वकाले अयं मठः वस्तुतः गौडपादाचार्यमठः इति उपाध्या प्रसिद्धः आसीत् । अस्य स्थापना क्रिस्तोरनन्तरं 740 तमे वर्षे गोवाराज्यस्य केलोशी इत्यस्य समीपे कुशस्थली इत्यत्र विवरणानन्दसरस्वतीमहाभागेन कृता । अयं महानुभावः आदिशङ्करेण सह गोविन्दभगवत्पादशिष्यः आसीत्, यः गौडपादस्य शिष्यः आसीत् । जनविश्वासः अस्ति अयं मठः गौडपादेन स्थापितः इति (“Gaud Saraswat Brahmin”) । एतेषु कालेषु पूर्णः समाजः शैवमतं मन्यते स्म । क्रिस्तोरनन्तरं 12 शतके मध्वाचार्यः स्वस्य दर्शनस्य प्रचारम् अकरोत्, फलतः गौडसारस्वतसमाजस्य एकः विशालः भागः वैष्णवमतं स्वीकृतवान् । पश्चात् क्रिस्तोरनन्तरं 1476 तमे वर्षे गोकर्णमठः तथा च 1542 तमे वर्षे काशीमठः इति वैष्णवसम्प्रदायमठद्वयस्य स्थापना

2 Avāptavān sa punariṣupātamasaramat ramāpatim sa paraśūrāmamādarāt sa śāṅkarapadadvijopahritamāpya govākhyagām..... , Madhvavijaya, X, 51&52.

अभवत् पश्चात् गौडपाडाचार्यमठस्य मुख्यालयः गोवाराज्यस्य कैवल्यपुरं वा काव्लेनगरं प्रति स्थानान्तरिकृतः, यतः 1546 तमे वर्षे पोर्चुगीस् शासकैः केलोशीमठः नष्टः अभवत्। तदनन्तरं गौडपाडाचार्यमठः कवलेमठः इति नाम्ना प्रसिद्धः अभवत्। पश्चात् केचन प्रादेशिककारणात् बृहत्तरात् काव्लेमठात् विभज्य 1708 तमे वर्षे चित्रपूर्मठः इति नूतनं मठं स्थापितवन्तः। एवं गौडसारस्वतसमाजस्य वैष्णवशैवसम्प्रदाययुक्तमठाः अभवन्।

3. गोकर्णमठस्थापनम्

मध्वाचार्येण द्वैतदर्शनस्य प्रसारार्थं उदुपीनगरे अष्टमठानां स्थापना कृता आसीत्। एतेषु एकः पालिमार्मठः आसीत्। भारतस्य पश्चिमतटे प्रसृतः गौडसारस्वताः वैष्णवसम्प्रदायस्य तत्त्वज्ञानम् अनुसरन् अस्य मठस्य आध्यात्मिकं मार्गनिर्देशं स्वीकृतवन्तः। ते मङ्गलूरुभटकल्लनगरयोः विशालानि निवासस्थानानि, अन्येषु तटीयनगरेषु लघुनिवासस्थानानि च निर्मितवन्तः। 15 शतके पलिमार्मठस्य नारायणतीर्थस्य प्रभावेण भटकल्लनगरे 1476 तमे वर्षे तेषां कृते पृथक् मठः स्थापितः (“Gokarna Math”)। अयं मठः पश्चात् गोकर्णं प्रति ततः गोवाराज्यस्य पर्टगलीनगरं प्रति स्थानान्तरितः, गोकर्णपर्टगलीमठः इति नाम्ना प्रसिद्धः अभवत्। गोवाराज्यस्य वैष्णवगौडसारस्वताः, उत्तरकानराप्रदेशस्य च अधिकांशाः जनाः तस्य अनुयायिनः आसन्। वीरविठ्ठलः मठस्य देवः अस्ति। केरलस्य दक्षिणकानरस्य च जनाः उत्तरादीमठे एव तिष्ठन्। शर्मा वदति यत् उत्तरकानरस्य माध्वव्यवस्थायाः अनुयायिनः उत्तरादीमठेन बहुधा प्रभाविताः नियन्त्रिताः च आसन् इति (Sharma 542)। गौडसारस्वतानां कृते पृथक् मठानां स्थापनायाः पूर्वं प्रायः उत्तरादीमठानुशासने एव गौडसारस्वताः आसन्।

4. काशीमठस्थापनम्

सर्वे केरलराज्यस्य गौडसारस्वताः वैष्णवाः तथा जयतीर्थस्य उत्तरादीमठस्य शिष्याः च आसन्। जयतीर्थस्य शिष्यद्वये अन्यतमः विभुदेन्द्रतीर्थः कुम्भकोणम् इत्यत्र मठं स्थापितवान् तथा च दक्षिणकानरस्य केरलस्य च गौडसारस्वताः कुम्भकोणमठं प्रति स्थानान्तरिताः। कोच्चिनिवासीगौडसारस्वतैः 1539-1540 तमे वर्षे चतुर्मास्यव्रतार्थं कुम्भकोणमठस्य कनिष्ठगुरुः विजयेन्द्रतीर्थः कोच्चिन् नगरं प्रति आमन्त्रितः, तस्मिन् समये एकस्य गौडसारस्वतबालकस्य सन्यासदीक्षानिर्वहणार्थं तेभ्यः प्रार्थितवन्तः। 1541 तमे वर्षे श्री हनुमन्तभक्तः चितः कुम्भकोणं प्रति नीतः। नूतनसन्यासिनः यादवेन्द्रतीर्थ इति नामकरणं कृतम्। सः क्रमेण 1542 तमे वर्षे वाराणसीनगरे नूतनस्थापितस्य काशीमठस्य अधिपः अभवत्। कोच्चिन् प्रदेशस्य जनाः काशीमठस्य कृते बनारस् नगरे भूमिं क्रेतुं साहाय्यं कृतवन्तः। काशीमठस्य पूज्यदेवः वेदव्यासः भवति। 1599 तमे वर्षे कुम्भकोणम् मठस्य सुधीन्द्रतीर्थः कोच्चिन् तिरुमलमन्दिरे वेङ्कटेश्वरस्य विग्रहं प्रतिष्ठापितवान्। क्रमेण केरलराज्यस्य अन्येषु भागेषु गौडसारस्वतैः भगवतः वेङ्कटेश्वरस्य विग्रहाः अधिदेवतारूपेण स्थापिताः, अयं वेङ्कटेश्वरः तिरुमलदेवः इत्यपि कथ्यते (“Kashi Math”)।

5. गौडसारस्वतेषु द्वैतदर्शनस्य दार्शनिकसांस्कृतिकप्रभावाः

द्वैतदर्शनं विष्णुं सेव्यरूपेण जीवं सेवकरूपेण च प्रतिपादयति । अतः तयोः स्वामीदाससम्बन्धः अस्ति । एवं भक्त्याधारिता विष्णुसेवा एव मानवजीवनस्य सर्वोच्चलक्ष्यं साधयितुं साधनम् अस्ति । सेवायाः त्रयः प्रकाराः सन्ति अङ्कनम् नामकरणम् भजनम् चेति ³ । आधुनिककाले अपि गौडसारस्वताः एतेषां त्रयाणां अनुसरणं जीवने कुर्वन्ति ।

5.1 अङ्कनम्

अङ्कनम् भगवतः विष्णोः शस्त्राणां स्वशरीरे धारणं भवति ⁴ । इदं विष्णोः विचारान् स्मारयितुं, सर्वोच्चलक्ष्यं प्राप्तुं च साहाय्यं करोति । चक्र-शङ्खा-गदा-पद्ममिति चतुर्णां धारणं गोपीचन्दनसहितं नित्यं भवति । चान्द्रमानस्य आषाढमासस्य शुक्लपक्षैकादशी सामान्यतः अस्य मुद्राधारणसमारोहस्य शुभदिनम् इति मन्यते । तस्मिन् दिने सुदर्शनहवनं कृत्वा तस्मिन् तप्तताम्रमुद्राः शरीरे स्वीक्रियन्ते । अयं समारोहः गृहेषु कर्तुं शक्यते, परन्तु अधुना मठाधिपस्य मार्गदर्शने प्रचलन्नस्ति ।

5.2 नामकरणम्

संस्कारदृष्ट्या षोडशसंस्कारेषु एकं भवति नामकरणम् । वैष्णवाः पुत्रादीनां नामकरणं विष्णोः नामधेयैः कुर्वन्ति । भगवान् विष्णोः अनेकानि रूपाणि सन्ति यथा परः, व्युहः, अर्चावतारः, अन्तर्यामी इत्यादयः । एतेषु व्युहः चतुर्विंशतिप्रकाराः । ते केशवः, नारायणः, माधवः, गोविन्दः, विष्णुः, मधुसूदनः, त्रिविक्रमः, वामनः, श्रीधरः, हृषीकेशः, पद्मनाभः, दामोदरः, संकर्षणः, वासुदेवः, प्रद्युम्नः, अनिरुद्धः, पुरुषोत्तमः, अधोक्षजः, नरसिंहः, अच्युतः, जनार्दनः, उपेन्द्रः, हरिः, श्रीकृष्णः च इति । भगवत्सेवा दृष्ट्या पुत्रादीनां केशवादिनाम्ना व्यवहारः भगवत्प्रेमानुस्मरणार्थमिति सर्वदर्शनसंग्रहे उक्तम् ⁵ ।

5.3 भजनम्

भजनम् इत्यस्य सामान्यतः आराधनम् इति अर्थः भवति । इदं मनसा वाचा कर्मणा च इति त्रिविधं भवति पुनः दशप्रकारेषु उपविभक्तम् च । तत्तु सत्यभाषणं, हानिरहितभाषणं, उत्तमभाषणं, वेदाध्ययनम्, दानम्, परोपकारः, परपरिरक्षणम्, कृपादृष्टिः, ईश्वरजिज्ञासा, ईश्वरस्य विषये एकाग्रता च ⁶ । एतेषां दशानां आचरणं ईश्वरे समर्पणं च भजनम् । गौडसारस्वतानां जीवने एतेषां परिपालने अतीव श्रद्धा द्रष्टुं शक्यते ।

3 Sā ca sevā añkananāmakaraṇabhajanabhedāt trividhā. Sarvadarsanasamgraha, p.225.

4 Tatrāñkanam nārāyaṇayudhādīnam tadrūpasmarāṇarthamapekṣitārtha sidhyartham ca. Sarvadarsanasamgraha, p.225.

5 Nāmkaṇam putrādīnam keśavādīnāmna vyavahārah. Sarvada tannāmā nusmarāṇārtham. Sarvadarsanasamgraha, p.227.

6 Bhajanam daśavidham nārāyaṇe samarpaṇam bhajanam. Sarvadarsanasamgraha, p.227.

5.4 गोपीचन्दनधारणम्

गोपीचन्दनधारणं तथा पञ्चमुद्राधारणम् सारस्वतानां सन्ध्यावन्दनेन साकं नित्यकर्म भवति। गोपिचन्दनं कर्णाटकराज्ये उपलभ्यमानमृत्तिकाविशेषः भवति। सन्ध्यावन्दनात् पूर्वं गोपीचन्दनस्य शरीरभागेषु धारणविधिरस्ति। एतत् सामान्येन वैष्णवानां धर्मः तथा चिह्नमपि भवति। शैवानां भस्मधारणं धर्मः तथा चिह्नमपि भवति। वैष्णवमतं प्रति परिवर्तनात् पूर्वं गौडसारस्वतानां भस्मधारणं एव आसीत् यत् शैवानां चिह्नं वर्तते। पञ्चमुद्राधारणं गोपीचन्दनमुपयुज्य अष्टाक्षरमन्त्रेण (ओम् नमो नारायणाय) सह शस्त्रचतुष्कस्य धारणं भवति।

5.5 एकादशी तथा द्वादशस्तोत्रपारायणम्

एकादशी प्रायेण चान्द्रमासस्य 11 तमः दिवसः भवति। एकस्य चान्द्रमासस्य द्वौ पक्षौ शुक्लः कृष्णः च इति। एवं मासे एकादशीद्वयं भवति। अस्मिन् दिने उपवासः, ध्यानं, विष्णुचिन्तनं च विहितम् अस्ति। एकादश्यां गौडसारस्वताः व्रतरूपेण सम्पूर्णरात्रौ जागरणं कृत्वा ध्यानं भजनं इत्यादीनि आचरन्ति। निद्रा न भविष्यति, तत् हरिजागरणम् इति कथ्यते। तत्र श्रीमन्मध्वाचार्यविरचितस्य द्वादशस्तोत्रपारायणं अतीवप्राधान्येन गौडसारस्वतैः क्रियते। अस्मिन् द्वादशाध्यायैः 126 श्लोकाः सन्ति। उदुपीश्रीकृष्णविग्रहप्रतिष्ठापने विरचितमेतत् स्तोत्रम् इति मन्यते।

5.6 हरिकथाश्रवणम् एवं हरिसंकीर्तनम्

हरिकथाश्रवणं तथा हरिसंकीर्तनं गौडसारस्वतानां जीवने अत्यन्तमपेक्षणीये। हरिकथाश्रवणमिति प्रायेण श्रीमन्महाभागवतस्य श्रवणम् भवति। हरिकथा इति गौडसारस्वतानां किञ्चित् कलाविशेषः अपि अस्ति। एतत् गद्यपद्यकाव्यैः मिश्रितं सांस्कृतिककलारूपं भवति। भागवतात् तथा अन्यैः आधिकारिकग्रन्थेभ्यः च स्वीकृतभगवत्कथानां प्रतिपादनं कलारूपेण भवति। हरिसंकीर्तने नामजपः भजनम् स्तोत्रपारायणम् इत्यादीनि भवन्ति। भगवद्गीतायाः व्याख्यायां मध्वाचार्यः ईश्वरज्ञानस्य साधनरूपेण एतयोः द्वयोः उल्लेखं करोति 7।

एवं गौडसारस्वतब्राह्मणसमाजस्य इतिहासभूमिशास्त्रबौद्धिकसांस्कृतिकमण्डलानां निरीक्षणेन अध्ययनेन च निरीक्षणस्य तेषु द्वैतदर्शनस्य प्रभावम् अवगन्तुं शक्यते यत् तेषां इतिहासे धार्मिकव्यवस्थायां संस्कृतौ आचारसंहितासु च प्रतिबिम्बते

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कारकं विभक्त्यर्थश्च

डा.के.नारायणन्¹

करोतीति कारकम् । क्रियानिर्वर्तकं कारकम् । क्रिया पूर्वापरभावक्रमेण प्रतीयमाना साध्यस्वभावा च । कारकं तु सिद्धस्वभावं द्रव्यवत् प्रतीयमानं साधनम् । कारकाणि षट्-कर्ता, कर्म, करणं, सम्प्रदानम्, अपादानम्, अधिकरणं चेति ।

1. कर्तृकारकम्

तत्र स्वातन्त्र्येणान्येषां कारकाणां प्रवर्तकः कर्ता [* सिद्धान्तकौमुदी](स्वतन्त्रः कर्ता 1-4-54/559) । धात्वर्थव्यापाराश्रयः स्वतन्त्रः । फलं व्यापारश्चेति द्वयं धात्वर्थः । यदुद्दिश्य व्यापार आरभ्यते यत्सिद्धौ च व्यापारः परिसमाप्यते तत् फलम्, यथा विविलत्स्यादि । णिजन्ते कर्ता द्विविधः प्रयोज्यकर्ता प्रयोजककर्ता चेति । यज्ञदत्तः पचति, देवदत्तो यज्ञदत्तेन पाचयतीत्यत्र देवदत्तः प्रयोजककर्ता यज्ञदत्तः प्रयोज्यकर्ता । प्रयोजककर्तुः हेतुरित्यपि संज्ञा वर्तते *(तत्प्रयोजको हेतुश्च 1-4-55/2575) । कर्तृभिन्नः फलाश्रयः कर्म । अकर्मकधातुषु फलं व्यापारश्च कर्तर्येव वर्तते । तत्र परत्वात् कर्तृसंज्ञेव न कर्मसंज्ञा ।

2. कर्मकारकम्

कर्म द्विधा ईप्सिततमम् (535/49-4-1) अनीप्सितं (538-50-4-1) चेति । निर्वृत्ये विकार्यं प्राप्यं चेति ईप्सिततमं कर्म त्रिविधम् । द्वेष्यम् उदासीनं चेत्यनीप्सितं कर्म द्विविधम् । ओदनं पचति, काष्ठं भस्म करोति, आदित्यं पश्यति, विषं भुङ्क्ते, मुखं व्यादाय स्वपितीति क्रमेणोदाहरणानि । दोग्धिं याचते इत्यादीनां प्रधानकर्मणा सम्बद्धम् अपादानादिकं कर्म वा भवति *(अकथितं च 539/51-4-1) । गोपो गां पयो दोग्धिं, वामनो बलि वसुधां याचते, अजां ग्रामं नयति इत्याद्युदाहरणम् । गोरिति बलेरिति च पञ्चम्यपि साध्वी ।

गत्यर्थानां ज्ञानार्थानां, भक्षणार्थानां, शब्दकर्मणाम्, अकर्मकाणां च धातूनां केवलक्रियायाम् (अप्यन्ते) कर्ता प्रयोजकक्रियायां (प्यन्ते) कर्म भवति (गति-बुद्धि प्रत्यवसानार्थ-शब्दकर्मकर्मकाणामणि कर्ता स णौ *(540/52-4-1) । पिता पुत्रं पाठशालां गमयति, आचार्यो माणवकं धर्मं बोधयति, माता पुत्रं मोदकं भोजयति, गुरुः

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शिष्यं वेदमध्यापयति, भाता शिशु शाययति इति क्रमेणोदाहरणम् । हारयति कारयति-
अनयोः प्रयोज्यकर्ता कर्म वा स्यात् * (हक्रोरन्यतरस्याम् 541/53-4-1) । देवदत्तः भृत्यं
/ भृत्येन कटं हारयति / कारयति ।

अधिरोते, अध्यास्ते अधितिष्ठति, अभिनिविशते, उपवसति. अनुवसति, अधिवसति,
आवसति एतेषामधिकरणं कर्म भवति (अधिशीङ्स्थासां कर्म, अभिनिविशश्च,
उपान्वध्याङ्वसः 544-542/48-46-4-1) । हरिः वैकुण्ठम् अधिशेते इत्याद्युदा-
हरणम् । पापेऽभिनिवेशः इत्यत्र तु सप्तम्येव ।

अकर्मकधातुभिर्योगे देशः, कालो, भावो, गन्तव्योऽध्वा च कर्म स्यात् (वा
1104+1103) । देवदत्तः कुरून् स्वपिति, मासमास्ते, गोदोहमास्ते, क्रोशमास्ते पर्वतः ।

3. करणकारकम्

क्रियानिष्पत्तौ प्रकृष्टोपकारकं कारकं करणं स्यात् * (साधकतमं करणम् 1-4-
42/560) । यन्निष्ठव्यापारात् समनन्तरं क्रियाया निष्पत्तिः तत् करणम् । तच्च व्यापारवत्
क्रियान्वयि च । एकस्य धर्मस्याभावे हेतुर्भवति । यथा दण्डेन घट इत्यत्र क्रियान्वयाभावात्
दण्डो न करणम् । पुण्येन दृष्टो हरिरित्यत्र पुण्यं व्यापाराभावात् न करणम् । किन्तु हेतुरेव ।
दिवु धातोः करणं कर्म वा भवति * (दिवः कर्म च 1-4-43/562) । अक्षान् / अक्षैर्दिव्यति ।

4. सम्प्रदानकारकम्

दानक्रियायाः कर्मणा सम्बन्धमिष्टं कारकं (प्रतिग्रहीतृ) सम्प्रदानं स्यात् * (कर्मणा
यमभिप्रैति स सम्प्रदानम् 1-4-32/570) । गृहिणी ब्रह्मचारिणे भिक्षां ददाति, शिष्यो
गुरवे दक्षिणां ददाति, विप्रः सूर्याय अर्घ्यं ददाति । रुच्यर्थानां प्रयोगे प्रीत्याश्रयः सम्प्रदानं
स्यात् * (रुच्यर्थानां प्रीयमाणः 1-4-33/571) । मोदको बालाय रोचते / स्वदते
(मोदककर्तृकप्रीतेराश्रयो बालः) ।

श्लाघते, हुते, तिष्ठते, शपते इत्येतेषामर्थविशेषे प्रयोगे बोधयितुमिष्टो जनः सम्प्रदानम्
* (1-4-34/572) । गोपी स्मरात् कृष्णाय श्लाघते, श्लाघया अभीप्सितं (स्वानुरागं) तं
बोधयतीत्यर्थः । हुते हुत्या निह्वेन स्वाभिप्रायं प्रकाशयति, तिष्ठते स्थितिविशेषेण बोधयति,
शपते उपालम्भेन बोधयति ।

धारयति = (ऋणं धत्ते) अस्य प्रयोगे उत्तमर्णः (ऋणस्य दाता) सम्प्रदानम्
* (धारेरुत्तमर्णः 1-4-35/573) । यज्ञदत्तः देवदत्ताय रूप्यकशतं धारयति । स्पृहयतीत्यस्य
कर्म प्रायेण सम्प्रदानं भवति * (स्पृहेरीप्सितः 1-4-36/574) । पुष्पेभ्यः स्पृहयति ।
ईप्सिततमत्वविवक्षायां तु पुष्पाणि स्पृहयति ।

क्रुध्यति, दुह्यति, ईर्ष्यति, असूयति एषां प्रयोगे कोपविषयो जनः सम्प्रदानम् * (1-4-
37/575) । दैत्यः हरये क्रुध्यति इत्यादि ।

राध्यति, ईक्षते अनयोः शुभाशुभप्रश्नार्थे प्रयोगे जिज्ञासाविषयो जनः सम्प्रदानं स्यात् *(राधीक्ष्योर्यस्य विप्रश्नः 1-4-39/577)। कृष्णाय राध्यति, ईक्षते वा ।परिक्रयणस्य करणं वा सम्प्रदानं भवति *(परिक्रयणे सम्प्रदानमन्यतरस्याम् 14-44/580)। शताय शतेन परिक्रीणीते (परिक्रयणं नाम भूत्या वेतनेन किञ्चित्कालपर्यन्तं भृत्यत्वेन स्वीकरणम्, प्रकृते शतं करणम्)। क्रयणे तु करणमेव, अरुणया पिङ्गाक्ष्या एकहायन्या सोमं क्रीणाति ।

5. अपादानकारकम्

विश्लेषजनकक्रियायाम् अवधिभूतोऽर्थः अपादानं स्यात् *(ध्रुवमपायेऽपादानम् 586/24-4-1)। वृक्षात् पर्णं पतति। द्वयोः विश्लेषे प्रायेणैकं स्थिरं भवति यथा वृक्षः। तदपादानम्। क्वचित् तदप्यस्थिरं भवति यथा धावतोऽश्वात् भटः पततीति । तथापि भटपतनन्य अवधिर्भवतीत्यश्वस्य अपादानसंज्ञा भवति ।भयार्थानां रक्षणार्थानां च प्रयोगे भयस्य निदानमपादानं स्यात्*(भीतार्थानां भयहेतुः 588/25-4-1)। बालः सर्पाद् बिभेति । हरिः गजं नक्रात् लायते

परापूर्वस्य जयतेः प्रयोगे असह्योऽर्थोऽपादानं स्यात् *(पराजेरसोढः 589/26-4-1) | अध्ययनात् पराजयते । अध्ययनक्लेशं न सहते इत्यर्थः ।

वारणार्थानां धातूनां प्रयोगे (कर्मणः) ईप्सितोऽर्थः अपादानं स्यात् *(वारणार्थानामीप्सितः 590/27-4-1)। कर्षकः यवेभ्यो गां वारयति ।येनात्मनो दर्शनमनिच्छन्नन्तर्दधाति तदपादानम् *(अन्तर्था येनादर्शनमिच्छति 591/28-4-1)। मातुर्निलीयते कृष्णः। माता मां मा द्राक्षीदिति अन्तर्हितो भवति ।नियमपूर्वकविद्याग्रहणे उपदेशा अपादानं स्यात् *(आख्यातोपयोगे 592/29-4-1) । गुरोर्वेदमधीते । उत्पद्यमानस्योपादानं कारणम् अपादानं स्यात् *(जनिकर्तुः प्रकृतिः 593/30-4-1)। बीजादङ्गो जायते, गोमयाद् वृश्चिको जायते ।प्रथमदर्शनस्थानमपादानं भवति। *(भुवः प्रभवः 594/31-4-1) हिमवतो गङ्गा प्रभवति । हिमवान्नोपादानकारणमिति पूर्वसूत्रेण न सिध्यति ।

6. अधिकरणकारकम्

कर्तृद्वारा कर्मद्वारा वा क्रियाया आधारः अधिकरणं भवति *(आधारोऽधिकरणम् 1-4-5/632)। तत् त्रिविधम् औपश्लेषिकम्, अभिव्यापकं, वैषयिकं चेति। बालः कटे (तदेकदेशे) शेते, तिले (तमभिव्याप्य) तैलमस्ति, गुरी (तद्विषये) भक्तिरस्तीति यथाक्रममुदाहरणं कर्तृद्वारा । स्थाल्यां तण्डुलं पचति, सर्वस्मिन् ईश्वरं पश्यति, पुत्रे वात्सल्यं प्रकटयतीति कर्मद्वारा ।

कारकविभक्तयः

कर्तारं करणे च तृतीया विभक्तिर्भवति (कर्तृकरणयोस्तृतीया 561/18-3-2)। चैत्रेण काष्ठः तण्डुलः पच्यते इत्युदाहरणम्। अन्नं चैत्रः कर्ता, काष्ठं करणम्।

शब्दान्तरेणानभिहितः कारकार्य एव विभक्त्या बोध्यते (अनभिहिते 536/1-3-2)। अभिधानं च तिङ्ङुत्तन्द्रितसमासैर्भवति। कर्तरि प्रयोगे कर्ता, कर्मणि प्रयोगे कर्म च तिङ्प्रत्ययेनाभिधीयते (यत्न धातुना युक्तस्य प्रत्ययस्यार्थः कर्ता स कर्तरि प्रयोगः, यत्न कर्म स कर्मणि)। तेन चैत्रस्तण्डुलं पचतीत्यन्त्र तिङा कर्तुरुक्तत्वात् कर्तरि तृतीया न भवति। किन्तु प्रातिपदिकार्ये प्रथमा।

कर्मणि द्वितीयाविभक्तिर्भावात् *(537/2-3-2)। चैत्रस्तण्डुलं पचति। चैत्रेण तण्डुलः पच्यते /पक्वा इत्यत्र तु तिङ्प्रत्ययेन क्तप्रत्ययेन च कर्मणोऽभिहितत्वाद् द्वितीया न। अपि तु प्रातिपदिकार्ये प्रथमा।

सञ्जानीते इत्यस्य कर्मणि तृतीया वा भवति *(संज्ञोऽन्यतरस्यां कर्मणि -3-2 567/22)। पित्रा / पितरं सञ्जानीते। अप्रयुज्यमानस्य (गम्यमानस्य) तुमुन्नन्तस्य कर्मणि चतुर्थी भवति *(क्रियार्थोपपदस्य च कर्मणि स्थानिनः 581/14-3-2)। पुष्पेभ्यो (पुष्पाण्याहर्तुं) याति। अनादरे द्योत्ये मन्यतेः कर्मणि चतुर्थी वा स्यात् *(मन्यकर्मण्यनादरे विभाषाप्राणिषु 584/17-3-2)। न त्वां तृणाय / तृणं मन्ये। नौ, काक, अन्न, शुक, सुगाल एतेभ्यश्चतुर्थी न भवति (या 1464)।

शरीरपरिस्पन्दपूर्वकगमनक्रियायाः अध्यभिन्ने कर्मणि द्वितीया चतुर्थी वा स्यात् *(गत्यर्थकर्मणि द्वितीयाचतुर्थ्यर्थी चेष्टायामनध्वनि 585/2.3.12)। ग्रामं / ग्रामाय गच्छति। पन्थानं गच्छतीत्यन्त्र न चतुर्थी, अनध्वनीति निषेधात्। मनसा काशीं गच्छतीत्यत्र न चतुर्थी चेष्टाभावात्। ल्यबन्तस्याप्रयोगे कर्मणि पञ्चमी स्यात् (वा 1474)। प्रासादात् (प्रासादमारुह्य) प्रेक्षते।

इन्नन्तस्य क्तान्तस्य कर्मणि सप्तमी स्यात् (वा 1485) अधीती व्याकरणे (अधीतमिति क्तान्तं, तस्मादिनिप्रत्ययः)। कृदन्तेन योगे कर्तरी कर्माणि च षष्ठी स्यात् *(कर्मणोः कृति 623/2.3.63)। कृष्णस्य कृतिरिति कर्तरि षष्ठी, जगतः सृष्टिरिति कर्मण षष्ठी। यत्न कर्तृकर्मणोरुभयोः प्रयोगः तत्र कर्मणि षष्ठी *(उभयप्राप्तौ कर्मणि 624/66-3-2)। कर्तरि तू तृतीया। अगोपेन गवां दोह आश्चर्यः।

कृत्यप्रत्ययान्तेन योगे कर्तरि षष्ठी वा भवति *(कृत्यानां कर्तरि वा 629/71-3-2)। गन्तव्या तक्ते / त्वया वसतिः।

प्रतिपदविधाना षष्ठी

अस्याः षष्ठ्याः समासो न भवति।

स्मरणार्थानां, दयधातोरीशधातोश्च कर्मणि षष्ठी स्यात् *(अधीगर्धदयेशां कर्मणि 2 - 3 -52/613)। मातुः स्मृति, सर्पिषो दयते, मधुन ईष्टे। प्रतिपद्यत्ने (गुणाधाने) कृजः कर्मणि षष्ठी स्यात् *(614/53-3-2)। एधोदकस्योपस्करते।

भावकर्तृकाणां रुजार्थानां कर्मणि षष्ठी स्यात् *(रुजार्थानां भाववचनानामज्वरे: 615/54-3-2)। रोगः चौरस्य रुजति। ज्वरति सन्तापयतीत्यनयोः कर्मणि षष्ठी न (वा 1507)।

आशंसाथै नाथधातोः कर्मणि षष्ठी स्यात् *(आशिषि नाथः 616/55-3-2)। सर्पिषो नाथते आसाहो। (सर्पिमें भूयादित्याशास्ते)। हिंसार्थानां जासयतीत्यादीनां कर्मणि षष्ठी स्यात् *(जासिनिप्रहणनाटक्राथपिषां हिंसायाम् 617/56-3-2)। चौरस्योज्जासयतीत्यादि। द्युते क्रयविक्रयव्यवहारे चार्थे व्यवहरति पणते दीव्यतीत्येतेषां कर्मणि षष्ठी स्यात् *(यवहृपणोः समर्थयोः, दिवस्तदर्थस्य 619+618/58+57-3-2)। शतस्य व्यवहरतीत्यादि। उपसृष्टस्य दिवः कर्मणि द्वितीया षष्ठी वा स्यात् *(विभाषोपसर्गे 620/59-3-2) शतं /शतस्य प्रतिदीव्यति। प्रतिपदविधाना षष्ठी न समस्यते। तेन मातुः स्मरणमित्यादौ न समासः।

कृद्योगषष्ठ्याः प्रतिषेधः

लकारादेशाः शतृशानजादयः, उप्रत्ययः, उकप्रत्ययः, क्त्वा, तुमुन्, निष्ठासंज्ञकौ क्तक्तवतु, खल्, युच्, तृन् - एतदन्तौंगे षष्ठी न भवति *(न लोकाव्ययनिष्ठाखलर्थतृनाम् 627/69 .2.3)। ओदनं पचन्, ओदनं पचमानः, अन्नं बुभुक्षुः, दैत्यान् घातुकः, ओदनं भुक्त्वा, ओदनं भोक्तुम्, चैत्रेण कृतम्, ओदनं भुक्तवान्, भवता घटः सुकरः, भवता सोमः सुपानः, कटान् कर्ता। अत्र चैत्रेण, भवता इत्यत्र कर्तरी षष्ठी न, अन्यत्र कर्मणि षष्ठी च न। लक्ष्म्याः कामुक इति कामुकयोगे षष्ठी भवति (वा 1519)।

प्रतिषिद्धायाः षष्ठ्याः पुनर्विधानम् :-

मतिबुद्धिपूजार्थेभ्यश्च *(3089/188-2-3) इति वर्तमानकाले क्तो विधीयते, क्तोऽधिकरणे च श्रीव्यगतिप्रत्यवसानार्थेभ्यः* (3087/76-4-3) इत्यधिकरणे क्तो विधीयते, नपुंसके भावे क्तः *(3090/114-3-3) इति भावे क्तो विधीयते। एतदन्तौंगे कर्तरि षष्ठी भवति *(क्तस्य च वर्तमाने, अधिकरणवाचिनश्च 626,625/68-67-3-2 + वा. 1514) राज्ञोऽभिमतः / ज्ञातः / पूजितः, मुकुन्दस्यासितम्, गतं तिरश्चीनमनूरुसारथेः।

यस्मात् क्तान्ताद् इनिप्रत्ययो भवति तस्य कर्मणि सप्तमी स्यात् (या 1485)। अशीती व्याकरणे, अर्चिती हरी।

*सम्प्रदाने चतुर्थी (570/13-3-2) अपादाने पञ्चमी *(587/28-3-2) च भवति। तथैवोदाहृतम्। अधिकरणे सप्तमी भवति *(सप्तम्यधिकरणे च 633/36-3-2)। कटे शेते इत्यादि। कालविशेषद्योतकात् नक्षत्रवाचकशब्दाद् अधिकरणे तृतीया वा स्यात् *(नक्षत्रे च लुपि 642/45-3-2)। मूलेन / मूले आवाहयद्देवीम्, श्रवणेन / श्रवणे विसर्जयेत्। ल्यब्लोपे अधिकरणे पञ्चमी स्यात् (वा. 1475)। आसनात् (आसने उपविश्य) प्रेक्षते।

कर्मप्रवचनीयाः

कर्मप्रवचनीयाः *(546/83-4-1) इति प्रादीनां (उपसर्गणाम्) क्वचित् उपसर्गसंज्ञापवादभूता कर्मप्रवचनीयसंज्ञा विधीयते। तद्योगे प्रायेण द्वितीया भवति* (कर्मप्रवचनीययुक्ते द्वितीया 2-3-8/548)। हेतुहेतुमद्भावे द्योत्ये अनुः कर्मप्रवचनीयः *(अनुर्लक्षणे 1-4-84/547) 1 जपमनु प्रावर्षत् । वृष्टिं प्रति जपस्य हेतुत्वं द्योत्पते। तृतीयार्थं साहित्ये द्योत्येऽनुः कर्मप्रवचनीयः *(549/85-4-1)। सीमानमनुबद्धा सेना। सीमरेखया सह सम्बन्ध स्थापितेत्यर्थः। निकर्षे द्योत्येऽनुः, निकर्षे उत्कर्षे च द्योत्ये उपश्च कर्मप्रवचनीया *(हीने, उपोऽधिके च 1551+550/87+86-4-)। अनु / उप हरिं सुराः, हरेहीनाः सुरा इत्यर्थः ।

उत्कर्षार्थकोपशब्दयोगे सप्तमी भवति (यस्मादधिकं यस्य चेश्वरवचनं तत्र सप्तमी -3-2 645/9)। उप खायँ द्रोणः, खार्यपेक्षया अधिक इत्यर्थः । प्रतियोगिवाचकाद् विभक्तिः। लक्षणेत्यम्भूताख्यानभागवीप्सासु प्रतिपर्यनवः *(552/90-4-1) भागवर्जितेषु एष्वर्थेषु अभिश्च *(553/91-4-1) कर्मप्रवचनीयः। लक्षणं चिह्नम्, इत्थंभूतस्य = अवस्थाविशेषं प्राप्तस्य आख्यानं = कथनम्, भागः अंशः, वीप्सा = सर्वव्यक्तिसम्बन्धः। वृक्षं प्रति विद्योतते विद्युत्, विष्णुं प्रति भक्तः, विष्णुं प्रति लक्ष्मीः, वृक्षं वृक्षे प्रति सिञ्चति इति क्रमेणोदाहरणम् । अभिपर्यनुयोगे चैवम् ।

वर्जने अपपरी, मर्यादाभिविध्योराड् च कर्मप्रवचनीयाः* (अपपरी वर्जने, आङ्गुर्यादाभिविध्योः 7-596/89-88-4-1)। एतैर्योगे पञ्चमी स्यात् *(पञ्चम्यपायरिभिः 598/10-3-2)। अप लिंगर्तेभ्यः, परि परि लिंगर्तेभ्यो वृष्टो देवा, आपरितोषाद् विदुषाम्, आजन्मनः शाक्यमशिक्षितः (अवधि विना मर्यादा, अवधिना सहाभिविधिः) ।

स्वस्वामिभावसम्बन्धे अधिः कर्मप्रवचनीयाः *(अधिरीश्वरे 644/97-4-1)। एतद्योगे सप्तमी स्यात् *(645/9-3-2)। इह स्ववाचकात् स्वामिवाचकाच्च पर्यायेण सप्तमी। अधि भुवि रामः, अधि रामे भूरिति । कर्मप्रवचनीयसंज्ञया गत्युपसर्गसंज्ञयोर्बाधात् तत्प्रयुक्तं कार्यं न भवति। यथा वृक्षं वृक्षं प्रति सिञ्चतीत्यत्र षत्वं न। अध्यागच्छतीत्यन्त्र गतिप्रयुक्तः स्वरो न। तस्मात् क्वचिदेतदर्थमेव कर्मप्रवचनीयसंज्ञा विधीयते। न तत्र विभक्तिविशेषः ।

उपपदविभक्तिः

उभयतः, सर्वतः, धिक्, उपर्युपरि, अध्यधि, अधोधा, अभितः, परिता, समया, निकषा, हा, प्रति, एभिः योगे द्वितीया भवति (वा. 43-1442)। कृष्णम् उभयतः / सर्वतः / अभितः / परितः / गोपाः, ग्रामं समया / निकषा, लोकम् उपर्युपरि / अध्यधि / अधोधा इत्याद्युदाहरणम् । अन्तरा अन्तरेण एतद्योगे द्वितीया *(545/4-3-2)। अङ्गनामङ्गना-मन्तरा माथवो, माधवं माधवं चान्तरेणाङ्गनाः। एनबन्तनेन योगे द्वितीया स्यात् *(-3-2 610/31)। दक्षिणेन वृक्षवाटिकामालापः श्रूयते ।

सहार्थेन शब्देन योगे तृतीया स्यात् *(सहयुक्तेऽप्रधाने 2-3-19/564) । पिता पुत्रेण सह / समं / साधे / गतः । नमः, स्वस्ति, स्वाहा, स्वधा, अलं, वषट् एतैर्योगे चतुर्थी स्यात् *(583/16-3-2) । नमो देवेभ्यः, स्वस्ति प्रजाभ्यः, अग्नये स्वाहा, पितृभ्यः स्वधा, हरिं दैत्येभ्यः, शिखायै वषट् I अन्यत्, आरात्, इतरत्, ऋते, दिक्शब्दाः (पूर्वोत्तरादयः) अञ्चत्तरपदाः (प्राक्प्रत्यगादयः) आजन्तः, आह्वन्तः, एतैर्योगे पञ्चमी स्यात् । *(-2 595/29-3) अन्यत्र भूताच्च भव्याच्च, आराद्धनात्, इतरो देवदत्तात्, ऋते कृशानोः, ग्रीष्मात् पूर्वी वसन्तः, प्रागन्तरिक्षगमनात् स्वमपत्यजातम्, दक्षिणा ग्रामात्, दक्षिणाहि ग्रामात् ।

पृथग्-विना-नानाभिर्योगे पञ्चमी तृतीया वा स्यात्*(603/32-3-2) । देवदत्तात् / देवदत्तेन पृथक् । विनायोगे द्वितीयापि दृश्यते । रामं / रामेण / रामाद् विना । दूरान्तिकथैर्योगे पञ्चमी षष्ठी वा स्यात् *(2-3-34/611) ग्रामाद् / ग्रामस्य दूरं / विप्रकृष्टम् / अन्तिकं / समीपम् । अतसर्थप्रत्ययेन योगे षष्ठी स्यात् *(609/30-3-2) । ग्रामस्य दक्षिणतः / उत्तरतः / पुरः / पुरस्तात् । तुल्यार्थैर्योगे षष्ठी तृतीया वा स्यात् *(630/72-3-2) । रामस्य / रामेण तुल्यः / सदृशः / समः । तुलोपमाभ्यां योगे तृतीया न भवति । रामस्य तुला / उपमा नास्ति ।

साध्वसाधुयोगे सप्तमी स्यात् (वा 1486) । कृष्णो मातरि साधुः, मातुलेऽसाधुः । स्वामी, ईश्वरः, अधिपतिः, दायादः, साक्षी, प्रतिभूः, प्रसूतः एभिर्योगे सप्तमी षष्ठी वा स्यात् *(636/39-3-2) । गवां / गोषु स्वामीत्यादि । आयुक्तः (तत्परः) कुशलः आभ्यां योगे षष्ठी सप्तमी वा । आयुक्तः हरिपूजने / हरिपूजनस्य । कुशलः कटकरणे / कटकरणस्य ।

विभक्तीनामर्थविशेषः

कालवाचकादध्ववाचकाच्च नैरन्तर्ये द्योत्ये द्वितीया भवति (2-3-5/558) । मासमधीते । क्रोशं कुटिला नदी । फैलप्राप्तौ सत्यामेतद्विषये तृतीया भवति । वर्षेणाष्टाध्यायधीता ।

ज्ञातकालक्रियाया अज्ञातकालक्रियाया बोधने ज्ञातकालक्रियावाचकात् कर्तृकर्माथककृदन्तात् सप्तमी भवति *(यस्य च भावेन भावलक्षणम् 2-3-37/634) । इयं सत्सप्तमीत्युच्यते । शापान्तो मे भुजगशयनादुत्थिते शाङ्गपाणौ । दृष्टे सूर्ये पुनरपि भवान् वाहयेदध्वशेषम् । अनादरे द्योत्ये एतद्विषये षष्ठी च स्यात् *(षष्ठी चानादरे -3-2 635/38) । रुदति / रुदतः प्राब्राजीत् (रुदन्तं पुत्रादिकमनादृत्य) ।

हेत्वर्थे तृतीया स्यात् *(568/23-3-2) । दण्डेन घटा, पुण्येन दृष्टो हरिः । फलमपि हेतुर्भवति, अध्ययनेन वसति । अवयविनो वैकृतस्य हेतुभूतादवयवात् तृतीया *(येनाङ्गविकारः 565/20-3-2) । अक्षणा काणः, पादेन पङ्गुः । प्रयोजन-वाचकात् चतुर्थी भवति । तादर्थ्ये चतुर्थी वाच्या (वा. 1458) । तदर्थं = प्रयोजनम् । मुक्तये हरिं

भजति । मुक्त्युपकारकं हरिभजनमित्यर्थः ।

तुमर्थे प्रयुज्यमानाद् भावप्रत्ययान्ताच्चतुर्थी स्यात् *(तुमर्थाच्च भातववचनात् -3-2 582 /15) । यागाय (याष्टुं) याति । हेत्वर्थे क्यचित् पञ्चमी भवति (विभाषा गुणेऽस्त्रियाम् 2-3-25/602) । जाड्याद् बद्धः, पर्वतो , वह्निमान् धूमात्, नास्ति घटोऽनुपलब्धेः । हेतुशब्दप्रयोगे षष्ठी भवति *(षष्ठी हेतुप्रयोगे 607/26-3-2) । अन्नस्य हेतोर्वसति । हेतुशब्दस्य सर्वनामशब्दस्य च प्रयोगे तृतीयापि भवति *(सर्वनामस्तृतीया च /27-3-2 608) । केन हेतुना / कस्य हेतोर्वसति । निमित्तपर्यायशब्दस्य सर्वनामश्च प्रयोगे सर्वा विभक्तयो भवन्ति । किं कारणं, केन कारणेन, कस्मै कारणायेत्यादि ।

समुदायादेकस्य पृथक् करणं निर्धारणम्, तत्र समुदायवाचकात् षष्ठी सप्तमी वा भवति *(यतश्च निर्धारणम् 638/41-3-2) । मनुष्याणां / मनुष्येषु क्षत्रियः शूरतमः । छात्राणां / छात्रेषु चैत्रः पटुतमः । समुदायं द्विधा विभज्य तारतम्यकरणे धर्मेण अपकृष्टात् पञ्चमी भवति *(पञ्चमी विभक्ते 639/42-3-2) । माथुराः पाटलिपुत्रकेभ्यः आढ्यतराः । जननी जन्मभूमिश्च स्वर्गादपि गरीयसी । उत्सर्गाद् अपवादो बलीयान् । सम्बन्धसामान्ये वाच्ये षष्ठी स्यात् *(षष्ठी शेषे 2 - 3 -50 /606) इदं च प्रायेण नामार्थयोरेव । राज्ञः पुरुषः वृक्षस्य शाखा , देवदत्तस्य भार्या इत्यादि । इह विशेषण वाचकात् (सम्बन्धस्य प्रतियोगिनः) एव षष्ठी , न तु विशेष्यवाचकात् (अनुयोगिनः)

यदा पूर्वोक्ता अर्थविशेषा न सन्ति , केवलं प्रातिपादिकार्थ एव प्रतीयते तदा प्रथमा विभक्तिर्भवति *(2- 3 - 46 / 532) । वृक्षः इत्यत्र वृक्षत्वजातिः , वृक्षरूपं द्रव्यं, पुल्लिङ्गम् एकत्वसंख्या च प्रतीयते । तत्राद्यं त्रयं प्रातिपादिकस्यार्थः, संख्या परं प्रत्ययार्थः । एवं च प्रातिपादिकार्थे प्रथमा इत्येव सूत्रं कर्तव्यमिति सिद्धान्तः । सूत्रकारेण तु प्रातिपादि कार्थलिङ्गपरिमाणवधनमात्रे प्रथमा इति सूत्रितम् । तदनुसारम् अनियतलिङ्गे तटस्तटी तटमित्यादौ प्रतीयमानं विविधं लिङ्गं, द्रोणो ब्रीहिरित्यादौ प्रतीयमानं परिमाणं च प्रथमार्थः इति, एकः, द्वी, बहवः इत्यन्त प्रातिपादिकेनैव संख्याया उक्तत्वात् प्रथमाया अप्राप्ती विधानार्थं वचनग्रहणमिति च सिद्धान्तकौमुदीकारेण व्याख्यातम् ।

दूरान्तिकार्थशब्देभ्यः प्रातिपादिकार्थे प्रथमा, द्वितीया, तृतीया, पञ्चमी, सप्तमी वा भवति *(दूरान्तिकार्थेभ्यो द्वितीया च, सप्तम्यधिकरणे प्रातिपादिकार्थ ... 633+532) ग्रामाद् दूरं, दूरेण, दूराद्, दूरे इति । सम्बोधने प्रथमा *(सम्बोधने च 533/47-3-2) दूरादाह्वानम् आभिमुख्यकरणं वा सम्बोधनम् ।

विवक्षातः कारकाणि भवन्ति । तण्डुलः पच्यते स्वयमेव, घटो भिद्यते स्वयमेव । रज्जुश्छिद्यते स्वयमेवेति कर्मणः कर्तृत्वम् (इह भिद्यते छिद्यते इति कर्तरि प्रयोगाः न तु कर्मणि) । अयमेव कर्मकर्तरीत्युच्यते) । असिश्छिनत्तीति करणस्य कर्तृत्वम्, स्थाली पचतीत्यधिकरणस्य कर्तृत्वम्, स्थाल्या पचतीत्यधिकरणस्य करणत्वम् । इदं च प्रयोगानुसारं न स्वेच्छया । उपपदविभक्तेः कारकविभक्तिर्बलीयसी । तेन मुनित्रयं

नमस्कृत्येत्यत्र कर्मणि द्वितीया भवति, न तु नमःशब्दयोगे चतुर्थी । गम्यमानापि क्रिया कारकविभक्तः प्रयोजिका । यथा- कस्मात् त्वम्? ग्रामात् । इह प्रश्ने चोत्तरे च गम्यमानाम् आगमनक्रियामाश्रित्य अपादाने पञ्चमी ।

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आतिरा . जी¹

विषयसारः।

शब्दानां अन्वाख्यानाय अथवा निर्माणाय हितकराः सहायकाः भवन्ति ये प्रत्ययाः ते तद्धितप्रत्ययाः । अथवा येषां प्रयोगेण भिन्नेषु अर्थेषु नूतनप्रातिपदिकानां निर्माणं भवति ते तद्धितप्रत्ययाः । तद्धितप्रत्ययेषु उपस्थिताः केचनवर्णाः प्रक्रियायां स्वयं भागं न स्वीकुर्वन्ति । प्रक्रियायाः आरम्भे एव लुप्यन्ते । एते सर्वे वर्णाः इत्संज्ञकवर्णाः अथवा अनुबन्धनाम्ना ज्ञायते । शिव -अण् इति स्थिते अल्ल णकारस्य उपस्थितिः न दृश्यते तस्य लोपः भवति । अल्ल णकारः अनुबन्धः अस्ति । नो चेत् इत्संज्ञकः अस्तीत्युच्यते । इत्संज्ञकवर्णस्य प्रयोजनं भवेदेव । यदि प्रयोजनं नास्ति, तर्हि वर्णस्य इत्संज्ञा न भवति । तद्धितप्रत्ययेषु इत्संज्ञाः केन प्रकारेण वर्तन्ते, तेषां प्रयोजनानि कानि इत्यादि विषयाः संक्षेपेण प्रबन्धेन अनेन प्रस्तूयन्ते ।

तद्धितप्रत्ययेषु इत्संज्ञकवर्णाः ।

कृततद्धितसमासैकशेषसनाद्यन्ताः पञ्चवृत्तयः सन्ति । वृत्तिर्नाम परार्थाभिधानं भवति । वृत्तिषु एकः भवति तद्धितः । तेभ्यः हिताः तद्धिताः इति । तेभ्यः नाम प्रयोगेभ्यः हिताः इत्युक्ते उपयोगिनः तद्धिताः इति । येषां प्रयोगेण भिन्नेषु अर्थेषु नूतनप्रातिपदिकानां निर्माणं भवति ते तद्धितप्रत्ययाः । । तद्धितप्रत्ययेषु इत् संज्ञाः भिन्नप्रकारेण वर्तन्ते ।

अष्टाध्यायाम् (१-३-२) उपदेशेऽजनुनासिक इत् इति सूत्रतः (१-३-९) तस्यलोपः इति सूत्रं यावत् इत्संज्ञाप्रकरणमस्ति । प्रक्रियायां सति प्रथमं सोपानम् इत्संज्ञकवर्णस्य लोपः भवति । कदापि प्रकृत्या सह तद्धितप्रत्ययानां योजनं भवति । तत्र सर्वप्रथमं प्रक्रियायां इत्संज्ञकवर्णानां लोपं करणीयम् । लोपं नाम अदर्शनं भवति । एवं इत्संज्ञकम् अनुसृत्य प्रत्ययसम्बोधनम् वर्तते । यथा

टित् -प्रत्ययः , णित् -प्रत्ययः कित् -प्रत्ययः , उदित् - प्रत्ययः इत्यादयः ।

1. टित्प्रत्ययाः – टकारः इत् संज्ञकः यस्य तस्य टित् संज्ञा । यथा डट् -प्रत्ययः ।
2. णित्प्रत्ययाः – णकारः इत् संज्ञकः यस्य तस्य णित् संज्ञा । यथा अण् – प्रत्ययः ।
3. कित्प्रत्ययाः - ककारः इत् संज्ञकः यस्य तस्य कित् संज्ञा । यथा ढक् – प्रत्ययः ।

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4. उदित्प्रत्ययाः - उँकारः इत् संज्ञकः यस्य तस्य उदित् संज्ञा । यथा वतुँप् - प्रत्ययः । तद्धितप्रत्ययेषु इत्संज्ञाप्रयोजनम् ।

स्तेन + यत् = स्तेय इत्यत्र यकारस्य स्वरितत्वं तकारेण निर्दिश्यते । अत्र तकारस्य इत्संज्ञाप्रयोजनः यकारस्य स्वरितस्वरत्वं भवति । अतः प्रथमप्रयोजनः निर्माते प्रातिपदिके स्वरस्य निर्णयः । उच्चैरुदात्तः (१-२-२९), नीचैरनुदात्तः (१-२-३०), समाहारः स्वरितः (१-२-३१), इति स्वरसम्बन्धिन्यः संज्ञाः सन्ति ।

तद्धितस्य (६.१.१६४)

अनेन सूत्रेण चित्प्रत्ययस्य अन्तिमस्वरः उदात्तः भवति । चित्प्रत्ययः - अत्र चकारः इत्संज्ञकः अस्ति तर्हि प्रकृतिप्रत्ययस्य अस्य समुदायस्य अन्तिमस्वरः उदात्तः भवति । यथा कुञ्च + च्फञ् = कौञ्चायन इत्यत्र अन्तिमनकोरोत्तरः अकारः उदात्तः भवति ।

कितः (६.१.१६५)

समुदायस्य अन्तिमस्वरः उदात्तः भवति । कित्प्रत्ययः - ककारः इत्संज्ञकः अस्ति चेत् समुदायस्य अन्तिमस्वरः उदात्तः भवति । यथा - दधि + ढक् = दाधिक इति समुदायस्य अन्तिमस्वरः भवति ककारोत्तरः अकारः । तस्य उदात्तत्वं अनेन इत्संज्ञकवर्गेण भवति ।

ञिगत्यादिर्नित्यम् (६.१.१९७)

समुदायस्य आदिस्वरः उदात्तः भवति । जित्प्रत्ययः जकारः इत्संज्ञकः अस्ति चेत् समुदायस्य आदिस्वरः उदात्तः भवति । यथा - गर्ग + यञ् = गार्ग्य । नित्प्रत्ययः - समुदायस्य आदिस्वरः उदात्तः भवति । यथा - वासुदेव + वुन् = वासुदेवक ।

तित्स्वरितम् (६.१.१८५)

तित्प्रत्ययस्य प्रथमः स्वरः स्वरितः भवति । तित्प्रत्ययः – अत्र तकारः इत्संज्ञकः अस्ति चेत् तित्प्रत्ययस्य प्रथमः स्वरः स्वरितः भवति । यथा – स्तेन + यत् = स्तेय । अत्र यकारोत्तरः अकारः स्वरितः भवति ।

उपोत्तमं रिति (६.१.१९७)

प्रत्ययस्य उपोत्तमः स्वरः उदात्तः भवति । रित्प्रत्ययः रेफः इत्संज्ञकः अस्ति चेत् प्रत्ययस्य उपोत्तमः स्वरः उदात्तः भवति । यथामृदु + जातीयर् = मृदुजातीय ।

स्त्रीप्रत्ययविधानम् ।

पथिन् + ष्कन् + डीष् = पथिकी इति । ष्कन् इति तद्धितप्रत्यययोजनेन पथिक इत्यस्ति । अत्र षकारककारयोः प्रयोजनः स्त्रीप्रत्ययविधानमस्ति । पथिकी इति स्त्रीवाचकसिद्धयर्थं डीष्प्रत्ययः योजनीयम् अत्र षकारः नास्ति चेत् ‘अजाद्यतष्टाप्’ (४.१.४) इति टाप् एव सिद्ध्यति तर्हि पथिका इति रूपं भवति । तस्मात् पथिकशब्दात् स्त्रीत्वं बोधयितुम् डीष् इति कश्चन स्त्रीप्रत्ययस्य प्रयोगः भवेत् ।

षिट्गौरादिभ्यश्च (४.१.४१)

षिट्प्रत्ययः प्रातिपदिकेभ्यो गौरादिभ्यश्च स्त्रियां डीष् प्रत्ययो भवति । षिट्प्रत्ययः षिट् प्रत्ययः अस्ति चेत् स्त्रीत्वं द्योतयितुं डीष्प्रत्ययः विधीयते स्त्रीत्वविवक्षायाम् । यथा- वत्स + ष्टरच् = वत्सतर + डीष् वत्सतरी ।

टिट्हाणञ्द्वयसज्दघ्नञ्मात्रचयण्ठक्ठञ्क्ववरपः (४.१.१५)

टिदादिभ्यः प्रातिपदिकेभ्यः स्त्रियां डीष्प्रत्ययो भवति । टिट्प्रत्ययः – टिट्प्रत्ययः अस्ति चेत् स्त्रीत्वं द्योतयितुं डीष्प्रत्ययः विधीयते स्त्रीत्वविवक्षायाम् । यथा- एकदशन् + डट् = एकादशा + डीष् = एकादशी ।

अङ्गकार्यम् ।

दक्ष + इञ् = दाक्षी इत्यत्र दा इति अङ्गस्य आदिवृद्धिः जितः प्रयोजनम् । ‘यस्मात् प्रत्ययविधिस्तदादि प्रत्ययेऽङ्गम्’ (१.४.१३) इति सूत्रेण यस्मात् शब्दात् प्रत्ययः विधीयते सः शब्दः तस्मिन् प्रत्यये परे अङ्गसंज्ञा प्राप्नोति इति विधीयते । तस्मात् अङ्गस्य इति अधिकारसूत्रेण इतः परं सप्तमाध्यायस्य समाप्तिपर्यन्तं यत्कार्यम् उच्यते तत् अङ्गस्य भवति इति सिद्ध्यति । सर्वे अङ्गाः भसंज्ञकः वा पदसंज्ञकः वा भवेत् । ‘यचिभम्’ (१.४.१८) इति सूत्रेण यकारादि तद्धितप्रत्यये परे अङ्गस्य भसंज्ञा भवति । एवं स्वादिष्वसर्वनामस्थाने इति सूत्रेण यकारं विहाय अन्यस्मिन् हलादितद्धितप्रत्यये परे अङ्गं पदसंज्ञकं च भवति । प्रत्ययस्य प्रथमं वर्णं दृष्ट्वा तदेव ज्ञातुं शक्यते यकारादिः अस्ति वा हलादिः अस्ति वा अजादिः वा इति । एवं इत्संज्ञकवर्णानां लोपं कृत्वा प्रत्ययस्य आवश्यकं अस्ति चेत् आदेशं च कृत्वा तदनन्तरमेव प्रत्ययः अजादिः अस्ति वा उत हलादिः वा इति निर्णयः कर्तुं शक्यते । यथा – विनता + ढक् > विनता + ईय = भसंज्ञा । अदिति + ण्य > अदिति + य = भसंज्ञा ।

जन+ तल् > जन +त = पदसंज्ञा । 'तसौ मत्वर्थे' (१.४-१९) इति तकारान्तः सकारान्तः शब्दः मत्वर्थे प्रत्यये परे भसंज्ञकः भवति । गरुत्+ मत् 'सिति च' (१.४.१६) इति सित् प्रत्यये परे अङ्गस्य पदसंज्ञा भवति । पर्शु +णस् । ऋतु + घस् ।

टे: (६.४.१५५)

अनेन सूत्रेण भस्य टेलोपो भवति ।डित्प्रत्ययः - डकारः इत्संज्ञकः अस्ति चेत्, भसंज्ञकस्य अङ्गस्य टिसंज्ञकस्य लोपः भवति । यथा - एकादशन् + डट् = एकादश + अ = एकादशा ।

उगिदचां सर्वनामस्थानेऽधातोः।(७.२.७०)

सर्वनामस्थाने प्रत्यये परे अङ्गस्य नुमागमः भवति । उदित् - उदित् अस्ति चेत् सर्वनामस्थाने प्रत्यये परे अङ्गस्य नुमागमः भवति । यथा - गरुत् + मतुप् = गरुत्मत् + सु = गरुत्मान् ।

तद्धितेष्वचामादेः। (७.२.११७)

अङ्गस्य आदिवर्णस्य वृद्धिः आदेशः भवति । णित्प्रत्ययः - णकारः इत्संज्ञकः अस्ति चेत् अङ्गस्य आदिवर्णस्य वृद्धिः भवति । यथा - अश्वपति अण् आश्वपति । शिव अण् शैव । उपगव अण् औपगव । जित्प्रत्ययः - जकारः इत्संज्ञकः अस्ति चेत् अङ्गस्य आदिवर्णस्य वृद्धिः भवति । यथा - दक्ष + इच् = दाक्षी , निषाद + इच् = नैषाधि , सुमित्रा + इच् = सौमित्रि ।

किति च (७.२.११८)

तद्धिते परतः अङ्गस्य आदिमवर्णस्य वृद्धिः आदेशः भवति । ककारः इत्संज्ञकः अस्ति चेत् अङ्गस्य आदिवर्णस्य वृद्धिः भवति । यथा - भरत + ढक् = भारतेय, विनता + ढक् = वैतनेयः । एवं स्वरनिर्णयः , स्त्रीप्रत्ययविधानम् , अङ्गकार्यम् च इत्संज्ञायाः प्रयोजनानि वर्तन्ते ॥

तद्धितप्रत्ययेषु इत्संज्ञाप्रयोजनम् - संक्षेपः ।

प्रत्ययः	स्वरनिर्णयः ।	स्त्रीप्रत्ययविधानम् ।	अङ्गकार्यम्
उदित्	-	-	सर्वनामस्थाने परे नुमागमः
कित्	समुदायस्य अन्तोदात्तत्वम्	-	आदिवृद्धिः
चित्	समुदायस्य अन्तोदात्तत्वम्	-	-
जित्	समुदायस्य आद्युदात्तत्वम्	-	आदिवृद्धि

टित्	-	डीप् -प्रत्ययविधानम्	-
डित्	-	-	टिसंज्ञकस्य लोपः
णित्	-	-	आदिवृद्धिः
तित्	प्रत्ययस्य आदिस्वरितत्वम्	-	-
नित्	समुदायस्य आद्युदात्तत्वम्	-	-
पित्	प्रत्ययस्य आद्यनुदात्तत्वम्	-	-
रित्	प्रत्ययस्य उपोत्तमस्वरस्य उदात्तत्वम्	-	-
लित्	प्रत्ययात् पूर्वस्वरस्य उदात्तत्वम्	-	-
षित्	-	डीप् -प्रत्ययविधानम्	-
सित्	-		अङ्गस्य पदसंज्ञा

सहायकग्रन्थाः ।

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भर्तृहरिमतमनुसृत्य उपसर्गाणां निपातानां च द्योतकत्ववाचकत्वविचारः

डा.राजीव् पी.पी¹

शोधसारः

उपसर्गाः निपाताश्च द्योतका वाचका वेति विवादः न अर्वाचीनः, अपि तु प्राचीनोऽयं विषयः। शाकटायनो निपातानां द्योतकत्वं गार्ग्यस्तु वाचकत्वं च अङ्गीकुरुतः। आचार्ययास्कः उत्तरपक्षरूपेण गार्ग्यमतम् अथवा निपातानां वाचकत्वमेव अङ्गीकरोति। महाभाष्यकारः पतञ्जलिः उपसर्गातिरिक्तनिपाताः वाचकाः द्योतकाः च इति मन्यन्ते। तस्य मते निपातानां वाचकत्वं द्योतकत्वं च भवतः, किन्तु उपसर्गाणां तु द्योतकत्वमेव। कौण्डभट्टः वैयाकरणभूषणसारे निपातानां द्योतकत्वमेव समर्थयति। सामान्यतया निपातानामर्थविषये शास्त्रेषु पक्षत्रयं दृश्यते। उपसर्गो द्योतकः, धातुरेव तद्वाचकः इति प्रथमः पक्षः। उपसर्गाः न केवलं द्योतका एव, अपि तु वाचका अपि इति द्वितीयः पक्षः। उपसर्गविशिष्टस्य च धातोः वाचकत्वमिति तृतीयः पक्षः। प्रादीनां चादीनां च निपातानां द्योतकत्वमेवेति भर्तृहरेः अभिप्रायः॥

कुञ्चिकापदानि- उपसर्गाः, निपाताः, द्योतकाः, वाचकाः, पतञ्जलिः, भर्तृहरिः, कौण्डभट्टः, नागेशभट्टः।

उपक्रमः

उपसर्गाः निपाताश्च द्योतका वाचका वेति विवादः न अर्वाचीनः, अपि तु प्राचीनोऽयं विषयः। शाकटायनस्य कालादारभ्य उपलब्धेषु संस्कृतव्याकरणग्रन्थेषु अन्येषु दार्शनिकग्रन्थेषु च विषयमिममधिकृत्य चर्चाः वर्तन्ते। यद्यपि शाकटायनस्य ग्रन्थः अद्य नोपलभ्यते तथापि निरुक्ते तस्य सिद्धान्ताः उपलभ्यन्ते। निरुक्तानुसारेण द्वौ पक्षौ स्तः। प्रथमः आचार्यशाकटायनपक्षः द्वितीयस्तु गार्ग्यपक्षः च। अत्र शाकटायनो निपातानां द्योतकत्वं गार्ग्यस्तु वाचकत्वं च अङ्गीकुरुतः। “न निर्बद्ध उपसर्गा अर्थान्निराहुरिति शाकटायनः। नामाख्यातयोस्तु कर्मोपसंयोगद्योतका भवन्ति” (यास्कः-, 11.) इति शाकटायनमतं निरुक्ते उक्तम्। “उच्चावचाः पदार्था भवन्तीति गार्ग्यः। तद्य एषु पदार्थाः प्राहुरिमे नामाख्यातयोर्विकरणम्” (निरुक्तम्, 11-12) इति गार्ग्यमतं च तत्र वर्तते। अर्थात् शाकटायनः ब्रवीति यत् नामाख्यातयोः यत् कर्म = अर्थः तत्रैव उपसंयुज्य

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कांश्चिदर्थविशेषान् उपसर्गा द्योतयन्ति। गार्ग्यस्य मते उच्चावचाः= बहुप्रकाराः, पदस्य= निपातोपसर्गाख्यस्य अर्थाः अभिधेयाः प्रकर्षादयः सन्ति इति। आचार्ययास्कः उत्तरपक्षरूपेण गार्ग्यमतम् अथवा निपातानां वाचकत्वमेव अङ्गीकरोति इति एतस्मात् ज्ञातुं शक्यते॥

महाभाष्यकारमतम्

महाभाष्यकारः पतञ्जलिः उपसर्गातिरिक्तनिपाताः वाचकाः द्योतकाः च इति मन्यन्ते। अत एव सः ‘अव्ययं विभक्तिः....’ (अष्टाध्यायी, 2-1-6) इति सूत्रभाष्ये ‘सुमद्राः, सुमगधाः, सपुत्रः, सच्छाल’ इत्यादौ अव्ययीभावसमासमाशङ्क्य पूर्वपदप्रधानस्याव्ययीभावत्वेन अत्र पूर्वपदप्राधान्यं नास्तीत्युक्त्वा “अथवा नेमे समासार्था निर्दिश्यन्ते। किं तर्हि अव्ययार्था इमे निर्दिश्यन्ते। एतेष्वर्थेषु यदव्ययं वर्तते, तत्सुबन्तेन सह समस्यत” (पतञ्जलिः 360) इत्यवोचत्। महाभाष्यव्याख्याकारः कैयटः तु अव्ययस्य श्रुतत्वादन्तरङ्गत्वात् तस्यैव विभक्त्यादयो विशेषणानि इति वदति। तत्र यदा उत्तरपदार्थावच्छिन्नाः समृद्ध्यादयः प्रतिपिपादादिष्विषिताः, तदा अव्ययं समृद्ध्यादीनां वाचकमिति तेषां तदर्थता भवतीत्युक्तम्। एवं सुमद्रा इत्यत्र तु मद्रशब्द एव समृद्धिविशिष्टमर्थमाह, सुशब्दस्तु समृद्धिद्योतकः न तु वाचकः इति कैयटेन व्याख्यायते। अनेन भाष्यकैयटव्याख्यानेन ज्ञातुं शक्यते यत् निपातानां वाचकत्वं द्योतकत्वं च भवतः, किन्तु उपसर्गाणां तु द्योतकत्वमेवेति ॥

कौण्डभट्टमतम्

कौण्डभट्टः वैयाकरणभूषणसारे (वै. भू) निपातानां द्योतकत्वमेव समर्थयति। तद्यथा-
द्योतका प्रादयो येन निपाताश्चादयस्तथा।

उपास्येते हरिहरौ लकारो दृश्यते यथा ॥ इति। (कारिका-42)

अत्र येन हेतुना प्रादयो द्योतकाः तेनैव हेतुना चादयः = निपाताः अपि द्योतका इत्यर्थः। किन्तु निपातानां वाचकत्वपक्षमपि कौण्डभट्टः समर्थयति। तद्यथा अन्वयव्यतिरेकाभ्यां निपातेषु बोधकतारूपायाः शक्तेः अबाधात् तदर्थवाचकत्वमपि युक्तमिति सः अभिप्रैति। तथा सति पचति इत्यादौ धातोरेव कर्तृविशिष्टभावनायां लक्षणा सम्भवति, तिडादेः तु तात्पर्यग्राहकत्वमालं स्यात्। तत्र युक्तमित्यतः पक्षान्तरमुच्यते कौण्डभट्टेन-

निपातानां वाचकत्वमन्वयव्यतिरेकयोः।

युक्तं वा न तद्युक्तं परेषां मतमेव नः ॥ इति। (कारिका-47)

अत्रायमर्थः यत् पचादि धातुना सह तिडादिप्रत्ययानां योगे कर्तृकर्माद्यर्थस्य प्रतीतिः भवति। किन्तु तिडादीनामप्रयोगे कर्त्ताद्यर्थस्य प्रतीतिः न भवति। एतादृशान्वयव्यतिरेकाभ्यां यथा तिडादीनां वाचकत्वं सिद्धयति तथा निपातानामपि वाचकत्वकल्पना उचिता इति कौण्डभट्टः अभिप्रैति ॥

नागेशभट्टमतम्

उपसर्गाणां द्योतकत्वम्, उपसर्गाभिन्ननिपातानां वाचकत्वं, ‘साक्षात्प्रत्यक्षतुल्ययोः’ इति कोशादिति नैयायिकाः अभिप्रयन्ति। तद्यथा ‘देवाय नमः’ इत्यत्र नमःपदेन नमस्कारार्थत्वं

सिद्धयति। किन्तु दानावसरे 'गवे नमः' इत्यत्र नमःपदेन पूजार्थत्वं च सिद्धयति। अतः उपसर्गभिन्ननिपातानां वाचकत्वकल्पने दोषो नास्तीति ते अभिप्रयन्ति। नैयायिकानामिदं मतं नागेशभट्टः एवं खण्डयति- "तत्र, वैषम्ये बीजाभावात्, अनुभूयते इत्यनेन साक्षात्क्रियत इत्यस्य सम्भवात्। नामार्थधात्वर्थयोर्भेदेन साक्षादन्वयाभावात् निपातार्थधात्वर्थयोरन्वयस्यैवासम्भवात्। निपातार्थफलाश्रयत्वेऽपि धात्वर्थान्वयं विना कर्मत्वानुपपत्तेश्च" (नागेशभट्टः, 145) इति। अत्र नागेशभट्टस्यायमभिप्रायः वर्तते यत् नामार्थधात्वर्थयोः भेदेन साक्षादन्वयः अव्युत्पन्नः इति व्युत्पत्त्या साक्षात्काररूपनिपातार्थस्य कृधात्वर्थव्यापारे अनुकूलत्वरूपभेदसम्बन्धेन अन्वयः न भवितुमर्हति। किन्तु विभक्त्याद्यर्थद्वारैव अन्वयः भवति। अत एव 'राज्ञः पुरुषः' इत्यादौ न साक्षाद् भेदसम्बन्धेन अन्वयः अपि तु विभक्तिद्वारैव अन्वयः भवति। एवमत्रापि साक्षात्क्रियते इत्यत्र साक्षात्काररूपनिपातार्थस्य कृधात्वर्थे अन्वयः न सम्भवति। एवं नैयायिकमतस्वीकारे सति साक्षात्काररूपार्थस्य निपातार्थतया धात्वर्थत्वाभावात् कर्मत्वमनुपपन्नं भवति। किन्तु वैयाकरणमतमनुसृत्य निपातानां द्योतकत्वस्वीकारे सति दोषो न भवति। तद्यथा अत्र साक्षात्काररूपार्थस्य धातुप्रतिपाद्यतया तदाश्रयस्य कर्मत्वमुपपन्नं भवति। अत एव 'देवदत्तः प्रयागात् काशीं गच्छति' इत्यत्र उत्तरदेशसंयोगानुकूलव्यापारप्रयोज्यविभागरूपफलाश्रयत्वात् प्रयागस्यापि कर्मत्वं प्राप्नोति। तद्वारणाथैव व्यापारप्रयोज्यफलशालित्वं कर्मत्वम् इत्यत्र फले धात्वर्थविशेषणं कृतम् ॥

भर्तृहरिमतमनुसृत्य उपसर्गार्थविचारः ।

सामान्यतया निपातानामर्थविषये शास्त्रेषु पक्षत्रयं दृश्यते। उपसर्गाणां निपातानां च द्योतकत्वं वाचकत्वं वा इति सन्देहः भवति अत्र पक्षत्रयस्य व्यवस्थापने मुख्यो हेतुः। ते च पक्षाः अधः प्रस्तूयन्ते-

प्रथमः पक्षः

अनुभवति इत्यादौ अनुभवरूपो अर्थः धातोः न भवति। किन्तु 'भवति' इत्यत्रापि तत्प्रतीत्यापत्तेः, न उपसर्गस्य अनुगच्छति इत्यादावपि तद्वोधप्रसङ्गः भवति। अतः उपसर्गो द्योतकः, धातुरेव तद्वाचकः इति सिद्धयति। अत एव च अनुः द्योतकः, धातुरेव तद्वाचकः इति सिद्धयति। एवम् अनुभवसाक्षात्कारादिरूपफलवाचकत्वेन कर्मणि लकारोऽपि उपपद्यते। अत्र द्योतकत्वं तात्पर्यग्राहकत्वमेव। अत एवोक्तं भर्तृहरिणा-

क्वचित्सम्भाविनो भेदाः केवलैरनिदर्शिताः ।

उपसर्गेण सम्बन्धो व्यज्यन्ते प्रपरादिना ॥ इति । (वाक्यपदीयम्, 2-187)

अत्रायमर्थः यत् क्वचित् 'पचति' इत्यादौ प्रकर्षादीनां सम्भवात् केवलैः तेषामप्रतीतेः उपसर्गसम्बन्धात् तदवगमः भवति। अतः उपसर्गाणां विशेषद्योतकत्वमुच्यते इति ॥

द्वितीयः पक्षः

उपसर्गाः न केवलं द्योतका एव, अपि तु वाचका अपि इति द्वितीयः पक्षः। तथा हि- तिष्ठति इत्यादौ स्था धातोः गतिनिवृत्तिवाचकत्वमस्ति। प्रतिष्ठते इत्यादौ प्र इति उपसर्गेण

गतिवाचकत्वं व्यवस्थाप्यते । अत एवोक्तं भर्तृहरिणा-

स वाचको विशेषाणां सम्भवात् द्योतकोऽपि वा । इति ॥ (वाक्यपदीयम्, 2-188)

तृतीयः पक्षः

अस्मिन् पक्षे उपसर्गविशिष्टस्य च धातोः वाचकत्वं भवति । तदुक्तं हरिणा-

शक्त्याधानाय धातोर्वा सहकारी प्रयुज्यते । इति ॥ (वाक्यपदीयम्, 2-188)

सम्भूय धातूपसर्गावर्थमाहुरिति शक्तिमात्रमुपसर्गः कुरुत इत्यर्थाभिधाने सहकारिणा उपसर्गाः इति विषयेऽस्मिन् पुण्यराजः अभिप्रैति (2-188, पुण्यराजकृतव्याख्यानम्-पृ-85.) । अस्मिन् पक्षे अडाद्यागमविषये द्विर्वचनादिविषये चोपसर्गस्य पृथक्कृतिः भविष्यति ॥

अत्र उपसर्गविषये त्रयः पक्षाः उपर्युक्ताः । तेषु त्रिषु पक्षेषु प्रथमः पक्षः अथवा उपसर्गाणां द्योतकत्वपक्षः एव युक्तः भवति । तद्यथा 'प्रतिष्ठते' इत्यत्र धातूनामनेकार्थत्वात् स्था धातोरेव गतिरर्थः, प्रशब्दस्तु तस्य गत्यर्थस्य द्योतकः भवति । अत एवोक्तं हरिणा-

स्थादिभिः केवलैर्यच्च गमनादि न गम्यते ।

तलानुमानात् द्विविधात्तद्धर्मा प्रादिरुच्यते ॥12 इति । (वाक्यपदीयम्, 2-189)

अर्थात् तिष्ठतिः गतिनिवृत्तिं प्रसिद्ध्या अभिदधाति । अतः तेन केवलेन गमनं न प्रतिपद्यते । अनेकार्था धातवः इति कृत्वा अनुमानाद् गतिवाचकत्वमपि तस्य व्यवस्थाप्यते । उपसर्गस्तु तद्योतक एव । एवमस्यां कारिकायां तलानुमानात् इति धातूनामनेकार्थत्वम् उपसर्गाणां द्योतकत्वं च अनुमानेन साधयति ॥

भर्तृहरिमतमनुसृत्य निपातार्थविचारः ।

उपसर्गाणां द्योतकत्वं वाचकत्वं वेति निर्णयाय त्रीन् पक्षान् उक्त्वा तत्र द्योतकत्वपक्ष एव शोभनः इति उपरि प्रतिपादितम् । अत्र निपातानां क्रियाविशेषस्य द्योतकत्वं स्वीकर्तव्यं वाचकत्वं वेति चर्चा क्रियते । अत्रापि त्रयः पक्षाः सन्ति । यथा-

निपाता द्योतका केचित् पृथगर्थाभिधायिनः ।

आगमा इव केऽपि स्युः सम्भूयार्थस्य वाचकाः ॥ इति । (वाक्यपदीयम्, 2-188)

एवमुपसर्गाणां द्योतकत्ववाचकत्वविषये उक्ताः त्रयः पक्षाः अत्रापि परिगणितव्याः । एतेषां पक्षाणां पर्यालोचनया ज्ञातुं शक्नुमः यत् यथा उपसर्गाः तथा निपाता अपि द्योतका इति पक्ष एव न्याय्यः इति । केवलानां चादीनामप्रयोगः अपि अत्र द्योतकत्वपक्षं द्रढयति ॥

यदि निपाताः वाचकाः स्युः तदा गवादिपदवत् केवला अपि प्रयुज्येरन् । 'न केवला प्रकृतिः प्रयोक्तव्या नापि केवलः प्रत्ययः' इति भाष्यात् यथा केवलायाः प्रकृतेः केवलस्य च प्रत्ययस्य प्रयोगो न भवति, तथैव केवलानां निपातानामपि । तस्मात् चादयो न वाचकाः केवलानामप्रयोगात्, प्रत्ययवत् इत्यनुमानं फलितम् । लोके अर्थप्रत्यायनाय शब्दाः प्रयुज्यन्ते । यथा लोके केवलया प्रकृत्या केवलेन च प्रत्ययेन नार्थबोधो भवति, तथैव

केवलेन निपातेनापि आकाङ्खाविरहात् बोधो न भवति । एवञ्च प्रादीनां चादीनां च निपातानां द्योतकत्वमेवेति भर्तृहरिः अभिप्रायः ॥

उपसंहारः

निपाता द्योतका....इत्यत्र भर्तृहरिः निपातानां सम्भूयार्थवाचकत्वं स्वीकरोति । किन्तु नागेशभट्टः निपातान् द्योतकान् अथवा वाचकान् अन्यतरस्वभावान् एव मन्यते, न तु सः तान् सम्भूयार्थवाचकान् स्वीकरोति । सम्भूयार्थस्य वाचका इत्यस्य क्रियानामान्यतरसमभिव्याहारे सत्येव निपाता वाचका इत्यर्थः भवति । किन्तु अयं स्वभावः निपातानां नास्तीति नागेशभट्टः अभिप्रैति । अत एव सः निपातानां वाचकत्वं द्योतकत्वं वा पृथक् पृथक् मत्वा एषां सम्भूयार्थवाचकत्वे अरुचिं प्रदर्शयति । अर्थात् अस्य मते केचन निपाताः सर्वथा द्योतकाः केचन च सर्वथा वाचकाः एव । अत्र द्योतकनिपातविषये तु नागेशभट्टः सम्भूयार्थद्योतकत्वं स्वीकरोति । किन्तु वाचकत्वसिद्धौ निपातानां सम्भूयार्थवाचकत्वं नास्तीति तस्याभिप्रायः । उपर्युक्तानां विवरणानां पर्यालोचनया अस्मिन् विषये एवमुपसंहारः कर्तुं शक्यते यत्- निपाताः न केवलं वाचका एव, नापि केवलं द्योतका एव वर्तन्ते, किन्तु ते उभयस्वभावाः इति । अर्थात् केचन निपाताः वाचकाः केचन द्योतकाश्च । अत्रायं सन्देहः जायते यत् कः निपातः वाचकः? कः तु द्योतकः? इति । अत्र तत्तत्स्थलीयं शिष्टजनप्रमाणप्रमाणितं शाब्दबोधमाश्रित्य निपातानां वाचकत्वद्योतकत्वकल्पनं करणीयमिति विषयेऽस्मिन् समाधानं वर्तते । अथवा निपातविशेषस्य वाचकत्वं द्योतकत्वं वा कल्पनीयमिति ॥

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डॉ झिलि-विश्वासः¹

प्रबन्धसारः

भारतवर्षस्य सभ्यतां संस्कृतिं च ज्ञातुं यस्य ग्रन्थस्य ज्ञानं निश्चयेन अपेक्षते स हि वेदः। वैदिकसंहितायाः प्राचीनतमे ऋग्वेदे स्तुतासु देवतासु मरुद्गणो ह्यन्यतमः। स देवो हि अन्तरिक्षस्थानीयः प्राणस्य सूक्ष्मतरं स्वरूपम्। मरुद्गणस्य ऋग्वेदे त्रिंशत्सूक्तेषु स्तुतिर्विहिता। ऋग्वेदे प्रथममण्डले मरुद्गणदेवताकानि लयोदश सूक्तानि विलसन्ति। तत्र पञ्चानां सूक्तानां येषु मन्त्रेषु वङ्गानुवादे वैलक्षण्यं दृश्यते, तानि एव समुद्धृत्य सायणस्कन्दस्वामिवेङ्कटमाधवादिभाष्यपर्यालोचनेन तेषां वङ्गानुवादः अस्मिन् प्रबन्धे समीक्ष्यते।

उपोद्घातः

वैदिकदेवतासु अन्यतमं स्थानं बिभर्ति मरुद्गणः। निरुक्ते स्थानानुसारेण यास्काचार्येण देवानां वर्गत्रयं विहितम् – पृथिवीस्थानीयः, अन्तरिक्षस्थानीयः, द्युलोकस्थानीयश्च। तत्र वायुः अन्तरिक्षस्थानीयः। एतेषाम् लयाणां देवानां भिन्नानि कर्माणि, भिन्नानि च विशेषणानि इतरेषां देवानां नामकरणे निमित्तानि। तत्र वायोः एव कार्यभेदाद् मातरिश्वा, इन्द्रः, रुद्रः, अपान्नपात्, मरुद्गणः इत्यादीनि नामानि। यास्कस्य मतमेतत् न कपोलकल्पितम् अपि तु ऋग्वेदसमर्थितमेव। ऋग्वेदे “सूर्यो नो दिवस्पातु वातोऽन्तरिक्षादग्निर्नः पार्थिवेभ्यः” (१०।१५१।१) इति मन्त्रः अत्र प्रमाणम्। पुनः अन्तरिक्षस्थानीयदेवतासु वायुवर्गे वातः, वायुः, मरुद्गणः मातरिश्वा इत्येते देवा वर्णिताः।

मरुद्गणः हि वायुः इव प्रथमगामीति निघण्टौ वर्णितः। ऋग्वेदे यद्यपि बहुषु मन्त्रेषु विक्षिप्ततया तस्य स्तुतिः दृश्यते परन्तु त्रिंशत्सूक्तेषु पूर्णतया स स्तूयते। सामान्यतया वेदे त्रिविधः देवगणः प्रसिद्धः वसुगणः रुद्रगणः आदित्यगणश्च। तेषु रुद्रगणः मरुद्गणः इति वक्तुं शक्यते। यतो हि “सत्यं त्वेषा अमवन्तो धन्वञ्चिदा रुद्रियासः।” (१।३८।७)

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इत्यास्मिन् मन्त्रे रुद्रियासः इति मरुतः स्तूयन्ते । रुद्रियासः नाम रुद्रपुत्राः । अध्यात्मदृष्ट्या अन्तरिक्षस्थानीयदेवतानां स्वरूपं प्राणः । तत्र प्राणस्य स्थूलं रूपं वातः, सूक्ष्मं रूपं वायुः सूक्ष्मतरं च रूपं मरुद्गणः इति प्रसिद्धिः ।

ऋग्वेदस्य प्रथममण्डले त्रयोदशसूक्तानि मरुद्गणदेवताकानि विद्यन्ते । तेषु पञ्चानां सूक्तानां येषु मन्त्रेषु वज्रानुवादे वैलक्षण्यं दृश्यते, तानि एव समुद्धृत्य सायणस्कन्दस्वामिवेङ्कटमाधवादिभाष्यपर्यालोचनेन वज्रानुवादानां समीक्षणम् अत्र विधीयते ।

मरुद्गणदेवताकसूक्तविचारः

प्रथममण्डलस्य पञ्चदशमन्त्रोपेतस्य सप्तत्रिंशत्तमस्य सूक्तस्य घोरपुत्रः कण्व ऋषिः, गायत्री छन्दः मरुद्गणः च देवता । तत्र

“क्रीलं वः शर्द्धो मारुतमनर्वाणं रथे शुभम् ।
कण्वा अभि प्र गायत ॥” (१।३७।१)

इत्यस्मिन् मन्त्रे अनर्वाणम् इति पदस्यार्थभेदः लक्ष्यते । अत्र सायणाचार्यः प्राह – ‘हे कण्वाः कण्वगोलोत्पन्ना महर्षयः । यद्वा मेधाविनः ऋत्विजः । यो युष्मदर्थं मारुतं मरुत्समूहरूपं शर्द्धो बलमभिप्रगायत । अभितः प्रकर्षेण स्तुध्वम् । कीदृशं शर्द्धः । क्रीलं विहरणशीलम् अनर्वाणं भ्रातृव्यरहितम् ।’ (ऋग्वेदसंहिता-३, पृ०-१९०८) इति । स्कन्दस्वामिना अत्र प्रोक्तम् – ‘अनर्वाणम् ऋ गतौ । अन्यत्र आश्रिततया गन्ता अर्वा । आश्रितः इत्यर्थः । ततोऽन्यः अनर्वा । तमनर्वाणम् । अन्यत्र अनाश्रितमित्यर्थः ।’ (विश्वबन्धुसम्पादितः ऋग्वेदः-१, पृ०-२९०) इति । वेङ्कटमाधवस्य नये ‘अप्रत्यृतमन्यस्मिन् रथे यः शोभते तम्’ (तत्रैव, पृ०-२९१) इति । अत्र दुर्गादासमहोदयेन मन्त्रार्थ उच्यते – ‘कण्वाः अकिञ्चनाः हे अस्मत्सदृशाः क्षुद्रजनाः वः युष्मदर्थं मारुतं मरुत्समूहरूपं शर्द्धः बलं शक्तिं क्रीलं विहरणशीलं सर्वत्र क्रीडमानम् अनर्वाणं शत्रुसंश्रवरहितं रथे शुभं रथे शोभमानं सर्वेषां हृद्देशे विराजमानम् ।’ (ऋग्वेदसंहिता-३, पृ०-१९०८) इति ।

अत्र दुर्गादासः वज्रानुवादे प्राह – ‘मरुद्देवगणेर शक्तिः, सर्वत्र क्रीडमान, शत्रुसंश्रवरहित एवं सकलेरङ्ग हृदये विराजमान ।’ (मरुद्देवगणस्य शक्तिः सर्वत्र क्रीडमाना, शत्रुसंश्रवरहिता सर्वेषां हृदि विराजमाना च ।) इति । अत्र रमेशचन्द्रमहाभागस्य अनुवादः – ‘हे कण्वगोलोद्भव ऋषिगण, क्रीडाशील ओ शत्रुरहित मरुत्समूहेर उद्देश्ये गाओ ।’ (ऋग्वेदसंहिता, पृ०-२२) (हे कण्वगोलोद्भव ऋषिगण, क्रीडाशीलं शत्रुरहितं मरुद्गणम् उद्दिश्य गानं कुरु) इति । जगदीश्वरानन्दः अत्र अनुवदति ‘भ्रातृव्यरहित’ (ऋग्वेद-प्रथमखण्डः, पृ०-२८४) (शत्रुरहितम् इति तात्पर्यम्) इति । वज्रानुवादे नीलाञ्जनामहोदया एतस्य पदस्य प्रतिद्वन्द्विरहितम् (वेदग्रन्थमाला-१, पृ०-९१) इत्यर्थं प्राह ।

अनर्वाणम् इत्यत्र निरुक्ते प्रोक्तम् 'अनर्वा अप्रत्यृतोऽन्यस्मिन्' (निरुक्तम्, नैगमकाण्डम् ६।५, पृ०-३२०) इति। स्वप्रधान एव तिष्ठति यः सः अनर्वा इत्युच्यते। ऋधातोः "अन्येभ्योऽपि दृश्यते" (३-२-७५) इत्यनेन सूत्रेण वनिप्रत्यये अर्वन् इति शब्दः निष्पद्यते। न अर्वा अनर्वा। अन्यस्मिन् अनाश्रितः अप्रत्यृतः इत्यर्थः। यथा "अनर्वाणं वृषभं मन्द्रजिह्वं बृहस्पतिं वर्धया नव्यमर्कैः" (ऋ० सं० २-५-१२-१) इत्यस्मिन् मन्त्रे निरुक्ते व्याख्यानावसरे पदस्यास्य 'अप्रत्यृतमन्यस्मिन्' इत्यर्थः स्वीकृतः।

प्रथममण्डलस्य पञ्चदशमन्त्रोपेतस्य अष्टत्रिंशत्तमस्य सूक्तस्य घोरपुत्रः कण्व ऋषिः, गायत्री छन्दः मरुद्गणः च देवता। तत्र

“मो षु णः परापरा निर्ऋतिर्दुर्हणा वधीत्।
पदीष्ट तृष्ण्या सह ॥” (१।३८।६)

इत्यस्मिन् मन्त्रे परापरा दुर्हणा इति पदद्वयस्य अर्थभेदः लक्ष्यते। अत्र सायणाचार्यः प्राह - 'हे मरुतः नः अस्मान् निर्ऋतिः रक्षोजातिः देवता मो षु वधीत् सर्वथा वधं मा कार्षीत्। कीदृशी परापरा उत्कृष्टाप्युत्कृष्टा अतिबलेत्यर्थः। अत एव दुर्हणा केनापि हन्तुं दुःशक्या।' (ऋग्वेदसंहिता-३, पृ०-१९८४) इति। स्कन्दस्वामिना अत्र भाष्ये प्रोक्तम् - 'नः अस्मान् परापरा अत्यन्तपरा। युष्मत्प्रसादादेव दूरवर्तिनीत्यर्थः। निर्ऋतिः मृत्युदेवता। दुर्हणा दुःखं निहन्तीति दुर्हणा।' (विश्वबन्धुसम्पादितः ऋग्वेदः-१, पृ०-३०२) इति। वेङ्कटमाधवेन भाष्ये प्रोक्तम् - 'मा एव अस्मान् अधोऽधः दुःखेन हन्तव्यं दारिद्र्यं वधीत्। सा निर्ऋतिः मदीयया तृष्ण्या सह पततु। धनसद्भावे हि तृष्णा विनश्यति।' (तलैव, पृ०-२९०) इति। अत्र दुर्गादासमहोदयेन मन्त्रार्थ उच्यते - 'हे मरुतः, परापरा अतिप्रभावशालिनी दुर्हणा दुर्दमनीया निर्ऋतिः पापवृत्तिः नः अस्मान् उषु सर्वथा आदौ मा वधीत् वधं मा कार्षीत्।' (ऋग्वेदसंहिता-३, पृ०-१९८४) इति।

अत्र दुर्गादासः वङ्गानुवादे प्राह - 'हे मरुदेवगण, अतिप्रभावशालिनी दुर्दमनीया पापवृत्ति आमादिगके आदौ वध करिते ना पारे।' (हे मरुदेवगण, अतिप्रभावशालिनी दुर्दमनीया पापवृत्तिः अस्मान् आदौ मा वधीत्।) इति। अत्र रमेशचन्द्रमहाभागः अनुवदति - 'निर्ऋति अतिशय बलवती एवं ताहाके विनाश करा याय ना।' (निर्ऋतिः अतिशयेन बलवती, तस्याः विनाशं कर्तुं न शक्यते।) (ऋग्वेदसंहिता, पृ०-२३) इति। जगदीश्वरानन्दः तथैव अनुवदति 'निर्ऋति अतिशय बलवती एवं ताहार विनाशसाधन अतीव दुःशक्य।' (ऋग्वेद-प्रथमखण्डः, पृ०-२९२) (निर्ऋतिः अतिशयेन बलवती, तस्याः विनाशसाधनम् अतीव दुःशक्यम्।) इति। नीलाञ्जनामहोदया अत्र अनुवदति - 'आमादिगेर येन अत्यन्त बलशालिनी दुर्निवारणीया दुष्टा निर्ऋति (राक्षसी) वध करते ना पारे।' (अस्माकं वधाय अत्यन्तं बलशालिनी दुर्निवारणीया दुष्टा निर्ऋतिः राक्षसी यथा समर्था न भवेत्।) (वेदग्रन्थमाला-१, पृ०-९५) इति।

“सत्यं त्वेषा अमवन्तो धन्वञ्चिदा रुद्रियासः।

मिहं कृण्वन्त्यवाताम् ॥” (१।३८।७)

इत्यस्मिन् मन्त्रे रुद्रियासः इति पदस्य अर्थभेदः लक्ष्यते। अत्र सायणाचार्यः प्राह – ‘धन्वञ्चित् मरुदेशेऽपि रुद्रियासः रुद्रेण पालितत्वात् तदीया आ सवतः आवातां वायुरहितां मिहं वृष्टिं कृण्वन्ति कुर्वन्ति तदेतत् सत्यम्। कीदृशा रुद्रियासः। त्वेषा दीप्ताः अमवन्तः बलवन्तः। मरुतां रुद्रपालनमाख्यानेषु प्रसिद्धम्।’ (ऋग्वेदसंहिता-३, पृ०-१९८७) इति। स्कन्दस्वामिना अत्र भाष्ये प्रोक्तम् – ‘रुद्रियासः अपत्येऽर्थे घप्रत्ययो द्रष्टव्यः। रुद्रपुत्राः।’ (विश्वबन्धुसम्पादित ऋग्वेदः-१, पृ०-३०३) इति। वेङ्कटमाधवेन भाष्ये ‘रुद्रपुत्राः’ इत्येवार्थः स्वीकृतः। अत्र दुर्गादासमहोदयेन मन्त्रार्थे ‘कठोरभावापन्नाः’ (ऋग्वेदसंहिता-३, पृ०-१९८७) इत्यर्थः स्वीकृतः।

अत्र रमेशचन्द्रमहाभागः अनुवदति – ‘दीप्तिमान् ओ बलवान् रुद्रीयगण सत्यइ मरुभूमितओ वायुरहित वृष्टि दान करेन।’ (दीप्तिमान् बलवान् च रुद्रीयगणः सत्यमेव मरुभूमौ अपि वायुरहितां वृष्टिं ददाति।) (ऋग्वेदसंहिता, पृ०-२३) इति। जगदीश्वरानन्दस्य नये ‘रुद्रपालित’ (रुद्रपालिताः) (ऋग्वेद-प्रथमखण्डः, पृ०-२९२) इत्यनुवादः। नीलाञ्जनामहोदयाया नये अत्र ‘रुद्रपुत्रगण’ (रुद्रपुत्राः) (वेदग्रन्थमाला-१, पृ०-९८) इत्यनुवादः।

प्रथममण्डलस्य पञ्चदशमन्त्रोपेतस्य चतुःषष्टितमस्य सूक्तस्य गौतमपुत्रः नोधा ऋषिः। अस्मिन् सूक्ते जगती त्रिष्टुप् च छन्दः मरुद्गणः च देवता। अत्र

“ईशानकृतो धुनयो रिशादसो वातान् विद्युतस्तविषीभिरक्रत।

दुहन्त्यूधर्दिव्यानि धूतयो भूमिं पिन्वन्ति पयसा परिज्रयः ॥” (१।६४।५)

इत्यस्मिन् मन्त्रे सायणाचार्यः प्राह – ‘ईशानकृतः स्तोतारमीशानं धनाधिपतिं कुर्वाणाः धूनयः मेघादीनां कम्पयितारः रिशादसः हिंसकानामत्तारः यद्वा रिशतां हिंसतामसितारो निरसितारः।’ (ऋग्वेदसंहिता-५, पृ-३२७२) इति। स्कन्दस्वामिना अत्र प्रोक्तम् – ‘ईशानकृतः स्तोतृणाम् ईश्वराणां कर्तारः धुनयः कम्पयितारः शलूणां रिशादसः रिशतिर्हिंसार्थः।’ (विश्वबन्धुसम्पादित ऋग्वेदः-१, पृ०-४८७) इति। वेङ्कटमाधवेन भाष्ये ईशानकृतः इत्यस्यार्थः प्रोक्तः – ‘स्तोतृन् ईशितृन् कुर्वाणाः’ इति। अत्र दुर्गादासमहोदयेन मन्त्रार्थ उच्यते – ‘ईशानकृतः परमैश्वर्यप्रदातारः’ (ऋग्वेदसंहिता-५, पृ०-३२७९) इति।

पदस्यास्य विषये दुर्गादासः वङ्गानुवादे प्राह ‘परमैश्वर्यप्रदाता’ (परमैश्वर्यप्रदातारः) इति। अत्र रमेशचन्द्रमहाभागस्य अनुवादः – ‘स्तोतृगणके धनाधिपति करिया’ (स्तोतृगणं धनाधिपतिं कुर्वाणाः) (ऋग्वेदसंहिता, पृ०-३९) इति। अनुवादे नीलाञ्जनामहोदया एतस्य पदस्य ‘यारा अधिकारी करेन’ (ये अधिकारिणं कुर्वन्ति) (वेदग्रन्थमाला-१, पृ०-१६०) इत्यर्थं प्राह।

प्रथममण्डलस्य षण्मन्त्रोपेतस्य सप्ताशीतितमस्य सूक्तस्य राहूगणपुत्रः गौतम ऋषिः,

जगती छन्दः मरुद्गणः च देवता । अत्र

“प्रत्वक्षसः प्रतवसो विरप्शिनोऽनानता अविथुरा ऋजीषिणः ।

जुष्टतमासो नृतमासो अञ्जिभिव्यानजे के चिदुसा इव स्तृभिः ॥” (१।८७।१)

इत्यस्मिन् मन्त्रे विरप्शिनः इत्यस्य पदस्यार्थभेदः परिलक्ष्यते । अत्र सायणाचार्यः प्राह – ‘विरप्शिनः विविधेन जयघोषेण उपेताः । यद्वा बहुनामैतत् । महान्तो हि विविधैः शब्दैः प्रशस्यन्ते ।’ (ऋग्वेदसंहिता-६, पृ-२८१) इति । स्कन्दस्वामिना अत्र प्रोक्तम् – ‘विरप्शिनः विरप्शी (निघ० ३।५) इति महन्नाम । महान्तः ।’ (विश्वबन्धुसम्पादित ऋग्वेदः-२, पृ०-६२५) इति । वेङ्कटमाधवेन भाष्ये भणितम् - ‘महान्तः अनेकाकिनः तृतीयसवनेऽन्यथात् आभरणैः व्यक्ता अभवन् ।’ (तलैव, पृ०-६२५) इति । अत्र दुर्गादासमहोदयेन मन्त्रार्थ उच्यते - ‘विरप्शिनः विजयघोषिणः जयप्रापका इत्यर्थः.....’ (ऋग्वेदसंहिता-६, पृ-२८०) इति ।

दुर्गादासः वङ्गानुवादे प्राह ‘जयप्रापकः.....नित्यभगवत्सम्बन्धयुत, सत्कर्मकारिणोरे द्वारा अतिशयरूपे सेवित, सेइ देवतागण ज्योतिःविच्छुरणरूप अलङ्कारसमूहेरे द्वारा अर्थात् सद्गुणाबलिर द्वारा प्रकाशित ह्येन ।’ (जयप्रापकाः, नित्यभगवत्सम्बन्धयुताः, सत्कर्मकारिभिः अतिशयेन सेविताः, ते देवाः ज्योतिर्विच्छुरणरूपैः अलङ्कारैः सद्गुणाबलिभिः प्रकाशिताः ।) इति । अत्र रमेशचन्द्रमहाभागस्य अनुवादः – ‘मरुद्गण शत्रुघाती प्रकृष्टबलसम्पन्न, जयघोषयुक्त, आनतिरहित, अवियुक्त, ऋजीषी ओ यजमानेर सेवित एवं मेघादिर नेता मरुत्-गण आभरणद्वारा नक्षत्रपूर्ण आकाशेर न्याय प्रकाशित हइलेन ।’ (मरुतः शत्रुघातिनः प्रकृष्टबलसम्पन्नाः, जयघोषयुक्ताः, आनतिरहिताः, अवियुक्ताः, ऋजीषिणः यजमानसेविताः मेघादीनां नेतारश्च आभरणैः नक्षत्रपूर्णाकाशसदृशाः प्रकाशिताः ।) (ऋग्वेदसंहिता, पृ०-३९) इति । अनुवादे नीलाञ्जनामहोदया विरप्शिनः इति पदस्य ‘प्राचुर्यसमन्वित’ (प्राचुर्यसमन्विताः) इत्यर्थं प्राह ।

प्रथममण्डलस्य षण्मन्त्रोपेतस्य अष्टाशीतितमस्य सूक्तस्य राहूगणपुत्रः गौतम ऋषिः, त्रिष्टुप् विराट् च छन्दः मरुद्गणः च देवता । अत्र

“आ विद्युन्मद्भिर्मरुतः स्वर्के रथेभिर्यात ऋष्टिमद्भिरश्वपर्णैः ।

आ वर्षिष्ठया न इषा वयो न पत्तता सुमायाः ॥” (१।८८।१)

इत्यस्मिन् मन्त्रे अश्वपर्णैः इत्यस्य पदस्यार्थभेदः परिलक्ष्यते । अत्र सायणाचार्यः प्राह – ‘मरुतो रथेभिरात्मीयै रथैरायात ।अश्वपर्णैः । अश्वं व्याप्तं पर्णं पतनं गमनं येषाम् अन्तरीक्षं व्याप्य वर्तमानैरित्यर्थः ।’ (ऋग्वेदसंहिता-६, पृ-२८१) इति । स्कन्दस्वामिना अत्र प्रोक्तम् – ‘ऋष्टिमद्भिः शक्तिमद्भिः तीरणसद्भिर्वा । अश्वपर्णैः अश्वपतनैः ।’ (विश्वबन्धुसम्पादित ऋग्वेदः-२, पृ०-६२५) इति । वेङ्कटमाधवस्य नये अश्वपक्षैः इत्यर्थः । अत्र दुर्गादासमहोदयेन मन्त्रार्थ उच्यते - ‘अश्वपर्णैः व्याप्तपतनैः पतननिवारकैः रथेभिः

अस्माकं कर्मरूपैः यानैः सह यूयम् आयात आगच्छत अस्मान् प्राप्तुत ।’ (ऋग्वेदसंहिता- ६, पृ-३१०) इति ।

दुर्गादासः ‘शोभनगमन अर्थात् सन्मार्गानुसारी, रिपुदमनसामर्थ्यसम्पन्न (शत्रुदमनायुधयुक्त), पतननिवारक आम्रादिगेर कर्मरूप याने आपनारा आगमन करुन ।’ (शोभनगमनैः सन्मार्गानुसारिभिर्वा, रिपुदमनसामर्थ्यसम्पन्नैः शत्रुदमनायुधयुक्तैः पतननिवारकैः अस्माकं कर्मरूपैः यानैः आगच्छत ।) इत्यनुवादे प्राह । अत्र रमेशचन्द्रमहाभागस्य अनुवादः – ‘शोभनगमनविशिष्ट आयुधसम्पन्न अश्वसंयुक्त मेघे आरोहण करिया आगमन कर ।’ (शोभनगमनविशिष्टैः आयुधसम्पन्नैः अश्वसंयुक्तैः मेघैः आरुह्य आगच्छत ।) (ऋग्वेदसंहिता, पृ-५१) इति । अनुवादे नीलाञ्जनामहोदया प्राह – ‘तोमादेर विद्युत् शोभित रथगुलि चालना करे येगुलि मधुर स्तुति अथवा सुष्ठु गतियुक्त ।’ (युष्माकं विद्युच्छोभितान् रथान् चालयति, ये हि मधुरस्तुतियुक्ताः सुष्ठु गतियुक्ताश्च ।) (वेदग्रन्थमाला-१, पृ-२०५) इति ।

समीक्षणम्

“क्रीलं वः शर्द्धो मारुतमनर्वाणं रथे शुभम् ।.....” (१।३७।१) इत्यस्मिन् मन्त्रे अनर्वाणम् इति पदस्य भातृव्यरहितम् इति सायणप्रोक्तात् शत्रुसंश्रवरहितम् इति दुर्गादासप्रोक्ताद् अर्थाद् अपेक्षया स्कन्दस्वामिप्रोक्तः ‘अनर्वाणम् ऋ गतौ । अन्यत्र आश्रिततया गन्ता अर्वा । आश्रितः इत्यर्थः । ततोऽन्यः अनर्वा । तमनर्वाणम् । अन्यत्र अनाश्रितमित्यर्थः ।’ इत्यर्थः श्रेयान् । दुर्गादासरमेशचन्द्रजगदीश्वरानन्दनीलाञ्जनामहोदयाः वङ्गानुवादकाः पदस्यास्य भावानुवादं विहितवन्तः इति निश्चितम् ।

“मो षु णः परापरा निर्ऋतिर्दुर्हणा वधीत् ।” (१।३८।६) इत्यस्मिन् मन्त्रे परापरा दुर्हणा इति पदद्वयं निर्ऋतिः इति पदस्य विशेषणम् । परापरा उत्कृष्टाप्युत्कृष्टा अतिबला इति सायणः । स्कन्दस्वामी अपि तथैव अभिप्रेत्य अत्यन्तपरा इत्यर्थं प्राह । अतिप्रभावशालिनी इत्यर्थः इति दुर्गादासः । अत्र रमेशचन्द्रदत्तजगदीश्वरानन्दनीलाञ्जनमहोदयाः वङ्गानुवादकाः सायणमेवानुसरन्ति ।

केनापि हन्तुं दुःशक्या दुर्हणा इति सायणः । तथैवार्थम् अभिप्रेत्य स्कन्दस्वामी प्राह दुःखं निहन्तीति । वेङ्कटमाधवेनोक्तं दुःखेन हन्तव्यम् इति । दुर्गादासनये दुर्दमनीया इत्यर्थः । रमेशचन्द्रदत्तजगदीश्वरानन्दनीलाञ्जनमहोदयाः वङ्गानुवादकाः सायणमेवानुसरन्ति ।

“सत्यं त्वेषा अमवन्तो धन्वञ्चिदा रुद्रियासः ।” (१।३८।७) इत्यस्मिन् मन्त्रे रुद्रियासः इति पदस्य सायणनये रुद्रपालिताः इति, स्कन्दस्वामिनो वेङ्कटमाधवस्य च नये रुद्रपुत्राः इति दुर्गादासमहोदयस्य च नये कठोरभावापन्नाः इति चार्थः । रमेशचन्द्रदत्तेन जगदीश्वरानन्देन च वङ्गानुवादे सायणमतं गृहीतम् । अयमेवार्थः सङ्गतः । दुर्गादासमहोदयेन स्वीकृतः कठोरभावापन्ना इत्यनुवादस्तु कथञ्चिदपि नान्वेति । नीलाञ्जनामहोदयाया

रुद्रपुत्राः इत्यनुवादस्तु भावानुवाद एव ।

“ईशानकृतो धुनयो रिशादसो वातान् विद्युतस्तविषीभिरक्रत।....” (१।६४।५) इत्यस्मिन् मन्त्रे ईशानकृतः इत्यत्र सायणाचार्यनये ‘स्तोतारमीशानं धनाधिपतिं कुर्वाणाः’ इति, स्कन्दस्वामिनये ‘स्तोतृणाम् ईश्वराणां कर्तारः’ इति, वेङ्कटमाधवनये ‘स्तोतृन् ईशितृन् कुर्वाणाः’ इति दुर्गादासमहोदयनये ‘परमैश्वर्यप्रदातारः’ इति चार्थः । वङ्गानुवादेशु रमेशचन्द्रदत्तः साक्षात् सायणमेव अनुसरति, अयमेवार्थः व्युत्पत्तिदिशा सङ्गतः । नीलाञ्जनामहोदयाया अनुवादस्तु भावानुवाद एव ।

“प्रत्वक्षसः प्रतवसो विरप्शिनोऽनानता” (१।८७।१) इत्यस्मिन् मन्त्रे मरुतः इत्यस्य विरप्शिनः अविधुराः जुष्टतमासः इति पदत्रयं विशेषणम् । “महाँ अमलो वृजने विरप्शीम्” (ऋ० सं० ३-२-१८-४) इति मन्त्रव्याख्यानावसरे निरुक्तविवृतौ विरप्शिन इति पदं व्याख्यातम् । तथाहि तत्र प्रोक्तम् - ‘विरप्शी तोष्यमानः । विरावरणशील इति दुर्गः । विरयणशीलः । भुजास्फालनेन युद्धार्थं शत्रूणामाह्वानकारीति सायणः ।’ (निरुक्तम्, नैगमकाण्डम्, पृ०-३१९) इति ।

निघण्टौ तु विरप्शिन-शब्दः महदर्थकः (निरुक्तनिघण्टुः-१, पृ-३०७) दृश्यते । ‘रप लप व्यक्तायां वाचि’ इत्यस्माद् धातोः “रपभूक्रम्यभिकुभ्यः शक्” इत्यनेन सूत्रेण शक्प्रत्यये रप्शशब्दो निष्पन्नः । विविधं रपन्तीति विरप्शाः स्तोतारः, ते अस्य सन्तीति विग्रहे मत्वर्थे विरप्शशब्दाद् इनिप्रत्यये विरप्शिन इति शब्दः निष्पद्यते । “विरप्शी गोमती मही” (ऋ० सं० १-१-१६-३), “क्रत्वे अपिवो विरप्शीम्” (ऋ० सं० ४-७-१२-२) “विरप्शिने वज्रिणे शन्तमानि” (ऋ० सं० ४-७-४-१) इत्यादौ विरप्शिन-शब्दस्य महदर्थे एव प्रयोगः दृश्यते । अतः महान्तः इत्यर्थ एव सुसङ्गतः । अतः सायणसम्मतः द्वितीयार्थः स्कन्दस्वामिप्रोक्तश्च अर्थः साधुः । अनुवादकेषु दुर्गादासरमेशचन्द्रदत्तौ सायणस्य प्रथमार्थम् अनुसरतः परन्तु नीलाञ्जनामहोदया तु सायणस्य द्वितीयार्थं निरुक्तं च अनुसरति । अतः तदीयानुवादः श्रेयान् । आङ्गलानुवादकेषु विलसन्-महोदयः सायणस्य प्रथमार्थम् अनुसृत्य विरप्शिनः इति पदस्य विविधेन जयघोषेण उपेताः इत्यर्थं स्वीकृत्य ‘loud-shouting’ (Rigveda Sanhita:A collection of ancient Hindu hymns, P-223) इत्यनुवादं प्राह । परन्तु तम् अर्थं परित्यज्य निघण्टुनिरुक्तसम्मतं सायणीयद्वितीयार्थं स्कन्दस्वामिनं च अनुसृत्य ग्रिफिथ्-महोदयः ‘full of strength’ (The Hymns of Rgveda-1, P-146) इत्यनुवादं प्राह ।

“आ विद्युन्माद्भिर्मरुतः स्वकै रथेभिर्यात ऋष्टिमद्भिरश्वपर्णैः ।” (१।८८।१) इत्यस्मिन् मन्त्रे अश्वपर्णैः इत्यस्य पदस्यार्थभेदः परिलक्ष्यते । सायणनये अश्वं व्याप्तं पर्णं पतनं गमनं येषाम् अन्तरिक्षं व्याप्य वर्तमानैरित्यर्थः । स्कन्दस्वामिनो नये अश्वपतनैः इति, वेङ्कटमाधवस्य नये अश्वपक्षैः इति, दुर्गादासस्य नये अश्वपर्णैः व्याप्तपतनैः पतननिवारकैः इति चार्थः । रमेशचन्द्रमहाभागस्य नये अश्वसंयुक्तैः इति नीलाञ्जनामहोदयाया नये च सुष्ठु

गतियुक्तैः इत्यर्थः ।

निरुक्ते “आ विद्युन्मद्भिर्मरुतः स्वर्के रथेभिर्यात ऋष्टिमद्भिश्चपर्णेः” इति मन्त्रस्य व्याख्यानावसरे अश्वपर्णेः इति पदस्य ‘अश्वपतनैः’ (निरुक्तम्, दैवतकाण्डम् ११।२, पृ०-४७२) इत्यर्थः स्वीकृतः । अश्वपर्णेः अशनपतनैः अश्रुवन्तो ये अन्तरिक्षे पतन्ति ये तैः इति तात्पर्यम् । ‘अशु व्याप्तौ’ इत्यस्माद् धातोः अश्वशब्दः निष्पन्नः । तस्य यौगिकार्थः व्याप्तम् । पततीति पर्णं पतनम् । अन्तरिक्षं व्याप्य येषां पतनं ते अश्वपर्णाः अश्वपतनाः । अतः निरुक्तप्रामाण्यात् सायणसम्मतः स्कन्दस्वामिसम्मतश्च अर्थः समीचीनः । तदनुसारेण दुर्गादासस्य नीलाञ्जनामहोदयायाश्च अनुवादः समीचीनः । अश्वसंयुक्तैः इति रमेशचन्द्रस्य अनुवादस्तु हेय एव । इत्थम् ऋग्वेदीयप्रथममण्डलस्य मरुद्गणदेवताकसूक्तीयमन्त्राणां सायणस्कन्दस्वामिवेङ्कटमाधवादिभाष्यस्वारस्येन वङ्गानुवादसमीक्षणं विहितम् इति शिवम् ।

परिशीलितग्रन्थावली

अनिर्वाणः । वैदिकसाहित्य - वेदमीमांसा, तृतीय खण्ड । संस्कृत बुक् डिपो । कोलकाता । २००६।
ऋग्वेदसंहिता । रमेशचन्द्रदत्तः (अनु०) । तथागतः । कलिकाता । २०१८।

ऋग्वेदसंहिता - प्रथम खण्ड । स्वामी जगदीश्वरानन्दः (सम्पा०) । श्रीरामकृष्णधर्मचक्र । बेलुडः । १३६५ वङ्गाब्दम् ।

ऋग्वेदसंहिता - तृतीयखण्ड । दुर्गादासलाहिडी (सम्पा०) । पृथिवीर इतिहास । हाओडा । १३२५ वङ्गाब्दम् ।

ऋग्वेदसंहिता - पञ्चमखण्ड । दुर्गादासलाहिडी (सम्पा०) । पृथिवीर इतिहास । हाओडा । १३२५ वङ्गाब्दम् ।

ऋग्वेदसंहिता - षष्ठ्यखण्ड । दुर्गादासलाहिडी (सम्पा०) । पृथिवीर इतिहास । हाओडा । १३२५ वङ्गाब्दम् ।

ऋग्वेदः स्कन्दस्वाम्युद्गीथवेङ्कटमाधवमुद्गलभाष्योपेतः (प्रथमो भागः) । विश्वबन्धुः (सम्पा०) । विश्वेश्वरानन्दवैदिकशोधसंस्थानम् । होशिआरपुरम् । १९६३।

ऋग्वेदः स्कन्दस्वाम्युद्गीथवेङ्कटमाधवमुद्गलभाष्योपेतः (द्वितीयो भागः) । विश्वबन्धुः (सम्पा०) । विश्वेश्वरानन्दवैदिकशोधसंस्थानम् । होशिआरपुरम् । १९६३।

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यास्काचार्यः । निरुक्तम् (निघण्टुः) । निर्वचनटीकासहितम् - प्रथमो भागः । देवराजः यज्वन् (टीका०) । क्लाइव रो । कलकत्ता । १९५२।

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देवज्योति-कुण्डुः¹

शोधसारः

श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता अद्वैतवेदान्तमतप्रतिष्ठापकः कश्चित् सरलग्रन्थः । श्रीशङ्कराचार्यः तद्रचितभाष्येण श्रीकृष्णार्जुनयोः संवादरूपतत्त्वानाम् अद्वैतपरकं व्याख्यानमकरोत् । संसारस्वरूपं ततो निवृत्त्युपायश्च गीतायां वर्णितः । सा च निवृत्तिः परमपुरुषार्थप्राप्त्या एव सम्भवति । ब्रह्म वस्तुतः अत्यन्तनिर्मलस्वच्छसूक्ष्मस्वभावविशिष्टम् । अतोऽस्माभिरविद्याध्यारोपनिराकरणमालं ब्रह्मणि कर्तव्यम् । विवेकिनः तु ब्रह्मणा साकं स्वस्य अभेदम् अवगम्य ब्रह्मणि लीनाः भवन्ति । नैष्कर्म्यसिद्धिं प्राप्तस्य ब्रह्मभावो उपजायते । एतम् एव विषयं भगवान् श्रीकृष्णः अर्जुनाय उपदिशति “सिद्धिं प्राप्तो यथा ब्रह्म” इत्यादिश्लोकेन । आत्मज्ञानमेव ब्रह्मज्ञाननिष्ठा । स्वस्वरूपावगमनेन खलु ब्रह्मप्राप्तिः भवति । तद्ब्रह्म आसक्तित्यागेन इन्द्रियजयेन स्पृहात्यागेन च प्राप्यते । अत एव अनासक्तः जितेन्द्रियः निःस्पृहः जन एव कर्मफलत्यागेन आत्मज्ञो भवति । तद् आत्मज्ञानमेव नैष्कर्म्यसिद्धिः उच्यते । ब्रह्मणि अविद्याध्यारोपो योऽस्ति, तस्य निराकरणमालं कर्तव्यम् । तेनैव आत्मस्वरूपानुभवः ब्रह्मभावप्राप्तिः वा स्यात् । तद्विचारपरकं नैष्कर्म्यलक्षणसिद्धेः ज्ञाननिष्ठत्वमलं शोधपत्रे भगवद्गीतासन्दर्भानुगुणं शाङ्करभाष्यानुसारं विचारितम् ।

कूटशब्दाः : श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता, शाङ्करभाष्यम्, नैष्कर्म्यसिद्धिः, ज्ञाननिष्ठा, ब्रह्मभावः, आत्मबुद्धिः, अविद्या, अध्यारोपः, विवेकी-अविवेकी ।

उपक्रमः

परमपुरुषार्थो हि मोक्षः । मोक्षप्राप्तये विविधानि साधनानि शास्त्रेषु उक्तानि । संसारत्यागेन स्वस्वरूपम् अवगम्य ब्रह्मणि लयः आवश्यकः । किन्तु मायायाः आवरणकारणात् साधारणाः स्वस्वरूपम् अवगन्तुं न परयन्ति । धीरपुरुषाः तु मोहं त्यक्त्वा ब्रह्मतत्त्वं ज्ञात्वा अमृतत्वं भजन्ते । कर्मयोगेन देवलोकप्राप्तिः भवति । ज्ञानयोगेन ब्रह्मलोकः प्राप्यते । अतः कर्म कर्मफलं च त्यक्त्वा ब्रह्मविद्याप्राप्तये सदा प्रयत्नः

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करणीयः। भारतीयधर्मग्रन्थेषु महाभारतम् अतिप्रसिद्धम्। महाभारतस्य एव अंशविशेषः श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता। अत्र श्रीकृष्णस्य अर्जुनं प्रति उपदेशप्रदानं प्रधानतया दृश्यते। कर्मस्वरूपं मोक्षस्वरूपं च उक्त्वा भगवान् श्रीकृष्णः अर्जुनाय विविधोपदेशपुरःसरं संसारबीजम् उक्तवान्। भाष्यकारः श्रीशङ्कराचार्यः गीताशास्त्रस्य व्याख्यानसमये एतं समस्तवेदार्थसारसंग्रहभूतं कथयति। अत्र अष्टादशाध्यायैः समस्तानामपि वेदानां सारः वर्णितोऽस्ति।

अष्टादशाध्यायेषु मोक्षसन्न्यासयोगो नाम अष्टादशोऽध्यायः अन्यतमः। अत्र आदौ अर्जुनः सन्न्यासस्य त्यागस्य च तत्त्वं ज्ञातुम् इष्टवान्। तस्य प्रश्नस्य उत्तरदानाय विविधैः श्लोकैः भगवान् अर्जुनाय सर्वमपि तत्त्वम् उपदिष्टवान्। सर्वोऽपि संसारोऽयं क्रियाकारकफललक्षणः सत्त्वरजस्तमोगुणात्मकः अविद्यापरिकल्पितः। अतः अविद्याध्यारेपेण जगति सर्वे व्यवहाराः भवन्ति। आवरणद्वारा एव खलु स्वरूपं कस्यचित् वस्तुनः न ज्ञायते। तादृशम् आवरणम् अत्र अविद्या। अतः अविद्यारूपावरणनिराकरणद्वारा ब्रह्मणः वस्तुतः स्वरूपम् अवगम्यते अभेदश्च प्रतिपाद्यते। अन्यत्रापि श्रुतिस्मृतिषु एतदेव तत्त्वं प्रतिपादितम् अस्ति। वयं सर्वेऽपि चैतन्यस्वरूपा एव। किन्तु अविद्याध्यारोपणात् तत्तत्त्वं नैव ज्ञातुं शक्यते। ब्रह्म तु वस्तुतः अत्यन्तनिर्मलस्वच्छसूक्ष्मस्वभावविशिष्टम्। किञ्च तत् प्रसिद्धमपि। अतः अस्माभिः अविद्याध्यारोपनिराकरणमात्रं ब्रह्मणि कर्तव्यम्। विवेकिनः तु ब्रह्मणा साकं स्वस्य अभेदम् अवगम्य ब्रह्मणि लीनाः भवन्ति। नैष्कर्म्यसिद्धिं प्राप्तस्य ब्रह्मभावो उपजायते। एतम् एव विषयं भगवान् श्रीकृष्णः अर्जुनाय उपदिशति “सिद्धिं प्राप्तो यथा ब्रह्म” इत्यादिश्लोकेन। तत्स्था एव विचाराः सम्प्रति अत्र शाङ्करभाष्यानुसारं विचार्यन्ते।

नैष्कर्म्यसिद्धिं प्राप्तस्य ब्रह्मभावप्राप्तिप्रतिपादिका भगवत्प्रतिज्ञा

सर्वेषु विषयेषु अनासक्तभावयुक्तः संयतचित्तः स्पृहाशून्यो जनः कर्मफलत्यागद्वारा प्रकृष्टां कर्मबन्धनक्षयरूपां सिद्धिं नैष्कर्म्यसिद्धिम् अधिगच्छति। भगवान् श्रीकृष्णः एवं नैष्कर्म्यसिद्धिविषये उक्तवान्। तत्र श्लोको हि –

“असक्तबुद्धिः सर्वत्र जितात्मा विगतस्पृहः।

नैष्कर्म्यसिद्धिं परमां सन्न्यासेनाधिगच्छति ॥” इति।(18.49)

कर्मजसिद्धिं प्राप्तस्य नैष्कर्म्यसिद्धिप्राप्तिः येन क्रमेण भवति, तं क्रमं सम्प्रति भगवान् श्रीकृष्णः वक्ष्यति। नैष्कर्म्यसिद्धिं प्राप्तस्य हि आत्मविवेकज्ञानम् उत्पद्यते। एषा सिद्धिः कथं प्राप्यते इति आह भगवान् –

“सिद्धिं प्राप्तो यथा ब्रह्म तथाप्नोति निबोध मे ।
समासेनैव कौन्तेय निष्ठा ज्ञानस्य या परा ॥” इति।(18.50)

अर्थात् स्वकर्मणा ईश्वरं समभ्यर्च्य तत्प्रसादजां कार्येन्द्रियाणां ज्ञाननिष्ठायोग्यतालक्षणां सिद्धिं प्राप्तः येन प्रकारेण ज्ञाननिष्ठारूपेण परमात्मानम् आप्नोति, तत् क्रमं मद्बचनाद् अवधारय इति। अत्र निष्ठा ज्ञानस्य या परा इति उक्तम्। निष्ठा पर्यवसानं परिसमाप्तिः

इत्येतत् । कस्य, ब्रह्मज्ञानस्य या परा परिसमाप्तिः । या ज्ञानस्य परा निष्ठा सेयमेव ब्रह्मप्राप्तिः इत्यर्थः ।

आत्मज्ञानमेव ब्रह्मज्ञाननिष्ठा । स्वस्वरूपावगमनेन खलु ब्रह्मप्राप्तिः भवति । तद् ब्रह्म कथं प्राप्यते? आसक्तित्यागेन, इन्द्रियजयेन, स्पृहात्यागेन च । अत एव अनासक्तः जितेन्द्रियः निःस्पृहः जन एव कर्मफलत्यागेन आत्मज्ञो भवति । तद् आत्मज्ञानम् एव नैष्कर्म्यसिद्धिः उच्यते । विविधोपनिषद्वाक्यैः न्यायादिभिश्च आत्मस्वरूपं वर्णितम् अस्ति । अत एव सदा अविद्याध्यारोपणनिराकरणेन आत्मस्वरूपज्ञानाय यतनीयम् इति भावः ।

ज्ञानात्मनोः निराकारत्वं समानत्वं च

सम्प्रति प्रश्नप्रतिवचनरूपेण ज्ञानात्मनोः निराकारत्वं समानत्वं च प्रतिपाद्यते । तत्र पूर्वपक्षी आत्माकारं ज्ञानम् अनुपपन्नम् इति प्रतिपादयति । किन्तु वस्तुतस्तु ज्ञानम् अपि अविद्याद्वारा कलुषितं भवति । अतः ज्ञानस्य निराकारत्वं सारल्येन अवगन्तुं न शक्यते । एतम् एव विषयं सम्प्रति प्रतिपादयति भाष्यकारः तच्छिष्यश्च । अत्र भाष्यकारः नित्यकर्मकरणाय भाष्यप्रवचनात् सम्प्रति किञ्चिद् विरत आसीद् इति श्रूयते । तत्समये तच्छिष्यः अन्यसिद्धान्तम् अप्रतिपादयत् ।

पूर्वपक्षी आह – ज्ञानं विषयाकारं भवति, परन्तु आत्मा न विषयो भवति, नापि आकारवान् इति । यदि वयं किमपि वस्तु पश्यामः, तदा तद्वस्त्वाकारकं ज्ञानम् अस्माकं जायते । अत एव ज्ञानं विषयाकारं भवति इत्युच्यते । किन्तु आत्मा खलु निराकारः इति प्रसिद्धम् । किञ्च आत्मानं विषयत्वेन अपि न स्वीकर्तुं शक्यते । तदा सिद्धान्तपक्षी आत्मनः आकारप्रतिपादिकश्रुतयः उदाहृतवान् । “आदित्यवर्णं तमसः परस्तात्” (श्वेताश्वतरोपनिषद् -3.8) इति श्रुत्या आत्मनः आदित्यवर्णत्वम् अवगम्यते । पुनश्च आत्मा भारूपः इति बुध्यते “तमेव भान्तमनुभाति सर्वं तस्य भासा सर्वमिदं विभाति” (कठोपनिषद् 2.2.15) इति श्रुत्या । पुनश्च आत्मा स्वयंज्योतिः इत्यपि श्रूयते । एवं तु आत्मनः आकारत्वं श्रुतिषु प्रसिद्धम् एव । सिद्धान्तिनः एतन्मतं न स्वीकरोति पूर्वपक्षी । आत्मा नापि आकारवान् भवति, नापि विषय इति सम्यक् प्रतिपाद्यते पूर्वपक्षिणा । “आदित्यवर्णम्” (श्वेताश्वतरोपनिषद् (3.8), “भारूपः” (छान्दोग्योपनिषद् (3.14.2), “स्वयंज्योतिः” (बृहदारण्यकोपनिषद् (4.3.9) इत्येतेषां वाक्यानां तमोरूपत्वप्रतिषेधार्थत्वम् अस्ति । अर्थात् आत्मनि द्रव्यगुणाद्याकारप्रतिषेधे तमोरूपत्वं प्राप्नोति । तस्य प्रतिषेधार्थमेव “आदित्यवर्णम्” (श्वेताश्वतरोपनिषद् 3.8) इत्यादीनि वाक्यानि उक्तानि । “अरूपम्” (कठोपनिषद् 1.3.15) इत्यादिवाक्यैः विशेषतः रूपप्रतिषेधः कृतः । एवञ्च आत्मा विषयो न भवति इत्यपि श्रुत्या प्रतिपाद्यते । तथाहि – “न सदृशे तिष्ठति रूपमस्य न चक्षुषा पश्यति कश्चनैनम्” (श्वेताश्वतरोपनिषद् 4.20), “अशब्दमस्पर्शमरूपमव्ययम्” (कठोपनिषद् 1.3.15) इत्यादि । तस्माद् आत्माकारं ज्ञानम् इति अनुपपन्नम् । एवम् अत्र पूर्वपक्षी तन्मतं प्रतिपादितवान् ।

कथं तर्हि आत्मनः ज्ञानं भवति इति प्रश्नः । सर्वम् एव ज्ञानं यद्विषयं भवति, तत् तदाकारं भवति । किञ्च आत्मा निराकारः इति प्रसिद्धम् । तर्हि आत्मनः ज्ञानं तु न कदापि सम्भवति । ज्ञानात्मनोः च उभयोः निराकारत्वे कथं तद्भावनानिष्ठ इति प्रश्नो भवति । यदि आकारः एव न स्यात्, तर्हि कथं तत्र भावना निष्ठा वा तिष्ठेद् इत्यभिप्रायः । पूर्वपक्षिणः एतां युक्तिं सिद्धान्ती निराकरोति । पूर्वपक्षिकथनम् अयुक्तम् । यतो हि आत्मा अत्यन्तनिर्मलत्वस्वच्छत्वसूक्ष्मत्व विशिष्ट एव इति प्रसिद्धम् । एवं च बुद्धिः अपि आत्मा इव निर्मलत्वादिविशिष्टा एव । तस्माद् बुद्धेः आत्मचैतन्याकारेण आभासनम् उपपद्यते एव । आत्मा यथा स्वच्छः, तथा बुद्धिः अपि स्वच्छा एव भवति । अविद्याद्यध्यारोपकारणाद् आत्मनि मलिनतोत्पत्तिकारणात् च भिन्नत्वेन प्रतीयते । एवम् एव बुद्धिविषयेऽपि अवगन्तव्यम् । बुद्धेः अपि आवरणकारणात् सम्यक् ज्ञानं न जायते । तेन आत्मस्वरूपबोधेऽपि बाधा उत्पद्यते । अत्र आत्मचैतन्याकारेण आभासिता बुद्धिः इत्युक्तम् । एतदाभासनं केन क्रमेण भवति इत्युच्यते भाष्यकारेण श्रीशङ्कराचार्येण – “बुद्ध्याभासं मनः तदाभासानि इन्द्रियाणि इन्द्रियाभासः च देहः अतो लौकिकैः देहमात्रे एव आत्मदृष्टिः क्रियते” (श्रीमद्भगवद्गीताशाङ्करभाष्यम् 18.50) इति । लौकिकास्तु देहम् एव आत्मत्वेन स्वीकुर्वन्ति । तत् कथं भवतीति आभासनक्रमः अत्र उक्तः । एवम् अत्र आत्मबुद्ध्योः निराकारत्वं समानत्वं च अवगम्यते ।

अन्यमतावलम्बिनां मतनिराकरणं ब्रह्मभावप्राप्त्युपायश्च

अन्यमतावलम्बिनः आत्मानम् अन्यथा स्वीकुर्वन्ति । केचिद् देहं, केचिद् मनः, केचिद् इन्द्रियाणि च आत्मत्वेन स्वीकुर्वन्ति । यथा देहचैतन्यवादिनः लोकायतिकाकः चेतनताविशिष्टं शरीरम् एव आत्मा इति अङ्गीकुर्वन्ति । अन्ये केचन इन्द्रियाणि एव आत्मा इति प्रतिपादयन्ति । अन्ये मन एव आत्मत्वेन चिन्तयन्ति । पुनश्च केचन बुद्धिचैतन्यवादिनो भवन्ति । ततोऽपि अन्तरव्यक्तम् अव्याकृताख्यम् अविद्यावस्थम् आत्मत्वेन प्रतिपन्नाः केचित् । किन्तु अत्र सर्वत्रैव आत्मचैतन्याभासः तिष्ठति । तस्माद् एव तत्र आत्मभ्रान्तिः भवति । अर्थात् इदम् एव आत्मा इति आत्मचैतन्याभासः तत्र भ्रान्त्या प्रतिपद्यते । तस्मात् प्रमादवशाद् आत्मत्वेन स्वीकुर्वन्ति । किन्तु वस्तुतः इन्द्रियादय आत्मा न भवन्ति । तद् वेदान्तवाक्यैः सुप्रतिपादितम् अस्ति ।

आत्मा तु प्रसिद्ध एव । पृथक्तया स ज्ञातव्यो न भवति । स स्वयं ज्ञानस्वरूपः । स ज्ञात एव अस्ति । केवलम् आवरणापसरणद्वारा तत्स्वरूपानुभूतिः कर्तव्या भवति । अत एव आत्मविषयं ज्ञानं न विधातव्यम् । नामरूपाद्यनात्माध्यारोपणनिवृत्तिरेव कार्या । आत्मज्ञानम् अविद्याया अध्यारोपितं वर्तते । तदध्यारोपनिवृत्तिद्वारा एव तत् ज्ञानं स्वयं प्रकाशते । शारीरकभाष्ये अपि एतद् एव उच्यते – विद्या अविद्यायाः निवर्तिका दृष्टा इति । किञ्च विविधासु उपनिषत्सु अपि एतद् एव तत्त्वं प्रतिपाद्यते । यथा मुण्डकोपनिषदि आत्मा स्वयं प्रकाशते इति उक्तम् । प्रदीपदृष्टान्तद्वारा तत्र आत्मस्वरूपं प्रतिपादितम् । दीपो यथा स्वं प्रकाशनाय अन्यं न अपेक्षते, तथा आत्मा अपि स्वयम् एव प्रकाशते । तं प्रकाशनाय न

कापि भिन्ना शक्तिः आवश्यकी । दीपस्थानीया विद्या, तमःस्थानीया अविद्या । भाष्यकारः श्रीशङ्कराचार्य एतम् अभिप्रायम् एवं वर्णयति – “अत आत्मविषयं ज्ञानं न विधातव्यम्, किं तर्हि, नामरूपाद्यनात्माध्यारोपणनिवृत्तिः एव कार्या न आत्मचैतन्यविज्ञानम् अविद्याध्यारोपि तसर्वपदार्थाकारैः एव विशिष्टतया गृह्यमाणत्वात्” (श्रीमद्भगवद्गीताशाङ्करभाष्यम् 18.50) इति ।

भाष्यकारः विज्ञानवादिनां मतम् अपि अत्र उदाहरति । ‘सर्वं क्षणिकं क्षणिकम्’ इति विज्ञानवादिनां क्षणिकवादिनां वा एकं मतम् । तद् अद्वैतवेदान्त इव किञ्चित् सादृश्यं भजते । ते बौद्धाः विज्ञानव्यतिरेकेण वस्त्वन्तरम् एव नास्ति इति चिन्तयन्ति । तज्ज्ञानाय च प्रमाणान्तरस्य आवश्यकता न तिष्ठति । एवम् एव अद्वैतवेदान्तेऽपि आत्मनः ज्ञानाय प्रमाणान्तरं न अपेक्षितम् । आत्मा स्वयम् एव प्रकाशकः प्रसिद्धश्च । दीपो यथा अन्यसाहाय्यं विना स्वयं प्रकाशते, तद्वदेव अत्र अवगन्तव्यम् । अत एव ब्रह्मज्ञानस्य अत्यन्तप्रसिद्धत्वात् तत्र यत्नो न कर्तव्यः । किन्तु ब्रह्मणि अविद्याध्यारोपो यः अस्ति, तस्य निराकरणमात्रं कर्तव्यम् । तेनैव आत्मस्वरूपानुभवः ब्रह्मभावप्राप्तिः वा स्यात् ।

अविवेकिनां विवेकिनां च दृष्ट्या आत्मा

ब्रह्मणि अविद्याध्यारोपो भवति इति ज्ञातम् । किन्तु वस्तुतो ब्रह्म तु अत्यन्तप्रसिद्धं सुविज्ञेयम् आसन्नतरम् आत्मभूतम् । अविद्यावशाद् एव एवंविशिष्ट आत्मा अन्यथा ज्ञायते । अविवेकिनः एव अविद्याध्यारोपिततया आत्मानं जानन्ति । अविद्याकल्पितेन नामरूपभेदेन अविवेकिनां बुद्धिः अपहृता भवति । अत एव अविवेकिनां ब्रह्म अप्रसिद्धं दुर्विज्ञेयम् अतिदूरम् अन्यद् इव च प्रतिभाति । किन्तु येषां बाह्याकारबुद्धिः निवृता, ये च गुरोः आत्मनश्च प्रसादं प्राप्तवन्तः, तेषां कृते नातः परं सुखं सुप्रसिद्धं सुविज्ञेयं स्वासन्नं किमपि अस्ति । अर्थात् ब्रह्म एव उत्कृष्टतमम् । तद्वद् न अन्यद् भवितुम् अर्हति । तथा च उक्तम् – “प्रत्यक्षावगमं धर्म्यं सुसुखं कर्तुमव्ययम्” इति । आत्मा प्रत्यक्षेण एव उपलब्धः धर्ममयश्च इति अवगम्यते । (श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता 9.2)

केचन पण्डितमन्याः चिन्तयन्ति यद् आत्मवस्तुनः निराकारत्वाद् बुद्ध्या तत् न प्राप्यते । अर्थात् आत्मा तु निराकारः । बुद्ध्या स न ज्ञायते तस्य आकाररहितत्वाद् इति । अतः दुःसाध्या सम्यग्ज्ञाननिष्ठा इति तेषाम् अभिप्रायः । आत्मविषयकज्ञानं न कथमपि प्राप्तुं शक्यते इति ते पण्डिताः मन्यन्ते । एतत् सत्यम् । ये गुरुसम्प्रदायरहिताः, अश्रुतवेदान्ताः, अत्यन्तबहिर्विषयासक्तबुद्धयः, सम्यक्प्रमाणेषु अकृतश्रमाः, तेषां कृते सम्यग्ज्ञाननिष्ठा दुःसाध्या एव । एवम् अत्र अविवेकिनां दृष्ट्या आत्मा वर्णितः । तद्विपरीतानां विवेकिनां तु लौकिकग्राह्यग्राहकभेदयुक्तवस्तुषु सद्भावसम्पादनम् अत्यन्तं कठिनम् । अर्थात् लौकिकवस्तु विवेकिनां कृते न कदापि सद् भवितुम् अर्हति । सत् केवलं ब्रह्म एव भवति । विवेकिनाम् आत्मचैतन्यव्यतिरेकेण वस्त्वन्तरस्य उपलब्धिः नैव भवति । विद्याविरोधाद् अविद्यानिवृत्तिः एवं प्रतिपादिता –

“या निशा सर्वभूतानां तस्यां जागर्ति संयमी ।
यस्यां जाग्रति भूतानि सा निशा पश्यतो मुनेः ॥” इति ।

(श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता 2.69)

एवमत्र विवेकिनाम् अविवेकिनां च दृष्ट्या आत्मा वर्णितः ।

आत्मस्वरूपावलम्बने कारणम्

अविद्याधारोपणनिराकरणमालं ब्रह्मणि कर्तव्यम् इति पूर्वम् एव प्रतिपादितम् । तस्मात् बाह्याकारभेदबुद्धिनिवृत्तिः एव आत्मस्वरूपालम्बने कारणम् । आत्मा कदाचित् कस्यचिद् अप्रसिद्धः प्राप्तव्यः त्याज्यः उपादेयो वा न भवति । सर्वोऽपि जनः अहम् अस्मि इत्येव व्यवहरति । अर्थात् सर्वेऽपि स्वसत्ताम् अङ्गीकुर्वन्ति । अहं नास्मि इत्येवम् अनुभवो न भवति । अत एव वयं सर्वे आत्मस्वरूपा एव । तस्मात् पृथक्तया आत्मा प्राप्तव्य इति नास्ति । द्वयोः अभिन्त्वात् न पृथक् ज्ञानं बुध्यते । यदि आत्मा अप्रसिद्धः इति स्वीक्रियते, सर्वाः प्रवृत्तयः निरर्थकाः स्युः । तदा देहाद्यचेतनार्थत्वं कल्पयितुं न शक्यम् । न च सुखार्थं सुखं दुःखार्थं वा दुःखम् आत्मावगत्यवसानार्थत्वाद् वा सर्वव्यवहारस्य । तस्माद् यथा स्वशरीरज्ञानाय प्रमाणान्तरस्य अपेक्षा न भवति, तथैव आत्मनः अन्तरतमत्वात् तदवगतिं प्रति न प्रमाणान्तरापेक्षा तिष्ठति । अत एव विवेकिनाम् आत्मज्ञाननिष्ठा सुप्रसिद्धा एव इति सिद्धम् ।

येषां मते ज्ञानं निराकाम् अप्रत्यक्षं च, तेषाम् अपि ज्ञेयावगतेः ज्ञानाधीनत्वात् सुखादिवद् एव ज्ञानम् अत्यन्तं प्रसिद्धम् इति अभ्युपगन्तव्यम् । तथा ज्ञानज्ञानाय जिज्ञासा न भवति । ज्ञानं प्रत्यक्षं भवति । यदि ज्ञानम् अप्रत्यक्षं स्यात्, तर्हि अन्यं ज्ञेयवस्तु इव तदपि ज्ञानाय इच्छा अभविष्यत् । अर्थात् यथा ज्ञाता घटादिरूपज्ञेयपदार्थान् ज्ञानेन अनुभवितुम् इच्छति, तथैव ज्ञानम् अपि अन्यज्ञानेन ज्ञातुम् इच्छा भवेत् । किन्तु एतत् न भवति । अतः ज्ञानम् अत्यन्तप्रसिद्धम् एव भवति, तस्माद् ज्ञाता अपि अत्यन्तप्रसिद्ध एव । तस्माद् ज्ञाने यत्नो न कर्तव्यः, किन्तु अनात्मबुद्धिनिवृत्तौ एव । अत एव ज्ञाननिष्ठा सुसम्पाद्या । तज्ज्ञानस्य एव परा निष्ठा । एवम् अत्र बाह्याकारभेदबुद्धिनिवृत्तिः एव आत्मस्वरूपालम्बने कारणम् इति प्रतिपादितम् ।

उपसंहारः

महाभारतस्य भीष्मपर्वणि वर्णितः अंशः एव श्रीमद्भगवद्गीतारूपेण ज्ञायते । अत्र विशेषतः अर्जुनं प्रति भगवान् श्रीकृष्णः उपदेशं प्रायच्छत् । द्विविधो हि वेदस्य धर्मः उक्तः – प्रवृत्तिलक्षणः निवृत्तिलक्षणश्च । तद्भर्मद्वयम् एव भगवान् श्रीकृष्णः शोकसागरे निमग्नाय अर्जुनाय उपदिदेश । श्रीमद्भगवद्गीतायाः मोक्षसन्ध्यासयोगाख्ये अष्टादशाध्याये आदौ सन्ध्यासस्य त्यागस्य च तत्त्वं ज्ञातुम् इष्टवान् अर्जुनः । तत्प्रश्नस्य उत्तरप्रदानाय विविधैः श्लोकैः भगवान् अर्जुनाय सर्वम् अपि तत्त्वम् उपदिष्टवान् । संसारस्तु क्रियाकारकफललक्षणः सत्त्वरजस्तमोगुणात्मकः अविद्यापरिकल्पितः । अतः एतादृशसंसारबन्धनाशेन मोक्षाय

प्रयत्नः करणीयः। अत एव आदौ संसारस्वरूपविषये भगवान् सम्यग् वर्णयति। तस्मात् ततः मोक्षोपायो वर्णयते।

नैष्कर्म्यसिद्धिं प्राप्तस्य हि आत्मविवेकज्ञानम् उत्पद्यते। तादृशी सिद्धिः केन क्रमेण भवतीति “सिद्धिं प्राप्तो यथा ब्रह्म” इति श्लोकेन उपदेशं प्रदत्तवान् भगवान् श्रीकृष्णः। भगवान् भाष्यकारः श्रीशङ्कराचार्यः श्लोकस्यास्य सम्यग् व्याख्यानं कृतवान्। ज्ञानात्मनोः निराकरणं निराकारत्वं च प्रतिपादितम् अत्र। यथा आत्मा निराकारो भवति, तथा बुद्धिः अपि भवति। अविद्याधारोपकारणाद् आत्मा बुद्धिश्च सम्यक् न ज्ञायते। आत्मा यथा स्वच्छो भवति, तथा बुद्धिरपि स्वच्छा एव। ततो भाष्यकारेण अन्यमतावलम्बिनां मतानि निराकृतानि। अविद्याधारोपनिराकरणमालं ब्रह्मणि कर्तव्यं न तु ब्रह्मज्ञाने यत्नः अत्यन्तप्रसिद्धत्वात्। अविद्याकल्पितेन नामरूपभेदेन अविवेकिनां बुद्धिः अपहृता भवति इत्यतः ते आत्मानम् अन्यथा जानन्ति। तद्विपरीतानां विवेकिनां तु लौकिकग्राह्यग्राहक भेदयुक्तवस्तुषु सद्भावसम्पादनम् अत्यन्तं कठिनम्, अतः तेषाम् आत्मचैतन्यव्यतिरेकेण वस्त्वन्तरोपलब्धिः न जायते। तस्माद् बाह्याकारभेदबुद्धिनिवृत्तिः एव आत्मस्वरूपालम्बनो कारणं भवति। तस्माद् ज्ञाने यत्नो न कर्तव्यः किन्तु अनात्मबुद्धिनिवृत्तौ एव। एवम् अत्र शाङ्करभाष्यदिशा नैष्कर्म्यलक्षणसिद्धेः ज्ञाननिष्ठत्वं विचारितमिति शम्।

परिशीलितग्रन्थाः

Advaita Sharada (<https://advaitasharada.sringeri.net/>)

ईशादि नौ उपनिषद् (शाङ्करभाष्यार्थ)। गीताप्रेस। गोरखपुर।

छान्दोग्योपनिषद् (शाङ्करभाष्यार्थ)। गीताप्रेस। गोरखपुर।

पंडा, गंगाधर (प्रकाशक)। संस्कृत वाङ्मय का बृहद् इतिहास। उत्तर प्रदेश संस्कृत संस्थान। लखनऊ।

बृहदारण्यकोपनिषद् (शाङ्करभाष्यार्थ)। गीताप्रेस। गोरखपुर।

भट्टः, नागराजः। स्वामि-वेदतत्त्वानन्दः। (सम्पादकौ)। भारतीयदर्शनम्। (1 भागः)।

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मिश्रः, आचार्यः श्रीरामचन्द्रः। संस्कृतसाहित्येतिहासः। चौखम्बा विद्याभवन। वाराणसी। 2017।

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श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता (शांकरभाष्य हिन्दी-अनुवादसहित)। गीताप्रेस। गोरखपुर।

सर्वज्ञभूषण। भारतीयदर्शनसार। संस्कृतगङ्गा। दारागञ्ज, प्रयाग। 21 जून, 2021 (द्वितीय संस्करण)। जनवरी 2019 (प्रथम संस्करण)।

आदिरन्त्येन सहेता इति सूत्रस्य महाभाष्यदिशा समीक्षणम्

ड० मलय-पोरे¹

प्रबन्धसारः

शास्त्रप्रवृत्तये माहेश्वरसूत्रेषु वर्णा उपदिष्टाः इति वैयाकरणराद्धान्तः। तत्र लाघवेन शास्त्रप्रवृत्तिस्तु अनुबन्धैः प्रत्याहारनिर्माणेन भवतीति धिया प्रत्याहारसंज्ञाविधायकम् “आदिरन्त्येन सहेता” (१/१/७१) इति सूत्रं महद् वैशिष्ट्यं बिभर्ति। तस्य सूत्रं महाभाष्ये व्याख्यानावसरे संज्ञासंज्ञिप्रत्ययाभावात् “आदिरिता सह तन्मध्यस्य” इति न्यासान्तरं प्रस्तुतम्। न्यासान्तरपक्षे संज्ञासंज्ञिप्रत्यये सत्यपि सूत्रेणैव संज्ञाशब्देन आदिरन्त्येन सहेता इत्यनेन संज्ञिनः स्वस्य आदेः मध्यगानां च ग्रहणात् सूत्रमेव समीचीनम्। इत्थं महाभाष्यपरिशीलनेन सूत्रमिदं प्रबन्धे समीक्षितम् इति शिवम्।

१.१ भूमिका

“अइउण्” इत्यादिनि माहेश्वरसूत्राणि कुतः उपदिष्टानीति प्रश्ने महाभाष्ये उत्तरं प्रोक्तं ‘वृत्तिसमवायार्थो उपदेशः’ (पतञ्जलिः ८०) इति। लाघवेन शास्त्रप्रवृत्त्यर्थः हि वर्णानाम् उपदेशः। लाघवेन शास्त्रप्रवृत्तिस्तु अनुबन्धद्वारा प्रत्याहारनिर्माणेन भवति। अतः लघुना उपायेन शास्त्रप्रवृत्तिमूलकप्रत्याहारसंज्ञाविधायकम् “आदिरन्त्येन सहेता” (१/१/७१) इति सूत्रं महद् वैशिष्ट्यं बिभर्ति। सूत्रमिदं महाभाष्यदिशा समीक्ष्यते।

१.२ सूत्रार्थः

अष्टाध्याय्याः प्रथमाध्यायस्य प्रथमपादस्य एकसप्ततितममिदं सूत्रम्। षड्विधेषु सूत्रेषु इदं संज्ञासूत्रम्। अनेन सूत्रेण प्रत्याहारसंज्ञा विधीयते। सूत्रमिदं पदचतुष्टयात्मकम्। आदिः अन्त्येन सह इता इति पदच्छेदः। अत्र यस्मात्पूर्वं नास्ति परमस्ति स आदिः। यस्मात्परं नास्ति पूर्वमस्ति सः अन्त्यः। अन्त्येन इत्यत्र “सहयुक्तेऽग्रधाने” (२/३/११) इत्यनेन तृतीया। इता इति अन्त्येनेत्यस्य विशेषणम्। अन्त्येन इता सह आदिः इति संज्ञादलम्। अन्त्येन इता सहादिर्हि अण् अच् हल् इत्यादिप्रत्याहाररूपः। अत्र आद्यन्त्यशब्दाभ्यां मध्यगा आक्षिप्यन्ते। “स्वं रूपं शब्दस्याशब्दसंज्ञा” (१/१/६८) इति सूत्रात् स्वमित्यनुवर्तते। अत्र स्वशब्देन आदिरेव परामृश्यते। अन्त्यस्याप्रधानत्वात् न तस्य परामर्शः। अत्र स्वं मध्यगाश्च संज्ञिभूताः। आदित्वमन्त्यत्वं च आद्यन्त्यशब्दाक्षिप्तसमुदायापेक्षम्। एवम्

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अन्त्येन इत्संज्ञकेन वर्णेन सह उच्चार्यमाण आदिः स्वस्य मध्यगानां च संज्ञा इति सूत्रार्थः समायाति। तथाह्युक्तं कौमुद्याम् – ‘अन्त्येनेता सहित आदिः मध्यगानां स्वस्य च संज्ञा स्यात्’ (भट्टोजिदीक्षितः ५) इति। अनेन सूत्रेण निष्पन्ना संज्ञा प्रत्याहारशब्देन व्यवहियते। प्रत्याहार इति प्राचां वैयाकरणानां संज्ञा।

अच् इत्युदाहरणम्। अन्त्येन “हलन्त्यम्” (१।३।३) इति सूत्रेण इत्संज्ञकेन ऐऔच् इति सूत्रस्थेन चकारेण सह उच्चार्यमाणः आदिः अइउण् इति सूत्रस्थः अकारः अच् इति प्रत्याहारः स्वस्य अकारस्य मध्यगानाम् इ उ ऋ लृ ए ओ ऐ औ इत्येतेषां वर्णानां संज्ञा भवति। अर्थाद् अच् इति प्रत्याहारः अ इ उ ऋ लृ ए ओ ऐ औ इत्येतेषां वर्णानां बोधकः।

१.३ महाभाष्यदिशा न्यासान्तरविचारः

१.३.१ न्यासान्तरपक्षः - “आदिरन्त्येन सहेता” (१।१।७१) इति सूत्रपर्यालोचनवेलायां महाभाष्ये आक्षेपः प्रस्तुतः यत् संज्ञिनः निर्देशाभावात् सूत्राद् बोधो न जायते। संज्ञि नाम बोध्यं संज्ञा च बोधिका भवति। अत्र सूत्रे बोध्यस्य संज्ञिनो निर्देशो नास्ति अतः सूत्राद् बोधो न जायते। तेन सूत्रस्य संज्ञासूत्रत्वमेव नोपपद्यते। यथा “वृद्धिरादैच्” (१।१।१) इत्यत्र वृद्धिः इति संज्ञाबोधकम् आदैच् इति च संज्ञिबोधकम्। एवम् आदिरन्त्येन इत्यत्र न ज्ञायते। अन्त्येन इता सह आदिः अच् हल् इत्यर्थकं वाक्यं संज्ञाबोधकम् इति चेत् तर्हि सम्पूर्णस्य संज्ञावाचकतया संज्ञिवाचकाभावेन संज्ञिनं विना संज्ञा नोपपद्यते। तथाह्युक्तं भाष्यकारेण वार्तिकम् – “आदिरन्त्येन सहेत्यसम्प्रत्ययः संज्ञिनोऽनिर्देशात्।” (पतञ्जलिः ५६५) इति।

बोधाभावे सति सूत्रस्य निष्फलत्वं स्यादिति धिया सूत्रस्य स्थाने “आदिरिता सह तन्मध्यस्य” इति सूत्राकारः आक्षेपकारिभिः परिकल्पितः। एवं सूत्राकारः क्रियते चेदस्य सूत्रस्यार्थो भवति – ‘आदिः अन्त्येन इता सह गृह्यमाणः स्वस्य तन्मध्यानां च ग्राहकः बोधकः स्यात्।’ इति। आदिरन्त्येन इता सह गृह्यमाणः संज्ञा बोधकः। संज्ञिनो बोध्या आदिमो वर्णः तन्मध्यगा वर्णाश्च। एवं संज्ञासंज्ञिबोधाद् “आदिरिता सह तन्मध्यस्य” इति सूत्रापेक्षया न्यासान्तरं समीचीनम्। तथाह्युक्तं महाभाष्ये – “सिद्धं त्वादिरिता सह तन्मध्यस्येति वचनात्” (पतञ्जलिः ५६५) इति।

१.३.२ सूत्रपक्षः

अत्र सूत्रपक्षवादिनां नये न्यासान्तरस्वीकारे नास्ति प्रयोजनम्। यथोक्तं सूत्रमेव सङ्गतम्। अस्मिन् पक्षे वार्तिकं प्रस्तौति – “सम्बन्धिशब्दैर्वा तुल्यम्” (पतञ्जलिः ५६५) इति। यथा सम्बन्धिशब्देन सम्बन्धिने आक्षेपो भवति एवमेव संज्ञाशब्देन संज्ञिन आक्षेपो भवति। यथा ‘मातरि वर्तितव्यम्’ इत्युच्यते। एतस्यार्थो भवति मातृविषये व्यवहारः कार्य इति। कस्य माता इति जिज्ञासा एव नोदेति। सम्बन्धिवाचकस्य मातृशब्दस्य बलादेव ज्ञायते यद् यस्य जनस्य या माता तस्यां व्यवहारः कथं सम्पादनीय इत्युच्यते।

एवमेवास्मिन् सूत्रे संज्ञिनः अनिर्देशे सत्यपि यं प्रति य आदिः अन्त्यश्च तस्य स्वस्य आदेः मध्यगानां च वर्णानां ग्रहणं करणीयमिति फलति। एवं स्वयम् आदिवर्णः मध्यगाश्च

वर्णाः संज्ञिन इति सिद्धम् । तथाह्युक्तं महाभाष्ये – ‘सम्बन्धिशब्दैर्वा तुल्यमेतत् । तद्यथा सम्बन्धिशब्दाः मातरि वर्तितव्यम्, पितरि शुश्रूषितव्यमिति । न चोच्यते स्वस्यां मातरि, स्वस्मिन् पितरीति । सम्बन्धाच्च गम्यते या यस्य माता, यो यस्य पितेति । एवमिहाप्यादिरन्त्य इति सम्बन्धिशब्दावेतौ । तत्र सम्बन्धादेतदवगन्तव्यम् – यं प्रति य आदिरन्त्य इति च भवति, तस्य ग्रहणं भवति, स्वस्य च रूपस्येति ।’ (पतञ्जलिः ५६६) इति ।

कैयटनये तु संज्ञया संज्ञी आक्षिप्यते अत्र (पतञ्जलिः ५६६) । आद्यन्तौ मध्यापेक्षौ इति मध्यगानामेव संज्ञित्वम् । अर्थात् संज्ञाबोधकेन अन्त्यसमभिव्याहृतेच्छब्दसहितादि शब्देन मध्यगानाम् आक्षेपः यद्यप्यादिशब्दः परमात्रमपेक्षते, अन्तश्च पूर्वमात्रम् । तथापि सह प्रयुज्यमानौ मध्यापेक्षाविति कैयटस्वारस्यम् । अत्र विप्रतिपद्यते नागेशः । तस्य नये तु आद्यन्तशब्दाभ्याम् अवयववाचकाभ्यां समुदायस्य आक्षेपो भवति । अत्र सम्बन्धित्वेन आदेरपि समुदाये ग्रहणम् । परन्तु इत्संज्ञकस्य अन्त्यस्य तु “आचारादप्रधानत्वाल्लोपश्च बलवत्तरः” इति वार्तिकबलात् लोपस्य बलवत्त्वात् न संज्ञित्वेन ग्रहणम् । तथाहि नागेशः उद्योते स्वारस्यं प्राह – ‘अन्ये तु आद्यन्तशब्दाभ्यामवयववाचकाभ्यामवयवी समुदाय आक्षिप्त इति सम्बन्धित्वेनाविशेषादादेरपि ग्रहणम् । अन्त्यस्य तु न आचारादप्रधानत्वाल्लोपश्च बलवत्तरः इत्युक्तेरन्यानुबन्धानामिवास्यापि संज्ञाकार्याभावात् ।’ (पतञ्जलिः ५६६) इति ।

“स्वं रूपं शब्दस्याशब्दसंज्ञा” (१।१।६८) इति सूत्रात् स्वपदानुवृत्तिमादाय अत्र दीक्षितनागेशयोः विप्रतिपत्तिः विद्यते । दीक्षितमते तु ‘यो हि बोधजनको भवति स बोधविषयो न भवति’ इति । एवञ्च अच् इत्यत्र अकारस्य ग्रहणं न भवति । तद्ग्रहणाय स्वं रूपमिति सूत्रात् स्वमित्यस्य पदस्यानुवृत्तिः । स्वशब्दस्य सर्वादिगणीयत्वात् सर्वनामत्वात् परामर्शकत्वम् । एवं स्वशब्देन प्रधानस्य आदेः परामर्शाद् आदेरपि प्रत्याहारसंज्ञा ।

नागेशमते यो हि बोधजनकः स बोधविषयो नास्तीति नियमो न विद्यते । तन्नये येन रूपेण बोधजनकता तेनैव रूपेण बोधविषयता न भवतीति नियमः । यथा “घेर्ङिति” (७।३।१११) इत्यत्र घिशब्दः संज्ञावाचकः । अतः स बोधकः । यदि च बोधविषयता न स्यात्तर्हि घिशब्दस्य घिसंज्ञाया अभावात् घेः इति प्रयोगो न स्यात् । अत्र सूत्रे घिशब्दस्य घित्वेन बोधजनकता इकारान्तत्वेन घिसंज्ञया बोधविषयता इति नास्ति दोषः । एवमेव आद्यन्तशब्दयोः आदित्वेनान्तत्वेन च समुदायघटकत्वेन बोधविषयता । अतः स्वपदस्य ग्रहणे नास्ति प्रयोजनम् । अन्त्यस्य तु अन्येनोपायेन निराकरणं कृतमेव ।

इत्थं परिशीलनेन ज्ञायते यद् “आदिरिता सह तन्मध्यस्य” इति न्यासान्तरस्वीकारस्य नास्ति प्रयोजनम् “आदिरन्त्येन सहेता” (१।१।७१) इति सूत्रमेव समीचीनम् ।

१.४ सूत्रपक्षे आद्यन्त्येच्छब्दविचारः -

एतत्सूत्रकृतायाः संज्ञायाः प्रत्याहार इति व्यपदेशः । प्रत्याहारशब्दो योगरूढः । प्रत्याह्रियन्ते संक्षिप्यन्ते वर्णा यत्र स प्रत्याहारः । प्रतिपूर्वकाद् आङ्-पूर्वकाद् हृधातोर्बाहुलकाद् घञा प्रत्याहारशब्दो निष्पन्नः । स हि यौगिकार्थः । यदि च यौगिकार्थः स्वीक्रियते तर्हि अ इत्यष्टादशानां संज्ञा, तस्यापि प्रत्याहारत्वापत्तिः । तद्वारणाय योगरूढत्वं

प्रत्याहारशब्दस्य स्वीकृतम् । प्रत्याहारशब्दः योगरूढः, आदिरन्त्येनेति सूत्रविहितसंज्ञापरकः नान्यः ।

वस्तुतस्तु सूत्रे आदिपदम् अन्त्यपदम् इत्यदं च लक्षणया स्वसदृशबोधकम् इति लक्ष्मीटाकाकृतः सभापतिशर्मोपाध्यायस्य मतम् (श्रीबालकृष्णपञ्चोली १६) । वस्तुतस्तु एतन्मतं हि समीचीनम् एव । अन्यथा अच् इत्यादिप्रत्याहारसिद्धिः न भवति । अन्त्येत् भवति ऐऔच् इति सूत्रघटकः चकारः, तत्सदृशः अच् इति प्रत्याहारघटकः चकारः । सादृश्यमतं स्ववृत्तिश्रावणप्रत्यक्षविषयतावच्छेदकधर्मवत्त्वसम्बन्धेन । यथा श्रावणप्रत्यक्षविषयः घटशब्दः । श्रावणप्रत्यक्षविषयतावच्छेदकं घटशब्दत्वम् ।

स्ववृत्तिः यः श्रावणप्रत्यक्षविषयतावच्छेदकधर्मः तद्वत्त्वसम्बन्धेन सादृश्यं विवक्षितम् । ऐऔच् इति सूत्रघटकचकारस्य सादृश्यम् अच् इति प्रत्याहारघटके चकारे गृहीतम् । एवं स्वं चकारः, तद्वृत्तिः श्रावणप्रत्यक्षविषयतावच्छेदकधर्मः चशब्दत्वधर्मः, तद्वत्त्वसम्बन्धेन अच् इति प्रत्याहारघटके चकारे सादृश्यम् । एवम् अन्त्येत्सदृशेन सहितः आदिसदृशः अच् समुदायस्य घटकानां संज्ञा ।

सादृश्यस्य प्रतियोगी ऐऔच् इति सूत्रघटकः चकारः । सादृश्यस्यानुयोगी अच् इति प्रत्याहारघटकः चकारः । स्वपदेन अच् इति प्रत्याहारस्य ग्रहणम् । तद्वत्त्वकः अकारः । अकारानुयोगिकसादृश्यस्य प्रतियोगी अइउण् इति सूत्रघटकः अकारः । तन्निष्ठा या आदिता, तन्निरूपकः समुदायः अकारादिचान्तसमुदायः अच् इति प्रत्याहारः । एवमेव अच् इति प्रत्याहारसूत्रघटकचकारानुयोगिकसादृश्य प्रतियोगित्वम् ऐऔच् इति माहेश्वरसूत्रघटके चकारे । तन्निष्ठान्त्यतानिरूपकः समुदायः अकारादिचान्तसमुदायः अच् इति प्रत्याहारः । तादृशसमुदायस्य घटकानां संज्ञा अस्ति अन्त्येत्सदृशेन सहित आदिसदृशः अच् इति प्रत्याहारः ।

१.५ समीक्षणम् -

अस्य सूत्रस्य व्याख्यानावसरे महाभाष्यकारेण “आदिरिता सह तन्मध्यस्य” इति न्यासान्तरं प्रस्तुतम् । न्यासान्तरमिदं स्वप्रत्याख्यानद्वारा सूत्रस्यैव संज्ञासंज्ञिप्रत्यायकत्वं विज्ञापयति । “आदिरन्त्येन सहेता” (१।१।७१) इति सूत्रे संज्ञिनः निर्देशाभावात् सूत्राद् बोधो न जायते । अतः सूत्रस्य स्थाने “आदिरिता सह तन्मध्यस्य” इति न्यासान्तरं परिकल्पितम् । तत्र च आदिरन्त्येन इता सह गृह्यमाणः इति संज्ञायाः आदिमो वर्णः तन्मध्यगा वर्णाश्च इति संज्ञिनो बोधाद् न्यासान्तरं समीचीनम् । सम्बन्धशब्देन सम्बन्धिन आक्षेपो यथा भवति तथैवाल संज्ञाशब्देन आदिरन्त्येन सहेता इत्यनेन संज्ञिनः समुदायस्य ग्रहणात् सूत्रमेव समीचीनमिति बोधनमेव न्यासान्तरस्य प्रयोजनम् । सूत्रपरिशीलनवेलायां नागेशमतस्य कैयटाद् युक्तियुक्ततया समुदायस्य ग्रहणमिति मतमेव ग्राह्यम् । बोधजनकस्य बोधविषयत्वस्वीकारे तु स्वशब्दानुवृत्तिः न कार्या इति नागेशनये लाघवम् । किञ्च सूत्रस्थस्य आदिपदस्य अन्त्यपदस्य इत्यदस्य च सादृश्ये लक्षणा स्वीकार्या इति सयुक्तिकं महाभाष्यादिपरिशीलनेन प्रतिपादितम् इति शिवम् ।

परिशीलितग्रन्थावली

नरसिंहमाचार्यः, एम एस् । *महाभाष्यप्रदीपव्याख्यानानि* (१ खण्डः) । फ्रेञ्च इनस्टिटिउट अफ पण्डिचेरी । पण्डिचेरी । १९७३।

पतञ्जलिः । *व्याकरणमहाभाष्यम्*, प्रथमखण्डः । भार्गवशास्त्री जोशी(सम्पा०) । चौखम्बा संस्कृत प्रतिष्ठान । दिल्ली । २०१४।

पाणिनिः । *अष्टाध्यायी* । गोपालशास्त्री (सम्पा०) । चौखम्बा संस्कृत संस्थान । वाराणसी । २०१०।

भट्टोजीदीक्षितः. शर्मा च (संशो०) सिद्धान्तमुक्तावली, मोतीलाल बनारसीदास । वाराणसी । २००४।

श्रीबालकृष्णपञ्चोली (सम्पा०), *वैयाकरणसिद्धान्तकौमुदी लक्ष्मीव्याख्योपेता* (१-भागः) । मोतीलाल बनारसीदास । वाराणसी । १९६६।

वामनजयादित्यौ । *काशिका न्यासपदमञ्जरीसहिता* (प्रथमो भागः) । डा०

जयशङ्करलालत्रिपाठी, डा० सुधाकरमालवीयः च (सम्पा०) । तारा बुक एजेन्सी । वाराणसी । २०००।

चन्द्रालोके नैतिकता : एकं सोदाहरणं विश्लेषणम्

सत्येनशीटः¹

शोधसारः

द्वादशशतकस्य पीयूषवर्षजयदेवाचार्येण विरचितः ग्रन्थोऽयं चन्द्रालोकः। अयं ग्रन्थः एकः अलङ्कारग्रन्थः। अतः अस्मिन् ग्रन्थे रस-गुण-अलङ्कारादीनाम् अर्थात् काव्यतत्त्वानां विस्तृता आलोचना जाता। परन्तु इत्यादौः आलोचनाभिः कानि कानि नैतिकतानि प्राप्तानि तथा समाजस्य कल्याणं कथं सम्भवेत्? – इति मम शोधकार्यस्य मुख्योद्देश्यः।

कुञ्चीपदानि- चन्द्रालोकः, नैतिकता, जयदेवाचार्यः, नीतिशास्त्रम्, अलङ्कारिकः।

भूमिका

“कत अजानारे जानाइले तुमि।” (गीताञ्जलिः - पृ. ४)

इतिहासदृष्ट्या मनुष्याणां मनसि यदा गम्भीरविचारस्य तथा विवेचनायाः उदयो भवति, तदा ते मनुष्याः ध्यानेन बाह्यजगतः समस्यानां समाधानं कुर्वन्ति। कियत्कालात् परं जीवनस्य व्यावहारिकावश्यकतानां समाधानं कुर्वन्ति। तदनन्तरं ते सम्पूर्णव्यक्तेः समाधानं चिन्तितवन्तः। जीवनस्य विभिन्नानाम् अङ्गानां मननं कृत्वा ते परिणामे उपनीता भवन्ति यद् – बुद्धिजीविव्यक्तयः केवलमात्रं शारीरिकस्पृहायाः उपरि तथा बाह्यस्पृहायाः उपरि न निर्भराः, ते सामाजिकचेतनया बुद्ध्या च स्वस्य कर्तव्यं तथा अधिकारं प्राप्तुमिच्छन्ति। अतः एषा प्रेरणा हि नैतिकतामुद्भावयति।

नैतिकदर्शनं तु नीतिशास्त्रम्। नीतिशास्त्रम् – इति पदस्य मध्ये द्वौ शब्दौ वर्तेते। एका हि नीतिः, अपरं शास्त्रम्। नीतेः अर्थः वामनशिवरायाष्टस्य संस्कृत-हिन्दी-कोषानुसारेण निर्देशनम्, दिग्दर्शनम्, आचरणम्, व्यवहारः, कार्यक्रमः, औचित्यम्, शालीनता, बुद्धिमत्ता, व्यवहार-कुशलता, उपायः, आचारशास्त्रम्, आचारदर्शनम् इत्यादीनि। नीतिपदस्य व्युत्पत्तिः – नी-धातोः उत्तरं क्तिन्-प्रत्यययोगेन भवति। यस्यार्थः भवति ज्ञानम्, दिग्दर्शनम्, निर्देशनम्, व्यवहारः, औचित्यम् इत्यादीनि। अनेन आचारणानुसारेण कृतं कार्यं व्यक्तिस्वमाजयोः उपकारं साधयति। शास्त्रपदस्यार्थः अमरकोषानुसारेण

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“निदेशग्रन्थयोः शास्त्रम् ।”(अमरकोषः - ३७३) अर्थात् आज्ञा, समादेशः, विधिः इत्यादयः अथवा कस्यचित् अध्ययनस्य संक्षिप्तः भाण्डारो हि शास्त्रम् । संक्षेपेण उच्यते यत्, यत्र देशकालयोः आचारणानुरूपस्य व्यवहारस्य निरूपणं भवति, अथवा यद् शास्त्रं मनुष्यसमाजयोः हिताय देशकालानुसारेण नैतिकाचरणस्यानुरूपव्यवहारस्य तथा शासनस्य विधानं करोति, तदेव शास्त्रम् । अतः उच्यते व्यक्ति-समाजयोः कल्याणस्य मानदण्डो हि नीतिशास्त्रम् ।

भारतीयनीतिशास्त्रे नैतिकता

भारतीयनीतिशास्त्रस्य प्रमुखा विशेषता विद्यते । यथा –

प्राचीनता

सभ्यतायाः इतिहासे भारतीयनीतिशास्त्रं हि प्राचीनतमं नीतिदर्शनम् । भारतीयग्रन्थः वेदः जगतः प्राचीनतमः ग्रन्थः । वेदेऽस्मिन् अहिंसायाः महत्त्वस्य तथा वर्णाश्रमधर्मस्य चर्चा अस्ति, या भारतीयनीतिशास्त्रस्य मूलाधारः ।

व्यावहारिकता

भारतीयनीतिशास्त्रं हि सर्वदा व्यावहारिकम् । यत् मनुष्यस्य बौद्धिकचिन्तने तथा वर्णाश्रमस्य कर्तव्यविचारे साहाय्यं करोति । शुभस्वरूपस्य विश्लेषणेन भारतीयनीतिशास्त्रं जीवनस्य पूर्णताप्राप्तेः उपायं वदति । भारतीयनीतिशास्त्रं चातुर्वर्ण्यस्य सिद्धान्तं तथा जीवनस्य साध्यसाधनञ्च स्पष्टीकरोति । बौद्धजैनयोः नीतिशास्त्रे तु दार्शनिकसमस्यां विहाय नैतिकविवेचनं प्रति ध्यानं प्रदत्तम् ।

आध्यात्मिकता

भारतीयनीतिशास्त्रं व्यावहारिकं भूत्वापि आध्यात्मिकम् । यथापवित्रहिन्दुग्रन्थे गीतायां दृश्यते यत्, विश्वरूपदर्शने विश्वपरिचालितवान् यः परमात्मा, स एव मानवस्य जीवनमपि परिचालयति । स परमात्मा हि मानवस्य मूललक्ष्यम् । यं विना मोक्षो न सम्भवेत् । कारणं मोक्षो मानवनां मुक्तिं प्रददाति । अनेन कारणेन भारतीयनीतिशास्त्रे मोक्षो हि परमपुरुषार्थः ।

पुरुषार्थसाधनता

भारतीयनीतिशास्त्रस्य लक्ष्यं भवति पुरुषार्थसाधनम् । पुरुषार्था हि धर्मार्थ-काम-मोक्षरूपाः चत्वारः भवन्ति । सर्वे भारतीयचिन्तकाः इमान् चतुरः पुरुषार्थान् मनुष्यजीवनस्य लक्ष्यं मन्यन्ते । अतः पुरुषार्थसाधनं हि भारतीयजीवनस्य मूललक्ष्यम् ।

अलङ्कारशास्त्रे चन्द्रालोकः

संस्कृतालङ्कारशास्त्रे बहवः आलङ्कारिकाः आविर्भूतवन्तः । तेषु अन्यतमो हि

द्वादशशतकस्य विशिष्टालङ्कारिकः पीयूषवर्षः जयदेवाचार्यः । यस्य पितरौ महादेवः सुमित्रा च । तस्य अन्यतमः काव्यतत्त्वमूलकग्रन्थो हि चन्द्रालोकः । अत्र १० मयूखाः सन्ति, तत्र प्रायः ३५० श्लोकाः विद्यन्ते । अस्मिन् ग्रन्थे काव्यस्य स्वरूपम्, हेतुः, प्रयोजनम्, दोषः, गुणः, रसः, अलङ्कारः इत्यादयः आलोचिताः । यद्यपि अयं ग्रन्थः अलङ्कारतत्त्वविषयकस्तथापि अलङ्कारतत्त्वानां विश्लेषणावसरे किञ्च उदाहरणानामालोचनावसरे स्थले स्थले जीवनदर्शनस्य नैतिकतायाः चिलमपि प्रतिफलितमस्ति । तस्मात् काव्यतत्त्वविश्लेषणवेलायां तानि नैतिकभावापूर्णानि स्थलान्यत्र संगृह्य उपस्थाप्यन्ते । वर्तमाने आलोच्येऽस्मिन् चन्द्रालोकग्रन्थे केचन नैतिकभावाः दृश्यन्ते तेषां चर्चा अधःस्तात् क्रियते । यथा-

काव्यस्य प्रयोजने नैतिकता

द्वादशशतकस्य विशिष्टालङ्कारिकः जयदेवाचार्यः तस्यचन्द्रालोकग्रन्थे काव्यस्य प्रयोजनप्रसङ्गे उक्तवान् -

“युक्त्यास्वाद्यलसद्रसैकवसतिः साहित्यसारस्वत-
क्षीराम्भोधिरगाधतामुपदधत्सेव्यः समाश्रीयताम् ।
श्रीरस्मादुपदेशकौशलमयं पीयूषमस्माज्जग-

ज्जाग्रद्भासुरपद्मकेशरयशःशीतांशुरस्माद् बुधाः ॥” (चन्द्रालोकः १.३)

अर्थात्, यथा क्षीरसागरमन्थनेन अमृतं निर्गतं भवति, तथा यदि कश्चन विद्वान् चन्द्रालोकग्रन्थाभ्यासं करोति तर्हि तस्य अमृतलाभो भवति । अत्र एका घटना स्मरणीया यत्, क्षीरसागरमन्थनस्य समये अमृतं न निर्गतं भवति । आदौ लक्ष्मी-चन्द्र-गरलादीनि १३ प्रकाराणि रत्नानि प्राप्तानि, पश्चात् अमृतं लब्धम् । अतः एतस्मात् अस्माभिः या नैतिकता प्राप्ता सा हि - “यदि साफल्यं प्राप्तुमिच्छति तर्हि जीवने अनेकसमस्यायां विद्यमानायामपि निरन्तरं चेष्टा करणीया ।”

पूर्वाचार्याणां सम्मानं प्रति नैतिकता

जयदेवाचार्येण तस्य चन्द्रालोकग्रन्थे भरत-भामह-वामन-मम्मटप्रमुखान् पूर्वाचार्यान् प्रति सम्मानप्रदानं कृत्वा उक्तम् -

“तं पूर्वाचार्यसूर्योक्तिज्योतिस्तोमोद्गमं स्तुमः ।” (चन्द्रालोकः १.४)

एषा हि संस्कृतालङ्कारशास्त्रस्य एका अन्यतमा परम्परा । अतोऽत्रास्माभिर्या नैतिकता दृष्टा सा हि - “अतिमहज्जनैरपि गुरुजनान् प्रति श्रद्धा करणीया ।” प्रसङ्गेऽस्मिन् गीतायामुक्तम् - “श्रद्धावान् लभते ज्ञानम् ।” (श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता ४.३९)

स्वकीयताप्रसङ्गे नैतिकता

संस्कृतालङ्कारशास्त्रे बहुषु अलङ्कारग्रन्थेषु सत्स्वपि जयदेवाचार्यः कथं चन्द्रालोकग्रन्थं लिखितवान् ? अस्मिन् प्रसङ्गे तेन उक्तम् -

“नाशङ्कनीयमेतेषां मतमेतेन द्रुष्यते ।

किन्तु चक्षुर्मृगाक्षीणां कज्जलेनेव भूष्यते ॥” (चन्द्रालोकः १.५)

अर्थात्, इमे चञ्चलसुन्दरमृगनयने निकषा कृष्णकज्जलं किमपि न, परन्तु एतादृशस्य कज्जलस्य एकांशः यदि मृगनयनयोः धारयति तर्हि तत् अतीव सौन्दर्यं वर्धयति ।

यथा – अनेकेषु नक्षत्रेषु विद्यमानेष्वपि ते न प्रकाशयन्ते सूर्यस्यालोकाप्रभावात्, किन्तु रात्रेः अन्धकारः एव तान् नक्षत्रान् प्रकाशयति । अतोऽत्र अस्माभिः या नैतिकता प्राप्ता सा हि - “ कदापि क्षुद्रस्य तथा अतितुच्छवस्तुनः ताच्छिल्यं न कुर्यात् ।”

काव्यहेतुप्रसङ्गे नैतिकता

अलङ्कारशास्त्रस्य परम्परायां जयदेवाचार्यः काव्यहेतुविषये चन्द्रालोकग्रन्थे उक्तवान् -

“ प्रतिभैव श्रुताभ्याससहिता कवितां प्रति ।

हेतुर्मृदम्बुसम्बद्धा बीजमाला लतामिव ॥” (चन्द्रालोकः १.६)

अर्थात् यथा एकस्याः लतायाः उत्पत्तेः कारणं भवति मृत्तिकाजलबीजानि एतानि लीणि, तथा काव्योत्पत्तेः कारणमपि प्रतिभाश्रुताभ्यासाः एतानि लीणि भवेयुः । अत्र एकस्य नूनाधिक्यमपि न भवेत् । अस्मिन् प्रसङ्गे मम्मटाचार्येण उक्तम् -

“ शक्तिर्निपुणता लोकशास्त्रकाव्याद्यवेक्षणात् ।

काव्यज्ञशिक्षयाभ्यास इति हेतुस्तदुद्भवे ॥” (काव्यप्रकाशः १.२)

यथा- यदि बहुजनैः किमपि कार्यं क्रियन्ते तर्हि तत् कार्यं अतिसहजम्, अल्पश्रमि तथा सुन्दरं भवति । किन्तु तत् कार्यं यदि कोऽपि एकाकी करोति तर्हि तत् कार्यं अतिकठिनम्, अतिपरिश्रमि तथा असुन्दरं भवति । अतः अत्र अस्माभिः या नैतिकता लब्धा सा हि - “ एकतैव वलम् ।”

काव्यस्य स्वरूपे नैतिकता

काव्यस्य स्वरूपप्रसङ्गे जयदेवाचार्येण अन्यान्यालङ्कारिकाणामिव उक्तं यथा-

“निर्दोषा लक्षणवती सरीतिगुणभूषणा ।

सालङ्कारसानेकवृत्तिवाक्काव्यनामभाक् ॥” (चन्द्रालोकः १.७)

अर्थात्, दोषाहीना, लक्षणयुक्ता, रीतियुक्ता, गुणयुक्ता, अलङ्कारयुक्ता, तथा वृत्तियुक्ता वाक् वाणी वा हि काव्यम् । अतः किमपि रचयित्वा काव्यमिति घोषणा न करणीया । निर्दिष्टनियमानुसारेण यदि काव्यं रचितं भवेत् अपि च तत् काव्यं यदि विद्वद्जनैः प्रशंसायाः विषयो भवेत् तर्हि तत् काव्यं स्वीकरणीयम् । अतः अलङ्कारशेखरकारेण श्रीकेशवमिश्रेण उक्तम् -

“श्लाघ्यः पामरपरिषदि कविरिति होलाककर्तापि ।

यस्मै स्पृहयति विद्वांस्तत्काव्यं काव्यमित्याहुः ॥” (अलंकारशेखरः - पृ. ११)

अत्र अस्माभिः या नैतिकता लब्धा सा हि - “ मनुष्याः हि नियमाधीनाः ।” कारणं

स्वानुमोदितः विषयो न यथार्थः, स यदि विद्वद्गण्डलीभिः ग्रहणयोग्यं भवेत् तर्हि स स्वीकृतः भविष्यति । अस्य नियमस्य प्रसङ्गे उक्तमस्ति यथा- “यस्मिन् देशे यदाचारः ।”

अलङ्काररहितकाव्यप्रसङ्गे नैतिकता

ये आलङ्कारिकाः अलङ्काररहितौ शब्दार्थौ काव्यमितिस्वीकृतवन्तः, तेषां प्रसङ्गे जयदेवाचार्येण चन्द्रालोकग्रन्थे उक्तम् -

“अङ्गीकरोति यः काव्यं शब्दार्थानलङ्कृती ।

असौ न मन्यते कस्मादनुष्णामनलङ्कृती ॥” (चन्द्रालोकः १.८)

अर्थात् , यः आलङ्कारिकः अलङ्काररहितौ शब्दार्थौ काव्यमिति स्वीकरोति, स विद्वान् कथं अग्निः तापरहितो इति न स्वीकरोति । अतः यथा अग्नेः अनुष्णत्वम् असम्भवम्, तद्वत् अलङ्काररहितौ शब्दार्थौ काव्यमित्यपि अस्वाभाविकम् । यद्यपि पूर्वाचार्यः काव्यप्रकाशकारः मम्मटाचार्यः तस्य ग्रन्थे शीलाभट्टारिकायाः श्लोकमुद्धृत्य उक्तविषयं प्रतिपादितवान्-

“कचित् तु स्फुटालङ्कारविरहेऽपि न काव्यत्वहानिः ।” (काव्यप्रकाशः १.४)

अतः वक्तुं शक्यते यत्, कचित् स्फुटरसस्थले अलङ्काररहितौ शब्दार्थौ काव्यं भवति । तथापि पूर्वाचार्याणां मतमपि जयदेवाचार्यं निकषा संशयात्मकम् ।

यथा – आनन्दवर्धनाचार्येण तस्य ध्वन्यालोकग्रन्थे विस्तृतभावेन ध्वनिः प्रतिपादितः । अपि च तेन उक्तं यत्, ध्वनिः नाम किमपि नववस्तु नास्ति, यः आदौ व्यवहृतः । रामायण-महाभारतयोः अपि अस्य ध्वनेः प्रयोगः प्रमाणयितुं शक्यते । तथापि विरोधिनां मध्ये ध्वनिविषयः संशयात्मकः तथा किमपि नववस्तु, अपि च अलङ्कारस्य मध्ये एषः निहितः इति ।

अतः अत्र अस्माभिः या नैतिकता दृष्टा सा हि - “उपकारि तथा व्यतिक्रमि चिन्तनं समाजे सहजतया गृहीतं न भवति ।”

अक्षरसंहतिलक्षणे नैतिकता

जयदेवाचार्येण चन्द्रालोकग्रन्थे अक्षरसंहतेः लक्षणप्रसङ्गे उक्तवान् -

“अल्पक्षरा विचित्रार्थव्यातिरक्षरसंहतिः ।

उषाकान्तेनानुगतः शुरः शौरिरयं पुनः ॥” (चन्द्रालोकः ३.१)

अर्थात्, यत्र अल्पाक्षरप्रयोगेन चमत्कारिणः अर्थस्य प्रतीतिः भवति , तत् अक्षरसंहतिलक्षणं भवति । उपर्युक्तश्लोकस्योदाहरणं यथा - “ उषाकान्तेनानुगतः ।” अर्थात् , यादववीरो हि भगवान् श्रीकृष्णः । यस्य अनुगमनं करोति उषाकान्तः अनिरुद्धः । अत्र उषाकान्तस्य अनिरुद्धस्य अनुगमनेन महाभारतस्य एका दीर्घा कथा वर्णिता ।

महाभारतस्य दशमस्कन्धस्य ६२- ६३ तमाध्याये वर्णितमस्ति यत्, शिवभक्तनृपवलेः पुत्रः वाणासुरः अस्ति शोणितपुरस्य शासकः । तस्य उषा नामका एका कन्या आसीत् । उषा

स्वप्ने अनिरुद्धस्य दर्शनं करोति । उषायाः सखि हि चित्रलेखा । सा वाणासुरस्य मन्त्रिणः कन्या । सा चित्रकलायां निपुणासीत् । चित्रकला चित्रस्य अङ्कनं कृत्वा उषां दर्शयति । तथा स्वप्ने यः दृष्टः स एव चिह्नितः । चित्रफलकमस्ति प्रद्युम्नपुत्रस्य अनिरुद्धस्य, यः खलु श्रीकृष्णपौत्रः । द्वारिकायाः चित्रलेखा अनिरुद्धमपहृत्य उषायाः प्रासादम् आनीतवती । अपि च उषानिरुद्धयोः विवाहो भवति । वाणासुरः एतत् ज्ञात्वा अनिरुद्धं कारागारे आबद्धं करोति । नारदेन एतां घटनां श्रुत्वा यादवसैनिकान् नीत्वा श्रीकृष्णः वाणासुरेण सह भयङ्करयुद्धं करोति । अतः वाणासुरस्य सहस्रबाहूनां कर्तनं कृत्वा तं हतवान् । अनन्तरं उषा-अनिरुद्धयोः विवाहो भवति । एषा विस्तृतघटना अल्पाक्षरेण प्रकाशिता । यया जयदेवाचार्यस्य पाण्डित्यं प्रकाशयति ।

अतःअत्र अस्माभिः या नैतिकता प्राप्ता सा हि - “यदि पण्डितो भवेत् तर्हि अल्पकथा वदनीया ।” पण्डिताः केवलमालं विचारविवेचनानुसारेण अल्पकथां वदन्ति । अस्मिन् प्रसङ्गे उक्तमस्ति यत् - विद्वांसः मितभाषिणः ।”

शोभालक्षणे नैतिकता

जयदेवाचार्यः शोभालक्षणस्य स्वरूपप्रसङ्गे उक्तवान् -

“शोभा ख्यातोऽपि यद्दोषो गुणकीर्त्या निषिध्यते ।

मुधा निन्दन्त संसारं कंसारिर्यत्र पूज्यते ॥” (चन्द्रालोकः ३.२)

अर्थात् , यत्र विद्यमानाः प्रसिद्धदोषाः अपि गुणस्य वर्णनेन आवृताः भवन्ति । तत् हि शोभालक्षणम् । यथा - अयं संसारः क्षणभङ्गुरः तथा नश्वरादिदोषेण युक्तो भवति । अतः इमं संसारं लोकः निन्दति । किन्तु पुनः अस्मिन् संसारे श्रीकृष्णस्य पूजा भवति । तदा संसारेऽस्मिन् सुखं विराजते ।

यथा सर्वे लोकाः कर्दमाक्तजलाशयस्य घृणां करोति, तदा इमं जलाशयं सर्वे ‘कर्दमाक्तजलाशयः’ इति उक्तवन्तः । परन्तु यदा तस्मिन् जलाशये पद्मं प्रस्फुटति तदा इमं जलाशयं लोकाः ‘पद्मजलाशयः’ - इति वदन्ति, तत्समये कोऽपि ‘कर्दमाक्तजलाशयः’ - इति न वदति । अतः पूर्वदोषः अत्र गौणो भवति ।

अतःअत्र अस्माभिः या नैतिकता लब्धा सा हि - “अतः अस्मिन् जीवने किञ्चन कार्यं करणीयं येन लोकैः तव अतीतं न उक्त्वा वर्तमानं कथयेयुः ।” यथा - वाल्मीकिमुनिः प्रथमे जीवने दस्युरत्नाकरो भूत्वापि रामायणं रचयित्वा लोकसमाजे स महर्षिवाल्मीकिमुनिरूपेण पूजितवान् ।

प्रतिषेधलक्षणे नैतिकता

पीयूषवर्षजयदेवाचार्यः तस्य चन्द्रालोकग्रन्थे प्रतिषेधस्य लक्षणे उक्तवान् -

“प्रतिषेधः प्रसिद्धानां कारणानामनादरः ।

न युद्धेन भ्रुवोः स्पन्देनैव वीरा निपातिताः ॥” (चन्द्रालोकः ३.५)

अर्थात्यत्र प्रसिद्धकारणस्य अनादरं कृत्वा किमपि अप्रसिद्धकारणं कार्यसिद्धेः कारणं भवति, तत् हि प्रतिषेधलक्षणम् ।

यथा – वीरस्य युद्धेन न, परन्तु नायिकायाः भ्रुकुटिसञ्चालनेन योद्धाः हताः । अत्र वीरविजयस्य प्रसिद्धकारणं युद्धो न दृश्यते, केवलमात्रं नायिकायाः भ्रुकुटिसञ्चालनं नाम अप्रसिद्धकारणमेव युद्धकारणम् ।

यथा – घटोत्पत्तिकक्षेत्रे मृत्तिका प्रधानकारणं भवति । अपि च घोटकः सूर्यः वा गौणकारणं भवति । तथापि अप्रसिद्धघटकोऽपि सूर्योऽपि वा घटोत्पत्तेः कारणं भवति । तं विना कार्यं न सिद्धति । अतःअत्र अस्माभिः या नैतिकता प्राप्ता सा हि – “केवलं वृहत्तुपकारीव्यक्तितं न, क्षुद्रोपकारीव्यक्तिमपि कदापि न विस्मरणीया ।”

रसस्य लक्षणे नैतिकता

पीयूषवर्षजयदेवाचार्यः तस्य चन्द्रालोकग्रन्थस्य षष्ठमयूखे रसस्य लक्षणे उक्तवान् –

“आलम्बनोद्दीपनात्मा विभावः कारणं द्विधा ।

कार्योऽनुभावो भावश्च सहायो व्यभिचार्यपि ॥” (चन्द्रालोकः ६.१)

अर्थात्, रसस्य कारणं हि विभावः । विभावः द्वौ प्रकारौ यथा – आलम्बनविभावोद्दीपनविभावश्च । अनुभावः अस्य कारणस्य कार्यं भवति । अपि च व्यभिचारभावः अस्य अनुभावस्य सहायको भवति । अत्र अस्माभिः दृश्यते यत्, रसोत्पत्तिकक्षेत्रे विभावः, अनुभावः अपि च व्यभिचारिभावः एतेषां त्रयाणां प्रयोजनम् । अस्य नूनाधिक्यमपि रसोत्पत्तेः वाधको भवति ।

यथा – एकमाल्यस्य निर्माणे पुष्पसमूहस्य प्रयोजनम् । एकेन द्वाभ्यां वा पुष्पाभ्यां माल्यं न निर्मायते । तद्वत् विभावानुभावव्यभिचारिश्चापि मिलित्वा रसमुत्पादयति । अतःअत्र अस्माभिः या नैतिकता प्राप्ता सा हि – “एकतैव वलम् ।”

उपसंहारः

विश्वस्य उन्नतशीलः श्रेष्ठो जीवो हि मनुष्यः । कारणं मनुष्याः एव केवलमात्रं चिन्तनं कुर्वन्ति । अपि च चिन्तनं कृत्वा शुभमन्दयोः विचारं कुर्वन्ति । तत्र चिन्तनस्य यथार्थं परामर्शं ददाति नीतिशास्त्रम् । वस्तुतः मनुष्याः जीवनधारणं कृत्वापि तस्य जीवनस्य आदर्शं न जानन्ति । बुद्धिवृत्तिसपन्नमनुष्याणां जीवनं केवलमात्रं धारणाय न, अपि तु निर्माणाय । अतोऽस्य जीवनस्य निर्माणाय कस्यचिदादर्शस्य प्रयोजनं - तद्वि नैतिकता । येन नैतिकादर्शालोकेन जीवनं सुन्दरं भवति, परन्तु तस्य ज्ञानं नास्ति साधारणमनुष्याणाम् । नैतिकदार्शनिकैः नैतिकादर्शिनिरूपणाय नीतिशास्त्रं रचितम् । अतः एतत् नीतिमूलकतत्त्वं नीतिशास्त्रे तु निहितमस्त्येव, परन्तु अस्याः नैतिकतायाः निर्देशः प्रायः सर्वेषु शास्त्रेष्वेव उपलभ्यते । तत्तु सूक्ष्मेक्षिकया द्रष्टव्यं चिन्तितव्यं विचारयितव्यं च । अस्माकं शास्त्राणि

विविधकौशलेन सामाजिकनां कृते नैतिकशिक्षामेव प्रयच्छन्ति । अतः अलालङ्कारशास्त्रमपि व्यतिक्रमरूपं न । अस्मिन् शोधप्रबन्धे अलङ्कारग्रन्थेषु चन्द्रालोकस्थालङ्कारतत्त्वविचारप्रसङ्गे ग्रन्थकारेण प्रकारन्तरेण या नैतिकताः प्रदत्ताः तासां सोदाहरणमुपस्थापनं कृत्वा विरम्यते । अस्य नीतिशास्त्रस्य गुरुत्वप्रसङ्गे वयं सर्वे स्मर्तुं शक्नुमः कविगुरोः वाणी-

“ आकाश हते प्रभात-आलो

आमार पाने हात वाडालो, ”(गीताञ्जलि: – पृ. ४४)

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न्यायवैशेषिकमते मनसः स्वरूपम्

सन्तोषमण्डलः¹

शोधसारः

न्यायवैशेषिकानुसारम् अन्तिमं द्रव्यं मनः। मनः अन्तरिन्द्रियम्। प्रत्येकस्य जीवस्य देहे मनः नाम प्रमेयमस्ति। मनसः स्वरूपव्याख्याने तर्कसंग्रहकारेण उक्तम् – सुखाद्युपलब्धिसाधनम् इन्द्रियं मनः। अर्थात् सुखं, दुःखं, इच्छा, द्वेषः इत्यादीनां प्रत्यक्षकरणम्, अनुभवकरणम्, उपलब्धिकरणं वा इन्द्रियं भवति मनः इति। सर्वस्य अपि आत्मनः एकैकं मनः अस्ति, इत्यतः मनः असंख्यं, नित्यं, परमाणुपरिमाणविशिष्टञ्चेति।

मुख्यशब्दाः – मनः, नैयायिकः, इन्द्रियम्, सुख-दुःखम्, गौतमः, किरणावली।

मनः नाम सर्वेषाम् इन्द्रियाणां प्रेरकम्। तच्च मनः राजसाहंकारसहकृतात् सात्त्विकाहंकाराद् उत्पद्यते इति सांख्याः पातञ्जलाश्च। पञ्चमहाभूतानां सर्वेषां सात्त्विकांशात् मनसः उत्पत्तिरिति अद्वैतवादिनां मतम्। नैयायिकानां वैशेषिकानां च मते मनः न भौतिकम्, अपि तु स्वतन्त्रं द्रव्यम्। तच्च मनः यद्यपि जडं तथापि आत्मसंस्पर्शनं चेतनवत् प्रतिभाति। सर्वेषां ज्ञानानां साधारणकारणं मनः, प्रत्यक्षानुमित्युपमितिशाब्देषु मनसः उपयोगित्वात्। बाह्यप्रत्यक्षे आत्मा यदा मनसा संयुज्यते, मनः इन्द्रियेन इन्द्रियं चार्थेन तदा बाह्यप्रत्यक्षं भवति। आन्तरप्रत्यक्षेऽपि आत्मसंयुक्तं मनः यदा आन्तरसुखदुःखादिभिः संयुज्यते तदैव आन्तरप्रत्यक्षं भवति। आत्मप्रत्यक्षेऽपि मनसः उपयोगित्वं स्वीकृतं नैयायिकैः। मानसप्रत्यक्षेनैव आत्मा ज्ञायते इति तेषाम् अभिप्रायः।

“स्पर्शरहितत्वे सति क्रियावत्त्वं मनसो लक्षणम्।” (तर्कसंग्रहदीपिका, टीका – 18)

पृथिवी-जल-तेजो-वायु-मनःसु क्रिया विद्यते। तत्र स्पर्शगुणः पृथिवी-जल-तेजो-वायुषु अस्ति, मनसि तु नास्ति इति स्पर्शरहितत्वे सति क्रियावत्त्वं मनसो लक्षणं भवितुम् अर्हति। स्पर्शरहितत्वम् आत्मन्यपि अस्तीति तत्र अतिव्याप्तिवारणाय क्रियावत्त्वम् इति। आत्मनि तु क्रिया नास्तीति न तत्रातिव्याप्तिप्रसङ्गः। इन्द्रियाणाम् अपि क्रियावत्वात् तत्रातिव्याप्तिवारणाय स्पर्शरहितत्वे सतीति। इन्द्रियाणाम् अतीन्द्रियत्वात् तेषां स्पर्शरहितत्वं सिद्धमेवेति न तत्रातिव्याप्तिः।

1 सहायकाचार्यः, यतीन्द्र-राजेन्द्र-महाविद्यालयः, आमतला

संख्या, परिमाणं, पृथक्त्वं, संयोगः, विभागः, परत्वम्, दैशिकापरत्वं, वेगाख्यसंस्कारश्चेति अष्टौ गुणाः मनसि वर्तन्ते। तदुक्तं कारिकावल्याम् –

“परापरत्वे संख्याद्याः पञ्च वेगश्च मानसे।” (न्यायसिद्धान्तमुक्तावली)

वाह्येन्द्रियवत् मनोऽपि अतीन्द्रियम् इति यद्यपि तस्य अस्तित्वं प्रत्यक्षेण न सिध्यति, तथापि अनुमानेन तस्य सिद्धिः भवति। तथाहि, सुखदुःखादिप्रत्यक्षज्ञानं करणजन्यं जन्यप्रत्यक्षज्ञानत्वात्, चाक्षुषप्रत्यक्षज्ञानवद् इत्यनुमानेन सुखदुःखादिज्ञानानां करणत्वेन मनः सिध्यति। आत्मनिष्ठाः सुखदुःखेच्छाद्वेषप्रयत्नरूपा गुणाः प्रत्यक्षसिद्धाः। प्रत्यक्षे च इन्द्रियम् अपेक्षितम्, इन्द्रियं विना प्रत्यक्षज्ञानानुत्पत्तेः। अतः आत्मनिष्ठगुणानां प्रत्यक्षार्थं किमपि इन्द्रियं स्वीकरणीयम्। तत्र दर्शनश्रवणादीनि पञ्चवाह्येन्द्रियाणि वाह्यविषयान् एव ग्रहीतुं समर्थानि न तु आन्तरविषयान् इति सुखदुःखादि आन्तरविषयग्रहणार्थं चक्षुरादिभ्यः भिन्नम् आन्तरम् इन्द्रियमेकं स्वीकरणीयम्। तदेव मनः। तदुक्तम् अन्नं भट्टपादेन –

“सुखदुःखाद्युपलब्धिसादनमिन्द्रियं मनः” (तर्कसंग्रहः, सूत्रम् – 18)

उपलब्धिर्नाम साक्षात्कारः। तथा च सुखादिसाक्षात्कारकरणत्वे सति इन्द्रियत्वं मनसो लक्षणम्। चक्षुरादिवाह्येन्द्रियेषु अतिव्याप्तिवारणाय सुखदुःखादि-उपलब्धिसाधनमिति। चक्षुरादीनि इन्द्रियाणि सुखदुःखानि अन्तरविषयग्रहणे असमर्थानि इति न तत्र तत्र अतिव्याप्तिः। आत्मनो ज्ञानादिकं प्रति समवायिकारणत्वात् तत्र अतिव्याप्तिवारणाय उक्तम् इन्द्रियेति। तथा च आत्मनः इन्द्रियत्वाभावात् न तत्र अतिव्याप्तिः। “साक्षात्कारै सुखादीनां करणं मन उच्यते” इति चोक्तं कारिकावल्याम्।

न केवलं सुखादीनां करणत्वेन मनसः सिद्धिः, तेषां कारणत्वेनापि तत् सिध्यति। तथाहि तेषां गुणानां समवायिकारणम् आत्मा, आत्ममनः संयोगः तत्र असमवायिकारणम्। मनसः अस्तित्वे स्वीकृते एव आत्ममनः संयोगरूपम् असमवायिकारणं सिध्यति। अतः आत्ममनः संयोगरूपस्य असमवायिकारणस्य आश्रयत्वेन मनः स्वीकार्यम्।

सर्वेषां वाह्यप्रत्यक्षज्ञानानां सिद्धार्थं च मनः स्वीकार्यम्। इन्द्रियेण सह मनसः संयोगाभावे न किमपि वाह्यम् इन्द्रियं स्वग्राह्यविषयग्रहणे समर्थं भवतीति सर्वेषु अपि वाह्यप्रत्यक्षेषु मनः अपेक्ष्यते। आत्मा मनसः संयुज्यते। मनः इन्द्रियेन, इन्द्रियम् अर्थेन, तद् अनन्तरम् एव प्रत्यक्षज्ञानं जायते इति वाह्यप्रत्यक्षसिद्धार्थं मनः स्वीकार्यम्। ननु आत्मना सह इन्द्रियाणां संयोगेनैव प्रत्यक्षज्ञानं भवतु, किं मनः संयोगेन इति चेत्। न, इन्द्रियैः सह आत्मनः साक्षात् संयोगस्य प्रत्यक्षं प्रति कारणत्वे सर्वेषाम् इन्द्रियाणां स्व-स्व-विषयैः सह युगपत्संयोगे सति सर्वैः इन्द्रियैः युगपत् ज्ञानोत्पादनप्रसङ्गात्। न च आत्मनि युगपत् अनेकज्ञानोत्पत्ति सम्भवति इति वाच्यम्, तथा सति युगपत् एव तत्तत् ज्ञानाभिव्यञ्जकवाक्यानां प्रयोगः प्रसज्यते। न तु एतत् सम्भवति। अतः ज्ञानाभिव्यञ्जकवाक्यानां पारम्पर्यात् ज्ञानानामपि पारम्पर्यं स्वीकरणीयम्।

प्रत्यात्मनियतत्वात् मनसः आनन्त्यम्। एकैकस्य आत्मनः एकैकं मनः। आत्मनः च

प्रतिशरीरं भिन्नत्वेन अनन्तत्वात् तन्निष्ठं मनोऽपि अनन्तम् । उक्तं च शिवादित्यैः – मनस्तु प्रत्यात्मनिष्ठत्वादनन्तम् इति । वस्तुतस्तु प्रतिदेहनियतं मनः, न तु प्रत्यात्मनियतम् । कायव्युहस्थले एकस्य योगिनो देहसंख्यानुसारं मनसो बहुत्वसिद्धेः । भिन्नेषु जीवदेहेषु भिन्नानि मनांसि । मनस एकत्वे भिन्नानां पुरुषाणां युगपत् ज्ञानं न उत्पद्येत मनसः अणुत्वात् । एकस्मिन् जीवदेहे अनेकमनः स्वीकारे च एकदेव अनेकैः इन्द्रियैः सह अनेकमनः संयोगसम्भवात् एकस्य पुरुषस्य युगपत् अनेकज्ञानोत्पत्तिप्रसङ्गः । एकस्मिन् पुरुषे ज्ञानयौगपद्यं तु न सम्भवति इति नैयायिकानां सिद्धान्तः । अतः प्रतिदेहम् एकम् एव मनः इति स्वीकार्यम् । तदुक्तं गौतमपादैः –

“ज्ञानोयौगपद्याद् एकं मनः ।” (न्यायसूत्रम्)

मनः अणुपरिमाणम्, अन्यथा इन्द्रियपञ्चकेन सह मनसः युगपत् संयोगेन ज्ञानयौगपद्यं प्रसज्यते । ज्ञानयौगपद्यं तु न सम्भवतीति नैयायिकसिद्धान्तः । मनसः अणुत्वे तु यदा मनो येन इन्द्रियेण संयुज्यते, तदा तद् इन्द्रियजन्यं ज्ञानम् उत्पद्यते इति उपपद्यते । अतः ज्ञानस्य अयौगपद्यम् एव मनसः अणुत्वे मानम् । तदुक्तम् –

“अयौगपद्याद् ज्ञानानां तस्याणुत्वमिहेष्यते ।” (भाषापरिच्छेदः, कारिका – 85)

मनसो मध्यमपरिमाणत्वे, यत् मध्यमपरिमाणं, तद् विनाशि इति व्याप्तेः मनसः अनित्यत्वं प्रसज्येत । अपि च मनसः मध्यमपरिमाणत्वे युगपत् सर्वैः इन्द्रियैः सह तस्य संयोगसम्भवात् युगपत् सर्वेन्द्रियजन्यज्ञानोत्पत्तिप्रसङ्गः । तस्य विभुत्वेऽपि तथैव सर्वैः इन्द्रियैः सह तस्य युगपत्संयोगसम्भवेन युगपत् सर्वेन्द्रियेभ्यः ज्ञानोत्पत्तिप्रसङ्ग इति तस्य विभुत्वमपि न स्वीकार्यम् । ननु मनः विभु, स्पर्शरहितत्वाद् आकाशादिवद् इत्यनुमानेन मनसः विभुत्वम् एव स्वीकरणीयम् । मनसः अणुत्वे तु यदा मनः पुरीतति नाड्यां प्रविशति तदा सुषुप्तिः, यदा निःसरति तदा ज्ञानोत्पत्तिरिति नानुपपत्तिः । अतो युगपज्ज्ञानानुत्पत्तिलक्ष् षणधर्मिग्राहकमानेन मनसोऽणुत्वसिद्धिः । तदुक्तं गौतमाचार्यैः –

“युगपज्ज्ञानानुत्पत्तिर्मनसो लिङ्गम् ।” (न्यायसूत्रम् – 16)

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रघुवंशकाव्यस्य वल्लभदेवकृता रघुपञ्चिका तथा च मल्लीनाथकृता सञ्जीविनी इति टीकाद्वयस्य द्वितीयं सर्गमधिकृत्य तुलनात्मकमध्ययनम् ।

राधिका देशपाण्डे¹

कालिदासविरचिते रघुवंशाख्ये महाकाव्ये त्रयस्त्रिंशत् संस्कृतटीकाः प्राप्यन्ते (Nandargikar, पृ. 26fn) । हस्तलिखितरूपेण पुस्तकरूपेण च ताः उपलब्धाः । तासु वल्लभदेवविरचिता रघुपञ्चिका प्राचीनतमा मल्लीनाथस्य च अर्वाचीना इति अभ्यासकानां मतम् (Nandargikar, पृ. 9) । तयोः प्राचीनार्वाचीनत्वात् इमे टीके अध्येतव्ये इति हेतुना लिखितोऽयं शोधनिबन्धः ।

1. द्वयोः टीकाकारयोः कालः, स्थानम् च । -

वल्लभदेवः ख्रिस्ताब्दस्य नवमशतकस्य उत्तरार्धे वा दशमशतकस्य पूर्वार्धे अभवत् इति तज्ज्ञाः वदन्ति । सः इमां रघुपञ्चिकां प्रायः दशमशतकस्य पूर्वार्धे लिलेख इति केचित् प्रतिपादयन्ति (Nandargikar, पृ. xvi) । सः कश्मीरराज्ये नाम भारतस्य उत्तरस्यां दिशि निवसति स्म (Nandargikar, पृ. 10) ।

मल्लीनाथः ख्रिस्ताब्दस्य चतुर्दशशतकस्य उत्तरार्धे अभवत् (Nandargikar, पृ. 6) । सः भारतस्य दक्षिणे प्रान्ते तेलङ्गणाराज्यस्य कोलचलाख्ये प्रदेशे निवसति स्म । कोलाचल इत्येव तस्य उपनाम अपि आसीदिति विदुषां मतम् (Lalye, पृ. 13) ।

2. बाह्यं परिशीलनम्

२.१ टीकाभिधाने

वल्लभदेवः तस्य टीकां पञ्चिका अथवा पञ्चिका इति नाम अददात् । राजशेखरस्य काव्यमीमांसाग्रन्थे पञ्चिकायाः लक्षणम् उक्तम्- विषमपदभञ्जिका पञ्चिका इति ।

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नाम विषमान् दुरुहान्पदान् भनक्ति इति । पच्यन्ते व्यक्तीक्रियन्ते अर्थाः अनया इति । राजशेखरस्य काव्यमीमांसाग्रन्थकालोपि ख्रिस्ताब्दस्य नवमशतकस्य उत्तरार्धः, दशमशतकस्य पूर्वार्धः इत्येव निश्चितः । तदनुसारेण तस्य परीक्षा करणीया । तथापि वल्लभेन इदं नाम तट्टीकां न केनापि हेतुना दत्तम् इति केषाञ्चित् अभ्यासकानां मतम् ।

मल्लीनाथस्तु आरम्भश्लोकेषु एव उक्तवान् –
भारती कालिदासस्य दुर्व्याख्याविषमूर्च्छिता ।
एषा संजीविनी टीका तामद्योज्जीवयिष्यति ॥

स्वयं मल्लिनाथ एव अत्र 'टीका' इति अवदत् । काव्यमीमांसायां टीकायाः लक्षणम् उक्तं- 'यथासंभवमर्थस्य टीकनं टीका ।' टीकेर्गत्यर्थत्वात् टीकनं बोधनम् इति । संजीविनी इति किम्, इत्यस्यापि उत्तरं अत्रैव तेन दत्तम् । किमर्थमेवमुक्तम् इति ज्ञातुं संजीविन्याः पूर्ववर्तिन्यः टीकाः द्रष्टव्याः । ताः दृष्ट्वा नन्दर्गिकरमहोदयः (पृ. 6-9) एवम् प्रतिपादयति- 'अस्मात् श्लोकात् एवं निगमितुं शक्यते यत् मल्लिनाथः सर्वाः टीकाः जानाति स्म । सः स्वयम् द्वौ टीकाकारौ उल्लेखयति- दक्षिणावर्तः नाथः च । तस्य टीकायां, अस्मिन् श्लोके च एतत् स्फुटीभवति यत् ताः सर्वाः उपलब्धाः टीकाः मल्लिनाथः पपाठ । संजीविनी सर्वाभ्यः टीकाभ्यः नवतरा अतः प्राचीनटीकानां सम्यक् परिशीलनं कृत्वा एव, तासु विद्यमानं न्यूनं दूरीकृत्य तेन इयं लिखिता इति स्यात् । इति ।'

२.२ टीकयोः आरम्भौ, रचने च -

पञ्जिकायाः आरम्भः साक्षात् 'वागर्थाविव संपृक्तौ' इत्यनेन एव श्लोकेन भवति । वल्लभेन अत्र स्वयमपि मङ्गलं न कृतम् । सर्गप्रारम्भेऽपि न मङ्गलश्लोकः । अपि तु गतसर्गस्य विषयस्य अक्षुण्णतां निर्दिश्य टीकां करोति । टीकारम्भे श्लोकस्य प्रतीकं न विद्यते । पुष्पिकायां सर्गनाम, टीकानाम, टीकाकारस्य अभिधानं न वर्तते ।

मल्लीनाथस्य टीका पञ्जिकायाः एतेषु स्थानेषु सर्वथा भिद्यते । संजीविन्याः आरम्भः नमस्कारात्मकेन श्लोकेन भवति । यथा

मातापितृभ्यां जगतो नमो वामार्धजानये ।
सद्यो दक्षिणदृक्पातसंकुचद्वामदृष्टये ॥

प्रत्येकं सर्गारम्भे एकः मङ्गलश्लोकः वर्तते । यथा द्वितीयसर्गे-

आशासु राशीभवदङ्गवल्लीभासैव दासीकृतदुग्धसिन्धुम् ।
मन्दस्मितैर्निन्दितशारदेन्दुं वन्देऽरविन्दासनसुन्दरि! त्वाम् ॥

श्लोकादनन्तरं अथ प्रजानामित्यादिकं आरब्धम् । पूर्वतनसर्गविषयम् उद्दिश्य, द्वयोः सर्गयोः संबन्धं दर्शयन् वाक्यम् अत्र नास्ति । टीकारम्भे प्रतीकं विद्यते । पुष्पिकायाः महद्बोधो भवति-

1. मल्लिनाथस्य उपाधिः - 'महामहोपाध्यायः'

2. प्रान्तः – कोलाचलाख्यः ।
3. टीकायाः अभिधानं – संजीविनी ।
4. सर्गस्य नामः, क्रमाङ्कः- नन्दिनीवरप्रदानम्, द्वितीयः सर्गः ।

२.३ स्वीकृतौ पाठौ

अत्र स्वीकृतपाठेषु भिन्नत्वं दृश्यते चेत् ते ते पाठाः केवलमुद्धृताः ।

श्लोकस्य अनुक्रमाङ्कः	पञ्जिका	संजीविनी
५	अव्याहृतस्वैरगतैः	अव्याहतैः स्वैरगतैः
८	रक्षापदेशाद्गुरुहोमधेनुः	रक्षापदेशान्मुनिहोमधेनुः
१३	पृक्तस्तुषारैर्वननिर्झराणाम् अनोकहाकम्पनपुष्पगन्धी	पृक्तस्तुषारैर्गिरिनिर्झराणाम् अनोकहाकम्पितपुष्पगन्धी
१४	आसीद्विशेषात्फलपुष्पवृद्धिः	आसीद्विशेषा फलपुष्पवृद्धिः
२१	शृङ्गान्तरं द्वारमिवात्सिद्धेः	शृङ्गान्तरं द्वारमिवात्मसिद्धेः
२५	दिनान्यमिलोद्गरणोचितस्य	दिनानि दीनोद्गरणोचितस्य
२८	नगेन्द्रदत्तां	नगेन्द्रसक्तां
२९	रोध्रद्रुमं सानुमतः प्रफुल्लम्	लोध्रद्रुमं सानुमतः प्रफुल्लम्
३१	नखप्रभारुषितकङ्कपत्ने	नखप्रभाभूषितकङ्कपत्ने
३२	बाहुप्रतिस्तम्भविवृद्धमन्युः	बाहुप्रतिष्ठम्भविवृद्धमन्युः
३३	विस्मापयन्विस्मितमात्मसिद्धौ भूपालसिंहं	विस्मापयन्विस्मितमात्मवृत्तौ (मल्लीनाथेन अन्योऽपि पाठः उक्तः टीकायाम्) सिंहोरुसत्त्वं
३८	तदाप्रभृत्येव मतङ्गजानाम्	तदाप्रभृत्येव वनद्विपानाम्
४२	तत्पूर्वसङ्गे वितथप्रयत्नः	तत्पूर्वसङ्गे वितथप्रयत्नः
४६	अथान्धकारं गिरिकन्दराणाम्	अथान्धकारं गिरिगह्वराणाम्
४७	विचारमुग्धः प्रतिभासि मे त्वम्	विचारमूढः प्रतिभासि मे त्वम्
५२	तथा समर्था गिरिमूचिवांसं प्रत्याह देवानुचरं दिलीपः	निशाम्य देवानुचरस्य वाचं मनुष्यदेवः पुनरप्युवाच
५५	न्याय्यं	न्याय्या
५६	स्थातुं नियोक्तुर्यदि शक्यमग्रे	स्थातुं नियोक्तुर्न हि शक्यमग्रे

५९	सद्यप्रतिस्तम्भविमुक्तबाहुः स न्यस्तशस्त्रं हरये स्वदेहम् धेन्वा तदध्यासनकातराक्ष्या	सद्यप्रतिष्टम्भविमुक्तबाहुः सन्न्यस्तशस्त्रो हरये स्वदेहम् धेन्वा तदध्यासितकातराक्ष्या
७१	संमङ्गलोदग्रतरानुभावः	संमङ्गलोदग्रतरप्रभावः

३. टीकापद्धती

अत्र द्वयोरपि टीकयोः पद्धती उदाहरणानि दत्त्वा निरीक्ष्यते । -

३.२.१ रघुपञ्जिका-

राज्ञी यथोक्तव्रतसाधनमाह -

अथ प्रजानामधिपः प्रभाते जायाप्रतिग्राहितगन्धमाल्याम् ।

वनाय पीतप्रतिबद्धवत्सां यशोधनो धेनुमृषेर्मुमोच ॥ २.१॥

अनन्तरं राजा ऋषेर्गा काननायामुञ्चत् वनं नेतुं विपाशितवान् । क्रियार्थोपपदस्य इत्यादिना चतुर्थी । जायया कर्त्या स्वीकारितं गन्धमाल्यं यया धेन्वा ताम् । जाययादापितं गन्धमाल्यं यस्या इति वा । धेनुरानुकूल्यात् शुभशंसित्वात् चानुलेपनपुष्पे गृह्णाति । राज्ञी प्रतिचोदिता ग्राहयति इति णिच् । पीतं पानं यस्यास्ति स पीतः । अर्शादित्वादकारः । पूर्वं पीतवान् पश्चात् प्रतिबद्धो वत्सो यस्याः । यशोधन इत्यनेन अनुचितमपि गोपलकर्म शापशान्तये न दोषाय इति सूचितम् । सर्गोपजाति वृत्तम् ।

तथा समर्था गिरमूचिवासं प्रत्याह देवानुचरं दिलीपः ।

धेन्वातदध्यासनकातराक्ष्या निरीक्ष्यमाणः सुतरां दयालुः ॥ २.५२॥

राजा हरकिङ्करं सिंहं प्रतीपमुवाच । पूर्वोक्तेन प्रकारेण संबद्धां वाचमुक्तवन्तं । सिंहाक्रमेण चञ्चले नेत्रे यस्यास्तया गवा दृश्यमानः । सुष्ठु कृपावान् ।

३.२.२. संजीविनी-

अथ प्रजानामधिपः प्रभाते जायाप्रतिग्राहितगन्धमाल्याम् ।

वनाय पीतप्रतिबद्धवत्सां यशोधनो धेनुमृषेर्मुमोच ॥ २.१॥

अथेति । अथ निशानयनानन्तरं यशोधनः प्रजानामधिपः प्रजेश्वरः प्रभाते प्रातःकाले जायया सुदक्षिणया प्रतिग्राहयित्वा । प्रतिग्राहिते स्वीकारिते गन्धमाल्ये यया सा जायाप्रतिग्राहितगन्धमाल्या । तां तथोक्तां । पीतं पानमस्यास्तीति पीतः । पीतवानित्यर्थः । अर्शादिभ्योऽच् इत्यच् प्रत्ययः । 'पीता गावो भुक्ता ब्राह्मणाः' इति महाभाष्ये दर्शनात् । पीतः प्रतिबद्धो वत्सो यस्यास्ताम् ऋषेर्धेनुं वनाय वनं गन्तुम् । 'कृत्यार्थोपपद' - इत्यादिना चतुर्थी । मुमोच मुक्तवान् । 'जाया'पदसामर्थ्यात् सुदक्षिणयाः पुलजननयोग्यत्वमनुसन्धेयम् । तथा हि श्रुतिः- 'पतिर्जायां प्रविशति गर्भो भूत्वेह मातरम् । तस्यां पुनर्नवो भूत्वा दशमे मासि जायते । तज्जाया जाया भवति यदस्यां जायते पुनः ।' इति 'यशोधन' इत्यनेन

पुत्रवत्ताकीर्तिलोभाद्राजानर्हे गोरक्षणे प्रवृत्त इति गम्यते । अस्मिन्सर्गे वृत्तमुपजातिः – अनन्तरोदीरितलक्ष्मभाजौ पादौ यदियानुपजातयस्ताः ।’

निशम्य देवानुचरस्य वाचं मनुष्यदेवः पुनरप्युवाच ।

धेन्वा तदध्यासितकातराक्ष्या निरीक्ष्यमाणः सुतरां दयालुः ॥ २.५२ ॥

निशम्येति । देवानुचरस्येश्वरकिङ्करस्य सिंहस्य वाचं निशम्य, मनुष्यदेवो राजा पुनरप्युवाच । किंभूतः सन्? तेन सिंहेन यदध्यासितं व्याक्रमणम् । नपुंसके भावे क्तः । तेन कातरे अक्षिणी यस्यास्तया । ‘बहुव्रीहौ सक्थ्यक्ष्णोः स्वाङ्गात् षच् इति षच् । षिद्वौरादिभ्यश्च इति डीष् । ‘किंवा वक्ष्यति’ इति भीत्वैवं स्थितयेत्यर्थः । धेन्वा निरीक्ष्यमाणः । अत एव सुतरां दयालुः सन् । ‘सुतरां इत्यल द्विवचनविभज्य’ - इत्यादिना सुशब्दात्तरप् । ‘किमेत्तिड्व्यय’ - इत्यादिनाम्प्रत्ययः । ‘तद्वितश्वासर्वविभक्तिः’ इत्यव्ययसंज्ञा ।

४. निरीक्षणानि

इमानि निरीक्षणानि उपरि विद्यमानाभ्यां द्वाभ्यां श्लोकाभ्यां तथा च अन्येभ्योऽपि सर्वेभ्यो द्वितीयसर्गस्य श्लोकेभ्यः समीक्ष्य दत्तानि ।

पञ्जिका	संजीविनी
टीकारम्भे श्लोकस्य प्रतीकं न विद्यते	टीकारम्भे श्लोकस्य प्रतीकं न विद्यते
श्लोकस्थाः शब्दाः पुनः टीकायां न दत्ताः । यथा प्रथमे श्लोके ‘अथ’ इत्यस्य अर्थः ‘अनन्तरम्’ इति अस्ति तथापि तं शब्दं अनुक्तवैव अर्थः लिखितः	श्लोकस्थाः शब्दाः पुनरपि अनूद्य तदनन्तरं तस्य पर्यायी शब्दः दत्तः । यथा- ‘अथ अनन्तरम्’
व्याकरणम् च उक्तं परं न सर्वत्र दृश्यते । क्वचित् उक्तं क्वचित् नोक्तम् ।	सर्वेषु स्थानेषु यथाशक्यं व्याकरणम् उक्तम् ।
प्रथमश्लोके टीकान्ते सर्गस्य वृत्तं उक्तम् ।	प्रथमश्लोके टीकान्ते सर्गस्य वृत्तं उक्तम् ।
बहूनि शास्त्रवचनानि न लभ्यन्ते । एकस्मिन्नेव स्थाने (२.७- अन्तर्मदावस्थ इव द्विपेन्द्रः) अन्तर्मदावस्थ इति शब्दं स्पष्टीकुर्वन् एकः श्लोकः प्राप्यते । – भद्रो मन्द्रो मृगश्चाथ सङ्कीर्णश्चेति जातयः । चतस्रः करिणां तत्र भद्रोन्तर्मद एव यः ॥ तथापि श्लोकस्यास्य मूलस्रोतः तु नोक्तः ।	बहूनि श्रुति-स्मृति-शास्त्रोक्तानि प्रमाणानि स्थाने स्थाने दरीदृश्यन्ते । तत्र तस्य पङ्क्तेः मूलस्रोतः कः, इत्यपि उक्तम् यथा- तथा हि श्रुतिः (२.१), इत्यमरः (२.१), इति विश्वः (२.९) इत्यादिः ।

<p>सर्गारम्भे गतसर्गम् उद्दिश्य एकं वाक्यं दत्तं यत् तं अग्रिमं सर्गं प्रति बध्नाति । यथा- राज्ञो यथोक्तव्रतसाधनमाह इति । परं संज्ञीविनी इव प्रत्येकं श्लोकात्पूर्वं यथावश्यकं तथा श्लोकस्य पार्श्वभूमिः न कथिता ।</p>	<p>सर्गारम्भे द्वयोः सर्गयोः मध्ये संबन्धं दर्शयन् वाक्यं नास्ति । यत्न यत्न आवश्यकं तत्र तत्र श्लोकात्पूर्वं श्लोकस्य पार्श्वभूमिः कथिता । यथा- 'विसृष्ट इत्यादिभिः षड्भिः श्लोकैः तस्य महामहिमतया द्रुमाद्रयोऽपि राजोपचारं चक्रुरित्याह ।(२.९)'</p>
<p>टीका अन्वयमुखेन न उक्ता । प्रथमं श्लोकस्य मुख्यं वाक्यं अन्यैः समानार्थकैः शब्दैः कथयित्वा अनन्तरम् अवशिष्टानि पदानि, मुख्यवाक्ये नाम्नां कृते उपयोजितानि विशेषणानि, विशदीकृतानि ।</p>	<p>मल्लिनाथः तु प्रथममेव उक्तवान् – 'इहान्वयमुखेनैव सर्वं व्याख्यायते मया ।' इति तदनुसृत्य अयं अन्वयमुखेन एव टीकां लिलेख ।</p>

५ .निष्कर्षः

1. पञ्जिकायां प्रारम्भे कोऽपि मङ्गलश्लोकः, परिचयात्मकं किमपि नास्ति येन टीकायाः पद्धतिः इत्यादिकम् ऊहितुं शक्यात् । मल्लिनाथेन सञ्जीविन्यां स्वस्य नाम, टीकायाः नाम, मूलग्रन्थस्य नाम, तस्य लेखकः, टीकापद्धतिः, टीकायाः प्रयोजनं सर्वं स्पष्टं कृतम् । इदमेव प्रमाणीभूतं पद्धतिशास्त्रम् सर्वैः अनुरणीयं च । अद्यापि किमपि शोधनिबन्धो वा पुस्तकं वा एवमेव लिखन्ति चेत् पाठकानां सौकर्यं भवेत् ।
2. पञ्जिकायां श्लोकार्थः ईषत् स्फुटो भवति । अतः इयं काव्यमीमांसोक्ता पञ्जिका एव, या केवलं अनवगम्यमानान् पदान् निर्वदति, इति वचनं नायोग्यम् । सञ्जीविनी तु सर्वशास्त्राणां प्रमाणानि दत्त्वा ऊहापोहपूर्वकं श्लोकं बोधयति । येन काव्यमीमांसायां उक्ता टीकायाः व्याख्या सञ्जीविन्याः विषये सार्थकतां भजति ।
3. पञ्जिका केवलं अर्थस्य अनवबोधे आधारभूता भवेत्, न तु विद्यार्थिणांकृते अध्ययने । यतः अन्ये श्लोकाः अन्यासु टीकासु ज्ञातुं शक्याः परं, यः पाठः दुर्लभः यथा
4. तथा समर्था गिरमूचिवांसं प्रत्याह देवानुचरं दिलीपः ।
5. धेन्वातदध्यासनकातराक्ष्या निरीक्ष्यमाणः सुतरां दयालुः ॥ २.५२ ॥
6. इत्यत्र श्लोकार्थः सामान्यतया ज्ञायते किन्तु पदशः ग्रहणं न भवति । संजीविनी विशदतमा । प्रत्येकं पदस्य भेदपूर्वकं सप्रमाणं विमर्शः करोति । क्वचित् शिष्यान् शिक्षयन् इव 'किमर्थम्?' 'कीदृशम्?' 'किंभूतः सन्?' एवं प्रश्नान् उपस्थाप्य निरूपयति ।
7. उभाभ्यामपि टीकाकाराभ्यां स्वीकृतौ पाठौ न अर्थदृष्ट्या भिन्नौ । केवलं शब्दाः, व्याकरण-रचनाः भिन्नाः । एकस्मिन्नेव श्लोके संपूर्णा पङ्क्तिः भिन्ना (२.५२) ।

विंशतिश्लोकेषु पाठभेदाः दृश्यन्ते ।

8. पञ्जिकाकारः वल्लभः उत्तरस्यां दिशि अभवत् । अतः तत्र यः पाठः प्रचलितः तस्य स्वीकारः तेन कृतः इति ऊहितुम् शक्यते । एवमेव मल्लीनाथेनापि प्रायेण दक्षिणे प्रान्ते विद्यमानः पाठः स्वीकृतः इति वक्तुं शक्यते परं सः अन्यटीकाभिः सह तेन तेन टीकाकारेण उद्धृतम् संस्करणमपि जानाति स्म इति विदुषां मतम् । तथा च एकस्मिन् स्थाने मल्लीनाथेन अन्यस्य पाठस्य उल्लेखः कृतः – विस्माययन (२.३३) इत्यत्र । अतः सः अन्ये पाठाः अपि जानाति स्म इति स्फुटीभवति ।
9. एवरूपेण प्राचीनतमा पञ्जिका संजीविन्याः भिद्यते । स्वयं मल्लीनाथः यथा प्रतिपादयति यत् दुर्व्याख्यामूर्च्छिता कालिदासस्य वाणी अनया संजीविन्या पुनरपि उज्जीविता इदं वाक्यं किमर्थमुक्तमिति अत्र भूयोऽपि परीक्षितुं अन्यासां टीकानामपि समीक्षणम् आवश्यकम् । तथापि यद् नन्दर्गिकरमहोदयः अवदत्, तदनुसारं यदि मल्लीनाथेन इयं टीका, अयं पाठः अन्ये टीकाः परीक्ष्य, अधीत्य लिखिता स्यात्, तर्हि सा रघुवंशस्य प्रथमा चिकित्सकावृत्तिः भवितुमर्हति वा, इति चिन्तनीयम् ।

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लिङ्गायतदर्शनम् - प्रमुखाः आचार्याः तेषां योगदानम् च

आतिरा पी.एच्¹

कर्णाटकराज्यस्य विशिष्टं दर्शनं भवति लिङ्गायतदर्शनम् अथवा वीरशैवदर्शनम् । अस्य स्थापकः बसवण्णाचार्यः । अस्य कालः क्रिस्तोः द्वादशशतके अभूत् । वीरशैवदर्शनं कर्णाटकस्य सामाजिक - सांस्कृतिकमूल्यानां निकषभूतमस्ति । अत्र भक्तिः मुख्यं स्थानमावहति । वीरशैवाः भगवतः शिवस्य वीराः भक्ताः । लिङ्गधारणं करोति इत्यतः ते लिङ्गायतः इत्यपि कथ्यन्ते । लिङ्गायतदर्शने सर्वेषां निर्बाधं प्रवेशः आसीत् ।

प्रबन्धस्य उपोद्घाते प्रथमं द्वादशशतके कर्णाटकस्य ऐतिहासिकसन्दर्भे मुख्याः दार्शनिकाशयाः प्रतिपाद्यन्ते । बसवण्णाचार्यस्य जीवनम् उपदेशाः च वर्णिताः । अनन्तरं दर्शनस्यास्य तत्त्वानि संक्षिप्य तस्य कालिकप्रसक्तिं चापि उक्त्वा प्रबन्धः समाप्यते ।

उपोद्घातः ।

आध्यात्मिकमार्गे प्रवेशः अतीव जटिलः कठिनः च । तथापि विविधदुःखाभिभूतसंसाराद् मुक्तये अयमेव केवलः उपायः । तदर्थं भारतस्य विभिन्नप्रान्तेषु भिन्नैराचार्यैः आविष्कृतानि बहूनि दर्शनानि प्रचलितानि सन्ति । एवं दक्षिणभारते कर्णाटकप्रान्ते आविर्भूतं दर्शनं भवति वीरशैवदर्शनम् । इदं दर्शनं सामाजिक-सांस्कृतिकसमभावं निर्दिशति ।

दर्शनेऽस्मिन् उपनयन-दीक्षादीनां स्थाने लिङ्गधारणस्य प्राधान्यमस्ति । अत्र गोल-वर्ण-वयोरूपेण कापि निबन्धना नास्ति । निरुपाधिकतया सर्वसमत्वमेव अस्य वैशिष्ट्यम् ।

वीरशैवदर्शनस्य मुख्यः प्रचारकः बसवण्णाचार्यः । सः न केवलं आत्मीयावबोधाय अपि तु समग्रस्य समाजस्य उन्नतये प्रयतितवान् । सः समाजे विद्यमानानां जातीय - वर्णायभेदानां प्रबलं विरोधं कृतवान् ।

जातिवर्णादीनां नाम्नि ये समाजे कष्टमनुभवन्ति, तस्माद् बहिरागन्तुं च इच्छन्ति, तेभ्यः दर्शनस्यास्य वातायनम् उद्घाटितम् । सामाजिकपुनर्जागरणमपि अनेन सम्पादितम् ।

द्वादशशतके कर्णाटकस्य ऐतिहासिकः दार्शनिकसन्दर्भः ।

1. शोधछात्रा, वेदान्तविभागः, श्रीशङ्कराचार्यसंस्कृतसर्वकलाशाला, कालटी

द्वादशशतकारम्भे कर्णाटकराज्ये जैनसिद्धान्तानां प्रभावः अधिकः आसीत् । तस्य प्रतिद्वन्द्विनः अभूवन् लिङ्गायताः । समाजे ब्राह्मणानाम् आधिपत्यं विरुध्य, शिशुविवाहादीनां निषेधद्वारा बहुविधसामाजिकपरिष्कारेण लिङ्गायतदर्शनं पुष्टिं प्रापत् । तस्मिन् काले सम्पदः विभाजने असमत्वमासीत् । वर्णभेदाधारेण बहवः समस्याः आसन् । लिङ्गायताः शिवशरणाः इति अपि प्रसिद्धाः । द्वादशशतके बसवण्णा, अल्लामा प्रभुः, अक्का महादेवी, सिद्धरामः, दासिमय्या, माच्चिदेवः, गङ्गाम्बिके, चौडय्या चेति बहवः वीरशैवाचार्याः आसन् । ते स्वकीयसिद्धान्त - प्रचारणार्थं कमपि ग्रन्थं वा भाष्यं वा न रचितवन्तः । गच्छता कालेन अस्य सम्प्रदायस्य अनेके उपविभागाः अपि जाताः येषु केचन समत्वभावनां नाङ्गीकुर्वन्तः आसन् ।

द्वादशशतके कर्णाटकदेशे भक्तिप्रस्थानं समारम्भम् । तत्र बसवण्णाचार्यस्य वचन-काव्यरूपमपि प्रसिद्धिं प्राप । वचनसम्प्रदाये देवतां प्रति भक्तिभावनया सह सामाजिकसमत्वस्यापि च प्रामुख्यं दत्तम् । तेन जातिप्रथा तिरस्कृता वान् । एतेन कर्णाटकस्य धार्मिकसामाजिकतले तस्य गहनः प्रभावः अभवत् । वचनं सविशेषरीत्या , प्राप्तेन च आलापनं कर्तुं शक्यते । इत्यतः सामाजिकस्त सर्वतलेषु वर्तमानाः सर्वेषां जनानां अपि अयं काव्यरूपः प्राप्तुं शक्यते । तावत् ललितः आसीत् । एतत् वचनकाव्यरूपेण कर्णाटकायाः साहित्य मेखला अपि पुष्टिः प्राप्तः । वीरशैवपरम्परायां वचनानां व षड्चरणव्यवस्थानुसारं वर्गीकरणं भवति । एवं महान् वचनकारानाम् आधुनिकसंस्करणाः काव्यानि षट् अध्यायेषु प्रस्तुतयन्ति वर्गीकरणं कदाचित् किञ्चित् मनमाना भवति ।

वीरशैवदर्शनं

“वीरशैवमितिपदस्य अर्थः एवमुच्यते -

विशब्देनोच्यते विद्या शिवजीवैक्यवोधिनी ।

तस्यां रामन्ते ये शिव वीरशैवास्तु ते मताः ॥” (वीरशैवमतसंवर्धिनी, श्लो-2)

इति वीरशैवमतसंवर्धिण्यां द्वितीय श्लोकः । अत्र “ वि “ इत्यस्य विद्या इति अर्थः उच्यते । “ र “ इत्यस्य रामन्ते अथवा क्रीडार्थं इत्यर्थः उच्यते । पुनः “ शैव “ इत्यस्य शिवस्य भक्तः अथवा शिव - जीव - ऐक्य बोधः इत्यपि उच्यते । एवं वीरशैवम् इत्यस्य पदार्थाः विन्यस्यते ।

“गर्भाष्टमो कृता दीक्षा मुख्या सा षोडशावधि ।

गौणी तदूर्ध्वमधवा वीरशैवान्वयवायिनाम् ॥” (वीरशैवमतसंवर्धिनी, श्लो-5)

इति वीरशैवमतसंवर्धिण्यां पञ्चमश्लोके वीरशैवानां प्रमुख तत्त्वं किमिति उच्यते । (अर्थात् , लिंगायताः पवित्रसूत्रेण सह निवेशस्य संस्कारं स्वीकृत्य वैदिकब्राह्मणवादस्य मुख्यसिद्धान्तस्य अनुसरणं कुर्वन्ति, एवं कुर्वन्तः ते गर्भधारणतिथितः ८ वर्षं यावत् उत्तमसमयं १६ वर्षपर्यन्तं अग्रिमः अनुमोदनीयः समयः इति स्वीकुर्वन्ति, १६ तमे वर्षात् परं च यथा दुष्टतमः समयः इत्युच्यते ।)

लिङ्गायताः चतुर्था विभज्यते । ते च, जङ्गमाः, शीलवन्ताः, बञ्जिकाः, पञ्चमशालिनः इति ।

जाति -संस्कार -प्रत्याख्यानम्

ब्राह्मणपृष्ठभूमिं तिरस्कृत्य, मानदण्डान् आव्हानं कृत्वा, समतावादी समावेशी च अधिकप्रतिष्ठितसमाजस्य वकालतम् कृत्वा सः बसवन्नाचार्यः आध्यात्मिकजिज्ञासामार्गेण लिङ्गायतदर्शनस्य उत्पत्तिं कृतवान् । वीरशैवव्यवस्थायां पुनर्विवाहं कदापि कर्तुं न प्रयतेत । तेषां विश्वासानुसारं पतिः वस्तुतः शिवः एव । तस्य मृत्योः अनन्तरं अन्यः विवाहः अपि न चिन्तनीयः इति तेषां नयः । अपि तु शिवस्य पूजां कृत्वा जीवितुं अवधारणा आसीत् । तदर्थं ते केषाञ्चन आचाराः अपि वदन्ति । परन्तु तत् सर्वं सामान्यतया अङ्गीकर्तुं न शक्यते । यतोहि जाति संस्कारेषु स्थिताः आचारानुष्ठानानि सर्वं परित्यज्य एव एतादृशः लिङ्गायतसमुदायस्य उद्भवः जातः एव । तादृशं उपपन्नाः, पुनः किमर्थम् आचारानुष्ठानानां नाम्ना एतावत् अधिकनियमाः स्थापिताः इति आशङ्का उत्पद्यते । अत्र तेषां एताः तत्त्वानां उपरि प्रश्नाः आगच्छन्ति च । अस्य सम्प्रदाये एव वदति सर्वैः समानाः इति । परन्तु अत्र स्त्रीणां विषये एतादृशं अधिकाः आचाराः करोति इति समदृष्ट्याः उपरि संशयः अपि आगच्छति । वीरशैवसम्प्रदाये भर्तुः वियोगानन्तरं स्त्रियः ब्रह्माचार्यव्रतं अतीव कठोररूपेण कुर्यात् । तदर्थं भूमौ शयनं करणीयम् । रात्रौ एव एकं भोजनं गृहीत्वा यथायोग्यं नित्यं स्नानं कुर्यात् । घृतादिकं किमपि, पौष्टिकं वा अपि तु उत्तेजकं भोजनं खादितुम् निवर्तयेत् । इत्यादि आचाराः कर्शनेन करणीयम् । सर्वं शिवपदप्राप्त्यर्थं निश्चयेन करणीयम् इति नियमः अपि अनुवर्तते । परन्तु एतत् सर्वम् स्त्रीणां कृते करोति इति अङ्गीकर्तुं क्लेशः अनुभूयते । एतत् सर्वं अस्य प्रस्थानस्य कालानुसारं व्यतियानाः जातः इति वक्तुं शक्यते । ते पूजादीनां कृते जंगमम् इति नाम्ना नून पौरोहित्यं स्थापितवन्तः ।

बासवन्नाः जीवनं उपदेशं च

ए . डि . ११०५ - ए . डि . ११६७ कालीयः बासवाचार्यस्य पिता अस्ति मदिराजा । सः षोडशवयसि एव तात्त्विकरीत्या चिन्तनं कर्तुम् आरब्धम् । उपनयनकाले एव स्व ब्राह्मणकुलस्य आचारान् त्यक्त्वः शिवलिङ्गधारणं कृत्वा शिवस्य मार्गं चरितवान् । राजा विज्जलस्य राजधान्यां कविः जातः सः अनन्तरं स्वसामर्थ्येन तत्रत्य मन्त्री जातः । एतत् विशदांशाः कस्यचित् जैनकवेः विज्जलराजचरितं इति ग्रन्थे आपि दृश्यते इत्यतः चरित्र प्राधान्यमपि वर्तते । विज्जल - बासव कथा अनेकमस्ति चेदपि ग्रन्थेषु चरित्रप्राधान्यतया अपि दृश्यते इत्यतः अधिकारिकमपि अस्ति ।

यथा सः विज्जलराजस्य मन्त्रिस्थानमलङ्कृतवान् तथा तस्य औद्योगिकपदवीं सम्यक् युक्तिसहजमुपयोगं कृतवान् । कालस्य सामाजिकवातावरणे जाति - मत - वर्ण - लिङ्गव्यवस्थायां तुल्यता नीत्वा आगन्तुं परिश्रमः कृतवान् । परन्तु एतत् नवोत्थानः समूहे

नानाविध प्रक्षोभाः निर्मितम् । लिङ्गायताः तु ब्राह्मणानां विरोधिनाः जाताः । एतत् तु चरित् - सांस्कारिक मण्डलेषु भिन्नता कृतम् । वीरशैवविभागाः अहिंसायाः मार्गाः वाञ्छन्ति । परन्तु प्रतिषेधानां पुरतः तेषां नियन्त्रणाः अपि नष्टं जातम् । कायकसेव कैलास इति आशयेन ते तेषां यात्रा पुनरारब्धं च । सः कायिकाध्वानः एव भक्तेः मार्गः न आचारानुष्ठानाः इति आशयः प्रचरितवान् । बासवन्नाचार्यस्य भक्तेः पाठनानि, सामाजिक तुल्यतायाः परिश्रमाः च लिङ्गायतदर्शनस्य मूलतत्त्वाः इति वर्तन्ते ।

कालिकप्रसक्तिः

आत्मीय - सामूहिक सन्तुलनावस्थायाः उदाहरणमेव लिङ्गायत दर्शनम् । आधुनिक लोकस्य मानसिक - सामाजिक व्यापाराः तेषां जनानां हस्ते न तिष्ठन्ति । एतादृशाः आत्मीय दर्शनेषु अभयं प्राप्यते चेत् समूहे वर्तमानाः असमत्वानां समस्याः किञ्चित् न्यूनं कर्तुं शक्यते । परन्तु अधिकतया आचारानुष्ठानाः आचरित्वा दोषाः अपि न स्वीकरोतु । अयं दर्शनं लिङ्गः धृत्वा एव आरब्धः करोति । लिङ्गधारणं केवलं सामुदायिकं नास्ति, ध्यानस्य उपाधिः अस्ति तत् । मानसिक - शारीरिक औरोग्यस्य मण्डले ध्यानस्य प्राधान्यं मुख्यमेव । सर्वैः लिङ्गायताः हस्ते एकं लिङ्गः स्थाप्य चरति । तत् आराधनायाः एवं ध्यानस्य कृते एव स्थापयति ।

एतादृशं लिङ्गः हस्ते स्थाप्य एव लिङ्गायताः ध्यानं करोति । वयं जानन्ति ध्यानेन अस्माकं वैकारिकमण्डलस्य स्थिरता प्राप्तुं शक्यते , दीर्घ आश्वासः प्राप्यते , सर्गात्मकता वर्धते - तेन राष्ट्रस्य अपि विकासः जायते , एकाग्रता प्राप्यते, सम्यक् निद्रातुं शक्यते चेति । एतत् दर्शनेन अस्मिन् लोके निश्चयेन गुणाः ददाति च । संसारसागरे निमग्नाः मानवानां दुःखस्य निवारणार्थं मोक्षमार्गः पाठनीयमेव । मोक्षस्य मार्गः सर्वदा भक्तेः आरभ्यते च ।

वैदिकवाङ्मये गणितमीमांसा

नीहारिका प्रधान¹ प्रो.का.इ.धरणीधरन्²

वेदः यस्तु सर्वलोकहिताय सदैव अनुग्रहरूपेण विराजते। हिते प्रवर्तनम्, अहितात् निवर्तनमिति हि तस्य प्रधानं लक्ष्यम् । इष्टप्राप्तिसाधनम् अनिष्टनिवृत्तिसाधनं चेत्येतदुभयसाधनबोधकं शास्त्रं वेदशास्त्रं भवति । शासनाद्धि शास्त्रम्, यत् शास्ति तत् शास्त्रं वेति व्युत्पत्तिः । विधानं तु अन्यैरुपायैः अप्राप्तमेव वेदवाङ्मये प्राप्यते । अज्ञातज्ञापनरूपं तत् इति ज्ञायते तदुच्यते –

प्रत्यक्षेणानुमित्या वा यस्तूपायो न बुध्यते ।

एनं विदन्ति वेदेन तस्मात् वेदस्य वेदता ॥ इति कुमारिलभट्टैः ।

“वेदशास्त्रात् परं नास्ति” इति प्रमाणवचनं सर्वशास्त्रस्यापि एतन् मूलत्वं प्रकटयति यतो हि “यस्य निःश्वसितं वेदाः” इति परमात्मनः उच्छ्वासरूपत्वेनास्य वेदस्य स्वरूपं निरूपितमस्ति ।

यो ब्राह्मणं विदधाति पूर्वं यो वै वेदांश्च प्रहिणोति तस्मै ।

तं ह देवमात्मबुद्धिं प्रकाशं मुमुक्षुः वै शरणमहं प्रपद्ये ॥

इति श्वेताश्वतरोपनिषदि परमात्मा चतुर्मुखं ब्राह्मणं सृष्ट्वा तस्मै वेदान् उपदिदेशेति स्पष्टमभिहितम् । एवमन्यत्र श्रूयते

“अनादि निधना ह्येषा वागुत्सृष्टा स्वयम्भुवा” इति ।

यामृषयः मन्त्रकृतो मनीषिणः । अन्वैच्छन् देवास्तपसा श्रमेण । तां देवीं वाचं हविषा यजामहे । सा नो दधातु सुकृतस्य लोके इति देवीं वाचमजनयन्त देवाः तां विश्वरूपाः पशवो वदन्ति इत्येवमादि वैदिकवाङ्मये वैभवं प्रकटयति । अत एव अस्य देववाणी आर्षवाणी, अमृतवाणी इत्यादि व्यवहारो दृश्यते । वेदानां संरक्षणार्थं वेदाङ्गानि प्रवृत्तानि ।

शिक्षा व्याकरणं छन्दःनिरुक्तं ज्योतिषं तथा ।

कल्पश्चेति षडङ्गानि वेदस्याहुः मनीषीणः ॥

इत्युक्तप्रकारेण षट् अङ्गानि । वेदानां संरक्षणं तेषां भवति । स्वरूपतः, अर्थतः,

1 शोधप्रबन्धकर्त्री, पाण्डिचेरी विश्वविद्यालयः

2 मार्गनिर्देशकः

प्रयोगतश्च संरक्षणीयो वेदः । वेदानां स्वरूपरक्षणं नाम आनुपूर्वीरक्षणम् तच्च उच्चारणानूच्चारणपूर्वकं गुरुमुखमूलं यदध्ययनं भवति तद्वारा वैदिकैः मौलिकपरम्पराया क्रियते तदर्थं छन्दोग्रन्थाः, शिक्षाग्रन्थाः, प्रातिशाख्यग्रन्थाश्च सन्ति । अर्थरक्षणागर्थं व्याकरणं निरुक्तं च स्तः । प्रयोगसंरक्षायै कल्पसूत्राणि, ज्योतिषं च वर्तते । सोऽयं विषयः तत्त्वाभेदीय निबन्धे तद्विकायां च श्रीवल्लभाचार्येण सविस्तरं निरूपितः । तदिदं त्रिविधं संरक्षणं पूर्वोक्ताः वैदिकाः, शास्त्रज्ञाः, प्रयोगकुशलाश्च यथाशक्तिं साम्प्रतमपि कुर्वन्ति । अतो जगदिदं तेषाम् अधमर्णं वर्तते । अत एवोक्तं श्रीवेङ्कटाध्वरिवर्यैः

नाध्यापयिष्यन् निगमान् श्रमेण उपाध्यायलोकाः यदि शिष्यवर्गान् ।

निर्वेदवादं किल निर्वितानम् उर्वीतलं हन्त तदाऽभविष्यत् । इति विश्वगुणादर्शे ॥

भोजकविना उच्यते –

उच्चै र्गतिः जगति सिद्धयति धर्मतश्चेत् तस्य प्रमा च वचनैः कृतकेतरैश्चेत् ।

तेषां प्रकाशनदशा च महीसुरैश्चेत् तानन्तरेण निपतेत् क्व नु मत्प्रणामाः ॥

पाणिनीय शिक्षायां षडङ्गानां वेदपुरुषस्य कृते कथमुपकारकत्वं भवतीति सूचितमस्ति-

छन्दः पादौ तु वेदस्य हस्तौ कल्पोऽथ पठ्यते

ज्योतिषामयनं चक्षुः निरुक्तं श्रोत्रमुच्यते ॥

शिक्षा घ्राणं तु वेदस्य मुखं व्याकरणं स्मृतम् ।

तस्मात् साङ्गमधीत्यिव ब्रह्मलोकं महीयते । (पाणिनीय शिक्षा)

ज्योतिषशास्त्रे अन्तर्भूतं भवति गणितम् । ज्योतिषक्षेत्रे ग्रहाणां सञ्चारविषये गणितशास्त्रं महदुपकारकं विद्यते । अंकगणितात् ग्रहगणित पर्यन्तं गणितस्य सर्वाङ्गीणविकासं दर्शितवन्तः पूर्वज्ञाः ग्रन्थकाराः । ज्योतिषविद्यायाः गणितविद्यायाः पार्थक्येन प्रदर्श्य अनयोः वैशिष्ट्यं सूचयति छान्दोग्योपनिषत् अधीहि भगव इति होपससाद सनत्कुमारं नारदस्तं होवाच यद्वेत्थ तेनमोपसीद् ततस्त उर्ध्वं वक्ष्यामीति सहोवाच “ऋगवेदं भगवोऽध्येमि यजुर्वेदं सामवेदम् आथर्वणं च चतुर्थमितिहासपुराणं पञ्चमं वेदानां वेदं पितृयं राशिं देवं निधिं वाकोवाकमेकायनं देवविद्यां ब्रह्मविद्यां भूतविद्यां क्षत्रविद्यां नक्षत्रविद्यां सर्पदेवजनविद्यामेतद् भगवोऽध्येमि ॥ (छान्दोग्योपनिषत् – ६/१/१/२) अत्र राशिविद्या शब्देन गणितशास्त्रं बोध्यते ।

गण्यते संख्यायते तद् गणितं, तत्र प्रतिपादकत्वेन तत्संज्ञं शास्त्रमुच्यते इति व्युत्पत्तिः । गण संख्याने इति धातोः भावे क्त प्रत्यये विहिते संख्यानां शास्त्रं गणितमिति लभ्यते । एवं संख्या इति शब्दस्यापि समान एवार्थः प्राप्यते । ख्या प्रकथने इति धातोः समित्युपसर्ग योजनेन संख्या शब्दः व्युत्पद्यते । “कल संख्याने इति धातोरपि संख्याशब्दः समानार्थकः लभ्यते । तथाच गणितशास्त्रं, संख्याशास्त्रं, कलनशास्त्रमिति पर्यायरूपेण व्यवह्रियते ।

वेदाङ्गेषु षट्स्वपि गणितस्य महद् योगदानं दृश्यते । तथाहि- शब्दोच्चारणप्रक्रियायां

गणनद्वारा मालाणामुच्चारण विधानं शिक्षा करोति । पापीनीयव्याकरणं पदसाधुत्व निरूपणावसरे गणनाकार्यं सेवते,विभिन्नानां वृत्तानां प्रयोगे लघु-गुरु वर्णानां च गणितीयः क्रमः छन्दश्शास्त्रे चितः । निरुक्ते विविधानां शब्दानामर्थवर्णनावसरे कलनस्यपेक्षा स्वीकृता, वेदीनां निर्माणप्रकरणे नाना प्रकाराः क्षेत्रगणितस्य सिद्धान्ताः स्वीकृताः तथाच लौकिकवैदिकादिषु सर्वत्र कर्मसु कलन विधेः संख्यानस्यापेक्षा अनिवार्येति सर्वं विदितम् एतत् । तदुक्तं

लौकिके वैदिके वापि तथा सामयिकेऽपि यः

व्यापारस्तत्र सर्वत्र संख्यानमुपयुज्यते ॥

अत एव ज्योतिषशास्त्रे अतीव प्राचीनतमे ग्रन्थे लगध नामकाचार्यं प्रणीते वेदाङ्ग ज्योतिषे गणितस्य प्राधान्यं सर्वं शास्त्रापेक्षया भणितम् –

यथा शिखा मयूराणां नागानां मणयो यथा ।

तद्वद् वेदाङ्गशास्त्राणां गणितं मूर्धनि स्थितम् ॥ (वेदाङ्ग ज्योतिषम्)

अस्यायमर्थः- यथा मयूराणां शिरसि विद्यमाना शिखा तेषां शोभां वर्धयति यथा वा केषाञ्चन नागानां शिरसि विद्यमानः मणिः तेषां शोभां समेधयति तथैव वेदाङ्गशास्त्राणां शिरसि विद्यमानं सत् गणितशास्त्रं विराजते इति ।

अमरकोषकारः-

विद्वान्विपाश्चिदोषज्ञः सन्सुधीः कोविदो बुधः ।

धीरो मनीषी ज्ञः प्राज्ञःसंख्यावान्पण्डितः सुधीः ॥

इति संख्यावान् इति विद्वानित्यस्य पर्यायवाचक रूपेण कथयति । अनेन ज्ञायते यत् गणितज्ञोऽपि विद्वान् पण्डितो भवतीति । एवं भारतीय ज्ञानपरम्परायां गणितस्य प्रमुखं स्थानं विद्यते । इदमत्र वक्तव्यमस्ति यत् वेदाङ्गसाहित्यादारभ्य गणितपरम्परायाः प्रादुर्भावविकासादिः इति भ्रमो लोके विद्यते ,तथा नेति, यतो हि वेदाङ्गानि वैदिकसाहित्यसंवर्धनपराणीति वेदोक्तान् अर्थानेव तानि पोषयन्ति विस्तृतरूपेणेति ज्ञातव्यम् इत्यत्र वैदिकसाहित्य एव गणितीयाः पदार्थाः दृश्यन्ते इत्यङ्गीकर्तव्यम् । अपि च वेदस्य अपौरुषेयत्वं स्वीकृत्य तत्कालनिर्णये अस्माकं प्राचीना प्रवृत्तिर्नासीत् । तथाऽपि केचन भौगोलिकदृष्ट्या ऐतिहासिकदृष्ट्या भूगर्भशास्त्रदृष्ट्या एवमन्यान्यविधया च तत्कालान्वेषणे बद्धश्रद्धाः विभिन्नमतयः अनिर्णीतसिद्धान्ताः वर्तन्ते । तथापि वेदस्तु वेदाङ्गैः पूर्वकालीन इत्यत्र न कस्यापि मतभेदः ।

अंकगणितम्,बीजगणितम्,रेखागणितम्(क्षेत्रगणितम्),भद्रगणितम् इति प्रमुखतया गणितस्य विभागः दृश्यते गणितग्रन्थेषु । एतेषाम् सर्वेषाम् उल्लेखः वैदिकग्रन्थेषु प्राप्यते ।

एतेषाम् गणितीयसिद्धानाम् वैदिकमूलत्वम् साधयितुं शोधप्रवन्धोऽयं प्रवर्तते ।

प्रबन्धस्य प्रविधिः

गणितीयसिद्धान्ताः आधुनिकयुगे प्रवर्तिताः वेदमूला इति साधयितुं वेदाङ्गसाहित्ये वैदिक साहित्ये च तान् सिद्धान्तान् सप्रमाणम् अन्विष्य तेषां समीक्षणम् अध्ययनरूपेण वैदिक गणितस्य अध्ययनम् अन्यत्र कृतमपि तत् क्वचित् भाषान्तरेण मौलिकोल्लेखं विना क्वचित् निवेशेन च दृश्यत इति तत्परिहाराय मौलिकप्रमाणान्वेषणपुरस्सरं प्रबन्धोऽयं नूतनपदं भजत इति मे विश्वासः ।

प्रबन्धस्यास्य उद्देश्यम्

एतादृशमध्यनं किमर्थमपेक्ष्यते ? तत्रेदमुत्तरम् –

1. वैदिकसाहित्यं केवलं कर्मकाण्डसमर्थनाय ज्ञानकाण्डपोषणाय वा न प्रवर्तते इति जागरणमस्माकम् अपेक्षितमस्ति ।
2. कर्मकाण्डज्ञानकाण्डयोरपि यच्च विज्ञानम् अवश्यापेक्षितं तत्र अन्वेषणमवश्यं कार्यम् । तच्च विज्ञानं गणितविज्ञानं यच्च सर्वव्यापकमिति सर्वविदितम् ।
3. ज्योतिषशास्त्रं यथा वेदोपकारकं तथा गणितमपि इति द्योतनमवश्यापेक्षितं भवति ।
4. गणितविज्ञानं लौकिकालौकिक फलसाधनमिति प्रकटनमवश्यकर्तव्यं विद्यते ।
5. गणितविज्ञानं वेदमूलमिति निरूपणं कार्यं विद्यते ।
6. गणितविज्ञानं शुल्बसूत्रादि मूलमित्येव न , अपि तु यथा वेदाङ्गमूलं तथा वेदमूलमपि इति वेदान्तमूलमपीति चावश्यं प्रकाशनीयम् ।
7. यजुर्वेद एव प्रायः गणिततत्वानि निगूहितानि सन्तीति अवधारणं विद्यते लोके , तदेव न, अपि च अथर्ववेदादिष्वपि केचन सिद्धान्ताः गणितीयाः संस्पृष्टाः इति संस्तोतव्यम् ।
8. केचन गणितीयास्सिद्धान्ताः विदेशीया इति यो भ्रमः प्रचारितः प्रसारितश्च तस्य उन्मूलनम् – यथा अङ्कगणितबीजगणितादिः विदेशात् प्राप्तः अस्माभिरिति यः प्रचारः तस्योन्मूलनं कार्यम् ।
9. भारतीयैः आविष्कृतस्य शून्यतत्त्वस्य सुविशदं सुविस्तृतं चाध्ययनम् ।
10. पैथगोरस प्रमेयविषये शुल्बसूत्रेण समीक्षणम् ।
11. अङ्कगणितविज्ञाने श्रीमच्छङ्कराचार्यकृत वैदिकगणितस्य प्रभावः कीदृश इति समालोचनम् ।
12. लिपि विज्ञानं (Art of writing) वेदकालादेव विद्यत इति प्रकटनम् ।

उत्तरत्र लाभः

शोधकार्येणैतेन गवेषकानां पाठकानां च नैकविधं प्रयोजनं भवदेति चिन्तयामि-

- * वैदिक गणितपद्धतिः साम्प्रतं प्रचाल्यमानायाः पद्धतेः मूलभूता इति लोके जागरणं भवति ।

- * एवमेव जीवविज्ञानं, भौतिकविज्ञानं, रसायनविज्ञानं इत्यादि विज्ञानमधिकृत्यापि वैदिक साहित्यम् समालोडनीयमिति प्रेरणा उत्साहश्च सञ्जायेताम् ।
- * वैदिकगणितपद्धतिः सरला, सरसाहृदयङ्गमा, शीघ्रफलदायिनी, मनोरञ्जनरूपा,
- * स्फूर्तिप्रदायिनी धारणशक्तिमेदिनी इत्येवं द्योतनम् ।
- * गणितीयसिद्धान्तेषु किमप्येकं तत्वमुपलक्ष्य विशिष्टाध्ययने प्रेरणा भवेत् ।
- * महाविद्यालयेषु सर्वत्र बालकवर्गमारभ्य वैदिकगणितस्य पठनपाठनादि परम्परायां संयोजनेन बालकानां ज्ञानप्रवर्धनम् ।
- * भारतीय ज्ञानपरम्परायाम् अनेकविधाः शिक्षिता आसन्निति छान्दोग्योपनिषदादितः अवगम्यते । परन्तु कतिपयविद्यानां लोपः कतिपयानां ह्रासश्च साम्प्रतं दृश्यते । एषा दुर्दशा निराकरणीया । न केवलं संस्कृतभाषा माध्यमेनास्य वैदिक गणितस्य प्रचारः कर्तव्यः परन्तु प्रान्तीय भाषाद्वारा सरलया वाण्या सरसेन मार्गेण च अस्य प्रवर्तनमवश्यापेक्षितं विद्यते येन युवकमण्डली सुसंस्कृता सती भव्यराष्ट्र निर्माणे सशक्ता भवेत् ।

वैदिकमूलत्वम् अनुसन्धीयते यथा-

अंकगणितम् –

अकिं चिन्ह इति धातोः अंक शब्दः व्युत्पन्नः । अंकैः चिन्हैः या गणना सा अंकगणितम् इति । अत्र चिन्ह रूपेण आर्षकाले रेखायाः उपयोगः आसीत्, ततश्च संख्यायाः विकासः । अतः संख्यया गणनम् अंकगणितम् इति उच्यते । एतद् व्यक्त गणितम्, पाटीगणितम्, संख्यागणितम् इत्येवं प्रकारेण व्यवहियते । यजुर्वेदस्य तैत्तिरीयशाखायाः संहितायां संख्यानामनेके प्रस्तावाः दृश्यन्ते यथा समसंख्या, विषमसंख्या, वृहत्संख्या, कलनम्, गुणनम्, दशांशविधानम्, श्रेणी इत्यादयः

सं	गणितीयः विषयः	संख्याभिः\आकृत्या प्रदर्शनम्	आधार ग्रन्थः
१	एकादि-दशपर्यन्तम्, दशगुणोत्तरम्	१, २, ३, ४, ५, ६, ७, ८, ९, १०, १००, १०००	तैत्तिरीय-आरण्यकम् -४-६९
२	एकोत्तरेण अङ्काः दशाङ्कान्तरम् शतसंख्यान्तरम्	१, २, ३, ४, ५, ६, ७, ८, ९, १०, ६४, २९, ९४, ५३, ८५, ४३ १००, २००, ३००, ४००	तैत्तिरीय-संहिता ७.२.११
३	अयुगमसंख्याश्रेणी (द्वि-अन्तरम्) दशाङ्कान्तरं	१, ३, ५, ७, ९, ११, १३, १५, १८ १९, २९, ३९, ४९, ५९	तैत्तिरीय-संहिता ७.२.१२

४	युग्मसंख्याश्रेणी (द्वि-अन्तरम्)	२,४,६,८, १०, १२, १४,१६, १८,२०	तैत्तिरीय-संहिता ७.२.१३
५	द्वयङ्कान्तरम् दशाङ्कान्तरम्	३,५, ७, ९,११, १३, १५, १९	तैत्तिरीयसंहिता
		१९,२९, ३९,४९, ५८,६९,७९,	७.२.१४
६	चतुःसङ्ख्या-श्रेणी (चतुरङ्कान्तरम्)	४, ८, १२, १६, २०, १६, १००	तैत्तिरीयसंहिता ७.२.१५
७	पञ्चसंख्या श्रेणी (पञ्चाङ्कान्तरम्)	५,१०, १५, २०, २५, १५, १००	तैत्तिरीयसंहिता ७.२.१६
८	दश-संख्या श्रेणी (दशाङ्कान्तरम्)	१०,२०, ३०,४०, ५०, ६०, ७०, ८०, ९०,१००	तैत्तिरीयसंहिता ७.२.१७
९	विंशतिसंख्या-श्रेणी विंशतिसंख्यान्तरम्	२०,४०,६०, ८०,१००	तैत्तिरीयसंहिता ७.२.१८
१०	शत संख्या श्रेणी शतसंख्यान्तरम्	१००, २००, ३००, ४००, ५००, ६००, ७००, ८००, ९००, १०००	तैत्तिरीयसंहिता ७.२.१९
११	अष्टादश-स्थानपर्यन्तं दश-गुणोत्तर-श्रेणी		तैत्तिरीयसंहिता ७.२.२०
१२	विषमसंख्याः (द्रव्यङ्कान्तरम्)	१,३, ५, ७,९, ११, १३, १५, १७, १९, २१, २३, २५, २७, २९, ३१, ३३	तैत्तिरीयसंहिता ४.७.११
	समसङ्ख्या (चतुराङ्कान्तरम्)	४, ८, १२, १६, २०, २४, २८, ३२, ३६, ४०, ४४, ४८	
१३	त्रयोदश-स्थान- पर्यन्तं दश-गुणोत्तर-श्रेणी	१०,१०१, १०२, १०३,१०१३	शुक्लयजुर्वेदः वाजसनेयसंहिता १७.२
१४	दशमानविधानेन अङ्कस्थानविशेषतया च सङ्ख्यया कथनम्	३,३३९= ३००० + ३०० + ३० + ९	ऋग्वेदः ३.९.९ ऋग्वेदः १०.५२.६ वाजसनेयसंहिता ३३.७ काण्वसंहिता ३२.७ तैत्तिरीय ब्राह्मणम् २.७.१२.२

१५	भाजन प्रक्रिया	१०००/३, शेषः - १	शतपथब्राह्मणम् ३.३.१
१६	गुणन प्रक्रिया निरग्रभाजकाः अभाजकाः च	७२० (२ × २ × २ × २ × ३ × ३ × ५) भाजकाः - २, ३, ४, ५, ६, ८, ९, १०, १२, १५, १६, १८, २०, २४, ३० अभाजकाः - ७, ११, १३, १४, १७, १९, २१, २२ २३, २५, २६, २७, २८, २९	शतपथब्राह्मणम् १०.२४.२.१-२०
१७	श्रेण्याः सङ्कलितम्	३ (२४ + २८ + ३२ + ३६ + ४० + ४४ + ४८) = ७५६	शतपथब्राह्मणम् १०.५.४
१८	भिन्न संख्याः	१- १/२, १/२; १- १/३, १/३, १- १/४, १/४, १/४, १/४	ऋग्वेदः ४.३३.५
१९	भिन्न संख्याः	१/१३, १८	तैत्तिरीयसंहिता ६.१.१०.१
२०	दशमानपद्धत्या दशगुणोत्तराः संख्याः लयोदशस्थानपर्यन्तम्	१०१, १०२, १०३, १०१३, ,	ऋग्वेदः १.१४.७ तैत्तिरीयसंहिता ४.४०.११.४ मैत्रायणीसंहिता २.८.१४ काठकसंहिता १७.१०
२१	युगपत्श्रेढीद्वयम्	१, १०, ३, ३०, ५, ५०, ...	अथर्ववेदसंहिता ६.२५.१-३ अथर्ववेदसंहिता ७.४.१
२२	गुणनप्रक्रिया	७२० × ८० = ५७,६००, ३६० × २ = ७२०	शतपथब्राह्मणम् २.३.४.१९-२०
२३	भिन्नपरिकर्म	१/४ + ३/४ = १	ऋग्वेदः १०.९०
२४	भिन्नपरिकर्म	१/३ + २/३ = १	शतपथब्राह्मणम् ४.६.७.३
२५	अर्धार्धसंख्यानां श्रेणी	१/२, १, १ १/२, २, २ १/२, ३, ३ १/२, ४	शतपथब्राह्मणम् ४.६.७.३
२७	गुणन प्रक्रिया	२१० = ३ × ७०	ऋग्वेदः ८.१९.३७

२८	गुणन प्रक्रिया	$२१=७*३$	ऋग्वेदः. १.१३३.६
२९	गुणन प्रक्रिया	$१,४७०=३*७*७०$	ऋग्वेदः ८.४६.२६
३०	संकलनक्रमेण दशमान पद्धतिः	$६०,०९९=६०,०००+९०+९$	ऋग्वेदः १.५३.९
३१	संकलनक्रमेण दशमान पद्धतिः	$३३३०=३०+३००+३०००$	ऋग्वेदः २.१.८
३२	गुणनश्रेणी	१२,२४,४८,९६	पञ्चवंशतिब्राह्मणम् १८.३
३३	दशभिः संङ्कलिता श्रेणी	२०,३०,४०,५०,६०,८०,९०,१००	ऋग्वेदः २.१.८

वैदिकगणितविज्ञानमधिकृत्य पाश्चात्यानां विदुषामभिप्रायः-

- * जर्मन् विद्वान् श्लेगल कथयति यत् दशांशविधानं भारतीयविदुषां योगदानमिति –
- * “The decimal ciphers, the honor of which, next to tens, the most important of human discoveries, has, with the common contact of historical authorities, been ascribed to the Hindus.” (Shelegel’s History of Literature p.p 143)
- * प्रो मेकडैनल अत्रैव निगदति – “ In Sciences too debt of Europe to India has been considerable. There is in the First place the great fact the Indians invented the numerical figures used all over the world, the influence which the decimal system of reckoning dependent on those figures has had not only on mathematics but on the progress of civilization, in general, can hardly be over-estimated. During the eighth and ninth centuries the Indian become the teachers in arithmatic and algebra of the Arabs and through them of the nations of the west. Thus through we call the latter Science by an Arabic name, it is a gift we owe to India.” (Macdonell’s History of Sanskrit Literature P.P-434)

एवमेव डां रे प्रकटयति स्वाभिप्रायं-

This conclusively proves that the decimal notation was familiar to Hindus when the Vyasya Bhasya was written, i.e., Centuries before the First appearance of the notation in the writing of

the Arabs or the Gerco intermediaries (Dr. Ray-History of Hindu Chemistry Vol 2 PP.117).

Dr.m. Monier Willams एवं निरूप्य अरबदेशीयाः भारतस्य कृते अधमर्णा भवन्ति इति प्रदर्शयति –“From them (Hindus) the Arabs received not only their First conception of Algebraic analysis, but also those numerical symbols and decimals notations now current everywhere in Europe, and which have rendered untold. Service to this progress of arithmetical science .”

वेदाः मन्त्रपराः यागहोमाद्यनुष्ठानोपकारकाः अथवा आध्यात्मिकचिन्तनपराः इत्येव लोकदृष्टिः विद्यते । तत् न सत्यं, यतो हि यादृशं विज्ञानं वैदिकमन्त्रेषु अत्यन्तं क्वचित् सूक्ष्मरूपेण निगूहितं क्वचित् प्रकाशमानं सुस्पष्टं विद्यते तत् सर्वमपि अस्माभिरवश्यं गवेषणीयम् । तत्र महान् परिश्रमः अपेक्षितो विद्यते । इत एव संगृह्य बहु विज्ञानं विदेशेषु सम्यक् प्रचारितं प्रसारितं विद्यत इत्यपि ज्ञेयम् ।

रेखागणितम् –(क्षेत्र गणितम्)

रेखागणितम् क्षेत्रगणित नाम्ना पूर्वम् व्यवहृतमासीत् । सूर्यचन्द्रग्रहोपग्रहादीनाम् सत्त्व विचारे इदं महतोपकरोति । चन्द्रसूर्यग्रहणादिकलनम् अनया पद्धत्या क्रियते अपि च वैदिककाले यागहोमादि प्रकरणावसरे हवनकुण्डनिर्माणप्रक्रिया वर्णिता विद्यते । तत्र कल्पशास्त्रं शुल्बशास्त्रं वा महदुपकरोति । तत्र वर्गः (Square), आयतः (rectangle), त्रिभुजम् (triangle) वर्तुलं (circle) अर्ध-वर्तुलम् (semi-circle) इत्यादीनाम् आकारविशेषाणां विवरणं विद्यते ।

यत्त्वा सूर्य स्वर्मानुस्तमसाविध्यदासुरः

अक्षयविद्यधा मग्धो भुवनान्यदीधयुः ॥

सं	गणितीयः विषयः	संख्याभिः\आकृत्या प्रदर्शनम्	आधार ग्रन्थः
१	अक्षया(जात्य त्रिभुजस्य कर्णः)	त्रिभुजस्य, चतुर्भुजस्य कर्णः	तैत्तिरीयसंहिता
२	समद्विबाहु-चतुरस्रस्य निर्माणम्	२४,३०पार्श्व-मानयुतस्य समद्विबाहु-चतुरस्रस्य निर्माणम्	शतपथब्राह्मणम् ३.५.१-६
३	रथानां निर्माणनम्	त्रिभुजाकृतिः लिचक्रयुता	ऋग्वेदः १.३४.२, १.११८,२
४	रथस्य चक्रविशेषः	पञ्च अरायुतः	ऋग्वेदः- १-१६४-१३
५	रथस्य चक्रविशेषः	३६०- अरायुतः	ऋग्वेदः १-१६४-४८
६	विविधानां रथानाम् आकृति विशेषाः	विभिन्नाः आकृतयः भिन्नाः चक्रसंख्याः च	यजुर्वेदः १६-२७

पैथागोरस् बोधायननिर्मितात् शुल्बसूत्रादेव प्रवर्तितमिति गणितज्ञाः निरूपयन्ति । अस्य विवरणम् अग्रिमाध्याये भविष्यति । क्षेत्रगणितस्य यथा वा परिचयः वैदिकमन्त्रेषु विद्यते तथैव बीजगणितस्य अङ्कगणितस्यापि वर्णनं विद्यते इत्यपि ज्ञातव्यम् अस्माभिः ।

बीजगणितम् -

इदानीं बीजगणितमधिकृत्य किंतित् पश्यामः- बीजगणितं नाम अव्यक्तानां मानानां (unknown values) कलनम् । अव्यक्त गणितमित्यपरं नाम । ALGEBRA इति आङ्गल भाषया उच्यते । अत्र करणी (SURDS) मध्यमाहरणम् outadratic equation इत्यादयः विषयाः सन्ति ।

बीजस्य अङ्कुरेण एव वृक्षस्य सृष्टिर्भवति । यथा समग्रो वृक्षः बीजे प्रत्यक्षम् अगोचरः तिष्ठति । तथैव समग्रः प्रपञ्चः ईश्वरे अव्यक्तरूपेण तिष्ठति अर्थात् ईश्वरे अव्यक्तरूपेण तिष्ठति अर्थात् ईश्वरः स्वयमपि अव्यक्तरूपे विद्यत इति तदिदं गीतायां वर्णयते

अव्यक्तादिनि भूतानि व्यक्तमध्यानि भारत ।

अव्यक्तनिधनान्येव तत्र का परिदेवना ॥ (श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता 2/28)

वस्तुतः अत्र छान्दोग्योपनिषदः षष्ठाध्याये द्वादशखण्डे विद्यमानः उद्दालकश्वतकेतुसंवादः द्रष्टव्यो भवति । यथा न्यग्रोधबीजेषु सूक्ष्मभूतेषु वृक्षः सूक्ष्मरूपेण विद्यते तथैव कार्यस्य प्रपञ्चः तत्त्वमिदं बीजगणितस्य मूलं भवति । यथा बीजानि अव्यक्तं वृक्षं व्यक्तीकुर्वन्ति तथैव समीकरण द्वारा (equations) अज्ञातराशीनां मानं व्यक्तं भवति । अत एव अव्यक्तगणितमित्यपि अस्य नामान्तरं विद्यते । बीजगणितक्षेत्रे प्रथमो ग्रन्थो भवति यस्तु ब्रह्मगुप्तेन रचितः ब्रह्मस्फुटसिद्धान्तः । स्वग्रन्थे ब्रह्मस्फुट सिद्धान्ते बीज अंकस्थाने अंक च प्रयुक्तवान् ।

वर्गाक्षराणि वर्गे अवर्गे अवर्गाक्षराणि कादडेतौ यः ।

ख द्विनदके स्वरा नव वर्ग अवर्गे तवान्त्वर्गे वा ॥

(सुधाकर द्विवेदी कृत - गणक तरङ्गिणी)

उक्त श्लोकानुसारं- क=१, ख=२, ग=३, घ=४, ङ=५, च=६, छ=७, ज=८, झ=९, ञ=१०, ट=११, ठ=१२, ड=१३, ढ=१४, ण=१५, त=१६, थ=१७, द=१८, ध=१९, न=२०, प=२१, फ=२२, ब=२३, भ=२४, म=२५, य=३०, र=४०, ल=५०, व=६०, श=७०, ष=८०, स=९०, ह=१००।

एतत्सम्बद्धानि वैदिक प्रमाणानि

श्रेण्याः सङ्कलितम्	३(२४+२८+३२+३६+४०+४४+४८) = ७५६	शतपथब्राह्मणम् १०.५.४
भिन्न संख्याः	१- १/२, १/२; १- १/३, १/३, १- १/४, १/४, १/४, १/४	ऋग्वेदः ४.३३.५

भिन्न संख्या:	१०, १०, १०, १०, १०, १०, १०, १०, १०, १०, १०,	तैत्तिरीयसंहिता ६.१.१०.१
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भद्रगणितम्

भद्रगणितम् मङ्गल सूचकं गणितं इति व्यवहारः । अस्य प्रथमः प्रचारः नागार्जुनस्य कछपूटे दृश्यते । विशतितमशताब्दगणितज्ञः श्रीमान् श्रीनिवास रामानुजः अस्मिन् गणिते अतिपरिचित आसीत् ।

पाईथागोरस् सिद्धान्तः

पाईथागोरस् सिद्धान्तः शुल्बसूत्र मूलः इति सर्वविदितम् तस्यापि प्रमाणम् वेदः भवति । तैत्तिरीयसंहितायाम् अनेके चयनरूपाः कर्मविशेषाः प्रोक्ताः । यथा श्येनचितं चिन्वीत (तै-सं ५-४-११) इत्यारभ्य पशुपक्ष्यादीनाम् आकृतिं उल्लिख्य चयनं कीर्तितम् । तादृश वेदीनिर्माणे शुल्बसूत्रस्य महान् उपकारः विद्यते । तत्र ये सिद्धान्ताः पठिताः तान् स्वीकृत्य पाईथागोरस् सिद्धान्तः प्रवर्तते । तन्निरूपणं अस्मिन् अध्याये क्रियते । वैदिकं प्रमाणं यथा-
चतुरस्त्रयाक्ष्ण्यारज्जुद्विस्तावर्ती भूमिं करोति ।

शून्यमधिकृत्य किञ्चित् प्रस्तूयते -

शून्यस्य आविष्कारः प्राचीनभारतीयानामाविष्कारेषु अन्यतमो विद्यते । बिन्दुरूपेण, लघुवृत्तरूपेण वा तस्य चिह्नं दशमानपद्धत्या च तस्य प्रयोगः अतिप्राचीनकालात् एव भारते आसीत् । शून्यं भारतदेशात् आदौ मध्यपूर्वदेशेषु प्रसृतमासीत् । ततः यूरोपभूभागीयेषु देशेषु प्रसृतम् आसीत् । विदेशेषु शून्यस्य अपरैः अङ्कैः सह तुल्यरूपेण प्रयोगः बहुकालपर्यन्तं नासीदेव ।

1. ऋग्वेदे शुनशब्दः श्वि धातोः निष्पन्नः बहुवारं प्रयुक्तः ।
2. एवमथर्ववेदे शून्यशब्दः 'रिक्तम्' इत्यर्थे प्रयुक्तोऽस्ति ।
3. अदर्शनं लोपः इत्यत्र लोपार्थकः शून्य इति पाणिनीयानां मतम् ।
4. वैशेषिकाभिमतः अभावः शून्यापरपर्याय एव ।
5. द्विरर्थे । रूपे शून्यम् । द्विःशून्ये । तावदर्धतद्गणितम् इति छन्दस्सूत्रे पिङ्गलाचार्येण वर्णानां प्रयोगविन्यस्तकथनावसरे 'रु' '0' इति चिह्नद्वयं प्रदर्शितम् । चिह्नत्वेन वर्णनमिदं प्रप्रथमं प्रमाणरूपेण शून्यस्य उपलभ्यते ।
6. बौद्धदर्शने शून्यवादः इति स्वीक्रियते । तत्र शून्यपदं निर्वाणं , मोक्षः इत्यस्य पर्यायवाचकं भवति ।
7. शून्यस्य संख्यारूपेण स्थानं भारतीयैरेव प्रप्रथमं दत्तम् ।
8. पूर्णमदः पूर्णमिदं पूर्णात् पूर्णमुदच्यते ।
9. पूर्णस्य पूर्णमादाय पूर्णमेवावशिष्यते ॥

इत्यत्र शुक्लयजुर्वेदे पूर्णार्थकः अनन्तराशोः परिकल्पना दृश्यते ।

10. अनन्ते अच्युते सृष्टिलयादिप्रक्रियायां विकारो न दृश्यते तथैव अनन्तराशौ (रवहरे) यः कोऽपि योज्यते अथवा तस्मात् वियोज्यते चेदपि तत्र न कोऽपि

विकारो न भवतीति बीजगणिते ग्रन्थे भास्कराचार्येण निरूपितम् ।

11. शून्यस्य सङ्ख्यात्वेन प्राचीतमः प्रयोगः-----
12. बक्षाली पाण्डुलिपिः (Baikhali Manuscript)
13. उपलभ्यमानेषु प्राचीन-गणितीय-ग्रन्थेषु बक्षाली-पाण्डुलिपि अन्यतमा अस्ति । न्युनातिन्यूनम् २,३०० संवत्सरेभ्यः पूर्वम् अस्याः पाण्डुलिपेः रचनाकालः स्यात् । एतस्यां पाण्डुलिप्यां शून्यस्य संख्यात्वेन प्रयोगः अस्ति । अधः अस्याः पाण्डुलिपेः कश्चन लघुभागः उद्धृतः अस्ति । अत्र द्वयोः भिन्नयोः गुणनम् अपवर्तनम् इत्यादिकर्मसु शून्यस्य प्रयोगः दृश्यते ।

उपरि मञ्जूषायां विद्यमाने उल्लेखे 'शून्यस्य' प्रयोगः अन्यैः अङ्कैः सह सामान्य-अङ्कत्वेन द्रष्टुं शक्यते । बक्षालीपाण्डुलिपिः प्रचीन भारते गणितः सम्बन्धितः पाण्डुलिपिः । भोजपत्र सम्बन्धित, अस्य लिपिः शारदा । अयं पाण्डुलिपिः अपूर्णः अस्ति । अत्र 70 पत्र नष्टः अभवत् । संस्कृत अंकगणितस्य सर्वप्रचीन पाण्डुलिपिः कलोकता नगरस्य एशियाटिक सोसाइटी स्थाने गणितावली ग्रन्थे प्रकाशितवान् ।

अत्र डब्ल्यु. डब्ल्यु. हन्टर मतम्

“To them (the Hindues) we owe the invention of the numerical symbol on the decimal scale . The Indian figures 1 to 9 being abbreviated forms of intial letters of the numerals themselves and the Zero,or o, representing the first letter of the Sanskrit word for empty (sunya).The Arabs borrowed them from the Hindus ,and transmited them to Europe.”

अनन्तसंख्या विकारराहित्यात्	संकलनादिषु प्रक्रियासु अनन्तसंख्याः निर्विकाराः	शान्तिमन्त्रः, शुक्लयजर्वेदः
अनन्त संख्या	अनन्तम्, पूर्णम्, अदिति, असंख्यातम्	यजुर्वेदः १३-५४ , बृहदारण्यकोपनिषद् २-५-१०
अनन्तपरिकर्म	अनन्तात् अनन्तोत्पत्ति अनन्त+/- अनन्तः = अनन्तः	अथर्ववेदः १०.८.२४

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भगवत्पादशङ्कराचार्याणां स्तोत्रसाहित्ये भक्तिसाधनाया मानवतायाश्च विवेचनम्

राधेश्याम् बारिक्¹

शोधसारः

भगवत्पादशङ्कराचार्येण सर्वेषां कल्याणार्थं मानवजीवन-साफल्यार्थञ्च नैकानां स्तोत्राणां सर्जनं कृतम् । सर्वाण्यपि स्तोत्राणि मनुष्यस्य शिक्षातत्त्वपरिपूर्णानि सन्ति । सर्वे वर्णाः सर्वे आश्रमाः तथा च कोऽपि मनुष्यः ईश्वरस्य प्रेमी भूत्वा भक्तियोग्यः भवतुं अर्हति । स्वस्वरूपानुसन्धानं भक्तिरित्याभिधीयते । शङ्कराचार्योऽपि स्वस्तोत्रसाहित्ये नवविधा भक्तिरुक्ता । उपासनम् - भारतीयास्तिकदर्शनेषु बन्धनात् अनेके मार्गाः मुक्तिसाधनतया वर्णिताः । उपासना द्विधा निर्गुणोपासना सगुणोपासना चेति । तत्र सगुणोपासना नाम- ब्रह्मविष्णुमहेश्वरादीनां यथाविधिः अर्चनादयः । तथैव निर्गुणोपासना ओंकारध्यानद्वारा निष्पद्यते । उपासना द्विविधा- बाह्याऽभ्यन्तरी चेति । मानवाः काम-क्रोध-लोभ-मद-अहंकार-रागद्वेषादिभ्यः सर्वथा दूरं स्थित्वा सांसारिककामवासनादिरहिताः शुभकर्मणि सदा भवेयुः । सगुणभक्तिमाध्यमेन साधारणमानवस्य चित्तशुद्धिः भवति तथा एकाग्रचित्तेन सगुणोपासनेन एव निर्गुणोपासना कृत्वा मुक्तेः प्राप्तिं कुर्वन्ति । भगवत्पादैरपि स्वस्तोत्रमाध्यमेन एवं च अद्वैतसिद्धान्तेन मानवस्य लोकव्यवस्था मर्यादिता सुरक्षिता तथा मानवतायाः महान् आदर्शः समुपस्थापितः ।

कूटशब्दः- शङ्करः, भक्ति, अधिकारी, नवधाभक्ति, उपासना, मानवता नैतिकता श्च ।

उपोद्घातः

आचार्यशङ्करः महान् दार्शनिकः विद्वान् साधकः रहस्यमयी व्यक्तित्वं समाजसुधारकः तथा च एकः उच्चकोटिः कविः आसीत् । जीव-जगतोः परस्परविरोधितत्त्वानां विश्लेषणं कृत्वा मानवसमाजकल्याणस्य मार्गं दर्शयति । लोकाय धर्मपथप्रदर्शनाय श्रेयमार्गं च नेतुं सदा समस्तजीवानां कल्याणकांक्षिराचार्यः शङ्करभगवत्पादः सदा तत्परः आसीत् । तेन लिखितानि स्तोत्राणि काव्यकल्पनायाः उत्कृष्टरूपाणि इति वक्तुं शक्यते । तस्य गद्यरचना

प्रौढः सरसः दृष्टात्मकः चासीत् । तस्य काव्येषु भावात्मकं माधुर्यं वर्तते । तस्य कृतिषु जगतः सत्यतायाः गहनः भावः अस्ति । अस्मिन् लोके मनुष्यजन्म दुर्लभं भवति एवञ्च तत्र ज्ञानप्राप्तिः अत्यन्ता दुर्लभा भवति । तथैव कवित्वं प्राप्तिः दुर्लभा एवं च काव्यलेखनस्य शक्तेः (सामर्थ्यस्य) प्राप्तिः जगति अतीव सुदुर्लभा ।

नरत्वं दुर्लभं लोके , विद्या तत्र सुदुर्लभा ।

कवित्वं दुर्लभं तत्र, शक्तिस्तत्र सुदुर्लभा ॥

शङ्कराचार्यस्य कवित्वम्

जगद्गुरुशङ्कराचार्यः न केवलं दार्शनिकानां मुकुटमणिः अपितु जगतः वर्णने अपि दार्शनिकेषु अग्रगण्यो भवति, ये स्वविचारैः मानवचिन्तनस्य मार्गं परिवर्तयन्ति स्म । शङ्कराचार्यस्य पाण्डित्येन साकं कवित्वस्य अद्वितीयः संयोगः आसीत् । यत् विचार्य ज्ञानमार्गी भक्तिमार्गी आचार्ययोः अत्यन्तं स्पष्टं अन्तरं प्रतिभासते । शङ्करः अत्यन्तः प्रौढः ज्ञानी चासीत् । तस्य दर्शने ज्ञानस्य अतीव महत्त्वं विद्यते ।

भक्तिः केवलं सगुणब्रह्मणः प्राप्तेः साधनं अस्ति , अस्माभिः तस्य माध्यमेन उच्चतरं आदर्शं प्राप्तुं शक्यते । आचार्येण न केवलं वेदान्तग्रन्थानामेवापितु साधारणजनमानवानां दुःखत्वारणार्थम् अनेकेषां स्तोत्रग्रन्थानामपि प्रणयनं कृतमस्ति । भगवत्पादशङ्कराचार्यप्रणीतेषु स्तोत्रेषु सगुणभक्तिमाध्यमेन मनुष्यस्य मनुष्येण सह समत्वभावः तथा च अतीतं वर्तमानेन सह संयोजयितुं च अद्वैतभावं प्रतिष्ठायितुं सुवर्णप्रकाशस्य इव सिद्धं भवति । तस्मिन् युगे जाति व्यवस्था अव्यवस्थिता अभवत् । भारतीय जनानां मध्ये परस्परं भातृत्वस्य भावो नासीत् । भारतीयसमाजः न केवलं ब्राह्मण-क्षत्रिय-वैश्य-शूद्र- चाण्डाल वर्गेषु विभक्तः अपितु वैष्णव-शाक्त-सौर-गाणपत्यादि साधकानां दृष्ट्या अपि अनेकेषु वर्गेषु विभक्तः आसीत् । तथैव अनेके सनातनधर्मविमुखाः आसन् । ते सम्प्रदायाः परस्परं द्वेषभावनां दर्शयन्ति स्म, येन सम्पूर्णस्य भारतीयसमाजस्य नैतिकजीवनस्य क्षयः तथा च परस्परं मानवतायाः ह्रासः जातः । अतः संसारात् मुक्तः आचार्यः शङ्कराचार्यः स्वसाहित्यमाध्यमेन सम्पूर्णसमाजस्य एकीकरणाय प्रशंसनीयः प्रयासः कृतवान् ।

भगवत्पादशङ्कराचार्येण सर्वेषां कल्याणार्थं मानवजीवन-साफल्यार्थञ्च नैकानां स्तोत्राणां सर्जनं कृतम् । सर्वाण्यपि स्तोत्राणि मनुष्यस्य शिक्षातत्त्वपरिपूर्णानि सन्ति । मया शोधपत्रेऽस्मिन् कनकधारास्तोत्रम्, शिवपराधक्षमापनस्तोत्रम्, चर्पटपञ्जिका स्तोत्रम् (भजगोविन्दम्), शिवानन्दलहरी, षट्पदी, दशश्लोकी कृष्णाष्टकमित्यादि स्तोत्राण्याधारीकृत्य भक्त्युपासनाः मानवतायाः शिक्षातत्त्वान्वेषणं च कृतम् ।

स्तोत्रशब्दस्यार्थः स्वरूपं च

स्तूयते अनेन इति स्तोत्रम् इति मूलतः ष्टुञ् स्तुतौ धातोः करणार्थे दम्नीशसयुजस्तुतुद सिसिचमिहपतदशनहः करणे इति सूत्रेण ष्टुन् प्रत्यये निर्मितम् अस्ति । स्तोत्रपदार्थनुरूपणे

श्रीवत्साङ्गमिश्राणां मतम् अस्ति -

स्तोत्रं नाम किमामनन्तिकवयो यद्यन्यदीयान् गुणान्
अन्यत्र त्वस्तोऽधिरोष्य भणितिः सा तर्हि बन्ध्या त्वयि ॥ (श्रीस्तव 3)

अमरकोशे स्तोत्रस्य पर्यायरूपेण स्तवः स्तुतिः नुतिः इत्यादयः प्रयुक्ताः सन्ति । स्तुतिशब्दः ष्टुञ् स्तुतौ धातोः क्तिन् प्रत्यये कृते निष्पद्यते । णु स्तवने धातोः क्तिन् प्रत्यये नुतिः शब्दः निष्पन्नः । शब्दकोशानुसारं प्रशंसनीयं सूक्तम् अथवा गुणकीर्तनं स्तवं वा स्तुतिः ।

शङ्कराचार्यस्य भक्तिः

अद्वैतवेदान्तदर्शनाचार्याणां शङ्करभगवद्पादानां मते केवलं ब्रह्मैव सत्यमन्यच्च सर्वं दृश्यं प्रपञ्च मायिकमसत्यम् । अतः अस्मिन् मिथ्याभूतप्रपञ्चे भक्तिदर्शनमपि भगवत्तत्त्वसाक्षात्कारेण अपवर्गद्वारमुद्घाट्य परमं पदं प्रापयति भक्तिः । शुद्धपरमब्रह्मज्ञानवादित्वेऽपि तं केवलं ज्ञानवादी इति स्वीकर्तुं न शक्नुमः । यतो हि ज्ञानेन सह आचार्यः कर्म-भक्त्योः उपयोगिताम् अपि स्वीकरोति । तस्य मते आत्मसाक्षात्कारः मनुष्यस्य जीवनस्य उद्देश्यं भवेत् । ब्रह्म सत्यं जगन्मित्येत्ययं रूपो विनिश्चयः (वि.चू.20)

अस्माकं अन्तरात्मा वस्तुतः एकमेव सत्यं परमात्मा च ब्रह्म एव । किन्तु मानवेषु इदं मम इति अहंकारः, ईर्ष्या, असत्यमित्यादिषु मिथ्या उपाधिषु वेष्टितम् अस्ति । तस्य मुख्यकारणम् अज्ञानमस्ति । आचार्यः शङ्करः आत्मसाक्षात्कारसाधनेषु भक्तिं प्रथमस्थानं दत्तवान् । परन्तु तस्य भक्तिः विशेषप्रकारस्य अस्ति येन भक्तस्य मानसिकस्तरस्य आत्मसाक्षात्कारस्य परिचयं भवति । तेषां मते भक्तिं विना मोक्षप्राप्तिः असम्भवा । विवेकचूडामणिग्रन्थे प्रोक्तम्- मोक्षकारणसामग्र्यां भक्तिरेव गरीयसी । (वि.चू. 31)

भक्तिशब्दस्य स्वरूपम्

भक्तिशब्दस्य प्रमुखतः उपासना ध्यानं सेवा ईश्वरभजनं इत्यर्थान्तरमस्ति । भगवत्प्रति प्रेम ध्यानं श्रद्धात्मसमर्पणं तथा च तन्महिमानुसन्धानं भवति । भक्त्या त्वनन्यया शक्यः, भक्त्या मामभिजानाति, इत्यादि वचनैः सिद्धमस्ति यत् भक्तिः मुक्तिसाधनमिति । मोक्षसाधनसामग्र्यां भक्तिरेव गरीयसी । भज सेवायामिति धातोः स्त्रियां क्तिन् (अष्टाध्यायी 3.3.94) सूत्रेण भावे क्तिन्प्रत्यये सति निष्पन्नस्य भक्तिशब्दस्यार्थः । तथैव शब्दकल्पद्रुमे वर्णितमस्ति- भज सेवायां इति अर्थे- विभागः, सेवा, गौणप्रवृत्तिः, भङ्गी, अनुरागविशेषः, पूज्येष्वनुरागोपासनादि परमेश्वरविषयकप्रेम इति । तथैव गरुडपुराणेऽपि भज इति धातोः सेवायां इति परिकीर्तितः ॥

भज इत्येष वै धातुः सेवायां परिकीर्तितः ।

तस्मात् सेवा बुधैः प्रोक्ता भक्तिसाधना भूयसी ॥ (गरुड.पु. उत्तरार्ध 2.3)

आचार्येण सर्ववेदान्तसिद्धान्तसारसंग्रहे वर्णितमस्ति- यत् ईश्वरस्य अनुग्रहेणैव

मानवः भवबन्धनात् मुक्तिं प्राप्नोति तत् भक्तिद्वारा सिद्ध्यति । तस्य प्रसादात् शुकादयः भवबन्धनात् मुक्ताः अभवन् ।

यस्य प्रसादेन विमुक्तसङ्गाः शुकादयः संसृतिबन्धमुक्ताः ।

तस्य प्रसादेन बहु जन्मलभ्यो भक्तैकगम्यौ भवमुक्ति हेतुः ॥ (स.वे. सि.स.280)

भक्तिः मुक्तिसाधनम् इति बोधनाय प्रबोधसुधाकरे प्रोक्तम्-

वैराग्यात्मबोधो भक्तिश्चेति त्रयं गदितम् मुक्तेः साधनम् ।

तथैव शुद्ध्यति नान्तरात्मा कृष्णपदाम्भोजमृते । (प्रबोधसुधाकर- 66-68)

भक्तेः अविद्याविनाशेन अन्तःकरणं शुद्धं भवति । एवं जीवः परमात्मनः साक्षात्कारं करोति ।

शङ्कराचार्येण विवेकचूडामणौ तु आत्मस्वरूपानुसन्धानमेव भक्तिरिति प्रोक्तम्-

स्वस्वरूपानुसन्धानं भक्तिरित्याभिधीयते

स्वात्मतत्त्वानुसन्धानं भक्तिरित्यपरे जगुः । (वि.के.चू.31)

तथैव शिवानन्दलहरीस्तोत्रे शङ्कराचार्येण भक्तेः परिभाषा प्रतिपादितास्ति-

अङ्गोलं निजबीजसन्तरिरयस्कान्तोपलं सूचिका

साध्वी नैजविभुं लता क्षितिरुहं सिन्धुः सरिद्वल्लभम् ।

प्राप्नोतीह यथा तथा पशुपतेः पादारविन्दद्वयं

चेतोवृत्तिरूपेत्य तिष्ठति सदा सा भक्तिरत्युच्यते । (शिवानन्दलहरी.61)

जगद्गुरुशङ्करमते भक्तिः मिथ्याप्रत्ययमाश्रिता न भवति । तस्य भक्तिः परिष्कृता संस्कृता च भवति । मिथ्यापूर्वकं एतत् साधयितुं न शक्नोति । तस्याधारः विश्वनियन्त्रकस्य सामर्थ्ये अनन्तः अविभज्यः च विश्वासः श्रद्धा भवति ।

भक्तेः अधिकारी

यः मानवः भगवतः नाम-रूप-शक्ति-गुण-प्रेम्णा आकृष्टः भवति तदनुसारं आचरति तथा च सांसारिकविषयेषु उदासीनो भूत्वा ईश्वरप्रीतौ निमग्नः तिष्ठति तथा च सदा लोक-संग्रहे प्रयत्नं करोति सः भक्तेः अधिकारी भवति । सर्वे वर्णाः सर्वे आश्रमाः तथा च कोऽपि मनुष्यः ईश्वरस्य प्रेमी भूत्वा भक्तियोग्यः भवितुं अर्हति ।

तथैव शङ्करः न केवलं मानवानां प्रति प्रोक्तम् । अपितु तेन एकस्मिन् स्तोत्रे स्पष्टतया उक्तम् यत् यस्य हृदयः परमेश्वरस्य चरणकमलयोः लीनः तिष्ठति सः मनुष्यः देवता पशुः पक्षी कीटः वा भवतु, सः भक्तेः अधिकारी भवति । तथैव भगवद्गीतायाः शङ्करभाष्ये वर्णितम्- तत्रापि सर्वेषां प्राणिनां भक्तेः अधिकारः प्रकीर्तितः ।

भक्तेः प्रकाराः

शङ्कराचार्येण भक्तिं स्थूलं सूक्ष्मं च द्विधा विभज्यते । प्रथमतः स्थूला भक्तिः भवति तदनन्तरं सूक्ष्मा भक्तिः उत्पद्यते । आचार्यः शङ्करः भक्तः निमित्तं ईश्वरस्य नियमानं अनुसरणं आवश्यकं मन्यते । सद्गुरुषुणां संज्ञतिः कुर्यात् । नेयं सज्जनं सङ्गे चित्तम् । (मोहमुद्गर -27) असत्यभाषणात्, परस्त्रीणां अपमानात्, दुष्टजनसङ्गात्, हिंसायाः इत्यादिभ्यः दूरं स्थितत्वात् भक्तिः श्रेयस्करी मन्यते ।

स्थूलसाधनव्यवस्थायां साधकः श्रद्धापूर्वकं बाह्याचरणात् मुख्यतया भक्तिक्रियाभिः सह सम्बद्धम् अस्ति । स्थूलभक्त्यभ्यासं कुर्वन् ईश्वरस्य कथा-नामश्रवण-कीर्तन-पूजादिवन्दनेन सूक्ष्मभक्तिः उत्पद्यते । येन मनुष्यः सारूप्य-सामीप्य-सालोक्य-सायुज्यमुक्तिं प्राप्नोति ।

सारूप्यं तव पूजने शिव महादेवेति सङ्कीर्तने ।
सामीप्यं शिवभक्तिं धुर्यजनतासाङ्गत्य संभाषणे
सालोक्यं च चराचरात्मकतनुध्याने भवानीपते ।
सायुज्यं मम सिद्धमत्र भवति स्वामिन्कृतार्थोऽस्म्यहम् ॥ शि.वा.न.ल.81

तदैव शङ्करस्य भक्तिः अहङ्कारशून्या पूर्णसमर्पणभावनापूर्णा च अद्वैतस्य प्रदर्शनम् अस्ति । हे नाथ मयि त्वत् अविच्छन्नेऽपि त्वं न मम । तरङ्गाः सदा समुद्रस्य न तु तरङ्गाणा सागरः ।

सत्यपि भेदापगमे नाथ तवाहं न मामकीनत्वम् ।
सामुद्रोहि तरङ्गः क्वचन समुद्रो न तारङ्गः ॥ (षट्पदी स्तोत्र-3)

आचार्यः मानवहृदयं ईश्वरस्य मन्दिरं आत्मसाक्षात्कारस्य स्थलं मन्यते । बहिः तदन्वेषणं आवश्यकता नास्ति । यतोहि कृष्णाष्टकस्तोत्रे वर्णितम्- मानवः यमनियम-आसन-प्राणायाम साधनेन जीवनं नियन्त्य मनः नियन्त्रणे हृदये समस्तकामान् विलीनं कृत्वा श्रेष्ठबुद्धियुक्तः मानवः ईश्वरं द्रष्टुं शक्यते । भगवत्पादानां दृढविश्वासः अस्ति यत् भगवद्भक्तिः तथा च साक्षात्कारं विना जीवः विविध योनिषु भ्रमणं करोति ।

विना यस्य ध्यानं ब्रजति पशुतां सुकर मुखां
विना यस्य ज्ञानं जनिमृतिमयं याति जनता ।
विना यस्य स्मृत्या कृमिशतजनिं याति सः विभुः
शरण्यो लोकेशो मम भवतु कृष्णोऽक्षिविषयः ॥ (कृष्णाष्टकं 6)

शङ्करस्तोत्रेषु नवधा भक्तिः

महर्षिवेदव्यासः श्रीमद्भागवते भक्तिवर्णने आध्यात्मिकपक्षाधारेण नवश्रेण्यः भक्तिः कृतास्ति । ताश्च नवधा भक्तिः इति नाम्ना प्रसिद्धाः । एताः नवभक्तयः यथा- श्रवणं, कीर्तनं, स्मरणं, पादसेवनं, अर्चनं, वन्दनं, दास्यं, सख्यं, आत्मनिवेदनञ्च । तथैव शङ्कराचार्योऽपि स्व स्तोत्रसाहित्ये नवविधा भक्तिरुक्ता ।

श्रवणभक्तिः

शङ्करस्तोत्रेषु स्पष्टतया उक्तम् यत् भगवत् श्रवणेन मनुष्यस्य क्लेशाः न केवलं दुरीकृताः अपितु ईश्वरस्य प्रसादेन मुक्तिं प्राप्नोति । एषा श्रवणभक्तिः महापुरुषसङ्गेन एव साधयितुं शक्यते ।

क्षीणो यस्य रथो रथाङ्गयपगलं चन्द्रर्कविम्बद्वयं ।
कोदण्डः कनकाचलो हरिरभूद्भागो विधिः सारथिः ।
तूणीरो जलधिर्हयाः श्रुतिवयो मौर्वी भूजङ्गाधिपः
तस्मिन्मे हृदयं सुखेन रमतां साम्ने परब्रह्मणि ॥ (दशश्लोकी-3)

कीर्तनभक्तिः

ईश्वरस्य नाम-गुण-महत्त्व-लीलानाञ्च उच्चैः स्वरेण वर्णनं गायनं पाठनं च कीर्तनभक्तिः इति कथ्यते । श्रीशङ्करः स्तुतिश्लोके वदति - हे पशुपते यः मनुष्यः भवतः शिव-महादेवादिना प्रेम्णा भक्तिपूर्वकं जपेत् सः भवतः नित्यं सामीप्यं प्राप्य मुक्तिं प्राप्नोति ।

श्रिया श्लिष्टो विष्णुः स्थिरचरगुरुर्वेदविषयो
धियां साक्षी शुद्धो हरिरसुरहन्ताञ्जनयनः ।
गद्दी शखी चक्री विमल वलमालीस्थिरखचिः ।
शरण्यो लोकेशो मम भवतु कृष्णोऽक्षि विषयः ॥ (कृष्णाष्टकम्-1)

स्मरण-भक्तिः

ईश्वरस्य नाम-गुण-रूप-माहात्म्यस्य सर्वव्याप्तिलीलायाश्च स्मरणं स्मरणभक्तिरुच्यते । भक्त्या भगवतः अमृतमयकथानां श्रद्धापूर्वकं पठनं मननञ्च कृत्वा शरीरस्य समस्तविषयं विस्मृत्य भावरूपं ध्रुववत् लीनं भवति तत् स्मरणभक्तिरूपम् । आचार्यशङ्करः स्वस्तोत्रेषु पदे पदे स्मरणभक्तेः महत्त्वं व्याख्यातम् ।

पवित्त्रं चरित्रं विचित्रं त्वदीयं नराः ये स्मरन्त्यन्वहं रामचन्द्र ।
भवन्तं भवान्तं भरन्तो लभन्ते कृतान्तं न पश्यन्त्यतोऽन्ते ॥ (श्रीराम भूजङ्ग-17)
महादेव देवेश देवादिदेव स्मरारे पुरारे यमारे हरेति
ब्रुवाणः स्मरिष्यामि भक्त्या भवन्तं ततो दयाशील देव प्रसीद ॥ (दक्षिणा-वर्ण-15)

पादसेवन-भक्तिः

यथा संसारे मानवाः स्वमातृ-पित्रोः चरणाम्बुजसेवां कुर्वन्ति तथैव साधकस्य अपि भगवतः मूर्तिपूजा गुरुपूजा च प्रथमावस्था भवति । अमृत चक्षुषा भगवच्चरणारविन्दस्य पुनः पुनः दर्शनं चरणोदकस्य शिरसि ग्रहणं पादसेवनभक्तिरुच्यते ।

आचार्यशङ्करः स्तोत्रस्य एकस्मिन् श्लोके वर्णितम्- यत् ईश्वरस्य चरणाम्बुजभक्तिः वलवत् नौका इव लौकिकसागरं लङ्घयितुं साहाय्यं करोति ।

ह्यम्भोराशो संसृति रूपे लुठतां तत्पारं यत्पदभक्तिर्दृढनौका । दक्षिणा-वर्ण-15

अपारसंसारसमुद्रमध्ये निमज्जतो मे शरणं किमस्ति ।

गुरोः कृपालो कृपया वदतद् विश्वेशपादाम्बुजदीर्घनौका ।

यदि ईश्वरस्य पादयोः स्पर्शेण निर्जीवशिला सजीवा भवति तर्हि तस्य पादसेवकस्य जीवितस्य भक्तस्य परिणामस्य विषये किं वा वक्तव्यम् ।

अर्चन-भक्तिः

बाह्यभौतिकरूपपूजनाय बाह्योपकरण पदार्थैः चन्दनपुष्पैः पत्रैः धूपैः नैवेद्यैः ताम्बूलादिभिः च भवति । शङ्कराचार्येण शिवानन्दलहर्या भगवतशिवस्य पूजाफलं ब्रह्मपदं विष्णुपदं च निर्दिष्टम् । श्रीविष्णु शिवार्चनसमये सहस्रनामावलिसहपद्मपुष्पसमर्पणाम्नि काऽर्चनायां पुष्पैकन्यूनतायां पुण्डरीकाक्षनाम स्मरन् स्वकीयनेत्रकमलसमर्पणाय समुद्यते ।

विष्णुर्यस्य सहस्रनामानियममादम्भोरुहाण्यर्चयन्

एकोनोषचित्तेषु नेत्रकमलं नैजं पदाब्जद्वये ।

संपूज्यासुरसंहतिं विफलैस्तरैलोक्यपालोऽभवत्

तस्मिन् मे हृदयं सुखेन रमतां साम्बे परब्रह्मणि ॥ (दशश्लोकि. 7)

वन्दन-भक्तिः

ईश्वरस्य रूपं नाम महत्त्वं च हृदये धारयितुं भगवतः मूर्तिं प्रति आदरपूर्वकं प्रणामं कर्तुं च पूजा भक्तिः च भवति । देवालयं गत्वा ईशमूर्तिं भक्त्या श्रद्धा सहितं प्रणामं कृत्वा चराचरात्मकजगत् सम्पूर्णं जीव ब्रह्म स्वरूपं मन्यते सा वन्दनभक्तिः । शङ्कराचार्यस्य स्तोत्रेषु सर्वत्रैव वन्दनभक्तिमाहात्म्यं वर्णितम् । तथैव भगवत्पादशङ्करः स्वस्तोत्रेषु वन्दनभक्तिः यथा-

नमस्ते नमस्ते विभो विश्वमूर्ते नमस्ते नमस्ते चिदानन्दमूर्ते ।

नमस्ते नमस्ते तपोयोगगम्य नमस्ते नमस्ते श्रुतिज्ञानगम्य ॥ (वेदसार शिवस्तोत्र-8)

नागेन्द्र हाराय त्रिलोचनाय भस्माङ्गरागाय महेश्वराय ।

नित्याय शुद्धाय दिग्म्बराय तस्मै नकाराय नमः शिवाय ॥ (शिवपञ्चाक्षरस्तोत्रम्)

दास्यभक्तिः

भगवतः गुणान् प्रभावान् च ज्ञात्वा तस्य सेवां कृत्वा आज्ञापालनं दास्यभक्तिः । इयं मानसिकभावना विद्यते । तस्य भक्तान्तर्गतं ते सर्वे भावाः स्वपुत्रं मातापितरं गुरुं च प्रति व्यक्तं कुर्वन्ति । तदेव आचार्यः शिवपादादिकेशान्तस्तोत्रे उच्च-नीच-स्थावर-जङ्गमेत्यादीन् समस्तभेदान् विस्मृत्य कीटपतङ्गस्य वन्दना क्रियते । परमशिवस्य दास्यभावोपासकनन्दिश्वरस्य शापवशात् त्रैलोक्यजयी रावणः विनाशमुपगतः । एवमेव दशश्लोकिस्तोत्रे- दास्यभक्तिः निरूपिता ।

सख्यभक्तिः

भगवतः प्रभावं रहस्यं च जानन्नपि मित्रभावेनोपासना सख्यभक्तिरुच्यते ।

भगवत्पादशङ्कराचार्यः कृष्णाष्टकस्तोत्रे भगवत ब्रजशिशु अर्जुनस्य ब्रजवनिता सुग्रीवो तथा विभिषमादश्च सख्यभाव उपासनायां अलौकिकं महत्त्वं प्राप्तवन्तः ।

धनश्यामो वायो ब्रजशिशुवयस्योऽर्जुनसखः । (कृष्णाष्टकम्-7)

आत्मनिवेदन-भक्तिः

साधकः यदा ममत्वाहंकाररहितो मनः धनमित्यादिसर्वाणि कर्माणि प्रेमपूर्वकं ईश्वरं समर्पयति सा आत्मनिवेदनभक्तिः । नवधाभक्तिषु आत्मनिवेदनम् इत्यस्य महत्त्वं अस्ति । आत्मनिवेदनभक्तौ साध्यं साधनं च ऐक्यं प्राप्नोति । आत्मनिवेदनभक्तौ व्यक्तिसत्ता चरमसत्तायां नदीसमुद्रवत् पूर्णविलीना भवति । केवलं शिवोऽहं शिवोऽहम् अनुभवति । पूर्णसमर्पणावस्थायां मातापितरौ गुर्वादीन् सर्वं ईश्वरमयं पश्यति ।

यल्लैव यल्लैव मनो मदीयं तल्लैव तल्लैव तव स्वरूपम् ।

यल्लैव यल्लैव शिरो मदीयं तल्लैव तल्लैव पदद्वयं ते ॥ (त्रिपूरसुन्दरी- 110)

शङ्करस्तोत्रेषु आत्मनिवेदनं द्विविधं प्रोक्तम्- भावसहितं आत्मनिवेदनं भावरहितं आत्मनिवेदनं च इति द्विविधं ख्यातं ।

नसस्ते पादाब्जे निवसतु वसस्तोत्रभणितो

करो चाम्पर्तायां श्रुतिरपि कथाकर्षणविधौ ।

तव ध्याने बुद्धिर्नयलयुगले मूर्तिविभवे

परग्रन्थान् कैर्वा परमशिवजाने परमतः ॥ (शिवानन्दलहरीस्तोत्रम्-7)

भक्तेः साधनम्

उपासनम्

भारतीयास्तिकदर्शनेषु बन्धनात् अनेके मार्गाः मुक्तिसाधनतया वर्णिताः । समस्तदुखात् मुक्तये उपनिषत्सु साधनतया विहिता उपासना इति । उपासनेयं समस्तमानवानां परमकल्याणकारी भवति । उपासना इति शब्दः उपपूर्वक-आस धातोः युचि टाप् प्रत्यये कृते उपासनाशब्दः निष्पद्यते । उप इति सामीप्यार्थकं तथा च आस इति उपवेशनार्थकधातोः निष्पन्नः भवति । उपासनाशब्दस्यऽर्थो भवति परमात्मसन्निध्यप्राप्ति आत्मसाक्षात्कारोपायः । ब्रह्मसूत्रे वर्णितम्- भेदस्योपासनार्थत्वाद्भेदे तात्पर्यात् इति । छान्दोग्योपनिषद्भाष्यभूमिकायां शङ्करपादेन वर्णितम्-

“उपासनं तु यथाशास्त्रसमर्थितं किञ्चिदालम्बनमुपादाय तस्मिन् समानचित्त वृत्तिसन्तानकरणं तद्विलक्षणप्रत्यययानन्तरितमिति विशेषः ।” (छा. उ.श.भा)

“उपासनं नाम यथाशास्त्रमुपास्यार्थस्य विषयीकरणेन सामीप्यमुपगम्य तैलधारावत्समानप्रत्ययप्रवाहेण दीर्घकालं पदासनं उदुपासनमाचक्षते ।” (गीता.श.12.3)

“उपासना नाम समानप्रत्ययमानप्रवाहकरणम् ।” (शङ्करभाष्यम्. 4.1.6)

उपासनायाः प्रकाराः

उपासना मुख्यतः भक्तिशब्देनापि उपनिषत्सु तत्र तत्र प्रतिपादिता । यतो हि उपासना हि भक्तिमूला भवति । भक्तिं विना उपासना न सम्भवति , यतो हि भक्तिरस्त्युपासनायाः प्राणरूपा । तदुपासना द्विधा निर्गुणोपासना सगुणोपासना चेति । किन्तु उपासना हि उपास्याधीना परन्तु उपास्यं तु ब्रह्म एव । तथैव अद्वैतवेदान्ते वर्णितम् - ब्रह्म द्विविधम्- निर्गुणं सगुणं च । निर्गुणब्रह्म सजातीयविजातीयं स्वगतं भेदशून्यं सर्वोपाधिवर्जितम् एकमेवाद्वितीयम् । अपरं च नामरूपविकारभेदोपाधिविशिष्टं सगुणब्रह्म । यतो हि विद्याविद्याभेदेन ब्रह्मणः द्विरूपता , तत्र अविद्यावस्थायां ब्रह्मणः उपास्योपासकादिविलक्षणं मुख्यतः सर्वव्यवहारः ।

श्रद्धावान् लभते ज्ञानं तत्परः संयतेन्द्रियः ।

ज्ञानं लब्ध्वा परा शान्तिमचिरेणाधिगच्छति । (गीता. 4.39)

शङ्कराचार्यः गीताभाष्ये अवर्णयत्- भक्तः ये सुकृतिनः पूर्वजन्मकृतपूर्णसंचयाः जनाः सफलजन्मानः ते एव, न अन्ये ,मां भजन्ते , ते च त्रयः सकामाः ,एकः अकामः इत्येवं चतुर्विधाः । यथा- आर्तः जिज्ञासुः, अर्थार्थी, ज्ञानी,इत्यादि चतुर्णां मध्ये ज्ञानी तत्त्ववित् भवति ।

चतुर्विधा भजन्ते मां जनास्सुकृतिनोऽर्जुन ।

आर्तो जिज्ञासुरर्थी ज्ञानी च भरतर्षभ ॥ (गीता. 7.16)

निर्गुणब्रह्मणः साक्षात्कीर्तिकठिनाऽस्ति । अत एव प्रथमं सगुणोपासना कर्तव्येति मत्वा निर्गुणोपासनापेक्षया सगुणोपासनायाः श्रेष्ठत्वं भवति । एवं च सगुणोपासनाऽपि निर्गुणब्रह्मणः एवोपासना । निर्गुणमपि सद्ब्रह्म नामरूपगतगुणैः सगुणमुपासनार्थं तत्र तत्रोपदिश्यते, इत्येतदप्युक्तमेव ।

तत्र सगुणोपासना नाम- ब्रह्मविष्णुमहेश्वरादीनां यथाविधिः अर्चनादयः । तथैव निर्गुणोपासना ओंकारध्यानद्वारा निष्पद्यते । कठोपनिषदि वर्णितं - तदेतद्ब्रह्म ओंशब्दवाच्यमोंशब्दप्रतीकं ॥ (क.उ 1.2.15)

उपासना द्विविधा- बाह्याऽभ्यन्तरी चेति । तत्र बाह्योपासना गन्धपुष्पादिभिः स्व स्वाराध्यदेवतां प्रति आराधनं पूजनं च भवति । अपरं च प्रबलभावनामाध्यमेन चित्तेन च स्वेष्टदेवताराधनमान्तरुपासनामुच्यते । तलान्तरोपासना विना बाह्योपासनायाः साफल्यं न भवति ।

श्रीशङ्कराचार्यविभावितस्तोत्रेषु मानवतायाः सन्देशः

भगवत्पादशङ्कराचार्यप्रणीतेषु स्तोत्रेषु सगुणभक्तिमाध्यमेन मनुष्यस्य मनुष्येण सह समत्त्वभावं अतीतं वर्तमानेन सह संयोजयितुं च अद्वैतभावं प्रतिष्ठायितुं सुवर्णप्रकाशस्य इव सिद्धं भवति । तस्मिन्गुणे जातिव्यवस्था अव्यवस्थिता अभवत् । भारतीय जनानां

मध्ये परस्परं भातृत्वस्य भावः नासीत् । भारतीयसमाजः न केवलं ब्राह्मण-क्षत्रिय-वैश्य-शूद्र-चाण्डालादिवर्गेषु विभक्तम् अपितु वैष्णव-शाक्त-सौर-गाणपत्यादिसाधकानां दृष्ट्या अपि अनेकेषु वर्गेषु विभक्तः आसीत् । तथैव अनेके मनुष्याः सनातनधर्मविमुखाः आसन् । ते सम्प्रदायाः परस्परं द्वेषं दर्शयन्ति स्म, येन सम्पूर्णस्य भारतीयसमाजस्य नैतिकजीवनस्य क्षयः जातः । अतः संसारात् मुक्तः शङ्कराचार्यः स्वसाहित्यमाध्यमेन सम्पूर्णसमाजस्य एकीकरणाय प्रशंसनीयः प्रयासः कृतवान् ।

भगवत्पाद-आदिशङ्कराचार्येण सर्वेषां कल्याणार्थं मानवजीवन-साफल्यार्थञ्च नैकानां स्तोत्राणां सर्जनं कृतम् । सर्वाण्यपि स्तोत्राणि मानवताशिक्षातत्त्वपरिपूर्णानि सन्ति । मया शोधपत्रेऽस्मिन् कनकधारास्तोत्रं, देव्यपराधक्षमापनस्तोत्रं, चर्पटपञ्जिकास्तोत्रं (भजगोविन्दम्), मोह-मुद्गर, शिवानन्दलहरी, शिवापराधस्तोत्रं, कृष्णाष्टकं, त्रिपुरासुन्दरी, दशश्लोकी, शिवभुजङ्गादिस्तोत्रमाधारीकृत्य भक्तिस्वरूपं तथा च मानवतायाः शिक्षातत्त्वान्वेषणं कृतम् ।

नैतिकाचरणम्

भक्तेः अधिकारी भवितुं मानवानां स्वस्य नैतिकाचरणशुद्धिः आवश्यकी भवति । मानवस्य सरलशुद्धहृदयः विनयशीलस्वभावः च भवेत् । मिथ्यावाक्-दुराचार-दुष्कृत-ब्रह्मद्वेषेभ्यः दूरं तिष्ठेत् । अर्थात् मानवाः काम-क्रोध-लोभ-मद-अहंकार-रागद्वेषादिभ्यः सर्वथा दूरं स्थित्वा सांसारिककामवासनादिरहिताः शुभकर्मणि सदा भवेयुः । तदेव शङ्कराचार्येणोक्तम्-

पौरोहित्यं रजनी चरितं ग्रामणीत्वं नियोगो ।
माठापत्यं ह्यनृतवचनं साक्षिवादः परान्नम् ।
ब्रह्मदेवः खलजनरहितः प्राणिनां निर्दयत्वम्
मा भृदवं पशुपते जन्मजन्मान्तरेषु ॥ (शिवापराध-14)

आचार्यशङ्करः यथा महान् एकत्ववादी दार्शनिकः तथा च महान् भक्तोऽपि आसीत् । एकत्ववादी विशुद्धज्ञानवादी च अभवत् अपि सः समस्तमानवानां लोक-संग्रहाय विविधदेवदेवीसम्बद्धानि स्तोत्राणि रचितवान् । तेषां मते भक्तिः एकप्रकारकी मनोवृत्तिः यत् भक्तः भगवतः चरणयोः लीनः भवति । एवं एषः सम्पूर्णः समर्पणभावः तस्य भक्तिविशेषः भवति । यदा मानवस्य व्यक्तित्वं अस्तित्वं परमसत्त्वे विलीयते तदा भक्तस्य शिवोऽहं शिवोऽहं अनुभावात्मकं भावरूपेण श्रूयते । साऽवस्था एव आत्मसाक्षात्कार उच्यते ।

तत्र संपूर्णमङ्गलमयी अधिष्ठात्री देवी महालक्ष्मी मम कृते मङ्गलमय भवतु-

अङ्गहरे पूलकभूषण माश्रयन्ती भृगांगनैव मुकुलाभरणं तमालम् ।
अङ्गिकृताखिल विभूतिरपांगलीला माङ्गल्यदास्तु मम मङ्गलदेवतायाः ।
(क.न.धा. 1)

यावज्जननं तावन्मरणं, तावज्जननी जठरे शयनम् ।

इह संसारे स्फुटरदोष, कथमिव मानव, तव संतोषः ॥ (मौहमुद्गर-5)

अस्मिन् प्रपञ्चभूतसंसारे भवतु नाम कुपुत्रो भवेत् परन्तु कुमाता कदापि न भवति ।
शङ्कराचार्यः वदति – मत्समः पातकी नास्ति कोऽपि अन्यः । जननी सर्वेषां पातकमानवानां
पापमियं नाशयति ।

मत्समः पातकी नास्ति पापघ्नी त्वत्समा न हि .

एवं ज्ञात्वा महादेवि यथायोग्यं तथा कुरु ।

तथापि त्वं स्नेहं मयि निरुपमं यत्प्रकुरुषे

कुपुत्रो जायेत क्वचिदपि कुमाता न भवति ॥ (मोहमुद्गर 3)

स्वस्तोत्रमाध्यमेन मानवतायै सन्देशं यच्छति - धन-जन-यौवनं प्रति कदापि गर्वं न
करणीयं यतो हि एतत् सर्वं मायामालं एव एकेनैव निमिषेण कालः सर्वं हरति । कदापि
नारीशरीरं प्रति मोहं न करणीयं एतत् सर्वं तु मांसवसादि विकाररूप इति मनसि सदा
चिन्तनीयम् ।

मा कुरु धनजनयौवनगर्वं हरतिनिमेषात्कालः सर्वम् ।

मायामयमिदमखिलं हित्वा ब्रह्मपदं त्वं प्रविश विदित्वा ॥

नारीस्तनभरजघननिवेशं दृष्ट्वा मोहावेशम् ।

एतन्मांसवसादिविकारं मनसि चिन्तय वारं वारम् ॥ (मोहमुद्गरः 11)

मानवस्यात्मज्ञानेनैव संसारे दृश्यमानमानवः मानवमध्ये स्वपरात्मकभेदनिर्वृत्तिः भवति
एवं च जनः सर्वभूतेषु सदा आत्मवत् पश्यति । एवं जगति परस्परभेदभावस्य सङ्घर्षस्य च
नाशः भवति, सर्वे आत्मवत्सर्वभूतेषु, सर्वे खल्वेदं ब्रह्म इति चिन्तने मानवताया स्थापनं
भवति । संसारस्य विषयासक्तेः विरक्तभावः प्रदशयन्ति ।

भजगोविन्दं भजगोविन्दं गोविन्दं भज मूढमते ।

सम्प्राप्ते सन्निहिते काले न हि न हि रक्षति डुकृजकरणे ॥

पुनरपि जननं पुनरपि मरणं, पुनरपि जननीजठरे शयनम् ।

इह संसारे खलु दुस्तारे, कृपयापारे पाहु मुरारे । भज.. (चर्पटपञ्चरिका 4)

निष्कर्षः

अत्र निष्कर्षतः इदं वक्तुं शक्यते – यत् शङ्कराचार्येण भारतीयसनातनधर्मोपासनायाः
आश्रयभूतेषु विभिन्नेषु प्रान्तेषु अनेकदेवादीनां महत्त्वं स्वस्तोत्रसाहित्यमाध्यमेन प्रदर्शनं
कृतम् । सगुणभक्तिमाध्यमेन साधारणमानवस्य चित्तशुद्धिः भवति तथा एकाग्रचित्तेन
सगुणोपासनेन एव निर्गुणोपासना कृत्वा मुक्तेः प्राप्तिं कुर्वन्ति । यः भौतिकवादी मानवः
वामवार्गे सदा भवति स तु मांस मीनं मदिरा मुद्रा मैथुनश्चेत्येतेषु कार्येषु मग्नः भवन्ति ।
तेषामेव सन्मार्गे प्रवृत्तिं कारयितुं शङ्कराचार्यः भक्त्युपासनामाध्यमेन स्वस्तोत्रेषु मानवताया
सन्देशं प्रतिपादयति । ब्रह्मणोपासनेन विविधफलानि प्राप्यन्ते । हिरण्यगर्भोपासनेनापिमादि

सिद्धिः भवति , ज्ञानकर्मोपासनेन वैराज्यप्राप्तिः भवति , ओंकारोपासनेन ब्रह्मलोकप्राप्तिः भवति, ब्रह्मोपासनेन ब्रह्मप्राप्तिः भवति । तदेतत्सर्वं उपासनायाः इष्टफलसाध्यस्य अद्वैतब्रह्मसिद्धेः प्राप्त्यर्थं भवति । आचार्यः स्वऽद्वैतवादः सिद्धान्तरूपेण प्रतिपादितः परन्तु लोकसंग्रहाय मनुष्येषु समत्वभावः मानवतायाः विकासाय तथा च भारतीसंस्कृतेः रक्षणाय अनेकानि मठमन्दिराणि स्तोत्रग्रन्थानि च निर्मितानि । शङ्करेण जन्मत एव मानवकल्याणं लोकव्यवहारोऽपि सर्वथा रक्षितः आसीत् । भगवत्पादैरपि स्वस्तोत्रमाध्यमेन एवं च अद्वैतसिद्धान्तेन मानवस्य लोकव्यवस्था मर्यादिता सुरक्षिता तथा मानवतायाः महान् आदर्शः समुपस्थापितः । यो मानवः सर्वेषां प्राणिनाम् अद्वैष्टा दयालुः निरहङ्कारः सुखदुःखेषुसमभावः समर्पणभावः दृढनिश्चयः स एव भक्तः परमेश्वरस्य प्रेयो भवति ।

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श्रीमच्छङ्करभगवत्पादकृतं स्फोटवादखण्डनम्

शुभदीप् दास्¹

शोधसारः

शब्दशास्त्रतत्त्वज्ञानां वैयाकरणानां प्राणभूतस्तावत् स्फोटः। प्रथमतो भगवता भर्तृहरिणा वाक्यपदीये स्फोटवादस्यास्य सौपत्तिकं निरूपणं विहितम्। तदनु नैके प्रसिद्धा आचार्याः स्फोटसिद्धान्तमिमं द्रढीकृतवन्तः। स्फोटस्य लक्षणं “वर्णातिरिक्तः वर्णाभिव्यङ्ग्यः अर्थप्रत्यायकः नित्यः शब्दः स्फोटः” इति ते अङ्गीकुर्वन्ति। अर्थबोधाय स्फोटः अत्यावश्यक इति वैयाकरणा मन्यन्ते। शब्दशास्त्रे जगतः अभिन्ननिमित्तोपादानकारणं शब्दब्रह्म इति यदुच्यते तस्याधारोऽयं स्फोटसिद्धान्त एव। परन्त्वस्य स्फोटतत्त्वस्य स्वीकारः अन्येषु शास्त्रेषु न कृतः। तस्मात्तत्र तत्र शास्त्रग्रन्थेषु शास्त्रकृतः उपपत्तिभिरस्य खण्डनमकुर्वन्। अद्वैते शङ्करभगवत्पादाः ब्रह्मसूत्रभाष्ये देवताधिकरणे तत्त्वमिदं निराकृतवन्तः। तत्र ते वर्णानां नित्यतां प्रतिपाद्य तैरेव अर्थबोधः सम्भवतीति तदर्थं स्फोटस्वीकारो निरर्थकः इत्याहुः। यतो हि वर्णानित्यत्वस्य तदारोपितक्रमस्य चाङ्गीकारेणैव अर्थबोधः सम्भवतीति सिद्धान्ते कल्पनालाघवं वर्तते। एवमेवान्या अप्यनेका पूर्वपक्षयुक्तयः सिद्धान्तयुक्तयश्च शोधनिबन्धेऽस्मिन् विस्तारेण प्रतिपादितास्तथा स्फोटवादा निरर्थक इत्ययं सिद्धान्तः उपपत्तिभिः स्वविवेकपुरःसरं द्रढीकृतः।

कूटशब्दाः – स्फोटः, शब्दब्रह्म, वर्णः, ध्वनिः, संस्कारः, नित्यः, अनित्यः

भूमिका

शब्दशास्त्रविशारदैः भर्तृहरिप्रदर्शितपन्थानमवलम्ब्य अङ्गीकृतस्य नित्यशब्दात्मकस्य स्फोटस्य खण्डनं श्रीमच्छङ्करभगवत्पादैः ब्रह्मसूत्रस्य प्रथमाध्यायस्य तृतीयपादस्य देवतारख्ये अष्टमाधिकरणे कृतम्। तत्र स्फोटवादनिराकरणपरकसिद्धान्तनिरूपणात् प्राक् वैयाकरणप्राणभूतः अयं स्फोटः किंस्वरूप इति निरूपणीयम्। यतो हि पूर्वपक्षनिरूपणात् परं सिद्धान्ते निरूपिते सिद्धान्तावगमः सुष्ठु सम्पद्यते।

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स्फोटस्वरूपम्

“वर्णातिरिक्तः वर्णाभिव्यङ्गयः अर्थप्रत्यायकः नित्यः शब्दः स्फोटः” इति स्फोटस्य लक्षणम्। वर्णभ्यो भिन्नः वर्णैः अभिव्यक्तः अर्थबोधजनकः नित्यशब्द एव स्फोट इत्युच्यते। अस्य द्विधा व्युत्पत्तिर्भवितुमर्हति। वर्णैः स्फुट्यते अभिव्यज्यते इत्यतः अयं स्फोटः। अथवा अर्थस्य स्फुटीभावः अभिव्यक्तिः भवति अनेन इत्यतः अयं स्फोटः। वर्णानां तृतीयक्षणविनाशित्वात् तेषाम् एकस्मिन्काले एकत्र समावेशाभावात् पदत्वं न सम्भवति। पदाभावे च पदसमावेशजन्यं वाक्यमपि न सम्भवति। तेन पदार्थवाक्यार्थयोः ज्ञानमपि न सम्भवति। तस्मात् वर्णादिभिः अभिव्यक्तस्य अर्थबोधानुकूलस्य स्फोटाख्यस्य नित्यशब्दस्य अङ्गीकारः कर्तव्य एव। स स्फोट एव वाच्यार्थमुपस्थापयति।

वर्णानां तृतीयक्षणविनाशित्वेऽपि ते एकमेकं संस्कारं जनयन्ति। सम्पूर्णे पदे वाक्ये वा उच्चारिते अनुभूते च सति तस्य पदस्य वाक्यस्य वा यः अन्त्यः वर्णः सः अनुभूतः सन् पूर्वपूर्ववर्णानां पूर्वपूर्वपदानां वा संस्कारान् उद्बोधयति। तदनुन्तरम् अन्तिमस्य वर्णस्य नाशे सति तदनुभवजन्येन संस्कारेण सह उद्बुद्धाः संस्काराः मिलिताः सन्तः तेषामाश्रयभूते चित्ते तत्तत्पदस्फोटं तत्तद्वाक्यस्फोटं वा अभिव्यञ्जयन्ति। तस्मादेव क्रमेण पदार्थस्य वाक्यार्थस्य वा ज्ञानं जायते। इयमेव स्फोटाभिव्यक्तेः सामान्या प्रक्रिया।

बहवः वर्णाः बहूनि पदानि वा मिलित्वा क्रमेण पदं वाक्यं वा भवति चेदपि एकत्वस्यैव ज्ञानं भवति, न तु बहुत्वस्य इति स्फोटस्यास्य अस्तित्वे प्रमाणम्। यथा गौः इति पदे गकारः औकारः विसर्गः इति वर्णत्रयमस्ति। शुक्लां गामानय इति वाक्ये च त्रीणि पदानि सन्ति। तथाप्यत्र एकत्वस्यैव ज्ञानं भवति। अतः अत्र एकत्वस्य आश्रयभूतः कश्चित् पदार्थः अस्तीति गम्यते। स पदार्थ एव स्फोटः इत्यङ्गीक्रियते।

शब्दाद्वैतवादिभिः वैयाकरणैरुच्यते – स्फोटाख्यः शब्दः शुद्धः नित्यः निरवयवः एकः अखण्डश्च। इदमेव जगतः अभिन्ननिमित्तोपादानकारणं शब्दब्रह्म। सम्पूर्णं जगत् अस्यैव विवर्तभूतम्। तथाह्युक्तं भर्तृहरिणा –

“अनादिनिधनं ब्रह्म शब्दतत्त्वं यदक्षरम्।

विवर्ततेऽर्थभावेन प्रक्रिया जगतो यतः ॥” (वाक्यपदीयम् – १.१)

सर्वेषां पुरुषाणामन्तः अयं स्फोटो विद्यते। तस्य स्फोटस्य एकत्वेऽपि तद्व्यञ्जकानां वर्णजन्यानां पदजन्यानां वा संस्काराणां सामर्थ्यात् विविधार्थबोधो भवति। किञ्च, स एक एव स्फोटः व्यञ्जकस्थानादीनां भेदात् विविधसंज्ञाः लभते। यथा – मूलाधारे अभिव्यक्तः स्फोटः ‘परा’ इत्युच्यते। नाभिदेशे अभिव्यक्तः स ‘पश्यन्ती’ इत्युच्यते। स एव हृदयदेशे आरूढः ‘मध्यमा’ इत्युच्यते। एतावत्पर्यन्तम् अयं श्रोतुः बुद्धिगोचरो न भवति। यदा अयं कण्ठताल्वादीनां व्यापारात् ध्वनिसहकारेण श्रोतुः श्रोत्रगोचररूपेण अभिव्यक्तो भवति तदा ‘वैखरी’ इत्युच्यते। उक्तं च-

“परा वाङ्मूलचक्रस्था पश्यन्ती नाभिसंस्थिता ।

हृदिस्था मध्यमा ज्ञेया वैखरी कण्ठदेशगा ॥” (तन्त्रागमः)

अत्र अन्तिमः वैखर्याख्यः स्फोट एव संस्कारेण ध्वनिना वा अभिव्यक्तः सन् पदार्थं वाक्यार्थं च जनयति । स्फोटस्य इदं ‘परा’ ‘पश्यन्ती’ इति रूपद्वयमेव योगिनाम् अनुभवविषयं भवति । योगबलेन समाधौ परास्फोटस्य साक्षात्कारे सति मोक्षः लभ्यते । अयं परास्फोट एव ओंकारस्फोटः नित्यः निरवयवः जगतः विवर्तोपादानहेतुः ।

केचित् स्फोटवादिनः वर्णानुभवजन्यसंस्कारस्य स्फोटाभिव्यञ्जकत्वं नाङ्गीकुर्वन्ति । तेषां मते, वर्ण एव स्फोटाभिव्यञ्जकः । तत्र नैयायिकादयः पूर्वपक्षिणः आक्षिपन्ति – स्फोटस्य अभिव्यक्तिर्न सम्भवतीत्यतः स्फोटवादः स्वीकर्तुं न शक्यते । तत्र अभिव्यक्तेन स्फोटेन अर्थज्ञानं सम्पद्यते उत अनभिव्यक्तेन स्फोटेन इति स्फोटवादिभिः वक्तव्यम् । अनभिव्यक्तेन स्फोटेन अर्थज्ञानं भवतीति द्वितीयविकल्पे वर्णादिभिः अभिव्यञ्जनात् प्राक् स्फोटः सर्वदा अनभिव्यक्तः इति सर्वदा अर्थज्ञानं स्यात् । अभिव्यक्तेन स्फोटेन अर्थज्ञानं भवतीति प्रथमविकल्पे एक एव वर्णः पदस्फोटम् अभिव्यञ्जयति उत सर्वे वर्णाः मिलित्वा अभिव्यञ्जयन्ति इति स्फोटवादिभिः वक्तव्यम् । तत्र प्रथमविकल्पे पदस्थानाम् अन्येषां वर्णानां वैयर्थ्यं स्यात् । द्वितीयविकल्पे तृतीयक्षणविनाशिनां वर्णानां समुदाय एव न सम्भवतीत्यतः वर्णा अपि पदस्फोटम् अभिव्यञ्जयितुं न समर्थाः । वर्णाः पदस्फोटस्य एकमेकम् अवयवम् अभिव्यञ्जयन्ति इत्यपि वक्तुं न शक्यते । यतो हि स्फोटवादिसम्मतः स्फोटः निरवयवः । तदा स्फोटवादिभिरुच्यते – प्रथमवर्णस्य उच्चारणेन पदस्फोटस्य किञ्चित्सफुटत्वं जायते । ततः द्वितीयतृतीयादिवर्णानाम् उच्चारणेन स क्रमेण स्फुटतरः स्फुटतमश्च भूत्वा अर्थबोधं जनयति । यथा ग्रन्थस्य सकृत्पाठेन ग्रन्थतात्पर्यं अनवगतेऽपि असकृत्पाठेन तदवगम्यते यथा वा असकृद्दर्शनेन एकस्य मणेः यथार्थं स्वरूपं निर्णीयते तथैव अत्रापि मन्तव्यम् । तस्मात् वर्णैः स्फोटस्य अभिव्यक्तौ न कापि अनुपपत्तिर्विद्यते । केचित् स्फोटवादिनः स्फोटः न शब्दस्वरूपः, अपि तु शब्दगतजातिः इत्याहुः । अन्ये जगत् स्फोटस्य परिणामः, न तु विवर्तः इत्याहुः । इत्थं स्फोटवादस्य नैके अवान्तरमतभेदाः परिलक्ष्यन्ते ।

तत्र स्फोटवादिभिः स्फोटस्य अष्टौ प्रकाराः स्वीकृताः – १. वर्णस्फोटः २. पदस्फोटः ३. वाक्यस्फोटः ४. अखण्डपदस्फोटः ५. अखण्डवाक्यस्फोटः ६. वर्णजातिस्फोटः ७. पदजातिस्फोटः ८. वाक्यजातिस्फोटः । एतेषु वाक्यस्फोटः एव प्रधानः ।

स्फोटतत्त्वखण्डनम्

अद्वैतनौकर्णधाराः श्रीमच्छङ्करभगवत्पादाः स्वीये शारीरकमीमांसाभाष्ये देवताधिकरणे अस्य स्फोटतत्त्वस्य सयुक्तिकं खण्डनं प्रस्तौति । तत्राधिकरणे मुख्यतो देवतानां विग्रहवत्त्वेन अनित्यत्वात् वेदाप्रामाण्यमाशङ्कितम् । यतो हि नित्यस्य शब्दस्य नित्येन अर्थेन सह नित्यसम्बन्धस्य प्रतीयमानत्वात् वेदप्रामाण्यं स्वीकृतम् । सम्प्रति तु देवतारूपार्थस्य

अनित्यत्वात् स नियमो न सङ्गच्छते। अस्याः शङ्कायाः निराकरणाय देवादिकस्य जगतः शब्दप्रभवत्वम् अङ्गीकृतम्। इदं जगतः शब्दप्रभवत्वं निमित्तकारणाभिप्रायेण उक्तम्, न तु उपादानकारणाभिप्रायेण।

इदानीं कीदृशं शब्दमादाय जगत इदं शब्दप्रभवत्वमुच्यते इति शङ्कायामुत्थितायां वैयाकरणा आहूः - स्फोटारख्यं नित्यशब्दम् अभिप्रेत्य जगत इदं शब्दप्रभवत्वमुक्तम्। ननु नित्येभ्यः वर्णेभ्यः जगदुत्पत्तेः सम्भवात् स्फोटकल्पना न सङ्गच्छते इति वक्तुं न शक्यते। यतो हि वर्णानाम् उत्पत्तिविनाशवत्त्वेन अनित्यत्वात् नित्येभ्यः शब्देभ्यः देवादिकस्य जगतः प्रभवः इति अनुपपन्नं स्यात्। ननु “सोऽयं गकारः” इत्यादिप्रत्यभिज्ञायाः वर्णानां नित्यत्वात् न कापि अनुपपत्तिर्वर्णपक्षे इति चेदुच्यते, वर्णाः उत्पत्तिविनाशशीलाः। यतो हि प्रत्युच्चारणं ते भिन्नभिन्नतया प्रतीयन्ते। तस्मादेव कश्चित् पुरुषो न दृश्यते चेदपि केवलं तस्य ध्वनिं श्रुत्वा अयमस्य ध्वनिः इति निश्चितुं शक्यते। यदि सर्वे ध्वनयः समानाः स्युः तर्हि अयं निश्चयः कदापि न सम्भवेत्। वर्णविषयकमिदं तारत्वमन्द्रत्वादिभेदज्ञानं मिथ्याभूतमिति वक्तुं न शक्यते। यतो हि यत् मिथ्याज्ञानं भवति तदवश्यं केनचित् सत्यज्ञानेन बाध्यते। इदं ज्ञानं तु न केनचित् बाध्यते इति नास्त्यस्य मिथ्याज्ञानत्वम्। तस्मात् वर्णाः विभिन्नाः अनित्याश्च इति सिध्यति।

किञ्च, वर्णेभ्यः अर्थज्ञानं भवति इति न सङ्गच्छते। अत्र विकल्पद्वयं सम्भवति। एकैकः वर्णः अर्थबोधं जनयतीति प्रथमविकल्पः। वर्णसमुदायः अर्थबोधं जनयतीति द्वितीयविकल्पः। तत्र प्रथमविकल्पो न युक्तः। यतो हि पदस्थात् प्रतिवर्णात् अर्थप्रतीतिर्भवतीति न दृश्यते। प्रत्येकं वर्णस्य अर्थबोधकत्वे एकस्मिन् पदे यावन्तः वर्णाः सन्ति तावन्तः अर्थाः तस्मात् पदात् प्रतीयेरन्। तच्चायुक्तम्। द्वितीयविकल्पोऽपि न युक्तः। यतो हि वर्णानां तृतीयवर्णविनाशित्वात् क्रमेण उच्चारितत्वाच्च सर्वेषां वर्णानां समुदाय एव न सम्भवति। ननु यथा प्रधानयज्ञजन्यः अपूर्वः अङ्गयज्ञजन्यैः अपूर्वैः सह मिलितः सन् महापूर्वं जनयति तथा पूर्वपूर्ववर्णानामनुभवैः जायमानाः ये संस्काराः तैः सह मिलितः अन्तिमः वर्णः अर्थबोधं जनयति इति चेदुच्यते, संस्कारसहितः अन्तिमः वर्णः ज्ञातः सन् अर्थबोधं जनयति उत अज्ञातः सन् अर्थबोधं जनयति इत्यादौ वक्तव्यम्। तत्र प्रथमविकल्पो न युक्तः। यतो हि अर्थज्ञानाय आवश्यकः यः अपूर्वाख्यः संस्कारः तेन सह सम्बन्धज्ञानमपेक्षते यः अन्तिमः वर्णः स स्वयं ज्ञातः सन् एव अर्थबोधं जनयति यथा धूमः वह्निना सह व्याप्तिसम्बन्धयुक्तत्वेन ज्ञातः सन् वह्न्यनुमितिं जनयति। द्वितीयविकल्पे अन्तिमः वर्णः प्रत्यक्षेण ज्ञायते उत अनुमानेन इति शङ्का भवति। तत्र संस्कारः अप्रत्यक्षः। अतः संस्कारसहितः अन्त्यवर्णोऽपि अप्रत्यक्षः। तस्मात् प्रत्यक्षेण तस्य ज्ञानं न सम्भवतीति प्रथमविकल्पो न युक्तः। पदान्तर्गतानां पूर्वपूर्ववर्णानाम् उच्चारणेन जायमानस्य अपूर्वाख्यसंस्कारस्य अर्थबोधरूपं यत् कार्यं तेन अनुमितः तत्कारणभूतः यः संस्कारसमूहः तद्विशिष्टः अन्त्यवर्णः अर्थबोधं जनयतीति द्वितीयविकल्पोऽपि अयुक्तः। यतो हि संस्कारकार्यं स्मरणमपि क्रमेण भवति। तस्मात् वर्णानां कथञ्चिदपि अर्थबोधकत्वाभावात् स्फोट एव शब्दः। यत्र एकैकस्य

वर्णस्य ज्ञानेन संस्काररूपाः बीजाः स्थापिताः यत्र च अन्तिमवर्णस्य ज्ञानेन जन्यः अन्तिमः संस्कारः समुत्पन्नः तस्मिन्नन्तःकरणे “इदमेकं पदम्” “इदमेकं वाक्यम्” इत्येवंविधस्य एकत्वप्रत्ययस्य विषयत्वेन स स्फोटः किमपि कारणमनपेक्ष्यैव स्पष्टतया प्रकाशते । बहुभिः वर्णैः अभिव्यक्तत्वेऽपि इदमेकत्वज्ञानं स्फोटविषये प्रमाणम् ।

नन्दिदमेकत्वज्ञानं पदस्फोटे वाक्यस्फोटे वा न प्रमाणम्, अपि तु इदं वर्णविषयिणी स्मृतिरिति चेन्न, यतो हि वर्णानामनेकत्वात् तेषाम् एकत्वावगाहिज्ञानविषयत्वं न सङ्गच्छते । ननु स्फोटस्य उत्पत्तिविनाशवत्त्वेन अनित्यत्वात् जगतः निमित्तकारणत्वं न सम्भवतीति चेन्न, प्रत्युच्चारणं “सोऽयं स्फोटः” इति प्रत्यभिज्ञावशात् तस्य नित्यत्वं सिध्यति । तत्र यो भेदप्रत्ययो भवति स वर्णविषयकः इत्यतः स्फोटस्य नित्यत्वं न विहन्यते । तस्मात् तस्य जगन्निमित्तकारणत्वम् उपपद्यते । नित्यवर्णानां शब्दत्वं भगवता उपवर्षेणापि अङ्गीकृतम् । ननु वर्णानाम् उत्पत्तिः विनाशश्च सम्भवतः इत्यतः वर्णानामनित्यत्वमिति चेन्न, यतो हि “ते एव इमे वर्णाः” इति प्रत्यभिज्ञायाः तेषां नित्यत्वं सिध्यति । ननु यथा केशानां सादृश्यात् “ते एव इमे केशाः” इति प्रत्यभिज्ञा भवति तथा उत्पत्तिविनाशशीलानां वर्णानामपि सादृश्यात् प्रत्यभिज्ञा भवति इति चेन्न, यतो हि वर्णविषयिणी प्रत्यभिज्ञा केनचित् प्रमाणेन न बाध्यते । तथाहि - केशप्रत्यभिज्ञा भ्राम्मिका । यतो हि नवकेशाः प्राक्तनकेशेभ्यो भिन्नाः इति प्रत्यक्षप्रमाणेन सा बाध्यते । वर्णप्रत्यभिज्ञा तु एतादृशेन केनचित् प्रमाणेन न बाध्यते इति नैतयोः समानता । ननु गोत्वादिरूपां जातिमवलम्ब्य “सोऽयं गकारः” इत्यादिप्रत्यभिज्ञाः भवन्ति, न तु गकारादिकमवलम्ब्य इति चेन्न, यतो हि अत्र प्रत्यभिज्ञा व्यक्तिविषयिणी एव भवति । तथाहि - यत्र जातिविषयिणी प्रत्यभिज्ञा भवति तत्र प्रत्युच्चारणं भिन्नाः भिन्नाः व्यक्तयः प्रतीयन्ते । वर्णप्रत्यभिज्ञास्थले भिन्नानां भिन्नानां वर्णव्यक्तीनां प्रतीतिर्नैव भवति । यतो हि प्रत्युच्चारणं “सोऽयं गकारः” इत्येवम् अभिन्नाः एव वर्णव्यक्तयः अत्र प्रत्यभिज्ञायन्ते । यथा गोशब्दस्य असकृत् उच्चारणे गोशब्दः द्विः उच्चारितः इत्येव प्रतीतिर्भवति । द्वौ गोशब्दौ उच्चारितौ इति प्रतीतिर्नैव भवति । तस्मादत्र प्रत्यभिज्ञा जात्याश्रया इति वक्तुं नैव शक्यते ।

ननु वर्णा अपि उच्चारणभेदेन भिन्नतया प्रतीयन्ते । तस्मादेव पुरुषस्य अदर्शनेऽपि तस्य ध्वनिं श्रुत्वा “अयं कस्य ध्वनिः” इति प्रत्येतुं शक्यते । तस्माद् वर्णानाम् अनेकत्वात् प्रत्यभिज्ञा गत्वादिजातिविषयिणी इत्येव अङ्गीकार्यमिति चेदुच्यते, वर्णविषयिणी प्रत्यभिज्ञा निश्चयेन भवति । तत्र कण्ठादिस्थानेषु वायोः संयोगविभागाभ्यां वर्णाः अभिव्यक्ताः इत्यतः अभिव्यञ्जकस्य वैचित्र्यात् वर्णविषयकं तारत्वमन्द्रत्वादिकं विचित्रज्ञानं भवति, न तु वर्णानां स्वरूपनिमित्तं तत् विचित्रज्ञानम् । अपि च, “ककाराः अनेके सन्ति” “खकाराः अनेके सन्ति” इत्येवं ककारादीनां भेदं ये स्वीकुर्वन्ति तैरपि प्रत्यभिज्ञायाः सिद्धये कत्वादिजातीनां कल्पना कर्तव्या । यतो हि तदभिमतानां क्षणिकानां वर्णानां “सोऽयं वर्णः” इत्येवंविधा प्रत्यभिज्ञा भवितुं नार्हति । अपि च, तासु जातिषु अन्येन उपाधिना प्रयुक्तस्य भेदस्य ज्ञानं भवतीत्यपि स्वीकर्तव्यं तैः । इत्यमेतैः अनित्यवर्णवादिभिः गत्वादिजातेः उपाधेश्च कल्पना कर्तव्या ।

तदपेक्षया नित्यवर्णवादिनां वर्णेष्वेव कण्ठादिस्थानेषु वायुसंयोगादिरूपोपाधिप्रयुक्तम् “उदात्तः गकारः” “अनुदात्तः गकारः” इत्येवं भेदज्ञानं तथा स्वरूपप्रयुक्तं “सोऽयं गकारः” इति प्रत्यभिज्ञानमिति कल्पना एव लघीयसी युक्ता च। ननु “उदात्तः गकारः” “अनुदात्तः गकारः” इत्येवंविधस्य तत्तद्वर्णव्यक्तीनां भेदज्ञानस्य मिथ्यात्वं वक्तुं न शक्यते बाधकप्रत्ययाभावात् इति चेन्न, यतो हि वर्णविषयकस्य भेदज्ञानस्य बाधिका “सोऽयं गकारः” इत्येवंकारा प्रत्यभिज्ञा एव। ननु तत्तद्वर्णानां प्रत्यभिज्ञासिद्धमेकत्वम् उदात्तादिभेदेन च भिन्नत्वम् इति उभयविधमपि ज्ञानं भवति। तस्मादेतयोः ज्ञानयोः प्रामाण्यसिद्धये वर्णानां भेदाभेदः एव सत्यभूत इत्यङ्गीकार्यमिति चेदुच्यते, एक एव गकारः एकस्मिन्नेव काले उदात्तत्वानुदात्तत्वादिधर्मभेदेन भिन्नो भवितुं नार्हति। यतो हि विरुद्धधर्मानामेकल स्थितिर्नैव सम्भवति। तस्मादेकस्यैव वर्णस्य उदात्तत्वानुदात्तत्वादिकृतो भेदः अवश्यमेव औपाधिकः इति स्वीकार्यम्। ततो भेदज्ञानस्य औपाधिकत्वेन मिथ्यात्वात् एकत्वप्रत्यभिज्ञानेन तदवश्यं बाध्यते।

अथवा अयम् उदात्तत्वादिभेदः ध्वनिकृतः, न तु वर्णकृतः। अतः उदात्तत्वादिभेदेन वर्णानामनेकत्वाभावात् न कश्चित् दोषलेशोऽपि। दूरात् शृण्वतो जनस्य वर्णानां भेदज्ञानं न प्रतीयते इति वर्णज्ञानव्यतिरेकेण स यं शृणोति तथा समीपस्थानां जनानां सविधे यः पटुत्वमृदुत्वादिभेदं वर्णेष्वारोपयति स एव वर्णातिरिक्तः शब्दः ध्वनिः। ध्वन्युपाधिवशादेव वर्णेषु उदात्तत्वादिभेदाः प्रतीयन्ते। यतो हि प्रत्युच्चारणं “सोऽयं गकारः” इति वर्णानां प्रत्यभिज्ञानेऽपि ध्वनिस्तु निवर्तते। इत्थं ध्वनेः उपाधित्वेन अङ्गीकारे उदात्तत्वादिज्ञानानि सकारणानि भवन्ति। अन्यथा प्रत्यभिज्ञाविषयाणां वर्णानाम् अभिन्नत्वात् उदात्तत्वादिभेदाः कण्ठादिस्थानेषु कोष्ठस्थवायोः संयोगेन विभागेन च जायन्ते इति कल्पयितव्यम्। तदा वायोः संयोगविभागयोः श्रोत्राग्राह्यत्वात् तदाश्रयेण “अयं वर्णः उदात्तः” “अयं वर्णः अनुदात्तः” इति ग्रहीतुं न शक्यते। तेन उदात्तत्वादिज्ञानानां निरालम्बनत्वं प्रसज्यते। तन्मा भूदिति ध्वनिरेव वर्णेषु उदात्तत्वाद्यारोपहेतुः इति अवगन्तव्यम्। किञ्च, उदात्तत्वादिभेदेन वर्णाः अपि भिन्नाः भवन्तीति न मन्तव्यम्। यतो हि यस्य वर्णस्य भेद एव न सम्भवति तस्य तदतिरिक्तस्य ध्वनेः भेदेन भेदः नैव सम्भवति। यथा गोव्यक्तीनां भिन्नत्वेऽपि गोत्वजातिः अभिन्नैव भवति तथा उदात्तादिभेदेन ध्वनेः भिन्नत्वेऽपि तदनुगताः वर्णाः न भिद्यन्ते। तस्मात् वर्णाः अभिन्नाः नित्याश्च। अतः वर्णानां नित्यत्वात् तेभ्य एव अर्थबोधः सम्भवतीति वैयाकरणानां स्फोटकल्पना व्यर्थैव।

ननु स्फोटस्य प्रत्यक्ष क्रियते, न तु कल्पना क्रियते। यतो हि एकैकवर्णविषयकज्ञानेन यत्र संस्काराः उत्पादिताः तस्यां बुद्धौ “इदमेकं पदम्” इति एकत्वज्ञानस्य विषयत्वेन स्फोटः झटित्येव प्रकाशते इति चेन्न, यतो हि एकत्वावगाहिन्या बुद्धेरपि विषयः वर्णः। यस्मिन् ज्ञाने यः पदार्थः प्रकाशते तज्ज्ञानमेव तत्पदार्थविषये प्रमाणम्। प्रकृते एकैकवर्णज्ञानोत्तरं गौः इति समस्तवर्णविषयिणी एका बुद्धिः उदेति, वर्णातिरिक्तस्फोटविषयिणी बुद्धिर्नैव उदेति। तस्मादियं बुद्धिः न स्फोटविषये प्रमाणभूता। ननु वर्णसमूह एव बुद्धिविषयो

भवति, न तु स्फोटः इत्यत्र का विनिगमना इति चेदुच्यते, गौः इत्यस्यां बुद्धौ गकारादयो वर्णा एव अनुवर्तन्ते, न तु अन्ये दकारादयः वर्णाः। यद्यत्र गकारादिभ्यो भिन्नः स्फोटः गौः इत्यस्याः बुद्धेः विषयः स्यात् तर्हि दकारादिवत् गकारादीनामपि अस्याः बुद्धेः निवृत्तिः स्यात्। किन्तु तत् न भवति। तस्मात् अनुवृत्तैः गकारादिवर्णैः गौः इति पदस्फोटस्य अभिव्यक्तिर्न सम्भवतीत्यतः गौः इत्याकारा बुद्धिः वर्णसमूहालम्बनकारिणी स्मृतिरेव, न तु स्फोटविषयिणी।

ननु वर्णानामनेकत्वात् तेषाम् एकबुद्धिविषयत्वं न सङ्गच्छते। तस्मात् स्फोटः स्वीकर्तव्य एव इति चेन्न, यतो हि बहूनां पदार्थानामपि एकबुद्धिविषयत्वं भवितुमर्हति। यतो हि पंक्तिवनसेनादिस्थलेषु तत् परिलक्ष्यते। ननु पंक्त्यादिस्थलेषु एकत्वबुद्धिः तत्तद्वस्तूनाम् एकदेशस्थत्वात् भवति। एकदेशस्थत्वं तत्र उपाधिः। “गौरित्येकोऽयं शब्दः” इत्यत्र तथा एकत्वबोधकस्य उपाधेः अभावात् एकत्वबुद्धिर्न सम्भवतीति चेदुच्यते, “गौरित्येकोऽयं शब्दः” इत्यत्र या एकत्वबुद्धिः सा बहुषु वर्णेषु एकार्थावच्छेदनिबन्धना। अर्थात् बहवो वर्णाः मिलित्वा एकस्य विषयस्य ज्ञानं जनयन्ति। तस्मात् पंक्त्यादिविषयिणी एकत्वबुद्धिरिव इयमपि औपचारिकी इति मन्तव्यम्।

ननु यदि वर्णाः मिलित्वा एकस्य ज्ञानस्य विषयत्वं प्राप्नुवन्ति तर्हि “जारा राजा” “कपिः पिकः” इत्यादिस्थलेषु भिन्नभिन्नपदानां ज्ञानं न स्यात्। यतो हि अत्र ते एव वर्णाः भिन्नभिन्नस्थलेषु भिन्नभिन्नतया प्रतीयन्ते इति चेदुच्यते, यथा पिपीलिकाः क्रमेण पंक्तिबद्धतया गच्छन्ति चेत् इयं पिपीलिकापंक्तिः इति ज्ञानं भवति तथा क्रमेण उच्चारिताः वर्णा एव पदत्वेन प्रतीयन्ते। जारा राजा इत्यादिस्थलेषु वर्णसाम्येऽपि क्रमवैषम्यात् भिन्नपदानां ज्ञानं भवतीति न कश्चित् विरोधः। किञ्च, वृद्धः येन क्रमेण वर्णान् उच्चारयति तच्छ्रुत्वा व्युत्पत्तिदशायां बालः तमेव क्रमं तेषु वर्णेषु आरोपयति। ततः इमे वर्णाः एतादृशक्रमेण उच्चारिताः एतमर्थं बोधयन्ति इति तं तमर्थं तत्तत्क्रमेणोच्चारितवर्णानां वाच्यं मन्यते। परं श्रोता बालः यदा स्वयं व्यवहरति तदा ते वर्णाः पूर्वानुभूतक्रमेणैव तस्य स्मृतौ आरूढाः तथैव उच्चारिताः श्रोतुः अर्थबोधं जनयन्ति। तस्मात् नित्यविभुवर्णानां वास्तवक्रमाभावेऽपि येन क्रमेण ते पुरुषैः उच्चार्यन्ते अनुभूयन्ते च तेनैव क्रमेण एकस्मृत्यारूढाः सन्तः अर्थबोधं जनयन्ति। अतः समानवर्णयुक्तानां भिन्नशब्दानाम् अर्थबोधाय स्फोटाङ्गीकारस्य अपेक्षा नास्ति। वर्णानां तदारोपितक्रमस्य च अङ्गीकारेणैव अर्थबोधः सम्भवति इति सिद्धान्ते कल्पनालाघवं वर्तते। स्फोटवादिनां मते तु, वर्णानाम् अर्थबोधनसामर्थ्यरूपस्य दृष्टविषयस्य परित्यागः स्फोटरूपस्य अदृष्टविषयस्य कल्पना च कर्तव्या। किञ्च, इमे वर्णाः क्रमेण गृहीताः स्फोटम् अभिव्यञ्जयन्ति, स च स्फोटः अर्थं प्रकाशयति इत्यपि कल्पना कर्तव्या। तस्मात् अस्मिन् पक्षे गौरवदोष आपतति। अपि च, प्रत्युच्चारणं वर्णाः यदि भिन्ना अपि भवन्ति तथापि प्रत्यभिज्ञायाः आश्रयत्वेन वर्णनिष्ठानां कत्वखत्वादीनां अवश्यमेव अङ्गीकारः कर्तव्यः इत्यतः वर्णेषु अर्थप्रतिपादनस्य या प्रक्रिया रचिता सा वर्णनिष्ठजातिष्वपि सञ्चारणीया। इत्थं श्रीमच्छङ्करभगवत्पादैः देवताधिकरणे

स्फोटवादस्य निराकरणेन वर्णवादः प्रतिष्ठापितः ।

उपसंहृतिः

शब्दशास्त्रे नित्यशब्दात्मकस्य स्फोटस्य महत्स्थानं प्रदीयते । यतो हि तेषां मते पदात् वाक्याद्वा अर्थप्रतीतिः स्फोटं विना न सम्भवति वर्णानामनित्यत्वात् । एवंभूतस्य स्फोटस्य लक्षणं, तदस्त्वित्त्वे प्रमाणं, तदभिव्यक्तेः सामान्या प्रक्रिया, तद्भेदाः इत्यादिविषयाः विस्तरेण प्रतिपादिताः अस्मिन् शोधनिबन्धे । ततः स्फोटवादिभिः कथं तत्पूर्वपक्षिणां नैयायिकादीनां मुखमुद्रणं क्रियत इत्यपि किञ्चित् प्रदर्शितम् । तदनु अद्वैतशिरोमणिभिः शङ्करभगवत्पादैः स्वभाष्येषु अस्य शब्दशास्त्रप्रपञ्चे बहुप्रथितस्य वैयाकरणप्राणभूतस्य स्फोटतत्त्वस्य यन्निराकरणं कृतं तत्स्वविवेकपुरःसरमुपपादितमिति शिवम् ।

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